

Fibonacci Sequence Type Selfie Numbers: Basic Operations

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Abstract

By **selfie numbers**, we understand that the numbers represented by their own digits by use of certain operations, such as, **basic operations, factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers**, etc. These operations are applied for single variable. In two variables, we worked with **binomial coefficients type selfie numbers with basic operations, factorial and square-root**. This paper extends authors previous work for **Fibonacci sequence type selfie numbers in basic operations**. For the operations, such as, **factorial and square-root**, the work shall be given elsewhere. The work is in **digit's order and in reverse order of digits**, and is up to 5-digits numbers. This extends considerably, author's previous work [23].

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1 Introduction

Let's analyse historical aspects of some numbers:

- (i) Consider the following classical number famous as **printer's error** (Dudeney, 1917, pp. 379 [5]):

$$2592 := 2^5 \times 9^2 \quad (1)$$

Actually it is not a **printer's error**, it represents a number in its own digits. The first number with a similar property is $25 = 5^2$, but in **reverse order**.

- (ii) Let consider another examples (Madachy, 1966, pp.167-175 [11]):

$$\begin{aligned} 34425 &:= 3^4 \times 425 \\ 312325 &:= 31^2 \times 325 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Above two are represented their own digits. Moreover, if we multiply by both sides by 10, they continued with property of same digits both sides. These kinds of numbers are famous as **number patterns**. Still there is another number with different property, i.e.,

$$27594 := 73 \times 9 \times 42 = 7 \times 3942 \quad (3)$$

In this case, the two expressions on right side of (4) are with same digits, but the total value is with different digits. This type of study is not under work.

- (iii) Madachy, 1966, pp.167-275 [11] also gave an interesting property with factorials know by **sum of factorials**:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &:= 1! \\ 2 &:= 2! \\ 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Above numbers also have the property of same digits on both sides, but with factorial and addition.

In all the three situations, we observe that we are dealing with numbers those have same digits on both sides, where one side is number another with same digits with certain operations. Based on above idea of numbers, the author studies numbers calling **selfie numbers**, i.e., numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. Some studies in this direction can be seen in the works of Friedman [6, 7] and Rose [2, 3, 4].

Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** extending the idea of equation (2) using the operations of addition and subtraction with **factorial**:

$$\begin{aligned} 145 &= 1! + 4! + 5! & 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! \\ 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! \\ 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{80518} := 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & \mathbf{361469} := 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\
 \mathbf{363239} := 36 + 323 + 9! & \mathbf{364292} := 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\
 \mathbf{363269} := 363 + 26 + 9! & \mathbf{397584} := -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\
 \mathbf{403199} := 40319 + 9! & \mathbf{398173} := 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\
 \mathbf{317489} := -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & \mathbf{408937} := -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\
 \mathbf{352797} := -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & \mathbf{715799} := -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\
 \mathbf{357592} := -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & \mathbf{720599} := -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\
 \mathbf{357941} := 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1! &
 \end{array}$$

1.1 Fibonacci Sequence

Below are few examples of **Fibonacci sequence type selfie numbers** studied by author in previous work [22]:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{235} := 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5)) & \mathbf{63} := 3 \times F(F(6)) \\
 \mathbf{256} := 2^5 \times F(6) & \mathbf{882} := 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\
 \mathbf{4427} := (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) & \mathbf{1631} := F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{46493} := F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3 & \mathbf{54128} := 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))
 \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [22].

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers**, etc. Below is item-wise details of author's work on **selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order**, and in **reverse order of digits**:

Selfie numbers with:

1. Basic Operations: [29];
2. Factorial: [26, 27];
3. Square-root: [14, 15];
4. Factorial and Square-root: [14, 15, 16];
5. Fibonacci sequence: [23, 24];
6. Triangular numbers: [21, 32, 33];
7. Fibonacci and Triangular numbers: [24];
8. Binomial coefficients: [22];
9. Binomial coefficients: Fibonacci: [31];
10. Binomial coefficients: Triangular: [34];
11. S-gonal numbers: [17];
12. Centered Polygonal: [17];
13. Concatenation-Type: [28];
14. Quadratic numbers: [25];
15. Cubic numbers: [29];

The last Section 4 is dedicated to summary of **selfie numbers** in different situations along with necessary references.

The aim of this work is to bring **Fibonacci sequence type selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations, factorial and square-root** extending considerably, the author's previous works [23]. Since there are very high quantity of numbers, we divided it in three parts, where each part with specific operations, such as, **basic operations, factorial and square-root**. This first part is only with **basic operations**. The other two part shall be given elsewhere.

Remark 1.1. *We must observe that the in the previous work we have written **Fibonacci sequence type selfie numbers** in terms of $F(.)$ as well as $F(F(.))$. The work in terms of $F(.)$ is up to 5 digits, and in terms of $F(F(.))$ is up to 4 digits. While this work is up to 5 digits in terms of $F(F(.))$, etc.*

2 Selfie Numbers With Fibonacci Values: Digit's Order

This subsection brings **Fibonacci type selfie numbers** with basic operations. The results are in digit's order. The work is up to 5 digits. This section is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and consecutive in blocks of 10. The second representations are for general values.

2.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$5490 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 0$$

$$5491 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 1$$

$$5492 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 2$$

$$5493 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 3$$

$$5494 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 4$$

$$5495 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 5$$

$$5496 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 6$$

$$5497 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 7$$

$$5498 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 8$$

$$5499 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 9$$

$$7920 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 0$$

$$7921 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 1$$

$$7922 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 2$$

$$7923 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 3$$

$$7924 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 4$$

$$7925 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 5$$

$$7926 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 6$$

$$7927 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 7$$

$$7928 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 8$$

$$7929 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 9$$

$$10980 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 0$$

$$10981 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 1$$

$$10982 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 2$$

$$10983 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 3$$

$$10984 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 4$$

$$10985 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 5$$

$$10986 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 6$$

$$10987 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 7$$

$$10988 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 8$$

$$10989 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 9$$

$$13530 := F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 0$$

$$13531 := F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 1$$

$$13532 := F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 2$$

$$13533 := F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 3$$

$$13534 := F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 4$$

$$13535 := F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 5$$

$$13536 := F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 6$$

$$13537 := F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 7$$

$$13538 := F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 8$$

$$13539 := F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 9$$

$$14640 := -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 0$$

$$14641 := -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 1$$

$$14642 := -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 2$$

$$14643 := -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 3$$

$$14644 := -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 4$$

$$14645 := -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 5$$

$$14646 := -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 6$$

$$14647 := -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 7$$

$$14648 := -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 8$$

$$14649 := -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 9$$

$$15250 := F(15) \times 25 + 0$$

$$15251 := F(15) \times 25 + 1$$

$$15252 := F(15) \times 25 + 2$$

$$15253 := F(15) \times 25 + 3$$

$$15254 := F(15) \times 25 + 4$$

$$15255 := F(15) \times 25 + 5$$

$$15256 := F(15) \times 25 + 6$$

$$15257 := F(15) \times 25 + 7$$

$$15258 := F(15) \times 25 + 8$$

$$15259 := F(15) \times 25 + 9$$

$$16420 := 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 0$$

$$16421 := 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 1$$

$$16422 := 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 2$$

$$16423 := 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 3$$

$$16424 := 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 4$$

$$16425 := 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 5$$

$$16426 := 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 6$$

$$16427 := 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 7$$

$$16428 := 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 8$$

$$16429 := 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 9$$

$$21960 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0$$

$$21961 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1$$

$$21962 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2$$

$$21963 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3$$

$$21964 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4$$

$$21965 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5$$

$$21966 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6$$

$$21967 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7$$

$$21968 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8$$

$$21969 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9$$

$$25840 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 0$$

$$25841 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 1$$

$$25842 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 2$$

$$25843 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 3$$

$$25844 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 4$$

$$25845 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 5$$

$$25846 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 6$$

$$25847 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 7$$

$$25848 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 8$$

$$25849 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 9$$

$$26470 := F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 0$$

$$26471 := F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 1$$

$$26472 := F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 2$$

$$26473 := F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 3$$

$$26474 := F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 4$$

$$26475 := F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 5$$

$$26476 := F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 6$$

$$26477 := F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 7$$

$$26478 := F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 8$$

$$26479 := F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 9$$

$$27450 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 0$$

$$27451 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 1$$

$$27452 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 2$$

$$27453 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 3$$

$$27454 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 4$$

$$27455 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 5$$

$$27456 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 6$$

$$27457 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 7$$

$$27458 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 8$$

$$27459 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 9$$

$$28670 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 0$$

$$28671 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 1$$

$$28672 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 2$$

$$28673 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 3$$

$$28674 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 4$$

$$28675 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 5$$

$$28676 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 6$$

$$28677 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 7$$

$$28678 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 8$$

$$28679 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 9$$

$$28730 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 0$$

$$28731 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 1$$

$$28732 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 2$$

$$28733 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 3$$

$$28734 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 4$$

$$28735 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 5$$

$$28736 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 6$$

$$28737 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 7$$

$$28738 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 8$$

$$28739 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 9$$

$$28890 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 0$$

$$28891 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 1$$

$$28892 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 2$$

$$28893 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 3$$

$$28894 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 4$$

$$28895 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 5$$

$$28896 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 6$$

$$28897 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 7$$

$$28898 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 8$$

$$28899 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 9$$

$$32850 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 0$$

$$32851 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 1$$

$$32852 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 2$$

$$32853 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 3$$

$$32854 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 4$$

$$32855 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 5$$

$$32856 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 6$$

$$32857 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 7$$

$$32858 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 8$$

$$32859 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 9$$

$$32940 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 0$$

$$32941 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 1$$

$$32942 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 2$$

$$32943 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 3$$

$$32944 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 4$$

$$32945 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 5$$

$$32946 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 6$$

$$32947 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 7$$

$$32948 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 8$$

$$32949 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 9$$

$$33490 := (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 0$$

$$33491 := (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 1$$

$$33492 := (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 2$$

$$33493 := (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 3$$

$$33494 := (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 4$$

$$33495 := (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 5$$

$$33496 := (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 6$$

$$33497 := (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 7$$

$$33498 := (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 8$$

$$33499 := (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 9$$

$$38760 := F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 0$$

$$38761 := F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 1$$

$$38762 := F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 2$$

$$38763 := F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 3$$

$$38764 := F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 4$$

$$38765 := F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 5$$

$$38766 := F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 6$$

$$38767 := F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 7$$

$$38768 := F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 8$$

$$38769 := F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 9$$

$$39360 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 0$$

$$39361 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 1$$

$$39362 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 2$$

$$39363 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 3$$

$$39364 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 4$$

$$39365 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 5$$

$$39366 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 6$$

$$39367 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 7$$

$$39368 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 8$$

$$39369 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 9$$

$$43460 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 0$$

$$43461 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 1$$

$$43462 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 2$$

$$43463 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 3$$

$$43464 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 4$$

$$43465 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 5$$

$$43466 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 6$$

$$43467 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 7$$

$$43468 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 8$$

$$43469 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 9$$

$$43640 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 0$$

$$43641 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 1$$

$$43642 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 2$$

$$43643 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 3$$

$$43644 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 4$$

$$43645 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 5$$

$$43646 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 6$$

$$43647 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 7$$

$$43648 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 8$$

$$43649 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 9$$

$$43760 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 0$$

$$43761 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 1$$

$$43762 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 2$$

$$43763 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 3$$

$$43764 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 4$$

$$43765 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 5$$

$$43766 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 6$$

$$43767 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 7$$

$$43768 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 8$$

$$43769 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 9$$

$$43780 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 0$$

$$43781 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 1$$

$$43782 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 2$$

$$43783 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 3$$

$$43784 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 4$$

$$43785 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 5$$

$$43786 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 6$$

$$43787 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 7$$

$$43788 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 8$$

$$43789 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 9$$

$$43860 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 0$$

$$43861 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 1$$

$$43862 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 2$$

$$43863 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 3$$

$$43864 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 4$$

$$43865 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 5$$

$$43866 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 6$$

$$43867 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 7$$

$$43868 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 8$$

$$43869 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 9$$

$$43880 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 0$$

$$43881 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 1$$

$$43882 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 2$$

$$43883 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 3$$

$$43884 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 4$$

$$43885 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 5$$

$$43886 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 6$$

$$43887 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 7$$

$$43888 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 8$$

$$43889 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 9$$

$$44360 := 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0$$

$$44361 := 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1$$

$$44362 := 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2$$

$$44363 := 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3$$

$$44364 := 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4$$

$$44365 := 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5$$

$$44366 := 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6$$

$$44367 := 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7$$

$$44368 := 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8$$

$$44369 := 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9$$

$$45750 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 0$$

$$45751 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 1$$

$$45752 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 2$$

$$45753 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 3$$

$$45754 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 4$$

$$45755 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 5$$

$$45756 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 6$$

$$45757 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 7$$

$$45758 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 8$$

$$45759 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 9$$

$$46370 := F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 0$$

$$46371 := F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 1$$

$$46372 := F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 2$$

$$46373 := F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 3$$

$$46374 := F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 4$$

$$46375 := F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 5$$

$$46376 := F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 6$$

$$46377 := F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 7$$

$$46378 := F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 8$$

$$46379 := F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 9$$

$$46660 := -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 0$$

$$46661 := -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 1$$

$$46662 := -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 2$$

$$46663 := -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 3$$

$$46664 := -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 4$$

$$46665 := -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 5$$

$$46666 := -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 6$$

$$46667 := -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 7$$

$$46668 := -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 8$$

$$46669 := -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 9$$

$$46670 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 0$$

$$46671 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 1$$

$$46672 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 2$$

$$46673 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 3$$

$$46674 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 4$$

$$46675 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 5$$

$$46676 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 6$$

$$46677 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 7$$

$$46678 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 8$$

$$46679 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 9$$

$$46680 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 0$$

$$46681 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 1$$

$$46682 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 2$$

$$46683 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 3$$

$$46684 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 4$$

$$46685 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 5$$

$$46686 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 6$$

$$46687 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 7$$

$$46688 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 8$$

$$46689 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 9$$

$$54290 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 0$$

$$54291 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 1$$

$$54292 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 2$$

$$54293 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 3$$

$$54294 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 4$$

$$54295 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 5$$

$$54296 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 6$$

$$54297 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 7$$

$$54298 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 8$$

$$54299 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 9$$

$$54560 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0$$

$$54561 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1$$

$$54562 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2$$

$$54563 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3$$

$$54564 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4$$

$$54565 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5$$

$$54566 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6$$

$$54567 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7$$

$$54568 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8$$

$$54569 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9$$

$$54670 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 0$$

$$54671 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 1$$

$$54672 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 2$$

$$54673 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 3$$

$$54674 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 4$$

$$54675 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 5$$

$$54676 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 6$$

$$54677 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 7$$

$$54678 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 8$$

$$54679 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 9$$

$$54680 := 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}54681 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 1 \\54682 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 2 \\54683 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 3 \\54684 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 4 \\54685 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 5 \\54686 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 6 \\54687 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 7 \\54688 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 8 \\54689 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54690 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 0 \\54691 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 1 \\54692 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 2 \\54693 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 3 \\54694 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 4 \\54695 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 5 \\54696 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 6 \\54697 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 7 \\54698 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 8 \\54699 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54710 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 0 \\54711 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 1 \\54712 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 2 \\54713 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 3 \\54714 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 4 \\54715 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 5 \\54716 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 6 \\54717 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 7 \\54718 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 8 \\54719 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54720 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 0 \\54721 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 1 \\54722 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 2 \\54723 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 3 \\54724 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 4 \\54725 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 5 \\54726 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 6 \\54727 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 7 \\54728 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 8\end{aligned}$$

$$54729 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned}54730 &:= 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 0 \\54731 &:= 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 1 \\54732 &:= 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 2 \\54733 &:= 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 3 \\54734 &:= 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 4 \\54735 &:= 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 5 \\54736 &:= 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 6 \\54737 &:= 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 7 \\54738 &:= 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 8 \\54739 &:= 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54740 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 0 \\54741 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 1 \\54742 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 2 \\54743 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 3 \\54744 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 4 \\54745 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 5 \\54746 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 6 \\54747 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 7 \\54748 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 8 \\54749 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54750 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 0 \\54751 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 1 \\54752 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 2 \\54753 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 3 \\54754 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 4 \\54755 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 5 \\54756 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 6 \\54757 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 7 \\54758 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 8 \\54759 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54760 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 0 \\54761 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 1 \\54762 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 2 \\54763 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 3 \\54764 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 4 \\54765 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 5 \\54766 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 6\end{aligned}$$

$$54767 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 7$$

$$54768 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 8$$

$$54769 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 9$$

$$54780 := 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 0$$

$$54781 := 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 1$$

$$54782 := 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 2$$

$$54783 := 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 3$$

$$54784 := 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 4$$

$$54785 := 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 5$$

$$54786 := 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 6$$

$$54787 := 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 7$$

$$54788 := 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 8$$

$$54789 := 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 9$$

$$54890 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 0$$

$$54891 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 1$$

$$54892 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 2$$

$$54893 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 3$$

$$54894 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 4$$

$$54895 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 5$$

$$54896 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 6$$

$$54897 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 7$$

$$54898 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 8$$

$$54899 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 9$$

$$54900 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 0$$

$$54901 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 1$$

$$54902 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 2$$

$$54903 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 3$$

$$54904 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 4$$

$$54905 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 5$$

$$54906 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 6$$

$$54907 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 7$$

$$54908 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 8$$

$$54909 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 9$$

$$55870 := 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 0$$

$$55871 := 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 1$$

$$55872 := 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 2$$

$$55873 := 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 3$$

$$55874 := 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 4$$

$$55875 := 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 5$$

$$55876 := 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 6$$

$$55877 := 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 7$$

$$55878 := 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 8$$

$$55879 := 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 9$$

$$59320 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 0$$

$$59321 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 1$$

$$59322 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 2$$

$$59323 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 3$$

$$59324 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 4$$

$$59325 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 5$$

$$59326 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 6$$

$$59327 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 7$$

$$59328 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 8$$

$$59329 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 9$$

$$65660 := -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 0$$

$$65661 := -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 1$$

$$65662 := -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 2$$

$$65663 := -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 3$$

$$65664 := -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 4$$

$$65665 := -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5$$

$$65666 := -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 6$$

$$65667 := -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 7$$

$$65668 := -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 8$$

$$65669 := -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 9$$

$$76720 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 0$$

$$76721 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 1$$

$$76722 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 2$$

$$76723 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 3$$

$$76724 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 4$$

$$76725 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 5$$

$$76726 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 6$$

$$76727 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 7$$

$$76728 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 8$$

$$76729 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 9$$

$$76860 := F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76861 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 1 \\ 76862 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 2 \\ 76863 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 3 \\ 76864 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 4 \\ 76865 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 5 \\ 76866 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 6 \\ 76867 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 7 \\ 76868 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 8 \\ 76869 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76890 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 0 \\ 76891 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 1 \\ 76892 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 2 \\ 76893 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 3 \\ 76894 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 4 \\ 76895 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 5 \\ 76896 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 6 \\ 76897 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 7 \\ 76898 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 8 \\ 76899 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 83620 &:= F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 0 \\ 83621 &:= F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 1 \\ 83622 &:= F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 2 \\ 83623 &:= F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 3 \\ 83624 &:= F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 4 \\ 83625 &:= F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 5 \\ 83626 &:= F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 6 \\ 83627 &:= F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 7 \\ 83628 &:= F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 8 \\ 83629 &:= F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 86880 &:= (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 0 \\ 86881 &:= (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 1 \\ 86882 &:= (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 2 \\ 86883 &:= (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 3 \\ 86884 &:= (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 4 \\ 86885 &:= (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 5 \\ 86886 &:= (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 6 \\ 86887 &:= (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 7 \\ 86888 &:= (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$86889 := (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned} 86920 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 0 \\ 86921 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 1 \\ 86922 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 2 \\ 86923 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 3 \\ 86924 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 4 \\ 86925 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 5 \\ 86926 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 6 \\ 86927 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 7 \\ 86928 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 8 \\ 86929 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87360 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 0 \\ 87361 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 1 \\ 87362 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 2 \\ 87363 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 3 \\ 87364 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 4 \\ 87365 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 5 \\ 87366 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 6 \\ 87367 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 7 \\ 87368 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 8 \\ 87369 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87480 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 0 \\ 87481 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 1 \\ 87482 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 2 \\ 87483 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 3 \\ 87484 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 4 \\ 87485 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 5 \\ 87486 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 6 \\ 87487 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 7 \\ 87488 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 8 \\ 87489 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87560 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 0 \\ 87561 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 1 \\ 87562 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 2 \\ 87563 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 3 \\ 87564 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 4 \\ 87565 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$87566 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 6$$

$$87567 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 7$$

$$87568 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 8$$

$$87569 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 9$$

$$87640 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 0$$

$$87641 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 1$$

$$87642 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 2$$

$$87643 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 3$$

$$87644 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 4$$

$$87645 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 5$$

$$87646 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 6$$

$$87647 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 7$$

$$87648 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 8$$

$$87649 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 9$$

$$87680 := (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 0$$

$$87681 := (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 1$$

$$87682 := (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 2$$

$$87683 := (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 3$$

$$87684 := (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 4$$

$$87685 := (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 5$$

$$87686 := (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 6$$

$$87687 := (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 7$$

$$87688 := (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 8$$

$$87689 := (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 9$$

$$87840 := F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 0$$

$$87841 := F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 1$$

$$87842 := F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 2$$

$$87843 := F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 3$$

$$87844 := F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 4$$

$$87845 := F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 5$$

$$87846 := F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 6$$

$$87847 := F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 7$$

$$87848 := F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 8$$

$$87849 := F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 9$$

$$88450 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 0$$

$$88451 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 1$$

$$88452 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 2$$

$$88453 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 3$$

$$88454 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 4$$

$$88455 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 5$$

$$88456 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 6$$

$$88457 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 7$$

$$88458 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 8$$

$$88459 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 9$$

$$88720 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 0$$

$$88721 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 1$$

$$88722 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 2$$

$$88723 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 3$$

$$88724 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 4$$

$$88725 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 5$$

$$88726 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 6$$

$$88727 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 7$$

$$88728 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 8$$

$$88729 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 9$$

$$89670 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 0$$

$$89671 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 1$$

$$89672 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 2$$

$$89673 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 3$$

$$89674 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 4$$

$$89675 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 5$$

$$89676 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 6$$

$$89677 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 7$$

$$89678 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 8$$

$$89679 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 9$$

$$98370 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 0$$

$$98371 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 1$$

$$98372 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 2$$

$$98373 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 3$$

$$98374 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 4$$

$$98375 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 5$$

$$98376 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 6$$

$$98377 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 7$$

$$98378 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 8$$

$$98379 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 9$$

$$98460 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98461 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 1 \\ 98462 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 2 \\ 98463 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 3 \\ 98464 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 4 \\ 98465 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 5 \\ 98466 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 6 \\ 98467 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 7 \\ 98468 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 8 \\ 98469 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98581 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 1 \\ 98582 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 2 \\ 98583 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 3 \\ 98584 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 4 \\ 98585 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 5 \\ 98586 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 6 \\ 98587 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 7 \\ 98588 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 8 \\ 98589 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98510 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 0 \\ 98511 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 1 \\ 98512 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 2 \\ 98513 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 3 \\ 98514 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 4 \\ 98515 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 5 \\ 98516 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 6 \\ 98517 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 7 \\ 98518 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 8 \\ 98519 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98820 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 0 \\ 98821 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 1 \\ 98822 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 2 \\ 98823 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 3 \\ 98824 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 4 \\ 98825 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 5 \\ 98826 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 6 \\ 98827 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 7 \\ 98828 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 8 \\ 98829 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$98580 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 0$$

2.2 General Representations

Remark 2.1. Most of the *selfie numbers* appearing below are with lot of extra brackets " $\dots$ ". These can be removed easily after making simplifications.

$$\begin{aligned} 34 &:= F((3 \times F(4))) \\ 55 &:= F((5 + 5)) \\ 63 &:= (F(F(6)) \times 3) \\ 64 &:= (F(6))^{F(F(4))} \\ 84 &:= (F(8) \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 143 &:= -1 + F(4 \times 3) \\ 144 &:= F((-1 + 4) \times 4) \\ 168 &:= 1 \times F(6) \times F(8) \\ 189 &:= ((-1) \times F(8)) \times (-9) \\ 233 &:= F(F(-(2 - (3 \times 3)))) \\ 234 &:= (F(2) + F(F((3 + 4)))) \\ 235 &:= (2 + F(F((F(3) + (5)))))) \\ 237 &:= ((F(2) + 3) + F(F(7))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 245 &:= 2 + F(4)^5 \\ 256 &:= 2^5 \times F(6) \\ 267 &:= (F((F(2) + F(6))) + F(F(7))) \\ 374 &:= (F((F(3) \times 7)) - F(4)) \\ 376 &:= (-F(F(3))) + F((-7) + F(F(6))) \\ 377 &:= F(3 \times 7 - 7) \\ 378 &:= (F(F(3)) + F((-7) + F(8))) \\ 466 &:= (F(F(4)) \times F((-F(6)) + F(F(6)))) \\ 472 &:= ((-F(4)) - F(F(7))) \times (-2) \\ 474 &:= ((4 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4))) \\ 484 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) + (F(8)))^{F(F(4))}) \\ 630 &:= (F(F(6)) \times 30) \\ 693 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (F(9) - F(F(3)))) \\ 784 &:= ((7 + F(8))^{F(F(4))}) \end{aligned}$$

$$840 := (F(8) \times 40)$$

$$882 := ((F(8) \times F(8)) \times 2)$$

$$986 := (F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6)))$$

$$1042 := F(10) + F(4^2)$$

$$1165 := (F(F((1 \times 1) + 6))) \times 5$$

$$1175 := (((1 + 1) + F(F(7))) \times 5)$$

$$1178 := F(11) \times F(7) + F(8)$$

$$1292 := 1 \times F(2 \times 9) / 2$$

$$1293 := F(12) \times 9 - 3$$

$$1294 := ((F(12) \times 9) - F(F(4)))$$

$$1364 := -(F(13)) + F((F(F(6)) - (4)))$$

$$1365 := ((13 \times F(F(6))) \times 5)$$

$$1368 := (((1 - 3) + F(F(F(6)))) / 8)$$

$$1397 := -(1) - ((3 - 9) \times F(F(7)))$$

$$1429 := 1 + 42 \times F(9)$$

$$1487 := -(F(14)) + (8 \times F(F(7)))$$

$$1525 := ((F(15) / 2) \times 5)$$

$$1536 := (1 + 5) \times F(3)^{F(6)}$$

$$1575 := (F(F((1 + 5))) \times 75)$$

$$1576 := (F(-(1 - 5) + F(7))) - F(F(6)))$$

$$1589 := -F(1 + 5) + F(8 + 9)$$

$$1592 := -((1 \times 5)) + F((F(9) / 2))$$

$$1593 := ((1 - 5) + F((F(9) / F(3))))$$

$$1594 := (F((F((1 + 5) + 9)) - F(4))$$

$$1596 := -((1^5)) + F((9 + F(6)))$$

$$1597 := F(1^5 + 9 + 7)$$

$$1598 := 1^5 + F(9 + 8)$$

$$1617 := ((-1) + F(F(6))) + F(17)$$

$$1618 := F(16 + 1) + F(8)$$

$$1645 := ((F(16) / F(4)) \times 5)$$

$$1680 := (F(F((1 \times 6))) \times 80)$$

$$1684 := ((-1) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(8)^{F(4)})$$

$$1687 := ((F(F((1 + 6))) + 8) \times 7)$$

$$1736 := (-1 + F(7))^3 + F(6)$$

$$1763 := -1 + (7 \times 6)^{F(3)}$$

$$1764 := (((1 \times 7) \times 6)^{F(F(4))})$$

$$1778 := ((1 \times 7) \times (F(F(7)) + F(8)))$$

$$1785 := (F((1 + 7)) \times 85)$$

$$1824 := ((1 + (F(F(8)) / (-2))) / (-F(4)))$$

$$1847 := (-1) - (8 \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(7))))$$

$$1848 := (1 + F(8)) \times 4 \times F(8)$$

$$1856 := -1 + F(8 + 5) \times F(6)$$

$$1862 := ((F(F(-(1 - 8))) \times F(6)) - 2)$$

$$1863 := ((F(F(-(1 - 8))) \times F(6)) - F(F(3)))$$

$$1864 := (F(F(-(1 - 8))) \times (6 + F(F(4))))$$

$$1865 := (1 - (-8) \times F((F(6) + (5))))$$

$$1871 := (-1) - (-8) \times (F(F(7)) + 1)$$

$$1872 := (F(-(1 - 8)) \times F((F(7) - F(2))))$$

$$1873 := (1 - (-8) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(3))))$$

$$1877 := (((1 \times 8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(7)))$$

$$1885 := (F(((1 + F(8)) - 8)) \times 5)$$

$$1890 := ((-1) \times F(8)) \times (-90)$$

$$1897 := ((1 - (8 \times F(9))) \times (-7))$$

$$1925 := (1 + F(9)) \times F(2 \times 5)$$

$$1972 := ((1 - F((9 + 7))) \times (-2))$$

$$1973 := -1 + F(9 + 7) \times F(3)$$

$$1974 := ((F(19) - F(F(7))) / F(F(4)))$$

$$1976 := 19 \times F(7) \times F(6)$$

$$1995 := (F(-(1 - 9)) \times 95)$$

$$2048 := 2^{F(04)+8}$$

$$2079 := ((-2) + F(F(07))) \times 9$$

$$2097 := (((2 \times 0) + 9) \times F(F(7)))$$

$$2185 := (F(21) - F(8)) / 5$$

$$2529 := F(2 \times 5) + F(2 \times 9)$$

$$2563 := (F(F((2 + 5))) \times (F(6) + 3))$$

$$2576 := F(25 - 7) - F(6)$$

$$2577 := F(25 - 7) - 7$$

$$2578 := ((2 + F((5 + F(7)))) - 8)$$

$$2582 := F(2 \times 5 + 8) - 2$$

$$2583 := -(F(2)) + F(((5) + F(8)) + F(3)))$$

$$2584 := F(2 \times (5 + 8 - 4))$$

$$2585 := F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5)$$

$$2586 := 2 + F((-5 + 8) \times 6)$$

$$2594 := ((2 \times 5) + F((9 \times F(F(4))))$$

$$2597 := (F((F(-(2 - 5))) \times 9)) + F(7)$$

$$2618 := (F((F(2) + F(6))) + F(18))$$

$$2639 := (F((2 + F(6))) + F((F(3) \times 9)))$$

$$2645 := (((2 + F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))}) \times 5)$$

$$2646 := (((2 \times F(F(6))) \times F(4)) \times F(F(6)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2648 &:= ((2^6) + F(-((F(4) - F(8)))) \\
 2688 &:= (((-2) \times F(6)) \times F(8)) \times (-8) \\
 2736 &:= (2 \times 7)^3 - F(6) \\
 2742 &:= (2 \times 7)^{F(4)} - 2 \\
 2743 &:= (((2 \times 7)^{F(4)} - F(F(3))) \\
 2744 &:= (-2 + F(7) + F(4))^{F(4)} \\
 2746 &:= (2 + 7^{F(4)}) \times F(6) \\
 2754 &:= (-((2^{F(7)})) + F(F((5 + F(4)))) \\
 2767 &:= (((-2^{F(7)}) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(7)) \\
 2772 &:= ((2 - F(F(7))) \times (-F(7) - F(2))) \\
 2784 &:= ((F(2) - F(F(7))) \times (-8 + 4)) \\
 2794 &:= (-2) + (F(F(7)) \times (9 + F(4))) \\
 2796 &:= ((-F(2)) \times F(F(7))) \times (9 - F(F(6))) \\
 2798 &:= (2 + (F(F(7)) \times (-9) + F(8))) \\
 2817 &:= (F((2 \times (8 + 1))) + F(F(7))) \\
 2937 &:= (-((F(2) - F(9))) \times F(-((F(3) - F(7)))) \\
 3178 &:= F(3) \times (F(17) - 8) \\
 3192 &:= (F(3) \times (-1) + F((F(9)/2))) \\
 3194 &:= (F(3) \times F((F((1 \times 9))/F(F(4)))) \\
 3196 &:= (F(3) \times (1 + F((9 + F(6)))) \\
 3364 &:= ((3 + F((F(3) + F(6))))^{F(F(4))} \\
 3367 &:= 3 + F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(7) \\
 3373 &:= -F(3) + (F(3) + F(7))^3 \\
 3374 &:= -((F(F(3)) - (((F(3) + F(7))^{F(4)}))) \\
 3382 &:= (((-F(F(3))) + F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(8)))))) / 2) \\
 3383 &:= ((F(F(3)) + F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(8)))))) / F(3)) \\
 3384 &:= ((3 + F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(8)))))) / F(F(4))) \\
 3495 &:= ((3 \times F((4 + 9))) \times 5) \\
 3528 &:= ((F((3 + 5))^2) \times 8) \\
 3569 &:= -((F(F(3)) + ((-5) \times F(F(6))) \times F(9))) \\
 3575 &:= (F((F(3) \times 5)) \times (F(7) \times 5)) \\
 3584 &:= (F(3) + 5) \times 8^{F(4)} \\
 3602 &:= F(3) + 60^2 \\
 3603 &:= 3 + 60^{F(3)} \\
 3635 &:= (((3^6) - F(3)) \times 5) \\
 3639 &:= (((-F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) / 3) - 9) \\
 3644 &:= (((-F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) / F(4)) - 4) \\
 3645 &:= (((3 + 6)^{F(4)}) \times 5) \\
 3648 &:= (((-F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) / F(-((4 - 8)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3649 &:= (((3 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(4)) / 9) \\
 3666 &:= ((F(F(3)) + F((-6) + F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 3726 &:= (-F(3) - (F(F(7)) \times (-2) \times F(6))) \\
 3728 &:= ((-F(3)) \times F(F(7))) \times (F(2) \times (-8)) \\
 3736 &:= (((F(3) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(3))) \times F(6)) \\
 3738 &:= ((F(3) \times F((F(7) - F(3)))) \times F(8)) \\
 3744 &:= ((F(3) \times F(7)) \times F((F(4) \times 4))) \\
 3773 &:= (-F(3) + F(7)) \times 7^3 \\
 3784 &:= ((3^7) + F((F(8) - (4)))) \\
 3786 &:= ((F((F(3) + F(7))) + (F(8))) \times 6) \\
 3844 &:= (((-F(3)) + (8^{F(F(4))})^{F(F(4))} \\
 3948 &:= F(3) \times 94 \times F(8) \\
 3966 &:= (-3) - (((-9) \times F(F(6))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 3968 &:= -((F(F(3)) + ((-9) \times F(F(6))) \times F(8))) \\
 3969 &:= (F(F(-((3 - 9)))) \times (F(F(6)) \times 9)) \\
 3979 &:= (F(F(3)) - (((-9) \times F(7)) \times F(9))) \\
 4176 &:= (-((4 + 1)) + F((F(7) + (6)))) \\
 4177 &:= (-4) + F((-((1 - 7)) + F(7))) \\
 4181 &:= F((-((4 - 1)) + F(8) + 1)) \\
 4182 &:= (F(F((4 - 1))) + F((F(8) - 2))) \\
 4183 &:= (F(F(4)) + F((F((1 \times 8)) - F(3)))) \\
 4184 &:= (F(4) + F(((1 + F(8)) - F(4)))) \\
 4197 &:= F(4) + F(19) + F(7) \\
 4198 &:= -4 + F(19) + F(8) \\
 4277 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) + (F((2 + F(7)))) \times 7) \\
 4372 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((3^7) - F(2))) \\
 4373 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times (3^7)) - F(F(3))) \\
 4374 &:= (((F(F(4)) + F(F(3)))^7) \times F(F(4))) \\
 4386 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) - (3^8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 4388 &:= ((F(4) - (3^8)) + F(F(8))) \\
 4394 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (F(-((F(3) - 9)))^{F(4)})) \\
 4427 &:= ((F(4) + ((4^2))) \times F(F(7))) \\
 4455 &:= ((F(4)^4) \times 55) \\
 4536 &:= (((F(F(F(4))) + (5)^3) \times F(F(6))) \\
 4576 &:= (-4) \times (((-5) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(6))) \\
 4578 &:= (((F(4) \times (-5)) + F(F(7))) \times F(8)) \\
 4624 &:= ((4 + (F(6)^2))^{F(F(4))} \\
 4632 &:= ((F(4) + (F(F(6))^3)) / 2) \\
 4647 &:= (F(-((F(F(4)) - F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(4)) \times F(F(7))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4720 &:= ((-F(4) - F(F(7))) \times (-20)) \\
 4746 &:= (((-F(4) + F(F(7))) - (4)) \times F(F(6))) \\
 4765 &:= (((4 \times F(F(7))) + F(F(6))) \times 5) \\
 4766 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (((F(F(7)) - (6)) \times F(F(6)))))) \\
 4767 &:= (F(4) \times ((F(F(7)) - (6)) \times 7)) \\
 4768 &:= (F(F(F(4))) - ((F(F(7)) - (6)) \times (-F(8)))) \\
 4776 &:= ((F((F(F(4)) + (F(7)))) - F(7)) \times F(6)) \\
 4788 &:= (((F(4) + F(F(7))) - 8) \times F(8)) \\
 4791 &:= F(4) \times F(7 + 9 + 1) \\
 4794 &:= 47 \times F(9) \times F(4) \\
 4847 &:= (-4) + (-F(8)) \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) \\
 4864 &:= ((F(F(4)))^8) \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) \\
 4871 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) + (-F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - 1))) \\
 4872 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(2)))) \\
 4873 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(3)))) \\
 4874 &:= (F(F(4)) - (-F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 4876 &:= -4 + F(8 + 7) \times F(6) \\
 4877 &:= (-F(4)) + ((F(8) \times F(F(7))) - (F(7))) \\
 4878 &:= -((F(F(4)) + (-8) \times F((7 + 8)))) \\
 4887 &:= ((F(F(4)) - 8) + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 4889 &:= (-4) + (F(8) \times F(-((F(8) - F(9)))) \\
 4892 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (F(8) \times F(F((9 - 2)))) \\
 4893 &:= F(4 + 8) \times F(9) - 3 \\
 4894 &:= ((F((4 + 8)) \times F(9)) - F(F(4))) \\
 4896 &:= (((F(4) \times (-8)) \times F(9)) \times (-6)) \\
 4899 &:= (F(4) - (F((F(8) - 9)) \times (-F(9)))) \\
 4913 &:= -4 + F(9 - 1)^3 \\
 4935 &:= (F(((4 + 9) + 3)) \times 5) \\
 4998 &:= ((F(F(4)) - 9) \times (-F(9) \times F(8))) \\
 5184 &:= ((51 + F(8))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 5439 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(4))))/F(3)) - F(9)) \\
 5463 &:= (((-((5 \times 4)) + F(F(F(6))))/F(3)) \\
 5464 &:= (-((5 + 4)) - (F(F(F(6)))/(-F(F(4)))) \\
 5468 &:= (-5) - (((-4) \times F(F(F(6))))/8) \\
 5473 &:= (F(F(((5 - 4) + 7)))/F(3)) \\
 5482 &:= ((5 + 4) - (F(F(8)))/(-2)) \\
 5483 &:= (((5 \times 4) + F(F(8)))/F(3)) \\
 5675 &:= (-5) \times ((6 - F(F(7))) \times 5) \\
 5785 &:= (((-5) \times F(F(7))) + 8) \times (-5) \\
 5825 &:= (F((5 + 8)) \times 25) \\
 6300 &:= (F(F(6)) \times 300) \\
 6548 &:= -F(6) - 5 + F(4)^8 \\
 6561 &:= ((F(6) - (5))^{F(6 \times 1)}) \\
 6562 &:= (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} + F(2) \\
 6563 &:= (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} + F(3) \\
 6564 &:= (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} + F(4) \\
 6615 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \times 15) \\
 6676 &:= ((F((-6) + F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 6728 &:= (((F(F(F(6)))/F(7)) - F(2)) \times 8) \\
 6736 &:= ((F(F(F(6)))/(-F(7))) \times (-F(3) + (6))) \\
 6744 &:= -((F(F(6)) - F(((F(7) + F(4)) + (4)))) \\
 6746 &:= ((-6) - F(7)) + F(-((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(6)))))) \\
 6757 &:= (-((6 - (7 \times 5))) \times F(F(7))) \\
 6762 &:= ((F(F(6)))/(-7)) + F((F(F(6)) - F(2))) \\
 6763 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (F((F(7) + (6))) + F(3))) \\
 6764 &:= (F((F(F(6)) - (7 - 6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 6765 &:= F(((6 + F(7)) + (6 - 5))) \\
 6771 &:= (6 + F((F(7) + (7 \times 1)))) \\
 6772 &:= ((F(6) + F((F(7) + (7)))) - F(2)) \\
 6773 &:= ((F(6) + F((F(7) + (7)))) \times F(F(3))) \\
 6774 &:= ((6 + F((F(7) + (7)))) + F(4)) \\
 6778 &:= ((-F(6)) + F((F(7) + (7)))) + (F(8)) \\
 6784 &:= ((F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times (-8 \times 4)) \\
 6786 &:= (F(F(6)) + F(((7 - 7) + F(8)) + (6))) \\
 6794 &:= F(6 + 7) + 9^4 \\
 6799 &:= (F((F(F(6)) - F(-((7 - 9)))) + F(9)) \\
 6845 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - ((8^4) + 5)) \\
 6867 &:= ((-6) + F((8 + F(6)))) \times 7 \\
 6924 &:= (-6) \times (-((F(9)^2) + F(F(4)))) \\
 6928 &:= 6 \times F(9)^2 - 8 \\
 6933 &:= 6 \times F(9)^{F(3)} - 3 \\
 6934 &:= ((6 \times (F(9)^{F(3)})) - F(F(4))) \\
 6936 &:= 6 \times F(9) \times F(3 + 6) \\
 6942 &:= (6 \times ((F(9)^{F(F(4))}) + F(2))) \\
 6954 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times 9) + (F((5 \times 4)))) \\
 6977 &:= (((F(F(6)) + 9) \times F(F(7))) - (F(7))) \\
 6993 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (9 \times (F(9) + 3))) \\
 7163 &:= (F((F(7) + 1)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(3))) \\
 7392 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F(3)) \times (F(9) - 2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$7448 := (((F(F(7)) \times 4) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 8)$$

$$7453 := ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(4))^5)) - 3)$$

$$7454 := ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(4))^5)) - F(F(4)))$$

$$7456 := (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(4)) + (5 \times 6)))$$

$$7464 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(4)) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4))))))$$

$$7476 := (((7^{F(4)}) + F(7)) \times F(F(6)))$$

$$7645 := ((F(F(7)) + (6^4)) \times 5)$$

$$7648 := ((F(F(7)) + (6)) \times (4 \times 8))$$

$$7663 := -((F(F(7)) + (-F(6)) \times F((F(6) \times F(3))))))$$

$$7689 := (F(F(7)) \times ((F(6)/(-8)) + F(9)))$$

$$7697 := ((F(7) \times F((6+9))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$7744 := (((F(7) \times 7) - F(4))^{F(F(4))})$$

$$7759 := (7 - ((F(F(7)) - (5)) \times (-F(9))))$$

$$7776 := (-7 + F(7))^{F(7)-F(6)}$$

$$7865 := (F(7) \times (F((F(8) - (6))) - (5)))$$

$$7875 := ((F(F(7)) - 8) \times (7 \times 5))$$

$$7883 := (-F(7) - (-8) \times F((8 \times F(3))))$$

$$7911 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) - 11)$$

$$7916 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) - (1 \times 6))$$

$$7917 := (-((F(7) - F(9))) \times F((1 + F(7))))$$

$$7934 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + (3 \times 4))$$

$$7935 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + F((F(3) + (5))))$$

$$7937 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + (F(3) + F(7)))$$

$$7938 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + (F(3) \times 8))$$

$$7943 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + F((4 \times F(3))))$$

$$7946 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + (4 \times 6))$$

$$7949 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + (F(4) \times 9))$$

$$7957 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + (5 \times 7))$$

$$7964 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(F(4))))$$

$$7974 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + (F(7) \times 4))$$

$$7978 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + (7 \times 8))$$

$$7985 := (F(-(((F(7) - 9) - F(8)))) \times 5)$$

$$7986 := ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + (8 \times F(6)))$$

$$8213 := F(8) + 2^{13}$$

$$8247 := (F((8+2)) + (F(F(4))^{F(7)}))$$

$$8294 := ((F((F(8) - 2)) - F(9)) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$8352 := ((F((F(8) - F(3))) - (5)) \times 2)$$

$$8361 := (F(F(8)) - (F((3 \times 6)) + 1))$$

$$8362 := (F(F(8)) - F(((3+6) \times 2)))$$

$$8363 := ((F(F(8)) + F(F(3))) - F((6 \times 3)))$$

$$8364 := ((F(F(8)) + F(3)) - F((6 \times F(4))))$$

$$8367 := (-F(8) + (36 \times F(F(7))))$$

$$8368 := -(((F((F(8) - 3)) - (6)) - F(F(8))))$$

$$8383 := (F(8) + (F(3) \times F((F(8) - F(3)))))$$

$$8396 := (-((F((F(8) - 3)) - F(9))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$8400 := (F(8) \times 400)$$

$$8464 := ((84 + F(6))^{F(F(4))})$$

$$8820 := ((F(8) \times F(8)) \times 20)$$

$$8849 := (F(F(8)) - (F(F((F(8)/F(4)))) \times 9))$$

$$8883 := (-F((8+8)) \times (-8 - F(F(3))))$$

$$8972 := (F(F(8)) + (F((9+7)) \times (-2)))$$

$$9248 := ((F(9)^{-2+4}) \times 8)$$

$$9346 := (-((F((F(9)/F(3))) + F(4))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$9348 := ((-F((F(9)/F(3)))) - F(F(F(4)))) + F(F(8)))$$

$$9349 := (-F((F(9)/F(3))) + F(F(F(-((F(4) - 9))))))$$

$$9363 := ((F(9) \times 3) + (F(F(6))^3))$$

$$9474 := 9^{F(4)} \times F(7) - F(4)$$

$$9477 := 9^{-4+7} \times F(7)$$

$$9586 := ((F(9) \times (-5 \times 8)) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$9756 := ((F(9) \times (-7 \times 5)) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$9837 := ((98^{F(3)}) + F(F(7)))$$

$$10176 := ((F(10) \times (-1 - F(7))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$10247 := (F(F((10-2))) - (F(4) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$10336 := (1 + 03) \times F(3 \times 6)$$

$$10394 := (-10) + ((3 \times F(9))^{F(F(4))})$$

$$10396 := ((-F(10)) \times (F(F(3)) + 9)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$10443 := (((F(10) + 4))^{F(F(4))}) \times 3)$$

$$10446 := ((-((10^{F(4)})/F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$10476 := (-((10 \times 47)) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$10616 := ((F(10) \times (-6)) + F(F(F((1 \times 6)))))$$

$$10639 := (((1 + F(F(06)))^3) - 9)$$

$$10644 := (((1 + F(F(06)))^{F(4)}) - 4)$$

$$10648 := ((1 + F(F(06)))^{F(-4+8)})$$

$$10658 := ((-F(10)) - F((F(6) + (5)))) + F(F(8)))$$

$$10679 := (F(F(F((1 \times 06)))) - ((F(F(7)) + F(9))))$$

$$10713 := (F(F((1+07))) - F(13))$$

$$10723 := ((10 - F(F(7))) + F(F((2^3))))$$

$$10736 := (-(((10 \times 7) \times 3)) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$10764 := (((F(10) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 10768 &:= ((F(10) - F((7 + 6))) + F(F(8))) \\
 10776 &:= ((-1) + ((0 - F(7)) \times F(7))) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 10777 &:= (F(F((1 + 07))) - (F(7) \times F(7))) \\
 10778 &:= ((1 + ((0 - F(7)) \times F(7))) + F(F(8))) \\
 10812 &:= ((10 + F(F(8))) - (F(12))) \\
 10816 &:= ((-10) \times F((8 - 1))) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 10836 &:= ((-F(10)) + F(F(8))) - F((F(3) + F(6))) \\
 10838 &:= ((-108) \times F(F(3))) + F(F(8)) \\
 10846 &:= (-((10^{8/4})) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 10847 &:= ((-10) + F(F(8))) - F((4 + 7)) \\
 10856 &:= ((-1) + F(F(08))) - (F((5 + 6))) \\
 10857 &:= ((F(10) + F(F(8))) - (F((5 + 7)))) \\
 10858 &:= (((F(10) \times 8)/(-5)) + F(F(8))) \\
 10863 &:= ((-(10 \times 8)) + F(F(F(6)))) - 3 \\
 10864 &:= ((-(10 \times 8)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(4)) \\
 10865 &:= (((-F(10)) + F(F(8))) - F(F(6))) - (5) \\
 10867 &:= ((-1) + F(F(08))) + (-6) \times F(7)) \\
 10868 &:= ((-10) + F(F(8))) - (68) \\
 10873 &:= (F(F((1 \times 08))) - (73)) \\
 10874 &:= ((-F(10)) + F(F(8))) - (F(7) + (4)) \\
 10876 &:= ((-F(10)) + F(F(8))) - (7 + F(6)) \\
 10877 &:= ((-F(10)) + F(F(8))) - (7 + 7) \\
 10878 &:= ((10 + F(F(8))) - (78)) \\
 10882 &:= ((-F(10)) + F(F(8))) - (8 + F(2)) \\
 10883 &:= ((-F(10)) + F(F(8))) - F((8 - F(3))) \\
 10884 &:= ((-F(10)) + F(F(8))) - (F(8)/F(4)) \\
 10891 &:= (F(F((1 \times 08))) - F((9 + 1))) \\
 10892 &:= ((1 + F(F(08))) - F((9 + F(2)))) \\
 10893 &:= ((-F(10)) + F(F(8))) + F((9/3)) \\
 10894 &:= ((-F(10)) + F(F(8))) + (9/F(4)) \\
 10895 &:= ((-F(10)) + F(F(8))) + (9 - 5) \\
 10896 &:= ((-10) + F(F(8))) - (F(9) + (6)) \\
 10923 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) - 23) \\
 10925 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) - F(F((F(2) + (5)))))) 10926 \\
 10927 &:= (-((10 + 9)) + F(F((F(2) + (7)))))) \\
 10928 &:= (((1 \times 0) - 9) \times 2) + F(F(8)) \\
 10933 &:= ((-10) + F(F(F((9 - 3)))) - 3) \\
 10934 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) - (3 \times 4)) \\
 10936 &:= -10 + F(9 \times 3 - 6) \\
 10937 &:= 1 \times 0 - 9 + F(3 \times 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 10938 &:= (F(((10 + 9) + F(3))) - 8) \\
 10939 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) + ((F(3) - 9))) \\
 10941 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) - (4 + 1)) \\
 10942 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) - (F(4) + F(2))) \\
 10943 &:= ((F((F(10) - F(9))) - (4)) + F(F(3))) \\
 10944 &:= ((F((F(10) - F(9))) - (4)) + F(F(4))) \\
 10945 &:= (-1) + F(F(((09 + 4) - 5))) \\
 10946 &:= F(10 + 9 - 4 + 6) \\
 10947 &:= (1 + F((F(((0 \times 9) + 4)) \times 7))) \\
 10948 &:= ((10/9 - 4) + F(F(8))) \\
 10951 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) + (5 \times 1)) \\
 10952 &:= F(F(10) - F(9)) + 5 + F(2) \\
 10953 &:= F(F(10) - F(9)) + 5 + F(3) \\
 10954 &:= F(F(10) - F(9)) + 5 + F(4) \\
 10956 &:= (10 + F(F(((9 + 5) - 6))) \\
 10958 &:= ((10 + F(F((9 - 5)))) + F(F(8))) \\
 10962 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) + (F(6) \times 2)) \\
 10963 &:= (((10 + 9) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(3)) \\
 10964 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) + (6 \times F(4))) \\
 10965 &:= (((-10) + F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (5) \\
 10966 &:= ((10 \times F((9 - 6))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 10967 &:= ((F(10) - F(9)) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 10968 &:= ((1 + F(F(((0 \times 9) + 6)))) + F(F(8))) \\
 10972 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) + (F(7) \times 2)) \\
 10974 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) + (7 \times 4)) \\
 10976 &:= ((10 \times F((-9) + F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 10978 &:= (((10 + 9) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \\
 10979 &:= ((-1) + F((F(09) - F(7)))) + F(9) \\
 10992 &:= ((F(10) - 9) + F(F((9 - F(2)))))) \\
 11035 &:= (F(11) + F(F((03 + 5)))) \\
 11036 &:= ((F(11) + F(F(03))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 11038 &:= ((F(11) + 03) + F(F(8))) \\
 11046 &:= (((1 \times 10)^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 11048 &:= ((F(11) + F(F(06)))) + F(9) \\
 11069 &:= ((F(11) + F(F(F(06)))) + F(9)) \\
 11076 &:= (((1 \times 10) \times F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 11125 &:= (F(11) \times 125) \\
 11126 &:= (((-1) - F(11)) \times (-2)) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 11166 &:= ((11 \times (-1) + F(F(6))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 11167 &:= ((-(1 + 11)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 11168** := $((-11) + F(F((1 + 6)))) + F(F(8))$
11176 := $((-(((1 + 1) + 1)) + F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6))))$
11177 := $-1 - 1 + F(17) \times 7$
11178 := $((-1) + F(F(((1 - 1) + 7)))) + F(F(8))$
11188 := $((11 \times (1 + F(8))) + F(F(8)))$
11236 := $((1 + F(12)) \times F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))$
11267 := $((F(11) - F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))$
11268 := $((F(11) + F(F((F(2) + (6)))))) + F(F(8))$
11298 := $((11 \times (-2) + F(9)) + F(F(8)))$
11323 := $(F((1 + 13)) + F(F((2^3)))$
11386 := $((F((11 - F(F(3)))) \times 8) + F(F(F(6))))$
11392 := $F(11) \times F(3)^{9-2}$
11458 := $((1 + 1)^{4+5}) + F(F(8))$
11466 := $(((-F(11)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(6))) \times (-6)$
11468 := $(((-F(11)) + F(F(4))) \times (-6)) + F(F(8))$
11489 := $(1 + (1 + 4)^8) / F(9)$
11495 := $((11^{F(F(4))}) \times 95)$
11556 := $(F(((1 + 1) \times 5) + 5)) + F(F(F(6)))$
11557 := $((1 + F(15)) + F(F((-5) + F(7))))$
11589 := $(((-1) + F(15)) + F(F(8))) + F(9)$
11606 := $((11 \times 60) + F(F(F(6))))$
11628 := $((11 \times 62) + F(F(8)))$
11645 := $((F(11) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F((F(4) \times 5))))$
11646 := $((1 + (F(F((1 + 6))) \times F(4))) + F(F(F(6))))$
11647 := $((1 + 1) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(4) \times F(F(7)))$
11648 := $((1 + F(F((1 + 6)))) \times F(4)) + F(F(8))$
11650 := $(F(F(((1 \times 1) + 6))) \times 50)$
11666 := $((F(11) \times F(6)) + F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))$
11750 := $((1 + 1) + F(F(7))) \times 50$
11787 := $(-1) + (((1 + F(7)) \times F(F(8))) / F(7))$
11828 := $((1 + 1) \times (F(8)^2)) + F(F(8))$
11836 := $((F(11) \times (8 + F(3))) + F(F(F(6))))$
11837 := $(F(11) \times ((F(8) - F(3)) \times 7))$
11844 := $((F(((1 + 1) \times 8)) \times F(4)) \times 4)$
11934 := $((1 + F(F(-(1 - 9)))) + (F(F(3^4))))$
11946 := $((1 \times 1) + 9)^{F(4)} + F(F(F(6)))$
11979 := $((11^{F(-9+F(7))}) \times 9)$
12238 := $((F((12 \times 2)) / F(3)) - F(F(8)))$
12264 := $((-((F(12) + 2)) \times F(F(6))) \times (-4))$
12348 := $(F(12) + 3) \times 4 \times F(8)$
12384 := $F(12) \times (F(3) + 84)$
12386 := $((F(12) \times (F(3) + 8)) + F(F(F(6))))$
12528 := $((1 + 2) \times (-5) + F((-2) + F(8)))$
12543 := $(F(((1 + 2) \times 5) + 4)) \times 3$
12544 := $((1 + F((2 \times 5))) \times F(F(4)))^{F(F(4))}$
12546 := $((F((12 + 5)) + F(4)) + F(F(F(6))))$
12576 := $(((-1) + F((2 \times 5))) \times F(F(7))) - (6)$
12577 := $(F(F(((1 + 2) + 5))) - (F(F(7)) \times (-7)))$
12578 := $(1 - ((F(F((2 + 5))) \times (-7)) - F(F(8))))$
12582 := $((-1) + F((2 \times 5))) \times F(F((8 - F(2))))$
12666 := $(-F(12)) + (F(F(6)) \times F((-6) + F(F(6))))$
12672 := $F(12) \times F(6) \times (F(7) - 2)$
12687 := $(-F(12)) + (F((F(6) + 8)) \times F(7))$
12727 := $((-1) + F(-(F(2) - F(7)))) \times F((-2) + F(7))$
12746 := $(-1) + ((F((2 + F(7))) - F(4)) \times F(F(6)))$
12748 := $(1 + ((F((2 + F(7))) - F(4)) \times F(8)))$
12749 := $(-1) - ((F((2 \times 7)) - F(F(4))) \times (-F(9)))$
12768 := $((1 - F(((2 + 7) + F(6)))) \times (-8))$
12776 := $F(1 + 2 + 7 + 7) \times F(6)$
12784 := $((-1) + F((2 \times 7))) \times F((8 + F(F(F(4))))$
12786 := $((-((1 + 2)) + F(F(7))) \times 8) + F(F(F(6)))$
12788 := $-1 + (-F(2) + F(7 + 8)) \times F(8)$
12796 := $((-1) + (F((2 \times 7)) \times F(9))) - F(F(6))$
12797 := $(-1 + F(2 \times 7)) \times F(9) + F(7)$
12798 := $1 + F(2 \times 7) \times F(9) - F(8)$
12816 := $F(12) \times (81 + F(6))$
12817 := $-1 + (F(2 \times 8) - 1) \times F(7)$
12818 := $(-1 + F(2 \times 8)) \times F(-1 + 8)$
12819 := $1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9)$
12827 := $(12 + (F((8 + 2)) \times F(F(7))))$
12844 := $((1 + F((2 \times 8))) \times F((F(4) + (4))))$
12857 := $((1 \times 2) + F((F(8) - (5)))) \times F(7)$
12871 := $(1 - (-F((2 + 8))) \times (F(F(7)) + 1))$
12915 := $((-1) + F((2 \times 9))) \times (1 \times 5)$
12918 := $((1 + 2)^9) - F((-1) + F(8))$
12925 := $((1^2) + F((9 \times 2))) \times 5$
12935 := $((F(((1 \times 2) \times 9)) + 3) \times 5)$
12945 := $((1 + F((2 \times 9))) + (4)) \times 5$
12959 := $(1 + F(2 \times 9)) \times 5 + F(9)$
12965 := $((1 + F((2 \times 9))) + F(6)) \times 5$

$$\begin{aligned} 13247 &:= -1 + F(3) \times F(24)/7 \\ 13276 &:= (((1 + (3^2)) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 13376 &:= (((13^3) + F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 13488 &:= (F((1 \times 3)) \times (F(-((F(F(F(4))) - (F(8)))))) - (F(8))) \\ 13489 &:= ((F((-1) + (3^{F(4)}))) + 8)/9 \\ 13520 &:= F(1 \times 3) \times (-5 + F(20)) \\ 13525 &:= F((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 2 - 5 \\ 13528 &:= ((F((13 + 5)) - 2) + F(F(8))) \\ 13530 &:= F((1 + 3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 0 \\ 13543 &:= 13 + F(5 \times 4) \times F(3) \\ 13546 &:= F(1 \times 3) \times (F(5 \times 4) + F(6)) \\ 13549 &:= 1 + F(3) \times (F(5 \times 4) + 9) \\ 13572 &:= (1 + 35) \times F(7 \times 2) \\ 13650 &:= ((13 \times F(F(6))) \times 50) \\ 13746 &:= (((1 + (3 \times F(F(7)))) \times 4) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 13747 &:= F(13) \times (F(7) \times 4 + 7) \\ 13765 &:= (((-1) - (F(3)^{F(7)})) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\ 13776 &:= (F(13) + F(7)) \times 7 \times F(6) \\ 13817 &:= (-1) - (F((F(3) \times 8)) \times (-1) - F(7))) \\ 13823 &:= -1 + (3 \times F(8 - 2))^3 \\ 13824 &:= ((1 + 3 + 8) \times 2)^{F(4)} \\ 13837 &:= (1 \times 3 \times 8)^3 + F(7) \\ 13846 &:= ((1 + ((3 \times 8)^{F(4)})) + F(F(6))) \\ 13924 &:= (((13 \times 9) + F(2))^{F(F(4))}) \\ 13949 &:= (F((1 + F(-((F(3) - 9)))))) \times (F(4) + F(9))) \\ 13975 &:= ((-1) + ((3 + 9) \times F(F(7)))) \times 5 \\ 13976 &:= (1 + ((F(-((F(3) - 9))) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\ 14179 &:= 1 + 417 \times F(9) \\ 14284 &:= ((-F(14)) - F(-((F(2) - F(8)))) \times (-F(F(4)))) \\ 14326 &:= F(14) \times (32 + 6) \\ 14336 &:= 14 \times F(3)^{F(3)+F(6)} \\ 14373 &:= F(14 + 3) \times (7 + F(3)) \\ 14374 &:= (1 - ((F(4) \times (-3)) \times F((F(7) + (4)))))) \\ 14447 &:= (1 - ((F(F(4)) - ((F^{F(4)}))) \times F(F(7)))) \\ 14617 &:= (1 - ((-F(4)) \times F(F(6))) \times (-1) + F(F(7)))) \\ 14637 &:= (((-1) - F(-((F(F(4)) - F(F(6)))))) / (-F(3))) \times 7 \\ 14638 &:= (((1 + 4)^6) - F((F(3) \times 8))) \\ 14642 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 + F(2) \\ 14643 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 + F(3) \\ 14644 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 + F(4) \\ 14658 &:= ((-1) + (F(4) \times F((F(6) + (5)))) \times F(8)) \\ 14672 &:= (-1) - (-F(4) \times ((F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))) - 2)) \\ 14673 &:= (F((1 \times 4)) \times ((F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))) - F(3))) \\ 14674 &:= (-1) + (((F(4) \times F(F(6))) \times F(F(7))) - (4)) \\ 14675 &:= (1 - (((-F(4)) \times F(F(6))) \times F(F(7))) + (5)) \\ 14678 &:= -1 + F(4) \times F(6 + 7) \times F(8) \\ 14679 &:= (F(F(((1^4) + 6))) \times (7 \times 9)) \\ 14682 &:= ((F(14) \times F(F(6))) + F((F(8) - F(2)))) \\ 14703 &:= ((F(14) \times F(7)) \times 03) \\ 14739 &:= (-1 + 4 \times F(7))^3/9 \\ 14768 &:= (((14 \times F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \\ 14783 &:= (-1) + ((F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) \times (-8^{F(3)})) \\ 14784 &:= (((1 - F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times (8^{F(F(4))})) \\ 14872 &:= ((-1) + F((F(4) + 8))) \times (F(7)^2) \\ 14884 &:= (((-1) + F((4 + 8))) - F(8))^{F(F(4))} \\ 14976 &:= F(-1 + 4 + 9) \times F(7) \times F(6) \\ 14987 &:= (-1 + F(4) \times F(9) \times F(8)) \times 7 \\ 15126 &:= ((-1) + F(F(F((5 + 1)))) + F((-2) + F(F(6)))) \\ 15127 &:= (F(F(F((1 + 5)))) + F((12 + 7))) \\ 15128 &:= (F(F(F((1 + 5)))) + (1 + F((-2) + F(8)))) \\ 15225 &:= ((F(15) - F(2)) \times 25) \\ 15325 &:= ((F(15) + 3) \times 25) \\ 15345 &:= (-15) \times (F(F(3)) - (4^5)) \\ 15377 &:= (-1) - ((-53) - F(7)) \times F(F(7))) \\ 15435 &:= ((F(F((1 + 5)))^{F(F(4))}) \times 35) \\ 15448 &:= F((1 + 5) \times 4) / F(4) - 8 \\ 15456 &:= F((1 + 5) \times 4) / (-5 + F(6)) \\ 15463 &:= ((-F(((1 + 5) \times 4))) - F(F(6))) / (-3) \\ 15464 &:= F(1 + 5) + F(4 \times 6) / F(4) \\ 15486 &:= ((-F(-((1 - 5)))) + F(-((F(4) - F(8)))) \times 6) \\ 15492 &:= (-((1 + 5)) \times (F(F(4)) - F((9 \times 2)))) \\ 15496 &:= (((1 + 5) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 9))) - F(6)) \\ 15497 &:= (((1 + 5) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 9))) - 7) \\ 15544 &:= (((1 + 5)^5) - 4) \times F(F(4)) \\ 15546 &:= (((1 + 5)^5) \times F(F(4))) - (6) \\ 15564 &:= (((1 + 5)^5) + 6) \times F(F(4)) \\ 15616 &:= -1 + 5^6 - 1 \times F(6) \\ 15625 &:= 1 \times 5^{F(6)} / 25 \end{aligned}$$

- 15627** := $1 + 5^6 + F(2)^{F(7)}$
15634 := $1 \times 5^6 + 3 \times F(4)$
15635 := $1 \times 5^6 + F(3) \times 5$
15636 := $1 \times 5^6 + 3 + F(6)$
15637 := $1 + 5^6 - F(3) + F(7)$
15638 := $((1 \times 5)^6 + F(-(F(F(3)) - 8)))$
15639 := $((1 + (5^6)) + F(-(F(3) - 9)))$
15646 := $(F(F((1 + 5))) + (((F(6) - F(4))^6)))$
15647 := $1 + 5^6 + F(4) \times 7$
15648 := $-1 + 5^6 + F(4) + F(8)$
15665 := $1 \times 5^6 + F(6) \times 5$
15666 := $((-(1 - (5^6))) + F(F(6))) + F(F(6)))$
15668 := $((1 + (5^6)) + F(F(6))) + (F(8))$
15673 := $-1 + 5^6 + 7^{F(3)}$
15674 := $((1 \times 5)^6 + (7^{F(F(4))}))$
15692 := $-1 + 5^6 + F(9) \times 2$
15693 := $1 \times 5^6 + F(9) \times F(3)$
15694 := $((1 + (5^6)) - (-(F(9)) \times F(F(4))))$
15696 := $-1 + 5^6 + 9 \times F(6)$
15748 := $((F(F(-(1 - 5))) \times (7^4)) + F(F(8)))$
15750 := $(F(F((1 + 5))) \times 750)$
15774 := $((-(1 - 5)^7) - F((F(7) + F(F(4))))))$
15792 := $((F((1 + 5)) \times F((7 + 9))) \times 2)$
15826 := $((F(15) \times 8) + F(F((2 + 6))))$
15828 := $((F(15) \times 8) + 2) + F(F(8))$
15839 := $(F(F(F((1 + 5)))) - (-(F(8)) \times F(F(-(F(3) - 9))))))$
15842 := $(F(F(-(1 - 5))) \times (F((8 + F(4))^2))$
15855 := $F(15) \times (F(8) + 5) - 5$
16347 := $-1 - 6^{F(3)} + 4^7$
16368 := $-16 + F(3)^{6+8}$
16371 := $-F(1 + 6) + F(3)^{F(7)+1}$
16372 := $-1 \times 6 + F(3)^{F(7)} \times 2$
16373 := $1 - 6 + F(3)^{F(7)} \times F(3)$
16374 := $((1 - 6) + (F(3)^{F(7)}) \times F(F(4)))$
16376 := $(1^6 + 3)^7 - F(6)$
16378 := $-1 \times 6 + F(3)^{-7+F(8)}$
16383 := $-1 + F(6)^{3+8} / F(3)$
16388 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) + ((-3) \times F(8)) \times F(8))$
16393 := $(1 - (((F(F(F(6))) / F(3)) - 9) \times (-3)))$
16413 := $((1 + ((F(F(F(6))) / (-F(F(4)))) + 1)) \times (-3))$
16416 := $((1 - (6^4)) + F((1 + F(F(6)))))$
16418 := $(F((1 + F(6))) + ((4^{-1+8})))$
16419 := $(((-1) \times F(F(F(6)))) / (-F(F(4)))) + F(F(-(1 - 9)))$
16450 := $((F(16) / F(4)) \times 50)$
16464 := $(((-1) + F(F(6))) + (4^6)) \times 4$
16479 := $((-1) - (F(6) \times (4 - F(F(7)))) \times 9)$
16483 := $(1 - (((F(F(F(6))) / (-F(F(4)))) - (F(8))) \times 3))$
16546 := $((F(F((1 + 6))) \times (-5)) + F((F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(6))))))$
16556 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - (55 \times F(F(6))))$
16572 := $((((1 + 6)^5) - F(F(7))) - 2)$
16573 := $((((1 + 6)^5) - F(F(7))) - F(F(3)))$
16574 := $((((1 + 6)^5) - F(F(7))) \times F(F(F(4))))$
16575 := $((1 - F((F(6) + (5)))) + (7^5))$
16576 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) + (-5) \times (F(F(7)) - (6)))$
16642 := $(1 + (((F(F(6)) \times 6) + F(4))^2))$
16644 := $(((-1) + F(F(6))) - F((F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))) \times (-4))$
16675 := $((1 + F(F(6))) \times (-6)) + (7^5)$
16678 := $(-1) + (((F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \times F(7)) + F(F(8)))$
16722 := $((-1) + (F((6 + F(7))) \times 2)) \times 2$
16723 := $(-1) + (F((6 + F(7))) \times (F(2) + 3))$
16724 := $(-F(16)) + F(((F(7) \times 2) - (4)))$
16725 := $(1 + (F((6 + F(7))) \times (-F(2) - (5))))$
16728 := $((1 + F((6 + F(7)))) / 2) \times 8$
16737 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - (-(F(7)) + F((3 + F(7))))))$
16744 := $((1 + F((6 + F(7)))) + (4)) \times 4$
16746 := $(1 + ((F((6 + F(7))) \times 4) + F(F(6))))$
16749 := $((F((1 \times 6)) \times F(F(7))) - F(4)) \times 9$
16764 := $((1 + F(F(6))) \times ((F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times F(4)))$
16766 := $((((-1) - F(F(6))) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6)))$
16768 := $((1 + F(6)) \times F(F(7))) \times F(6) - 8$
16769 := $(-(1 + 6)) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) \times 9))$
16773 := $(-(F((1 + F(6))) - ((7^{7-F(3)})))$
16775 := $(-1) + ((-6) \times F(F(7))) \times (-7 + 5))$
16776 := $((16 - 7) \times F(F(7))) \times F(6)$
16777 := $(1 + (-6) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(7))) + F(F(7))))$
16779 := $F(16) \times ((F(7) + F(7)) - 9)$
16786 := $((1 + 6)^{F(7)-8} - F(F(6)))$

- 16787** := $((1 - F(F(6))) + ((7^{-8+F(7)}))$
16789 := $(F((1 + 6)) + (F(F(7)) \times (8 \times 9)))$
16792 := $(F((1 \times 6)) \times ((F(F(7)) \times 9) + 2))$
16793 := $(1 - (F(6) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-9)) - F(3))))$
16794 := $-F(1 + 6) + 7^{9-4}$
16796 := $(-1) + (((F(6) \times F(F(7))) \times 9) + F(F(6)))$
16798 := $(1 + (((F(6) \times F(F(7))) \times 9) + (F(8))))$
16800 := $(F(F((1 \times 6))) \times 800)$
16807 := $(1 + 6)^{-8+F(07)}$
16815 := $F(1 \times 6) + (8 - 1)^5$
16847 := $-1 + 6^{8-4} \times F(7)$
16863 := $F(16) + (F(8) \times 6)^{F(3)}$
16868 := $((1 \times 6) \times F((8 + F(6)))) + F(F(8))$
16869 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(8))/F(F(6)) - F(9))))$
16870 := $((F(F((1 + 6))) + 8) \times 70)$
16896 := $((1 + F(F(6))) \times (8 \times 96))$
16935 := $((F((-1) + F(F(6)))) + 9)/F(3) \times 5$
16963 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - (F(9) \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(3))))$
16967 := $(-1) - (-F(F(6))) \times (-F(9) - (F(F(F(6)))/(-F(7))))$
16982 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - (9^{F(8/2)}))$
16997 := $((F(F((1 \times 6))) \times (-F(9))) + F((9 + F(7))))$
17239 := $1 + F(7)^2 \times 3 \times F(9)$
17246 := $((1 + (F(F(7)) \times (-2))) + F((F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(6))))))$
17275 := $((-1) - F(F(7))) \times (-2) + (7^5)$
17334 := $(-F((1 + F(7)))) + F((F(F(3)) + F((F(3)^{F(4)})))$
17336 := $(-((F((1 + F(7))) - F(3))) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))))$
17346 := $((F(17) + 3) \times 4) + F(F(F(6)))$
17375 := $(1 - (-73) \times (F(F(7)) + (5)))$
17399 := $(1 + 7)^3 \times F(9) - 9$
17422 := $-(((17^{F(F(4))}) - F(22)))$
17469 := $((-1) \times F(F(7))) + F((F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(6)))) - 9)$
17473 := $((1 + 74) \times F(F(7))) - F(3)$
17474 := $((F((1 - (-7) \times F(4)))) - F(F(7))) - (4)$
17475 := $(F((17 - 4)) \times 75)$
17476 := $(1 - (F(F(7)) \times (F(4) + (F(7) \times (-6))))$
17477 := $((-1) - F(F(7))) + F(((F(4) + F(7)) + F(7)))$
17478 := $((F((17 + F(4))) - F(F(7))) + F(F(8)))$
17479 := $((-1) - F(F(7))) + F(F(4)) + F((F(7) + 9))$
17481 := $((-1) - F(F(7))) + (4) + F((F(8) + 1))$
17482 := $((-1) \times F(F(7))) + (4) + F((F(8) + F(2)))$
17483 := $((1 - F(F(7))) + (4)) + F((F(8) + F(F(3))))$
17486 := $((F(F((1 + 7))) + (F(4)^8)) - F(F(6)))$
17496 := $(-1 + F(7)^{F(4)} - 9) \times F(6)$
17562 := $(-((F((-1) + F(7))) + (5))) + F((F(F(6)) + F(2)))$
17563 := $((-1) \times F(7)) + ((5 + F(F(6)))^3)$
17564 := $F(17) \times (5 + 6) - F(4)$
17567 := $(-F(17)) \times (F((-5) + F(6))) - (F(7))$
17568 := $(-1 + F(7)^{-5+F(6)}) \times 8$
17583 := $1 \times 7 + (5 + F(8))^3$
17584 := $1 + 7 + (5 + F(8))^{F(4)}$
17622 := $-F(17 - 6) + F(22)$
17636 := $((1 - 76) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))))$
17640 := $((-F((1 + 7))) \times F(F(6))) \times (-40)$
17648 := $(F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - ((F(4) \times F(8))))$
17663 := $(-((1 + 7) \times 6)) + F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))))$
17669 := $(F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - (F(6) + F(9)))$
17676 := $((F(F((1 + 7))) \times F(F(6)))/F(7)) - (6)$
17682 := $((F(F((1 + 7))) \times F(F(6)))/F((8 - F(2))))$
17683 := $((-1) \times 7) - F(F(6)) + F((F(8) + F(F(3))))$
17684 := $(-((F((1 + 7)) + (6))) + F((F(8) + F(F(F(4))))))$
17685 := $(F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - (F(8) + (5)))$
17693 := $(F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - (9 \times F(3)))$
17694 := $(F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - (F(9)/F(F(4))))$
17696 := $(F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - (9 + 6))$
17697 := $-1 - F(7) + F(6 + 9 + 7)$
17698 := $(F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - (F(9) - F(8)))$
17699 := $((1 - F(7)) + F((F(F(6)) + (9/9))))$
17710 := $(-1) + F((77 - F(10)))$
17711 := $F(17 + 7 - 1 - 1)$
17712 := $(1 + F((F(7) + ((7 \times 1) + 2)))$
17713 := $(F(((1^7) + F((7 + 1)))) + F(3))$
17714 := $(F(((1^7) + F((7 + 1)))) + F(4))$
17715 := $(F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))) - ((1 - 5)))$
17716 := $((-1) + F(7)) - (7) + F((1 + F(F(6))))$
17717 := $(F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))) - ((1 - 7)))$
17718 := $((1 \times 7) + F((F(7) + (1 + 8))))$
17719 := $((1 + 7) + F((F(7) + (1 \times 9))))$
17723 := $((-1) + F(7)) + F(((F(7) - 2) \times F(3)))$
17724 := $(F((1 \times 7)) + F(((F(7) \times 2) - (4))))$
17726 := $((1 + 7) + 7) + F((F(2) + F(F(6))))$

- 17728** := $17 + F(7 \times 2 + 8)$
17729 := $(F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) + (2 \times 9))$
17732 := $(F((1 + 7)) + F((F(7) + (3^2))))$
17736 := $(((-1) + F(7)) + F(7)) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))))$
17737 := $(F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) + (F(3) \times F(7)))$
17738 := $((1 + F(7)) + F(7)) + F((F(F(3)) + F(8)))$
17745 := $(F((1 + 7)) \times ((F(7)^{F(F(4))}) \times 5))$
17749 := $(F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) + (4 + F(9)))$
17761 := $((1 + (7 \times 7)) + F((F(F(6)) + 1)))$
17766 := $(((-1) - F(F(7)))/(-F(7)) \times F((F(6) + F(6))))$
17767 := $(F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) + (F(6) \times 7))$
17784 := $((-1) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(7) + (F(8) \times F(4)))$
17788 := $((-(1 - 7)) - (-F(7) \times F(F(8))))/8$
17792 := $(F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) + (9^2))$
17816 := $((1 - (F(7) \times (-8))) + F((1 + F(F(6)))))$
17849 := $-1 + (F(7) + 8^{F(4)}) \times F(9)$
17850 := $(F((1 + 7)) \times 850)$
17854 := $(-1) + (((F(F(7)) - F(F(8))) \times 5)/(-F(4)))$
17855 := $(F((-1) + F(7)) + F((F(8) + (5/5))))$
17856 := $((1 + (7 \times F((F(8) - (5)))))) + F(F(F(6)))$
17863 := $((F((-1) + F(7)) + 8) + F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))))$
17879 := $((1 + 7) \times F(8)) + F((F(7) + 9))$
17936 := $((1 + F(F(7))) - 9) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))))$
17943 := $((-1) + F(F(7))) + F((9 + F((4 + 3))))$
17944 := $(F(F((1 \times 7))) + F((F(9) - (F(4) \times 4))))$
17945 := $((1 + F(F(7))) + F(((9 \times F(4)) - (5))))$
17947 := $F(17) - F(9) + 4^7$
17948 := $((-1) - (-7 \times F(9))) + F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8)))$
17954 := $-((F(F((1 + 7))) - ((F(9) \times 5)^{F(F(4))})))$
17966 := $(((-1) - F(F(7))) \times (-9 - F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6)))$
17979 := $((1 + F(F(7))) + F(9)) + F((F(7) + 9))$
17983 := $((1 + 7) \times F(9)) + F((F(8) + F(F(3))))$
17997 := $(-1 \times F(7) + F(9 + 9)) \times 7$
18079 := $F(18) \times 07 - 9$
18152 := $(F((1 + F(8))) + (F(F((1 + 5)))^2))$
18174 := $(((-1) - F(F((8 - 1)))) \times F(F(7)))/(-F(4))$
18177 := $-F(18) + F(17) \times F(7)$
18235 := $((-1) - ((F(F(8)) - 2)/(-3))) \times 5$
18243 := $((1 + (F(F(8)) \times (-2) - F(4)))/(-3))$
18245 := $(((-1) - F(F(8)))/F(2) - (4)) \times 5$
18277 := $((F(18) + (27)) \times 7)$
18278 := $(F((1 + F(8))) + (27 \times F(8)))$
18436 := $(F((1 + F(8))) - ((4 - (3^6))))$
18473 := $F((18 - 4)) \times (7^{F(3)})$
18480 := $((F(F(-(1 - 8)))) - F(F(4))) \times 80$
18482 := $((-1) - ((F(8)^{F(4)} - F(8))) \times (-2))$
18496 := $(F(1 + 8) \times 4)^{F(9-6)}$
18522 := $((F((1 \times 8))^{5-2}) \times 2)$
18523 := $1 + F(8)^{5-2} \times F(3)$
18524 := $((1 + (F(8)^{5-2})) \times F(F(4)))$
18689 := $((F((1 + F(8))) + F((F(6) + 8))) - 9)$
18697 := $((-1) + F((8 + F(6)))) + F((9 + F(7)))$
18698 := $((F(18) \times (-6 - 9)) + F(F(8)))$
18735 := $(F((1 + F(8))) + ((7 - 3)^5))$
18756 := $(1 + (-8 + F(7))^5) \times 6$
18792 := $((-(1^8)) + F(F(7))) \times (9^2)$
18842 := $(F(F((1 \times 8))) + (8 \times F((4^2))))$
18843 := $((1 + F(F(8))) - (-8) \times F((4^{F(3)})))$
18850 := $(F(((1 + F(8)) - 8)) \times 50)$
18863 := $(F((1 + F(8))) - (-8) \times F((6 \times F(3))))$
18868 := $((F((1 + 8)) \times F((F(8) - F(6)))) + F(F(8)))$
18869 := $((1 + F(F(8))) - (F((F(8) - F(6))) \times (-F(9))))$
18873 := $(F(F(-(1 - 8))) \times (8 + 73))$
18876 := $((F(-(1 - 8))) \times F((8 + 7))) + F(F(F(6)))$
18877 := $((1 + F(F(8))) + (F((8 + 7)) \times F(7)))$
18887 := $(F((1 + F(8))) + (F(8) \times (8 \times 7)))$
18900 := $((-1) \times F(8)) \times (-900)$
18937 := $((1 + F(F(8))) + (F(9) \times (F(3) + F(F(7))))$
18946 := $(((-1) + F(8))^{9/F(4)}) + F(F(F(6)))$
18963 := $((F((1 + 8)) + 9) \times (F(F(6))^{F(3)}))$
18970 := $(-1 + 8 \times F(9)) \times 70$
19046 := $((1 \times 90)^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(F(6)))$
19137 := $((-1) + F(F((9 - 1)))) + (F(3)^{F(7)})$
19278 := $1 \times F(9) \times 27 \times F(8)$
19279 := $1 + 9^2 \times 7 \times F(9)$
19308 := $((F(19) \times F(3)) + F(F(08)))$
19447 := $-1 + F(9) \times 44 \times F(7)$
19449 := $-1 - F(9 + 4) + F(4)^9$
19454 := $((19 \times (4^5)) - F(F(4)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 19552 &:= ((1 - F(9 + 5)) \times (-52)) \\ 19649 &:= (1 + F(9) - F(6))^{F(4)} - F(9) \\ 19652 &:= 1 \times F(9)^{F(6)-5} / 2 \\ 19653 &:= 1 + F(9)^{F(6)-5} / F(3) \\ 19664 &:= (-19) + ((F(F(6)) + (6))^{F(4)}) \\ 19665 &:= ((1 \times 9) \times ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(6)))) / 5)) \\ 19682 &:= -1 + (9 - 6)^{8+F(2)} \\ 19684 &:= 1 + (9 - 6)^8 \times F(4) \\ 19695 &:= (-1) + (((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F(9)) / 5) \\ 19697 &:= 1 + (9 - 6)^9 + F(7) \\ 19720 &:= ((1 - F(9 + 7)) \times (-20)) \\ 19734 &:= (F(F(-(1 - 9))) + ((F(7)^3) \times 4)) \\ 19735 &:= (((F(19) - F(F(7))) - F(F(3))) \times 5) \\ 19745 &:= ((-1) + (F((9 + 7)) \times (-4))) \times (-5) \\ 19747 &:= 1 + 9 \times (7 + F(4)^7) \\ 19772 &:= -1 + 9 \times F(7) \times F(7)^2 \\ 19773 &:= 1 \times 9 \times F(7)^{F(7)-3} \\ 19774 &:= 1 + 9 \times F(7)^{7-4} \\ 19775 &:= (((F(19) + (7)) - F(F(7))) \times 5) \\ 19828 &:= ((-1) + (9 \times F((8 \times 2)))) + F(F(8)) \\ 19829 &:= (F(F(-(1 - 9))) + (F((8 \times 2)) \times 9)) \\ 19845 &:= (F(-(1 - 9)) \times (F(8) \times 45)) \\ 19866 &:= ((-1) + F(9)) \times (F((F(8) - (6))) - F(6)) \\ 19918 &:= ((F(19) \times 9) - F((1 + F(8)))) \\ 19950 &:= (F(-(1 - 9)) \times 950) \\ 19965 &:= (-1 + F(9)) \times (F(9 + 6) - 5) \\ 19986 &:= ((1 + (F(9) \times (-98))) \times (-6)) \\ 20193 &:= (((F(20) \times (-1)) + F(9)) \times (-3)) \\ 20274 &:= (F(20) \times F(2) - 7) \times F(4) \\ 20295 &:= F(20) \times F(2) \times F(9 - 5) \\ 20304 &:= (F(20) + 3) \times F(04) \\ 20316 &:= ((F(20) \times 3) + F(F((1 \times 6)))) \\ 20329 &:= F(20) \times 3 \times F(2) + F(9) \\ 20343 &:= ((F(20) + (F(3)^4)) \times 3) \\ 20347 &:= F(20) \times 3 + 4 \times F(7) \\ 20364 &:= (((F(20) + F(3)) + F(F(6))) \times F(4)) \\ 20373 &:= ((F(20) + (F(3) \times F(7))) \times 3) \\ 20384 &:= ((F(20) \times 3) + F((8 + F(4)))) \\ 20394 &:= (((F(20) - F(F(3))) + F(9)) \times F(4)) \\ 20439 &:= F(20) \times F(4) + F(3 + 9) \\ 20484 &:= (F(20) + F(4) \times F(8)) \times F(4) \\ 20672 &:= ((F(20) \times F(F(6))) - F((F(7) \times 2))) \\ 20692 &:= 20 + F(6) \times F(9 \times 2) \\ 20728 &:= ((F(-(F(2) - F(07))))^2) - 8) \\ 20733 &:= ((F(-(F(2) - F(07))))^{F(3)} - 3) \\ 20734 &:= (-2) + ((F(07) - F(F(3)))^4) \\ 20735 &:= (F((2 \times 07)) \times F((F(3) \times 5))) \\ 20736 &:= (-F(2) + F(07))^{-F(3)+6} \\ 20737 &:= (F(((2 \times 07) - 3)) \times F(F(7))) \\ 20738 &:= (F(2) + (F(F(07)) \times F((3 + 8)))) \\ 20739 &:= (2 + (F(F(07)) \times F((F(3) + 9)))) \\ 20748 &:= ((F(2) + F((F(07) + F(4)))) \times F(8)) \\ 20790 &:= ((-2) + F(F(07))) \times 90 \\ 20865 &:= ((F((-2) + F(08))) - F(6)) \times 5 \\ 20946 &:= (((F(2) + 09)^4) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 21138 &:= (2 \times (-F((1 + 13))) + F(F(8))) \\ 21168 &:= (21 + F(16)) \times F(8) \\ 21426 &:= (2 \times (-F(F(((1 + 4) + 2)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 21464 &:= ((-214) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(F(4)) \\ 21578 &:= (2 \times (-157) + F(F(8))) \\ 21593 &:= -((F((F(2) + F(F((1 + 5)))) - (F(9)^3))) \\ 21636 &:= ((2 \times F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) - (F(3)^{F(6)})) \\ 21638 &:= ((2 \times (1 + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(3)^8)) \\ 21647 &:= (((F(21) - (6)) \times F(F(4))) - F(F(7))) \\ 21661 &:= ((2 \times (1 + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F((6 + 1)))) \\ 21667 &:= ((2 \times F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) + (F(6) - F(F(7)))) \\ 21678 &:= ((2 \times (-1) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(7)) - (F(8)))) \\ 21698 &:= (2 \times ((1 + F(F(F(6)))) - (98)) \\ 21736 &:= (2 \times (((-1) - F(F(7))) / 3) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 21744 &:= ((F(21) - 74) \times F(F(4))) \\ 21746 &:= (2 \times ((1 - 74) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 21748 &:= ((2 \times F(F((1 + 7)))) - F((4 + 8))) \\ 21762 &:= F(21) + (F(7) \times F(6))^2 \\ 21764 &:= (2 \times (F(F((1 + 7))) - (64))) \\ 21766 &:= ((2 \times F(F((1 + 7)))) + (-6) \times F(F(6))) \\ 21782 &:= ((-F(((2 + 1) + 7)) + F(F(8))) \times 2) \\ 21788 &:= ((F(21) + (F(7) \times (-8))) + F(F(8))) \\ 21796 &:= ((2 \times F(F((1 + 7)))) - (96)) \\ 21798 &:= (2 \times (((-1) \times F(7)) - F(9)) + F(F(8))) \end{aligned}$$

- 21824** := $((F(21) - F((8 + F(2)))) \times F(F(4)))$
21826 := $(2 \times ((1 + F(F(8))) - F((F(2) + F(6))))$
21828 := $((F(21) - (8^2)) + F(F(8)))$
21830 := $(2 \times ((-1) + F(F(8))) - (30))$
21835 := $((2 \times (-1) + F(F(8))) - F((F(3) \times 5)))$
21837 := $(F(21) - F(8)) \times F(3) - F(7)$
21838 := $(2 \times (-((1 + 8) \times 3)) + F(F(8)))$
21839 := $((2 \times (1 + F(F(8)))) - F((F(F(3)) + 9)))$
21842 := $((F(21) - F(8)) - (4)) \times 2$
21844 := $((F(21) - F(8)) - F(4)) \times F(F(4))$
21845 := $((F(21) - F(8)) \times F(F(4))) - (5)$
21846 := $((2 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))) - 46)$
21847 := $((2 \times (1 + F(F(8)))) - 47)$
21848 := $(2 \times (((1 + F(F(8))) - F(F(4))) - (F(8))))$
21852 := $(2 \times ((1 + F(F(8))) - F(F((5 + F(2))))))$
21854 := $(2 \times ((1 + F(F(8))) - (5 \times 4)))$
21856 := $(2 \times (-((F(-((1 - 8))) + (5))) + F(F(F(6))))))$
21857 := $((2 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))) - (5 \times 7))$
21858 := $(2 \times ((-1) + F(F(8))) - (-5) + F(8))$
21862 := $((F(21) - F(8)) + (6)) \times 2$
21863 := $(-((21 + 8)) - (F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(3)))$
21864 := $((F(21) - (8 + 6)) \times F(F(4)))$
21866 := $(2 \times ((-1) + F(F(8))) - (6 + 6))$
21867 := $((2 \times ((-1) + F(F(8))) - F(6)) - (7))$
21868 := $((-((2 + 1)) + F(F(8))) - F(F(6))) + F(F(8))$
21869 := $((2 \times ((-1) + F(F(8))) - (6)) - 9)$
21871 := $((F(21) - F(8)) + F(F((7 + 1))))$
21872 := $((-((2 + 1)) + F(F(8))) - (7)) \times 2$
21873 := $((2 \times (1 + F(F(8)))) - (7 \times 3))$
21874 := $((-((2) + F(F((1 \times 8)))) - (7)) \times F(F(4)))$
21875 := $((2 \times ((1 + F(F(8))) - (7))) - (5))$
21876 := $(2 \times ((-1) + F(F(8))) - (F(7) - (6)))$
21877 := $((2 \times ((-1) + F(F(8))) - (F(7))) + (F(7)))$
21878 := $((2 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))) - (-7) + F(8))$
21881 := $((2 \times (-1) + F(F(8))) - (8 + 1))$
21882 := $((2 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))) - (8 + 2))$
21883 := $((F(21) - 8) + F(F(8))) - F(F(3))$
21884 := $(2 \times ((-1) + F(F(8))) - F((8 - 4)))$
21885 := $((-((2) + F(F((1 \times 8)))) + F(F(8))) - (5))$
21886 := $((-((2 + 1)) + F(F(8))) \times (8 - 6))$
21887 := $((2 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))) - (-8) + F(7))$
21888 := $(2 \times ((-1) + F(F(8))) - (8/8))$
21889 := $((2 \times (-1) + F(F(8))) + ((8 - 9)))$
21890 := $(2 \times (-1) + F(F((8 + (9 \times 0))))$
21891 := $((-F(2)) + F(F((1 \times 8))) + F(F((9 - 1))))$
21892 := $(F(21) \times (-((8 - 9) \times 2))$
21893 := $((2 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))) + F(F((9/3))))$
21894 := $2 \times (1 + F(8 + 9 + 4))$
21895 := $((2 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))) + F((9 - 5)))$
21896 := $((2 + F(F((1 \times 8)))) \times F((9 - 6)))$
21897 := $((2 \times (1 + F(F(8)))) + F((-9) + F(7)))$
21898 := $((-((2 + 1)) + F(F(8))) + 9) + F(F(8))$
21899 := $((2 \times ((-1) + F(F(8))) + 9) - 9)$
21908 := $(2 \times (-((1 - 9)) + F(F(08))))$
21912 := $((F(21) + (9 + 1)) \times 2)$
21913 := $(21 - (F(F((9 - 1))) \times (-F(3))))$
21918 := $(2 \times (F(-((1 - 9) + 1))) + F(F(8)))$
21924 := $(2 \times (F(F(-((1 - 9)))) + (2^4)))$
21926 := $((F(21) + F(9)) + F(F((2 + 6))))$
21928 := $((F(21) + F(9)) + 2) + F(F(8))$
21934 := $((F(21) + F(F((9 - 3)))) \times F(F(4)))$
21936 := $(2 \times (F(F(-((1 - 9)))) + (F(F(3)) + F(F(6))))$
21938 := $(2 \times ((F(-((1 - 9))) + F(3)) + F(F(8))))$
21946 := $(2 \times (((1 \times 9) \times F(4)) + F(F(F(6))))$
21947 := $((F(21) + F(9)) \times F(F(4))) - (F(7))$
21948 := $(2 \times ((1 + (9 \times F(4))) + F(F(8))))$
21953 := $F(2) + (-1 + F(9) - 5)^3$
21954 := $2 + (-1 + F(9) - 5)^{F(4)}$
21957 := $((2 \times F(F(-((1 - 9)))) - (-5) \times F(7))$
21974 := $((F(21) + F(9)) + (7)) \times F(F(4))$
21976 := $(2 \times (F(F(-((1 - 9)))) + (7 \times 6))$
21986 := $(2 \times ((F((1 + 9)) + F(F(8))) - F(6))$
21994 := $((2 \times F(F(-((1 - 9)))) + ((F(9) \times F(4))))$
21998 := $(2 \times ((19 + F(9)) + F(F(8))))$
22125 := $((2 \times F(21)) + F(F((2 + 5)))$
22127 := $((2 \times F(21)) + 2) + F(F(7))$
22135 := $2 \times F(21) + 3^5$
22148 := $((2 \times F(21)) + (F(F(4))^8))$
22167 := $((2 \times (F(21) + F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))$
22176 := $(2 \times ((-2) + F((-1) + F(7))) + F(F(F(6))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22178 &:= (2 \times ((-F(2)) + F((-1) + F(7))) + F(F(8))) \\
 22356 &:= (2 \times ((-F(2)) + F(F((F(3) + (5)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 22357 &:= (-F(2)) - ((-2) \times (F(F((3 + 5))) + F(F(7)))) \\
 22358 &:= (2 \times (F(F(2^3))) + F((5 + 8))) \\
 22468 &:= (2 \times ((2 \times F((4 + F(6)))) + F(F(8))) \\
 22528 &:= (2 + 2)^5 \times (F(2) + F(8)) \\
 22646 &:= (2 \times (F(((2 + F(6)) + (4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 22647 &:= (F(2) - ((-2) \times (F(F(F(6))) + F((F(F(4)) \times 7)))) \\
 22776 &:= (2 \times ((F((2 + 7)) \times F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 22784 &:= ((2 \times (2^7)) \times F((8 + F(4)))) \\
 22797 &:= (2 - ((2 + F(F(7))) \times (-97))) \\
 22837 &:= (F(22) + ((F(8) + F(F(3))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 22873 &:= ((F(2) + (2^8)) \times F((F(7) - F(3)))) \\
 22877 &:= (F(22) - ((-F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(7)))) \\
 22879 &:= ((2 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + (F((7 + 9)))) \\
 22883 &:= ((2 \times (2 + F(F(8)))) + F((8 \times F(3)))) \\
 22916 &:= (2 \times ((2^9) + F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) \\
 22918 &:= (2 \times (((2^9) + 1) + F(F(8))) \\
 22995 &:= ((F(2) - (2^9)) \times (-9 \times 5)) \\
 23182 &:= -2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)/2 \\
 23183 &:= (-2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8))/F(3) \\
 23184 &:= F(23 + 1)/(8/4) \\
 23257 &:= (F(2) - ((-3^2) \times F((5 + F(7)))) \\
 23278 &:= (2 \times ((3 \times (-2) + F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) \\
 23488 &:= (-F(2)) - (((-3) \times F(-(F(F(4)) - (F(8)))))) - F(F(8))) \\
 23489 &:= ((F(F(2^3)) \times F(F(4))) + (F((8 + 9)))) \\
 23576 &:= (2 \times ((F(F((3 + 5)))/F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 23578 &:= (2 \times ((F((3 \times 5)) + F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) \\
 23664 &:= ((F(2) - F((F(3) \times F(6)))) \times (-6 \times 4)) \\
 23674 &:= (((-F(2)) + F(-(F(F(3)) - F(F(6)))))) \times 7)/F(F(4)) \\
 23676 &:= (((2 - F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) \times (-6)) \\
 23686 &:= (-2) - (((-3) \times F(6)) \times F((8 + F(6)))) \\
 23688 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(8 + 8) \\
 23732 &:= ((-F(2)) + (3 \times F(F(7)))) \times F((3^2)) \\
 23736 &:= ((2 + F((3 + F(7)))) \times (3 \times F(6))) \\
 23744 &:= F(23) - (F(7) + 4)^{F(4)} \\
 23748 &:= (2 \times (((F(F(3)) - F(F(7))) \times (-4)) + F(F(8))) \\
 23762 &:= (F(23) - ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + 2)) \\
 23763 &:= (F(23) - ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + F(F(3)))) \\
 23764 &:= (-2) - (((-3) \times F(F(7))) \times F((6 + F(4))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23767 &:= (F(2) - ((F(3) - (F(7) \times F(6))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 23776 &:= ((-F(2)) + (F((3 + F(7)) \times F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 23778 &:= (F(2) - ((F((3 + F(7))) \times (-F(7))) - F(F(8)))) \\
 23795 &:= (((F(2) + (3 \times F(F(7)))) \times F(9)) - (5)) \\
 23798 &:= (((-F(2)) - F((F(3) \times 7))) \times (-F(9))) + F(F(8))) \\
 23799 &:= (-F(2)) - (((3 \times F(F(7))) \times (-F(9))) - F(9)) \\
 23826 &:= ((-2) - ((3 \times F(8))^2) \times (-6)) \\
 23856 &:= (((-2) + F((-3) + F(8))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 23862 &:= (2 \times ((-F(3)) + F(F(8))) + F((F(6) \times 2))) \\
 23863 &:= ((2 \times (F((F(3) \times 8)) + F(F(F(6)))) - 3) \\
 23864 &:= (((F(2) - F((F(3) \times 8))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(F(4)))) \\
 23865 &:= (-F(2)) - (F(3) \times (-F(F(8))) - F((F(F(6)) - (5)))) \\
 23866 &:= (2 \times ((F(F(3)) \times F(F(8))) + F((F(6) + F(6)))) \\
 23868 &:= (2 \times ((F(F(3)) + F(F(8))) + F((F(6) + 8)))) \\
 23945 &:= ((2 - (3 \times F((F(9)/F(4)))) \times (-5)) \\
 23965 &:= (((-2) - (3 \times F((9 + F(6)))) \times (-5)) \\
 23972 &:= (2 - (((-3) \times F(9)) \times (F(F(7)) + 2))) \\
 23978 &:= (((F(2) - ((-3) \times F(9))) \times F(F(7))) - (F(8))) \\
 24068 &:= ((2 \times (F(4)^{F(6)})) + F(F(8))) \\
 24255 &:= ((F((2 \times 4))^2) \times 55) \\
 24297 &:= F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7) \\
 24334 &:= 2 \times (-4 + 3^3)^{F(4)} \\
 24447 &:= F(2 \times 4 \times 4 - 4)/F(7) \\
 24465 &:= ((F(((2^4) - F(4))) \times F(F(6))) \times 5) \\
 24467 &:= (2 - (((-F(4)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(6))) \times F(F(7))) \\
 24468 &:= (F(24) + (((-F(F(4))) \times F(F(F(6)))) - 8)) \\
 24475 &:= (((-2) + (-F((4 + 4))) \times F(F(7))) \times (-5)) \\
 24476 &:= (F((2 + F((4 + 4)))) - F((F(7) + (6)))) \\
 24482 &:= (F(24) + (((-F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times (-2))) \\
 24484 &:= (((2 + 4)^4) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4)) \\
 24573 &:= (((-F(2)) + (-((F(4) - (5)))^{F(7)})) \times 3) \\
 24574 &:= -2 - (F(4) - 5)^{F(7)} \times F(4) \\
 24577 &:= F(2) + F(4) \times (-5 + 7)^{F(7)} \\
 24625 &:= (((-2) + F((F(F(4)) \times F(6)))) \times 25) \\
 24637 &:= (-2) - ((-F(4)) \times (F(F(6)) + (F(3)^{F(7)}))) \\
 24646 &:= (((2 \times (4^6)) + (F(4) \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 24647 &:= (F(2) - (((-F(4)) \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F(4))^{F(7)})) \\
 24649 &:= -F(2) + (F(4)^6 - 4) \times F(9) \\
 24673 &:= (-2) - (((-4) - F(F(6))) \times F((F(7) + 3)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 24674** := $(-(F(2)) - ((-4) - F(F(6))) \times F((F(7) + F(4))))$
24675 := $(F((2^4)) \times ((F(6) - F(7)) \times (-5)))$
24696 := $((F((2^4)) - (F(F(6)) \times (-9))) \times F(F(6)))$
24725 := $((2 + F((F(4) + F(7)))) \times 25)$
24746 := $(2 \times ((F(F(4))^{F(7)} + F(-(F(F(4)) - F(F(6))))))$
24785 := $((-F(2)) - ((-F(4)) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(8))) \times (-5)$
24843 := $((2 + F((F(4) + 8)))^{F(F(4))} \times 3)$
24964 := $((-2) + (4 \times (F(9) + (6))))^{F(F(4))}$
24989 := $(-F(2)) - ((F(F(F(4))) + F(9)) \times (-F(8) \times F(9)))$
24997 := $((F((2^4)) + F((9 + 9))) \times 7)$
25086 := $(F((-2) + F(((5 \times 0) + 8))) \times 6)$
25368 := $2 \times (F(5 \times 3) - 6) \times F(8)$
25387 := $((2 \times F((5 \times 3))) \times F(8)) - F(F(7))$
25397 := $(F(F((2 + 5))) \times ((3 \times F(9)) + (7)))$
25662 := $((2^5) - 6) \times F((F(6) \times 2))$
25663 := $(F(2) + ((5 + F(F(6))) \times F((F(6) \times F(3))))$
25664 := $(2 - ((-5) - F(F(6))) \times F((F(6) \times F(F(4))))$
25669 := $((F((2 \times 5)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(F(6)))/9$
25678 := $(2 \times ((F((-5) + F(F(6)))) \times F(7)) + 8)$
25726 := $(F(2) - (-((5 \times 7)^2)) \times F(F(6)))$
25746 := $((F(2) + ((5 \times 7)^{F(F(4))})) \times F(F(6)))$
25775 := $(((-2) \times F((5 + F(7)))) + (F(7))) \times (-5)$
25795 := $(((-2) \times F((5 + F(7)))) + 9) \times (-5)$
25834 := $(2 \times ((5 \times F((F(8) - 3))) - F(4)))$
25835 := $((2 \times 5) \times F((F(8) - 3))) - (5)$
26047 := $((F(2) + (60))^{F(F(4))} \times 7)$
26236 := $(-2 + 6) \times (-2 + 3^{F(6)})$
26244 := $((F(2) + (6 + 2))^4) \times 4$
26246 := $2 + 6^2 \times F(4)^6$
26248 := $(-2 + 6) \times (F(2) + F(4)^8)$
26411 := $((F(2) + (6))^4) \times 11$
26448 := $(F((-F(2)) + F(F(6)))) + ((F(4) \times (F(4)^8)))$
26449 := $((F((-F(2)) + F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(4)^9))$
26450 := $((2 + F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))} \times 50)$
26460 := $((F((2 + 6))^{F(F(4))} \times 60)$
26464 := $((F((2 + F(6))) + (F(4)^{F(6)})) \times 4)$
26484 := $((F((-F(2)) + F(F(6)))) - F((4 + 8))) \times 4$
26496 := $(((-2) - F(F(6))) \times F((F(4) + 9))) \times (-F(6))$
26497 := $(F(2) + ((F(F(F(6))) - (F((F(4) \times 9))))/(-7))$
26498 := $((2 \times 6)^{F(4)} \times 9) + F(F(8))$
26565 := $((-F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (((5^6) - 5))$
26566 := $((F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) + (((5^6) - 6))$
26568 := $-(((F(-(2 - 6))) - (5^6)) - F(F(8)))$
26571 := $(F(F((2 + 6))) + ((5^{7-1}))$
26572 := $((F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((5^{7-F(2)}))$
26573 := $((2 + F(F(F(6)))) + ((5^{7-F(F(3))}))$
26637 := $((2^{F(6)} \times F(6)) + F(F(3))) \times F(7)$
26645 := $((-F((2 \times 6))) - (F(F(F(6)))/(-F(F(4)))) \times 5)$
26647 := $(-2) + ((F(F(6)) + (6)) \times F((F(4) + F(7))))$
26648 := $(-F(2)) - ((-6) - F(F(6))) \times F((F(4) \times 8))$
26649 := $(F((2 \times F(6))) \times ((6 - F(4)) \times 9))$
26657 := $((2 + F(F(6))) \times (-6) + (5 \times F(F(7))))$
26675 := $((-F(2)) - (F(F(6)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(7)))) \times (-5)$
26676 := $((-2) + F(F(6))) \times ((6 \times F(F(7))) + (6))$
26683 := $((-2) \times F((F(6) + F(6)))) + F((F(8) + F(3)))$
26738 := $((F((2 \times F(6))) \times (F(7) + 3)) + F(F(8)))$
26765 := $(((-2) - F(F(6))) \times F(F(7)) + (6)) \times (-5)$
26767 := $((2^6) + 7) \times F((F(F(6)) - (7)))$
26778 := $((2 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (-7) + (F(F(7)) \times F(8)))$
26783 := $((-2) + (F(F(6)) \times F(F(7)))) + (F(F(8)) \times F(3))$
26784 := $((-F(2)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(F(7)))) + (F(F(8)) \times F(F(4)))$
26786 := $((F(2) + ((F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(8)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
26792 := $((2 + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(9) \times (-2)))$
26793 := $(F((2 + F(F(6)))) + (F(F(7)) \times (-F((9 - 3))))$
26797 := $-((F((2 + F(F(6)))) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(9) \times 7)))$
26827 := $((-(2 - 6)) \times F((F(8) - F(2)))) - F(F(7))$
26855 := $((2^{F(6)} \times F(8)) - (5)) \times 5$
26880 := $(((-2) \times F(6)) \times F(8)) \times (-80)$
26893 := $(F((2 + F(F(6)))) - ((8 + F(9))^{F(3)}))$
26924 := $((F((-F(2)) + F(F(6)))) - F(9)) \times (F(2) + F(4))$
26963 := $(F((F(2) + F(F(6)))) - (9 - (F(F(6))^3)))$
26984 := $-2 \times F(6) + (9 + F(8))^{F(4)}$
26992 := $(2 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(9) - F((9 \times 2))))$
27136 := $((2^7) \times (F(13) - F(F(6))))$
27144 := $((-F(2)) + (F(F(7))^{-1+F(4)})) / F(F(4))$
27164 := $(((-2) \times F(7)) - F((-1) + F(F(6)))) \times (-4)$
27204 := $(F(-(F(2) - F(7))) - (F(20) \times (-4)))$
27259 := $(-2) + (F(F(7)) \times (F((2 + 5)) \times 9))$

$$27261 := (((-F(2)) - F(F(7)))/(-2)) \times F(F((6+1)))$$

$$27279 := ((2 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(2) \times F(7)))) \times 9)$$

$$27287 := ((2 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(2) + 8))) \times F(7))$$

$$27296 := (((2^7)^2) - F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$27326 := (-(((2) + F(7))^3)) + F((2 + F(F(6))))$$

$$27328 := (((2^7)^{F(3)} - 2) + F(F(8)))$$

$$27336 := (((2^{F(7)} + 3) \times F(3)) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$27339 := ((2 + (F(F(7)) \times 3)) \times 39)$$

$$27345 := (((F(F((F(2) + (7)))))/F(3)) - 4) \times 5)$$

$$27363 := (-2) - (((-7) + F(3)) \times F(F(F(6))))/F(3))$$

$$27364 := (-F(2)) - (((-7) + F(3)) \times F(F(F(6))))/F(F(4))$$

$$27365 := ((F(F((F(2) + (7)))))/F(-(3-6))) \times 5)$$

$$27366 := (F(2) - (((F(7) + F(3)) \times F(F(F(6)))))/(-6))$$

$$27379 := (F(2) + ((F(F(7)) + F(F(3))) \times (F(7) \times 9)))$$

$$27382 := (((F(2) + F(F(7)))^{F(3)} + 8)/2)$$

$$27440 := (2 \times (7^{F(4)} \times 40))$$

$$27465 := (((2 \times 7)^4) - F(F(F(6)))) - (5)$$

$$27467 := (((-2) + F(7))^{F(F(4))} \times (-6) + F(F(7)))$$

$$27494 := ((-2) \times F(F(7))) \times (-4 - F((9 + F(F(F(4))))))$$

$$27495 := ((2 + F(F(7))) \times (F(4) \times (F(9) + (5))))$$

$$27497 := (2 - ((F(F(7)) + F(F(4))) \times (-9) \times F(7)))$$

$$27574 := -((F(((2) + F(7)) + (5))) - (F(7)^4))$$

$$27634 := 2 \times (-7 + (F(6) \times 3)^{F(4)})$$

$$27636 := ((F((2+7)) - (6)) \times F((F(3) \times F(6))))$$

$$27637 := (F(2) - ((-7) - F(F(6))) \times F((3 + F(7))))$$

$$27638 := (2 - ((-7) - F(F(6))) \times F((F(3) \times 8)))$$

$$27644 := 2^7 \times 6^{F(4)} - 4$$

$$27648 := 2^7 \times 6^{F(-4+8)}$$

$$27675 := ((F((2 \times 7)) - F(6)) \times 75)$$

$$27727 := (((2^7) - 7) - 2) \times F(F(7))$$

$$27752 := (F(F((F(2) + (7)))) + ((7^5) - F(2)))$$

$$27753 := (F(F((F(2) + (7)))) + ((7^5) \times F(F(3))))$$

$$27754 := ((F(F((F(2) + (7)))) + (7^5)) + F(F(F(4))))$$

$$27758 := (-(((2-7) - (7^5))) + F(F(8)))$$

$$27764 := ((2^{F(7)} - ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) \times (-4)))$$

$$27783 := (2 + 7/7) \times F(8)^3$$

$$27945 := (-2 + F(7) \times 9) \times F(4)^5$$

$$27963 := ((F(2) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(9) + (6)))) \times 3)$$

$$27964 := ((-F(2)) - (F(F(7)) \times (9 + F(F(6)))) \times (-4))$$

$$27968 := ((F(2) - (F(F(7)) \times (-9 + 6))) \times 8)$$

$$27976 := (((2 + F(F(7))) + F(9)) \times (F(7) \times F(6)))$$

$$28047 := (F((2 + F(8))) - F((F(F(04)) + (F(7))))$$

$$28216 := (F((2 + F(8))) + (-21) \times F(F(6)))$$

$$28226 := 2 + F(8)^2 \times 2^6$$

$$28266 := ((2 - (F(8) \times (-2^6))) \times F(F(6)))$$

$$28273 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((2^7) \times 3))$$

$$28275 := (F(((2 \times 8) - 2)) \times 75)$$

$$28278 := ((-2) + F((F(8) + 2))) - F((-7) + F(8)))$$

$$28288 := ((F(2) + (F(8)^2)) \times (8 \times 8))$$

$$28328 := ((F((2 \times 8))/(-3)) + F((2 + F(8))))$$

$$28352 := (F((2 + F(8))) + (F((3 \times 5))/(-2)))$$

$$28358 := ((F((F(2) + 8))^{-F(3)+5}) - F(F(8)))$$

$$28366 := (((F((F(2) + 8))^3) + F(6)) - F(F(F(6))))$$

$$28369 := (F((2 + F(8))) - (F(3) \times F((F(F(6)) - 9))))$$

$$28387 := (F((2 + F(8))) + (3 - (F(8) \times F(7))))$$

$$28397 := ((F((2 + F(8))) - (3 \times 9)) - F(F(7)))$$

$$28414 := (F((2 + F(8))) - (F(4)^{1+4}))$$

$$28417 := ((F(-(F(2) - 8))^4) - F((-1) + F(7)))$$

$$28423 := ((-F(2)) - F(F((F(8)/F(4)))) + (F(23)))$$

$$28424 := (F((2 + F(8))) - F(((F(4)^2) + (4))))$$

$$28425 := ((F(2) + F((F(8) + F(F(4)))) - (F(F((2 + 5))))$$

$$28426 := ((F((2 + F(8))) + F(F(4))) - F(F((F(2) + (6))))$$

$$28427 := ((F((2 + F(8))) + F(4)) - F((F(2) \times F(7))))$$

$$28428 := ((F((2 + F(8))) + (4)) - F(F(-(F(2) - 8))))$$

$$28437 := (F((2 + F(8))) - (4 \times F((3 + 7))))$$

$$28446 := ((2 + F((F(8) - F(4)))) \times (F(4) + F(6)))$$

$$28453 := ((2 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(4)^{5+3}))$$

$$28456 := ((F(-(F(2) - 8))^4) + (-5) \times F(F(6)))$$

$$28457 := (((F(2) + F(F(8))) - F(F(4)))/5) \times F(7)$$

$$28468 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((F(4) + (6)) \times F(8)))$$

$$28469 := ((F(2) + F((F(8) + F(F(4)))) + (F(F(6)) \times (-9)))$$

$$28472 := ((F(-(F(2) - 8))^4) - (F((F(7) - 2))))$$

$$28474 := ((2 - F((8 + F(4)))) + (F(7)^4))$$

$$28476 := ((2 \times F(8)) \times ((F(4) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(6))))$$

$$28479 := ((F((2 + F(8))) - F(-(F(F(F(4))) - F(7)))) - F(9))$$

$$28486 := (F((2 + F(8))) - (F(4) + (F(8) \times F(6))))$$

$$28487 := ((F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(4) \times F(8)))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$28488 := ((-F(2)) + F((F(8) + F(F(4)))) + (-8) \times F(8))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28489 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (-4) \times (-8) - F(9))) \\
 28492 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (F(4) \times F((9 + F(2)))))) \\
 28493 &:= ((F(-(F(2) - 8)))^4) - ((F(9) \times F(3)))) \\
 28513 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - F(((5 - 1) \times 3))) \\
 28527 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (-((5 \times 2) \times F(7)))) \\
 28531 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((5^3) + 1)) \\
 28532 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((5^3) \times F(2))) \\
 28533 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - ((5^3))) + F(F(3))) \\
 28534 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - ((5^3))) + F(F(4))) \\
 28535 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (F((5 \times 3)/5)) \\
 28547 &:= -F(2) + (8 + 5)^4 - F(7) \\
 28552 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (5 \times F(F((5 + F(2)))))) \\
 28561 &:= (F(-(F(2) - 8)))^{-5+F(6)+1} \\
 28562 &:= F(2) + (8 + 5)^{6-2} \\
 28563 &:= 2 + (8 + 5)^{F(6)/F(3)} \\
 28564 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (F((5 + 6) + (4)))) \\
 28568 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - F(((5) + F(6) + 8))) \\
 28573 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) + (5)) - F((F(7) - F(3)))) \\
 28574 &:= F(2) \times (8 + 5) + F(7)^4 \\
 28576 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (5 + 76)) \\
 28581 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((5 - 81))) \\
 28584 &:= 2 + F(8) + (5 + 8)^4 \\
 28587 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (5 \times (F(8) - (7)))) \\
 28588 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (5 + (8 \times 8))) \\
 28589 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (F(-(5 - 8)) \times F(9))) \\
 28592 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (5 \times F((9 - 2)))) \\
 28593 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (-((5 - 9))^3)) \\
 28594 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (59 + 4)) \\
 28598 &:= ((F((F(2) + F(8))) - (59)) + F(F(8))) \\
 28602 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - F((F(6) + 02))) \\
 28610 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(6) - F(10)))) \\
 28613 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((F(F(6)) + 1) \times F(3))) \\
 28615 &:= ((-2) \times F(8) + F((F(6) + 15))) \\
 28616 &:= (((F((2 + F(8))) - F(F(6))) + 1) - F(F(6))) \\
 28618 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - F(F(6))) - 18) \\
 28621 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((6^2) \times 1)) \\
 28622 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((6^2) - F(2))) \\
 28623 &:= F(2 \times 8) \times (6 + 23) \\
 28624 &:= F(2) + (F(8) + F(6)) \times F(2^4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28625 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (F((6/2))^5)) \\
 28626 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - F(F(6))) - (2 + F(6))) \\
 28627 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((6 \times (2 - 7)))) \\
 28628 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((6 + 2) + F(8))) \\
 28629 &:= (-28) + F(-(6 - 29)) \\
 28629 &:= -28 + F(-6 + 29) \\
 28632 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((F(6) - 3)^2)) \\
 28633 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((6 + F(3)) \times 3)) \\
 28634 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - F(F(6))) + ((F(3) - (4)))) \\
 28635 &:= -F(2) - F(8) + F(6 \times 3 + 5) \\
 28636 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - F(((6/3) + 6))) \\
 28637 &:= ((F(2) - F(8)) + F(((F(6) + F(3)) + F(7)))) \\
 28638 &:= ((2 - F(8)) + F(((6/3) + F(8)))) \\
 28639 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((6/3) \times 9)) \\
 28640 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - F(F(6))) + (4 + 0)) \\
 28641 &:= -2 \times 8 + F(6 \times 4 - 1) \\
 28642 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (-6) + F((4 \times 2))) \\
 28643 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((F(6) + F(4)) + 3)) \\
 28644 &:= (-F(2) + 8) \times (F(6)^4 - 4) \\
 28645 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (-6) \times (F(4) - (5))) \\
 28646 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((6 - F(4)) + F(6))) \\
 28647 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((6 - F(4)) + (7))) \\
 28648 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (F((6 - 4) + 8)) \\
 28649 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - F(((6) + F(4) + 9))) \\
 28651 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - F(6)) + F(F((5 - 1)))) \\
 28652 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (F(6) - (5 - 2))) \\
 28653 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((6 - 5) + 3)) \\
 28654 &:= F(2 \times (8 + 6) - 5) - F(4) \\
 28655 &:= -2 + F(8 \times 6 - 5 \times 5) \\
 28656 &:= (-F(2) + F((F(8) + (-6)/(5 - F(6)))))) \\
 28657 &:= F(2 + (-8 + 6 + 5) \times 7) \\
 28658 &:= (F(2) + F((F(8) + F(((6 + 5) - 8)))) \\
 28659 &:= 2 + F((8 - 6)^5 - 9) \\
 28661 &:= (((-2) + F(F(8))) + (6)) + F((F(F(6)) + 1))) \\
 28662 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (F(6) - (6/2))) \\
 28663 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (F(6) - (6/3))) \\
 28664 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (F(6) - F((6 - 4)))) \\
 28665 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + F(((6/6) + 5))) \\
 28666 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (F(6) + (6/6))) \\
 28667 &:= ((2 + 8) + F(((6 \times 6) - F(7))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28669 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (6 \times F(-(6 - 9)))) \\
 28670 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((6 + 7) + 0)) \\
 28671 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((6 + 7) + 1)) \\
 28672 &:= ((2^8) \times F(6)) \times (7 \times 2) \\
 28673 &:= ((2 \times 8) + F(((F(6) + F(7)) + F(3)))) \\
 28674 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((6 + 7) + 4)) \\
 28675 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((6 + 7) + 5)) \\
 28676 &:= ((-2) + F(8)) + F(((F(6) + (7)) + F(6))) \\
 28677 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((6 + 7) + 7)) \\
 28678 &:= F(2 + 8 + 6 + 7) + F(8) \\
 28679 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((6 + 7) + 9)) \\
 28682 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((6 + F(8)) - 2)) \\
 28683 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(6) + F(8)) - 3)) \\
 28684 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) + (F(6) + F(8))) - F(4)) \\
 28685 &:= (28 + F((F(F(6)) + F((8 - 5)))) \\
 28686 &:= (((F((F(2) + F(8))) + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) + F(6)) \\
 28687 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (-6) \times (8 - F(7))) \\
 28689 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((6 - 8) + F(9))) \\
 28691 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - F(F(6))) + F((9 + 1))) \\
 28692 &:= ((F((F(2) + F(8))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(9) + F(2))) \\
 28693 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (6 \times (9 - 3))) \\
 28694 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((6 + F(9)) - F(4))) \\
 28706 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) + 70) - F(F(6))) \\
 28712 &:= (F((2 + 8)) + F((F((7 + 1)) + 2))) \\
 28719 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (71 - 9)) \\
 28725 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (F(7) + F((2 \times 5)))) \\
 28728 &:= (-2 + F(8)) \times 72 \times F(8) \\
 28729 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((7 + F(2)) \times 9)) \\
 28743 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (F((7 + 4)) - 3)) \\
 28744 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) + F((7 + 4))) - F(F(4))) \\
 28746 &:= ((F(((2 + 8) + 7)) \times F(4)) \times 6) \\
 28748 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (7 - (-4) \times F(8))) \\
 28761 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (F(7) \times F((6 \times 1)))) \\
 28762 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(7) \times F(6)) + F(2))) \\
 28763 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(7) \times F(6)) + F(3))) \\
 28764 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(7) \times F(6)) + F(4))) \\
 28769 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(7) \times 6) + F(9))) \\
 28774 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (F(7) \times (F(7) - (4)))) \\
 28783 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (7 \times (F(8) - 3))) \\
 28784 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(F(7)) + (F(8)))/F(F(4))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28785 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (F(8) \times (-5))) \\
 28794 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - (7)) + F((9 + F(4)))) \\
 28795 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (95)) \\
 28823 &:= -2 + 8 \times F(8) + F(23) \\
 28824 &:= ((F(-(F(2) - F(8)))) + (F(8)^2)) \times 4 \\
 28825 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (F(8) \times F((F(2) + (5)))) \\
 28826 &:= ((F(2) + (8 \times F(8))) + F((2 + F(F(6)))) \\
 28846 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (F(8) \times (F(4) + (6)))) \\
 28865 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (8 \times (F(F(6)) + (5)))) \\
 28869 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (8 - (-6) \times F(9))) \\
 28876 &:= (((F((2 + F(8))) - 8) + F(F(7))) - (6)) \\
 28877 &:= (((F((F(2) + F(8))) + F(F(8))) - (F(7))) + F(F(7))) \\
 28882 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - 8) + F(F((8 - F(2)))) \\
 28885 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) + F((-8) + F(8))) - (5)) \\
 28913 &:= ((2^8) + F((F((9 - 1)) + F(3))) \\
 28924 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F((9 + 2)) \times F(4))) \\
 28928 &:= 2^8 \times (92 + F(8)) \\
 28929 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((-9) + F(2)) \times F(9)) \\
 28945 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (9 \times (F(F(4))^5)) \\
 28946 &:= (289 + F((F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))) \\
 28962 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (F((9 + 6)) / (-2))) \\
 28963 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (9 \times F((6 + 3)))) \\
 29125 &:= (F(F(-(2 - 9))) \times 125) \\
 29184 &:= (2 + F(9 + 1)) \times 8^{F(4)} \\
 29197 &:= (((F(2) + 9) - F(19)) \times (-7)) \\
 29264 &:= (((-2 - 9) \times F((-2) + F(F(6)))) - F(4)) \\
 29267 &:= (-2 + 9) \times F(2 \times 6 + 7) \\
 29288 &:= (((-2 - 9) \times F((-2) + F(8))) + (F(8))) \\
 29358 &:= (F(F(-(2 - 9))) \times ((F(F(3)) + (5)) \times F(8))) \\
 29364 &:= (((-2) - (F(9)^{F(3)})) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(4) \\
 29376 &:= (2 \times (9 + ((3 \times F(F(7))) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 29384 &:= (-((2 - (9^3))) + F((F(8) + F(F(4)))) \\
 29435 &:= ((29^{F(F(4))}) \times 35) \\
 29466 &:= (-2 + F(9)^{F(4)} / F(6)) \times 6 \\
 29522 &:= (-F(2) + 9^5) / 2 - 2 \\
 29523 &:= (F(2) + 9^5) / 2 - F(3) \\
 29525 &:= (F(2) + 9^5) / F(-2 + 5) \\
 29537 &:= (-F(2) + 9^5) / F(3) + F(7) \\
 29546 &:= (((F(2) + (9^5)) / F(F(4))) + F(F(6)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29584 &:= (2 + F(9) \times 5)^{8/4} \\
 29644 &:= F(29 - 6) + F(4 \times 4) \\
 29664 &:= ((2 - (F(9) \times (-6))) \times F((F(6) + (4)))) \\
 29736 &:= (2 \times ((9 + (F(F(7)) \times 3)) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 29744 &:= ((2 + 9) \times ((F(7) \times 4)^{F(F(4))})) \\
 29766 &:= (((-2) \times F(9)) - (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) \times (-6)) \\
 29793 &:= 2 + (9 + F(7) + 9)^3 \\
 29799 &:= (((2 \times F(9)) + F(F(7))) \times 99) \\
 29824 &:= (F(F(-(2 - 9))) \times (8 \times (2^4))) \\
 29986 &:= (-2) - (-((F(9) + F(9)) \times F(8)) \times F(F(6))) \\
 29988 &:= (F(2) \times F(9) + F(9)) \times F(8) \times F(8) \\
 29989 &:= (F(2) - (F(9) \times (-98 \times 9))) \\
 30696 &:= (3 \times (F(F(F(06)))) + (-F(9)) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 31248 &:= 31 \times (F(2^4) + F(8)) \\
 31256 &:= F(3) \times (1 + 2 + 5^6) \\
 31584 &:= (F((F(3)^{-1+5})) \times (8 \times 4)) \\
 31638 &:= (-3) \times (((-1) + F(F(6)))^{F(3)} - F(F(8))) \\
 31648 &:= ((F(3) + F(16)) \times (4 \times 8)) \\
 31668 &:= (((3 + 1) \times F(F(6))) \times F((6 + 8))) \\
 31676 &:= (F(3) \times ((-1) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 31678 &:= (F(3) \times ((F(F((1 \times 6))) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 31684 &:= (((31 \times 6) - 8)^{F(F(4))}) \\
 31757 &:= -F(31 - 7) + 5^7 \\
 31848 &:= ((3 \times (-1) + F(F(8))) - F((F(F(4)) \times 8))) \\
 31884 &:= ((-318) + F(F(8))) \times F(4) \\
 31944 &:= (3 + 19)^{F(4)} \times F(4) \\
 32136 &:= (3 \times (-((F(2) + F(13))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 32139 &:= (3 \times (F(21) - F(F(-(F(3) - 9)))) \\
 32372 &:= ((3 \times F(F((2^3))) + (F(F(7)) \times (-2))) \\
 32463 &:= (((-((3 + 2)^{F(4)})) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3) \\
 32496 &:= (F(3 \times 2)^4 - F(9)) \times F(6) \\
 32526 &:= (3 \times (-((2 \times 52)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 32535 &:= ((F((3 \times 2)^5) - F(F((F(3) + (5)))) \\
 32537 &:= ((F(3) + ((2^5)^3)) - F(F(7))) \\
 32538 &:= (3 \times (-((2 \times 5)^{F(3)})) + F(F(8))) \\
 32568 &:= (3 \times (-((F(2) + F((5 + 6))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 32586 &:= (3 \times (((F(2) - 5) \times F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 32587 &:= ((3 \times (-((F(2) + 5))) + F(F(8))) - F(F(7))) \\
 32637 &:= (32 - ((F(F(F(6))) \times (-3)) + F(F(7))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32643 &:= (3 \times ((-F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((4^3))) \\
 32646 &:= (3 \times (F(F((2 + 6))) - (F(F(4))^6)) \\
 32658 &:= (3 \times (-((2 \times 6) \times 5)) + F(F(8))) \\
 32661 &:= (3 \times ((2 + F(F(F(6)))) - 61)) \\
 32664 &:= (((3 + F((2 + F(6)))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(4))) \\
 32667 &:= (3 \times ((-F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(6) \times 7)) \\
 32672 &:= ((3 \times (F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(7)^2)) \\
 32673 &:= (3 \times (F(F((2 + 6))) - (F((7 + 3)))) \\
 32675 &:= (((-3) - F((-F(2)) + F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) \times (-5) \\
 32676 &:= (3 \times ((2 + F(F(F(6)))) - (7 \times F(6))) \\
 32684 &:= (((F(3)^{F(F(2)+6)}) - (F(8))) \times 4) \\
 32688 &:= (3 \times (((-2) \times F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) - 8) \\
 32694 &:= ((3 \times F(F((2 + 6)))) - F((9 + F(4)))) \\
 32696 &:= (F(3)^{2 \times 6} - 9) \times F(6) \\
 32697 &:= (3 \times (F(F((2 + 6))) - (F(9) + F(7)))) \\
 32699 &:= ((3 \times ((-F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(9)) - F(9)) \\
 32726 &:= (F(3) \times (((2^7)^2) - F(F(6)))) \\
 32734 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} - 34 \\
 32736 &:= (-F(3) + F((2 + 7) \times 3)) / 6 \\
 32739 &:= 3 \times (F(2) + F(7 \times 3) - F(9)) \\
 32744 &:= ((F(3) - ((2^{F(7)}) - (4))) \times (-4)) \\
 32746 &:= -(((F(F(3)) - ((2^{F(7)}) \times 4)) + F(F(6))) \\
 32747 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)}) - (F(4) \times 7)) \\
 32748 &:= (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 4 - 8 \\
 32749 &:= ((3 \times F(F((F(2) + (7)))) - F((F(F(4)) + 9))) \\
 32753 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)}) - (5 \times 3)) \\
 32757 &:= F(3) + (F(2) + 7)^5 - F(7) \\
 32758 &:= -F(3) + (F(2) + 7)^5 - 8 \\
 32760 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)}) - F((6 + 0))) \\
 32761 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)}) - (6 + 1)) \\
 32762 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)}) - (F(6) - 2)) \\
 32763 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)}) - (F(6) - 3)) \\
 32764 &:= ((F(3)^{2+7+6}) - (4)) \\
 32766 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)}) + (6 - F(6))) \\
 32767 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)}) + ((6 - 7))) \\
 32769 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)}) - (F(6) - 9)) \\
 32772 &:= F(3) \times (2^{7+7} + 2) \\
 32773 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} + 7 - F(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32774 &:= F(3) \times (2^{7+7} + F(4)) \\
 32775 &:= (3 \times (-F((F(2) + (7)))) + F(F((F(7) - (5)))))) \\
 32776 &:= F(3) \times 2^{7+7} + F(6) \\
 32778 &:= (3 \times (-((27 - 7)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 32781 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} + F(8 - 1) \\
 32783 &:= (-F((3^2)) + ((-7) + F(F(8))) \times 3) \\
 32784 &:= (((F(3)^{2 \times 7}) + 8) \times F(F(4))) \\
 32786 &:= (-((3 - (2^{7+8}))) + F(F(6))) \\
 32788 &:= ((3 \times (-((2 \times 7)) + F(F(8)))) - 8) \\
 32789 &:= ((3 \times ((2 - 7) + F(F(8)))) - F(9)) \\
 32793 &:= (3 \times ((-2) - F(7)) + F(F(F(9 - 3)))) \\
 32796 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} + F(9) - 6 \\
 32797 &:= ((3 \times F(F((F(2) + (7)))))) - (F(9) + (7))) \\
 32798 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} + 9 + F(8) \\
 32804 &:= (-F((3^2)) + (F(F(8)) \times F(04))) \\
 32805 &:= (((F(3) + F(2))^8) \times 05) \\
 32808 &:= (3 \times ((-2) + F(F(8))) - 08) \\
 32811 &:= (3 \times ((2 + F(F(8))) - 11)) \\
 32814 &:= ((-F((3 \times 2)) + F(F(8))) \times F((1 \times 4))) \\
 32816 &:= (((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - 1) - F(F(6))) \\
 32817 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - F((1 + 7))) \\
 32818 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - (-1) + F(8)) \\
 32819 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - (19)) \\
 32822 &:= ((3 \times (2 + F(F(8)))) - (22)) \\
 32823 &:= ((-((3 + 2)) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(3))) \\
 32824 &:= (-F(3) + (((2 - F(F(8))) + 2) \times (-F(4)))) \\
 32825 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - F((2 + 5))) \\
 32826 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - (2 \times 6)) \\
 32827 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - (-2) + F(7)) \\
 32828 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - (2 + 8)) \\
 32829 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - (F(2) \times 9)) \\
 32830 &:= (-F(3) + ((2 - F(F(8))) \times (-3 + 0))) \\
 32831 &:= (((-F(3) + F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \times 3) - 1) \\
 32832 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - (3 \times 2)) \\
 32833 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - (F(3) + 3)) \\
 32834 &:= (((-F(3) + F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \times 3) + F(F(4))) \\
 32835 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + ((F(3) - (5)))) \\
 32836 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - F(-((3 - 6)))) \\
 32837 &:= (((F(3) + F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \times 3) - (7)) \\
 32838 &:= 3 \times F(2 \times 8 - 3 + 8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32839 &:= (-F(3) + (((2 - F(F(8))) \times (-3)) + 9)) \\
 32840 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + F(F((4 + 0)))) \\
 32841 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + (4 - 1)) \\
 32842 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + (F(4) + F(2))) \\
 32843 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + (F(4) + F(3))) \\
 32844 &:= 3 \times (2 + F(84/4)) \\
 32845 &:= (((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + F(F(4))) + (5)) \\
 32846 &:= ((3 \times F(F((2 \times (8 - 4)))))) + F(6)) \\
 32847 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + (-4) + F(7)) \\
 32848 &:= (((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + F(F(4))) + 8) \\
 32849 &:= (((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + F(F(4))) + 9) \\
 32850 &:= (3 \times ((-F(2)) + F(F(8))) + ((5 + 0))) \\
 32851 &:= ((3 \times ((-F(2)) + F(F(8))) + (5))) + 1) \\
 32852 &:= ((3 \times (2 + F(F(8)))) + F((5 + F(2)))) \\
 32853 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + (5 \times 3)) \\
 32854 &:= (F(F(3)) + ((F((F(2) \times F(8))) + (5)) \times F(4))) \\
 32855 &:= ((3 \times ((-F(2)) + F(F(8))) + (5))) + (5) \\
 32856 &:= 3 \times (F(2 \times 8 + 5) + 6) \\
 32857 &:= ((3 \times ((-F(2)) + F(F(8))) + (5))) + (7) \\
 32858 &:= ((3 \times (-2) + F(F(8)))) + (5 + F(8)) \\
 32859 &:= (F(F((3 \times 2))) + (F(F(8)) \times F(-((5 - 9)))))) \\
 32861 &:= ((3 \times (F(2) + F(F(8)))) + (F(F(6)) - 1)) \\
 32862 &:= ((F((3 \times 2)) + F(F(8))) \times (6/2)) \\
 32863 &:= (F(F(3)) + ((F((F(2) \times F(8))) + F(6)) \times 3)) \\
 32864 &:= (F(3) + ((F((F(2) \times F(8))) + F(6)) \times F(4))) \\
 32865 &:= (((3^2) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(6) - (5))) \\
 32868 &:= (3 \times (((2 \times 8) - 6) + F(F(8)))) \\
 32869 &:= ((3 \times (F(2) + F(F(8)))) + (-6) + F(9)) \\
 32871 &:= (3 \times ((-F(2)) + F(F(8))) + (F(7) - 1)) \\
 32872 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + F((7 + 2))) \\
 32873 &:= (F(3) - (((-2) + F(F(8))) + (F(7))) \times (-3))) \\
 32874 &:= (((3 + 2) + F(F(8))) + (7)) \times F(4) \\
 32875 &:= ((3 \times ((F(2) + F(F(8))) + (F(7)))) - (5)) \\
 32877 &:= 3 \times (F(28 - 7) + F(7)) \\
 32878 &:= ((3 \times (2 + F(F(8)))) + (F(7) + F(8))) \\
 32879 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + (7 + F(9))) \\
 32883 &:= (((-((3 \times 2)) + F(8)) + F(F(8))) \times 3) \\
 32884 &:= (-F(3) - (((2 \times 8) + F(F(8))) \times (-F(4)))) \\
 32886 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + (8 \times 6)) \\
 32889 &:= (3 \times (F((F(2) \times F(8))) + (8 + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 32892** := $(3 \times (F((F(2) \times F(8))) + (9 \times 2)))$
32893 := $((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + F((9 + F(F(3)))))$
32896 := $((3 \times (F(2) + F(F(8)))) + (F(9) + F(F(6))))$
32899 := $((3 \times (F((F(2) \times F(8))) + 9)) + F(9))$
32925 := $(3 \times (29 + F(F(F((F(2) + (5)))))))$
32927 := $((3 \times F(F(-(F(2) - 9)))) + (F((-2) + F(7))))$
32928 := $(3 \times ((29 + F(2)) + F(F(8))))$
32931 := $(3 \times (F(F(-(F(2) - 9)))) + (31))$
32934 := $((32 + F(F(F((9 - 3)))) \times F(4))$
32935 := $((F(F(F((3 \times 2)))) + F(9)) \times 3) - (5)$
32937 := $3 \times (-F(2) + F(9) + F(3 \times 7))$
32958 := $(3 \times (((F(2) + F(9)) + (5)) + F(F(8))))$
32964 := $((F(F(F((3 \times 2)))) + (F(9) + F(6))) \times F(4))$
32967 := $(3 \times (((2 + F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7))$
32969 := $((3 \times (F((F(2) + 9)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(9))$
32976 := $(3 \times (-((F(2) - F(9)) - F(7))) + F(F(F(6))))$
32979 := $(3 \times (F(F(-(F(2) - 9)))) + (F(7) + F(9)))$
32988 := $(3 \times ((29 + F(8)) + F(F(8))))$
33246 := $(3 \times ((F((3^2)) \times 4) + F(F(F(6))))$
33268 := $(-F(3)) + (3 \times (F((2 \times 6)) + F(F(8))))$
33276 := $(3 \times ((F(3) + F(-(F(2) - F(7)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
33286 := $F(3 \times 3) \times (F(2 \times 8) - F(6))$
33446 := $-F(3) + F(3 + 4 \times 4) \times F(6)$
33448 := $(F(((3^3) - 4) - 4)) \times 8$
33456 := $((-F(F(3))) - F((-F(3) + F((F(4) + (5)))))) \times (-F(6))$
33463 := $((F(3) + 3)^4) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 3)$
33464 := $(F((3 + 3)) \times (F(F(4)) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))))))$
33466 := $(F(3) - ((F(3) + F(-(F(F(4)) - F(F(6)))))) \times (-F(6)))$
33474 := $(F(F((3 + 3))) \times (-F(4) + F((F(7) + (4))))$
33476 := $(F(3) + ((-3) + F((4 + F(7)))) \times F(F(6)))$
33486 := $(3 \times (((3^{F(4)}) \times 8) + F(F(F(6))))$
33488 := $(((-3) - F(3)) - F(-(F(F(4)) - (F(8)))))) \times (-8)$
33489 := $(-F(F(3))) + ((-F(3) + F((F(F(4)) \times 8))) \times F(9))$
33516 := $((F((F(3) + (3 \times 5))) - 1) \times F(F(6)))$
33528 := $(3 \times ((-3) + F(F((5 + 2)))) + F(F(8)))$
33536 := $((F(F(3)) - (F((F(3) + (5 \times 3))) \times F(F(6))))$
33537 := $(F(F((3 + 3))) \times F(((5 \times F(3)) + (7))))$
33538 := $(F(F(3)) + (F((F(3) + (5 \times 3))) \times F(8)))$
33546 := $(3 \times ((F(F((F(3) + (5)))) + F(4)) + F(F(F(6))))$
33547 := $(-3) + (F((3 \times 5)) \times F((F(4) + (7))))$
33548 := $(-F(3)) + (F((3 \times 5)) \times F((F(4) + 8)))$
33549 := $(-3) + (F(F((F(3) + (5)))) \times F((F(4) + 9)))$
33552 := $F(3) + F(3 \times 5) \times F(5 \times 2)$
33553 := $(3 + (F((F(3) \times 5)) \times F((5 \times 3)))$
33558 := $((F(3) + (F(3)^5)) \times F((-5) + F(8)))$
33559 := $(F(F(3)) + (F((F((3 + 5)) - (5))) \times F(9)))$
33564 := $((-(F(F(3)) - (3^5))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(4)$
33566 := $((F((3 \times 3)) \times F((-5) + F(F(6)))) + F(6))$
33567 := $(3 \times ((3^5) + F((F(6) + F(7))))$
33576 := $(3 \times ((F((F(3) + (5))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6))))$
33577 := $(-F(3)) + ((F(F(3)) - F((5 + F(7)))) \times (-F(7)))$
33588 := $(3 \times ((3^5) + F(F(8))) + (F(8)))$
33589 := $(-3) + ((F(F(3)) + F((-5) + F(8))) \times F(9))$
33592 := $(F(3 + 3) + 5) \times F(9 \times 2)$
33593 := $(F(F(3)) + (F((F(3) + (5))) \times F((9 \times F(3))))$
33594 := $(F(3) + (F((F(3) + (5))) \times F((9 \times F(F(4))))$
33606 := $(3 \times ((F(3)^{F(6)}) + F(F(F(6))))$
33614 := $(F(3) \times ((F(F(3)) + (6))^{1+4}))$
33615 := $(F(F(3)) + (F(3) \times ((6 + 1)^5)))$
33618 := $(F(3) + F(3 \times 6)) \times F(-1 + 8)$
33626 := $((F(3) + F((F(3) \times F(6)))) \times F((F(2) + F(6))))$
33629 := $(3 + ((F(3) + F((F(6) \times 2))) \times F(9)))$
33647 := $3 + (F(3 \times 6) + 4) \times F(7)$
33656 := $(F(3) \times (((F(F(3)) + (6))^5) + F(F(6))))$
33657 := $(F(F(3)) \times ((F((3 \times 6)) + (5)) \times F(7)))$
33659 := $(-F(F(3))) + ((3 + F((F(F(6)) - (5)))) \times F(9))$
33667 := $-3 + (F(3 \times 6) + 6) \times F(7)$
33696 := $((3 - F((-F(3) + F(F(6)))) - F(9)) \times (-F(6)))$
33767 := $((3 \times (-((F(F(3)) - F(F(7)))) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7)))$
33785 := $((F(((3^3) - 7)) - 8) \times 5)$
33787 := $(F(3) + (-((F(3) - (7 \times F(8)))) \times F(F(7)))$
33792 := $F(3)^{3+7} \times (F(9) - F(2))$
33815 := $((F(F(3)) - 3) + F((F(8) - 1))) \times 5$
33816 := $((3 \times (-3) + F(F(8))) + (F(16)))$
33823 := $((F(3) + 3) \times F((F(8) - F(2)))) - F(3)$
33824 := $(-((F(F(3)) - ((3 \times F(F(8))) + (F((2^4))))))$
33825 := $(F(3) + 3) \times F(8/2 \times 5)$
33826 := $(F(F(3)) + ((3 \times F(F(8))) + F((2 \times F(6))))$
33827 := $(F(3) + (F(-(F(F(3)) - (F(8)))) \times (-2 - 7)))$
33828 := $(3 + ((3 \times F(F(8))) + (F((2 \times 8))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33834 &:= ((3 \times (3 + F(F(8)))) + F((F(3)^4))) \\
 33835 &:= ((-F(3)) - F(((F(3) + 8) \times F(3))) \times (-5)) \\
 33845 &:= ((F(-((3/3)) + F(8))) + (4)) \times 5 \\
 33846 &:= (((F(3) + 3) \times F((F(8) - F(F(4)))))) + (F(F(6)))) \\
 33855 &:= (((-F(F(3))) - F(-(F(F(3)) - (F(8)))))) - (5)) \times (-5) \\
 33856 &:= (((F(3) + F(-(F(F(3)) - (F(8)))))) \times 5) + (F(F(6)))) \\
 33859 &:= ((F(-((3/3)) + F(8))) \times 5) + F(9) \\
 33865 &:= ((F(-((3/3)) + F(8))) + F(6)) \times 5 \\
 33867 &:= (F(3) + ((F(-3) + F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times F(7)) \\
 33873 &:= (3 \times ((F(3) + F(F(8))) + ((7^3))) \\
 33875 &:= (((-3) + F(-(F(F(3)) - (F(8)))))) + F(7)) \times 5 \\
 33984 &:= ((3 + F(F(-(F(3) - 9)))) \times F((8 + 4))) \\
 33994 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(-(3 - 9)))))) + (F(9)^{F(4)}) \\
 33995 &:= ((F((F(3) + (F(3) \times 9))) + F(9)) \times 5) \\
 34269 &:= (-3) + ((F((4^2)) + F(F(6))) \times F(9)) \\
 34365 &:= (F((34/F(3))) + (F(6)^5)) \\
 34445 &:= (((F(3) + (F(4)^4))^{F(4)}) \times 5) \\
 34475 &:= ((F(3) - F((4 \times 4))) \times (-7 \times 5)) \\
 34476 &:= (((F(3 \times 4) + (4)) \times F(F(7))) - F(6)) \\
 34477 &:= (((F(3 \times 4) + (4)) \times F(F(7))) - (7)) \\
 34484 &:= (F(F((3 + 4))) \times (4 + F((8 + 4)))) \\
 34487 &:= (3 + ((4 + F((4 + 8))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 34518 &:= (((3 + 4)^5) + F((1 + F(8)))) \\
 34545 &:= ((F(3 \times 4) + F((5 \times 4))) \times 5) \\
 34579 &:= (F(F(3)) + (((4^5) - 7) \times F(9))) \\
 34662 &:= ((F((3^{F(4)})) \times 6) / F((F(6) + F(2)))) \\
 34666 &:= (-F(3)) + (F(4) \times (F(F(F(6))) + F((-6) + F(F(6)))))) \\
 34667 &:= (-F(F(3))) + (F(4) \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F((F(6) + (7)))))) \\
 34668 &:= (3 \times (F((F(4) + (6 + 6))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 34669 &:= (F(F(3)) + (F(4) \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F((6 + 9)))))) \\
 34674 &:= (3 \times ((F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F((F(7) + F(F(4)))))) \\
 34693 &:= ((F(3) \times F((F(F(4))) + (F(F(6)))))) - ((9^3)) \\
 34717 &:= (((F(3) + F(4)) + F((F(7) - 1))) \times F(F(7))) \\
 34742 &:= F(3) \times (4^7 + F(4^2)) \\
 34749 &:= (((-3^4) \times F(7)) \times (F(F(F(4))) - F(9))) \\
 34758 &:= (3 \times (((F(F(4))^7) \times 5) + F(F(8)))) \\
 34776 &:= (((-3) - ((-4) - F(F(7))) \times 7) \times F(F(6))) \\
 34816 &:= ((F(3)^{F(4)+8}) \times F((1 + F(6)))) \\
 34848 &:= (((3 + (F(4) \times F(8)))^{F(4)}) \times 8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34876 &:= (F(3) \times (F((F(F(4))) + (F(8)))) - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 34950 &:= ((3 \times F((4 + 9))) \times 50) \\
 34968 &:= (3 \times (-4) - ((-F(9)) \times F(F(6))) - F(F(8))) \\
 34974 &:= 3 \times (-4 + F(9) \times 7^{F(4)}) \\
 34986 &:= (3 \times ((F(F(4)) + ((F(9) \times F(8)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 34989 &:= 3 + 49 \times F(8) \times F(9) \\
 34992 &:= 3 \times ((F(4) + 9) \times 9)^2 \\
 35136 &:= (((3^5) + 1) \times F((F(3) \times 6))) \\
 35280 &:= ((F((3 + 5))^2) \times 80) \\
 35316 &:= (F(3) \times (-53) + F((1 + F(F(6)))))) \\
 35367 &:= (3 \times ((F((5 \times 3)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7)))) \\
 35414 &:= (F(3) \times (F((F((5 + F(4))) + 1)) - 4)) \\
 35416 &:= ((F(3) \times F((F((5 + F(4))) + 1))) - 6) \\
 35418 &:= (F(3) \times ((-5) + F(4)) + F((1 + F(8)))) \\
 35421 &:= F(3) \times F(5 \times 4 + 2) - 1 \\
 35422 &:= F(3) \times F((5 - 4) \times 22) \\
 35423 &:= (F(F(3)) + (F((5 \times 4)) + F(23))) \\
 35424 &:= ((F(F(3)) + (F(((5 \times 4) + 2))) \times F(F(4))) \\
 35426 &:= (F(3) \times ((5 - F(4)) + F((F(2) + F(F(6)))))) \\
 35428 &:= (F(3) \times ((5 - F(F(4))) + F((F(2) + F(8)))) \\
 35432 &:= (F(3) \times (5 + F((F((4 \times F(3))) + F(2)))) \\
 35436 &:= (F(3) \times ((5 + F(F(4))) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))))) \\
 35438 &:= (F(3) \times (F(((5 \times 4) + F(3))) + 8)) \\
 35448 &:= (F(3) \times (F((5 + F(F(4)))) + F((F(F(F(4))) + (F(8)))))) \\
 35462 &:= (F(3) \times ((5 \times 4) + F((F(F(6)) + F(2)))) \\
 35464 &:= ((F((F(3) + ((5 \times 4)))) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(4))) \\
 35478 &:= (((-3^5) \times (F(F(F(4))) - (7 \times F(8)))) \\
 35643 &:= (3 \times (((5 \times F(F(6))) + (4))^{F(3)})) \\
 35649 &:= (F(F((F(3) + (5)))) \times (F((F(6) + (4))) + 9)) \\
 35712 &:= (((-3 \times 5) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(12))) \\
 35750 &:= (F((F(3) \times 5)) \times (F(7) \times 50)) \\
 35924 &:= (((F((F(3) + (5))) - ((F(9) - F(2))^{F(4)})) \\
 35933 &:= ((F(F(3)) - (5)) + ((F(9) - F(F(3)))^3)) \\
 35934 &:= (-F(-3 + 5) + F(9))^3 - F(4) \\
 35937 &:= (-F(-3 + 5) + F(9))^{F(-3+7)} \\
 35943 &:= ((F(F(3)) + (5)) + ((F(9) - F(F(F(4))))^3)) \\
 35944 &:= ((F(3) + (5)) + ((F(9) - F(F(F(4))))^{F(4)})) \\
 35964 &:= ((3^5) + ((9 \times F(F(6)))^{F(4)})) \\
 35987 &:= -3 + 59 \times F(8 + 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 36173** := $F(3 \times 6) \times (1 + F(7)) - 3$
36174 := $((F(3 \times 6) \times (1 + F(7))) - F(F(4)))$
36176 := $F(3 \times 6) \times (1 + 7 + 6)$
36193 := $F(3)^{F(6)} + (-1 + F(9))^3$
36246 := $(-((F(3) - ((6 \times 2)^{F(4)}))) \times F(F(6)))$
36288 := $36 \times (F(2 \times 8) + F(8))$
36350 := $((3^6) - F(3)) \times 50$
36438 := $(3 \times (((F(F(6)) + F(F(4)))^3) - (F(8))))$
36446 := $(F(3) \times ((F(6)^{F(4)} + F((F(F(4))) + (F(F(6)))))))$
36450 := $((3 + 6)^{F(4)} \times 50)$
36478 := $((((-F(3) + F(F(F(6))))/F(4)) \times F(7)) - F(F(8)))$
36483 := $(3 \times (-6) + ((F(F(4)) + (F(8)))^3))$
36485 := $((((F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6))))/(-F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times 5)$
36498 := $((F((F(3) \times F(6))) \times (F(4) + F(9))) - (F(8)))$
36519 := $(F((F(3) \times F(6))) \times (F((5 - 1)) + F(9)))$
36573 := $-((F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + (5 - (F(F(7))^{F(3)}))))$
36576 := $(F((F(F(3)) + (6 + 5))) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6))))$
36579 := $(F(((3 \times 6) + 5)) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(9))))$
36593 := $((F(3) + F((F(F(6)) - (5)))) \times (F(9) + 3))$
36660 := $((F(F(3)) + F((-6) + F(F(6)))) \times 60)$
36731 := $((F(3) + F(F(6))) \times F((F(7) + (3 + 1))))$
36786 := $-((F((F(3) + F(F(6)))) + (F(F(7)) - (F(F(8)) \times 6))))$
36864 := $F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(8 \times 6/4)$
36875 := $((F(-((F(F(3)) - F(F(6)))) + (F((8 + 7)))) \times 5)$
36924 := $(F((F(3) \times F(6))) + ((F(9) - F(2))^{F(4)}))$
36934 := $((3 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((9 - 3)^4))$
36936 := $(((-F(3) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (9 \times 3))/F(6))$
36985 := $-((F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + (F(9) + (F(F(8)) \times (-5))))$
36992 := $((((F(3) \times F(6)) \times F(9)) \times F(9)) \times 2)$
36993 := $(F(F(3)) + ((F(6) \times ((F(9) + F(9))^{F(3)}))))$
36994 := $(F(3) + (((F(6) \times F(9)) \times F(9)) \times 4))$
37044 := $((3 \times 7)^{F(04)} \times 4)$
37168 := $((3^7) \times (1 + F(F(6)))) - F(F(8))$
37196 := $(3^7 + 1) \times (9 + F(6))$
37210 := $((F((F(3) + F(7)))^2)/10)$
37280 := $((-F(3)) \times F(F(7))) \times (F(2) \times (-80))$
37288 := $((F(F(3)) + (F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) - F(8)))) \times 8)$
37295 := $((3 - (F(F(7)) \times (2 - F(9)))) \times 5)$
37346 := $(-3) + (-((F(7)^3)) \times (4 - F(F(6))))$
37347 := $-F(3) + F(7)^3 \times (4 + F(7))$
37348 := $-((F(F(3)) + ((F(7)^3) \times (4 - F(8))))$
37392 := $((F((3 + F(7))) - ((3^9))) \times (-2))$
37439 := $F(3) \times F(7)^4 - 3^9$
37440 := $((F(F(3)) + F(F(7))) \times (4 \times 40))$
37446 := $((F(3) \times (F(F(7)) + (4)))^{F(F(4))}/6)$
37485 := $((3 \times 7)^{F(F(4))} \times 85)$
37498 := $((F((3 + F(7))) \times (4 + F(9))) - 8)$
37512 := $((F(((F(3) - (7)) \times (-5))) - 1)/2)$
37513 := $((F(((F(3) - (7)) \times (-5)) + 1)/F(3))$
37522 := $3 + (F(7) + F(5^2))/2$
37523 := $(3 \times 7 + F(5^2))/F(3)$
37532 := $((3 \times F(7)) + F((5^{F(3)})))/2$
37557 := $(((-3) - F(F(7))) + ((5^5))) \times F(7)$
37584 := $((F(3) + (7)) \times (-5) + F((F(8) - F(F(4))))$
37619 := $-((F(F(3)) + ((F((F(7) + (6))) - 1) \times (-9))))$
37623 := $(((-3) \times F((F(7) + (6)))) + 2) \times (-3)$
37626 := $(-3) - (F((F(7) + (6))) \times (-F(2) + F(6))))$
37627 := $(-F(3) - (F((F(7) + (6))) \times (-2 + 7)))$
37628 := $-((F(F(3)) + (F((F(7) + (6))) \times (-F(2) + 8))))$
37629 := $(F(F(3)) \times (F((7 + (6 \times 2))) \times 9))$
37632 := $3 \times (7 \times F(6) \times F(3))^2$
37638 := $((F(F(3)) + F((F(7) + (6)))) \times (F(F(3)) + 8))$
37639 := $(F(F(3)) - ((F((F(7) + (6))) + F(F(3))) \times (-9)))$
37647 := $((F(3) + F((F(7) + (6)))) \times (-4) + F(7))$
37648 := $((F((F(3) + F(7))) + (F(6)^4)) \times 8)$
37649 := $(F(3) + ((F((F(7) + (6))) + F(F(4))) \times 9))$
37674 := $((F((3 + F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times (F(7) \times F(4)))$
37683 := $((F(3) + (7)) \times (6 + F((F(8) - F(3))))$
37684 := $((F((3 + F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4))$
37726 := $(F(3) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(7))) + (2 \times F(F(F(6))))))$
37728 := $(3 \times (((F(F(7)) \times 7) - F(2)) + F(F(8))))$
37736 := $(F(3) \times ((F(F(7)) \times F((7 + F(3)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
37744 := $(-F(3) + ((F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) \times (F(4)^4))$
37746 := $((-F(3)) \times F(F(7))) \times (-F((7 + 4) - F(6)))$
37747 := $(F(F(3)) + (F(F(7)) \times ((F(7)^{F(F(4))}) - (7))))$
37860 := $((F((F(3) + F(7))) + (F(8))) \times 60)$
37884 := $((F(3) - F(F(7))) \times ((-8) \times F(8)) + (4))$
37946 := $((3 \times 7 + 9)^{F(4)} + F(F(F(6))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 37968 &:= (((F(3) + F(F(7))) - 9) \times (F(6) \times F(8))) \\
 37989 &:= (((F(3) + F(F(7))) - F(9)) \times (F(8) \times 9)) \\
 38267 &:= (-F(3) + (((F(F(8)))/(-2)) + (6)) \times (-7)) \\
 38272 &:= (((-F(3) + F(F(8))) + (2^{F(7)})) \times 2) \\
 38273 &:= (-3) + ((F(F(8)) + (2^{F(7)})) \times F(3)) \\
 38274 &:= (-F(3) + ((F(F(8)) + (2^{F(7)})) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 38276 &:= (F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + ((2^{7+6}))) \\
 38277 &:= (((3 + (F(F(8)))/(-2))) \times (-7)) - (F(7)) \\
 38279 &:= (F(3) + (((F(F(8)))/(-2)) \times (-7)) - F(9)) \\
 38317 &:= -((F(F(3)) + (((F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) - 1) \times 7)) \\
 38318 &:= (((-F(3) - F(F(8)))/F(3)) \times (1 - 8)) \\
 38325 &:= ((-F(3) + (F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) \times (-2 + 5)) \\
 38327 &:= (F(3) - (((F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) - 2) \times 7) \\
 38328 &:= 3 \times 8 \times F(3^2 + 8) \\
 38367 &:= (((F(F(3)) \times F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) - F(6)) \times (-7) \\
 38374 &:= -F(3) \times F(8) + (F(3) \times 7)^4 \\
 38376 &:= (((-F(F(3))) - F((F(8) + F(F(3)))))) \times (-F(7)) / 6) \\
 38414 &:= (-F(3) + ((F((F(8)/F(4))) + 1)^4)) \\
 38416 &:= (((F(F(3)) - 8)^4) \times 16) \\
 38427 &:= (-3) + ((F(8) \times F(4)) \times F((2 + F(7)))) \\
 38438 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + F(8))) + (F(4^{F(3)})) \times F(8)) \\
 38445 &:= ((3 \times F(F((F(8)/F(4)))) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \\
 38447 &:= (F(3) + ((F(8) + F((F(4) \times 4))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 38448 &:= F(3 + 8) \times F(4) \times F(4 + 8) \\
 38475 &:= ((F(F(3)) + (8^{F(4)})) \times 75) \\
 38478 &:= (3 \times (F(F(8)) - ((F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times (-8))) \\
 38479 &:= (((F((F(3) + 8)) \times F(4)) \times F(F(7))) + F(9)) \\
 38493 &:= (F((F(3) \times 8)) \times ((4 \times 9) + 3)) \\
 38495 &:= (F(3) + (F((8 \times F(F(4)))) \times (F(9) + (5)))) \\
 38616 &:= ((F((F(3) + F(8))) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(16))) \\
 38635 &:= (((F((3 \times 8))/6) - F(F(3))) \times 5) \\
 38637 &:= (-3) + ((F(8) \times F(6)) \times (-3) + F(F(7)))) \\
 38640 &:= ((F((F(3) \times 8)) - F(F(6))) \times 40) \\
 38645 &:= (((F((3 \times 8))/6) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5) \\
 38647 &:= (-((F(3) - ((8 + 6)^4))) + F(F(7))) \\
 38674 &:= (((-F(3) - (F(8) \times F(6)))) \times F(F(7))) - (4) \\
 38675 &:= (((F((3 \times 8)))/(-6)) - (7)) \times (-5) \\
 38693 &:= -(((F(F(3)) + F((F(8) - (6)))) - (F(9)^3)) \\
 38694 &:= -((F(((F(3) + F(8)) - F(6))) - (F(9)^{F(4)}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38736 &:= (((F(3)^8) + F(7)) \times F((F(3) \times 6))) \\
 38745 &:= ((3 \times F(8)) \times (F((F(7) + F(F(4)))) + (5))) \\
 38747 &:= ((F((-3) + F(8))) \times (F(7) + F(F(4)))) - (F(7)) \\
 38763 &:= 3 + (8 + 7) \times F(6 \times 3) \\
 38845 &:= (-F(3)^8 + F(8)^4) / 5 \\
 38889 &:= ((F((F(3) + F(8))) + F(F(8))) - ((F(8) \times F(9)))) \\
 38897 &:= (F(F(3)) - ((-88) \times F(9)) \times F(7)) \\
 38967 &:= (3 \times (F(F(8)) - (9 \times (6 - F(F(7))))) \\
 39106 &:= (((F(3)^9) \times F(10)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 39168 &:= ((-F((3 + 9))) \times F((1 + F(6)))) \times (-8) \\
 39176 &:= ((F(F(3)) + (F(9) \times F((-1) + F(7)))) \times F(6) \\
 39194 &:= -F(3) \times F(9 + 1) + F(9)^{F(4)} \\
 39236 &:= (-F(3) + F(9)^2) \times F(3 + 6) \\
 39239 &:= 3 + (F(9)^2 - F(3)) \times F(9) \\
 39249 &:= ((F(F(-((3 - 9))))^2) \times F((F(F(4)) + 9))) \\
 39268 &:= (-F(3) - ((-F(9)) \times F((2 + F(6)))) \times F(8)) \\
 39269 &:= -((F(F(3)) + ((F((9 + F(2))) \times F(F(6))) \times (-F(9)))) \\
 39273 &:= 3 - F(9) + F(2 + 7)^3 \\
 39275 &:= ((F(F(3)) + (F(9) \times (-2) + F(F(7)))) \times 5) \\
 39282 &:= (((3^9) - (2 \times F(8))) \times 2) \\
 39284 &:= (F(3 \times 9) + 2) / (8 - F(4)) \\
 39285 &:= (F(3 \times 9) - F(2) + 8) / 5 \\
 39293 &:= F(3) - F(9 - 2) + F(9)^3 \\
 39294 &:= -3 - 9 + 2 + F(9)^{F(4)} \\
 39296 &:= -F(3) + F(9)^2 \times F(9) - 6 \\
 39297 &:= (F(F(3)) \times (((F(9)^2) \times F(9)) - (7))) \\
 39298 &:= F(3) + F(9)^2 \times F(9) - 8 \\
 39302 &:= -3 + F(9)^3 + F(02) \\
 39303 &:= F(3) + F(9)^3 - 03 \\
 39304 &:= F(3 \times 9/3)^{F(04)} \\
 39305 &:= F(F(3)) + F(9)^3 + 0 \times 5 \\
 39306 &:= F(3) + F(9)^3 + 0 \times 6 \\
 39307 &:= 3 + F(9)^3 + 0 \times 7 \\
 39315 &:= 3 + F(9)^3 + F(1 + 5) \\
 39316 &:= 3 + F(9)^3 + 1 + F(6) \\
 39317 &:= (F(F(3)) + (((F(9)^3) - 1) + F(7))) \\
 39318 &:= ((F(F(3)) + (F(9)^3)) + F(-((1 - 8))) \\
 39323 &:= -F(3) + F(9)^3 + F(2^3)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 39324** := $((3^9) - F(F(3 \times 2))) \times F(F(4))$
39325 := $((F(F(3)) \times (F(9)^3)) + F(F((F(2) + (5))))$
39326 := $(F(F(3)) + (((F(9)^3) + F((2 + 6))))$
39327 := $-3 + F(9)^3 + 2 \times F(7)$
39328 := $F(3) + F(9)^3 + F(2) + F(8)$
39332 := $3^9 \times F(3) - F(3^2)$
39333 := $3^9 \times F(3) - 33$
39334 := $3 + F(9)^3 + 3^{F(4)}$
39335 := $-((F(F(3)) - (((F(9)^3) + (F(3)^5))))$
39336 := $-F(3) + F(9)^3 + F(3 + 6)$
39337 := $-(((F(F(3)) - (F(9)^3)) - F((F(3) + (7))))$
39338 := $((F(F(3)) \times (F(9)^3)) + F((F(F(3)) + 8)))$
39339 := $((3^9) \times F(3)) - ((3 \times 9))$
39345 := $((3^9) \times F(3)) - F((F(4) + (5)))$
39346 := $(F(3) \times (((F(9)^3)/F(F(4))) + F(F(6))))$
39347 := $((3^9) - 3) \times F(F(4)) - (F(7))$
39348 := $3^9 \times F(3) + F(4) - F(8)$
39352 := $((-(3^9) + F(3)) + (5)) \times (-2)$
39353 := $((3^9) \times F(3)) - F((5 + F(3)))$
39354 := $((3^9) - F(F(3))) - (5) \times F(F(4))$
39373 := $((3^9) \times F(3)) + (7) \times F(F(3))$
39374 := $F(3) \times (9 \times 3^7 + 4)$
39377 := $F(39/3) \times F(7) \times F(7)$
39384 := $3^9 \times F(3) + F(8) - F(4)$
39387 := $3^9 \times F(3) + 8 + F(7)$
39392 := $-((F(F(3)) - (((F(9)^3) + F((9 + 2))))$
39393 := $3^9 \times F(3) + 9 \times 3$
39394 := $-3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)}$
39395 := $3^9 \times F(3) + F(9) - 5$
39396 := $F(3) \times (9 + 3^9 + 6)$
39397 := $F(3) \times (9 + 3^9) + F(7)$
39398 := $(3 + F(9)^{F(3)}) \times F(9) - 8$
39434 := $F(3) \times (F(9) + F(4)^{3 \times F(4)})$
39446 := $-((F(3) - (F(9)^{F(4)}))) + F((4 + F(6)))$
39447 := $-((F(F(3)) - (F(9)^{F(4)}))) + F(-((F(F(F(4))) - F(7))))$
39448 := $(F(F(3)) \times ((F(9)^{F(4)}) + F((4 + 8))))$
39449 := $((F(F(3)) + (F(9)^{F(4)})) + F((F(4) + 9)))$
39466 := $(F(F(3)) + (9 \times (-((F(4)^{F(6)})) + F(F(F(6))))))$
39468 := $(3 + (9 \times (-((F(4)^{F(6)})) + F(F(8))))$
39472 := $-((F(F(3)) - (((F(9)^{F(4)}) + (F(7)^2))))$
39473 := $(F(F(3)) \times ((F(9)^{F(4)}) + (F(7)^{F(3)}))$
39474 := $F(3) \times 9 \times (-4 + F(7)^{F(4)})$
39475 := $(F(F(3)) - (F(9) \times (4 - (F(F(7)) \times 5))))$
39486 := $((F(F(3)) - ((9^4) + F(8))) \times (-6))$
39496 := $((3 + (F(9)^{F(4)})) - (-9) \times F(F(6)))$
39498 := $((F(-((F(3) - 9)))^4) + (-9) + F(F(8)))$
39537 := $((39 - 5)^3) + F(F(7))$
39556 := $((F(F(3)) - F((F(9) - (5)))) / (-5 - F(6)))$
39569 := $((F(((F(3) \times 9) + (5))) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(9))$
39573 := $(-3) + (F(9) \times ((5 \times F(F(7))) - F(F(3))))$
39574 := $(-F(3)) + (F(9) \times ((5 \times F(F(7))) - F(F(F(4))))$
39577 := $(3 - ((F((F(9) - (5))) + F(F(7))) / (-F(7))))$
39579 := $(3 - (((F(9) \times (-5)) \times F(F(7))) + F(9)))$
39585 := $(F(F(3)) \times ((F((9 + 5)) \times F(8)) \times 5))$
39593 := $((F((-3) + F(9))) - (5)) / F(9) - 3$
39594 := $((F((-3) + F(9))) - (5)) / F(9) - F(F(4))$
39597 := $-((F(-((F(3) - 9))) - ((5 \times F(9)) \times F(F(7))))$
39603 := $(F(F(F(-((3 - 9)))) + (F((F(F(6)) + F(03))))$
39615 := $((F(F(3)) - (-F(9) \times F((6 + 1)))) \times 5)$
39618 := $(-3) + ((F((9 + F(F(6)))) + 1) / F(8))$
39621 := $((F(F(3)) + F((9 + F(F(6)))) / 21)$
39625 := $((3 + (F(9) \times F(F((F(6) - F(2)))))) \times 5)$
39636 := $((-((F(F(3)) - F(9))) + F(F(F(6)))) + F((F(3) + F(F(6))))$
39638 := $((F(F(3)) + F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F((F(3) + F(8))))$
39658 := $(F(3) \times ((9 \times F((F(F(6)) - (5)))) + F(F(8))))$
39690 := $(F(F(-((3 - 9)))) \times (F(F(6)) \times 90))$
39726 := $((3 - F(((F(9) - (7)) + F(2)))) / (-F(6)))$
39728 := $(F(3) + (9 \times (F(F(7)) + F((-2) + F(8))))$
39765 := $((F(F(3)) - F(9)) \times ((F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times (-5)))$
39795 := $((3 + ((F(9) \times F(F(7))) + F(9))) \times 5)$
39832 := $((-(3^9) - F(F((F(8)/3)))) \times (-2))$
39836 := $(F(F(-((F(3) - 9)))) + (F(F(8)) + F((F(3) + F(F(6))))$
39874 := $((3^9) + F(8)) + F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))$
39925 := $(F((F(-((3 - 9))) + 9)) \times 25)$
39936 := $((F(3)^9) \times F((9 - F(3)))) \times 6$
39984 := $((-3) \times F(9)) \times (-98 \times 4)$
41472 := $(F(F(4)) \times (F(((1 + 4) + 7)^2))$
41474 := $(F(-((F(4) - 14))) \times (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))))$

- 41687** := ((F(F(4)) × (F(16) × F(8))) + F(F(7)))
41736 := (4 × (-((1 + 7)³) + F(F(F(6))))
41760 := (F(4) × ((1 - F(F(7))) × (-60)))
41810 := (F(-((F((4 - 1) - F(8)))) × 10)
41848 := (-4) × (((1 + F(8))^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(8)))
42276 := (4 × (-((F(2) × F((2 × 7)))) + F(F(F(6))))
42336 := (((4 × F((2³)))^{F(3)}) × 6)
42441 := F(4²) × (44 - 1)
42443 := (F(F(4)) + (F((2⁴)) × 43))
42632 := (F(F(4)) × ((F((2 × 6)) + F(3))²))
42696 := (4 × (F(F((2 + 6))) - (F(9) × F(6))))
42699 := (F(4²) + 6) × (9 + F(9))
42768 := (-4) × ((F((F(2) × F(7))) + F(F(6))) - F(F(8)))
42770 := ((F(F(F(4))) + (F((2 + F(7)))) × 70)
42784 := (-((F((4²)) + F(7))) + (F(F(8)) × 4))
42797 := ((4 × F(F((F(2) + (7)))))) - (F((9 + 7)))
42844 := (4 × ((-2) + F(F(8))) - F(F((F(4) + (4))))))
42848 := (4 × ((-F(2) - F(F((F(8)/F(4)))))) + F(F(8)))
42849 := (((F(4) × (2 + F(8)))^{F(F(4))}) × 9)
42852 := (-4) × ((-F(2)) × F(F(8))) + F(F((5 + 2)))
42856 := (-4) × ((-F(2) - F(F(8))) + F((5 + F(6))))
42864 := (((-F(4) + F(F(-((F(2) - 8)))))) - F(F(F(6)))) × (-4))
42872 := (((-4) × (2 + F(8))) × F(F(7))) × (-2)
42873 := -((F(F(4)) - ((28 + 7)³))
42874 := -((F(F(F(4))) - ((28 + 7)^{F(4)}))
42876 := (-4) × (((-F(2)) × F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (6))
42888 := (-4) × ((28 × 8) - F(F(8)))
42896 := (4 × ((-((2⁸)) + F(9)) + F(F(F(6))))
42968 := (-4) × (((F(2) × F(9)) × 6) - F(F(8)))
43146 := ((F(4)³) × (1 + F((-4) + F(F(6))))
43173 := F(4)³ × (F(17) + F(3))
43264 := (((4 × F(3)) × 26)^{F(F(4))})
43276 := (4 × ((F(F(3)) - (2⁷)) + F(F(F(6))))
43343 := ((F(F((4 + 3)))^{F(3)}) - F(F((4 × F(3))))
43346 := (((F(F((4 + 3)))^{F(3)}) + F(4)) - F(F(F(6))))
43376 := (4 × ((-3) × F((F(3) + (7)))) + F(F(F(6))))
43428 := ((F(F(4)) × F((F(3)⁴))) × (F(2) + F(8)))
43448 := (-4) × (((3⁴) + F(4)) - F(F(8)))
43487 := (-((4³)) + ((4 × F(F(8))) - F(F(7)))
43496 := (4 × (F(F((F(3))^{F(4)}))) + (-9) × F(6)))
43528 := ((4 × F(F((3 + 5)))) - (2⁸))
43546 := (-((F(F((4 + 3))) + (5))) - (-4) × F(F(F(6))))
43547 := (((4 × F(F((3 + 5)))) - (4)) - F(F(7)))
43548 := (-4) × ((F((F(3) × 5)) + (4)) - F(F(8)))
43556 := (4 × (-((F(3) + (55))) + F(F(F(6))))
43562 := ((4 × (-F((F(3) × 5))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 2)
43563 := ((4 × (-F((F(3) × 5))) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(3)))
43564 := (4 × (F(F((3 + 5))) - F((6 + 4))))
43567 := ((4 × (-((F(F(3)) - (5))) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(7)))
43568 := (-4) × (-((F(3) - (56))) - F(F(8)))
43576 := (((F(F(F(4))) + F(F((F(3) + (5)))))) × F(F(7))) - F(F(F(6)))
43596 := (4 × (-((F(3) + (5 × 9))) + F(F(F(6))))
43616 := (4 × ((-F(3)) × F(F(6))) + F(F(F((1 × 6))))
43628 := (-4) × ((3 + (6²)) - F(F(8)))
43636 := (4 × ((-3) + F(F(F(6)))) - F((3 + 6)))
43640 := (-F((4 × 3)) - (F(F(F(6))) × (-4 + 0)))
43641 := (-F((4 × 3)) - ((F(F(F(6))) × (-4)) - 1))
43642 := (-F((4 × 3)) + ((F(F(F(6))) × 4) + 2))
43643 := (-F((4 × 3)) + ((F(F(F(6))) × 4) + 3))
43644 := (((-F((F(4))^{F(3)}))) + F(F(F(6))) × 4) - 4)
43645 := (-F((4 × 3)) + ((F(F(F(6))) × 4) + (5)))
43646 := (F(F(4)) - ((F(3) × F(F(F(6)))) - (4^{F(6)})))
43647 := (-F((4 × 3)) + ((F(F(F(6))) × 4) + 7))
43648 := (-4) × (F((36/4)) - F(F(8)))
43649 := (-F((4 × 3)) + ((F(F(F(6))) × 4) + 9))
43656 := (4 × ((-F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (5 × 6))
43664 := (((F(4) × (-3)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(6))) × 4)
43666 := ((4 × (F(3) + F(F(F(6)))) + (-6) × F(F(6)))
43668 := (-4) × (((F(3) + (6)) + F(F(6))) - F(F(8)))
43672 := (4 × ((-F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(7) × 2))
43674 := (F(F(4)) × ((F(3) × F(F(F(6)))) - (F((F(7) - F(4))))))
43676 := (4 × ((F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (7 + F(F(6))))
43679 := ((4 × (3 + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(7) × (-9)))
43683 := ((4 × (-3) + F(F(F(6)))) - F((8 + 3)))
43684 := (((-4) - F((F(3) + (6)))) + F(F(8))) × 4)
43685 := (((F(4)³⁺⁶) - F(F(8))) × 5)
43686 := ((-4) × ((F(3) + F(F(6))) - F(F(8)))) - (6)
43687 := (((-4) × (-F((3 + 6))) - F(F(8))) - F(F(7)))
43688 := (-4) × (-((3 - 6) × 8)) - F(F(8)))

$$\begin{aligned}
 43690 &:= ((4 \times (-F(F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))) - (90)) \\
 43692 &:= ((4 \times F(F((F(3) + (6)))) - (92)) \\
 43694 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (94)) \\
 43696 &:= (4 \times (((F(3) \times 6) - F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 43698 &:= ((4 \times (3 + F(F(F(6)))) - (98)) \\
 43699 &:= ((4 \times (-F(F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((9 \times 9)) \\
 43716 &:= (4 \times (((-3) - F(7)) - 1) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 43718 &:= ((4 \times ((F(3)^{F(7)} + 1)) + F(F(8))) \\
 43720 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) - (3^7)) \times (-20)) \\
 43724 &:= (-4) \times ((F(3) + F(7)) - F(F((2 \times 4)))) \\
 43728 &:= (-4) \times ((F(3) \times 7) - F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \\
 43729 &:= ((4 \times F((3 \times 7))) - F((F(2) + 9))) \\
 43732 &:= ((F(F((4 \times F(3)))) - F(7)) \times (F(3) + 2)) \\
 43735 &:= (((4 \times (3^7)) - F(F(3))) \times 5) \\
 43736 &:= 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - F(3) \times 6) \\
 43738 &:= -((F(F(4)) - (-((3^7) \times (F(F(3)) - (F(8)))))) \\
 43742 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - 42 \\
 43744 &:= (-4) \times ((3 + 7) - F(F((4 + 4)))) \\
 43745 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) + ((3^7) \times 4)) \times 5) \\
 43746 &:= ((-4) - F((F(3) + (7)))) - (-4) \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 43748 &:= (-4) \times ((3 \times (7 - 4)) - F(F(8))) \\
 43749 &:= (((4 \times F((3 \times 7))) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(9)) \\
 43752 &:= (-4) \times (-F((3 \times 7)) + F((5 + F(2)))) \\
 43756 &:= 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 5) - F(6) \\
 43757 &:= 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 5) - 7 \\
 43758 &:= 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 5) - F(8) \\
 43771 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - F(7) \times 1 \\
 43772 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - F(7) + F(2) \\
 43773 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - F(7) + F(3) \\
 43774 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - F(7) + F(4) \\
 43776 &:= ((4 \times F(((F(3) \times 7) + (7)))) - F(6)) \\
 43777 &:= ((4 \times F(((F(3) \times 7) + (7)))) - (7)) \\
 43778 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((-3) + F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) + F(F(8))) \\
 43779 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(3)) + F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) - 9) \\
 43780 &:= (-4) + (-((3 - 7) \times F(F((8 + 0)))) \\
 43781 &:= (-4) + (-((3 - 7) \times F(F(8))) + 1) \\
 43782 &:= (-4 + F(3 \times 7) \times 8) / 2 \\
 43783 &:= ((F(F(4)) - (F((3 \times 7) \times 8)) / (-F(3))) \\
 43784 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) \times F(8/4) \\
 43785 &:= ((4 \times F((3 \times 7))) + F(F((8 - 5)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43786 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) + 8 - 6 \\
 43787 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) + F(8) / 7 \\
 43788 &:= 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) + 8 / 8) \\
 43789 &:= (-4) + (((-3 - 7) \times F(F(8))) + 9) \\
 43791 &:= ((4 \times (F(3) + F(-((F(7) - F(9)))))) - 1) \\
 43792 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) + 9 - F(2) \\
 43793 &:= (((4 \times F((3 \times 7))) + 9) \times F(F(3))) \\
 43794 &:= (((4 \times F((3 \times 7))) + 9) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 43796 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(7 \times (9 - 6))) \\
 43797 &:= ((4 \times F((F((3 + 7)) - F(9)))) + (F(7))) \\
 43804 &:= (((F(4) + F(3)) + F(F(8))) \times 04) \\
 43808 &:= (-4) \times ((F(3) - F(F(8))) - 08) \\
 43814 &:= (F((F(4)^{F(3)})) - ((F(F(8)) - 1) \times (-4))) \\
 43816 &:= 4 \times (F(3 \times (8 - 1)) + F(6)) \\
 43817 &:= ((-4) \times (-3) - F(F(8))) + F((1 + 7)) \\
 43818 &:= (((F(F(4)) + F(3)) \times F(F(8))) + F((1 + 8))) \\
 43819 &:= (((F(F(4)) + F(3)) \times F(F(8))) + (1 + F(9))) \\
 43824 &:= (((4 \times F(3)) + F(F(8))) + 2) \times 4 \\
 43826 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((F(3) \times F(F(8))) + F((2 + 6)))) \\
 43828 &:= (-4) \times ((-3) - F(F(8))) - (F(2) \times 8)) \\
 43829 &:= ((-4) \times (-3) - F(F(8))) - ((F(2) - F(9))) \\
 43832 &:= (((4 \times 3) + F(F(8))) \times (F(3) + 2)) \\
 43835 &:= ((-4) \times (F(F(3)) - F(F(8)))) + F((F(3) \times 5)) \\
 43836 &:= ((F((4 + 3)) + F(F(8))) \times (-F(3) - (6))) \\
 43838 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (((-3) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(3))) + (F(8))) \\
 43839 &:= (((F(F(4)) + F(3)) \times F(F(8))) + F((F(F(3)) + 9))) \\
 43844 &:= (((4 \times 3) + F(F(8))) + F(4)) \times 4 \\
 43846 &:= -(((F(F(F(4))) - (3 \times F(8))) + (-4) \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 43847 &:= ((-4) \times (-F(3)) - F(F(8))) + F((F(4) + (7))) \\
 43848 &:= (((4^{F(3)}) + F(F(8))) \times (-4 - 8)) \\
 43849 &:= (-F(4)) + (F(3) \times ((F(F(8)) \times F(F(4))) + F(9))) \\
 43856 &:= (-4) \times (((-F(3)) - F(F(8))) + (5)) - F(F(6))) \\
 43857 &:= ((-4) \times (-F(3)) - F(F(8))) - (-5) \times F(7)) \\
 43858 &:= ((F((4 \times 3)) + (8^5)) + F(F(8))) \\
 43872 &:= (4 \times ((F(F(3)) + F(F(8))) + F((7 + F(2)))) \\
 43873 &:= (((F(F(4)) + F(3)) \times F(F(8))) + F((F(7) - F(3)))) \\
 43876 &:= (-4) \times ((-F(3)) - F(F(8))) - (F(7) + F(6))) \\
 43878 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + (F(7)))) + (F(8)))) \\
 43894 &:= (((F(F(4)) - F((-3) + F(8))) \times (-F(9))) / F(F(4))) \\
 43896 &:= (-4) \times ((-F(3)) - F(F(8))) - (F(9) - F(6)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43897 &:= ((-4) \times (F(F(3)) - F(F(8)))) - (-9) \times F(7)) \\
 43899 &:= ((-4) \times ((3 - F(F(8))) - F(9))) - 9 \\
 43908 &:= (-4) \times ((3 - F(9)) - F(F(08))) \\
 43916 &:= (4 \times (-((F(F(3)) - F(9))) + F(F(F((1 \times 6)))))) \\
 43923 &:= F(4) \times (F(3) + 9)^{2 \times F(3)} \\
 43924 &:= (4 \times ((F(F(3)) + F(9)) + F(F((2 \times 4)))) \\
 43928 &:= (-4) \times (-((F(3) + F(9))) - F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \\
 43929 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + ((F((F(3) \times 9))/(-2)) \times (-F(9)))) \\
 43932 &:= (4 \times ((3 + F(9)) + F(F(F((3 \times 2)))))) \\
 43936 &:= (4 \times (((F(3) + F(9)) + F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 43948 &:= (-4) \times (((-3) - F(9)) - (4) - F(F(8))) \\
 43956 &:= (4 \times (-((F(3) - (9 \times 5))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 43962 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (F((F(3) + 9)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 2))) \\
 43964 &:= (((F(4) + F(3)) \times 9) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4) \\
 43974 &:= (F((4 \times F(3))) \times ((9 \times F(F(7))) - F(4))) \\
 43976 &:= (F(F(4)) + ((-3) + (9 \times F(F(7)))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 43978 &:= (4 + ((-3) + (9 \times F(F(7)))) \times F(8)) \\
 43984 &:= (((4^{F(3)} + F(9)) + F(F(8))) \times 4) \\
 43988 &:= (-4) \times (-((3 \times (9 + 8))) - F(F(8))) \\
 43996 &:= ((4 + F((F(3) \times 9))) \times (9 + F(6))) \\
 44064 &:= (F((F(4) \times F(4))) \times (06^4)) \\
 44288 &:= (-4) \times ((-((4 + 2)) \times F(8)) - F(F(8))) \\
 44296 &:= (4 \times ((-4) \times (2 - F(9))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 44328 &:= (-4) \times ((-4) \times F((3^2))) - F(F(8))) \\
 44348 &:= (-4) \times ((F(4) - F((3 \times 4))) - F(F(8))) \\
 44376 &:= (4 \times ((4 \times 37) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 44395 &:= ((-4) + (F((4^{F(3)})) \times 9)) \times 5 \\
 44396 &:= (4 \times ((F((4 \times 3)) + 9) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 44415 &:= ((F(4) \times F((4 \times 4))) \times 15) \\
 44436 &:= (((F(F(4)) + 44)^{F(3)} \times F(F(6))) \\
 44496 &:= (4 \times ((F((F(4) \times 4)) + F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 44498 &:= ((4 \times F(F((4 + 4)))) + ((F(9) \times F(8)))) \\
 44538 &:= ((-F(4)) \times F((F(4) \times 5))) + F((3 \times 8)) \\
 44550 &:= ((F(4)^4) \times 550) \\
 44636 &:= (4 \times (-((F(4) - ((6^3)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 44646 &:= (-F(F(4))) + (4 \times ((6^{F(4)} + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 44648 &:= ((F(F(4)) + F(F(4))) \times ((6^{F(4)} + F(F(8)))) \\
 44664 &:= (((4F((4 + 6))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4) \\
 44666 &:= F(F(4)) \times (F(F(4)) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \\
 44676 &:= (4 \times ((-4) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(7)) - (6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44679 &:= (-F(4) + ((4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7)))) - F(9))) \\
 44683 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times F((F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(6)))))) + (F(8)^3)) \\
 44684 &:= ((F(F((F(4) + (4)))) + (-F(6)) + F(F(8)))) \times 4 \\
 44687 &:= (F(4) + (-4) \times ((F(6) - F(F(8))) - F(F(7)))) \\
 44708 &:= (-4) \times ((F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) - F(F(08))) \\
 44715 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (4 \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(F((1 + 5))))))) \\
 44716 &:= ((4 \times F((4 + F(7)))) \times (1 + 6)) \\
 44717 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + ((4 \times 7) \times F(17))) \\
 44718 &:= (F(F(4)) + (-4) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-1)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 44719 &:= (F(4) + (4 \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(-((1 - 9)))))) \\
 44724 &:= (((F(F((4 + 4))) + F(F(7))) + 2) \times 4) \\
 44726 &:= (F(F(4)) + (4 \times ((F(F(7)) + 2) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 44728 &:= (-4) \times ((-F(4) - F(F(7))) - F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \\
 44732 &:= (4 \times ((4 + F(F(7))) + F(F(F((3 \times 2)))))) \\
 44733 &:= (((-((4^{F(4)})) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(3))) \times (-3)) \\
 44734 &:= (((4^{F(4)} \times F(F(7))) \times 3) - F(F(4))) \\
 44736 &:= ((-((4 \times 4)) \times F(F(7))) \times (F(3) \times (-6))) \\
 44737 &:= (((-4) \times F((4 + F(7)))) - 3) \times (-7) \\
 44746 &:= ((-4) + ((F(4) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 44748 &:= (-4) \times (((-4) - F(F(7))) - (4) - F(F(8))) \\
 44756 &:= (4 \times ((-((4 - 7))^5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 44764 &:= (((F(4) \times 4) + F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 \\
 44767 &:= ((-4) + F((F(F(4)) \times F(7))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 44768 &:= ((4 - ((4 \times F(F(7))) \times (-6))) \times 8) \\
 44776 &:= (4 \times (((F(F(4)) + (F(7))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 44784 &:= ((F((4 \times 4)) + F(7)) + (F(F(8)) \times 4)) \\
 44788 &:= (-4) \times (((F(4) - F(F(7))) - F(F(8))) - (F(8))) \\
 44789 &:= (-4) - ((-4) - F(F(7))) \times (F(8) \times 9)) \\
 44796 &:= (F(4) + (((-4) - F(F(7))) \times (-9)) \times F(F(6))) \\
 44808 &:= (4 \times ((F(F(4))^8) + F(F(08)))) \\
 44828 &:= ((-4) - F((-4) + F(8))) \times (-28) \\
 44869 &:= (-F(4) + (4 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(6) \times F(9)))) \\
 44876 &:= ((F(F(4)) + F(F(4))) \times (F(F(8)) + (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 44878 &:= (F(F(4)) + (-4) \times (-((F(8) \times F(7))) - F(F(8)))) \\
 44898 &:= (-4 + F(4) \times F(8) \times F(9)) \times F(8) \\
 44924 &:= 44 \times (F(9) + F(2^4)) \\
 44936 &:= (4 \times ((F(F(4)) \times F((9 + 3))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 44944 &:= (((4 + 49) \times 4)^{F(F(4))}) \\
 44967 &:= -((F(F(4)) - ((4 - (-9) \times F(F(6)))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 44968 &:= (-4) \times (-((F(4) + F(9)) \times F(6)) - F(F(8)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44982 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times ((F(4) \times F(9)) \times (F(8)^2))) \\
 44983 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + ((F(4) \times F(9)) \times (F(8)^{F(3)}))) \\
 44984 &:= (F(F(4)) + ((F(4) \times F(9)) \times (F(8)^{F(F(4))})) \\
 44986 &:= (4 - (-((F(4) \times F(9)) \times F(8))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 44988 &:= (F(4) \times (F(F(4)) + ((F(9) \times F(8)) \times F(8))) \\
 44996 &:= (4 \times (-((F(4) - (9 \times F(9)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 45344 &:= -4^5 + F(3 \times (4 + 4)) \\
 45346 &:= -4^5 + F(3) + F(4 \times 6) \\
 45357 &:= -(((F(F(4))^{5 \times 3}) - (5^7))) \\
 45366 &:= (F(4) \times ((-5) + F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 45384 &:= (((4 \times 5)^{F(3)} + F(F(8))) \times 4) \\
 45436 &:= ((-4) \times F(F((5 + F(F(4))))) + (F((3 \times F(6)))) \\
 45467 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - ((-54) \times F(F(F(6)))) / (-F(7)))) \\
 45486 &:= (((F(4)^{5+F(F(4))}) - (F(8))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 45648 &:= (4 \times ((F((5 + F(6))) \times F(F(4))) + F(F(8))) \\
 45666 &:= ((-F(4)) - F((-5) + F(F(6)))) + (6^6) \\
 45696 &:= (((4 \times 56) \times F(9)) \times 6) \\
 45717 &:= (((F((4 \times 5)) - F(F(7))) - 1) \times 7) \\
 \\
 45783 &:= -45 \times F(7) + F(8 \times 3) \\
 45832 &:= (((4^5) + (F(F(8)) \times F(3))) \times 2) \\
 45864 &:= ((-4) \times (-5 - F(8))) \times (F(F(6))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 45868 &:= (-4) \times (((5 - F(F(8))) / F(F(6))) - F(F(8))) \\
 45885 &:= (((F((F(4) + (5))) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(8))) / 5) \\
 45938 &:= (((F(4)^5) \times F((9 + 3))) + F(F(8))) \\
 45948 &:= (((F(F(4)) + (5)) \times (9^4)) + (F(8))) \\
 45963 &:= (-((45 \times 9)) + F((F(6) \times 3))) \\
 46096 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(09) \times F(6) \\
 46124 &:= -4 \times 61 + F(24) \\
 46125 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (1 + 2)^5 \\
 46133 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(13) - F(3) \\
 46134 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) - 1) - F(F((3 + 4)))) \\
 46135 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) - F(F(-((1 - 3) - 5)))) \\
 46136 &:= (F(F(F(4))) - (F(F((6 + 1))) - F((3 \times F(6)))) \\
 46137 &:= (F(4) \times ((F((6 + 1))^3) \times 7)) \\
 46138 &:= ((F(4) - F(F((6 + 1)))) + F((3 \times 8))) \\
 46169 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) - F(F((1 + 6)))) + F(9)) \\
 46172 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (1 + F(7))^2 \\
 46179 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(1 + 7) \times 9 \\
 46184 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 184
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46208 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 20 \times 8 \\
 46224 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(2 \times (2 + 4)) \\
 46226 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 2 - F(2 \times 6) \\
 46240 &:= ((F((F(4) + (6)))^2) \times 40) \\
 46243 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (F(2) + 4)^3 \\
 46256 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 2 \times 56 \\
 46264 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 26 \times 4 \\
 46265 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) + 2) + (F(F(6)) \times (-5))) \\
 46274 &:= ((F(F(4)) + F((F(F(6)) + F(2)))) + (F(7)^4)) \\
 46277 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(2) \times F(7) \times 7 \\
 46279 &:= -((F((F(4) + F(6))) - F(((2 + F(7)) + 9)))) \\
 46283 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 2 - 83 \\
 46284 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times F(2) - 84 \\
 46285 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 85 \\
 46288 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (2 + 8) \times 8 \\
 46294 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 2 \times (F(9) + F(4)) \\
 46295 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 2 \times F(9) - 5 \\
 46296 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(2) \times 9 \times F(6) \\
 46298 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 9 \times 8 \\
 46299 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(2) - F(9) - F(9) \\
 46305 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times ((F(F(6))^3) \times 05)) \\
 46310 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 - F(10) \\
 46313 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(-3 + 13) \\
 46315 &:= ((F(F(4)) + (F(F(6))^3)) \times (1 \times 5)) \\
 46316 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) - (31)) - F(F(6))) \\
 46317 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 \times 17 \\
 46322 &:= (-46) + F((F(3) + (22))) \\
 46324 &:= -46 + F(3) + F(24) \\
 46325 &:= ((-4) - (F(F(6))^3)) \times (F(2) \times (-5)) \\
 46326 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3^2) - F(6) \\
 46327 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3^2) - 7 \\
 46328 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 32 - 8 \\
 46329 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 - 2 - F(9) \\
 46332 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (3 + 3)^2 \\
 46333 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 33 \\
 46334 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(-3 + 3 \times 4) \\
 46335 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) - 35 \\
 46336 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) - F(3 + 6) \\
 46337 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) + 3) - F((F(3) + (7)))) \\
 46338 &:= -(4 + 6) \times 3 + F(3 \times 8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46339 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 3 \times 9 \\
 46341 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3^{4-1} \\
 46342 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3+4) \times 2 \\
 46343 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (F(3) + F(4))^{F(3)} \\
 46344 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 \times (4+4) \\
 46345 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 - 4 \times 5 \\
 46346 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) - 4 \times 6 \\
 46347 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 34 + F(7) \\
 46348 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 \times 4 - 8 \\
 46349 &:= ((F(F(4)) - F(F(6))) + F((F(3) \times (F(4) + 9)))) \\
 46351 &:= ((4 - F(F(6))) + F((3 \times F((5 + 1)))) \\
 46352 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (3 + 5) \times 2 \\
 46353 &:= (((F((4 \times 6)) / (-3)) + (5)) \times (-3)) \\
 46354 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) \times 5 - 4 \\
 46355 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 - 5 - 5 \\
 46356 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (3 - 5) \times 6 \\
 46357 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 + 5 - F(7) \\
 46358 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 3 - 5 - 8 \\
 46359 &:= -F(4) - 6 + F(3 \times 5 + 9) \\
 46360 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) - F(3)) - (6 + 0)) \\
 46361 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) - F(3)) - (6 - 1)) \\
 46362 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) - (3 + (6/2))) \\
 46363 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) - (3 + (6/3))) \\
 46364 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) - 3) - F((6 - 4))) \\
 46365 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) - (3 \times (6 - 5))) \\
 46366 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) - (3 - (6/6))) \\
 46367 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) - F(((3 + 6) - 7))) \\
 46368 &:= F((4 + (((6/3) \times 6) + 8))) \\
 46369 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) + ((3 + 6)/9)) \\
 46370 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3 + 7 \times 0) \\
 46371 &:= F(4) + F(6 \times 3 + 7 - 1) \\
 46372 &:= 4 + F(6^3 / (7 + 2)) \\
 46373 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) + F(7 - 3) \\
 46374 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 3 + 7 - 4 \\
 46375 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) - F(F(3))) + (F(7) - (5))) \\
 46376 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 3 + F(7) - F(6) \\
 46377 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 3 - 7 + F(7) \\
 46378 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) - F(7) + F(8) \\
 46379 &:= ((F(4) + F(6)) + F(((F(3) + F(7)) + 9))) \\
 46380 &:= ((4 + F(6)) + F(((3 \times 8) + 0))) \\
 46381 &:= (((4 + F(6)) + F((3 \times 8))) + 1) \\
 46382 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) - F(3)) + ((8 \times 2))) \\
 46383 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) + (3 \times (8 - 3))) \\
 46384 &:= (((4 + F(6)) + F((3 \times 8))) + (4)) \\
 46385 &:= (((4 + F(6)) + F((3 \times 8))) + (5)) \\
 46386 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) + ((3 \times 8) - 6)) \\
 46387 &:= (((F((4 \times 6)) - F(3)) + 8) + F(7)) \\
 46388 &:= (((4 + F(6)) + F((3 \times 8))) + 8) \\
 46389 &:= (((4 + F(6)) + F((3 \times 8))) + 9) \\
 46391 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) + F(9 - 1) \\
 46392 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F((3 + 9) \times 2) \\
 46393 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) + 9 \times 3 \\
 46394 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) \times (9 + 4) \\
 46395 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) + F(9) - 5 \\
 46396 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) + F(9) - F(6) \\
 46397 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) + F(9) - 7 \\
 46398 &:= (F(((4 + F(6)) \times F(3))) + (9 + F(8))) \\
 46399 &:= -F(4) + F(6^3 / 9) + F(9) \\
 46402 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) + F((F(4)^{02}))) \\
 46404 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 40 - 4 \\
 46407 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times F(07) \\
 46416 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 16 \\
 46419 &:= -4 + F(6 \times 4) + F(1 + 9) \\
 46423 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(4 + 2 \times 3) \\
 46424 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + ((F((6 + 4)) + F(24)))) \\
 46425 &:= (F(F(4)) + ((F((6 \times 4)) + F((2 \times 5)))) \\
 46426 &:= ((F(4) + F((6 \times 4))) + F((2 + F(6)))) \\
 46427 &:= ((4 + (6^{4+2})) - F(F(7))) \\
 46428 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(4) \times (F(2) - F(8)) \\
 46429 &:= ((-4) - F((F(F(6)) - (4)))) \times (-29) \\
 46431 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 4^3 - 1 \\
 46432 &:= (F(4 \times 6) + 4^3) \times F(2) \\
 46433 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) + (4^3)) + F(F(3))) \\
 46434 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) + (4^3)) + F(F(4))) \\
 46436 &:= 4 + F(6 \times 4) + F(3)^6 \\
 46439 &:= F(4) + F(6 \times 4) + F(3) \times F(9) \\
 46446 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) + (F((F(4) + (4))) \times 6)) \\
 46448 &:= -4 + F(6 \times 4) + 4 \times F(8) \\
 46449 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times F(4) \times 9 \\
 46452 &:= ((4 \times F(F(6))) + F((-4) \times (-5) - F(2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46456 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F((5 + 6)))) \\
 46457 &:= (F((F(4) + F(6))) + F((F(4) \times (-5) + F(7)))) \\
 46464 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 4 \times 6 \times 4 \\
 46467 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(4)^6))) - F(F(7))) \\
 46472 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 4 \times F(7) \times 2 \\
 46476 &:= 4 + F(6 \times 4) + F(7) \times F(6) \\
 46478 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(4 + 7) + F(8) \\
 46487 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + F(8)) \times 7 \\
 46488 &:= ((F(4) \times 6)^{F(4)} - F(8)) \times 8 \\
 46493 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3 \\
 46494 &:= ((F((F(4) \times 6)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times (9 \times F(F(4)))) \\
 46495 &:= ((4 + ((F(F(6))^{F(4)} + F(9))) \times 5) \\
 46496 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 4 \times F(9) - F(6) \\
 46497 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 4 \times F(9) - 7 \\
 46512 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F((5 + 1) \times 2) \\
 46517 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) + (5)) + F((-1) + F(7))) \\
 46524 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 52 \times F(4) \\
 46533 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 5 \times 33 \\
 46536 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(5 + 3) \times F(6) \\
 46537 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) + (F((5 + F(3))) \times F(7))) \\
 46538 &:= ((F((F(4) + (6))) \times 5) + F((3 \times 8))) \\
 46546 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times F((6 + 5))) + (F((4 \times 6)))) \\
 46547 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) - (54)) + F(F(7))) \\
 46563 &:= ((F(4) \times 65) + F((F(6) \times 3))) \\
 46566 &:= -F(4) \times 6 \times 5 + 6^6 \\
 46576 &:= -((F(F(4)) + (((6^5) - F(7)) \times (-6)))) \\
 46596 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) - (5)) + F((F(9) - F(F(6)))) \\
 46597 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) + ((5 - 9))) + F(F(7))) \\
 46601 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) + F(F((6 + 01)))) \\
 46607 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) + (6)) + F(F(07))) \\
 46618 &:= -4 + 6^6 - F(1 + 8) \\
 46619 &:= -4 + 6^6 + 1 - F(9) \\
 46624 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (6 - 2)^4 \\
 46625 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + (((6^6) - (2^5)))) \\
 46627 &:= -F(4) + 6^6 - 2 \times F(7) \\
 46628 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times ((6^6) - 28)) \\
 46629 &:= (F(F(4)) + (((6^6) - 29))) \\
 46634 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - ((6^6) - F((F(3)^{F(4)})))) \\
 46635 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times ((6^6) - F((3 + 5)))) \\
 46636 &:= 4 + 6^6 - 3 \times F(6) \\
 46637 &:= -4 + 6^6 - F(3) - F(7) \\
 46638 &:= F(4) + (6 \times 6)^3 - F(8) \\
 46639 &:= ((4 - F(F(6))) + (6^{-3+9})) \\
 46642 &:= (F(F(4)) + (((6^6) - (4^2)))) \\
 46643 &:= F(4) + 6^6 - 4^{F(3)} \\
 46645 &:= 4 + 6^6 - F(4) \times 5 \\
 46646 &:= -4 + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} - 6 \\
 46647 &:= 4 + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} - F(7) \\
 46649 &:= (F(F(4)) + (((6 \times 6)^{F(4)} - 9))) \\
 46650 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (((6^6) - 5) + 0))) \\
 46653 &:= -4 + 6^6 + F(5 - 3) \\
 46654 &:= -4 + 6^6 + 5 - F(4) \\
 46657 &:= F(4) + 6^6 + 5 - 7 \\
 46658 &:= 4 + 6^6 - F(-5 + 8) \\
 46659 &:= F(4) + 6^{F(6) \times 5 - F(9)} \\
 46670 &:= (F(F(F(4))) - (-((6^6)) - F((7 + 0)))) \\
 46671 &:= F(4) + 6^6 + F(7) - 1 \\
 46672 &:= (F(4) + 6^6 + F(7)) \times F(2) \\
 46674 &:= -F(4) + 6^6 + 7 \times F(4) \\
 46675 &:= -(((F(F(4)) - (6^6)) - F((F(7) - (5)))) \\
 46676 &:= (F(F(F(4))) - ((-((6^6)) - F(7)) - (6))) \\
 46677 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + (((6^6) + 7) + F(7))) \\
 46678 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + (((6^6) + F(7)) + 8)) \\
 46679 &:= -4 + 6^6 - 7 + F(9) \\
 46690 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times ((6^6) + F((9 + 0)))) \\
 46691 &:= (F(F(4)) - ((-((6^6)) - F(9)) + 1)) \\
 46692 &:= 4 + 6^6 + F(9) - 2 \\
 46693 &:= ((F(F(4)) + ((6^6) + F(9))) + F(F(3))) \\
 46694 &:= (F(F(4)) + (((6^6) + (9 \times 4)))) \\
 46695 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times (((6^6) + F(9)) + (5))) \\
 46696 &:= -((F(F(4)) + ((-((6^6)) - F(9)) - F(6)))) \\
 46697 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times (((6^6) + F(9)) + (7))) \\
 46698 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 6 \times (F(9) + F(8)) \\
 46699 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times (((6^6) + 9) + F(9))) \\
 46724 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) + (F((F(7) - 2)) \times 4)) \\
 46743 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) + F((7 \times F(F(4)))) - F(3)) \\
 46744 &:= ((F((4 \times 6)) + F((7 \times F(F(4)))) - F(F(F(4))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 46745** := $(F((4 \times 6)) + F((F(7) - ((4 - 5))))$
46746 := $((-F(4)) \times F(F(6))) \times (-F(7) + (F(4)^6))$
46748 := $((F(4) + F((F(F(6)) - (7)))) + (F((F(4) \times 8)))$
46753 := $(F((4 \times 6)) + (7 \times F((5 \times F(3))))$
46764 := $(4 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F(7)) + (F(6)^{F(4)})))$
46766 := $((F((4 \times 6)) + F((-7) + F(F(6)))) + (F(F(6))))$
46768 := $((((-4) - F(F(6))) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times (-8)$
46774 := $((4 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(7) \times (F(F(7)) - F(4))))$
46779 := $F(4 \times 6) + F(7 + 7) + F(9)$
46784 := $F(4 \times 6) + F(7) \times 8 \times 4$
46797 := $F(4 \times 6) + F(7) \times F(9) - F(7)$
46834 := $(F((4 \times 6)) + (F(F((F(8)/3))) \times F(F(4))))$
46836 := $(468 + F((3 \times F(6))))$
46865 := $((F(4)^6 - 8) \times 65)$
46866 := $(4 + 6) \times F(8) + 6^6$
46944 := $F(4 \times 6) + 9 \times 4^{F(4)}$
46946 := $(((-4) + F(F(6))) \times F(9)) + (F((4 \times 6)))$
46966 := $(46 \times (F(9) + F((F(6) + F(6))))$
46969 := $F(4 \times 6) - 9 + F(6 + 9)$
46978 := $(F((-((4 + 6)) + F(9))) + (F((7 + 8))))$
46987 := $F(4 \times 6) + 9 + F(8 + 7)$
46993 := $F(4 \times 6) + (F(9) - 9)^{F(3)}$
47125 := $(F((F(F(4)) \times 7)) \times 125)$
47156 := $(4 \times ((F(F(7)) + F(15)) + F(F(F(6))))$
47200 := $((-F(4)) - F(F(7))) \times (-200)$
47206 := $-((F(F(4)) - (-7) \times (-F(20)) + F(F(6))))$
47208 := $(F(F(F(4))) \times (7 \times (F(20) - F(8))))$
47266 := $(F((F(4) \times (7 - 2))) + (6^6))$
47267 := $(F(4) + ((F(7) - F((-F(2)) + F(F(6)))) \times (-7)))$
47289 := $(-F(4)) + (7 \times (F(-((F(2) - F(8)))) - 9))$
47296 := $(-F(4)) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(2) + (F(9) \times (-6))))$
47297 := $-((F(F(4)) + (F(F(7)) \times (-29 \times 7))))$
47327 := $((-4) + F(((7 + 3) \times 2))) \times 7$
47336 := $(F(F(4)) + (7 \times (-3) + F(-((F(F(3)) - F(F(6))))))$
47338 := $(4 + (7 \times (-3) + F(-((F(F(3)) - F(8))))))$
47345 := $4 + 7 \times (-F(3) + F(4 \times 5))$
47346 := $-F(F(4)) + 7 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))))$
47348 := $F(F(F(4))) \times 7 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(-F(F(F(4))) + F(8)))$
47351 := $(-4) - (-7) \times F((F((3 + 5)) - 1))$
47352 := $(-F(4)) - (-7) \times F((F(3) \times (5 \times 2)))$
47353 := $-((F(F(4)) + (-7) \times F(((F(3) \times 5) \times F(3))))$
47354 := $-((F(F(F(4))) + ((7 \times F(F(3))) \times (-F((5 \times 4))))$
47355 := $(F(F(F(4))) \times (7 \times F(((3 \times 5) + 5)))$
47356 := $(F(F(F(4))) + (7 \times F(-((F(-((3 - 5))) - F(F(6))))))$
47357 := $(F(F(4)) - (F(((7 - 3) \times 5)) \times (-7)))$
47358 := $(F(4) + (7 \times F(-((F(-((3 - 5))) - F(8))))))$
47361 := $-((F(F(F(4))) + (7 \times (-F(F(3))) - F((F(F(6)) - 1))))$
47362 := $((F(F(F(4))) \times 7) \times (F(F(3)) + F((F(F(6)) - F(2))))$
47363 := $(F(F(F(4))) + (7 \times (F(F(3)) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3))))))$
47364 := $(F(F(4)) + (7 \times (F(F(3)) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4))))))$
47365 := $((4 + (F(7) \times (-3^6))) \times (-5))$
47366 := $(F(4) + ((7 \times F(-((F(F(3)) - F(F(6)))))) + F(6)))$
47367 := $(-F(F(F(4)))) + ((7 \times F(-((F(F(3)) - F(F(6)))))) + F(7))$
47368 := $((F(F(F(4))) + (F((F(7) + 3)) \times (-6))) \times (-8))$
47374 := $((F((F(F(4)) \times 7)^{F(3)} - 7) / F(4))$
47376 := $((F(((F(4) + 7) \times F(3))) \times 7) + F(F(6)))$
47377 := $(F(F(F(4))) + (-7) \times (-3) - F((F(7) + 7))))$
47384 := $(F(F(F(4))) + (7 \times (F(-((F(F(3)) - F(8)))) + 4))$
47389 := $(F((F(4) + F(7))) + ((F((3 \times 8)) + F(9)))$
47433 := $((F(F(F(4))) + (F(7) \times F((4 \times F(3)))) / 3)$
47434 := $((4 + (F(7) \times F(F((4 \times F(3)))))) / F(4))$
47437 := $((F(F(F(4))) + (F((7 \times F(4)))) / 3) \times F(7))$
47448 := $(-4) \times (((F(F(7)) - 4) \times (-4)) - F(F(8)))$
47464 := $((F(4) - F(F(7))) \times (-4)) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4$
47467 := $((F(4) + F(7)) + F(-((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(6)))))) \times 7)$
47493 := $((F(F(4))^{F(7)} - ((F(4) - (F(9)^3))))$
47494 := $((F(F(4))^{F(7)} - F(F(4))) + (F(9)^{F(4)}))$
47524 := $((F(F(4)) + (F(7))) - F(F((5 + 2))))^{F(F(4))}$
47526 := $((F((4 + 7))^{F(5-2)}) \times 6)$
47529 := $(-F(4)) - (F(F(7)) \times ((-5) - F(2)) \times F(9))$
47532 := $((4 \times F(F(7))) \times (53 - 2))$
47536 := $(F(4) + ((F(F(7)) \times 5) + F((3 \times F(6))))$
47538 := $((F(F(F(4))) + F(F(7))) \times 5) + F((3 \times 8))$
47548 := $(((-F(4)) - F(F(7))) \times (-5)) + F((F(4) \times 8))$
47566 := $((F(4) \times (F(F(7)) + (5^6))) - F(6))$
47567 := $((F(4) \times (F(F(7)) + (5^6))) - 7)$
47574 := $(F(4) \times (F(F(7)) + (5^{7-F(F(4))})))$
47634 := $((-F(4)) + (F(F(7)) \times (-6))) \times (-34)$
47643 := $(F((F(4) + F(7))) + ((6^{F(4)})^{F(3)}))$
47650 := $((4 \times F(F(7))) + F(F(6))) \times 50$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47664 &:= (F(-((4-7) \times F(6))) + (6^4)) \\
 47670 &:= (F(4) \times ((F(F(7)) - (6)) \times 70)) \\
 47697 &:= (((F(F(4)) + (F(F(7)) \times (-6))) \times (-F(9))) + F(F(7))) \\
 47736 &:= (((F(F(4))^{F(7)} - F(F(7))) - 3) \times 6) \\
 47744 &:= ((F(F(4))^7) \times (F((7 \times F(F(4)))) - 4)) \\
 47754 &:= (-(((F(F(4))^{F(7)} - F(F(7)))) \times (-5) - F(F(F(4)))))) \\
 47765 &:= (-((4 \times 7) + F(F(7))) \times F((F(6) + (5)))) \\
 47767 &:= (((F(F(4))^{F(7)} - F(F(7))) \times 6) + (F(7))) \\
 47769 &:= ((4 + F(F(7))) + (F(F(7)) \times (6 \times F(9)))) \\
 47784 &:= (((F((F(4) + F(7))) + (F(7))) + F(F(8))) \times 4) \\
 47793 &:= ((F(F(4))^{F(7)} + ((F(F(7)) - F(9))^{F(3)})) \\
 47845 &:= (((F(F(4))^{F(7)} + F(F(8)))/F(F(4))) \times 5) \\
 47848 &:= (-4) \times (((F(F(7)) + (F(8))) \times (-4) - F(F(8)))) \\
 47897 &:= ((F((4 + F(7))) \times (F(8) + 9)) - (F(7))) \\
 47916 &:= (((F(4)^7) - 9) \times (1 + F(F(6)))) \\
 47946 &:= (((F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9)) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6) \\
 47965 &:= (-F(((4 + 7) + 9)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-5))) \\
 47966 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) - F((F(7) + 9))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6))) \\
 47968 &:= ((F(4) - F((F(7) + 9))) + (6 \times F(F(8)))) \\
 47985 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times F(F(7))) - 9) \times (F(8) \times 5)) \\
 47996 &:= (4 \times ((F(7) \times (9 \times 9)) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 48339 &:= (F((F(F(4)) + (F(8)))) - (F(F(3)) - ((3^9)))) \\
 48342 &:= (F((F(4) \times 8)) + ((F(3) \times F((4^2)))))) \\
 48363 &:= ((48 + F(F(3))) \times F((F(6) \times F(3)))) \\
 48373 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times (-F(F(8)) - (((3 \times F(7))^3)))) \\
 48374 &:= (F(F(F(4))) - ((F(F(8)) - (((3 \times F(7))^{F(4)})))) \\
 48377 &:= ((F(F(4)) + (F((8 \times F(3))) \times 7)) \times 7) \\
 48382 &:= 48^{F(3)} \times F(8) - 2 \\
 48383 &:= (((48^{F(3)}) \times F(8)) - F(F(3))) \\
 48384 &:= (((F(4) \times 8)^{F(3)}) \times 84) \\
 48426 &:= (((48^{F(F(4))}) + 2) \times F(F(6))) \\
 48463 &:= ((F(4) \times F(F(8))) + ((4 + F(F(6)))^3)) \\
 48477 &:= (F(4) \times ((8 + (4^7)) - F(F(7)))) \\
 48486 &:= (((F(F(4)) + (F(8))) \times F(-((F(4) - F(8)))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 48623 &:= (F((F(4) \times 8)) + (F((F(F(6)) - F(2))/3)) \\
 48664 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times F((F(8) - (6)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4) \\
 48672 &:= 48 \times 6 \times F(7)^2 \\
 48673 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + (8 \times ((6 \times F(7))^{F(3)})) \\
 48674 &:= ((4 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))) - F(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48677 &:= ((4 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(6) + F(7)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 48697 &:= (((4 + F(8)) \times F(6)) + 9) \times F(F(7)) \\
 48748 &:= (F((F(4) \times 8)) - (-((7^4) + F(8))) \\
 48768 &:= (-4) \times ((-F(8)) - F(F(7))) \times (6 \times 8)) \\
 48828 &:= ((-F(4) + 8)^8 - F(2))/8 \\
 48864 &:= (F((F(F(4)) + (F(8)))) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(F(6))^{F(4)}))) \\
 48918 &:= (F((F(4) \times 8)) - (F(9) - F(18))) \\
 48927 &:= (-F(4)) - ((F(8) \times (-9) - F(2)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 48930 &:= ((F((-4) + F(8))) + F(9)) \times 30 \\
 48935 &:= (((-F(4)) + F(F(8))) - (F(9)^{F(3)})) \times 5) \\
 48945 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) - ((F(F(8)) - (F(9)^{F(4)})))) \times (-5)) \\
 48946 &:= ((F((F(4) \times 8)) + F((9 \times F(F(4)))) - 6) \\
 48952 &:= (F((F(4) \times 8)) + F((9 \times F((5 - 2)))) \\
 48960 &:= (((F(4) \times (-8)) \times F(9)) \times (-60)) \\
 49152 &:= F(4) \times (9 - 1)^5/2 \\
 49164 &:= (F(4) + 9) \times (1 + F(6)^4) \\
 49239 &:= (((-4) + F(F((9 - F(2)))))/F(3)) \times 9) \\
 49253 &:= (-4) + ((9 \times F(F(F((F(2) + (5)))))/F(3))) \\
 49254 &:= (-F(4)) + ((9 \times F(F(F((F(2) + (5)))))/F(F(4)))) \\
 49262 &:= (-4) + (9 \times ((-2) - F(F(F(6))))/(-2)) \\
 49263 &:= (-F(4)) - (9 \times ((-2) - F(F(F(6))))/F(3)) \\
 49264 &:= (-F(F(4))) - (9 \times ((-2) - F(F(F(6))))/F(F(4))) \\
 49266 &:= (-((F(4) \times F(9))) \times ((-2) - F(F(6))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 49278 &:= (-F(4) + 9) \times (2^{F(7)} + F(8)) \\
 49282 &:= -((F(F(4)) - (((F(9) - (2^8))^2))) \\
 49283 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (((F(9) - (2^8))^{F(3)}))) \\
 49284 &:= (((F(4) + F(9)) \times (-2 - 8))^{F(4)}) \\
 49285 &:= (((-((F(F(F(4))) - F(9)))^2) - F(F(8))) \times (-5)) \\
 49350 &:= (F(((4 + 9) + 3)) \times 50) \\
 49368 &:= ((F(4) - ((9^3))) \times (-68)) \\
 49376 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F((9 - 3)))) - (F(F(7)) \times (-6)))) \\
 49396 &:= (F((4 + 9)) \times (F(F(-(F(3) - 9))) - (F(F(6)))) \\
 49436 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times (-F(9))) \times (F(F(4)) - ((3^6))) \\
 49464 &:= (-4 + F(9 + 4)) \times 6^{F(4)} \\
 49486 &:= (((-((F(4) - F(9))) \times F((-4) + F(8))) - F(F(6))) \\
 49575 &:= ((F(-((F(4) - 9)))^5) + (7^5)) \\
 49631 &:= ((-4) - F((9 + F(6)))) \times (-31) \\
 49664 &:= ((F(F(4))^9) \times (F(6) + F((F(6) + F(4)))) \\
 49674 &:= ((F(4) \times F(9)) \times (F(F(6)) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49693 &:= (-((F(4) - F(9))) \times (6 + F((F(9)/F(3)))) \\
 49732 &:= (F(4) + (((-9) + F(F(7))) - F(F(3)))^2) \\
 49733 &:= (4 + (((-9) + F(F(7))) - F(F(3)))^{F(3)}) \\
 49764 &:= (-4) \times ((-F(9) + F((F(7) + (6)))) \times (-F(4))) \\
 49784 &:= (49 \times ((F(F(7)) + (F(8))) \times 4)) \\
 49785 &:= (((F(F(4)) + (F((9 + 7)))) - F(F(8))) \times (-5)) \\
 49795 &:= ((F(F(F(-((F(4) - 9)))) - (F((7 + 9)))) \times 5) \\
 49896 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) - F(9)) \times ((F(8) \times (-9)) \times F(6))) \\
 49923 &:= (((F(4) \times (9 + F(9)))^2) \times 3) \\
 49928 &:= (((F(F(4)) - ((9 \times 9)))^2) \times 8) \\
 49994 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((-F(9) + F((F(9) - 9)))/F(4))) \\
 50337 &:= ((50 + F(F(3))) \times F((3 + F(7)))) \\
 50653 &:= (50 - F(6) - 5)^3 \\
 51324 &:= ((51 + F(F(3))) \times F((2^4))) \\
 51675 &:= (-5) + ((-1) + F(F(6))) \times F((F(7) + (5))) \\
 51984 &:= ((-5) + F((F((1 \times 9)) - F(8))))^{F(F(4))} \\
 52146 &:= ((5 \times F(21)) - F((F(4) \times 6))) \\
 52441 &:= ((F(F((5 + 2))) - 4)^{F(4-1)}) \\
 52442 &:= (F(F(5 + 2) - 4)^{F(F(4))} + F(2)) \\
 52443 &:= (F(F(5 + 2) - 4)^{F(F(4))} + F(3)) \\
 52444 &:= (F(F(5 + 2) - 4)^{F(F(4))} + F(4)) \\
 52464 &:= (F((5 + F(2))) \times ((F(4)^{F(6)} - F(4))) \\
 52484 &:= ((F((5 + F(2))) \times (F(4)^8)) - 4) \\
 52486 &:= -F(5 - 2) + F(4)^8 \times F(6) \\
 52733 &:= 5 + (2 \times F(7))^3 \times 3 \\
 52743 &:= -5 + (2 \times F(7))^{F(4)} \times 3 \\
 52876 &:= ((-5) \times (-2 - F(F(8)))) - (F(F(7)) \times F(6))) \\
 53128 &:= (-5) + (3 \times F(((1^2) + F(8)))) \\
 53132 &:= ((F((F((5 + 3)) + 1)) \times 3) - F(2)) \\
 53133 &:= (F(((5^3-1) - 3)) \times 3) \\
 53134 &:= ((F((F((5 + 3)) + 1)) \times 3) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 53136 &:= ((5 - F(3)) \times (1 + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))))) \\
 53138 &:= (5 + (3 \times F(((1^3) + F(8)))) \\
 53163 &:= (((5 \times F(3)) + F((1 + F(F(6)))) \times 3) \\
 53167 &:= (-5) + (3 \times (F((1 + F(F(6)))) + F(7))) \\
 53248 &:= (F((5 + F(3))) \times (2^{4+8})) \\
 53357 &:= (F(F((5 + F(3)))) \times ((F(F(3)) - 5) + F(F(7)))) \\
 53374 &:= (F((5 + F(3))) + ((-F(3) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 53488 &:= (((5^3) - (F(4)^8)) \times (-8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53515 &:= (-5) \times ((3^5) - F(F(F((1 + 5)))) \\
 53563 &:= ((-5) \times (F(F((F(3) + (5)))) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(3)) \\
 53564 &:= ((-5) \times (F(F((F(3) + (5)))) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 53565 &:= ((F(F((5 + 3))) - F((5 + F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 53567 &:= ((5 - 3) + (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7)))) \\
 53578 &:= (F((5 + F(3))) + (-5) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 53586 &:= ((-5) \times (F(F((F(3) + (5)))) - F(F(8)))) + (F(F(6))) \\
 53673 &:= (-((F((5 \times 3)) + (6))) + (F(F(7))^{F(3)})) \\
 53680 &:= F(5 \times 3) \times (F(6) + 80) \\
 53743 &:= ((5 \times F((3 \times 7))) - F((4^{F(3)})) \\
 53823 &:= (F(F((5 + F(3)))) \times (F(F((8 - F(2)))) - F(3)) \\
 53824 &:= ((F(F(((5 \times 3) - 8))) - F(2))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 53827 &:= (-5) - (-3) \times (F((F(8) + F(2))) + F(F(7))) \\
 53837 &:= (5 - (-3) \times (F((F(8) + F(F(3)))) + F(F(7)))) \\
 53887 &:= ((F(-((F((5 - 3)) - F(8)))) \times 8) - F(F(7))) \\
 53895 &:= (-5) \times ((-3) - F(F(8))) + (F(9) \times 5)) \\
 53985 &:= (((5 + F((3 + 9))) - F(F(8))) \times (-5)) \\
 53987 &:= ((-5) \times ((3 \times F(9)) - F(F(8)))) - F(F(7)) \\
 54120 &:= (5 + F(4)) \times 1 \times F(20) \\
 54128 &:= (((F((5 \times 4)) \times (-1)) - F(2)) \times (-8)) \\
 54136 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 1 \times F(3)) \times F(6) \\
 54164 &:= (-((5^{F(4)})) + (F(F((1 + 6)))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 54168 &:= ((F((5 \times 4)) + (1 \times 6)) \times 8) \\
 54176 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 1 \times 7) \times F(6) \\
 54248 &:= ((F((5 \times 4)) + ((2^4))) \times 8) \\
 54262 &:= ((F(((5 + 4) \times 2)) \times F(F(6))) - 2) \\
 54263 &:= ((F(((5 + 4) \times 2)) \times F(F(6))) - F(F(3))) \\
 54264 &:= (F((5 + F(4))) \times F(((F(2) \times 6) \times F(4)))) \\
 54268 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))^{F(F(-2+6))}) - (F(8))) \\
 54272 &:= ((F((5 + 4))/(-2)) + (F(F(7))^2)) \\
 54273 &:= ((5 - F((4 \times 2))) + (F(F(7))^{F(3)})) \\
 54274 &:= ((-5) \times F(4) + (F((F(2) \times F(7)))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 54276 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))^2) - (7 + 6)) \\
 54277 &:= ((F((5 \times F(4))) \times F((-2) + F(7))) - (F(7))) \\
 54281 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))^2) - (8 \times 1)) \\
 54282 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))^2) - (8 - F(2))) \\
 54283 &:= ((F((5 \times F(F(4))) \times F((2 \times 8))) - F(3)) \\
 54284 &:= (-5) + (F((F(4) + (2 + 8)))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 54285 &:= (F(((5 \times 4)/2)) \times F((F(8) - (5))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54287 &:= ((-5) \times (42 - F(F(8)))) - F(F(7)) \\
 54288 &:= (((F((5 \times 4)) \times F(2)) + F(8)) \times 8) \\
 54289 &:= (F((5 + (4 \times 2))) \times F(-(F(8) - F(9)))) \\
 54298 &:= (F(5 + 4) \times F(2)) \times F(9 + 8) \\
 54327 &:= ((F(((5 \times 4) - F(F(3)))) - 2) \times F(7)) \\
 54336 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 3^3) \times F(6) \\
 54343 &:= (54 + (F(F((3 + 4)))^{F(3)})) \\
 54344 &:= (F((5 \times F(F(4)))) + ((F(F((3 + 4)))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 54348 &:= (F(54/3) + 4) \times F(8) \\
 54353 &:= (F((5 + F(F(4)))) \times F((F(3 + 5)) - F(3))) \\
 54367 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))^{F(3)})) + (6 \times F(7))) \\
 54385 &:= ((-((5 + (4^3))) + F(F(8))) \times 5) \\
 54387 &:= (-5) - ((F(4) + F(-(F(3) - F(8)))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 54455 &:= (5 \times (F(F((4 + 4))) - (55))) \\
 54459 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))}) + (5 \times F(9))) \\
 54465 &:= (((-54) + F(F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 54467 &:= ((5 \times (F(F((4 + 4))) - (6))) - F(F(7))) \\
 54476 &:= (((5 \times F(F((4 + 4)))) - F(F(7))) - F(F(6))) \\
 54477 &:= ((-5) \times (4 - F((F(4) \times 7)))) - F(F(7)) \\
 54485 &:= (((5 + 44) - F(F(8))) \times (-5)) \\
 54487 &:= ((-5) \times ((4 - F(F(4))) - F(F(8)))) - F(F(7)) \\
 54497 &:= ((5 \times F(((F(4) \times 4) + 9))) - F(F(7))) \\
 54517 &:= ((-5) \times (-4 - F(F(F((5 + 1)))))) - F(F(7)) \\
 54522 &:= (F(F((5 + F(F(4)))) + (F(F((5 + 2)))^2)) \\
 54527 &:= (5 - ((F(F(F(4))) + (F(F((5 + 2)))) \times (-F(F(7)))) \\
 54576 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 57) \times F(6) \\
 54585 &:= (((5 - F((4 + 5))) + F(F(8))) \times 5) \\
 54594 &:= ((5 \times F(F((F(4) + (5)))) - (F(9) \times 4)) \\
 54605 &:= ((-((5^{F(F(4))})) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 05) \\
 54615 &:= (-5) \times ((F(F(4)) + F(F(6))) - F(F(F((1 + 5)))) \\
 54620 &:= (-5) \times ((F(F(4)) - F(F(F(6)))) + (20)) \\
 54625 &:= ((F((5 + F(4))) - F(F((6 + 2)))) \times (-5)) \\
 54626 &:= (F((5 + F(F(4)))) \times (F(F(6)) + F((-2) + F(F(6)))) \\
 54634 &:= ((-5) \times (F(4) - F(F(F(6)))) - ((3^4))) \\
 54635 &:= (5 \times ((F(F(4)) - F(F(6))) + F(F((3 + 5)))) \\
 54636 &:= ((-5) \times (F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) - F((3 + F(6)))) \\
 54644 &:= ((-5) \times (F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(4)^4)) \\
 54645 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(4)))) - (F(F(6)) - (4))) \times 5) \\
 54646 &:= (((5 \times F(F(F(4)))) \times F(F(F(6)))) + (-4) \times F(F(6))) \\
 54653 &:= (((-5) \times F(4) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) - F(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54654 &:= ((((-5) \times F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) - F(F(F(4))) \\
 54655 &:= (((-((5 \times 4)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (5)) \times 5) \\
 54656 &:= ((-5) \times (-F(4) - F(F(F(6)))) - (F((5 + 6)))) \\
 54658 &:= ((-((5 + 4)) \times F(6)) - (-5) \times F(F(8))) \\
 54659 &:= (((F(F((5 + F(4)))) - (F(F(6)))) \times 5) + F(9)) \\
 54660 &:= ((-5) \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(F(6)))) - (60)) \\
 54663 &:= ((-5) \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + 6)) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(3)) \\
 54664 &:= ((-5) \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + 6)) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 54665 &:= (((5 \times F(F(F(4)))) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (65)) \\
 54666 &:= (((5 \times F(F(F(4)))) \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(6) \times F(6)))) \\
 54667 &:= ((-5) \times (-F(4) - F(F(F(6)))) + (-6) \times F(7)) \\
 54668 &:= ((-5) \times (4 - F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(6)) + (F(8)))) \\
 54669 &:= ((-5) \times (-((F(F(4)) - F(F(6))) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(9)) \\
 54690 &:= (5 \times ((F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) - (9 + 0)) \\
 54691 &:= ((-5) \times (F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) - F((9 \times 1))) \\
 54692 &:= ((-5) \times (4 - F(F(F(6)))) - (9 \times 2)) \\
 54693 &:= (((5 \times F(F(F(4)))) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(9) + 3)) \\
 54694 &:= (((5 \times F(F(F(4)))) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (9 \times 4)) \\
 54695 &:= (((5 - F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) - 9) \times 5) \\
 54696 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + F(6) \times 9) \times F(6) \\
 54697 &:= ((5 \times ((F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 9)) + 7) \\
 54698 &:= ((-5) \times (F(4) - F(F(F(6)))) - (9 + 8)) \\
 54699 &:= ((-5) \times ((4 - F(F(F(6)))) + 9) + F(9)) \\
 54705 &:= ((-5) + F((F(4) \times 7))) \times 05) \\
 54720 &:= (5 \times (F((F(4) \times 7)) - (2 + 0))) \\
 54721 &:= ((5 \times (F((F(4) \times 7)) - 2)) + 1) \\
 54722 &:= (-F((5 + 4)) + ((F(F(7)) + F(2))^2)) \\
 54723 &:= ((5 \times (F((F(4) \times 7)) - 2)) + 3) \\
 54724 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) - (2 + 4)) \\
 54725 &:= (-5) \times (((F(4)^7) + 2) \times (-5)) \\
 54726 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + ((2 - 6))) \\
 54727 &:= ((5 \times (F((F(4) \times 7)) - 2)) + (7)) \\
 54728 &:= ((-5) + F(4)) - (-((7 - 2) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 54729 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) - (F(2)^9)) \\
 54730 &:= (5 \times F(F(((4 + 7) - 3) + 0))) \\
 54731 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + F((3 - 1))) \\
 54732 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + (F(3) \times F(2))) \\
 54733 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + F((F(3) + F(3)))) \\
 54734 &:= ((5 \times F(F(((4 + 7) - 3))) + (4)) \\
 54735 &:= (((5 - 4) + F((7 \times 3))) \times 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54736 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) - ((F(3) - F(6)))) \\
 54737 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(7 \times 3)) - F(7) \\
 54738 &:= ((5 \times F(F((4 + 7) - 3))) + 8) \\
 54739 &:= ((5 \times F(F((4 + 7) - 3))) + 9) \\
 54740 &:= (5 \times (F(F(4)) + F((7 \times F(4 + 0)))))) \\
 54741 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(4)) + F((7 \times F(4)))))) + 1) \\
 54742 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(4)) + F((7 \times F(4)))))) + 2) \\
 54743 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + F((4 + 3))) \\
 54744 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(4)) + F((7 \times F(4)))))) + (4) \\
 54745 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + (F(4) \times 5)) \\
 54746 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + (F(F(4)) \times F(6))) \\
 54747 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + (4 + F(7))) \\
 54748 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) - ((F(4) - F(8)))) \\
 54749 &:= ((-5) \times (F(4) - F((7 \times F(4)))))) + F(9) \\
 54750 &:= (-5) \times (-4) - F(F((F(7) - ((5 + 0)))))) \\
 54751 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + F(F((5 + 1)))) \\
 54752 &:= ((-5) \times (-4) - F(F((F(7) - (5)))))) + 2) \\
 54753 &:= (((5 + F((F(4) \times 7))) \times 5) - F(3)) \\
 54754 &:= (((5 + F((F(4) \times 7))) \times 5) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 54755 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + ((5 \times 5))) \\
 54756 &:= (((5 - 4) + F(F(7)))^{F(-5+F(6))}) \\
 54757 &:= ((-5) \times (-4) - F(F((F(7) - (5)))))) + 7) \\
 54758 &:= (((5 \times F(4)) + F(7)) - (-5) \times F(F(8))) \\
 54759 &:= ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) - (5 - F(9))) \\
 54775 &:= (-5) \times ((4 - F(7)) - F(F((F(7) - (5)))))) \\
 54776 &:= (((5 \times 47) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(6))) \\
 54779 &:= ((-5) \times (-F(4) - F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) + F(9)) \\
 54795 &:= 5 \times F(4 \times 7) / (F(9) - 5) \\
 54796 &:= ((5 \times (F((F(4) \times 7)) + 9)) + F(F(6))) \\
 54805 &:= (((5 \times F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 05) \\
 54815 &:= (-5) \times ((4 - F(F(8))) - F(F((1 + 5)))) \\
 54820 &:= (-5) \times ((F(F(4)) - F(F(8))) - (20)) \\
 54825 &:= (((5 \times 4) + F(F(8))) - F(2)) \times 5) \\
 54829 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(4)) + F(F(8)))) + (F((2 + 9)))) \\
 54835 &:= (((5 \times 4) + F(F(8))) + F(F(3))) \times 5) \\
 54839 &:= ((-5) \times (-4) - F(F(8))) + F((F(3) + 9)) \\
 54845 &:= (((5^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(8))) - F(F(4))) \times 5) \\
 54853 &:= (((5^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(8))) \times 5) - F(3) \\
 54854 &:= (((5^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(8))) \times 5) - F(F(F(4))) \\
 54855 &:= (((5 \times 4) + F(F(8))) + (5)) \times 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54856 &:= (((F((5 + F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times 5) + F(F(6))) \\
 54864 &:= ((-5) \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(8)))) + F((F(6) + (4)))) \\
 54865 &:= (((F((5 + F(4))) + F(F(8))) + (6)) \times 5) \\
 54866 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(4)) + F(F(8)))) - (-6) \times F(F(6))) \\
 54867 &:= ((-5) \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(8)))) + (F(F(6)) \times 7) \\
 54869 &:= (((5 \times F(F(4))) \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)))) + F(9)) \\
 54874 &:= (((5 \times F(F(F(4)))) \times F(F(8))) + F((F(7) - F(F(F(4)))))) \\
 54884 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(4)) + F(F(8)))) + F((8 + 4))) \\
 54885 &:= (((5 \times F(F(4)) + (F(8))) + F(F(8))) \times 5) \\
 54887 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(4)) + F(F(8)))) + (F(8) \times 7)) \\
 54888 &:= ((-5) \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(8)))) - (-8) \times F(8)) \\
 54889 &:= ((-5) \times (-F(4) - F(F(8)))) + F((F(8) - 9)) \\
 54915 &:= (-5) \times (-((F(4) + F(9))) - F(F(F((1 + 5)))))) \\
 54936 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + F(9) \times 3) \times F(6) \\
 54955 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(4)))) + (9 \times 5)) \times 5) \\
 54958 &:= ((-5) + F((4 + 9))) - (-5) \times F(F(8)) \\
 54963 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(-((F(4) - 9)))))) + F(F((F(6) - F(F(3)))))) \\
 54965 &:= (((F((5 + F(F(4)))) + F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 54975 &:= (-5) \times (-49) - F(F((F(7) - (5)))) \\
 54997 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(-((F(4) - 9)))))) - (-F(9) - F(F(7)))) \\
 55125 &:= (((5 \times F(F((5 + 1))))^2) \times 5) \\
 55339 &:= F(5 \times 5) - 3 - 3^9 \\
 55342 &:= F(5 \times 5) - 3^{F(4)^2} \\
 55389 &:= ((-5) \times (-((5^3)) - F(F(8)))) + F(9) \\
 55447 &:= ((F(((5 + 5) + F(F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))}) \times 7) \\
 55454 &:= ((5 + F(F((5 + F(F(4)))))) \times F(F((5 + F(F(4)))))) \\
 55677 &:= (-((5 + 5)) + ((6 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 55885 &:= ((55 \times F(8)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-5))) \\
 55924 &:= -5^5 + 9^{F(2)+4} \\
 56105 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(10) \times 5))) \\
 56259 &:= (F((-5) + F(F(6))) \times (-2 - 59)) \\
 56266 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((2^{F(6)}) \times (-6))) \\
 56284 &:= (((5^{6-F(2)}) - F(F(8))) \times (-4)) \\
 56317 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(3))) + F(17)) \\
 56327 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((3 + (2 \times 7)))) \\
 56448 &:= 56 \times (F(4 \times 4) + F(8)) \\
 56615 &:= (-5) \times (-F((F(6) + (6)))) - F(F(F((1 + 5)))) \\
 56636 &:= (((5 + F((-F(6)) + F(F(6))))^{F(3)}) - F(6)) \\
 56637 &:= (((5 + F((-F(6)) + F(F(6))))^{F(3)}) - 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 56642 &:= (((5 + F((-F(6)) + F(F(6))))^{F(F(4))}) - 2) \\
 56643 &:= (((5 + F((-F(6)) + F(F(6))))^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(3))) \\
 56644 &:= ((5 + F(((F(6) + F(6)) - F(4))))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 56750 &:= (-5) \times ((6 - F(F(7))) \times 50) \\
 56827 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((8 + F(2)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 56848 &:= (((5 \times 6) - 8) \times F(-(F(4) - F(8)))) \\
 56855 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((85 \times 5))) \\
 56873 &:= (F(((5 - F(6)) + F(8))) + (F(F(7))^{F(3)})) \\
 56997 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(9))) + (9 \times F(F(7)))) \\
 57121 &:= (((5 + F(F(7))) + 1)^2 \times 1) \\
 57122 &:= (((5 + F(F(7))) + 1)^2) + F(2) \\
 57123 &:= (((5 + F(F(7))) + 1)^2) + F(3) \\
 57124 &:= (((5 + F(F(7))) + 1)^2) + F(4) \\
 57132 &:= (((-5) - (F(7)^{1+3})) \times (-2)) \\
 57246 &:= ((57 + F(2)) \times F((F(F(4)) \times F(6)))) \\
 57254 &:= (((5 + F(F(7)))^2) + F((5 \times F(4)))) \\
 57283 &:= (-5) - ((F(7) - F((2 + F(8)))) \times F(3)) \\
 57304 &:= (((-5) + F(-(7 - 30))) \times F(F(4))) \\
 57312 &:= ((F((F((-5) + F(7))) + F(3))) - 1) \times 2) \\
 57314 &:= (F(-(5 - (7 \times (3 + 1)))) \times F(F(4))) \\
 57324 &:= ((5 + F(((7 \times 3) + 2))) \times F(F(4))) \\
 57326 &:= ((5 + 7) - (-F(3)) \times F((2 + F(F(6)))))) \\
 57327 &:= ((F((F((-5) + F(7))) + F(3))) \times 2) + F(7) \\
 57339 &:= (-5) - (-7) \times (F(3)^{F(-F(3)+9)}) \\
 57349 &:= 5 + 7 \times F(3)^{4+9} \\
 57358 &:= ((5 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F((F(3) + (5)))) + 8)) \\
 57384 &:= (((5 \times 7) + F((F(3) + F(8)))) \times F(F(4))) \\
 57387 &:= (5 - ((F(F(7)) + F(-(F(3) - F(8)))) \times (-F(7)))) \\
 57492 &:= (((5 + 7) \times F(4)) \times F((F(9)/2))) \\
 57494 &:= ((F((5 + F(7))/4) \times F((9 + F(F(4)))))) \\
 57547 &:= ((F(((5 + F(7)) + (5))) \times F(F(4))) + F(F(7))) \\
 57645 &:= 5^7 - F(6)^4 \times 5 \\
 57669 &:= (5 + ((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times (F(6) \times F(9)))) \\
 57815 &:= (-5) \times ((-7) - F(F(8))) - F(15)) \\
 57845 &:= (-5) \times ((-F(7)) - F(F(8))) - F((F(4) \times 5))) \\
 57850 &:= (((-5) \times F(F(7))) + 8) \times (-50) \\
 57855 &:= ((5 \times F((F(7) + 8))) + ((5^5))) \\
 58250 &:= (F((5 + 8)) \times 250) \\
 58384 &:= (((-5) + F(8)) \times ((F(F(3)) + F(F(8)))/F(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 58674 &:= ((F((5 + 8)) + F(F(6))) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(4)))) \\
 58686 &:= (((-5) \times F((F(8) - F(6)))) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 58716 &:= ((F((5 + 8)) \times (F(7) - 1)) \times F(F(6))) \\
 58746 &:= ((5 - ((-F(8)) \times F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)))) \times 6) \\
 58826 &:= ((5 \times F(F(8))) + ((8/2)^6)) \\
 58944 &:= (((-5) \times F(8)) + (9^{F(F(4)+F(4)})) \\
 58957 &:= -5 \times F(8) + 9^5 + F(7) \\
 59044 &:= (-5) + (9^{F(F(04)+F(4)})) \\
 59049 &:= F(-5 + 9) \times F(04)^9 \\
 59053 &:= ((5 + (9^{05})) - F(F(3))) \\
 59054 &:= ((5 + (9^{05})) \times F(F(F(4)))) \\
 59057 &:= -5 + 9^{05} + F(7) \\
 59177 &:= (-5) + ((F((9 - 1)) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(7))) \\
 59277 &:= (((-5) + (9^{-2+7})) + F(F(7))) \\
 59314 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 - 1 - 4 \\
 59315 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 + 1 - 5 \\
 59318 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 - 1^8 \\
 59319 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 \times 1^9 \\
 59338 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 - F(3) + F(8) \\
 59347 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 + 4 \times 7 \\
 59349 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 - 4 + F(9) \\
 59374 &:= (((5 + F(9))^3) + F((F(7) - F(4)))) \\
 59383 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 + 8^{F(3)} \\
 59392 &:= (-5 + F(9)) \times F(3)^{9+2} \\
 59426 &:= F(5 + 9) + F(4)^{2+F(6)} \\
 59447 &:= (((5 + F(9))^{F(4)}) + (F(F(4))^7)) \\
 59463 &:= (((5 + F(9))^{F(4)}) + F((6 \times F(3)))) \\
 59547 &:= (((-5) + ((F(9) + (5))^{F(4)})) + F(F(7))) \\
 59648 &:= (F(F((5 + F((9 - 6)))) \times (F(F(4))^8)) \\
 59665 &:= ((F((F(F(-((5 - 9)))) \times F(6))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 59787 &:= (((-5) + 9) + F(F(7))) \times (F(8) \times F(7)) \\
 59876 &:= (((5 \times (F(9) + 8)) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 60945 &:= 60 + 9 \times F(4 \times 5) \\
 61467 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + 1)) + (4 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 7))) \\
 61476 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (1 + (F(4) \times F(F(7)))) \times 6) \\
 61483 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + 1)) + (4 \times (F(F(8)) - 3))) \\
 61485 &:= (F((F(F(6)) - 1)) - ((F(F(4)) - F(F(8))) \times 5)) \\
 61488 &:= 61 \times 48 \times F(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 61495** := $(F((F(F(6)) - 1)) - (F(F(F(-(F(4) - 9)))))) \times (-5))$
61745 := $(F(F((6 + 1))) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(F(4))^5)))$
61824 := $((F(6) - F(18)) \times (-24))$
61848 := $F(6) \times (F(18) \times F(4) - F(8))$
62016 := $F(6) \times (F(20) + F(16))$
62244 := $(F(F(6)) \times ((F(2) + F((2^4))) \times F(4)))$
62426 := $((F(6) - F(2))^4 \times 26)$
62482 := $((F((F(F(6)) - F(2))) \times (-F(4))) - F(F(8))) \times (-2)$
62564 := $F(6)^2 + 5^6 \times 4$
62568 := $((-(((6 - F(2))^5)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8)$
62622 := $((F(F(6))^2) \times (F((6 \times 2)) - 2))$
62656 := $(-((F(6)^2) \times (F(6) - F((-5) + F(F(6))))))$
62677 := $((6^2) + F((6 + 7))) \times F(F(7))$
62715 := $(F(((6 \times 2) + 7)) \times 15)$
62736 := $((F((F(F(6)) - 2)) \times (F(7) + F(3))) + (F(F(6))))$
62749 := $((F((F(F(6)) - 2)) \times (F(7) + F(F(4)))) + F(9))$
62782 := $-((F(F(F(6))) - ((2^{F(7)}) \times (8 + F(2))))$
62835 := $((F(6) + F((-2) + F(8))) \times (3 \times 5))$
62874 := $(-6) \times ((F(2) - F(F(8))) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))))$
62896 := $(F(6) \times F(2 \times 8) - F(9)) \times F(6)$
62946 := $-6 - F(2 \times 9) + 4^{F(6)}$
63000 := $(F(F(6)) \times 3000)$
63164 := $F(6)^{F(3)} \times F(16) - 4$
63168 := $((6 + F(3)) \times F(16)) \times 8$
63175 := $F(6 \times (3 + 1)) + 7^5$
63296 := $((F((F(6) + 3))^2) - 9) \times F(6)$
63364 := $((F((F(6) + 3))^{F(3)}) \times F(6)) - (4)$
63368 := $((F((F(6) + 3))^{F(-3+6)}) \times 8)$
63373 := $((F(6) \times F((3 \times 3))) \times F(F(7))) - 3$
63374 := $((F(6) \times F((3 \times 3))) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(4))$
63376 := $F(6) \times F(3 \times 3) \times F(7 + 6)$
63378 := $((F((F(6) + F(3)))^{F(3)}) - (7)) \times F(8)$
63384 := $(F(6) \times (F(3) + (F((3 + 8))^{F(F(4))})))$
63392 := $(F(6) \times (3 + (F((F(3) + 9))^2))$
63397 := $(F(F(6)) - (-((F((3 + 3)) \times F(9))) \times F(F(7))))$
63414 := $(6 \times (F(F((F(3)^{F(4)}))) - (F(14))))$
63424 := $F(6)^{F(3)} \times (4 + F(2^4))$
63462 := $(F(F(6)) \times (-3) + (F((4 + 6))^2))$
63469 := $(F((6 \times 3)) + (F(-(F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(6)))))) \times 9)$
63478 := $(F((6 + 3)) \times (F(4) + (F(F(7)) \times 8)))$
63483 := $(F(F(6)) \times ((F((3 \times 4)) \times F(8)) - F(F(3))))$
63496 := $((F(F(6))^{F(3)}) \times F((F(4) + 9))) - F(6)$
63497 := $((F(F(6))^{F(3)}) \times F((F(4) + 9))) - (7)$
63523 := $((F(F(6)) \times (F((F(3) \times 5))^2)) - F(3))$
63524 := $((F(F(6)) \times (F((F(3) \times 5))^2)) - F(F(F(4))))$
63525 := $((F(F(6)) \times F((F(3) \times 5))) \times F((2 \times 5)))$
63546 := $((F((F(6) + 3)) \times F((5 + 4))) \times F(F(6)))$
63567 := $(F(F(6)) \times (-F(3)) - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (-F(7))))$
63579 := $((6 \times F(F((3 + 5)))) + (F(F(7)) \times (-9)))$
63583 := $-((F(F(F(6))) - ((F((F(3) + 5))) \times F(8))^{F(3)}))$
63654 := $(6 \times ((-F(3)) - (F(F(6)) \times (-5)))^{F(F(4))})$
63667 := $(F(F(F(6))) - (-((3^{F(6)}) \times F(6))) - F(F(7)))$
63674 := $(F(F(F(6))) - ((-3) \times F(6)) \times (F(7)^{F(4)}))$
63687 := $(F((F(6) - F(F(3)))) \times (6 + (F(8) \times F(F(7))))$
63735 := $(F(F(6)) \times ((-3) + F((F(7) + F(3)))) \times 5)$
63737 := $((6^{F(3)} \times 7)^{F(3)} + F(F(7)))$
63744 := $((F(6) \times F(3)) + F(F(7))) \times (4^4)$
63749 := $-((F(F(F(6))) - (-3) + ((F(7)^{F(4)}) \times F(9))))$
63758 := $((F(F(6))^3) - F(F(7))) - (-5) \times F(F(8)))$
63765 := $((-6) + F((3 + F(7)))) \times 65$
63766 := $(-((F(6)^3)) + ((F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6)))$
63777 := $(F(F(6)) \times (F(F(3)) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(7)) + (7))))$
63778 := $(F((F(6) - F(F(3)))) \times (F(7) + (F(F(7)) \times F(8))))$
63786 := $((F(F(6)) \times (-F(3) + F(7))) + F(F(8))) \times 6$
63792 := $(F((6 \times F(3))) \times ((F(7) \times F(9)) + F(2)))$
63798 := $((F((F(6) - F(F(3)))) \times F(F(7))) + 9) \times F(8)$
63846 := $-((F(F((F(6) - F(F(3)))) - (-F(F(8))) + F((4 + F(F(6))))))$
63847 := $-((F(F(F(6))) - ((F(F(3)) + F((F(8) + 4))) - F(F(7))))$
63936 := $6^3 \times (F(9) + 3) \times F(6)$
63948 := $(-6) \times ((F(3) \times F((9 + F(4)))) - F(F(8)))$
63964 := $-6^{F(3)} + (F(9) + 6)^{F(4)}$
63994 := $-6 + (-3 + 9 + F(9))^{F(4)}$
64021 := $(F(F(6)) + ((40^{2+1}))$
64075 := $((F((6 + 4)) \times F(F(07))) \times 5)$
64079 := $(F((6 \times 4)) + F((F(07) + 9)))$
64155 := $(-F(F(6))) \times ((F(F(F(4))) + F(15)) \times (-5))$
64266 := $((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4))) - F(F((F(2) + (6)))) \times 6)$
64272 := $(6 \times ((F(F((4 \times 2))) - F(F(7))) - F(2)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64274 &:= ((6 \times (F(F((4 \times 2))) - F(F(7)))) - (4)) \\
 64276 &:= ((F(F(6)) - F((42 - F(7)))) / (-F(6))) \\
 64278 &:= (-6) \times (F(((4 + 2) + 7)) - F(F(8))) \\
 64296 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(4)) - F(F(-(2 - 9)))) \times 6) \\
 64356 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (4 \times F((F(3) \times 5)))) \times 6) \\
 64366 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + F(F(F(4)))) - (F(F(3)) - (6^6))) \\
 64367 &:= (((F(F(6)) + (4)) \times F((3 \times 6))) - F(F(7))) \\
 64386 &:= (((F(6)^{F(4)}) - F(F(3))) \times (F(8) \times 6)) \\
 64488 &:= (((6^4) + F(-(F(F(F(4))) - (F(8)))))) \times 8) \\
 64512 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((4^5) \times (1 + 2))) \\
 64533 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((4^5) \times 3) + F(F(3)))) \\
 64596 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((4 \times 5) \times 9)) \times 6) \\
 64597 &:= (((F((F(6) \times F(F(4)))) \times 5) + F(9)) \times F(7)) \\
 64638 &:= (6 \times ((F(F(F(4))) + (F(6)^3)) \times F(8))) \\
 64654 &:= -((((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) - (F(6)^5)) \times F(F(4))) \\
 64656 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F((F(4) + (6))) \times 5)) \times 6) \\
 64665 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - 4) \times 6) - F((F(F(6)) - (5)))) \\
 64668 &:= (-6) \times (((F(F(4)) + (6)) \times F(F(6))) - F(F(8))) \\
 64674 &:= (6 \times ((F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(7)^{F(4)}))) \\
 64675 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) - F(F(6))) \times 7) - (5) \\
 64683 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 6) - (F((8 \times F(3)))) \\
 64686 &:= (((F(F(6)) + F((4 + F(6)))) - F(F(8))) \times (-6)) \\
 64689 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (-4) + F(F(6))) - F((-8) + F(9))) \\
 64727 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times (4 + F(F(7)))) + 2) \times F(7)) \\
 64736 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) - (F(7))) \times (F(F(3)) + (6))) \\
 64738 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 7) - (F((3 + 8)))) \\
 64744 &:= (F(F(F(6))) \times F(4) - F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)) \\
 64763 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 7) - ((F(6)^{F(3)})) \\
 64764 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 7) + (F(F(6)) \times (-F(4)))) \\
 64769 &:= F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) \times F(-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \\
 64772 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-F(4) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - 2)))) \\
 64773 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-4 - (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(3)))) \\
 64774 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) - (7)) \times 7) - (4) \\
 64775 &:= ((F(F(6)) + (4)) \times (7 + F((F(7) + (5)))) \\
 64788 &:= (-6) \times (F(F(F(4))) - ((-7) \times F(8)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 64792 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 7) - (F(9) + F(2))) \\
 64793 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 7) - F(9)) \times F(F(3)) \\
 64794 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 7) - F(9)) + F(F(F(4))) \\
 64812 &:= ((F(6) - F(F(4))) \times (F(F(8)) - (F(12))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64818 &:= (-6) \times ((F((4 + 8)) - 1) - F(F(8))) \\
 64824 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) - (8 + F(2))) / F(4)) \\
 64827 &:= ((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times (F(8) - (2 \times 7))) \\
 64832 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) + (F(8))) / 3) - 2) \\
 64833 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) + (F(8) - 3)) / 3) \\
 64834 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) + (F(8))) \times F(F(3))) / F(4)) \\
 64836 &:= (-6) \times ((-4) - F(F(8))) + F((F(3) \times 6))) \\
 64837 &:= 6 + 4 + F(8)^3 \times 7 \\
 64843 &:= ((F(6) \times F(F(4))) - ((F(8)^4) / (-3))) \\
 64844 &:= (F(F(6)) - (4 - ((F(8)^4) / F(4)))) \\
 64847 &:= -F(6) + (4 + F(8)^{F(4)}) \times 7 \\
 64848 &:= (((F(F(6)) / F(4)) \times (F(8)^{F(4)})) + (F(8))) \\
 64872 &:= 6 \times (-4 + (8 \times F(7))^2) \\
 64878 &:= (-6) \times (((F(F(4)) - (F(8))) \times (-7)) - F(F(8))) \\
 64883 &:= ((F(F(6)) / F(4)) \times (8 + (F(8)^3))) \\
 64956 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - F((F(4) + 9))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 64974 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times (-F(9) \times F(7))) / (-F(4))) \\
 64976 &:= (F(6) \times (-4) - (-F(9)) \times (F(F(7)) + (6))) \\
 64981 &:= ((F(6)^4) + (9 \times F((F(8) - 1)))) \\
 64986 &:= (((F(F(6)) - (4 \times F(9))) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 65142 &:= (65 + 1) \times F(4^2) \\
 65164 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (5 + 1)) - (F(6)^{F(4)})) \\
 65233 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(F((5 + 2)))^{F(3)}) - F(3))) \\
 65234 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(F((5 + 2)))^{F(3)})) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 65235 &:= ((F((F(6) + (5)))^2) + F(F((3 + 5)))) \\
 65236 &:= (((F((F(6) + (5)))^2) + F(F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 65238 &:= (((F((F(6) + (5)))^2) + 3) + F(F(8))) \\
 65268 &:= (6 \times (F(F(F((5 + F(2)))))) - (68)) \\
 65269 &:= (((F((F(6) + (5)))^2) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(9)) \\
 65286 &:= ((-65) + F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \times 6) \\
 65298 &:= (-6) \times (((5 + 2) \times 9) - F(F(8))) \\
 65346 &:= (6 \times (F(F((5 + 3))) - F((4 + 6)))) \\
 65364 &:= (6 \times ((-F((5 \times F(3)))) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(4)) \\
 65366 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - 53) \times 6) + F(6)) \\
 65368 &:= F(6)^5 \times F(3) - F(6) \times F(8) \\
 65376 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (5 \times (3 + 7))) \times 6) \\
 65377 &:= (((6 \times 5) \times (3^7)) - F(F(7))) \\
 65378 &:= (((-((6^5)) \times F(F(3))) \times (-7)) + F(F(8)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 65388** := $(-6) \times (((5 + F(F(3))) \times 8) - F(F(8)))$
65406 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5 + 40)) \times 6)$
65436 := $((F(6) \times 5) - F(F((4 \times F(3)))) \times (-6))$
65437 := $((6 \times (F(F((5 + F(4)))) - F(F(3)))) - F(F(7)))$
65443 := $((F((6 + 5)) - F((F(4))^{F(4)})) / (-3))$
65446 := $-6 \times 5 \times F(4) + 4^{F(6)}$
65447 := $-F(6 + 5) + 4 \times 4^7$
65448 := $(-6) \times ((F((5 + 4)) + (4)) - F(F(8)))$
65463 := $((-((F(6)^5) + F(F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-3))$
65466 := $((F(F(F(6))) - F((5 + 4))) \times 6) - 6$
65467 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (5)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 6 - F(F(7))$
65468 := $-F(6 + 5) + 4^{F(6)} + F(8)$
65472 := $((F(F(F(6))) - F((5 + 4))) \times (7 - F(2)))$
65478 := $(-6) \times ((5 + (4 \times 7)) - F(F(8)))$
65484 := $(-6) \times ((F((5 + 4)) - F(F(8))) - F(F(4)))$
65488 := $-F(6) \times 5 + 4^8 - 8$
65489 := $-F(6) - 5 + 4^8 - F(9)$
65494 := $((F(6)^5 - F(F(-(F(4) - 9)))) \times F(F(4)))$
65496 := $((F(6)^5 \times F(F(4))) - (F(9) + (6)))$
65497 := $((6 \times (F(F((5 + F(4)))) + 9)) - F(F(7)))$
65522 := $((F(6)^5 - (5 + 2)) \times 2)$
65523 := $(F(6)^5 - 5) \times 2 - 3$
65524 := $((F(6)^5 - (5)) \times 2) - F(F(4))$
65526 := $(-6) \times ((5 \times 5) - F(F((2 + 6))))$
65528 := $F(6)^5 \times F(5 - 2) - 8$
65532 := $((F(6)^5 - (5 - 3)) \times 2)$
65533 := $F(6)^5 \times (5 - 3) - 3$
65534 := $((F(6)^5 - F((5 - 3))) \times F(F(4)))$
65536 := $F(6)^5 \times (5 + 3 - 6)$
65538 := $(F(6)^5 + 5) \times F(3) - 8$
65541 := $(F(F(6)) \times ((5^5) - 4) \times 1)$
65542 := $((F(6)^5 + (5)) - F(F(4))) \times 2$
65543 := $((F(F(6)) \times ((5^5) - 4)) + F(3))$
65544 := $((F(F(6)) \times (5^5)) - ((F(4)^4)))$
65546 := $(F(6)^5 + 5) \times (-4 + 6)$
65549 := $((F(F(6)) \times ((5^5) - F(F(4)))) - F(9))$
65556 := $((F(F(F(6))) - ((5 \times 5) - 5)) \times 6)$
65562 := $((F(6)^5 + (5)) + F(6)) \times 2$
65566 := $((F(F(6)) \times (-5)) - (5)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6))$
65568 := $(-6) \times (((5 + 5) + F(6)) - F(F(8)))$
65572 := $((F(6)^5 + (5)) + F(7)) \times 2$
65583 := $((F(F(6)) \times (5^5)) - (F(8) \times F(3)))$
65585 := $((F(F(6)) \times (5^5)) - (8 \times 5))$
65586 := $((F(6) - (5)) \times (-5)) + F(F(8)) \times 6$
65591 := $((F(F(6)) \times (5^5)) - F((9 \times 1)))$
65592 := $F(F(6)) \times 5^5 - F(9) + F(2)$
65593 := $F(F(6)) \times 5^5 - F(9) + F(3)$
65594 := $F(F(6)) \times 5^5 - F(9) + F(4)$
65598 := $(-6) \times (F((5 + F(F(-(5 - 9)))))) - F(F(8))$
65610 := $((F(6) - (5))^{F(6)}) \times 10$
65616 := $((F(F(F(6))) - ((5 + 6) - 1)) \times 6)$
65622 := $(6 \times ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) - (2 + 2))$
65623 := $((F(F(6)) \times (5^{6-F(2)})) - F(3))$
65624 := $((F(F(6)) \times (5^{6-F(2)})) - F(F(F(4))))$
65625 := $(F(F(6)) \times (5 \times 625))$
65626 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) - (-F(2) + F(F(6)))$
65627 := $((6 \times ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(2)) - F(7))$
65628 := $(-6) \times ((5 + (6/2)) - F(F(8)))$
65632 := $((6 \times ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(3)) - 2)$
65633 := $((6 \times ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(3)) - F(F(3)))$
65634 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) - (3 \times 4)$
65635 := $((6 \times ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(3))) - (5))$
65636 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) - (F(3) + F(6))$
65637 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) - (3 \times F(7))$
65638 := $-(((F(F(6)) + (5)) + (-6) \times (-F(3) + F(F(8))))$
65639 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) - (3 + F(9))$
65640 := $(6 \times ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(F(4 + 0))))$
65641 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) - (4 + 1)$
65642 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(4)^2))$
65643 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) - (F(F(4)) + F(F(3)))$
65644 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) - (4 - F(F(4)))$
65645 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) + ((4 - 5))$
65646 := $(F(F(6)) + ((F((5 + 6)) + (4^{F(6)})))$
65647 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) + F(F(-(4 - 7)))$
65648 := $((F(6) \times (-5)) + (6 \times (F(F(4)) + F(F(8))))$
65649 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(4) \times 9)$
65651 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) + (5 \times 1)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65652 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) + (5 + F(2))) \\
 65653 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (5)) \times 6) - 53) \\
 65654 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) + (5 + F(4))) \\
 65655 &:= ((6 \times 5) + (F(F(6)) \times (5^5))) \\
 65658 &:= (-6) \times (F(((5 - 6) + 5)) - F(F(8))) \\
 65659 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times ((5^6)/5)) + F(9)) \\
 65671 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5) \times (F((F(6) + F(7))) - 1))) \\
 65672 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (5)) \times 6) - F((7 + 2))) \\
 65673 &:= -F(6) + 5 + 6 \times F(7 \times 3) \\
 65674 &:= ((6 \times F(F((56/7)))) - F(F(4))) \\
 65675 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F((7 - 5))) \\
 65676 &:= (6 \times F(((5 - 6) \times F(7)) + F(6))) \\
 65677 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + (7/7)) \\
 65678 &:= (F((F(6) - (5))) + (6 \times F((F(7) + 8)))) \\
 65679 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + F((F(7) - 9))) \\
 65681 &:= ((-6) \times ((5 - 6) - F(F(8))) - 1) \\
 65682 &:= (-6) \times ((5 - 6) - F((F(8) \times F(2)))) \\
 65683 &:= ((-6) \times ((5 - 6) - F(F(8)))) + F(F(3)) \\
 65684 &:= (F(6) + ((F((-5) + F(6))) \times F(F(8))) \times F(4)) \\
 65686 &:= (-F(6) + (((5 - F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times (-6))) \\
 65687 &:= ((6 + 5) + (6 \times F((8 + F(7)))) \\
 65688 &:= (-6) \times (-F(((5 + 6) - 8)) - F(F(8))) \\
 65689 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) - (((F(F(6)) - F(F(8))) - F(9)))) \\
 65692 &:= ((F(F(6)) - (5)) + (6 \times F(F((9 - F(2))))) \\
 65693 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(9)/F(3))) \\
 65694 &:= 6 \times (F(5 \times 6 - 9) + F(4)) \\
 65695 &:= ((6 \times ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9) - (5)) \\
 65697 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) + ((F(F(6)) + F((F(9) - F(7))))) \\
 65706 &:= (-6) \times (-5) - F((F(7) + F(06)))) \\
 65712 &:= (-6) \times ((-5) - F(F((7 + 1))) - F(2)) \\
 65716 &:= ((F(6) \times 5) + (F(F((7 + 1))) \times 6)) \\
 65718 &:= (-6) \times (((5 - F(7)) + 1) - F(F(8))) \\
 65724 &:= (-6) \times ((5 - F(7)) - F(F((2 \times 4)))) \\
 65736 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((-5) + F(7)) + F(3)) \times 6) \\
 65746 &:= 6 \times 5 \times 7 + 4^{F(6)} \\
 65748 &:= (-6) \times (((5 - F(7)) - (4)) - F(F(8))) \\
 65754 &:= (6 \times (F(F((-5) + F(7)))) + F((5 + F(F(4))))) \\
 65765 &:= ((6 \times F(F((-5) + F(7)))) + (F((6 + 5)))) \\
 65766 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F((-5) + F(7))) - (6)) \times 6) \\
 65768 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times 5) - (F(7))) + (6 \times F(F(8))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65776 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5) \times ((F(7) + (7)) + F(F(F(6))))) \\
 65782 &:= ((-6) \times ((-5) - F(7)) - F(F(8))) - 2) \\
 65783 &:= ((-6) \times ((-5) - F(7)) - F(F(8))) - F(F(3)) \\
 65784 &:= (6 \times ((F((-5) + F(7))) + F(F(8))) - F(4)) \\
 65796 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (5 \times (F(7) - 9))) \times 6) \\
 65826 &:= (((F(F(6)) + (5)) + F(F(8))) - F(2)) \times 6) \\
 65831 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5) \times (F(F(8)) + (31))) \\
 65832 &:= (((F(F(6)) + (5)) + F(F(8))) \times (3 \times 2)) \\
 65838 &:= (-6) \times (((-5) - F(F(8))) - F(F(3))) - (F(8))) \\
 65846 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (5 \times (F(F(8)) + F((F(4) + (6))))) \\
 65862 &:= (-6) \times ((5 - F(F(8))) - (6^2)) \\
 65868 &:= (-6) \times ((-5) - F(F(8))) - (6 + F(8))) \\
 65874 &:= (-6) \times ((-5) - F(F(8))) - (7 \times 4)) \\
 65886 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5) \times ((F(F(8)) + (F(8))) + F(F(6)))) \\
 65887 &:= ((-6) \times (5 - F(F(8)))) + (8 + F(F(7))) \\
 65892 &:= (65 - 8) \times F(9)^2 \\
 65896 &:= ((F(F(6)) - (5)) + ((F(F(8)) + F(9)) \times 6)) \\
 65897 &:= ((-6) \times ((-5) - F(F(8))) - F(9)) - (F(7)) \\
 65898 &:= (-6) \times ((5 - F(F(8))) - (F(9) + 8)) \\
 65916 &:= (((F(6) \times 5) + F(F((9 - 1)))) \times 6) \\
 65946 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (5 \times 9)) \times (-F(F(4)) - F(6))) \\
 65964 &:= (6 \times ((5 \times 9) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(4)) \\
 66036 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (60)) \times (-F(3) - F(6))) \\
 66048 &:= (-6) \times ((-60) - F(F(4))) - F(F(8)) \\
 66078 &:= (-6) \times (-((60 + 7)) - F(F(8))) \\
 66129 &:= (F((F(6) + F(6))) \times (-1) - (-2) \times F(9)) \\
 66146 &:= (F((F(6) + (6 + 1))) + (4^{F(6)})) \\
 66150 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \times 150) \\
 66162 &:= (6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((1 + F(6))^2)) \\
 66168 &:= (-6) \times ((-61) - F(F(6))) - F(F(8)) \\
 66186 &:= (6 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((1 - 86))) \\
 66210 &:= (6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F((F(2) + 10)))) \\
 66274 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 2) + F((F(7) + F(F(4))))) \\
 66278 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (F((2 + F(7))) - 8)) \\
 66286 &:= ((6 \times F(F((6 + 2)))) + F((F(8) - (6)))) \\
 66287 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (F(2) + F((8 + 7)))) \\
 66294 &:= (6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(2) + (F(9) \times F(4)))) \\
 66306 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (30 \times F(F(6)))) \\
 66336 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F((F(6) + F(3))) \times F(3)) \times 6) \\
 66372 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (3 \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 66373** := ((F(F(F(6))) × 6) + ((3 × F(F(7))) - F(3)))
66374 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 6) - ((F(F(3)) - (F(F(7)) × F(4))))
66378 := (-6) × ((-(6 + 3) × F(7)) - F(F(8)))
66386 := (F(F(F(6))) - (((F(F(6))³) - (F(8))) × (-6)))
66388 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 6) + (F((3 + 8) × 8))
66389 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 6) - ((F(F(3)) - ((F(8) × F(9))))))
66393 := ((6 × (F(F(F(6))) - F(3))) + ((9³)))
66396 := (6 × (F(F(F(6))) + (3 × (F(9) + (6))))
66414 := (6 × (F(F(F(6))) + (41 × F(4)))
66444 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 6) + (F(4) × (4⁴)))
66468 := (6 × (((F(F(6)) + F(F(F(4)))) × 6) + F(F(8))))
66489 := (F((F(6) + F(6))) - (-((4⁸) + F(9)))
66491 := ((6 × (F(F(F(6))) + (4 × F(9)))) - 1)
66492 := (6 × (F(F(F(6))) + ((4 × F(9)) × F(2))))
66493 := ((6 × (F(F(F(6))) + (4 × F(9)))) + F(F(3)))
66494 := ((6 × (F(F(F(6))) + (4 × F(9)))) + F(F(4)))
66498 := (6 + (-6) × ((-4) × F(9)) - F(F(8)))
66528 := (F(F(6)) × (6 × 528))
66558 := (((-F(F(6))) - F(F(F(6)))) × 5) + F((5 + F(8)))
66564 := (((F(6) × 6) - 5) × 6)^{F(F(4))}
66565 := (((F(F(F(6))) - (6⁵)) × F(F(6))) - 5)
66576 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (6 + F((5 + 7)))) × 6)
66629 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 6) + (F((F(6) × 2)) - F(9)))
66636 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(6) × (F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) × 6)
66638 := ((6 × (F(F(6)) + (F(F(6))³))) + F(F(8)))
66642 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 6) - ((F(F(6)) - (F((4²))))))
66648 := (6 × (F(F(F(6))) + ((6⁴)/8))
66654 := (F(F(6)) × (F(F(F(6))) - ((6⁵) - 4)))
66662 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 6) + (F((F(6) + F(6)) - F(2)))
66663 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 6) + (F((F(6) × (6/3))))
66664 := (((F(F(F(6))) × 6) + (F((F(6) + F(6)))) + F(F(F(4))))
66666 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (-F((6 + 6)) - F(F(6)))) × 6)
66678 := (-6) × ((66 - F(F(7))) - F(F(8)))
66682 := ((-6) × ((-F(6)) × F(F(6))) - F(F(8))) - 2)
66683 := ((-6) × ((-F(6)) × F(F(6))) - F(F(8))) - F(F(3))
66684 := (((F(F(F(6))) × 6) + (F(F(6)))) + F((8 × F(F(4))))
66726 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (6 + (F(7)²))) × 6)
66728 := (F(6) × ((F((6 + F(7))) × 2) - (F(8))))
66738 := (-6) × (-((F(6) + (F(7)^{F(3)}))) - F(F(8)))
66744 := (6 × (F(F(F(6))) + (F((7 + 4) × F(F(4))))))
66768 := ((-F(6)) + F((6 + F(7))) × (F(6) + 8))
66784 := ((F(6) + F(6)) × (-7) + F((F(8) - F(F(4))))
66786 := (((F(6) × (-6)) + F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) × 6)
66792 := (F(6) × (F(F(F(6))) - (F(7) + F((9 × 2))))
66832 := (F(6) × (-F(6)) + (F((F(8) - F(3))) × 2))
66848 := (F(6) × ((-6) - F((F(8) - F(4)))) + F(F(8)))
66863 := (((6⁶) + F(F(8))) + (F(F(6))³))
66875 := -((F(F(6)) - (F(6) × (F(F(8)) - F((F(7) + (5))))))
66877 := ((-6) × ((-6) - F(F(8))) - F(F(7))) - F(F(7))
66896 := ((F(6) + F(6)) × F((F(8) - F((9 - 6))))
66927 := (F(F(6)) × ((F((F(6) + 9)) × 2) - (7))
66936 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (-6) × (-F(9)) - F(F(3)))) × 6)
66948 := (-6) × ((F(F(6)) - (F((9 + 4))) - F(F(8)))
66972 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 6) - (-9) × F((F(7) - F(2))))
66976 := ((F((-6) + F(F(6)))) + F(9)) × (F(7) × F(6))
66978 := (-6) × (((-6) × F(9)) - F(7)) - F(F(8))
67062 := (6 × ((F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) - 2))
67066 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) × 06) - F(6))
67067 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) × 06) - 7)
67074 := ((6 × 7) × F((F(07) + (4))))
67087 := ((6 × (F(F(7)) + F(F(08)))) + (F(7)))
67116 := (67 + 1) × F(16)
67144 := ((F(F(6)) - ((7¹⁺⁴))) × (-4))
67176 := ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(7)) + 17))) × 6)
67184 := 6 × F(7) × F(18) / F(4)
67188 := (-6) × (-((F(7) - 1) × F(8))) - F(F(8))
67273 := ((F(F(F(6))) × F(7)) - (F((-((2 - 7))^{F(3)})))
67278 := (-6) × ((-F((7 + 2))) - F(F(7))) - F(F(8))
67280 := (((F(F(F(6))) / F(7)) - F(2)) × 80)
67335 := ((67^{F(3)}) × (3 × 5))
67337 := (((F(6) + (7)) + F(3))^{F(3)} × F(F(7)))
67347 := (F(F(6)) × (F(7) - (-F(3)) × F((4 + F(7))))
67363 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 7) + (F(3) - (F(F(6))³)))
67364 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 7) - (-3) + (F(F(6))^{F(4)}))
67392 := (F(6) × ((F(F(7)) + F(F(3))) × (F(9) + 2))
67468 := -((F(F(F(6))) - (7 × ((F(F(4))^{F(6)}) + F(F(8))))
67565 := (F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(7)) × (-((-5) + F(6))⁵)))
67666 := ((F(6) × F(F(7))) + ((-F(F(6))) - F(F(F(6)))) × (-6))
67710 := ((-6) - F((F(7) + (7)))) × (-10))

$$\begin{aligned}
 67712 &:= F(6) \times (F(7) \times 7 + 1)^2 \\
 67739 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 7) - (F((F(7) + 3)) \times 9)) \\
 67772 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - ((-F(7)) - F(F(7))) \times (F(F(7)) - 2)) \\
 67840 &:= ((F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times (-8 \times 40)) \\
 67847 &:= (((F(F(6)) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8))/F(F(4)))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 67873 &:= ((6 \times F((F(7) + 8))) + ((F(7)^3)) \\
 67938 &:= (6 \times (F((7 \times F((9/3)))) + F(F(8))) \\
 67977 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((F(F(7)) + (9 + 7)) \times F(7))) \\
 67986 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (7 \times (F(9) + F(8)))) \times 6) \\
 68229 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((F(8) - 2)^2) \times 9)) \\
 68247 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(24) - F(7)))) \\
 68248 &:= (((6 - F(F(8))) \times (-2)) + F((F(4) \times 8))) \\
 68252 &:= ((-F(6)) - F((F(8) - F(2)))) + F((5^2)) \\
 68254 &:= ((-6) - F((F(8) - F(2)))) + F((5^{F(F(4))})) \\
 68274 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (((F((F(8) + 2)) + (7)) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 68286 &:= (((-6) + (F(8)^2)) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 68316 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (((F(8)^{F(3)}) - 1))) \times 6) \\
 68322 &:= (6 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(F((3 \times 2))^2))) \\
 68328 &:= (-6) \times (-(((F(8)^{F(3)}) + F(2))) - F(F(8))) \\
 68346 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(8)^{F(3)}) + (4))) \times 6) \\
 68376 &:= (6 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(3) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6)))) \\
 68397 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((F(8) \times F((3 + 9))) + F(F(7)))) \\
 68467 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times F((8 \times F(F(4)))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 68471 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(F(4)) \times F(F(7)))) - 1) \\
 68472 &:= (-6) \times (((F(F(8))/F(F(4))) + F(F(7))) \times (-2)) \\
 68473 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(F(4)) \times F(F(7)))) + F(F(3))) \\
 68474 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(F(4)) \times F(F(7)))) + F(F(4))) \\
 68537 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (-F(8)) \times F((5 \times F(3)))) \times 7) \\
 68544 &:= ((-6) \times F(8)) \times (-544) \\
 68546 &:= (((6 \times 8) \times 5)^{F(F(4))} + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 68644 &:= ((6 + ((8 \times F(6)) \times 4))^{F(F(4))} \\
 68670 &:= ((-6) + F((8 + F(6)))) \times 70) \\
 68748 &:= (-6) \times (-((8^{7-4}) - F(F(8)))) \\
 68763 &:= ((6 \times F(F(8))) + (7 \times (F(F(6))^{F(3)})) \\
 68796 &:= 6 \times F(8) \times F(7) \times (F(9) + F(6)) \\
 68913 &:= -F(6) + (8 + F(9) - 1)^3 \\
 68947 &:= -((F(F(6)) - ((8 \times (F(9) + F(4))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 68973 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - (F(-((F(8) - F(9)))) \times (7^3))) \\
 68978 &:= ((6 + 8) \times (F(9) + (F(F(7)) \times F(8)))) \\
 69336 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + F((9 + 3) + 3)) \times 6) \\
 69344 &:= ((F(F(6)) - F((F(9)/F(3)))) \times (-44)) \\
 69552 &:= ((F(F(F(6)))/(-F(F((9 - 5)))) + F((5^2))) \\
 69579 &:= ((F(F(6)) + (F(9) \times (5 - F(F(7)))) \times (-9)) \\
 69626 &:= -6 + F(9) \times F(6) \times 2^{F(6)} \\
 69632 &:= (((F(6) \times F(9)) \times F(6)) \times 32) \\
 69638 &:= 6 + F(9) \times F(6) \times F(3)^8 \\
 69667 &:= ((F(F(6)) + (((F(9) \times F(6)) + (6)))) \times F(F(7))) \\
 69696 &:= (F(6) \times F(9) - F(6))^{F(9-6)} \\
 69727 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F((9 + 7)) - 2)) \times 7) \\
 69768 &:= (F((F(F(6)) - F((-9) + F(7)))) \times (6 + F(8))) \\
 69836 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 9) - (F((F(8) + F(3))) + F(F(6)))) \\
 69846 &:= (-6) \times ((F(9) - F(F(8))) - ((F(4)^6))) \\
 69857 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 9) - (F((F(8) - ((5 - 7)))))) \\
 69863 &:= ((6 - (-9) \times F(F(8))) - F((F(F(6)) + F(3)))) \\
 69875 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(9) - F(8)) \times F(F(7)))) \times 5) \\
 69938 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times F(9)) + F(9))^{F(3)})/8) \\
 69961 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - ((F(9) - (9^{6-1}))) \\
 69972 &:= (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(9) \times 7^2 \\
 69984 &:= 6 \times 9 \times 9 \times F(8 + 4) \\
 69995 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((9 - 9) + 9)^5) \\
 70844 &:= (F((F(((7 \times 0) + 8)) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 4) \\
 71065 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((F(10) + (6)) \times 5)) \\
 71084 &:= (-F(7)) \times ((10 - F(F(8)))/F(F(4))) \\
 71162 &:= (F(7) \times (((1 + 1) + F(F(F(6))))/2)) \\
 71382 &:= (F(F(7)) - ((13 \times F(F(8)))/(-2)) \\
 71442 &:= (((F((F(7) + 1)) + F(F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))})/2) \\
 71568 &:= (71 \times (F((-5) + F(F(6)))) + (F(8))) \\
 71736 &:= (7 \times ((1 - (F(F(7)) \times 3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 71764 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((1 + 76) \times 4)) \\
 71824 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (F((1 + 8)) + F(2)))^{F(F(4))} \\
 71997 &:= ((F((F(7) + 1)) - ((F(9) + F(9)))) \times F(F(7))) \\
 72384 &:= ((F((7 \times 2)) \times 3) \times (8^{F(F(4))})) \\
 72666 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) - (6))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 72696 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (-((2 - (6 \times 9)) \times 6)) \\
 72893 &:= -7 + (-2 + 8 \times F(9))^{F(3)} \\
 72929 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (-2) - ((F(9) + F(2)) \times (-9))) \\
 72934 &:= -((F(F(7)) + (-((29^3)) \times F(4))) \\
 72946 &:= (((F(F(7)) - 2) \times (-9)) + F((4 + F(F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 73162 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (316 - 2)) \\
 73284 &:= ((F((F(7) + F(3))) + F((F(2) + F(8)))) \times 4) \\
 73367 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-F(3))) + F(F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 73395 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 3) \times F(F(-(3 - 9)))) \times 5) \\
 73628 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (((3 \times 6)^2) - 8)) \\
 73648 &:= ((-F((7 + 3))) + (F(F(6))^{F(4)})) \times 8) \\
 73674 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((-F(3)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(7)))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 73719 &:= (((F(F((7 - 3)))^{F(7)}) - 1) \times 9) \\
 73728 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((3 + 7))) \times (2^8)) \\
 73739 &:= -7 + (F(3)^{F(7)} + F(3)) \times 9 \\
 73769 &:= -F(7) + (F(3)^{F(7)} + 6) \times 9 \\
 73791 &:= ((-7) - (F(3)^{F(7)})) \times (-9 \times 1)) \\
 73792 &:= (7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times 9 + F(2) \\
 73793 &:= (7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times 9 + F(3) \\
 73794 &:= (7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times 9 + F(4) \\
 73861 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((F(3)^8) + (61))) \\
 73878 &:= (-((7^3) \times 8)) - (-7) \times F(F(8))) \\
 73963 &:= -7 \times 3 + (F(9) \times F(6))^{F(3)} \\
 73972 &:= ((F((7 - 3))^9) + (F(F(7))^2)) \\
 73982 &:= -((F(F((7 - 3))) - (((F(9) \times 8)^2)))) \\
 73983 &:= -((F(F(F((7 - 3)))) - ((F(9) \times 8)^{F(3)})) \\
 73984 &:= ((F(F(7)) + 39)^{8/4}) \\
 74325 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-F(4))) - F(F(3))) + F(25)) \\
 74326 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(4))) + F(((F(3) + 2) + F(F(6)))) \\
 74327 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (43 \times 2)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 74379 &:= 7 \times F(4) + 3^7 \times F(9) \\
 74382 &:= ((7 + 4) \times (-3) + F((F(8) - F(2)))) \\
 74386 &:= ((F(7) \times (F(4) + (3^8))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 74397 &:= (((F(7)^{F(4)} - F(3)) \times F(9)) - F(F(7))) \\
 74415 &:= (7 + 4) \times F(4 \times 1 \times 5) \\
 74426 &:= ((7 + 4) \times (F(F(F(4))) + F((-F(2)) + F(F(6)))) \\
 74431 &:= (((7^{F(F(4))})^{F(F(4))}) \times 31) \\
 74439 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))}) + ((3^9))) \\
 74448 &:= ((7 + 4) \times (F(4) + F(-(F(F(F(4))) - (F(8)))))) \\
 74453 &:= ((F(7) \times (-44)) + F((5^{F(3)}))) \\
 74480 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 4) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 80) \\
 74487 &:= (((F((F(7) + F(F(4))))/F(F(4))) - F(F(8))) \times (-7)) \\
 74493 &:= (((7^4) + F(F(4))) \times (F(9) - 3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74528 &:= (((F(7)^{F(4)} - 5) \times F((F(2) + 8))) \\
 74529 &:= (((F(7) \times (F(F(4)) + 5))^2) \times 9) \\
 74538 &:= -((((F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) - F((5^{F(3)}))) + (F(8)))) \\
 74554 &:= (-((((F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) + 5)) + F((5^{F(F(4))}))) \\
 74557 &:= -((((F(F(7)) + F(F(4))) - (F((5 \times 5)))) + F(F(7)))) \\
 74559 &:= (-((F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)))) + F((5^{F(F(-5+9))})) \\
 74564 &:= (-((((F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) - 5)) + F((F(F(6)) + 4))) \\
 74584 &:= (F(((7 - F(F(4))) \times 5)) - ((F(8)^{F(F(4))})) \\
 74644 &:= -((((F((7 \times F(F(4)))) - F((F(F(6)) + 4))) + 4)) \\
 74646 &:= ((7 + 4) \times (F((F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F(F(6)))) \\
 74648 &:= -((F(-(7 \times (4 - 6))) - F((4 + F(8)))) \\
 74654 &:= -((((F((7 \times F(F(4)))) - 6) - F((5^{F(F(4))}))) \\
 74659 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6))))/(-5)) \times F(9))) \\
 74665 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(4))^6) + F(F(6))) \times 5) \\
 74666 &:= ((-F(F(7)) + F((4 + F(F(6)))) + (-6) \times F(F(6))) \\
 74673 &:= (F((F(7) - F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(F(6)) \times F(7))^{F(3)})) \\
 74676 &:= (((F(7)^{F(F(4))}) \times F(F(6)) + 7) \times F(F(6))) \\
 74682 &:= -((7^{F(4)}) + F(((6 + F(8)) - 2))) \\
 74688 &:= (((F(7) + F((-4) + F(F(6)))) - F(F(8))) \times (-8)) \\
 74694 &:= F(7)^{-F(4)+6} \times F(9) - 4 \\
 74696 &:= ((-F(F(7)) + F((4 + F(F(6)))) - (96)) \\
 74698 &:= F(7)^{F(4)} \times F(6) \times F(9)/8 \\
 74732 &:= (F((F(7) - 4)) \times ((F(7)^3) + F(2))) \\
 74739 &:= (7 + ((F(F(F(4))) + ((F(7)^3)) \times F(9))) \\
 74752 &:= -F(7) \times F(4) \times 7 + F(5^2) \\
 74753 &:= ((-((F(7) \times F(4))) - F(F(7))) + F((5^{F(3)}))) \\
 74762 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(7) \times F(F(6)))^2)) \\
 74763 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(7) \times F(F(6)))^{F(3)})) \\
 74764 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(F(4))) + ((F(7) \times F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 74774 &:= (((-F(7) - F(F(4))) + F(F(7))) \times (7^{F(4)})) \\
 74784 &:= ((-F(F(7)) - F(F(F(4)))) - (7 - F((F(8) + 4)))) \\
 74786 &:= -((((F(F(7)) - F((4 + F(7)) + 8)) + 6)) \\
 74788 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(F(4))) + (F(7) \times F(8)))) + F(F(8))) \\
 74789 &:= -((((F(F(7)) + F(4)) - F(((F(7) + F(8)) - 9))) \\
 74791 &:= -((((F(F(7)) - F(((F(4) + F(7)) + 9))) + 1)) \\
 74792 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F(((F(4) + F(7)) + 9))) \times (-F(2))) \\
 74793 &:= -((((F(F(7)) - F(((F(4) + F(7)) + 9))) - F(F(3)))) \\
 74794 &:= -((((F(F(7)) - F(F(4))) - F(((F(7) + 9) + F(4)))) \\
 74795 &:= (F(7) + F(4)^7) \times F(9) - 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74796 &:= (-((F(F(7)) - (4))) + F(((F(7) - 9) + F(F(6)))))) \\
 74798 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F((F(F(4)) \times 7) - 9)) - F(F(8))) \\
 74799 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(4)))) - (F(F(7)) - F((F(9) - 9)))) \\
 74826 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - F((4 + F(8)))) - F((F(2) + F(6)))))) \\
 74844 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 4) - 8) \times (F(4)^4)) \\
 74847 &:= ((F((F(7) - F(4))) + F((F(8) + (4)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 74848 &:= -((((F(7)^{F(4)}) + 8) - F((4 + F(8)))))) \\
 74855 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (((F(4) \times F(8)) + F((5 \times 5)))))) \\
 74857 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - F((4 + F(8)))) - (5 \times F(7)))) \\
 74864 &:= ((-7) \times (F(F(4)) + (F(8)))) + F((F(F(6)) + (4))) \\
 74865 &:= (7 \times ((-((F(F(4))^8)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (5))) \\
 74867 &:= (-F(7)) \times ((F(F(4)) + (F(8) \times F(F(6)))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 74872 &:= 7^{F(4)} + (F(8) \times F(7))^2 \\
 74874 &:= ((-7) + F((4 + F(8)))) - F((F(7) - F(F(F(4)))))) \\
 74878 &:= F(-7 + 4 \times 8) - 7 \times F(8) \\
 74886 &:= ((-F(7)) + F((4 + F(8)))) + (F(8) \times (-6)) \\
 74894 &:= ((F(7) + F((4 + F(8)))) - F((9 + F(4)))) \\
 74899 &:= ((7 \times (F(4) - F(8))) + F((F(9) - 9))) \\
 74929 &:= ((F(7)^4) + F(((F(9) - F(2)) - 9))) \\
 74936 &:= (-7 + 4 \times 9) \times F(3 \times 6) \\
 74938 &:= F(7)^4 + 9 + F(3 \times 8) \\
 74944 &:= (F(((F(7) + F(4)) + 9)) - ((F(4)^4))) \\
 74945 &:= (-F(7)) \times ((F(4) - (F(9)^{F(4)})) \times 5) \\
 74946 &:= (((74 - F(9))^{F(4)}) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 74948 &:= ((-7) \times (F(F(4)) + 9)) + F((4 + F(8))) \\
 74952 &:= -F(7) \times F(4) - F(9) + F(5^2) \\
 74953 &:= (((7 + F(F(F(4)))) \times (-9)) + F((5^{F(3)}))) \\
 74955 &:= ((-7) \times (F(F(F(4)) + 9)) + (F((5 \times 5)))) \\
 74956 &:= (7 \times (-((F((4 + 9)) + (5))) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 74963 &:= (((F(7)^4) + F(9)) + F((F(6) \times 3))) \\
 74964 &:= (((F(7) \times (-4)) - 9) + F((F(F(6)) + (4)))) \\
 74973 &:= ((F(7) \times (-4)) + F(((9 + F(7)) + 3))) \\
 74976 &:= (-((7^{F(4)})) + F(((9) + F(7)) + F(F(6)))) \\
 74977 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(4))) - F((F(9) - F(7)))) \times (-7)) \\
 74978 &:= (-F(7)) + ((F(F(4)) - 9) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 74983 &:= (F(((F(7) + F(4)) + 9)) - (F(8) \times F(3))) \\
 74984 &:= ((-7) \times F(F(F(4)))) - (F(9) - F((F(8) + (4)))) \\
 74985 &:= (F(((F(7) + F(4)) + 9)) - (8 \times 5)) \\
 74986 &:= (-((F(7) \times F(4))) + F(((9 + 8) + F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74991 &:= (F(((F(7) + F(4)) + 9)) - F((9 \times 1))) \\
 74992 &:= F(F(7) + F(4) + 9) - F(9) + F(2) \\
 74993 &:= F(F(7) + F(4) + 9) - F(9) + F(3) \\
 74994 &:= F(F(7) + F(4) + 9) - F(9) + F(4) \\
 74996 &:= (F(7)^{F(4)} + 9) \times F(9) - F(6) \\
 74997 &:= -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7) \\
 74998 &:= ((-7) + F(F(F(4)))) + ((F((F(9) - 9)) - (F(8)))) \\
 74999 &:= (-((F(7) + (4 + 9))) + F((F(9) - 9))) \\
 75012 &:= -F(7) + F((5 \times 01)^2) \\
 75018 &:= (-7) + F(((5 - 01) + F(8))) \\
 75025 &:= F(7 \times 5 \times 0 + 25) \\
 75026 &:= -7 + F(5^{02}) + F(6) \\
 75029 &:= F(7) + F(5^{02}) - 9 \\
 75031 &:= ((7 + F((5^{F(03)}))) - 1) \\
 75032 &:= 7 + F(5^{0 \times 3 + 2}) \\
 75033 &:= ((7 + F((5^{F(03)}))) + F(F(3))) \\
 75034 &:= ((7 + F((5^{F(03)}))) + F(F(4))) \\
 75038 &:= F(7) + F(5 \times (-03 + 8)) \\
 75046 &:= (F((75/F(04))) + F(F(6))) \\
 75169 &:= F(7 + 5) + F(16 + 9) \\
 75229 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) - (29)))) \\
 75236 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) - F(F(3))) - F(F(6))) \\
 75237 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) - ((3 \times 7)))) \\
 75238 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) + F(F(3))) - (F(8))) \\
 75242 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) - ((4^2)))) \\
 75245 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) - F((F(F(4)) + (5)))) \\
 75246 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((F((5^2)) - (4)) - F(6)))) \\
 75247 &:= (F(F(7)) + (F((5^2)) - (4 + 7))) \\
 75248 &:= ((F(F(7)) - (5 \times 2)) + F((4 + F(8)))) \\
 75249 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((5^{-2+4}))) - 9) \\
 75252 &:= (F(F(7)) - ((5 + F(2)) - F((5^2)))) \\
 75253 &:= ((F(F(7)) - (5)) + F(((F(2) \times 5)^{F(3)})) \\
 75254 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(((5 \times F(2)) \times 5))) - (4)) \\
 75255 &:= (F(F(7)) - ((5 - 2) - F((5 \times 5)))) \\
 75256 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) - F((-5) + F(6))) \\
 75257 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) - F(-(5 - 7))) \\
 75258 &:= (F(F(7)) + (F((5 \times ((2 - 5) + 8)))) \\
 75259 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) + F(F(F(-(5 - 9)))) \\
 75262 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) + (6 - 2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 75263 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) + F(6)) - 3)) \\
 75264 &:= ((F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) + F(6)))) - F(F(4))) \\
 75265 &:= ((7 + F((5^2))) + F((F(6) + (5)))) \\
 75266 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((-5) \times (F(2) - (6)))) + F(6)) \\
 75271 &:= (F(F(7)) - ((F((5^2)) + F(7)) \times (-1))) \\
 75272 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) + (7 \times 2))) \\
 75273 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) + F(7)) + F(3))) \\
 75274 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((F((5^2)) + F(7)) + F(4)))) \\
 75276 &:= ((F(7) + (5)) \times (F(2) + F((F(7) + (6)))))) \\
 75279 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) - F(7)) + F(9))) \\
 75291 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((F((5^2)) + F(9)) - 1))) \\
 75292 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) + F(9)) \times F(2))) \\
 75293 &:= ((F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) + F(9)))) + F(F(3))) \\
 75294 &:= (F(F(7)) + (F((5^2)) + (9 \times 4))) \\
 75347 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((5^{F(3)}))) + F((4 + 7))) \\
 75348 &:= ((-F(7)) \times F(((5 + 3) \times F(4)))) / (-8)) \\
 75366 &:= ((F(7) + (5)) \times (F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + 6)) \\
 75376 &:= (7 \times ((F((5 \times F(3))) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 75392 &:= (-F(F(7))) + ((5 \times F((F(F(3)) + 9)))^2) \\
 75394 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((5^{F(3)}))) + (F(9) \times 4)) \\
 75395 &:= ((-7) + F((5^{F(3)}))) + (F((9 + 5))) \\
 75457 &:= ((7 \times F(F((5 + F(4)))))) - (5 \times F(F(7)))) \\
 75465 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-5)) + (4)) \times (-65)) \\
 75466 &:= (F((75/F(4))) + (F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 75492 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (((5 + 4) + 9)^2)) \\
 75546 &:= ((F((F(7) + (5))) \times (5^{F(F(4))})) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 75625 &:= 75 \times F(6) + F(25) \\
 75627 &:= -((F(7) - (F((5 \times 6)) / (-2) + F(7)))) \\
 75628 &:= (-7) + (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F((-2) + F(8)))))) \\
 75632 &:= (7 + ((5 \times F((F(6) + F(3))))^2)) \\
 75635 &:= ((F(F((F(7) - (5)))) + F((F(F(6)) - F(3)))) \times 5) \\
 75636 &:= ((F(7) + (5)) \times (F(F(6)) + F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))))) \\
 75645 &:= (((F((7 + 5)) - F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))}) \times 5) \\
 75647 &:= 7 + F(5 \times 6) / (4 + 7) \\
 75648 &:= ((7 \times F((5 + 6))) + F((4 + F(8)))) \\
 75649 &:= (7 \times ((5 + F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(4) + 9)))) \\
 75725 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (((5 \times F(7)) \times F(2)) \times 5)) \\
 75735 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (5 \times F(7))) + F(3)) \times 5) \\
 75745 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (5 \times F(7))) + (4)) \times 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 75759 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times ((5 \times F(7)) \times 5)) + F(9)) \\
 75765 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (5 \times F(7))) + F(6)) \times 5) \\
 75866 &:= ((7 \times ((-5) \times F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(6)))) \\
 75884 &:= ((-7) \times ((5 \times F(8)) - F(F(8)))) - F(4) \\
 75887 &:= (-7) \times ((5 \times F(8)) - F((8 + F(7)))) \\
 75936 &:= (7 \times (-((5 + 93)) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 75957 &:= ((F(F((F(7) - (5)))) - (95)) \times 7) \\
 75978 &:= (-7) \times (-((5 - 97)) - F(F(8))) \\
 76076 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((0 - F(7)) \times 6))) \\
 76139 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (1 + (F(3) \times F(9)))))) \\
 76146 &:= (7 \times (-((F((F(6) + 1)) \times F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 76167 &:= (((F(7) \times (6 - 1)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76174 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((1 + 7)^{F(F(4))})) \\
 76179 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (-1 - (F(7) \times F(9)))) \\
 76182 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (1 - (F(8)^2))) \\
 76188 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 1)) - (F(8) \times F(8))) \\
 76237 &:= (-7) \times (F((F(6) + 2)) - (F((3 \times 7)))) \\
 76244 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (2 \times (F(4)^{F(4)}))) \\
 76245 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F(-((F(2) + (F(4) \times (-5)))))) \\
 76247 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + 2) - F((F(F(4)) \times 7))) \\
 76248 &:= ((-F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(2) - (4^8)) \\
 76251 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (2 + 51))) \\
 76258 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (2 \times (5 + F(8)))) \\
 76259 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 2)) - (F((5 + 9)))) \\
 76272 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(2) + ((7^2)))) \\
 76279 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F((2 \times 7)) - F(9))) \\
 76286 &:= (-7) \times (((F(F(6)) \times 2) - F(F(8))) + (6)) \\
 76311 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - 311) \\
 76328 &:= (-7) \times ((F(F(6)) \times F(3)) - F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \\
 76334 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(3) \times F((3 \times 4)))) \\
 76342 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(3) - 42))) \\
 76347 &:= (-F(F(7))) + ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(3) + (4))) \times 7) \\
 76349 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (3 + (4 \times 9)))) \\
 76356 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((F(3)^5) + (6)))) \\
 76357 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(3)^5) + F(F(7)))) \\
 76358 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((3^5) + F(8))) \\
 76363 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(3)^{F(6)}) + 3)) \\
 76364 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(3)^{F(6)}) + F(F(4)))) \\
 76365 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 36)) - (5)) \\
 76366 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(-((3 - 6)))^{F(6)}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76367 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))) + F(F(7)))))) \\
 76368 &:= -(((F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) - ((F(F(3)) + (6) \times F(F(8)))))) \\
 76373 &:= (-F(F(7))) + (((F(F(F(6))) - F(3)) \times 7) - F(3)) \\
 76374 &:= (-F(F(7))) + (((F(F(F(6))) - F(3)) \times 7) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 76376 &:= (-F(F(7))) + (((F(F(F(6))) - 3) \times 7) + F(6)) \\
 76377 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(3)) - F(F(7))) - (F(7)))) \\
 76378 &:= -(((F(F(7)) + (F(6) + 3)) + (-7) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 76379 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((3^7)/9)) \\
 76382 &:= ((-7) \times (F((6 + 3)) - F(F(8)))) - 2 \\
 76383 &:= ((-7) \times (F((6 + 3)) - F(F(8)))) - F(F(3)) \\
 76384 &:= (-7) \times (((6^{F(3)}) - F(F(8))) - F(F(4))) \\
 76386 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (3 + F((F(8) - F(6)))) \\
 76387 &:= (-((F((7 + 6)) + F(3))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-7))) \\
 76388 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(3)) + F((-8) + F(8)))) \\
 76389 &:= -((F(F(7)) - ((-63) \times F(F(8)))/(-9))) \\
 76391 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(3) - F(9)) - 1))) \\
 76392 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (-3 + F(F((9 - 2)))) \\
 76393 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(3)) - F(9)))) + F(3)) \\
 76394 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(3)) - F(9)))) + F(4)) \\
 76396 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3)))) - F((F(9) - F(F(6)))) \\
 76397 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(3)) - 9) + F(F(7)))) \\
 76398 &:= (F(7) \times F(6) + 3) \times F(9) \times F(8) \\
 76399 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (3 \times 9))) - F(9)) \\
 76416 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) \times 41)) - F(6)) \\
 76417 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) \times 41)) - (7)) \\
 76419 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (-((4 + 1)) + F(9)))) \\
 76423 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + F((4 + F(2^3)))) \\
 76424 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (((6 \times F(4))^2) + (4))) \\
 76425 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 6) + F(F(4))) + F(25)) \\
 76426 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (-4) \times (F(2) - F(6)))) \\
 76432 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(4)^3))) - F(2)) \\
 76433 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(4) \times (3 \times 3)))) \\
 76434 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(4)^3))) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 76447 &:= (-7) \times ((F(F(6)) + (4)) - F((F(4) \times 7))) \\
 76450 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (6^4)) \times 50) \\
 76453 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F((F(F(4)) + (5)))^{F(3)})) \\
 76454 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((4 \times 5) + 4)) \\
 76457 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(4))) - F((5 + 7))) \\
 76459 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) - (5 \times F(9))) \\
 76461 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((4 \times 6) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76462 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))) + F(2)) \\
 76463 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))) + F(3)) \\
 76464 &:= (7 \times F(6) + F(4)) \times 6^4 \\
 76467 &:= (F(7) + ((F(F(F(6))) - (4 \times 6)) \times 7)) \\
 76468 &:= (((7 - F(F(6))) + (4^{F(6)})) + F(F(8))) \\
 76469 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F((4 + F(6)) + 9)) \\
 76471 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) - F((F(7) - 1))) \\
 76473 &:= ((-7) \times (F(F(6)) - F((F(4) \times 7))) - F(3)) \\
 76474 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(4)) \times 74)) \\
 76475 &:= (-7) \times (F(F(6)) - F(F((4 \times (7 - 5)))) \\
 76476 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(4)))) - (7 \times F(F(6)))) \\
 76478 &:= (((-7) \times F(F(6))) + F(4) - (-7) \times F(F(8))) \\
 76480 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (6)) \times (4 \times 80)) \\
 76481 &:= (F((F(7) + F(6))) + ((4^8) - 1)) \\
 76482 &:= (F((F(7) + F(6))) + (4^{F(8-2)})) \\
 76483 &:= ((F((F(7) + F(6))) + (4^8)) + F(F(3))) \\
 76484 &:= ((F((F(7) + F(6))) + (4^8)) + F(F(4))) \\
 76486 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F((4 + 8)) - F(6))) \\
 76488 &:= ((-7) \times ((6 \times F(4)) - F(F(8))) - 8) \\
 76489 &:= (-7) \times (((6 + 4) - F(F(8)) + 9)) \\
 76493 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(4)) \times 9))) - 3) \\
 76494 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(4))^9)/4)) \\
 76496 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(4) \times (F(9) + F(6)))) \\
 76497 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 4) - (97)) \\
 76499 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6))) - F((F(F(4)) + 9))) - F(9)) \\
 76517 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5 \times F((1 + 7)))) \\
 76518 &:= (((-F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F((5 + 1))) - F(F(8)) \\
 76522 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 \times 2)^2)) \\
 76524 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((5 \times 2) + 4)) \\
 76531 &:= (((-F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times ((5 + 3) - 1)) \\
 76532 &:= (((-F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (5 + F(3))) + F(2)) \\
 76533 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F(((5 + 3) + 3))) \\
 76534 &:= (((-F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (5 + F(3))) + F(4)) \\
 76538 &:= (-7) \times ((6 \times (5 - 3)) - F(F(8))) \\
 76539 &:= (((-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (5 + F(3))) - F(9)) \\
 76542 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5 \times (4^2))) \\
 76545 &:= (7 \times (-((6 + 5)) + F(F((F(4) + (5)))))) \\
 76546 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6))) - F((5 \times F(F(4)))) - (F(F(6)))) \\
 76547 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5 \times (F(F(4)) + (F(7)))) \\
 76549 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5 - (F(F(4)) \times (-F(9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$76551 := ((7 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - (5 + 5)) - 1)$$

$$76552 := (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (5 \times F((5 - 2))))))$$

$$76553 := ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (5 + 5))) + F(F(3)))$$

$$76554 := ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (5 + 5))) + F(F(4)))$$

$$76558 := (-F(7) + ((F(F(6)) \times (5^5)) + F(F(8))))$$

$$76559 := (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((5 - 5) + 9)))$$

$$76562 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 \times 6) \times 2))$$

$$76563 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (56 + 3))$$

$$76564 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (56 + F(F(4))))$$

$$76566 := (-7) \times (F(6) - F(((5 + F(6)) + F(6))))$$

$$76567 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((-5) + F(6) + 7))$$

$$76572 := (-F(7) + (((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 7) - 2))$$

$$76573 := ((-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (5 + F(F((7 - 3))))$$

$$76574 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 + 7) \times 4))$$

$$76575 := (-7) + (((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 7) - (5))$$

$$76578 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 \times F(7)) - F(8)))$$

$$76581 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 \times 8) + 1))$$

$$76582 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5 \times F((8 - 2))))$$

$$76583 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 + 8) \times 3))$$

$$76584 := (((F(7) - 6) \times (-5) + F(F(8)))) - F(4)$$

$$76585 := ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (5))) - F((8 - 5)))$$

$$76586 := ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (5))) - F((8 - 6)))$$

$$76587 := (((7 \times F(F(6))) \times F((5 + F(8)))) / F(F(7)))$$

$$76588 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 + 8) + F(8)))$$

$$76589 := (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(-((5 - 8)))) - F(9))$$

$$76592 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((-5) + F(9) + F(2)))$$

$$76593 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((-5) + F(9) \times F(F(3))))$$

$$76594 := 7 \times (F(6 \times 5 - 9) - 4)$$

$$76597 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5^{9-7}))$$

$$76598 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 \times 9) - F(8)))$$

$$76599 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 + 9) + 9))$$

$$76601 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F(F((6 \times 01))))$$

$$76602 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(6)) - F(02)))$$

$$76603 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(6)) - F(03)))$$

$$76604 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (6 \times F(04)))$$

$$76606 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(6) + F(06))))$$

$$76607 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(6) - (0 - 7)))$$

$$76608 := (-7) \times ((F(6) - 6) - F(F(08)))$$

$$76609 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(6)) - F(09))))$$

$$76611 := (((F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6)))) - 11)$$

$$76612 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((6 - 1) \times 2))$$

$$76613 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((6 \times 1) + 3))$$

$$76614 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((6 \times (1^4))))$$

$$76615 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (6 + (1^5)))$$

$$76616 := ((7 \times F((F(6) + F((6 + 1)))) - (6))$$

$$76617 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (6 - (1^7)))$$

$$76619 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (((6 \times 1) - 9)))$$

$$76620 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F(((6/2) + 0)))$$

$$76621 := (((F(7) - 6) \times F(F((6 + 2)))) - 1)$$

$$76622 := 7 \times F((6 + 6^2)/2)$$

$$76623 := (((F(7) - 6) \times F(F((6 + 2)))) + F(F(3)))$$

$$76624 := (((F(7) - 6) \times F(F((6 + 2)))) + F(F(4)))$$

$$76625 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 + 2) - 5))$$

$$76626 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(6) + ((2 - 6))))$$

$$76627 := ((F(7) - F(6)) + (F(F((6 + 2))) \times 7))$$

$$76628 := (F((F(7) + F(6))) + (-6) \times (-F(2) - F(F(8))))$$

$$76629 := (-7) \times ((F(6) - F(F((6 + 2)))) - 9)$$

$$76630 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F((6 + (3 \times 0))))$$

$$76631 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 + 3) \times 1))$$

$$76632 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6) - 3) \times 2))$$

$$76633 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 + F(3)) + 3))$$

$$76634 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 - 3) \times 4))$$

$$76635 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 \times 3) - 5))$$

$$76636 := (((F(F(7)) \times F((F(6) + F(6)))) / 3) - F(F(6)))$$

$$76637 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((6 - (3 \times 7))))$$

$$76638 := -((F((F(7) + F(6))) + (F(6) \times (-F(3) - F(F(8))))))$$

$$76639 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 + F(3)) + 9))$$

$$76640 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (6 \times F((4 + 0))))$$

$$76641 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 \times F(4)) + 1))$$

$$76642 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 + 4) \times 2))$$

$$76643 := (7 \times (F(F(((6 + 6) - 4)) + 3))$$

$$76644 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (6 + (4 \times 4)))$$

$$76645 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 \times F(4)) + (5)))$$

$$76646 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 - F(4)) \times F(6)))$$

$$76647 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6) + (4)) + F(7)))$$

$$76648 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((6 - (4 \times 8))))$$

$$76649 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 - F(4)) \times 9))$$

$$76651 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 \times 5) - 1))$$

$$76652 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6 \times 5) \times F(2)))$$

$$76653 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (6 + (5^{F(3)})))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76654 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(6)) - (5)) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 76655 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(6) + ((5 \times 5))) \\
 76656 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6) \times 5) - (6))) \\
 76657 &:= ((F(F((7 + (6/6)))) + (5)) \times 7) \\
 76658 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (6^{F(-5+8)})) \\
 76659 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6) - (5)) + F(9))) \\
 76662 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(6) \times (6 - F(2)))) \\
 76663 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(6)) + F(F(6))) - F(F(3)))) \\
 76664 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F((F(6) + F(6)))) + F(F(6)))/F(4)) \\
 76665 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6) \times 6) - (5))) \\
 76666 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(6) + (6 \times 6))) \\
 76667 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 6)) + (F(F(6))/7)) \\
 76669 &:= (F(7) + ((F(6) \times 6) \times F((F(6) + 9)))) \\
 76671 &:= (-7) \times ((-F(6)) - F((F(6) + F(7)))) + 1) \\
 76672 &:= (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7)) + F(2) \\
 76672 &:= (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7)) + F(3) \\
 76673 &:= (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7)) + F(4) \\
 76674 &:= (((F((F(7) + F(6))) + F(6)) \times 7) - (4)) \\
 76677 &:= (((F((F(7) + F(6))) + (6)) \times 7) + (F(7))) \\
 76678 &:= 7 \times (F(6) + F(6 + 7 + 8)) \\
 76679 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((6 - (7 \times 9)))) \\
 76682 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (6 \times (8 + 2))) \\
 76683 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6) \times 8) - 3)) \\
 76684 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6) \times 8) - F(F(4)))) \\
 76685 &:= (-7) \times (((-6) - F(6)) - F(F(8))) + (5)) \\
 76686 &:= (((F(7) - (6)) \times (F(6) + F(F(8)))) + F(6)) \\
 76687 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + ((F(F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times (-7))) \\
 76689 &:= ((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) + (6 \times (F(F(8)) + 9))) \\
 76691 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (69 \times 1)) \\
 76692 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 69 + F(2) \\
 76693 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 69 + F(3) \\
 76694 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 69 + F(4) \\
 76697 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 6)) - (-9) \times F(7)) \\
 76698 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F(6)) + (F(9) + F(8)))) \\
 76699 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(-((6 - 9))) + 9))) \\
 76711 &:= ((7 \times F((F(6) + F(7)))) + (F(11))) \\
 76712 &:= (((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) - (1^2) \\
 76713 &:= (7 \times (F((F(6) + F(7))) + 13)) \\
 76714 &:= (((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) + (1^4) \\
 76715 &:= (((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) + F(F(-((1 - 5))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76717 &:= (((-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) + F((-1) + F(7))) \\
 76718 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(7) - 1) \times 8)) \\
 76732 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((7 + 3)) \times 2)) \\
 76733 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) + 3))) - F(F(3))) \\
 76734 &:= (7 \times (F((F(6) + F(7))) + ((F(3)^4)))) \\
 76736 &:= (((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) + (F(3) + F(F(6)))) \\
 76737 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(7) - (F(3)^7))) \\
 76739 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(7) \times F(F(3))) \times 9)) \\
 76741 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) + (4 \times 1)))) \\
 76742 &:= (F(7) + (((F(F(6)) \times F(7)) + (4))^2)) \\
 76743 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((7 + 4)^{F(3)})) \\
 76744 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) + (4)))) + F(4)) \\
 76745 &:= (((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) + (F(F(4))^5) \\
 76747 &:= (((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) + F((-4) + F(7))) \\
 76748 &:= (-7) \times (-((6 \times (7 - 4)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 76749 &:= (((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) + (4 \times 9)) \\
 76752 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(7) \times (5 \times 2))) \\
 76754 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (7 + (5^{F(4)}))) \\
 76756 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) + (5)))) + F(6)) \\
 76758 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((7 + 5)) - 8)) \\
 76762 &:= (7 \times ((F(F(6)) + F((F(7) + F(6)))) - F(2))) \\
 76764 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) \times (F(F(6))/F(4)))) \\
 76765 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(7) \times (6 + 5))) \\
 76766 &:= ((7 \times F((F(6) + F(7)))) + F((6 + 6))) \\
 76768 &:= ((F(7) \times F(6)) + (-7) \times (-6) - F(F(8)))) \\
 76769 &:= (7 \times (F(F(6)) + F(-((7 \times (6 - 9))))) \\
 76773 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + 7) + F((F(7) - F(F(3)))) \\
 76776 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (7 + (7 \times F(F(6)))) \\
 76777 &:= (((-F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) - (-F(7)) - F(F(7))) \\
 76778 &:= (-F(7)) \times ((F(F(6)) \times (F(F(7)) + (7))) - F(F(8))) \\
 76783 &:= (-7) \times (((-F(6) + F(7)) - F(F(8))) - F(3)) \\
 76788 &:= ((F(7) + (6)) + (-7) \times (-F(8)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 76789 &:= (((-7) \times ((-6) - F(7)) - F(F(8)))) + F(9)) \\
 76794 &:= (((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) + ((9^{F(F(4))})) \\
 76797 &:= (((-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) - (9 - F(F(7))) \\
 76798 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (6)) + (-7) \times (9 - F(F(8)))) \\
 76813 &:= (((-7) \times (6 - F(F(8)))) + F(13)) \\
 76818 &:= (((7 + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times (-1 - 8)) \\
 76825 &:= (((F(F(7)) - F(6)) \times 8) + F(25)) \\
 76826 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((8 + F(2))) \times 6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76827 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((-6) + F(F(8))) + 2) \times 7)) \\
 76829 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(8) + 2) \times 9)) \\
 76832 &:= -7^6 + F(8)^{F(3) \times 2} \\
 76834 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + (F(F(8)) \times (3 + 4))) \\
 76836 &:= (((-7) \times (6 - F(F(8)))) + (F(3)^{F(6)})) \\
 76837 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (-((F(8) - 3)) + F(F(7)))) \\
 76839 &:= (-7) \times ((6 - F(F(8))) - (3 + F(9))) \\
 76843 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (8 \times 4))) - 3) \\
 76844 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (8 \times 4))) - F(F(4))) \\
 76846 &:= (-7) \times (((-F(6)) - F(F(8))) - (4 \times 6)) \\
 76847 &:= ((F(F(7)) + 6) + ((F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 7)) \\
 76848 &:= (-7) + ((F(F(6)) \times F((F(8) - F(F(4)))) - F(F(8)))) \\
 76849 &:= ((F(F(7)) - 6) - (F(F(8)) \times (F(F(4)) - 9))) \\
 76853 &:= -7 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(5 \times 3) \\
 76854 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((8 + 5)))) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 76855 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(F((8 - (5/5)))) \\
 76857 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((8 - 5)) + F(F(7)))) \\
 76873 &:= (F(7) + ((6 \times F(8)) \times F((F(7) + F(3)))) \\
 76874 &:= (-7) \times (((-F(6)) - F(F(8))) - (7 \times 4)) \\
 76876 &:= (((F(7) - 6) \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(6))) \\
 76878 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((F(8)/7)^8)) \\
 76882 &:= (-F(7)) \times ((F(F(6)) \times (-F(8))) + (F(F(8))/(-2))) \\
 76887 &:= (((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - 8) - (F(F(8)) \times (-7))) \\
 76889 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((6 \times 8) \times F((8 + 9)))) \\
 76916 &:= (7 \times ((F(F(6)) + F(F((9 - 1)))) + F(F(6)))) \\
 76917 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 9)) - (1 - F(F(7)))) \\
 76918 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F(F(F(6))) + 9) \times (-1 - 8))) \\
 76919 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(9) - 1) \times (-9))) \\
 76928 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(9) \times (F(2) + 8))) \\
 76937 &:= (((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(9) - F(3))) \times 7) \\
 76944 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(9) + (F(4) \times 4))) \\
 76949 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(9))) + F((F(F(4)) + 9))) \\
 76958 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (9 \times 5))) + (F(8))) \\
 76962 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(9) \times (F(6) + 2))) \\
 76965 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((9 \times 6) - 5))) \\
 76973 &:= (-F(7)) \times (((-6) \times F((9 + 7))) + F(F(3))) \\
 76974 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (9 + (7^{F(4)}))) \\
 76978 &:= F(7) \times 6 \times F(9 + 7) - 8 \\
 76986 &:= ((7 \times ((F(F(6)) + F(9)) + F(F(8)))) - F(F(6))) \\
 76987 &:= (-F(7)) + (((6 \times 9) + F(F(8))) \times 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77084 &:= (-7) \times (((-70) - F(F(8))) + (4)) \\
 77119 &:= (7 \times (71 + F(F(-((1 - 9)))))) \\
 77126 &:= (7 \times ((71 + F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 77128 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F((F(7) + 1)) + F(2))) - F(F(8))) \\
 77168 &:= (-7) \times ((F(7) \times (-1 \times 6)) - F(F(8))) \\
 77238 &:= (7 \times ((F((F(7) - 2)) - F(F(3))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 77245 &:= (7 \times (F((F(7) - 2)) + F(F((F(4) + 5)))) \\
 77266 &:= ((7 \times (F((F(7) - 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F(6)))) \\
 77336 &:= (7 \times ((F((7 + F(3))) \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 77355 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (7 + 3)) + (F((5 \times 5)))) \\
 77356 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (((7^3) - 5) - 6)) \\
 77376 &:= ((F((7 + 7)) \times F(3)) + (7 \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 77448 &:= (7 \times (((F(F(7)) + F(4))/F(F(4))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 77455 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((F(7)^{F(4)}) + F((5 \times 5)))) \\
 77478 &:= (F(F(7)) + (-7) \times (-F((4 + 7)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 77546 &:= (7 \times ((7 + (5^{F(4)})) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 77589 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (F((7 + 5)) + (F(8) \times 9))) \\
 77616 &:= (77 \times (F(F(6)) + F(16))) \\
 77617 &:= (-F(7)) + (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F((-1) + F(7)))) \\
 77637 &:= (7 + (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(7))))))) \\
 77643 &:= (F(7) + (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F((4 \times 3)))) \\
 77651 &:= (7 \times ((7 \times F(F(6))) + F(F(F((5 + 1)))))) \\
 77658 &:= ((7 \times (7 + F(F(F(6)))) + (F((-5) + F(8)))) \\
 77664 &:= ((7 \times F((-7) + F(F(6)))) + F((F(F(6)) + (4)))) \\
 77686 &:= (7 \times (((F(7) + 6) \times 8) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 77744 &:= ((7 - F(F(7))) \times (-((7^{F(4)}) - F(F(F(4)))))) \\
 77784 &:= (-7) \times (((-((F(7) \times F(7))) - F(F(8))) + F(4))) \\
 77787 &:= -(((F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) - ((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 7)) \\
 77834 &:= (-7) + (((F(F(7)) - (8^3))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 77842 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((7 \times F(F(8))) + (F((4^2)))) \\
 77847 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - (F(7) \times (-8)) \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(7)))) \\
 77863 &:= (F(F(7)) + (7 \times (F(F(8)) + F((6 \times F(3)))))) \\
 77876 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) - F((-7) + F(F(6)))) \\
 77889 &:= (-7) \times (((-7) \times F(8)) - F(F(8)) - F(9)) \\
 77892 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (((F(7) - 8)^{9-2}))) \\
 77896 &:= (-7) \times ((7 - F(F(8))) + (-9) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 77966 &:= (-7) - (-79) \times F((F(6) + F(6)))) \\
 77986 &:= (F(7) + (79 \times F((8 + F(6)))) \\
 78125 &:= (F(7) - 8)^{1 \times 2 + 5} \\
 78142 &:= ((F(F(7)) - ((F((8 + 1))^{F(4)})) \times (-2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78197 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) + ((1 - 9))) \times 7) \\
 78217 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) + (-2) + F(17)) \\
 78219 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) + F(-(2 - 19))) \\
 78239 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) - 2) \times (-F(3) - 9)) \\
 78246 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) - F(2)) / F(4)) \times F(F(6)) \\
 78252 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times (2 + 5)) - F(2)) \\
 78253 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times ((2 \times 5) - 3)) \\
 78254 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times (2 + 5)) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 78256 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(8)) - 2) \times (-5) + F(F(6))) \\
 78267 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) + 2) \times (-6) + F(7)) \\
 78274 &:= (-7) \times (((F(F(8)) \times (-F(2))) - F(F(7))) - F(4)) \\
 78284 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F(8) \times (2 \times 8))) - 4) \\
 78288 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((F(8) \times F(2)) \times (8 + 8))) \\
 78323 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + (3^{2+3})) \\
 78325 &:= ((F(F(7)) + 8) \times 325) \\
 78336 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(8)) + 3) \times (F(3) \times F(6))) \\
 78337 &:= (F(F(7)) - (F(8) - ((F(3) + 3)^7)) \\
 78357 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F(F(F((8/F(3)))))) + (5^7)) \\
 78384 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F((F(8) - F(F(3)))) \times (-8 + 4)) \\
 78386 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + ((F(3) \times F(8)) \times 6)) \\
 78393 &:= (-7) + ((8 \times (F(F(3)) + F(9)))^{F(3)}) \\
 78414 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + ((4 \times 1)^4)) \\
 78428 &:= (7 \times ((F(F(8)) + F(F(4))) + (2^8)) \\
 78445 &:= ((F(F(7)) - (F((8 \times F(4))) / (-F(4))) \times 5) \\
 78478 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(F(F(4))) - F(F(7))) \times 8)) \\
 78486 &:= (((7 \times 8) \times F((-4) + F(8))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 78487 &:= (((7 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(F(4)))) + (8 \times F(F(7)))) \\
 78498 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) - (4 - (F(9) \times 8))) \\
 78547 &:= ((7^{8-5}) \times (-4) + F(F(7))) \\
 78568 &:= (((F(F(7)) - 8) \times 5) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-8) \\
 78624 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times (2^4)) \\
 78638 &:= (-7) \times ((-8) \times (6^{F(3)}) - F(F(8))) \\
 78689 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(8)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (F(8) - F(9))) \\
 78694 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + ((F(6) \times (F(9) + F(4)))))) \\
 78719 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) - (F(F(7)) \times (-1 \times 9))) \\
 78729 &:= (7 \times ((F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) - (-2) \times F(9))) \\
 78735 &:= (F(7) - 8)^7 + F(3 \times 5) \\
 78750 &:= ((F(F(7)) - 8) \times (7 \times 50)) \\
 78827 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) + (82)) \times 7) \\
 78894 &:= (-((F(7) - F((8 + 8)))) \times (9^{F(F(4))}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78926 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) - (-9) \times (2^{F(6)})) \\
 78934 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(9)^{F(3)}) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 78987 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (8 + 98)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 78997 &:= (F(F(7)) - ((F(F(8)) + (9 \times F(9))) \times (-7))) \\
 79202 &:= (((F(F(7)) - F(9))^2) \times 02) \\
 79210 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-F(9))) + F(2)) \times (-10)) \\
 79215 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (F(9) \times (-2))) + 1) \times (-5)) \\
 79220 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((F(9)/2) \times 20)) \\
 79225 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (F(9) \times (-2))) - F(2)) \times (-5)) \\
 79235 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (F(9) \times (-2))) - 3) \times (-5)) \\
 79268 &:= (-7) \times (((-9 \times 2) \times F(F(6))) - F(F(8))) \\
 79274 &:= -((F(F(7)) - ((9 + F((2 + 7)))^{F(4)})) \\
 79299 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(9)) \times ((F(2) - F(9)) \times (-9))) \\
 79453 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (-F(9) + (F(4) \times (-5^3)))) \\
 79454 &:= ((F((7 + F(F((9 - F(4)))))) + (5)) / 4) \\
 79478 &:= (7 \times ((-F(9)) \times (F(F(F(4))) - F(7))) + F(F(8))) \\
 79492 &:= ((-F(7)) - (F(9)^{F(F(4))})) \times (F(9) \times (-2)) \\
 79494 &:= (-F(7)) + (((9 \times F(F(F(4)))) + F(9))^{F(4)}) \\
 79524 &:= (((F(7) + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2)))^{F(4)}) \\
 79638 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(9))) - (F(6) \times (F(F(3)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 79646 &:= (7 \times ((-9) + (F(F(6))^{F(F(4))})) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 79648 &:= (((F((7 + 9)) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(4)) \times (-8)) \\
 79662 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(9))) - (-F(6)) \times (F(F(F(6))) + 2)) \\
 79666 &:= (((-F((7 + 9))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(6)) - 6) \\
 79672 &:= ((-F((7 + 9))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (7 + F(2)) \\
 79677 &:= ((-7) + F(9)) \times ((6 - F(F(7))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 79686 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((9 + (6 \times 8)) \times 6)) \\
 79716 &:= (7 \times ((F(9) \times F(7)) + F(F(F((1 \times 6)))))) \\
 79744 &:= ((F(F(7)) - 9) \times (F((7 + 4)) \times 4)) \\
 79850 &:= (F(-((F(7) - 9) - F(8))) \times 50) \\
 79926 &:= ((F((7 + 9)) \times (9^2)) - F(F(6))) \\
 79927 &:= (-7) - (F(9) \times (-F((9 \times 2))) + F(F(7))) \\
 79929 &:= (((F((7 + 9)) \times 9) - 2) \times 9) \\
 79934 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F((9 + 9))) \times (-34)) \\
 79944 &:= ((F((7 + 9)) \times (9^{F(F(4))})) - F(4)) \\
 79947 &:= F(7 + 9) \times (F(9) + 47) \\
 79968 &:= (F(7) \times F(9) + F(9)) \times F(6) \times F(8) \\
 81088 &:= ((810 - F(F(8))) \times (-8)) \\
 81175 &:= ((F((F(8) - 1)) \times (-1) + F(7)) - (5)) \\
 81186 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (1 + F(18))) \times 6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$81557 := ((F((F(8) - 1)) + (F((5 \times 5)))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$81634 := (F((8 + 1)) \times ((F(6) - F(F(3)))^4))$$

$$81648 := ((81 \times F(F(6))) \times 48)$$

$$81736 := (8 \times (F(F((1 + 7))) - ((3^6))))$$

$$81794 := (F(F(8)) - ((-1) - F((F(7) + 9))) \times 4)$$

$$81796 := ((F(8) + 1) \times F(7))^{F(9-6)}$$

$$82366 := ((F(F(8)) \times (-F(2))) + (F(3) \times (6^6)))$$

$$82467 := ((F(8)^2) \times (-46) + F(F(7)))$$

$$82656 := (-82) \times (-F(F(6))) - F((-5) + F(F(6))))$$

$$82667 := (((F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times F(6)) - (F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$82672 := (8 \times ((-2) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F((F(7) + 2))))$$

$$82688 := (((F(F(8)) \times (-F(2))) + F((-6) + F(8))) \times (-8))$$

$$82696 := ((F(F(8)) + ((F(2) - F((6 + 9)))) \times F(6))$$

$$82715 := (F(F((8 - F(2)))) \times (71 \times 5))$$

$$82824 := (F(8) \times ((F(2) - F((8 \times 2))) \times (-4)))$$

$$82936 := (8 \times (2 + F(9)))^{F(3)} - F(6)$$

$$82937 := (8 \times (2 + F(9)))^{F(3)} - 7$$

$$82942 := (((8 \times (2 + F(9)))^{F(F(4))}) - 2)$$

$$82943 := (((8 \times (2 + F(9)))^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(3)))$$

$$82944 := (-8 - 2 + F(9))^4 / 4$$

$$83076 := ((F(F(8)) + (-30) \times F(F(7))) \times F(F(6)))$$

$$83169 := (((-((F(8)^3) + 1)) + F(F(6))) \times (-9))$$

$$83232 := 8 \times (F(3^2) \times 3)^2$$

$$83246 := (F((F(8) + F(F(3)))) - (F(2) - (4^{F(6)})))$$

$$83247 := (F((F(8) + F(F(3)))) + (2^{F(4)+F(7)}))$$

$$83248 := (F((F(8) + F(F(3)))) + (F(2) + (4^8)))$$

$$83259 := (((F(8)^3) - (2 \times 5)) \times 9)$$

$$83328 := ((F(8) \times 3)^{F(3)} - F(2)) \times F(8)$$

$$83343 := (((F(8)^3) \times (-3)) + F(F(4))) \times (-3)$$

$$83349 := F(8)^3 \times 3^4 / 9$$

$$83385 := ((F((F(8) + F(3))) - F(3)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-5)))$$

$$83386 := -(((F((F(8) - F(3))) + F(F(3))) + (F(F(8)) \times (-F(6))))$$

$$83387 := (F((F(8) - (3/3))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-7)))$$

$$83388 := -(((F((F(8) - F(3))) - F(F(3))) + (-8) \times F(F(8))))$$

$$83488 := (((-((8^3)) + F(F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times 8)$$

$$83496 := (((F(F(8)) + 3) - (F(F(4))^9)) \times F(6))$$

$$83520 := ((F((F(8) - F(3))) - (5)) \times 20)$$

$$83615 := ((F((F(8) - F(3))) \times (F(F(6)) - 1)) - (5))$$

$$83664 := (83 \times (F(F(6)) + F((F(6) \times F(F(4))))))$$

$$83749 := (-F((8 + 3)) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-4)) - 9))$$

$$83764 := ((F((F(8) - F(F(3)))) \times F(7)) - F((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))))$$

$$83779 := ((F(F(8)) / (F(3) \times F(7))) \times (F(F(7)) - F(9)))$$

$$83784 := ((F(F(8)) - (3^7)) + F((F(8) + (4))))$$

$$83826 := ((F(F(8)) + (F((F(3) + 8))^2)) \times 6)$$

$$83895 := (F((8 \times F(3))) \times ((8 + 9) \times 5))$$

$$83968 := (((F(8)^{F(3)} + 9) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-8))$$

$$84000 := (F(8) \times 4000)$$

$$84208 := ((F(F(8)) - 420) \times 8)$$

$$84284 := (F((F(8) + (4))) + (-2) + (F(8)^{F(4)}))$$

$$84286 := ((F(8)^{F(4)} + F(((F(8) + (4))))$$

$$84287 := (F(F(8)) + (((F(4) \times F(28)) / F(7)))$$

$$84368 := (((F(8) - F(F(F(4))))^{F(3)} - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-8))$$

$$84374 := ((F((F(8) + F(F(4)))) \times 3) - F((F(7) + (4))))$$

$$84474 := (((F(8) - F(F(4)))^{F(F(4))} \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(4))))$$

$$84664 := (-8) + (F(4) \times ((F(6) \times F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))}))$$

$$84755 := ((F((8 + 4)) + (7^5)) \times 5)$$

$$84777 := ((F(F(8)) - ((-4) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(7))) \times 7)$$

$$84784 := (F((8 \times F(4))) + ((-7) + F(8))^4)$$

$$84791 := (-F(8)) + ((4 \times F(F(7))) \times 91)$$

$$84866 := (((F(8)^{F(4)} - F(8)) \times F(6)) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$84872 := (8 \times (((F(F(F(4))) + (-8) \times F(7)))^2))$$

$$84882 := (F((8 \times F(F(4)))) \times (88 - 2))$$

$$84946 := (((F(8)^{F(4)} \times 9) + F((-4) + F(F(6))))$$

$$84984 := ((F(F(8)) \times (F(4) + 9)) - F((8 \times F(4))))$$

$$84985 := ((F((F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) - ((F(9) \times F(8)))) \times 5)$$

$$85184 := (F(8) + 5 + 18)^{F(4)}$$

$$85224 := 8 \times (5 + 22^{F(4)})$$

$$85368 := (8 \times ((-5) \times F((F(3) + F(6)))) + F(F(8)))$$

$$85664 := (8 \times ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F((F(F(6)) / F(4))))$$

$$85666 := ((F((8 + 5)) - F((F(6) + F(F(6)))) / (-6))$$

$$85672 := (8 \times ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(7)) - F(2))))$$

$$85677 := ((8 \times ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(7))) + F(7))$$

$$85678 := (-((F(8) + (5))) - (F(6) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(8))))$$

$$85696 := ((F(F(8)) + ((5 + F(F(6))) \times (-9))) \times F(6))$$

$$85728 := (((F(F(8)) + (5)) - F(F(7))) - 2) \times 8)$$

$$85734 := (-((8 - ((5 \times 7)^3)) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$85736 := (((F(F(8)) + (5)) - F(F(7))) - F(F(3))) \times F(6))$$

$$85742 := -8 + (5 \times 7)^{F(4)} \times 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 85744 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (5)) - F(F(7))) \times (4 + 4)) \\
 85746 &:= ((8 - 5) \times ((F(7)^4) + F(F(6)))) \\
 85764 &:= F(8) \times (-5 - 7 + F(6)^4) \\
 85848 &:= F(8) \times ((-5 + F(8))^{F(4)} - 8) \\
 85888 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (5 \times (F(8) + F(8)))) \times 8) \\
 85896 &:= (8 \times ((-5) + F(F(8))) + (F(9) \times (-6))) \\
 85963 &:= (-8) + (F((-5) + F(9)) - (6)) \times 3) \\
 85966 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (5)) + F(((9 + F(6)) + F(6)))) \\
 85968 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (5 \times (F(9) + (6)))) \times 8) \\
 85971 &:= (F(F(8)) - (F((5^{9-7})) \times (-1))) \\
 85972 &:= (F(F(8)) + ((F((5^{9-7})) + F(2)))) \\
 85973 &:= (F(F(8)) + (F((5^{9-7})) + F(3))) \\
 85974 &:= (F(F(8)) + (F((5^{9-7})) + F(4))) \\
 85976 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (5)) + F((-9) + F(7) + F(F(6)))) \\
 85977 &:= ((-8) - ((5 - F(9)) \times F(7))) \times F(F(7)) \\
 85978 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((5 - 9))) + (7)) + F(F(8)) \\
 86034 &:= ((F(8) + F((F(F(6)) + F(03)))) \times F(4)) \\
 86176 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + ((1 - F(F(7))) \times 6)) \\
 86184 &:= F(8) \times (F(6) + 1 \times 8^4) \\
 86248 &:= (8 \times ((F((F(6) + 2)) \times (-F(4))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 86264 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(2))) - ((6^4))) \\
 86266 &:= ((F(8) \times (-62)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times F(6))) \\
 86288 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(6) \times (F(2) - F(8)))) \times 8) \\
 86289 &:= (F(8) \times (F((F(F(6)) - 2)) - ((8 \times 9))) \\
 86348 &:= (F((8 + 6)) - (-3) \times F((F(F(4)) + (F(8)))) \\
 86368 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (6)) - F((F(3) \times 6))) \times 8) \\
 86376 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(F(6))) - (F(3)^7)) \times F(6)) \\
 86384 &:= (-8) \times ((F((6 \times F(3))) - F(F(8))) + (4)) \\
 86416 &:= ((F(F(8)) - F((F(6) + (4)))) \times F((1 \times 6))) \\
 86432 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F((4 \times 3)) - 2)) \\
 86436 &:= (((F(8) + (F(6)^4)) - F(F(3))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 86437 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + (-F(4)) \times F((F(3) \times 7))) \\
 86448 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F((F(6) + (4)))) + (4)) \times 8) \\
 86456 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F((F(6) + (4)))) + (5)) \times F(6)) \\
 86457 &:= ((F(8) + (F(6)^4)) \times F((-5) + F(7))) \\
 86464 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (46 \times F(4)))) \\
 86476 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + ((-4) \times F(7)) \times F(F(6))) \\
 86477 &:= ((-F((8 + 6))) \times (F(4) - F(F(7)))) - F(F(7)) \\
 86483 &:= ((F(F(8)) + F((F(F(6)) + (4)))) + (8^3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 86497 &:= ((F(8) \times ((F(6)^4) + F(9))) - F(F(7))) \\
 86528 &:= (8 \times (F(6) + 5))^2 \times 8 \\
 86544 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((5^{F(4)}) + F(4)))) \\
 86581 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - F((-5) + F((8 \times 1)))) \\
 86582 &:= F(F(8)) \times F(6) - F(-5 + F(8)) + F(2) \\
 86583 &:= F(F(8)) \times F(6) - F(-5 + F(8)) + F(3) \\
 86584 &:= F(F(8)) \times F(6) - F(-5 + F(8)) + F(4) \\
 86586 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + (5)) - F((8 + F(6)))) \\
 86644 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (F(F(6)) \times 44)) \\
 86672 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(6) \times (7 \times 2)))) \\
 86686 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - ((F(F(6)) + (F(8))) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 86688 &:= (F(8) \times (6 \times 688)) \\
 86728 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(6) \times F(7)) + F(2))) \times 8) \\
 86736 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - ((F(7) \times (F(3)^6)))) \\
 86762 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + (F(7) \times (-62))) \\
 86772 &:= (F(8) \times (F((6 + F(7))) - (7^2))) \\
 86776 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(6) - (-7) \times F(7))) \times F(6)) \\
 86784 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (784)) \\
 86798 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 7)) - ((F(9) \times F(8)))) \\
 86827 &:= ((86 - F((F(8) - F(2)))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 86848 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (6 + 84)) \times 8) \\
 86854 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (F(8) \times F((5 + 4)))) \\
 86856 &:= (F((8 + F(6))) \times (8 \times (5 + 6))) \\
 86864 &:= (8 - (-F(6)) \times (F(F(8)) - F((F(6) + F(4)))) \\
 86867 &:= (((86 - F(F(8))) \times (-F(6))) - (F(7))) \\
 86871 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (87))) - 1) \\
 86872 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (87 \times F(2)))) \\
 86873 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (87))) + F(F(3))) \\
 86874 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (87))) + F(F(4))) \\
 86892 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - ((-8) + F(9))^2) \\
 86899 &:= (-F(8)) - (-F(6)) \times (F(F(8)) - ((9 \times 9))) \\
 86919 &:= F(8) \times (-F(6) - F(9) + F(19)) \\
 86944 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(9) + 44))) \\
 86966 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (F((9 + 6)) - F(6))) \\
 86967 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + 9) - F((F(6) + (7)))) \\
 86968 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (69 + 6)) \times 8) \\
 86984 &:= (8 \times ((-69) + F(F(8))) - (4)) \\
 86986 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(6) \times (-9))) \times 8) - (6)) \\
 86992 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(6) \times (-9))) \times (9 - F(2))) \\
 87008 &:= ((F(F(8)) - 70) \times 08)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87016 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((70 - 1))) \times F(6)) \\
 87078 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 70) \times 7) + F(F(8))) \\
 87128 &:= ((F(F(8)) - F(((7 + 1) + 2))) \times 8) \\
 87152 &:= (8 \times (F(F((7 + 1))) - 52)) \\
 87167 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F((7 + 1)))) \times F(6)) - F(F(7))) \\
 87168 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 71) + F(F(6))) \times 8) \\
 87176 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((7 \times 1) \times 7)) \times F(6)) \\
 87256 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (7 + (2^5))) \times F(6)) \\
 87263 &:= (-F(F(8))) - (F((-7) + F((F(2) + F(6)))))/(-F(3))) \\
 87264 &:= (8 \times ((-F((7 + 2))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 4) \\
 87285 &:= (((F(8) + F(F(7))) - F((F(2) + F(8)))) \times (-5)) \\
 87287 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (7 - F(2))) \times 8) - F(F(7))) \\
 87288 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (7 + 28)) \times 8) \\
 87293 &:= ((8 \times (F(F((7 + F(2)))) - F(9))) - 3) \\
 87294 &:= ((8 \times (F(F((7 + F(2)))) - F(9))) - F(F(4))) \\
 87296 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (7 + F(2))) - (F(9) \times F(6))) \\
 87318 &:= (-F(8)) \times ((F(F(7)) - F(3)) \times (-18)) \\
 87327 &:= ((8 \times (F((7 \times 3)) - F(2))) - F(F(7))) \\
 87328 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(7) + F(3)) \times 2)) \times 8) \\
 87335 &:= ((8 \times F((7 \times 3))) - F(F((F(3) + (5)))))) \\
 87336 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(7) \times F(3)) + 3)) \times F(6)) \\
 87337 &:= (((8 \times F((7 \times 3))) + F(3)) - F(F(7))) \\
 87354 &:= (-F(8)) - (F(F(7)) \times (-3) \times (5^{F(4)})) \\
 87356 &:= ((F(8) - F(F(7))) + (F(F((3 + 5))) \times F(6))) \\
 87373 &:= (((F((F(8) - (7))) - F(3)) \times F(F(7))) - F(3)) \\
 87374 &:= (((F((F(8) - (7))) - F(3)) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 87375 &:= (((8 - F(F(7)))/3) \times F(F(7))) \times (-5) \\
 87376 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(7) - F(3)) + F(7))) \times F(6)) \\
 87384 &:= (8 \times ((-((F(7) \times F(3))) + F(F(8))) + F(4))) \\
 87387 &:= (-F(8) + F(7 \times 3)) \times 8 - F(7) \\
 87432 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(7) + (4))) \times F((3 \times 2))) \\
 87448 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((7 + 4) + 4)) \times 8) \\
 87454 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) \times 4) - (5)) \times F(F(4))) \\
 87456 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(7) - ((4 - 5)))) \times F(6)) \\
 87457 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) \times (F(4) + (5))) - (7)) \\
 87462 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) \times (F(F(4)) + (6))) - 2) \\
 87463 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) \times (F(F(4)) + (6))) - F(F(3))) \\
 87464 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) \times (4 \times (6 - 4))) \\
 87466 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times F(6)) - 6) \\
 87467 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (7 + 4)) \times F(6)) - (F(7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87468 &:= (((-8) \times F(7)) + (4)) - (-F(6) \times F(F(8))) \\
 87469 &:= (-F(F(8))) + ((-((7 + 4) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9)) \\
 87472 &:= (8 \times (F((7 \times F(4))) - (F(7) - F(2)))) \\
 87477 &:= ((8 \times F((7 \times F(4)))) + (-7) \times F(7)) \\
 87493 &:= ((8 \times (F((7 \times F(4))) - 9)) - 3) \\
 87494 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (7)) \times 4) - 9) \times F(F(4)) \\
 87496 &:= ((8 \times F((7 \times F(4)))) + (-9) \times F(6)) \\
 87498 &:= (F(F(8)) + (-7) \times (F(F(F(4))) - (-9) + F(F(8)))) \\
 87511 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (7)) \times F((5 + 1))) - 1) \\
 87512 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (7)) \times ((5 - 1) \times 2)) \\
 87513 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (7)) \times F((5 + 1))) + F(F(3))) \\
 87514 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (7)) \times F((5 + 1))) + F(F(4))) \\
 87526 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - (2 \times F(F(6)))) \\
 87528 &:= ((F((8 + F(7))) - (5)) \times (F(2) \times 8)) \\
 87533 &:= (F(F(8)) + (7 \times (-5) + F(F(F((3 + 3)))))) \\
 87534 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - 34) \\
 87536 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((7 + 5)/3)) \times F(6)) \\
 87537 &:= ((8 \times (F(F((F(7) - (5)))) - 3)) - 7) \\
 87542 &:= ((8 \times (F(F((F(7) - (5)))) - F(4))) - 2) \\
 87543 &:= ((8 \times (F(F((F(7) - (5)))) - F(4))) - F(F(3))) \\
 87544 &:= (8 \times (F(F(((7 - 5) \times 4))) - F(4))) \\
 87546 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - F(F(F(4)))) - (F(F(6)))) \\
 87547 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - (F(4) \times 7)) \\
 87548 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 7) - (5 \times 4)) + F(F(8))) \\
 87552 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (7 - 5)) \times F((5 + F(2)))) \\
 87553 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - (5 \times 3)) \\
 87558 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 7) - (5 + 5)) + F(F(8))) \\
 87568 &:= 8 \times F(7 \times 5 - 6 - 8) \\
 87573 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 7) + (5 + F((7 \times 3)))) \\
 87574 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) + (7)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 87576 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - (F(7))) + F(F(6))) \\
 87581 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) + F((8 - 1))) \\
 87582 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7 - 5)) \times 8) - 2) \\
 87583 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7 - 5)) \times 8) - F(F(3))) \\
 87584 &:= (8 \times ((-((7 - 5)) + F(F(8))) + (4))) \\
 87588 &:= (((8 + 7) + 5) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 87589 &:= -(((F(F(8)) - F((F(7) - (5)))) + (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))) \\
 87596 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) + (F(9) - (6))) \\
 87597 &:= (((-8) + F((F(7) + (5)))) \times F(9)) + (F(7)) \\
 87598 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) + (9 + F(8)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87608 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(7) - F(6))) \times 08) \\
 87612 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) - 12) \\
 87613 &:= ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) - 1)) - 3) \\
 87614 &:= ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) - 1)) - F(F(4))) \\
 87616 &:= ((F((8 + F(7))) + (6)) \times F((1 \times 6))) \\
 87617 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) - (1 \times 7)) \\
 87621 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 87622 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) - (F(2) + F(2))) \\
 87623 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) + ((2 - 3))) \\
 87624 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times ((6 - 2) + 4)) \\
 87625 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) + (F(2)^5)) \\
 87626 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) + F(F(-(2 - 6)))) \\
 87627 &:= ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + 2)) - F(7)) \\
 87631 &:= ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(3)))) - 1) \\
 87632 &:= ((8 + F((F(7) + F(6)))) \times F((3 \times 2))) \\
 87633 &:= ((-8) + F((F(7) + (6)))) \times F(F((3 + 3))) \\
 87634 &:= ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(3)))) + F(F(4))) \\
 87635 &:= ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + F(3))) - (5)) \\
 87636 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) + (F(3) \times 6)) \\
 87637 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times (6 + F(3))) + (F(7))) \\
 87638 &:= (F(F(8)) + (-7) \times (-((F(6) + F(3))) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87639 &:= F(8) + (-7 + F(6 \times 3)) \times F(9) \\
 87651 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) - F(F((5 + 1)))) \\
 87654 &:= (F(8) \times ((F((F(7) + (6))) - (5)) - F(F(4)))) \\
 87656 &:= ((F((8 + F(7))) + (6 + 5)) \times F(6)) \\
 87657 &:= ((F(8) \times F((F(7) + (6)))) - (F((5 + 7)))) \\
 87662 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) - (F(6) + 2)) \\
 87663 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) - (6 + 3)) \\
 87664 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) - (6)) - F(F(4))) \\
 87666 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) + F(F(6))) + F(F(6))) \\
 87667 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) + ((F(6) - F(7)))) \\
 87669 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) + ((6 - 9))) \\
 87671 &:= ((8 \times (F(7) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) - 1) \\
 87672 &:= 8 \times (F(7) + F(6 \times 7/2)) \\
 87673 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) + (7^{F(3)})) \\
 87674 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) + F((7 - 4))) \\
 87675 &:= ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + 7)) - (5)) \\
 87676 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(F(7))) - F(F(6))) \\
 87692 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) - (F(9) \times (-2))) \\
 87693 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) + F(F((9 - 3))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87694 &:= ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + 9)) - F(F(4))) \\
 87696 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) - (-9) \times F(6)) \\
 87698 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) + (F(9) - 8)) \\
 87712 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F((-7) + F(7))) + (F(12))) \\
 87720 &:= ((8 - F(F(7))) + (F(7) \times F(20))) \\
 87728 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(7) + (7))) \times (F(2) \times 8)) \\
 87736 &:= 8 + F(7) + F(7 \times 3) \times F(6) \\
 87737 &:= ((-8) \times F(7)) + (F(F(7)) \times F((F(3) \times 7))) \\
 87738 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F((F(7) + (7)))) - 3) \times F(8)) \\
 87739 &:= ((F((F(8) - (7))) \times F(F(7))) + (-3) \times F(9)) \\
 87754 &:= ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (F((F(7) + (5))) - F(4))) \\
 87764 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7 \times 7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4) \\
 87766 &:= ((F(8) + F(F(7))) + ((-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(6)) \\
 87768 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7) + F(7))) \times F(6)) - 8) \\
 87769 &:= ((F((F(8) - (7))) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) \times (-9))) \\
 87776 &:= ((F((8 + F(7))) + (F(7) + F(7))) \times F(6)) \\
 87784 &:= (8 \times (((F(7) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 87786 &:= (((-8) + F(F(7))) - (7)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-F(6))) \\
 87820 &:= -F(8) + F(7) \times (-8 + F(20)) \\
 87822 &:= (F(8) \times (F((F(7) + (8 - 2))) + F(2))) \\
 87833 &:= (-8) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(((8 + 3) + 3)))) \\
 87836 &:= (F(F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times F((8 + F(3)))) \times 6)) \\
 87838 &:= ((F(8) + F(F(7))) - ((F(F(8)) + F(3)) \times (-8))) \\
 87856 &:= (F(8) + F(7)) \times F((8 - 5) \times 6) \\
 87861 &:= (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times (-F((8 + 6)))) + 1)) \\
 87862 &:= (F(8) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F((8 + 6) \times F(2)))) \\
 87863 &:= (F(8) - ((F(F(7)) \times (-F((8 + 6)))) - F(F(3)))) \\
 87864 &:= (8 - (-((F(7) + F(8))) \times F((6 \times F(4)))) \\
 87867 &:= ((F((F(8) + ((7 - 8)))) - (6)) \times F(7)) \\
 87878 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times 8) + F(F(7))) + (F(8)) \\
 87886 &:= ((F(8) + F(F(7))) - ((-8) - F(F(8))) \times F(6)) \\
 87888 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(7) - 8) \times 8)) \times 8) \\
 87893 &:= ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(8))) + F(9))) - 3) \\
 87894 &:= ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(8))) + F(9))) - F(F(4))) \\
 87896 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times 8) + (F(9) \times F(6))) \\
 87897 &:= (F(F(8)) + (((F(7) + F(F(8))) + F(9)) \times 7)) \\
 87924 &:= (-F(8) - (-F(7)) \times F(((F(9)/2) + F(4)))) \\
 87927 &:= (-F(8)) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-9 \times 2)) + (7)) \\
 87928 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(7) + F(9)) - 2)) \times 8) \\
 87936 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7) + F(9))) - F(F(3))) \times F(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87937 &:= -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7) \\
 87944 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(7) + F(9))) \times (4 + 4)) \\
 87945 &:= (-8 - F(7) + F(9)) \times F(4 \times 5) \\
 87948 &:= (-F(8)) \times (-7 - F((9 \times F(4)) - 8))) \\
 87966 &:= (F(8) - (-F(7)) \times F(((F(9) - F(6)) - (6)))) \\
 87967 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (79)) \times F(6)) - F(F(7))) \\
 87979 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F((F(7) + 9))) \times (-F(7))) + F(9)) \\
 88168 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (81 - 6)) \times 8) \\
 88176 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + (1 \times 76))) \\
 88178 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) + F((1 \times 7) + 8)) \\
 88184 &:= (8 \times ((81 + F(F(8))) - (4))) \\
 88186 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 1)) + F((F(8) - (6)))) \\
 88200 &:= ((F(8) \times F(8)) \times 200) \\
 88216 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (82 - 1)) \times F(6)) \\
 88218 &:= ((F(8) + F((F(8) - F(2)))) \times F(-((1 - 8))) \\
 88224 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (82)) \times (2 \times 4)) \\
 88242 &:= ((F(8) + F((F(8) - 2))) \times F((4 \times 2))) \\
 88248 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (82 + F(4))) \times 8) \\
 88263 &:= (F(8) \times ((F((F(8) - 2)) + F(F(6))) + F(F(3)))) \\
 88264 &:= (8 \times ((F(F(8)) - 2) + F((F(6) + F(4)))) \\
 88267 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) + (F(-((2 - 6))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 88272 &:= (8 \times ((F(F(8)) - F(2)) + F((F(7) - 2))) \\
 88273 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) + ((2 + F(F(7))) \times 3)) \\
 88275 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + F((-2) + F(7)))) - (5)) \\
 88284 &:= (-F(8)) \times ((-F(8)) - F((-2) + F(8))) - F(F(4))) \\
 88288 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (82 + 8)) \times 8) \\
 88296 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (82 + 9)) \times F(6)) \\
 88298 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 2)) + ((F(9) \times F(8)))) \\
 88336 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) + (3 \times (F(3))^{F(6)})) \\
 88347 &:= (F(8) \times (F((F(8) - F(3))) + (F(F(4)) \times F(7)))) \\
 88368 &:= (((F(8) + F((F(8) - F(3)))) + (6)) \times F(8)) \\
 88369 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) + (F((3 + F(6))) \times 9)) \\
 88376 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + (-3) + (F(7) \times F(6)))) \\
 88384 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + (F((F(F(3)) + 8)) \times F(4))) \\
 88387 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) - ((-3) \times F(8)) \times F(7)) \\
 88392 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + ((3 \times F(9)) + F(2))) \\
 88397 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) - (-3) \times F(9))) + (F(7))) \\
 88408 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) - (-40) \times F(8)) \\
 88435 &:= (((-F(8)) + F((F(8) + F(F(F(4)))))) - 3) \times 5) \\
 88445 &:= (((-F(8)) + F((F(8) + F(F(F(4)))))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 88448 &:= (8 \times ((F((8 + F(F(4)))) \times F(F(4))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 88476 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) - (-4) \times (F(F(7)) - (6))) \\
 88487 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F((8 + 4))) \times 8) - F(F(7))) \\
 88494 &:= (F(8) \times ((F((F(8) - F(F(4)))) + F(9)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 88495 &:= (((F(8) - F((F(8) + F(F(F(4)))))) - 9) \times (-5)) \\
 88515 &:= ((-8) + F((F(8) + F(F(F((5 - 1)))))) \times 5) \\
 88526 &:= ((-8) - F(8)) + (5 \times F((F(2) + F(F(6)))) \\
 88544 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + ((5^{F(4)}) - F(4))) \\
 88545 &:= ((F((F(8) + F(F((8 - 5)))) - F(F(4))) \times 5) \\
 88553 &:= ((F((F(8) + F(F((8 - 5)))) \times 5) - F(3)) \\
 88554 &:= ((F((F(8) + F(F((8 - 5)))) \times 5) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 88555 &:= ((F(F(8)) + F((F(8) - (5/5)))) \times 5) \\
 88563 &:= ((8 + F((F(8) + (5)))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times 3)) \\
 88576 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + (F((-5) + F(7))) \times 6)) \\
 88578 &:= (-F(8)) \times (((F(F(8)) \times (-5))/F(7)) - 8) \\
 88584 &:= ((8 + F(8)) + (5 \times F((F(8) + F(F(F(4)))))) \\
 88589 &:= (((8 \times F(F(8))) + F((-5) + F(8))) + F(9)) \\
 88595 &:= (8 + F(8 + 5 + 9)) \times 5 \\
 88597 &:= ((F(8) + F(8)) - (-5) \times F((9 + F(7)))) \\
 88635 &:= (((-8 + 8) - F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) \times (-5)) \\
 88672 &:= (8 \times ((F(F(8)) - (6)) + F((F(7) - F(2)))) \\
 88683 &:= (-F(8)) \times (((-F(8)) - F(F(6))) - F((F(8) - F(3)))) \\
 88712 &:= (8 \times ((F(F(8)) + F((F(7) - 1))) - F(2))) \\
 88715 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + F((F(7) - 1))) - (5)) \\
 88733 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(3) + 3))) \\
 88736 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(8) \times 7)) - F(F(3))) \times F(6)) \\
 88744 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(8) \times 7)) \times (4 + 4)) \\
 88777 &:= (((-8 \times 8) - F((F(7) + (7)))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 88778 &:= (((F(8) \times F(8)) - F(7)) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(8)) \\
 88788 &:= (((8 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (F((8 + 8))) \\
 88848 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + ((F(8) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 8)) \\
 88892 &:= (((-F(8)) - F(F(8))) \times (-8)) + (F(9)^2) \\
 88936 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + (9 \times (-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) \\
 88966 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) - (F((F(9) - F(F(6)))) \times (-6)) \\
 88967 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) - (F(9) \times (-6)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 88976 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(8) \times 9) - F(7))) \times F(6)) \\
 88996 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(9) \times (F(9) + F(6)))) \\
 89166 &:= ((F((8 + 9)) + 1) + (F(F(F(6))) \times F(6))) \\
 89253 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 9) - (F(F((F(2) + (5))))^3) \\
 89266 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F(9)^2)) \times F(6)) + F(F(F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 89346** := $((8 \times (F(9) + F(F(3))))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(F(6))))$
89368 := $(((-8) + F(F((9 - F(3)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8)$
89376 := $((-F((8 + 9))) + F(F(3))) \times (-7) \times F(6))$
89432 := $((F(F(8)) + (F((9 + 4)))) \times F((3 \times 2)))$
89448 := $((F(F(8)) + (F((9 + 4)))) + F(F(4))) \times 8$
89464 := $(8 \times ((F((9 + 4)) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4))$
89472 := $((F(8) \times 9) + F(4)) \times F(F(7)) \times 2$
89488 := $((F(F(8)) + ((F(9) - 4)) \times 8)) \times 8$
89647 := $((-F(F(8))) + (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(4)) - F(F(7))))))$
89665 := $((-F(F(8))) + (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F((F(6) + (5)))))))$
89712 := $89 \times 7 \times F(12)$
89747 := $(F(8) - ((F(9) \times (-7)) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 7))))$
89768 := $((F(F(8)) + F(9)) + F(F(7))) + F(6)) \times 8$
89817 := $((F((F(8) - 9)) + F((F(8) - 1))) \times F(7))$
89964 := $F(8) \times F(9) \times (F(9) + F(6)) \times F(4)$
89968 := $((F(F(8)) - ((F(9) \times (-9)) + (6))) \times 8)$
89976 := $((F(F(8)) - ((9 + F(9)) \times (-7))) \times F(6))$
89984 := $(8 \times (((9 \times F(9)) + F(F(8))) - 4))$
91125 := $(F(9) + 11)^{-2+5}$
91145 := $9 + F(11) \times 4^5$
91146 := $((F(9) + 11)^{F(4)} + F(F(6)))$
91664 := $((F(F((9 - 1))) \times F(6)) + (F(6)^4))$
91728 := $(9 \times ((F((1 + F(7))) \times (-2)) + F(F(8))))$
91948 := $((-F(9)) + (F(19) \times (F(F(F(4))) + (F(8)))))$
91982 := $F(9 + 1 + 9) \times (F(8) + F(2))$
92274 := $(F((9 - F(2))) \times (2 \times (F(7)^{F(4)})))$
92449 := $((-F((9 + F((2 \times 4)))) - F(F(F(4)))) / (-9))$
92480 := $((F(9)^{-2+4}) \times 80)$
92626 := $(F((F(9)/2)) \times (-6 - (2^6)))$
92644 := $((-92) + (F((6 \times 4)) \times F(F(4))))$
92684 := $(F(9) \times (((-2) \times F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) / 4)$
92727 := $((-9) + (2 \times F(((F(7) - 2) + F(7)))))$
92728 := $((F(((9 + 2) + F(7))) \times 2) - 8)$
92732 := $((F(((9 + 2) + F(7))) - F(3)) \times 2)$
92733 := $((F(((9 + 2) + F(7))) \times F(3)) - 3)$
92734 := $((F(((9 + 2) + F(7))) \times F(3)) - F(F(4)))$
92736 := $((9 \times F(2)) - 7) \times F((3 \times F(6)))$
92738 := $((F((9 + 2)) + F(F(7)))^{F(3)} - F(F(8)))$
92742 := $((F(((9 + 2) + F(7))) + F(4)) \times 2)$
92744 := $((F(((9 + 2) + F(7))) + 4) \times F(F(4)))$
92745 := $((-9^2) \times ((F(F(7)) - 4) \times (-5)))$
92754 := $((9 + F((2 \times (7 + 5)))) \times F(F(4)))$
92784 := $(F(9) - (2 \times (-7) - F((8 \times F(4))))))$
92967 := $((-9) - ((-2) \times F(9)) \times 6) \times F(F(7))$
93068 := $((9 + (F(30)/F(6))) - F(F(8)))$
93312 := $((F(9) + F(3))^3 \times (1 \times 2))$
93314 := $((F(9) + F(3))^3 + 1) \times F(F(4))$
93346 := $F(9) + F(3) \times (F(3) + 4)^6$
93393 := $(F(9)^{F(3)} - 3) \times 9^{F(3)}$
93628 := $(9 \times F(3 + 6))^2 - 8$
93633 := $(9 \times F(3 + 6))^{F(3)} - 3$
93634 := $((9 \times F((3 + 6)))^{F(3)} - F(F(4)))$
93636 := $(9 \times F(3 + 6))^{F(-3+6)}$
93738 := $(F(9) \times (-((F(3)^{F(7)}) - 3)) + F(F(8)))$
93744 := $((93 \times 7) \times F((F(4) \times 4)))$
93765 := $((F(9) \times 3) - 7) \times F((F(F(6)) - 5))$
93906 := $(9 \times (-((F(3)^9)) + F(F(F(06)))))$
94365 := $((-9^{F(F(4))}) \times F(F((F(F(3)) + 6)))) \times (-5)$
94459 := $((F((F(9)/F(F(4)))) + 4) \times 59)$
94464 := $((F(9)/F(F(4)))^4 + F(F(F(6)))) - F(4)$
94467 := $((F(9)/F(F(4)))^4 + F((F(6) + F(7))))$
94488 := $((F(9)/F(F(4)))^4 + (F(8))) + F(F(8))$
94566 := $((F(9) \times (-4)) - (5^6)) \times (-6)$
94626 := $(9 \times (-((F(4) \times F((6 \times 2)))) + F(F(F(6)))))$
94647 := $((-9) - (-F(F(4)) \times F((F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))))) \times 7)$
94676 := $((-F(9)) - (F(-((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(6)))))) \times (7 - F(F(6)))))$
94792 := $((F(9)^{F(F(4))}) \times (-7) + F((9 + 2)))$
94986 := $(9 \times (-((4 \times 98)) + F(F(F(6)))))$
95297 := $((F((9 + 5)) - 2) + F(9)) \times F(F(7))$
95744 := $(F(9) \times ((5 + (F(F(7)) \times F(4))) \times 4))$
95766 := $((F((9 + 5)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + F(6))$
95774 := $((F(9) \times (F((5 + F(7))) + F(F(7)))) - 4)$
95778 := $(F(9) \times (((5 + 7) \times F(F(7))) + (F(8))))$
96228 := $(9 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (2 - (2^8))))$
96327 := $((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(3) + F(2))^7))$
96345 := $(9 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(3) - (F(4)^5))))$
96354 := $(9 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (-((3^5)) + F(4)))$
96372 := $(9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((3 + F(F(7))) + 2))$
96377 := $((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (-3 - F(F(7)))) - F(7))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 96378 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(3) + F(F(7)))))) - (F(8))) \\
 96396 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(-(F(3) - 9)))))) - (F(F(6)))) \\
 96417 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(-(4 - 17)))) \\
 96426 &:= (9 \times ((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) - F(F((F(2) + (6)))))) \\
 96435 &:= (9 \times ((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) - F(F((F(3) + (5)))))) \\
 96438 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(F((4 + 3)))))) + (F(8))) \\
 96444 &:= (9 \times ((F(F(F(6))) + F(4)) - F(F((F(4) + (4)))))) \\
 96453 &:= (9 \times ((F(F(F(6))) + 4) - F(F((5 + F(3)))))) \\
 96466 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(4))^{F(6)}) \times F(6))) \\
 96489 &:= (((-9) - (6^{F(4)})) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 96498 &:= (-9) \times (F(F((F(F(6))/F(4)))) + (-9 - F(F(8)))) \\
 96534 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F((5 \times F(3))) \times 4))) \\
 96674 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (-F(6)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(4))) \\
 96678 &:= (9 \times (((F(6) + F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 96684 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((-6) + F(8))) \times (-F(4))) \\
 96687 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F(6)) \times (-87))) \\
 96696 &:= (9 \times (((-F(6)) \times F(F(6))) - F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 96767 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(7))) - (F(6) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 96768 &:= ((-F(9)) + F((F(6) + (7)))) \times (F(6) \times F(8)) \\
 96795 &:= (9 \times ((-6) - F(F(7))) \times (-9 \times 5)) \\
 96849 &:= (((-9) \times F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) + (4) \times 9 \\
 96863 &:= ((F(9) - (-F(6)) \times F(F(8)))) + (F(F(6))³) \\
 96876 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(8) \times F(7)) \times (-6))) \\
 96896 &:= -((F((9 + F(6))) - ((F(F(8)) \times 9) - F(F(6)))) \\
 96912 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(9) + F(12)))) \\
 96917 &:= -((F((9 + F(6))) - (9 \times F(F((1 + 7)))))) \\
 96926 &:= (-F((9 + F(6)))) + (9 \times (F(2) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 96938 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F((F(9)/F(3))) - (F(8)))) \\
 96957 &:= ((-9) \times F(F(6))) \times (-9 \times 57)) \\
 96984 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(9) \times (8 - F(4)))) \\
 96998 &:= -((F((9 + F(6))) - (9 \times (9 + F(F(8)))))) \\
 97218 &:= (9 \times ((F((F(7) - F(2))) \times (-1)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 97236 &:= (9 \times (-((F((F(7) - F(2))) - F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 97333 &:= (-9 + F(7 + 3))³ - 3 \\
 97334 &:= (((-9) + F((7 + 3)))³ - F(F(4))) \\
 97336 &:= (-9 + F(7 + 3))⁻³⁺⁶ \\
 97344 &:= 9 \times F(7)^{F(3)} \times 4^{F(4)} \\
 97367 &:= ((F((F(9) - (7)))/F(3)) + (F(F(F(6)))/(-F(7)))) \\
 97417 &:= (9 + F(7) \times 4) \times F(17) \\
 97564 &:= (-F(9)) - ((F(F(7)) - ((5^{F(6)})/4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 97569 &:= ((F((F(9) - F(7))) + (-5) \times F(F(6)))) \times 9 \\
 97578 &:= (9 \times ((F(7) \times (5 - F(7))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 97627 &:= (((F(9) \times F(7)) - F(F(6))) - 2) \times F(F(7)) \\
 97644 &:= ((9 \times (F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F((4 \times 4)))) \\
 97672 &:= (((F(9) \times F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))) \\
 97682 &:= (F(9) \times F(7))⁻⁶⁺⁸/2 \\
 97743 &:= ((F((F(9) - (7))) - (F(F(7)) \times 4))/F(3)) \\
 97758 &:= (9 \times (-((7 \times (7 + 5))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 97826 &:= (-F(9)) - ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(8) - F(2))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 97839 &:= (9 \times ((-7) + F(F(8))) - ((F(3) \times F(9)))) \\
 97848 &:= (9 \times (-((78 - 4)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 97859 &:= (F((F(9) - (7))) - ((F(F(8)) + (5)) \times 9)) \\
 97866 &:= (9 \times ((-78) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6) \\
 97875 &:= ((F((9 + F(7))) + (8 \times F(F(7)))) \times 5) \\
 97884 &:= (9 \times ((-7) + F(F(8))) - ((F(8) \times F(4)))) \\
 97886 &:= (F(9) \times (F(F(7)) + ((F(8) \times F(8)) \times 6))) \\
 97896 &:= (F((F(9) - (7))) - ((F(F(8)) \times 9) + F(6))) \\
 97897 &:= (F((F(9) - (7))) + ((F(F(8)) \times (-9)) - (7))) \\
 9792 &:= (F(9) \times (F(F(7)) + F((9 + F(2)))) \\
 97938 &:= (9 \times (-((F(7) - 9)³)) + F(F(8))) \\
 97942 &:= ((-F(9)) - F(F(7))) - (F((9 \times F(4)))/(-2)) \\
 97947 &:= (9 \times (-((7 \times 9)) + F((F(4) \times 7)))) \\
 97967 &:= (F((F(9) - (7))) - (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 7))) \\
 97968 &:= ((9 \times (-((7 \times 9)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(8))) \\
 98019 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - F((01 + 9)))) \\
 98073 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (07^{F(3)}))) \\
 98136 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (F((1 \times 3)) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 98137 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(-((1 - 3) \times 7))) \\
 98163 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (F((1 + 6)) \times 3))) \\
 98192 &:= F(9) \times 8 \times (19²) \\
 98196 &:= (((-F(9)) + F(F(8))) + 1) \times 9 - F(F(6)) \\
 98199 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((1 + F(9)) \times (-9))) \\
 98208 &:= ((-F(9)) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + 08) \\
 98226 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (2 \times F((2 \times 6)))) \\
 98235 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((F(2) - (F(3)⁵)))) \\
 98243 &:= (F(9) - (F((F(8) + (2 + 4)))/(-F(3)))) \\
 98253 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - ((2⁵) - 3)) \\
 98257 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (257)) \\
 98258 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((2⁵) \times 8)) \\
 98262 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (26 + 2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98263 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - 2)) - F(F((F(6) - F(F(3))))) \\
 98266 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((2^{F(6)} - F(6))) \\
 98267 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((-2) + F(F(6))) \times F(7)) \\
 98271 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (27 \times 1))) \\
 98272 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(2))) + (F(F(7)) \times (-F(2)))) \\
 98273 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(2))) - (F(F(7)) - F(F(3)))) \\
 98274 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(2))) - (F(F(7)) - F(F(4)))) \\
 98275 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(2)) - F(F(7))) - (5) \\
 98276 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(2)) - F(F(7))) - (6) \\
 98277 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(2))) + (-F(7)) - F(F(7))) \\
 98278 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + 2)) - (F(F(7)) + (F(8)))) \\
 98281 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - F((F(2) \times F((8 - 1)))) \\
 98282 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(2)) - F(F((8 - F(2)))) \\
 98283 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + 2) - F(F((F(8)/3))) \\
 98284 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(-(F(2) - 8)))) + F(4) \\
 98286 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (2 + F(8)))) - F(F(6))) \\
 98287 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((2 - 8))) - F(F(7))) \\
 98289 &:= (((-F(9)) + F(F(8))) + (F(2) + 8)) \times 9) \\
 98294 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F((F(2) + 9)) \times 4)) \\
 98297 &:= (F(9) + (((F(F(8)) - 2) \times 9) - F(F(7))) \\
 98298 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - ((-2) + F(9)) - 8)) \\
 98307 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (30 - 7))) \\
 98316 &:= (9 \times ((F(F(8)) - F(F(3))) - F(F((1 \times 6)))) \\
 98317 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 1))) - F(F(7))) \\
 98323 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F((3 \times 2)))) - F(3)) \\
 98324 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F((3 \times 2)))) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 98325 &:= 9 \times (-F(8) + F(3 \times (2 + 5))) \\
 98334 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - ((-3) - F(3)) \times (-4))) \\
 98336 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(3) \times F((3 + F(6)))) \\
 98343 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - ((F(3)^4) + 3)) \\
 98346 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(3)^{F(4)}) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 98349 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (3 \times F((F(F(F(4))) + 9))) \\
 98352 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (3 \times (5 + F(2)))) \\
 98358 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (3 \times 5))) - (F(8))) \\
 98359 &:= (F(9) + ((F(F(8)) - F((3 + 5))) \times 9)) \\
 98361 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - ((3 \times 6) - 1)) \\
 98365 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - F((F(3) \times 6))) - (5)) \\
 98367 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F((F(3) + (6))) \times 7)) \\
 98369 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(3))) - F((F(F(6)) - 9))) \\
 98376 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (F(3)^{F(7)} + 6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98386 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(3) \times 8) \times F(6))) \\
 98388 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (3 \times (F(8) + F(8)))) \\
 98389 &:= (-98) + ((-3) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98393 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(3) + 9)^{F(3)})) \\
 98394 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(3))) - ((F(9) \times F(4)))) \\
 98397 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) \times F(F(3))) + (-9) \times F(7)) \\
 98398 &:= ((((-9) + F(F(8))) - 3) \times 9) - 8) \\
 98399 &:= ((((-9) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(3))) \times 9) - F(9) \\
 98406 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (4 + F(06)))) \\
 98412 &:= ((-F(9)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-F(4)))) \times (1 + 2) \\
 98424 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - ((4 + 2) + 4)) \\
 98425 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - F((4^2) - 5)) \\
 98426 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (-4) \times (-F(2)) - F(F(6)))) \\
 98427 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(4))) - F((-2) + F(7))) \\
 98429 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (-4) + F((2 + 9))) \\
 98432 &:= (((-9) + F(F(8))) \times (F(4)^{F(3)}) - F(2)) \\
 98433 &:= ((-9) + F(F(8))) \times ((4 \times 3) - 3) \\
 98434 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(F(4)))) - ((3^4))) \\
 98436 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F((4 + 3)) \times 6)) \\
 98437 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4^3) + F(7))) \\
 98438 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (-4) \times (F(3) - F(8))) \\
 98439 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (4))) - 39) \\
 98441 &:= ((9 \times (-8) + F(F((4 + 4)))) - 1) \\
 98442 &:= (9 \times (-8) + F(F(((4 \times 4)/2)))) \\
 98443 &:= ((9 \times (-8) + F(F((4 + 4)))) + F(F(3))) \\
 98444 &:= (-F(9)) + ((F(F(8)) - (4)) \times (F(4) \times F(4))) \\
 98445 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4^{F(4)} + 5))) \\
 98446 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(F(4)) \times F((F(4) + (6)))) \\
 98447 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (F(4) + F(4)))) - (F(7))) \\
 98448 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(4) + (F(4) \times F(8)))) \\
 98449 &:= F(9) + (8 - F(4)) \times F(4)^9 \\
 98451 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (F(4) + (5 - 1)))) \\
 98452 &:= ((9 \times ((F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) - (5))) + F(2)) \\
 98453 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (4))) - (5^{F(3)})) \\
 98454 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F(4) \times (-5 \times 4))) \\
 98455 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4 + 55)) \\
 98456 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(4))) - 56) \\
 98457 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (4))) - F((-5) + F(7))) \\
 98458 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(4))) - (58)) \\
 98459 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((4 - 59)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98471 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (4))) - (7 \times 1)) \\ 98472 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(4) \times (7 \times 2))) \\ 98473 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(4) \times F(7)) + F(3))) \\ 98474 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(4) + (7)) \times 4)) \\ 98475 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4 + (7 \times 5))) \\ 98476 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((4 - (7 \times 6)))) \\ 98477 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (4))) - (7/7)) \\ 98478 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4 \times 7) + 8)) \\ 98479 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(F(4)) \times F(7)) + 9)) \\ 98480 &:= (-(F(9)) - ((8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times (-F(F((8 + 0)))))) \\ 98481 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4 \times 8) + 1)) \\ 98482 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4 \times F((8 - 2)))) \\ 98483 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4 \times 8)) + F(F(3))) \\ 98484 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(4))) - (8 \times 4)) \\ 98485 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(4) \times 8) + (5))) \\ 98486 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(F(4)) \times (8 + 6))) \\ 98487 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(4)^{F(8)/7})) \\ 98488 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (((F(4) - F(8)) - 8))) \\ 98489 &:= (-(F(9)) + ((F((8/4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\ 98491 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(4))) - (F((9 - 1)))) \\ 98492 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4 + (9 \times 2))) \\ 98493 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(4) \times (9 - F(3)))) \\ 98494 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4 \times (9 - 4))) \\ 98495 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(4)))) - F(F(F((9 - 5)))) \\ 98496 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(4) + ((9 + 6)))) \\ 98497 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((-4) + F(9)) - F(7)) \\ 98498 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(4) + F(9)) - F(8))) \\ 98499 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (49 - F(9))) \\ 98504 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (5 \times F(F(04)))) \\ 98505 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (5/05))) \\ 98506 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(((5 \times 0) + 6))) \\ 98507 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((5 \times 0) + 7)) \\ 98509 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (5 + (0 \times 9))) \\ 98514 &:= 9 \times F((85 - 1)/4) \\ 98520 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (5 + F((2 + 0)))) \\ 98521 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 98522 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 \times 2) - 2)) \\ 98523 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 - 2) \times 3)) \\ 98524 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((5 \times (2 - 4)))) \\ 98525 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 + F(2)) + (5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98526 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F((5 - 2)) \times 6)) \\ 98527 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 + F(2)) + (7))) \\ 98528 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 + F(2)) + 8)) \\ 98529 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 + F(2)) + 9)) \\ 98531 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5 - 3))) - 1) \\ 98532 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F((5 - 3)) + F(2)))) \\ 98533 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F((5 + 3)) - F(3))) \\ 98534 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 \times F(F(3))) \times 4)) \\ 98535 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(((5 - F(3)) + (5)))) \\ 98536 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F((5 - 3))) + F(F(6))) \\ 98537 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 \times F(3)) + F(7))) \\ 98538 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 - F(3)) \times 8)) \\ 98539 &:= (F(9) + ((F(F(8)) - F((5 - 3))) \times 9)) \\ 98541 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5 - F((4 - 1)))) \\ 98542 &:= ((9 \times ((F(F(8)) + (5)) - F(F(4)))) + F(2)) \\ 98543 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - (5)) + F((F(4)^{F(3)})) \\ 98544 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F((5 + 4)) - (4))) \\ 98545 &:= ((9 \times ((F(F(8)) + (5)) - F(F(F(4)))) - (5)) \\ 98546 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 - F(F(F(4)))) \times F(6))) \\ 98547 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (5 + (4 \times 7))) \\ 98548 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(((5 - 4) + 8))) \\ 98549 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 - 4) + F(9))) \\ 98551 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5))) - F((5 + 1))) \\ 98552 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5))) - (5 + 2)) \\ 98553 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5))) - (5 + F(F(3)))) \\ 98554 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 + 5) \times 4)) \\ 98556 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5))) - (-5 + F(6))) \\ 98557 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5))) + ((5 - 7))) \\ 98558 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5))) - F(F(-(5 - 8)))) \\ 98559 &:= ((F((F(9) - (8 + 5))) + (5)) \times 9) \\ 98562 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5))) + (6/2)) \\ 98563 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5))) + (F(6)/F(3))) \\ 98564 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (5 \times (6 + 4))) \\ 98565 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (56 - 5)) \\ 98567 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 \times F(6)) + F(7))) \\ 98568 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5 + (F(6)/8)))) \\ 98569 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F((5 + 6)) - F(9))) \\ 98571 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (57 \times 1)) \\ 98572 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 57 + F(2) \\ 98573 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 57 + F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98574 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 57 + F(4) \\ 98577 &:= 9 \times (F((8-5) \times 7) + 7) \\ 98578 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((-5) + F(7)) \times 8) \\ 98586 &:= 9 \times (F(8+5+8) + F(6)) \\ 98592 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 + F(9)) \times 2)) \\ 98593 &:= (F(9) + (((F(F(8)) + 5) \times 9) \times F(F(3)))) \\ 98594 &:= ((F(9) + ((F(F(8)) + 5) \times 9)) + F(F(F(4)))) \\ 98595 &:= ((-9) - F(F(8))) \times ((5-9) - 5) \\ 98598 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (-((5-9) \times F(8))) \\ 98603 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + F((F(6) + 03))) \\ 98604 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (6 + 04))) \\ 98611 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(6) + F(11)))) \\ 98613 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(6) + (1 \times 3)))) \\ 98616 &:= (((-9) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(6) + 1)) + F(F(6))) \\ 98618 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F((6+1) \times 8)) \\ 98619 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6))) + (-1) + F(9)) \\ 98621 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (6 \times 2))) - 1) \\ 98622 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(6) + (2 + 2)))) \\ 98623 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (6 \times 2))) + F(F(3))) \\ 98624 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F((F(6) + 2) \times F(F(4)))) \\ 98628 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (-6) \times (2 - F(8))) \\ 98629 &:= (((-9) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(6) + F(2))) + F(9) \\ 98631 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((6 \times F(3)) + 1))) \\ 98632 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6) - F(F(3)))) + F(2) \\ 98633 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6) - F(F(3)))) + F(3) \\ 98634 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6) - F(F(3)))) + F(4) \\ 98637 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(6))) + F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(7)))))) \\ 98639 &:= (98 + ((F(F(F(6))) + 3) \times 9)) \\ 98642 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (64 \times 2)) \\ 98646 &:= ((9 \times ((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) - (4))) - F(F(6))) \\ 98647 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) \times 7)) \\ 98648 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)))) - F((F(F(4)) + 8))) \\ 98649 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F((F(6) + (4)))) - 9) \\ 98654 &:= ((9 \times ((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) - (5))) - (4)) \\ 98657 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((6 + 5) \times F(7))) \\ 98658 &:= (9 \times ((8 \times F((F(6) - (5)))) + F(F(8)))) \\ 98661 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F(F(6)) \times (6 + 1))) \\ 98664 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + (6)) + F((F(6) + (4)))) \\ 98666 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F(6) + F((6 + 6)))) \\ 98667 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + (6)) + (F(F(6)) \times 7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98673 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(6))) + (F(F(7)) - F(3))) \\ 98674 &:= (((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(6))) + F(F(7))) - F(F(F(4)))) \\ 98676 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((F(F(6))/7) \times 6))) \\ 98677 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (-6) + (F(7) \times F(7))) \\ 98681 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(6) \times F(8)) - 1)) \\ 98682 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(6) \times F(8)) \times F(2))) \\ 98683 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F(6) \times F(8))) + F(F(3))) \\ 98684 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F(6) \times F(8))) + F(F(4))) \\ 98685 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((6 + 8) + 5))) \\ 98688 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (-6) \times (-8 - F(8))) \\ 98692 &:= (-9) + (((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 9) - 2) \\ 98693 &:= (-9) + (((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 9) - F(F(3))) \\ 98694 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (6 \times (F(9) - (4)))) \\ 98703 &:= 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03)) \\ 98712 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F((7+1) + F(2)))) \\ 98726 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - F((2+6))) \\ 98728 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (-2) + F(8)) \\ 98729 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (2 \times 9)) \\ 98731 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (7 \times 31)) \\ 98733 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (73 \times 3)) \\ 98734 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F((7+3) \times (-4))) \\ 98736 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (3 + F(6))) \\ 98737 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (3 + 7)) \\ 98738 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - F(F(3))) - 8) \\ 98739 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - F(-((3-9))) \\ 98742 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (F(4) + 2)) \\ 98743 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (4)) \times F(F(3)) \\ 98744 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(7) \times F(F(4)))) - (4)) \\ 98745 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + ((F(4) - (5)))) \\ 98746 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - F(-((4-6))) \\ 98747 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) \times F(F((7-4)))) + F(F(7))) \\ 98748 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(7) \times (F(4) - F(8)))) \\ 98751 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (5 - 1)) \\ 98752 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (5 \times F(2))) \\ 98753 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (5)) + F(F(3)) \\ 98754 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (5)) + F(F(4)) \\ 98763 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (F(6) \times F(3))) \\ 98764 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(6))) - (4) \\ 98766 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((7 \times 6) \times 6)) \\ 98768 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F((7+6) + F(8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98773 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (F(7) \times F(3))) \\
 98774 &:= ((-9) + ((-F(8) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(7)))) \times F(F(4)) \\
 98775 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(7)))) + F((7 + 5))) \\
 98778 &:= (-9) + ((F((F(8) - (7))) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) \\
 98781 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + F((8 + 1))) \\
 98784 &:= 98 \times 7 \times F(8 + 4) \\
 98786 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (((F(7) + F(8)) \times F(6)))) \\
 98787 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(7) \times (-8 - F(7)))) \\
 98789 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (8 + F(9))) \\
 98793 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(7) + (9 \times F(3)))) \\
 98796 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(7) + F(9)) \times 6)) \\
 98811 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F((8 + 1)) - 1))) \\
 98815 &:= (((-F(9) - F(F(8))) \times (-8 + 1)) - (5)) \\
 98837 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (8 + F(3)))) + F(F(7))) \\
 98843 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F((8 \times F(F(4))))/3)) \\
 98847 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((8 \times F(4)) + F(7)))) \\
 98854 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((85 \times 4))) \\
 98856 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (8 + (5 \times 6)))) \\
 98872 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(8)))) + (F(7)^2)) \\
 98874 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (8 \times (7 - F(F(4)))))) \\
 98883 &:= (9 \times ((F(F(8)) + (F(8) + F(8))) - F(F(3)))) \\
 98886 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(8) + F(8)))) - (6)) \\
 98891 &:= (((F(9) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9) - 1 \\
 98892 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(8) \times (-9 \times 2))) \\
 98893 &:= (((F(9) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9) + F(F(3)) \\
 98894 &:= (((F(9) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9) + F(F(4)) \\
 98910 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(9) + 10))) \\
 98928 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (-9) + F((2 + 8)))) \\
 98937 &:= (9 \times (((F(F(8)) + F(9)) \times F(F(3))) + (F(7)))) \\
 98946 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((9 - F(4)) \times F(6)))) \\
 98956 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(9) \times (-5) - F(6))) \\
 98964 &:= (((-F(9) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) + F((F(6) + (4)))) \\
 98967 &:= (((-F(9) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) + (F(F(6)) \times 7)) \\
 98972 &:= (((-9) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) + (F((7 \times 2))) \\
 98974 &:= F(9) \times (F(8) \times F(9) + F(7)^{F(4)}) \\
 98976 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((9 + F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 98982 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((F(9) - 8) \times 2))) \\
 98988 &:= (((-F(9) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) - (-8) \times F(8)) \\
 99126 &:= (9 \times ((F(9) \times (1 \times 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 99144 &:= (F(9) \times ((9^{F(1 \times 4)}) \times 4)) \\
 99223 &:= (9 \times (F(9) + F(2)))^2 - F(3) \\
 99224 &:= (((9 \times (F(9) + F(2)))^2) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 99225 &:= (9 \times (F(9) + F(2)))^{F(-2+5)} \\
 99243 &:= (9 \times ((9^2) + F(F((4 \times F(3)))))) \\
 99246 &:= (((9 \times (F(9) + F(2)))^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(6))) \\
 99315 &:= (9 \times (F((9 + F(3))) + F(F(F((1 + 5)))))) \\
 99351 &:= (9 \times (93 + F(F(F((5 + 1)))))) \\
 99378 &:= (9 \times ((F((9 + F(3))) + (7)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 99396 &:= (9 \times ((9 + F((F(3) + 9))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 99398 &:= (-F(9) + (9 \times ((3 \times F(9)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 99432 &:= (9 \times ((F(9) \times F(4)) + F(F(F((3 \times 2)))))) \\
 99486 &:= (9 \times (((F(9) \times F(4)) + F(F(8))) + (6))) \\
 99648 &:= (9 \times (((F(9) + F(6)) \times F(4)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 99738 &:= (9 \times ((F(9) \times (7 - 3)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 99828 &:= (9 \times ((F((-9) + F(8))) + 2) + F(F(8))) \\
 99844 &:= (F(9) + (9 \times (F(F(8)) + F((F(4) \times 4)))) \\
 99846 &:= (9 \times ((F((-9) + F(8))) + (4)) + F(F(F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Selfie Numbers With Fibonacci Values: Reverse Order of Digits

This subsection brings **Fibonacci type selfie numbers** with basic operations. The results are in reverse order of digits. The work is up to 5 digits. This section is divided in three parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and consecutive in blocks of 10. The second part is with symmetrical and non consecutive results. The third part is for general values.

3.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$5490 := 0 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5491 := 1 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5492 := 2 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5493 := 3 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5494 := 4 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5495 := 5 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5496 := 6 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5497 := 7 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5498 := 8 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5499 := 9 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$7920 := 0 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7921 := 1 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7922 := 2 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7923 := 3 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7924 := 4 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7925 := 5 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7926 := 6 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7927 := 7 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7928 := 8 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7929 := 9 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$01440 := 0 + F(F(4) \times 4) \times 10$$

$$01441 := 1 + F(F(4) \times 4) \times 10$$

$$01442 := 2 + F(F(4) \times 4) \times 10$$

$$01443 := 3 + F(F(4) \times 4) \times 10$$

$$01444 := 4 + F(F(4) \times 4) \times 10$$

$$01445 := 5 + F(F(4) \times 4) \times 10$$

$$01446 := 6 + F(F(4) \times 4) \times 10$$

$$01447 := 7 + F(F(4) \times 4) \times 10$$

$$01448 := 8 + F(F(4) \times 4) \times 10$$

$$01449 := 9 + F(F(4) \times 4) \times 10$$

$$01650 := 0 + 5 \times 6 \times F(10)$$

$$01651 := 1 + 5 \times 6 \times F(10)$$

$$01652 := 2 + 5 \times 6 \times F(10)$$

$$01653 := 3 + 5 \times 6 \times F(10)$$

$$01654 := 4 + 5 \times 6 \times F(10)$$

$$01655 := 5 + 5 \times 6 \times F(10)$$

$$01656 := 6 + 5 \times 6 \times F(10)$$

$$01657 := 7 + 5 \times 6 \times F(10)$$

$$01658 := 8 + 5 \times 6 \times F(10)$$

$$01659 := 9 + 5 \times 6 \times F(10)$$

$$01680 := 0 + F(8) \times F(6) \times 10$$

$$01681 := 1 + F(8) \times F(6) \times 10$$

$$01682 := 2 + F(8) \times F(6) \times 10$$

$$01683 := 3 + F(8) \times F(6) \times 10$$

$$01684 := 4 + F(8) \times F(6) \times 10$$

$$01685 := 5 + F(8) \times F(6) \times 10$$

$$01686 := 6 + F(8) \times F(6) \times 10$$

$$01687 := 7 + F(8) \times F(6) \times 10$$

$$01688 := 8 + F(8) \times F(6) \times 10$$

$$01689 := 9 + F(8) \times F(6) \times 10$$

$$01870 := 0 + (F(7) + F(8)) \times F(10)$$

$$01871 := 1 + (F(7) + F(8)) \times F(10)$$

$$01872 := 2 + (F(7) + F(8)) \times F(10)$$

$$01873 := 3 + (F(7) + F(8)) \times F(10)$$

$$01874 := 4 + (F(7) + F(8)) \times F(10)$$

$$01875 := 5 + (F(7) + F(8)) \times F(10)$$

$$01876 := 6 + (F(7) + F(8)) \times F(10)$$

$$01877 := 7 + (F(7) + F(8)) \times F(10)$$

$$01878 := 8 + (F(7) + F(8)) \times F(10)$$

$$01879 := 9 + (F(7) + F(8)) \times F(10)$$

$$01890 := 0 + 9 \times F(8) \times 10$$

$$01891 := 1 + 9 \times F(8) \times 10$$

$$01892 := 2 + 9 \times F(8) \times 10$$

$$01893 := 3 + 9 \times F(8) \times 10$$

$$01894 := 4 + 9 \times F(8) \times 10$$

$$01895 := 5 + 9 \times F(8) \times 10$$

$$01896 := 6 + 9 \times F(8) \times 10$$

$$01897 := 7 + 9 \times F(8) \times 10$$

$$01898 := 8 + 9 \times F(8) \times 10$$

$$01899 := 9 + 9 \times F(8) \times 10$$

$$10980 := 0 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10981 := 1 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10982 := 2 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10983 := 3 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10984 := 4 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10985 := 5 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10986 := 6 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10987 := 7 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10988 := 8 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10989 := 9 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$13530 := 0 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$13531 := 1 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$13532 := 2 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$13533 := 3 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$13534 := 4 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$13535 := 5 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$13536 := 6 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$13537 := 7 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$13538 := 8 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$13539 := 9 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$14640 := 0 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14641 := 1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14642 := 2 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14643 := 3 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14644 := 4 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14645 := 5 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14646 := 6 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14647 := 7 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14648 := 8 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14649 := 9 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1$$

$$17640 := 0 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71$$

$$17641 := 1 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71$$

$$17642 := 2 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71$$

$$17643 := 3 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71$$

$$17644 := 4 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71$$

$$17645 := 5 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71$$

$$17646 := 6 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71$$

$$17647 := 7 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71$$

$$17648 := 8 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71$$

$$17649 := 9 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71$$

$$20970 := 0 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2)$$

$$20971 := 1 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2)$$

$$20972 := 2 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2)$$

$$20973 := 3 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2)$$

$$20974 := 4 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2)$$

$$20975 := 5 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2)$$

$$20976 := 6 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2)$$

$$20977 := 7 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2)$$

$$20978 := 8 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2)$$

$$20979 := 9 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2)$$

$$21960 := 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21961 := 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21962 := 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21963 := 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21964 := 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21965 := 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21966 := 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21967 := 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21968 := 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21969 := 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$22180 := 0 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2$$

$$22181 := 1 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2$$

$$22182 := 2 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2$$

$$22183 := 3 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2$$

$$22184 := 4 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2$$

$$22185 := 5 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2$$

$$22186 := 6 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2$$

$$22187 := 7 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2$$

$$22188 := 8 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2$$

$$22189 := 9 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2$$

$$25840 := 0 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$25841 := 1 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$25842 := 2 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$25843 := 3 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$25844 := 4 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$25845 := 5 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$25846 := 6 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$25847 := 7 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$25848 := 8 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$25849 := 9 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$28670 := 0 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28671 := 1 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28672 &:= 2 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28673 &:= 3 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28674 &:= 4 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28675 &:= 5 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28676 &:= 6 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28677 &:= 7 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28678 &:= 8 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28679 &:= 9 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28890 &:= 0 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28891 &:= 1 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28892 &:= 2 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28893 &:= 3 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28894 &:= 4 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28895 &:= 5 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28896 &:= 6 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28897 &:= 7 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28898 &:= 8 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2) \\ 28899 &:= 9 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32850 &:= 0 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3 \\ 32851 &:= 1 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3 \\ 32852 &:= 2 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3 \\ 32853 &:= 3 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3 \\ 32854 &:= 4 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3 \\ 32855 &:= 5 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3 \\ 32856 &:= 6 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3 \\ 32857 &:= 7 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3 \\ 32858 &:= 8 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3 \\ 32859 &:= 9 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32940 &:= 0 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32941 &:= 1 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32942 &:= 2 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32943 &:= 3 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32944 &:= 4 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32945 &:= 5 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32946 &:= 6 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32947 &:= 7 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32948 &:= 8 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$32949 := 9 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33490 &:= 0 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33491 &:= 1 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33492 &:= 2 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33493 &:= 3 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33494 &:= 4 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33495 &:= 5 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33496 &:= 6 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33497 &:= 7 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33498 &:= 8 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33499 &:= 9 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38760 &:= 0 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38761 &:= 1 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38762 &:= 2 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38763 &:= 3 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38764 &:= 4 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38765 &:= 5 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38766 &:= 6 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38767 &:= 7 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38768 &:= 8 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38769 &:= 9 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39270 &:= 0 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39271 &:= 1 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39272 &:= 2 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39273 &:= 3 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39274 &:= 4 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39275 &:= 5 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39276 &:= 6 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39277 &:= 7 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39278 &:= 8 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39279 &:= 9 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39360 &:= 0 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39361 &:= 1 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39362 &:= 2 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39363 &:= 3 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39364 &:= 4 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39365 &:= 5 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39366 &:= 6 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39367 &:= 7 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39368 &:= 8 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39369 &:= 9 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39770 &:= 0 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39771 &:= 1 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39772 &:= 2 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39773 &:= 3 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39774 &:= 4 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39775 &:= 5 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39776 &:= 6 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39777 &:= 7 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39778 &:= 8 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39779 &:= 9 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43640 &:= 0 + 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \\ 43641 &:= 1 + 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \\ 43642 &:= 2 + 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \\ 43643 &:= 3 + 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \\ 43644 &:= 4 + 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \\ 43645 &:= 5 + 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \\ 43646 &:= 6 + 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \\ 43647 &:= 7 + 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \\ 43648 &:= 8 + 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \\ 43649 &:= 9 + 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43760 &:= 0 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\ 43761 &:= 1 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\ 43762 &:= 2 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\ 43763 &:= 3 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\ 43764 &:= 4 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\ 43765 &:= 5 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\ 43766 &:= 6 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\ 43767 &:= 7 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\ 43768 &:= 8 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\ 43769 &:= 9 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43780 &:= 0 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4 \\ 43781 &:= 1 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4 \\ 43782 &:= 2 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4 \\ 43783 &:= 3 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4 \\ 43784 &:= 4 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4 \\ 43785 &:= 5 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4 \\ 43786 &:= 6 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4 \\ 43787 &:= 7 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4 \\ 43788 &:= 8 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4 \\ 43789 &:= 9 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43860 &:= 0 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\ 43861 &:= 1 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\ 43862 &:= 2 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\ 43863 &:= 3 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\ 43864 &:= 4 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\ 43865 &:= 5 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\ 43866 &:= 6 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\ 43867 &:= 7 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\ 43868 &:= 8 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\ 43869 &:= 9 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43880 &:= 0 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\ 43881 &:= 1 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\ 43882 &:= 2 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\ 43883 &:= 3 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\ 43884 &:= 4 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\ 43885 &:= 5 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\ 43886 &:= 6 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\ 43887 &:= 7 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\ 43888 &:= 8 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\ 43889 &:= 9 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44360 &:= 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\ 44361 &:= 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\ 44362 &:= 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\ 44363 &:= 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\ 44364 &:= 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\ 44365 &:= 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\ 44366 &:= 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\ 44367 &:= 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$44368 := 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4$$

$$44369 := 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4$$

$$46370 := 0 + F(F(7-3)) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46371 := 1 + F(F(7-3)) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46372 := 2 + F(F(7-3)) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46373 := 3 + F(F(7-3)) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46374 := 4 + F(F(7-3)) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46375 := 5 + F(F(7-3)) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46376 := 6 + F(F(7-3)) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46377 := 7 + F(F(7-3)) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46378 := 8 + F(F(7-3)) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46379 := 9 + F(F(7-3)) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46380 := 0 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4$$

$$46381 := 1 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4$$

$$46382 := 2 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4$$

$$46383 := 3 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4$$

$$46384 := 4 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4$$

$$46385 := 5 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4$$

$$46386 := 6 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4$$

$$46387 := 7 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4$$

$$46388 := 8 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4$$

$$46389 := 9 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4$$

$$46660 := 0 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46661 := 1 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46662 := 2 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46663 := 3 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46664 := 4 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46665 := 5 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46666 := 6 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46667 := 7 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46668 := 8 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46669 := 9 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46670 := 0 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46671 := 1 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46672 := 2 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46673 := 3 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46674 := 4 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46675 := 5 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46676 := 6 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46677 := 7 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46678 := 8 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46679 := 9 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46680 := 0 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46681 := 1 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46682 := 2 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46683 := 3 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46684 := 4 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46685 := 5 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46686 := 6 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46687 := 7 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46688 := 8 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46689 := 9 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46690 := 0 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46691 := 1 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46692 := 2 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46693 := 3 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46694 := 4 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46695 := 5 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46696 := 6 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46697 := 7 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46698 := 8 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46699 := 9 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$54290 := 0 + F(9+2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54291 := 1 + F(9+2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54292 := 2 + F(9+2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54293 := 3 + F(9+2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54294 := 4 + F(9+2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54295 := 5 + F(9+2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54296 := 6 + F(9+2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54297 := 7 + F(9+2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54298 := 8 + F(9+2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54299 := 9 + F(9+2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54560 &:= 0 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5+4)) \times 5 \\ 54561 &:= 1 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5+4)) \times 5 \\ 54562 &:= 2 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5+4)) \times 5 \\ 54563 &:= 3 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5+4)) \times 5 \\ 54564 &:= 4 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5+4)) \times 5 \\ 54565 &:= 5 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5+4)) \times 5 \\ 54566 &:= 6 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5+4)) \times 5 \\ 54567 &:= 7 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5+4)) \times 5 \\ 54568 &:= 8 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5+4)) \times 5 \\ 54569 &:= 9 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5+4)) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54670 &:= 0 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54671 &:= 1 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54672 &:= 2 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54673 &:= 3 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54674 &:= 4 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54675 &:= 5 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54676 &:= 6 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54677 &:= 7 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54678 &:= 8 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54679 &:= 9 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54680 &:= 0 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54681 &:= 1 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54682 &:= 2 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54683 &:= 3 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54684 &:= 4 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54685 &:= 5 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54686 &:= 6 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54687 &:= 7 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54688 &:= 8 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54689 &:= 9 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54690 &:= 0 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54691 &:= 1 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54692 &:= 2 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54693 &:= 3 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54694 &:= 4 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54695 &:= 5 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54696 &:= 6 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54697 &:= 7 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54698 &:= 8 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54699 &:= 9 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54710 &:= 0 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54711 &:= 1 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54712 &:= 2 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54713 &:= 3 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54714 &:= 4 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54715 &:= 5 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54716 &:= 6 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54717 &:= 7 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54718 &:= 8 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54719 &:= 9 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54720 &:= 0 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54721 &:= 1 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54722 &:= 2 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54723 &:= 3 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54724 &:= 4 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54725 &:= 5 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54726 &:= 6 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54727 &:= 7 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54728 &:= 8 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54729 &:= 9 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54730 &:= 0 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54731 &:= 1 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54732 &:= 2 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54733 &:= 3 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54734 &:= 4 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54735 &:= 5 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54736 &:= 6 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54737 &:= 7 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54738 &:= 8 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54739 &:= 9 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54740 &:= 0 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54741 &:= 1 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54742 &:= 2 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54743 &:= 3 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54744 &:= 4 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$54745 := 5 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54746 := 6 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54747 := 7 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54748 := 8 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54749 := 9 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54750 := 0 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54751 := 1 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54752 := 2 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54753 := 3 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54754 := 4 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54755 := 5 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54756 := 6 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54757 := 7 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54758 := 8 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54759 := 9 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54760 := 0 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54761 := 1 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54762 := 2 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54763 := 3 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54764 := 4 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54765 := 5 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54766 := 6 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54767 := 7 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54768 := 8 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54769 := 9 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54780 := 0 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54781 := 1 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54782 := 2 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54783 := 3 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54784 := 4 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54785 := 5 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54786 := 6 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54787 := 7 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54788 := 8 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54789 := 9 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54890 := 0 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54891 := 1 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54892 := 2 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54893 := 3 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54894 := 4 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54895 := 5 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54896 := 6 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54897 := 7 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54898 := 8 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54899 := 9 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$55870 := 0 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5$$

$$55871 := 1 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5$$

$$55872 := 2 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5$$

$$55873 := 3 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5$$

$$55874 := 4 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5$$

$$55875 := 5 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5$$

$$55876 := 6 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5$$

$$55877 := 7 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5$$

$$55878 := 8 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5$$

$$55879 := 9 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5$$

$$65660 := 0 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6))$$

$$65661 := 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6))$$

$$65662 := 2 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6))$$

$$65663 := 3 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6))$$

$$65664 := 4 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6))$$

$$65665 := 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6))$$

$$65666 := 6 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6))$$

$$65667 := 7 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6))$$

$$65668 := 8 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6))$$

$$65669 := 9 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6))$$

$$74290 := 0 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74291 := 1 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74292 := 2 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74293 := 3 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74294 := 4 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74295 := 5 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74296 := 6 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74297 := 7 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74298 := 8 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74299 := 9 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76720 &:= 0 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76721 &:= 1 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76722 &:= 2 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76723 &:= 3 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76724 &:= 4 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76725 &:= 5 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76726 &:= 6 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76727 &:= 7 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76728 &:= 8 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76729 &:= 9 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76860 &:= 0 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76861 &:= 1 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76862 &:= 2 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76863 &:= 3 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76864 &:= 4 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76865 &:= 5 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76866 &:= 6 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76867 &:= 7 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76868 &:= 8 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76869 &:= 9 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76890 &:= 0 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7)) \\ 76891 &:= 1 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7)) \\ 76892 &:= 2 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7)) \\ 76893 &:= 3 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7)) \\ 76894 &:= 4 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7)) \\ 76895 &:= 5 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7)) \\ 76896 &:= 6 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7)) \\ 76897 &:= 7 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7)) \\ 76898 &:= 8 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7)) \\ 76899 &:= 9 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 83620 &:= 0 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8)) \\ 83621 &:= 1 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8)) \\ 83622 &:= 2 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8)) \\ 83623 &:= 3 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8)) \\ 83624 &:= 4 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8)) \\ 83625 &:= 5 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8)) \\ 83626 &:= 6 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 83627 &:= 7 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8)) \\ 83628 &:= 8 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8)) \\ 83629 &:= 9 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 86880 &:= 0 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8 \\ 86881 &:= 1 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8 \\ 86882 &:= 2 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8 \\ 86883 &:= 3 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8 \\ 86884 &:= 4 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8 \\ 86885 &:= 5 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8 \\ 86886 &:= 6 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8 \\ 86887 &:= 7 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8 \\ 86888 &:= 8 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8 \\ 86889 &:= 9 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87360 &:= 0 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8))) \\ 87361 &:= 1 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8))) \\ 87362 &:= 2 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8))) \\ 87363 &:= 3 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8))) \\ 87364 &:= 4 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8))) \\ 87365 &:= 5 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8))) \\ 87366 &:= 6 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8))) \\ 87367 &:= 7 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8))) \\ 87368 &:= 8 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8))) \\ 87369 &:= 9 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87480 &:= 0 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8 \\ 87481 &:= 1 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8 \\ 87482 &:= 2 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8 \\ 87483 &:= 3 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8 \\ 87484 &:= 4 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8 \\ 87485 &:= 5 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8 \\ 87486 &:= 6 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8 \\ 87487 &:= 7 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8 \\ 87488 &:= 8 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8 \\ 87489 &:= 9 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87560 &:= 0 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8)) \\ 87561 &:= 1 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8)) \\ 87562 &:= 2 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8)) \\ 87563 &:= 3 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8)) \\ 87564 &:= 4 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87565 &:= 5 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8)) \\ 87566 &:= 6 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8)) \\ 87567 &:= 7 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8)) \\ 87568 &:= 8 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8)) \\ 87569 &:= 9 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87640 &:= 0 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\ 87641 &:= 1 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\ 87642 &:= 2 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\ 87643 &:= 3 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\ 87644 &:= 4 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\ 87645 &:= 5 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\ 87646 &:= 6 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\ 87647 &:= 7 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\ 87648 &:= 8 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\ 87649 &:= 9 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87680 &:= 0 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\ 87681 &:= 1 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\ 87682 &:= 2 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\ 87683 &:= 3 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\ 87684 &:= 4 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\ 87685 &:= 5 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\ 87686 &:= 6 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\ 87687 &:= 7 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\ 87688 &:= 8 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\ 87689 &:= 9 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87840 &:= 0 + F(4+8) \times F(7+8) \\ 87841 &:= 1 + F(4+8) \times F(7+8) \\ 87842 &:= 2 + F(4+8) \times F(7+8) \\ 87843 &:= 3 + F(4+8) \times F(7+8) \\ 87844 &:= 4 + F(4+8) \times F(7+8) \\ 87845 &:= 5 + F(4+8) \times F(7+8) \\ 87846 &:= 6 + F(4+8) \times F(7+8) \\ 87847 &:= 7 + F(4+8) \times F(7+8) \\ 87848 &:= 8 + F(4+8) \times F(7+8) \\ 87849 &:= 9 + F(4+8) \times F(7+8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88450 &:= 0 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\ 88451 &:= 1 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88452 &:= 2 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\ 88453 &:= 3 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\ 88454 &:= 4 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\ 88455 &:= 5 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\ 88456 &:= 6 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\ 88457 &:= 7 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\ 88458 &:= 8 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\ 88459 &:= 9 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88720 &:= 0 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\ 88721 &:= 1 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\ 88722 &:= 2 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\ 88723 &:= 3 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\ 88724 &:= 4 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\ 88725 &:= 5 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\ 88726 &:= 6 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\ 88727 &:= 7 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\ 88728 &:= 8 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\ 88729 &:= 9 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 89670 &:= 0 + 7 \times F(6+9) \times F(8) \\ 89671 &:= 1 + 7 \times F(6+9) \times F(8) \\ 89672 &:= 2 + 7 \times F(6+9) \times F(8) \\ 89673 &:= 3 + 7 \times F(6+9) \times F(8) \\ 89674 &:= 4 + 7 \times F(6+9) \times F(8) \\ 89675 &:= 5 + 7 \times F(6+9) \times F(8) \\ 89676 &:= 6 + 7 \times F(6+9) \times F(8) \\ 89677 &:= 7 + 7 \times F(6+9) \times F(8) \\ 89678 &:= 8 + 7 \times F(6+9) \times F(8) \\ 89679 &:= 9 + 7 \times F(6+9) \times F(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98370 &:= 0 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98371 &:= 1 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98372 &:= 2 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98373 &:= 3 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98374 &:= 4 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98375 &:= 5 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98376 &:= 6 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98377 &:= 7 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98378 &:= 8 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98379 &:= 9 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98460 &:= 0 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98461 &:= 1 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98462 &:= 2 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98463 &:= 3 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98464 &:= 4 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98465 &:= 5 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98466 &:= 6 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98467 &:= 7 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98468 &:= 8 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98469 &:= 9 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98510 &:= 0 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98511 &:= 1 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98512 &:= 2 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98513 &:= 3 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98514 &:= 4 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98515 &:= 5 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98516 &:= 6 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98517 &:= 7 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98518 &:= 8 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98519 &:= 9 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98580 &:= 0 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98581 &:= 1 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98582 &:= 2 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98583 &:= 3 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98584 &:= 4 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98585 &:= 5 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98586 &:= 6 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98587 &:= 7 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98588 &:= 8 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98589 &:= 9 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98820 &:= 0 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98821 &:= 1 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98822 &:= 2 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98823 &:= 3 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98824 &:= 4 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98825 &:= 5 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98826 &:= 6 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98827 &:= 7 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98828 &:= 8 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98829 &:= 9 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Symmetric and Non Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned} 0105 &:= 50 + F(10) \\ 0127 &:= 72 + F(10) \\ 0138 &:= 83 + F(10) \\ 0149 &:= 94 + F(10) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 00134 &:= F(F(4))^{F(3)} + 100 \\ 00234 &:= F(F(4))^{F(3)} + 200 \\ 00334 &:= F(F(4))^{F(3)} + 300 \\ 00434 &:= F(F(4))^{F(3)} + 400 \\ 00534 &:= F(F(4))^{F(3)} + 500 \\ 00634 &:= F(F(4))^{F(3)} + 600 \\ 00734 &:= F(F(4))^{F(3)} + 700 \\ 00834 &:= F(F(4))^{F(3)} + 800 \\ 00934 &:= F(F(4))^{F(3)} + 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 00136 &:= 6^{F(3)} + 100 \\ 00236 &:= 6^{F(3)} + 200 \\ 00336 &:= 6^{F(3)} + 300 \\ 00436 &:= 6^{F(3)} + 400 \\ 00536 &:= 6^{F(3)} + 500 \\ 00636 &:= 6^{F(3)} + 600 \\ 00736 &:= 6^{F(3)} + 700 \\ 00836 &:= 6^{F(3)} + 800 \\ 00936 &:= 6^{F(3)} + 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 00163 &:= 3 \times F(F(6)) + 100 \\ 00263 &:= 3 \times F(F(6)) + 200 \\ 00363 &:= 3 \times F(F(6)) + 300 \\ 00463 &:= 3 \times F(F(6)) + 400 \\ 00563 &:= 3 \times F(F(6)) + 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$00663 := 3 \times F(F(6)) + 600$$

$$00763 := 3 \times F(F(6)) + 700$$

$$00863 := 3 \times F(F(6)) + 800$$

$$00963 := 3 \times F(F(6)) + 900$$

$$00164 := F(F(4))^6 + 100$$

$$00264 := F(F(4))^6 + 200$$

$$00364 := F(F(4))^6 + 300$$

$$00464 := F(F(4))^6 + 400$$

$$00564 := F(F(4))^6 + 500$$

$$00664 := F(F(4))^6 + 600$$

$$00764 := F(F(4))^6 + 700$$

$$00864 := F(F(4))^6 + 800$$

$$00964 := F(F(4))^6 + 900$$

$$00184 := 4 \times F(8) + 100$$

$$00284 := 4 \times F(8) + 200$$

$$00384 := 4 \times F(8) + 300$$

$$00484 := 4 \times F(8) + 400$$

$$00584 := 4 \times F(8) + 500$$

$$00684 := 4 \times F(8) + 600$$

$$00784 := 4 \times F(8) + 700$$

$$00884 := 4 \times F(8) + 800$$

$$00984 := 4 \times F(8) + 900$$

3.3 General Representations

Remark 3.1. Most of the *selfie numbers* appearing below are with lot of extra brackets "**(...)**". These can be removed easily after making simplifications.

$$34 := F((F(4)^{F(3)}))$$

$$36 := (6^{F(3)})$$

$$55 := F((5 + 5))$$

$$63 := (3 \times F(F(6)))$$

$$64 := (F(F(4))^6)$$

$$84 := 4 \times F(8)$$

$$143 := F(3 \times 4) - 1$$

$$144 := F(4 \times (4 - 1))$$

$$168 := F(8) \times F(6) \times 1$$

$$189 := 9 \times F(8) \times 1$$

$$231 := F(13) - 2$$

$$233 := F(F(((3 \times 3) - 2)))$$

$$234 := (F(F((4 + 3))) + F(2))$$

$$235 := (F(F((5 + F(3)))) + 2)$$

$$237 := (F(F(7)) + (F(3) + 2))$$

$$243 := 3^{F(4)+2}$$

$$256 := ((F(F(6)) - (5))^2)$$

$$267 := (F(F(7)) + F((F(6) + F(2))))$$

$$374 := (-F(4) + F((7 \times F(3))))$$

$$376 := (F((F(F(6)) - (7))) - F(F(3)))$$

$$377 := F(-7 + 7 \times 3)$$

$$378 := (F((F(8) - (7))) + F(F(3)))$$

$$438 := F(8)^{F(3)} - F(4)$$

$$466 := (F((-F(6)) + F(F(6)))) \times F(F(4))$$

$$472 := (2 \times (F(F(7)) + F(4)))$$

$$474 := ((4 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$484 := ((F(F(F(4))) + (F(8)))^{F(F(4))})$$

$$693 := -(((F(F(3)) - F(9)) \times F(F(6))))$$

$$882 := 2 \times F(8) \times F(8)$$

$$986 := (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9)$$

$$0134 := F(4 \times 3) - 10$$

$$0136 := (-F(6) + F((F(3) + 10)))$$

$$0137 := (-7) + F((F(3) + 10))$$

$$0142 := (-2) + F((F(F(4)) + 10))$$

$$0147 := (7 \times F(F(-(4 - 10))))$$

$$0165 := (-5 + F(6)) \times F(10)$$

$$0174 := ((-4) + F(F(7))) - (F(10))$$

$$0186 := 6 \times (F(8) + 10)$$

$$0233 := F(33 - 20)$$

$$0247 := (-F(7)) \times (F(F(F(4))) - (20))$$

$$0253 := (F(F((F(3) + (5)))) + (20))$$

$$0287 := 7 \times (F(8) + 20)$$

$$0347 := (F((7 \times F(F(4)))) - (30))$$

$$0377 := F(((7 + 7) + (3 \times 0)))$$

$$0417 := (F((F(7) + 1)) + 40)$$

$$0488 := 8 \times (F(8) + 40)$$

$$0568 := 8 \times (F(F(6)) + 50)$$

$$1165 := (5 \times F(F(((6 \times 1) + 1))))$$

$$1175 := (5 \times (F(F(7)) + (1 + 1)))$$

$$1178 := F(8) + F(7) \times F(11)$$

$$1292 := F(2 \times 9) / 2 \times 1$$

$$1293 := ((F((F(3) \times 9)) / 2) + 1)$$

$$1367 := ((F(F(7)) \times 6) - (31))$$

$$1397 := ((F(F(7)) \times (9 - 3)) - 1)$$

$$1536 := F(6)^3 \times F(5 - 1)$$

$$1546 := (F((F(F(6)) - (4))) - (51))$$

$$1576 := ((F(F(6)) \times 75) + 1)$$

$$1589 := F(9 + 8) - F(5 + 1)$$

$$1594 := (-F(4) + F((9 + F((5 + 1))))))$$

$$1596 := (F((F(6) + 9)) - F(F(F((5 - 1))))))$$

$$1597 := F((F(7) + ((9 - 5) \times 1)))$$

$$1598 := (F((F(8) - (9 - 5))) + 1)$$

$$1618 := F(8) + F(16 + 1)$$

$$1631 := F(13) \times (6 + 1)$$

$$1684 := ((F(F(4)) \times F(F(8))) / F((6 + 1)))$$

$$1687 := ((F(F(7)) + 8) \times (6 + 1))$$

$$1764 := ((-4) \times F(F(6))) \times (-F((7 + 1)))$$

$$1778 := ((-F(8)) - F(F(7))) \times (-7 \times 1))$$

$$1847 := (((F(F(7)) - F(F(4))) \times 8) - 1)$$

$$1848 := 84 \times (F(8) + 1)$$

$$1856 := F(6) \times (F(5 + 8) - 1)$$

$$1862 := (-2) - (-F(6) \times F(F((8 - 1))))$$

$$1863 := ((F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 81)$$

$$1864 := ((F(F(4)) + (6)) \times F(F((8 - 1))))$$

$$1865 := ((F((5 + F(6))) \times 8) + 1)$$

$$1871 := (((-1) - F(F(7))) \times (-8)) - 1)$$

$$1872 := ((-F(2)) - F(F(7))) \times (-8 \times 1))$$

$$1873 := (((F(F(3)) + F(F(7))) \times 8) + 1)$$

$$1877 := (F(7) - (F(F(7)) \times (-8 \times 1)))$$

$$1885 := (5 \times F((F(8) - (8 - 1))))$$

$$1897 := 7 \times (F(9) \times 8 - 1)$$

$$1925 := F(5 \times 2) \times (F(9) + 1)$$

$$1972 := 2 \times (F(7 + 9) - 1)$$

$$1973 := F(3) \times F(7 + 9) - 1$$

$$1974 := (F(F(4)) \times F(((7 + 9) \times 1)))$$

$$2079 := (9 \times (F(F(7)) - 02))$$

$$2097 := (F(F(7)) \times (9 + (0 \times 2)))$$

$$2176 := -((F(F(6)) - (F(7)^{1+2})))$$

$$2197 := F(7)^{9/(1+2)}$$

$$2296 := (-F(6) + F(9)^2) \times 2$$

$$2478 := (-F(8)) \times ((F(F(7)) + F(4)) / (-2))$$

$$2529 := F(9 \times 2) - F(5 \times 2)$$

$$2563 := ((3 + F(6)) \times F(F((5 + 2))))$$

$$2576 := -F(6) + F(-7 + 5^2)$$

$$2577 := -7 + F(-7 + 5^2)$$

$$2578 := ((-8) + F((F(7) + (5)))) + 2$$

$$2581 := F(18) - 5 + 2$$

$$2582 := -2 + F(8 + 5 \times 2)$$

$$2583 := (F((-3) + F(8))) - F(F((5 - 2)))$$

$$2584 := F((-4 + 8) \times 5 - 2)$$

$$2585 := F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2)$$

$$2586 := F(6 \times (8 - 5)) + 2$$

$$2592 := (F((2 \times 9)) + F((5 + F(2))))$$

$$2594 := (F((F(F(4)) \times 9)) + (5 \times 2))$$

$$2597 := (F(7) + F((9 \times F((5 - 2)))))$$

$$2639 := (F((9 \times F(3))) + F((F(6) + 2)))$$

$$2645 := (5 \times ((F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))^2))$$

$$2646 := (F((6 \times F(4))) + 62)$$

$$2648 := (F((F(8) - F(4))) + ((F(6)^2)))$$

$$2667 := (((F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(6))) / 2)$$

$$2688 := 8 \times F(8) \times F(6) \times 2$$

$$2704 := (4 \times F(07))^2$$

$$2736 := ((F(F(6)) - F(3)) \times F((F(7) - F(2))))$$

$$2772 := ((2 - F(F(7))) \times (-F(7) - F(2)))$$

$$2784 := ((4 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(2)))$$

$$2794 := (((F(4) + 9) \times F(F(7))) - 2)$$

$$2796 := ((F(F(6)) - 9) \times F((F(7) \times F(2))))$$

$$2798 := (((F(8) - 9) \times F(F(7))) + 2)$$

$$2817 := (F(F(7)) + F(((1 + 8) \times 2)))$$

$$2937 := (F((F(7) - F(3))) \times (F(9) - F(2)))$$

$$3025 := F(5 \times 2)^{F(03)}$$

$$3087 := 7 \times F(8)^{F(03)}$$

$$3136 := ((F((F(6) + F(3))) + 1)^{F(3)})$$

$$3194 := (F(F(4)) \times F((F(9) / F((1 \times 3))))))$$

- 3196** := ((F((F(6) + 9)) + 1) × F(3))
3249 := ((F((9 + F(F(F(4)))))) + 2)^{F(3)}
3364 := (F(4 + 6) + 3)^{F(3)}
3372 := (2 + F(7))³ - 3
3373 := (F(3) + F(7))³ - F(3)
3374 := (((F(F(4)) + (F(7)))³) - F(F(3)))
3376 := (((F(6) + (7))³) + F(F(3)))
3381 := ((F((-1) + F(8)) - 3)/F(3))
3382 := ((-F(2)) + F((F(8) - F(F(3)))))/F(3))
3383 := ((F(F(3)) + F((F(8) - F(F(3)))))/F(3))
3384 := ((F(4) + F((F(8) - F(F(3)))))/F(3))
3385 := ((-5) - F((F(8) - F(F(3)))))/(-F(3))
3495 := 5 × F(9 + 4) × 3
3528 := F(8)² × (5 + 3)
3569 := (((-F(9)) × F(F(6))) × (-5)) - F(F(3)))
3575 := ((5 × F(7)) × F((5 × F(3))))
3628 := (-F(8)) - ((-F(2)) - F(F(F(6))))/3)
3635 := 5 × (3⁶ - F(3))
3639 := (-9) + ((-F(3)) + F(F(F(6))))/3)
3644 := (-4) - ((-F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))))/(-3))
3645 := 5 × (F(4) + 6)³
3646 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(4)) + (6)))/3)
3647 := (((-7) + F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))))/3)
3648 := ((F(F(8)) - F(F(4)))/(6 - 3))
3649 := ((F(F((9/F(4)))) + F(F(F(6))))/3)
3652 := (((2 × 5) + F(F(F(6))))/3)
3653 := ((F((F(3) + (5))) + F(F(F(6))))/3)
3664 := ((46 + F(F(F(6))))/3)
3666 := (6 × (F((-6) + F(F(6)))) + F(F(3)))
3694 := (((4 × F(9)) + F(F(F(6))))/3)
3718 := (F(8) + 1) × F(7)^{F(3)}
3726 := (((F(6) × 2) × F(F(7))) - F(3))
3728 := ((-8) × F((F(2) × F(7)))) × (-F(3))
3736 := (F(6) × ((F(3) × F(F(7))) + F(F(3))))
3738 := ((F(8) × F(3)) × F((F(7) - F(3))))
3744 := (F((F(4) × 4)) × (F(7) × F(3)))
3773 := (-F(3) + F(7)) × 7³
3786 := (-6) × (-F(8)) - F((F(7) + F(3)))
3789 := ((-9) × F(F(8)))/(-F(7) × F(3))
3796 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(9) × F(7)))/3)
3844 := (((F(F(F(4))) - ((F(4) × F(8))))^{F(3)})
3864 := (-4) × (F(F(6)) - F((8 × F(3))))
3927 := ((F(F(7)) - 2) × (F(9)/F(3)))
3948 := (F((F(8) - F(F(4)))) - F(F((9 - F(3))))
3961 := (F(F((1 + 6))) × (F(9)/F(3)))
3966 := (((F(F(6)) × F(F(6))) × 9) - 3)
3968 := (((F(8) × F(F(6))) × 9) - F(F(3)))
3969 := (9 × 6 + 9)^{F(3)}
3979 := (((F(9) × F(7)) × 9) + F(F(3)))
3999 := (9 + F(9)) × 93
4096 := F(6)^{9×0+4}
4147 := (7 + 4) × F(14)
4167 := (F((F(7) + (6))) - 14)
4176 := (F((6 + F(7))) - (1 + 4))
4177 := (F((F(7) + (7 - 1))) - (4))
4181 := F(18 + 1⁴)
4182 := F(2) + F((F(8) + 1) - F(4))
4183 := F(3) + F((F(8) + 1) - F(4))
4184 := F(4) + F((F(8) + 1) - F(4))
4277 := (7 × (F((F(7) + 2)) + F(F(F(4))))
4356 := ((65 + F(F(3)))^{F(F(4))})
4373 := (((3⁷) × F(3)) - F(F(F(4))))
4374 := F(4)⁷ × (-F(3) + 4)
4378 := ((-8) + (F(7)³) × F(F(4)))
4394 := (((4 + 9)³) × F(F(4)))
4427 := (F(F(7)) × (-2) + F((4 + 4)))
4428 := ((-F((F(8) + F(2)))) - F(F(F(4))))/(-4))
4455 := 55 × F(4)⁴
4536 := ((6³) × F((5 + F(4))))
4576 := ((F(F(6)) - (F(F(7)) × 5)) × (-4))
4578 := (F(8) × (F(F(7)) - (5 × F(4))))
4624 := ((4 + (2⁶))^{F(F(4))})
4647 := ((F(F(7)) × F(F(4))) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))))
4693 := ((F(3)⁹) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))))
4736 := F(6)^{F(3)} × 74
4746 := (F(F(6)) × ((-F(4) + F(F(7))) - (4)))
4765 := (5 × (F(F(6)) + (F(F(7)) × 4)))
4766 := ((F(F(6)) × (-6) + F(F(7))) - F(F(F(4))))
4767 := ((F(F(7)) - (6)) × (7 × F(4)))

- 4768** := $((-F(8)) \times (6 - F(F(7)))) + F(F(F(4)))$
4776 := $(F(6) \times (-F(7) + F((F(7) + F(F(4)))))$
4781 := $F(18) + F(7)^{F(4)}$
4788 := $(-F(8)) \times ((8 - F(F(7))) - F(4))$
4791 := $F(1 + 9 + 7) \times F(4)$
4847 := $((F(F(7)) - F(F(4))) \times F(8)) - (4)$
4864 := $((F(F(4))^{F(6)}) \times (F(8) - F(F(4))))$
4871 := $((1 - F(F(7))) \times (-F(8))) - F(F(F(4)))$
4872 := $((F(2) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(8))) \times F(F(F(4)))$
4873 := $((F(F(3)) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(8))) + F(F(F(4)))$
4874 := $((F(F(F(4))) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(8))) + F(F(4))$
4876 := $F(6) \times F(7 + 8) - 4$
4877 := $(-F(7) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(8)) - F(4)))$
4878 := $(8 \times F((7 + 8))) - F(F(4))$
4887 := $((F(F(7)) \times F(8)) - 8) + F(F(4))$
4889 := $(F((F(9) - F(8))) \times F(8)) - (4)$
4892 := $(F(F(-(2 - 9))) \times F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))$
4893 := $-3 + F(9) \times F(8 + 4)$
4894 := $(-F(F(4)) - (F(9) \times F((8 + 4))))$
4896 := $6 \times F(9) \times 8 \times F(4)$
4899 := $(F(9) \times F((-9) + F(8))) + F(4)$
4913 := $(-F(3) + 19)^{F(4)}$
4935 := $5 \times F(3 + 9 + 4)$
4956 := $(F(F(6)) \times (59 \times 4))$
4964 := $((F(4)^{F(6)}) - F((F(9)/F(F(4))))$
4987 := $((F(F(7)) \times F(8)) + (94))$
4998 := $(-((F(8) \times F(9))) \times (-9) + F(F(4)))$
5346 := $((F(F(6)) + F(F(F(4)))) \times (3^5))$
5376 := $(F(F(6)) \times (F(7) + (3^5)))$
5428 := $((F(F(8))/2) - 45)$
5464 := $(-4) - ((F(F(F(6)))/(-F(F(4)))) + (5))$
5468 := $((F(F(8)))/(6 - 4)) - (5)$
5469 := $(-9) + ((F(F(F(6)))/F(F(4))) + (5))$
5473 := $F(3 \times 7)/(-F(4) + 5)$
5478 := $((F(F(8)))/F((7 - 4))) + (5)$
5486 := $(F(6) + ((F(F(8)))/F(F(4))) + (5))$
5528 := $((F(F(8))/2) + (55))$
5675 := $(-5) \times ((F(F(7)) - (6)) \times (-5))$
5679 := $((-9) \times F(F(7))) + ((6^5))$
5728 := $F(8)^2 \times F(7) - 5$
5738 := $F(8)^{F(3)} \times F(7) + 5$
5785 := $(-5) \times (8 - (F(F(7)) \times 5))$
5825 := $5^2 \times F(8 + 5)$
6327 := $(-((F(F(7)) + (F(2) - (3^{F(6)}))))$
6328 := $(-((F(F((8 - F(2)))) - (3^{F(6)})))$
6394 := $((4 \times F((F(9)/F(3)))) + (6))$
6408 := $((80^{F(F(4))}) + F(6))$
6417 := $(-((F((F(7) - 1)) - (F(4)^{F(6)})))$
6456 := $((F(F(6)) \times (-5)) + (F(4)^{F(6)}))$
6472 := $(-((F((-2) + F(7))) - (F(4)^{F(6)})))$
6489 := $-9 \times 8 + F(4)^{F(6)}$
6493 := $-F(3) \times F(9) + F(4)^{F(6)}$
6561 := $1 \times (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)}$
6562 := $F(2) + (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)}$
6563 := $F(3) + (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)}$
6564 := $F(4) + (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)}$
6676 := $(F(F(F(6))) - (7 \times F((-6) + F(F(6))))$
6736 := $((F(F(F(6)))/F(F(3)) \times F(7)) \times F(6))$
6744 := $(F(((F(4)^{F(4)}) - (7))) - F(F(6)))$
6746 := $(F((F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))) - (F(7) + (6)))$
6757 := $(F(F(7)) \times ((5 \times 7) - 6))$
6763 := $(-F(3) + F((F(F(6)) - (7 - 6))))$
6764 := $(F((F(4) + F(6))) \times 76)$
6765 := $F(-56 + 76)$
6771 := $(F(((1 \times 7) + F(7))) + (6))$
6772 := $((-F(2) + F((F(7) + (7)))) + F(6))$
6773 := $((F(F(3)) \times F((F(7) + (7)))) + F(6))$
6774 := $((F(4) + F((F(7) + (7)))) + (6))$
6778 := $((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) - F((F(7) + (6))))$
6784 := $(-4) \times ((F(8) - F(F(7))) \times F(6))$
6786 := $(F(F(6)) + F((F(8) - (7 - 6))))$
6799 := $(F(9) + F(((F(9) + (7)) - F(F(6))))$
6867 := $(-7) \times (6 - F((8 + F(6))))$
6936 := $F(6 + 3) \times F(9) \times 6$
6954 := $(F((4 \times 5)) - (-9) \times F(F(6)))$
6977 := $(-F(7) + (F(F(7)) \times (9 + F(F(6))))$
6993 := $((3 + F(9)) \times 9) \times F(F(6))$
7163 := $((-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times F((1 + F(7))))$
7223 := $((32 - F(2)) \times F(F(7)))$

$$7392 := ((-2) + F(9)) \times (-F(3) + F(F(7)))$$

$$7448 := (-8) \times (F(F(F(4))) - (4 \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7456 := (((F(F(6)) - 5) \times F(F(4))) \times F(F(7)))$$

$$7458 := ((85^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(7)))$$

$$7463 := (-((3^6)) + (F(F(4))^{F(7)}))$$

$$7464 := (F(-((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(6)))))) + (F(4) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7476 := (F(F(6)) \times ((7^{F(4)}) + F(7)))$$

$$7543 := (((F(3) + 4)^5) - F(F(7)))$$

$$7648 := ((8 \times 4) \times (6 + F(F(7))))$$

$$7663 := ((F((F(3) \times F(6))) \times F(6)) - F(F(7)))$$

$$7689 := ((F(9) - F((8 - 6))) \times F(F(7)))$$

$$7697 := ((F(7) \times F((9 + 6))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$7756 := 6^5 - F(7) - 7$$

$$7759 := ((F(9) \times (-5) + F(F(7)))) + (7)$$

$$7776 := 6^{F(7)-F(-7+F(7))}$$

$$7865 := ((-5) + F((-6) + F(8))) \times F(7)$$

$$7875 := (-5) \times ((F(F(7)) - 8) \times (-7))$$

$$7883 := ((F((F(3) \times 8) \times 8) - (F(7)))$$

$$7896 := F(6) \times 987$$

$$7902 := (-20) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7)))$$

$$7911 := (-11) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7)))$$

$$7916 := (-6) + (F((1 \times 9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7917 := (F((F(7) + 1)) \times (F(9) - F(7)))$$

$$7923 := F(F(3)) + F(2) \times F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7924 := F(F(4)) + F(2) \times F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7934 := ((4 \times 3) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7935 := (F((5 + F(3))) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7937 := ((F(7) + F(3)) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7938 := ((8 \times F(3)) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7939 := ((F(9)/F(3)) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7943 := (F((F(3)^{F(4)})) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7946 := ((6 \times 4) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7949 := ((9 \times F(4)) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7954 := ((F(F(4))^5) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7957 := ((7 \times 5) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7964 := ((F(F(4)) \times F(F(6))) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7974 := ((4 \times F(7)) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7978 := ((8 \times 7) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$7985 := (5 \times F((F(8) + 9) - F(7)))$$

$$7986 := ((F(6) \times 8) - (-F(9) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$8172 := 2^{F(7)} + 1 - F(8)$$

$$8174 := ((F(F(4))^{F(7)}) - 18)$$

$$8184 := ((F(F(4))^{F(8-1)}) - 8)$$

$$8294 := (F(F(4)) \times (-F(9) + F((-2) + F(8))))$$

$$8352 := (2 \times (-5) + F(-((F(3) - F(8))))))$$

$$8361 := ((-1) - F((6 \times 3))) + F(F(8))$$

$$8362 := (2 \times F((F(6) + (3 + 8))))$$

$$8363 := F(F(3)) - F(6 \times 3) + F(F(8))$$

$$8364 := F(F(4)) - F(6 \times 3) + F(F(8))$$

$$8367 := ((F(F(7)) \times (6^{F(3)})) - (F(8)))$$

$$8368 := ((F(F(8)) + 6) - F((-3) + F(8)))$$

$$8383 := ((F(3) \times F((F(8) - F(3)))) + (F(8)))$$

$$8396 := (F(F(F(6))) - (-F(9) + F((-3) + F(8))))$$

$$8738 := (F(F(8)) - ((3^7) + F(8)))$$

$$8759 := (-((F((9 - 5))^7)) + F(F(8)))$$

$$8849 := ((-9) \times F(F(-((F(F(F(4))) - 8)))) + F(F(8)))$$

$$8883 := ((F(F(3)) + 8) \times F((8 + 8)))$$

$$8906 := ((-60) \times F(9) + F(F(8)))$$

$$8972 := ((-2) \times F((7 + 9))) + F(F(8))$$

$$9248 := F(8)^{F(4)} - F(-2 + 9)$$

$$9349 := (-F((F(9)/F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(-((3 - 9))))))$$

$$9586 := (F(F(F(6))) + (-((8 \times 5) \times F(9)))$$

$$9756 := (F(F(F(6))) - ((5 \times 7) \times F(9)))$$

$$9792 := ((F((F(2) + 9)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9))$$

$$00174 := F(F(4)) \times (-F(7) + 100)$$

$$01023 := -((F(F(3)) - (2^{010})))$$

$$01037 := (F(7) + (F(3)^{010}))$$

$$01042 := (F((2^4)) + F(010))$$

$$01098 := ((F(F(8)) + F(9))/010)$$

$$01134 := (F((4 \times F(3))) \times (-1) + F(10))$$

$$01153 := (-F(3) + (F(F((5 + 1))) \times F(10)))$$

$$01154 := -((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F((5 + 1))) \times F(10))))$$

$$01155 := (F((5 + F((5 - 1)))) \times F(10))$$

$$01157 := (F(7) \times F((F(F((5 + 1))) - 10)))$$

$$01168 := (-8) + (F(F(6)) \times (1 + F(10)))$$

$$01175 := ((5 \times F(F(7))) + (1 \times 10))$$

$$01176 := ((F(6) + F(7)) \times (1 + F(10)))$$

$$01178 := (F(8) + (F(7) \times F((1 + 10))))$$

$$01189 := (F(9) + (F(8) \times F((1 \times 10))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}01257 &:= (F(F(7)) + (F((5-2))^{10})) \\01275 &:= ((5 \times F(F(7))) - (-2) \times F(10)) \\01278 &:= ((F(8) + F(F(7))) + (2^{10})) \\01293 &:= (-3) + (9 \times F((2+10))) \\01294 &:= -((F(F(4)) + (-9) \times F((2+10)))) \\01296 &:= ((F(6) \times F(9)) + (2^{10})) \\01325 &:= (-((5^2)) \times (F(3) - F(10))) \\01328 &:= (8 \times (F(2) + (3 \times F(10)))) \\01335 &:= ((5 \times 3) \times F((F(F(3)) + 10))) \\01336 &:= (F(6) \times (F(3) + (3 \times F(10)))) \\01344 &:= ((4^{F(4)}) \times F(-(F(3) - 10))) \\01364 &:= (F((-4) + F(F(6)))) - (F((3+10))) \\01365 &:= 5 \times F(F(6)) \times (3+10) \\01368 &:= (8 \times (6 + (3 \times F(10)))) \\01375 &:= (-5) \times ((-7) + F(3)) \times F(10) \\01376 &:= (F(6) \times (7 + (3 \times F(10)))) \\01386 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((8+3) + F(10))) \\01424 &:= ((4^2) \times F((F(F(F(4)) + 10))) \\01425 &:= ((5^2) \times (F(F(4)) + (F(10)))) \\01428 &:= ((F(8) \times 2) \times F(-(F(F(F(4)) - 10))) \\01435 &:= -5 + F(3 \times 4) \times 10 \\01456 &:= ((F(F(6)) + 5) \times (F(F(F(4)) + (F(10)))) \\01476 &:= (-6) \times (-F(7) - F((F(4) + 10))) \\01485 &:= (-((5 - (8 \times 4))) \times F(10)) \\01487 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times 8) - (F((4+10)))) \\01488 &:= (8 \times (F(8) + (F(4) \times F(10)))) \\01524 &:= (F(4) \times (-2 - 510)) \\01527 &:= -((F(F(7)) + (-2^5)) \times F(10)) \\01542 &:= (F((2 - (F(4) \times (-5)))) - (F(10))) \\01547 &:= (F((F(7) + 4)) - (5 \times 10)) \\01593 &:= -((F(3) - ((F(9) - 5) \times F(10))) \\01596 &:= (-6) \times (9 - (5 \times F(10))) \\01597 &:= (F((7+9)) + F((5+10))) \\01635 &:= (-5) \times (3 + (-6) \times F(10)) \\01637 &:= -((F(F(7)) - ((F(3+6)) \times F(10))) \\01638 &:= -((F(8) \times (F(3) + (F(6) \times (-10)))) \\01645 &:= (-5) \times (F(F(F(4))) + (-6) \times F(10)) \\01646 &:= (F((F(F(6)) - 4)) + (-6) + F(10)) \\01648 &:= (8 \times (-4) - (F(F(6)) \times (-10))) \\01667 &:= (-F(7)) - (F(F(6)) \times (F(6) \times (-10)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}01677 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(7)) + F(6))) - 10) \\01691 &:= (19 \times F((F(F(6)) - 10))) \\01692 &:= ((-2) - F(9)) \times (F(6) - F(10)) \\01695 &:= (-5) \times (-9) + (-6) \times F(10) \\01728 &:= ((8 - 2) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(10)))) \\01746 &:= (-6) \times ((-F(4)) - F(F(7))) - (F(10)) \\01764 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times F(F(6))) \times (-F(7) - F(10))) \\01777 &:= (((-F(7)) - F(F(7))) \times (-7)) + (F(10)) \\01783 &:= -((F(F(3)) - (8 \times (F(F(7)) - 10))) \\01784 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times (8 \times (F(F(7)) - 10))) \\01785 &:= ((5 \times F(8)) \times (7+10)) \\01788 &:= (-F(8)) - ((-8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(10)) \\01854 &:= ((F(F(F(F(4)) + 5))) \times 8) - 10 \\01869 &:= ((F(9) \times F(F(6))) + (F(8) \times F(10))) \\01923 &:= -((F(3) - ((F(2) + F(9)) \times F(10))) \\01924 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - ((F(2) + F(9)) \times F(10))) \\01925 &:= (-((5 \times (2 - 9))) \times F(10)) \\01934 &:= ((4^3) + (F(9) \times F(10))) \\01944 &:= ((F(4)^4) \times (F(9) - 10)) \\01946 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((F(F(F(4)) + F(9)) \times F(10))) \\01967 &:= -((F(F(7)) + ((-6) - F(9)) \times F(10))) \\01976 &:= ((F(6) \times F(7)) \times (9+10)) \\01977 &:= (-F(7)) - ((F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times (-10)) \\02097 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (9 + (0 \times 20))) \\02217 &:= ((F(7)^{1+2}) + (20)) \\02237 &:= ((F(7)^3) + (2 \times 20)) \\02268 &:= (F(8) \times (-6 \times (2 - 20))) \\02276 &:= (-((67^2)) + F(20)) \\02292 &:= ((2 \times (F(9)^2)) - (20)) \\02347 &:= -((F(F(7)) + 4)) + F(-(F(3) - (20))) \\02387 &:= (7 \times (F(8) + 320)) \\02448 &:= -((F((8+4)) \times (F(4) - (20))) \\02488 &:= (-8) + ((F(8)^{F(4)}) - F(20)) \\02496 &:= ((F(F(6))^{9/F(4)}) - F(20)) \\02564 &:= (F(((F(F(4)) + F(F(6))) - 5)) - (20)) \\02576 &:= (-F(6)) + F(-((7-5) - 20)) \\02577 &:= (-7) + F(-((7-5) - 20)) \\02599 &:= (F((9+9)) - ((5-20))) \\02604 &:= (F((F(4) \times 06)) + (20)) \\02639 &:= ((9 - F(3)) \times F(-(6-20)))\end{aligned}$$

- 02645** := $((5^{F(4)}) \times F(F(6))) + (20)$
02647 := $-((F(F(7)) - (F((4 + F(6))) \times 20)))$
02648 := $-(((F(8) + (4^6)) - F(20)))$
02666 := $((F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \times 6) + (20)$
02688 := $(F(8) \times (8 + (6 \times 20)))$
02769 := $((F(9) - F(F(6))) \times (F(F(7)) - (20)))$
02776 := $((F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(7))) + (20)$
02783 := $((3 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) + (20)))$
02796 := $((F(F(6)) - 9) \times F(F((7 + (2 \times 0))))$
02837 := $((F(F(7)) + F((-3) + F(8))) + (20))$
02968 := $(8 \times (-6) + F((F(9) - (20))))$
02978 := $((87 \times F(9)) + (20))$
03288 := $(8 \times ((F(8)^2) - (30)))$
03345 := $((5 \times F(4))^3 - (30))$
03448 := $(8 \times (F(F(F(4))) + 430))$
03465 := $((-5) \times F(F(6))) \times (-F(4) + (30)))$
03645 := $5 \times F(4)^6 + 3 \times 0$
03728 := $((8 \times 2) \times F(F((7 + (3 \times 0))))$
03758 := $((F(8) - 5) \times F(F(7))) + (30)$
03791 := $(F(19) - (F(7) \times 30))$
04136 := $F(6)^{3+1} + 40$
04181 := $F((18 + (1^4 0)))$
04182 := $(F(2) + F(((F(8) \times (-1)) + 40)))$
04183 := $(F(3) + F(((F(8) \times (-1)) + 40)))$
04184 := $(F(4) + F(((F(8) \times (-1)) + 40)))$
04374 := $((F(4)^7) \times F((3 + (4 \times 0))))$
04387 := $((F(F(7)) \times (F(8) - F(3))) - 40)$
04467 := $((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))) + 40)$
04474 := $(F(F(4)) \times ((F(7)^{F(4)}) + 40))$
04735 := $(5 \times (F((3 + F(7))) - 40))$
04773 := $(3 \times ((F(F(7)) \times 7) - 40))$
04794 := $((F(4) \times F(9)) \times (7 + 40))$
04853 := $((F(F((F(3) + 5))) \times F(8)) - 40)$
04864 := $((F(F(4))^{F(6)}) \times (-F(8) - 40))$
04872 := $((F(2) - F(F(7))) \times (-F((8 + (4 \times 0))))$
04936 := $((F((6 \times F(3))) \times F(9)) + 40)$
04967 := $((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + ((F(9) + 40)))$
04975 := $((5 \times F((7 + 9))) + 40)$
05389 := $(-F(9) - ((F(F(8)) / (-F(3))) + 50))$
05423 := $((F(F(F((3 \times 2)))) / F(F(4))) - 50)$
05426 := $((F(F(F(6))) / 2) + ((F(4) - 50)))$
05489 := $(-F(9) + ((F(F(8)) / F(F(4))) + 50))$
05528 := $((F(F(8)) / 2) + ((5 + 50)))$
05575 := $(-5) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-5)) + 50)$
05767 := $-((F(F(7)) + (F(6) \times (-750))))$
05846 := $((F((6 \times 4)) / 8) + 50)$
05916 := $(6 \times (-1) + F(-(F(9) - 50)))$
05946 := $(6 \times (4 + F(-(F(9) - 50))))$
05996 := $(F(F(F(6))) - ((99 \times 50)))$
06448 := $((F((F(8) - 4)) \times 4) + (60))$
06621 := $((1 + 2)^{F(6)} + (60))$
06636 := $(F(F(6)) \times ((F(3)^{F(6)}) + (60)))$
06676 := $((F(F(F(6))) / (-F(7))) \times (-F(6))) - (60)$
06684 := $(F(-(F(F(F(4))) - (F(8)))) - (F(F(6)) + (60)))$
06718 := $(F((F(8) - 1)) + ((F(7) - (60))))$
06747 := $((F(7) \times F(4)) \times (F(F(7)) - (60)))$
06823 := $((-F(3)) + F(-(F(2) - F(8)))) + (60)$
06824 := $-(((F(F(F(4))) - F(-(F(2) - F(8)))) - (60)))$
06825 := $(F(-(F(F((5 - 2))) - (F(8)))) + (60))$
06846 := $(F((F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))) + (F(8) + (60)))$
07826 := $((F(6) \times F((2 \times 8))) - 70)$
07839 := $(9 \times (F(F(3)) + (870)))$
07846 := $((6^{-F(4)+8}) + 70)$
07847 := $((F((7 \times F(F(4)))) \times F(8)) - 70)$
07985 := $(5 \times F(((8 + 9) + (7 \times 0))))$
07992 := $((F(F(-(2 - 9))) \times F(9)) + 70)$
08272 := $((2^{F(7)}) \times F(2)) + (80)$
08273 := $((F(3)^{F(7)} + F(2)) + (80))$
08274 := $((F(F(4))^{F(7)} + ((2 + 80)))$
08568 := $(F(8) \times (F(6) + (5 \times 80)))$
08672 := $((2^{F(7)}) + (6 \times 80))$
08963 := $((F((F(3) \times F(6))) \times 9) + (80))$
09348 := $((F(8)^{F(4)}) - (3 - 90))$
09351 := $((F(F((1 + 5)))^3) + (90))$
09686 := $(F(F(F(6))) - (((8 + 6) \times 90)))$
09768 := $(F(F(8)) - ((F(6) + (F(7) \times 90))))$
09776 := $(F((F(6) + F(7))) - (F(7) \times 90))$
09786 := $((F(F(6)) + (F(8))) \times F(F((7 + (9 \times 0))))$
10247 := $((F(F(7)) \times (-F(4))) + (F((20 + 1))))$

- 10336** := $F(6 \times 3) \times (3 + 01)$
10679 := $((-F(9)) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F((6 \times 01))))$
10712 := $((F(21) - F(F(7))) - 01)$
10736 := $(F(F(F(6))) - ((3 \times 70) \times 1))$
10764 := $(46 \times (F(F(7)) + 01))$
10776 := $(F(F(F(6))) - ((F(7) \times F(7)) + 01))$
10777 := $(-((F(7) \times F(7))) + F(F((7 + 01))))$
10778 := $(F(F(8)) - ((F(7) \times F(7)) - 01))$
10856 := $((-F((6 + 5))) + F(F(8))) - 01$
10863 := $((-3) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((80 \times 1))$
10864 := $((-F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((80 - 1))$
10867 := $(F((F(7) + F(6))) - ((80 - 1)))$
10868 := $(F(F(8)) - (6 \times F((8 - 01))))$
10878 := $(F(F(8)) + ((F(7) - (80 + 1))))$
10883 := $((-3) \times F(8)) + F(F((8 \times 01)))$
10884 := $((-((F(4) \times F(8))) + F(F(8))) + 01)$
10886 := $((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) - ((80 + 1)))$
10888 := $(F(F(8)) + ((F(8) - ((80 - 1))))$
10891 := $(-F((1 + 9))) + F(F((8 \times 01)))$
10892 := $-(((F((F(2) + 9)) - F(F(8))) - 01))$
10912 := $F(21) - F(9 \times 01)$
10925 := $-((F(F((5 + F(2)))) - (F(F((9 - 01))))))$
10926 := $-(((F(F(6)) - F(2)) - F(F((9 - 01))))$
10928 := $(F(F(8)) - ((2 \times 9) \times 01))$
10929 := $((F(9)/(-2)) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10934 := $(-((4 \times 3)) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10936 := $(-((F(6) + F(3))) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10937 := $F(7 \times 3) - 9 \times 01$
10938 := $(F(F(8)) - F(((3 - 9) \times (0 - 1))))$
10939 := $((-9) + F(3)) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10941 := $(-((1 + 4)) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10942 := $((F(2) \times (-4)) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10943 := $((F(F(3)) - (4)) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10943 := $F(F(3)) - 4 + F(F(9 - 01))$
10944 := $((-4) + F(F(4))) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10944 := $F(F(4)) - 4 + F(F(9 - 01))$
10945 := $(-((5 - 4)) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10946 := $F(F((64/(9 - 01))))$
10947 := $(F(F((7 - 4))) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10948 := $(F(F(8)) + F((4 - ((9 \times 0) + 1))))$
10949 := $((9/F(4)) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10951 := $((1 \times 5) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10952 := $F(2) + 5 + F(F(9 - 01))$
10953 := $F(3) + 5 + F(F(9 - 01))$
10954 := $F(4) + 5 + F(F(9 - 01))$
10962 := $((2 \times F(6)) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10964 := $((F(4) \times 6) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10966 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(6)) - ((9 \times 0) + 1)))$
10967 := $((F(7) + F(6)) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10968 := $((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + ((9 \times 0) + 1))$
10972 := $((2 \times F(7)) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10974 := $((4 \times 7) + F(F((9 - 01)))$
10979 := $(F((F(9) - F(7))) + (F(9) - 01))$
10982 := $F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(9) + 01$
10983 := $F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(9) + 01$
10984 := $F(4) + F(F(8)) + F(9) + 01$
11035 := $(F(F((5 + 3))) - (0 - F(11)))$
11036 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(3)) - (0 - F(11))))$
11038 := $(F(F(8)) + (3 + F(011)))$
11066 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (60 \times (1 + 1)))$
11069 := $((F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) - (0 - F(11)))$
11125 := $5^{2+1} \times F(11)$
11126 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (2 \times (1 + F(11))))$
11166 := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(6)) - 1) \times 11))$
11167 := $((F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (1 + 11))$
11168 := $((F(F(8)) + F(F((6 + 1)))) - 11)$
11176 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) - ((1 + 1) + 1)))$
11177 := $((F(F(7)) + F(F((7 + 1)))) - (1 + 1))$
11178 := $((F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) - (1^{11}))$
11188 := $(F(F(8)) + ((F(8) + 1) \times 11))$
11264 := $(4 \times F(6))^2 \times 11$
11267 := $((F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(2) - F(11)))$
11268 := $((F(F(8)) + F(F((F(6) - F(2)))) + (F(11)))$
11298 := $(F(F(8)) + ((F(9) - 2) \times 11))$
11323 := $(F(F(F((3 \times 2)))) + (F((3 + 11))))$
11378 := $(F(F(8)) + ((7^3) + F(11)))$
11386 := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((F(8)^{F(3)}) - (1 \times 1)))$
11388 := $(F(F(8)) + ((F(8)^{F(3)}) + (1 \times 1)))$
11392 := $2^{9-F(3)} \times F(11)$
11466 := $((F(F(6)) \times 6) \times (F(F(4)) + (F(11))))$

- 11468** := $(F(F(8)) - (6 \times (F(F(4)) - (F(11))))$
11478 := $(F(F(8)) - ((F(7) \times (-41)) + 1))$
11556 := $(F(F(F(6))) + F((5 \times ((5 - 1) - 1))))$
11576 := $((((6 - F(F(7))) \times (-51)) - 1)$
11645 := $((F((5 \times F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(11)))$
11646 := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((F(4) \times F(F((6 + 1)))) + 1))$
11647 := $((F(F(7)) \times F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (1 + 1))$
11648 := $(F(F(8)) + (F(4) \times (F(F((6 + 1))) + 1)))$
11664 := $(F(4) \times 6 \times 6)^{1+1}$
11666 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (F(6) + (F(6) \times F(11))))$
11786 := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(8))/F(7)) - (1 + 1)))$
11788 := $(F(F(8)) + (F(F(8))/F(((7 + 1) - 1))))$
11828 := $(F(F(8)) + (2 \times (F(8)^{1+1})))$
11836 := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((F(3) + 8) \times F(11)))$
11837 := $7 \times (-F(3) + F(8)) \times F(11)$
11838 := $-((F(F(8)) - ((F(3)^8) \times F(11))))$
11844 := $F(4) \times 4 \times F(8 \times (1 + 1))$
11878 := $(F(F(8)) + (F(F(7)) \times (8/(1 + 1))))$
11934 := $((F((4^{F(3)})) + F(F((9 - 1)))) + 1)$
12238 := $F(8 \times 3)/2 - F(21)$
12373 := $((F(3)^{F(7)}) + F(-((F(3) - (21)))))$
12441 := $(F(14) \times (F((F(4)^2) - 1))$
12528 := $((F((F(8) - 2)) - (5)) \times (2 + 1))$
12537 := $(-F(7) + F(3 \times 5)) \times 21$
12543 := $3 \times F((4 + 5) \times 2 + 1)$
12544 := $((F(4) \times F(((4 \times 5) - F(2)))) + 1)$
12548 := $(F((F(8) - (4))) + (5 + F(21)))$
12576 := $(-6) + (F(F(7)) \times (F((5 \times 2) - 1)))$
12577 := $((F(F(7)) \times 7) + F(F(((5 + 2) + 1))))$
12578 := $(F(F(8)) - ((F(F(7)) \times (-5 + 2)) - 1))$
12582 := $(F(F(-(F(2) - 8))) \times (F((5 \times 2) - 1))$
12727 := $(F((F(7) - 2)) \times (F((F(7) - F(2)) - 1))$
12746 := $((F(F(6)) \times (-F(4)) + F((F(7) + 2)))) - 1)$
12748 := $((-F(8)) \times (F(4) - F((F(7) + 2)))) + 1)$
12749 := $((-F(9)) \times (F(F(4)) - (F((7 \times 2)))) - 1)$
12768 := $(F(8) \times 6 - F(7))^2 - 1$
12769 := $(9 + F(6) \times F(7))^2 \times 1$
12776 := $F(6) \times F(7 + 7 + 2 + 1)$
12784 := $(F((F(F(4)) + 8)) \times (F((7 \times 2) - 1))$
12786 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (8 \times (F(F(7)) - (2 + 1))))$
12788 := $F(8) \times (F(8 + 7) - F(2)) - 1$
12794 := $((F((F(F(F(4))) + 9)) \times F(F(7))) - (21))$
12796 := $-((F(F(6)) - ((F(9) \times F((7 \times 2))) - 1)))$
12797 := $F(7) + F(9) \times (F(7 \times 2) - 1)$
12798 := $-F(8) + F(9) \times F(7 \times 2) + 1$
12815 := $5 \times (F(18) - 21)$
12816 := $((F(F((6 + 1))) \times F((8 + 2))) + 1)$
12817 := $F(7) \times (-1 + F(8 \times 2)) - 1$
12818 := $F(8 - 1) \times (F(8 \times 2) - 1)$
12819 := $F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1$
12831 := $13 \times F(8 \times 2 \times 1)$
12844 := $(F((F(4) + (4))) \times (F((8 \times 2) + 1))$
12857 := $(-F(7)) \times ((F((-5) + F(8))) + 2) \times (-1))$
12871 := $(((-1) - F(F(7))) \times (-F((8 + 2)))) + 1)$
12873 := $3 + F(7 + 8) \times 21$
12915 := $5 \times (-1 + F(9 \times 2 \times 1))$
12925 := $5 \times (F(2) + F(9 \times 2)) \times 1$
12935 := $5 \times (3 + F(9 \times 2 \times 1))$
12945 := $5 \times (4 + F(9 \times 2) + 1)$
12959 := $F(9) + 5 \times (F(9 \times 2) + 1)$
12965 := $5 \times (F(6) + F(9 \times 2) + 1)$
13176 := $6 \times (F(7)^{1 \times 3} - 1)$
13347 := $((7^4) + F(F(((3 \times 3) - 1))))$
13377 := $F(7) \times 7^3 \times 3 \times 1$
13488 := $((-F(8)) + F((F(8) - F(F(F(4)))))) \times (3 - 1)$
13525 := $-5 + 2 \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$
13529 := $((F((9 \times 2)) + F(F((5 + 3)))) - 1)$
13546 := $(F(6) + F(4 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
13549 := $(9 + F(4 \times 5)) \times F(3) + 1$
13566 := $(F(F(6)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5^{3+1})))$
13572 := $F(2 \times 7) \times (5 + 31)$
13671 := $((-F((1 + 7))) \times F(F(6))) \times (-31))$
13689 := $(9 \times (F(8) - F(6)))^{3-1}$
13715 := $5 \times ((1 + F(7))^3 - 1)$
13746 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (-4) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-3)) - 1))$
13747 := $(F(F(7)) \times ((4 \times 7) + 31))$
13784 := $((F(4)^8) - (F(F(7)) \times (-31)))$
13796 := $((F(F(6)) \times (9 \times 73)) - 1)$
13798 := $F(8) \times 9 \times 73 + 1$
13817 := $((F(7) + 1) \times F((8 \times F(3)))) - 1)$

- 13837** := $F(7) + (3 \times 8)^3 \times 1$
13846 := $(F(F(6)) + (((F(4) \times 8)^3) + 1))$
13949 := $((F(9) + F(4)) \times F((F(9 - F(3)))) + 1))$
13975 := $(-5) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-9 + 3)) + 1)$
13976 := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(7)) \times F((9 - F(3)))) + 1))$
14325 := $(((-5) + F(23))/F(F(4))) - 1$
14326 := $((F((F(F(6)) + 2)) - 3)/F(F(4))) - 1$
14328 := $((F((F(8) + 2)) - F(F(3)))/F((4 - 1)))$
14336 := $F(6)^3 \times (3^{F(4)} + 1)$
14373 := $((F(3) + (7)) \times F(((F(3)^4) + 1)))$
14374 := $((F((4 + F(7))) \times (3 \times F(4))) + 1)$
14399 := $((9 \times (F((F(9)/F(3))) + F(4))) - 1)$
14447 := $((F(F(7)) \times ((4^{F(4)} - F(F(4)))) + 1)$
14584 := $(-4) \times (((F(F(8)) - 5)/(-F(4))) + 1)$
14596 := $((F(F(6)) - (F((9 + 5)))) \times (-41))$
14617 := $((((F(F(7)) - 1) \times F(F(6))) \times F(4)) + 1)$
14635 := $-5 + (3 + F(6))^4 - 1$
14636 := $-6 + (3 + F(6))^4 + 1$
14642 := $F(2) + (F(4) + F(6))^4 \times 1$
14643 := $F(3) + (F(4) + F(6))^4 \times 1$
14644 := $F(4) + (F(4) + F(6))^4 \times 1$
14658 := $(-F(8)) \times ((F((5 + F(6))) \times (-F(4))) + 1)$
14672 := $(((-2) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) \times F(4)) - 1$
14673 := $(3 \times ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) - F((4 - 1))))$
14674 := $((F(4) \times F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - (4 + 1)$
14675 := $(-5) - (((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) \times (-F(4))) - 1)$
14678 := $F(8) \times F(7 + 6) \times F(4) - 1$
14679 := $((9 \times 7) \times F((F(6) + (4 + 1))))$
14759 := $(9^5 - F(7))/4 \times 1$
14796 := $((6 \times 9) \times (F(F(7)) + 41))$
14847 := $((F(F(7)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times (8^{F(F(4))}) - 1)$
14848 := $((8^{F(F(4))}) \times (F(F((F(8)/F(4)))) - 1))$
14879 := $(-F(9)) + ((F(F(7)) \times (8^{F(F(4))})) + 1)$
14976 := $F(6) \times F(7) \times F(9 + 4 - 1)$
14987 := $7 \times (F(8) \times F(9) \times F(4) - 1)$
15126 := $((F((F(F(6)) - 2)) - 1) + F(F(F((5 + 1))))$
15128 := $((F((F(8) - 2)) + 1) + F(F(F((5 + 1))))$
15174 := $((F((F(F(4)) \times F(7))) - 1)/F((5 + 1)))$
15251 := $F(15) \times 25 + 1$
15309 := $((9^{03}) \times F(F((5 + 1))))$
15366 := $6 \times (F(6)^3 \times 5 + 1)$
15377 := $((7 \times (F(7)^3)) - F(F((5 - 1))))$
15436 := $((F(F(6))^3)/(-F(4))) \times (-5) + 1$
15448 := $((F((8 \times F(4)))/F(4)) - F((5 + 1)))$
15456 := $(F(((F(F(6)) + 5)) - F(F(4))))/F((5 - 1))$
15464 := $F(4 \times 6)/F(4) + F(5 + 1)$
15486 := $(6 \times (F((F(8) - F(4))) - F((5 - 1))))$
15488 := $8 \times 8 \times (F(4)^5 - 1)$
15492 := $((F((2 \times 9)) - F(F(4))) \times (5 + 1))$
15496 := $((6 \times F((9 \times F(F(4)))) - F((5 + 1)))$
15497 := $(-7) - (F((9 \times F(F(4)))) \times (-5 + 1))$
15498 := $F(8) \times (9 + F(4)^{5+1})$
15536 := $-((F((F(6) + 3)) - (5^{5+1})))$
15544 := $-F(4)^4 + 5^{5+1}$
15552 := $((F(2) + 5)^5) \times F(F((5 - 1)))$
15563 := $F(3) \times (6^5 + 5) + 1$
15564 := $(F(F(4)) \times (((6^5) + 5) + 1))$
15568 := $((8 + (6^5)) \times F(F((5 - 1))))$
15583 := $-F(3) \times F(8) + 5^{5+1}$
15591 := $-1 \times F(9) + 5^{5+1}$
15592 := $F(2) - F(9) + 5^{5+1}$
15593 := $F(3) - F(9) + 5^{5+1}$
15594 := $F(4) - F(9) + 5^{5+1}$
15623 := $-F(3) + (-F(2) + 6)^{5+1}$
15624 := $((F(4) + 2)^6) - F(F(F((5 - 1))))$
15626 := $((6 - F(2))^6) + F(F(F((5 - 1))))$
15627 := $((7 - 2)^6) + F(F((5 - 1)))$
15633 := $(F(3) + 3)^6 + F(5 + 1)$
15646 := $((F(6) - F(4))^6) + F(F((5 + 1)))$
15659 := $F(9) + 5^{F(6) - F(F(5-1))}$
15665 := $5^6 + F(6) \times 5 \times 1$
15676 := $(-F(6) + F(7))^6 + 51$
15697 := $((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + ((6^5) - 1))$
15748 := $(F(F(8)) - (F(F(4)) \times (-7^{5-1})))$
15771 := $F(1 + 7) \times 751$
15774 := $((4^7) - F((7 + F((5 + 1))))$
15788 := $(F(F(8)) - ((-F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + (51))$

- 15792** := $2 \times F(9 + 7) \times F(5 + 1)$
15793 := $((F(3) \times F(9)) \times F(F(7))) - (51)$
15839 := $((F(F((9 - F(3)))) \times F(8)) + F(F(F((5 + 1))))$
15842 := $(2 \times (F((F(4) + 8))^{F(F(5-1))}))$
15868 := $(-8) + ((6 \times F(8))^{F(F(5-1))})$
15876 := $((6 \times (F(7) + 8))^{F(F(5-1))})$
15968 := $(8 \times ((F(F(6)) \times 95) + 1))$
16077 := $((F(F(7)) \times 70) - F(F((6 + 1))))$
16287 := $((F(F(7)) + F((8 + F(2)))) \times 61)$
16349 := $(-F(9)) + ((4^{F(F(3))+6}) - 1)$
16364 := $((4^{F(6)-F(F(3))}) - (F(F(6)) - 1))$
16376 := $-F(6) + (7 - 3)^{6+1}$
16382 := $-2 + (8/F(3))^{6+1}$
16383 := $F(3)^{8+3} \times F(6) - 1$
16388 := $((F(8) \times F(8)) \times (-3)) + F((F(F(6)) + 1))$
16415 := $(-((5 + 1)^4)) + F((F(F(6)) + 1))$
16418 := $F(8 + 1) + 4^{6+1}$
16419 := $F(9) + 1 + 4^{6+1}$
16426 := $((F(F(6)) \times 2) + (4^{6+1}))$
16428 := $((F(F(8))/(-2)) \times (-F(4))) + (F(6) + 1)$
16439 := $(F((9 + F(F(3)))) + (4^{6+1}))$
16448 := $((8^{F(F(4))}) + (4^{6+1}))$
16464 := $(-4) \times ((-((F(6)^4)) - F(F(6))) + 1)$
16469 := $((((-F(9)) - F(F(F(6))))/(-4)) \times 6) - 1$
16473 := $(F(-((F(3) - F(7)))) + (4^{6+1}))$
16474 := $((4^7) + F((F(4) + F(6)))) + 1$
16479 := $(9 \times (((F(F(7)) - 4) \times F(6)) - 1))$
16483 := $((3 \times ((F(F(8))/F(F(4))) + F(F(6)))) + 1)$
16491 := $((F(19) \times 4) - F(F((6 + 1))))$
16546 := $(F((F(F(6)) + F(F(F(4)))) - (5 \times F(F((6 + 1))))$
16556 := $((F(F(6)) \times (-55)) + F((F(F(6)) + 1))$
16563 := $((3 \times (6^5)) - F((F(F(6)) - 1))$
16572 := $(-((2 - (7^5))) - F(F((6 + 1))))$
16573 := $(-(((F(F(3)) - (7^5)) + F(F((6 + 1))))$
16574 := $(F(F(F(4))) \times ((7^5) - F(F((6 + 1))))$
16576 := $((6 - F(F(7))) \times 5) + F((F(F(6)) + 1))$
16627 := $(-F(7)) \times (2 + (F(F(6)) \times (-61)))$
16644 := $(4 \times (F(-((F(F(4)) - F(F(6)))) - (F(F(6)) - 1)))$
16653 := $((F((F(3) + 5))) \times F(F(6))) \times 61$
16678 := $(F(F(8)) - (((-F(7)) \times F(F(6))) \times F(F(6))) + 1)$
16694 := $((F(F(4))^9) - F(F(6))) \times F((F(6) + 1))$
16714 := $((41 + F(F(7))) \times 61)$
16722 := $(2 \times ((2 \times F((F(7) + (6)))) - 1))$
16723 := $((F(3) + 2) \times F((F(7) + (6)))) - 1$
16724 := $4 \times F(2 \times 7 + 6 - 1)$
16725 := $((5 - F(2)) \times F((F(7) + (6)))) + 1$
16728 := $((8/2) \times (F((F(7) + (6))) + 1))$
16737 := $((F(7) - F((3 + F(7)))) + F((F(F(6)) + 1)))$
16739 := $-F(9) \times F(3) + 7^{6-1}$
16744 := $(-4) \times ((-4) - F((F(7) + (6)))) - 1$
16746 := $(F(F(6)) + ((4 \times F((F(7) + (6)))) + 1))$
16749 := $(9 \times (-4) - ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(6))) - 1))$
16752 := $-F(2 \times 5) + 7^{6-1}$
16758 := $F(8) \times (5 + F(7) \times 61)$
16764 := $((4 + F(6)) \times ((F(F(7)) \times 6) - 1))$
16766 := $((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 1)))$
16768 := $(-8) + ((F(6) \times F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + 1))$
16769 := $((9 \times F(6)) \times F(F(7))) - (6 + 1)$
16773 := $(-((F((F(3) + (7))) - ((7^{6-1}))))$
16775 := $((5 + 7) \times F(F(7))) \times 6 - 1$
16776 := $((-6) \times F(F(7))) \times (-((7 + 6) - 1))$
16777 := $((F(F(7)) \times F(7)) - F(F(7))) \times 6 + 1$
16779 := $((9 - F(7)) \times F(F(7))) + F((F(F(6)) + 1))$
16784 := $(-((F(F(4)) + ((F(8) - (7^{6-1}))))$
16787 := $((7^{-8+F(7)}) - F(F(6))) + 1$
16789 := $((9 \times 8) \times F(F(7))) + F((6 + 1))$
16792 := $((2 + (9 \times F(F(7)))) \times F((6 \times 1))$
16793 := $((F(3) + (9 \times F(F(7)))) \times F(6)) + 1$
16796 := $((F(6) \times 9) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(6)) - 1$
16798 := $((8 \times 9) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(6)) + 1$
16828 := $F(8) + (-F(2) + 8)^{6-1}$
16868 := $(F(F(8)) - (-6) \times F((8 + F((6 \times 1))))$
16926 := $62 \times (F(9) \times F(6) + 1)$
16963 := $(F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) - (F(9) \times (F(F(6)) + 1)))$
16997 := $(F((F(7) + 9)) - (F(9) \times F(F((6 \times 1))))$
17199 := $9 \times 91 \times F(7 + 1)$
17246 := $(F((F(F(6)) + F(F(F(4)))) + ((-2) \times F(F(7))) + 1)$
17253 := $3^5 \times F(2) \times 71$
17334 := $(F((F((4 \times F(3))) + F(F(3)))) - (F((F(7) + 1))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17336 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) + (F(3) - F((F(7) + 1)))) \\
 17339 &:= F(9)^{F(3)} \times (F(3) + F(7)) - 1 \\
 17456 &:= F(6) \times (-5 + F(4)^7 \times 1) \\
 17469 &:= ((-9) + F((F(F(6)) + F(F(F(4)))))) + (F(F(7)) \times (-1)) \\
 17473 &:= -(F(3)) + (F(F(7)) \times (4 + 71)) \\
 17474 &:= ((-4) - F(F(7))) + F(((F(4) \times 7) + 1)) \\
 17475 &:= ((5 \times F(F(7))) \times ((F(4) + F(7)) - 1)) \\
 17476 &:= (((6 \times F(7)) - F(4)) \times F(F(7))) + 1 \\
 17477 &:= ((F(((F(7) + F(7)) - (4))) - F(F(7))) - 1) \\
 17478 &:= ((F(F(8)) - F(F(7))) + F(((F(4) \times 7) - 1))) \\
 17479 &:= (((F((9 + F(7))) + F(F(4))) - F(F(7))) - 1) \\
 17481 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) + F(4)) - F(F((7 \times 1))) \\
 17482 &:= ((F((F(2) + F(8))) + (4)) - F(F((7 \times 1))) \\
 17483 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + F(8))) + ((4 - F(F(7))) + 1)) \\
 17484 &:= -4 + 8 \times (F(4)^7 - 1) \\
 17486 &:= -(((F(F(6)) - F(F(8))) - ((F(4)^{7+1}))) \\
 17488 &:= 8 \times (F(8 - 4)^7 - 1) \\
 17496 &:= F(6) \times (9/F(4))^7 \times 1 \\
 17498 &:= (F(F(8)) + (-9) + (F(4)^{7+1})) \\
 17562 &:= (F((F(2) + F(F(6)))) - (5 + F((F(7) - 1)))) \\
 17568 &:= ((F((F(8) - (6)))/5) \times F((F(7) - 1))) \\
 17576 &:= F(6) \times F(7)^{-5+7+1} \\
 17627 &:= ((-F(7)) + F((F(2) + F(F(6)))) - (71)) \\
 17635 &:= ((-5) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) - (71)) \\
 17647 &:= F(7)^{F(4)} \times F(6) + 71 \\
 17661 &:= (F((1 + F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(6)) - 71))) \\
 17662 &:= (F(2) - (-F(F(6))) \times ((F(F(F(6)))/F(7)) - 1)) \\
 17663 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) - (6 \times (7 + 1))) \\
 17664 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times F(6)/F(7 + 1) \\
 17669 &:= (-((F(9) + F(6))) + F(((F(6) + F(7)) + 1))) \\
 17676 &:= (((F(F(F(6)))/(-F(7))) \times (-F(F(6)))) - (7 - 1)) \\
 17681 &:= ((((-1) \times F(F(8))) \times F(F(6)))/(-F(7)) - 1) \\
 17682 &:= (F((F(2) + F(8))) - (F(6) + F((7 + 1)))) \\
 17683 &:= (((F(F(3)) \times F(F(8))) \times F(F(6)))/F(7)) + 1) \\
 17684 &:= (F(F(4)) + ((F(F(8)) \times F(F(6)))/F((7 \times 1)))) \\
 17685 &:= ((-5) - F(8)) + F(((F(6) + F(7)) + 1)) \\
 17693 &:= ((F(3) \times (-9)) + F(((F(6) + F(7)) + 1))) \\
 17696 &:= (-((6 + 9)) + F(((F(6) + F(7)) + 1))) \\
 17697 &:= F(7 + 9 + 6) - F(7) - 1 \\
 17698 &:= ((F(8) - F(9)) + F(((F(6) + F(7)) + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17699 &:= (F(((9/9) + F(F(6)))) - (F(7) - 1)) \\
 17701 &:= (-10) + F((F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + 1)) \\
 17711 &:= F((1 + 1) \times 7 + 7 + 1) \\
 17712 &:= F(21 + 7/7) + 1 \\
 17713 &:= F(3) + F((1^7) + F(7 + 1)) \\
 17714 &:= F(4) + F((1^7) + F(7 + 1)) \\
 17715 &:= ((5 - 1) + F((F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + 1)) \\
 17716 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + 1)) + (F(7) - (7 + 1))) \\
 17717 &:= ((7 - 1) + F((F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + 1)) \\
 17718 &:= (F((F(8) + 1)) + (F(7) - (7 - 1))) \\
 17719 &:= ((F(9) + F((1 \times 7))) \times F((F(7) + 1))) \\
 17723 &:= (F(((3^2) + F(7))) + (F(7) - 1)) \\
 17724 &:= (F(((F(4)^2) + F(7))) + F((7 \times 1))) \\
 17725 &:= F(-5 + 27) + F(7) + 1 \\
 17726 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + F(2))) + ((7 + 7) + 1)) \\
 17729 &:= ((9 \times 2) + F((F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + 1)) \\
 17732 &:= (F((F(2) + ((3 \times 7))) + (F((7 + 1)))) \\
 17736 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) + ((F(7) + F(7)) - 1)) \\
 17737 &:= ((F(7) \times F(3)) + F((F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + 1)) \\
 17738 &:= (F((F(8) + F(F(3)))) + ((F(7) + F(7)) + 1)) \\
 17739 &:= -((9^{F(3)}) \times ((F(7) - F(F(7))) + 1)) \\
 17745 &:= (F((5 + 4) + F((F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + 1)) \\
 17749 &:= ((F(9) + (4)) + F((F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + 1)) \\
 17761 &:= (F((1 + F(F(6)))) + ((7 \times 7) + 1)) \\
 17767 &:= ((7 \times F(6)) + F((F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + 1)) \\
 17782 &:= (F(((F(2) + 8) + F(7))) + 71) \\
 17784 &:= (((F(F(4)) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(7)))/(7 + 1)) \\
 17816 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + 1)) + ((8 \times F(7)) + 1)) \\
 17847 &:= (((F(7)^4) - F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - 1) \\
 17849 &:= (((-F(9)) + F(-((F(4) - F(8)))) \times 7) - 1) \\
 17855 &:= (F(((5/5) + F(8))) + F((F(7) - 1))) \\
 17856 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - ((F((-5) + F(8))) \times (-7)) - 1) \\
 17863 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + (8 + F((F(7) - 1)))) \\
 17873 &:= (((3^7) \times 8) + F((F(7) + 1))) \\
 17879 &:= (F((9 + F(7))) + (8 \times F((7 + 1)))) \\
 17884 &:= (((F(4)^8) + F(F(8))) + F((F(7) + 1))) \\
 17909 &:= ((-90) \times (F(9) - F(F(7)))) - 1) \\
 17936 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) + ((-9) + F(F(7)) + 1)) \\
 17943 &:= ((F(F((3 + 4))) + F((9 + F(7)))) - 1) \\
 17944 &:= (F(((4) \times F(4)) + F(9)) + F(F((7 \times 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 17945** := ((F((-5) + (F(4) × 9))) + F(F(7))) + 1)
17947 := ((F(F(7)) + F(4)) + F((9 + F((7 × 1))))
17948 := (F((F(8) + F(F(F(4)))))) + ((F(9) × 7) - 1)
17953 := (((3⁵) + F((9 + F(7)))) - 1)
17954 := ((F(4)⁵) + F((9 + F((7 × 1))))
17966 := (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(F(6)) + 9) × (F(F(7)) + 1))))
17979 := (((F(9) + F(F(7))) + F((9 + F(7)))) + 1)
17983 := (F((F(F(3)) + (F(8)))) - (F(9) × (-7 + 1)))
17997 := (-F(7) + F(9 + 9)) × 7 × 1
18177 := ((F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) + F((1 + F((8 × 1))))
18269 := ((9 × 62) + F((F(8) + 1)))
18321 := (F((12 + 3)) + F((F(8) + 1)))
18387 := ((F(F(7)) - (8 - F(3))) × 81)
18407 := (F(F(7)) × ((0 - F(F(4))) + (81)))
18439 := (((9³) - F(F(F(4)))) + F((F(8) + 1)))
18473 := (F((F(3) × 7)) × (48 + 1))
18482 := 2 × (F(8)^{F(4)} - F(8) + 1)
18494 := (F(F(4)) × (((F(9)^{F(F(4))}) × 8) - 1))
18496 := (((-((F(6) × F(9))) × F(F(4))) × (-F((8 + 1))))
18592 := (-2 + F(9)) × 581
18689 := (((-9) + F((8 + F(6)))) + F((F(8) + 1)))
18697 := ((F((F(7) + 9)) + F((F(6) + 8))) - 1)
18698 := (F((8 × F(9 - 6))) + F((F(8) + 1)))
18711 := (((-1 + 1) + F(F(7))) × 81)
18756 := 6 × (5^{F(7)-8} + 1)
18764 := (F((F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(6)))))) + (F(7) × 81))
18784 := -((F((F(4) + 8)) + (F(F(7)) × (-81))))
18792 := (((-((F(2)⁹)) + F(F(7))) × 81)
18839 := (-F(9) + (F(F(-((F(F(3)) - 8)))) × 81))
18842 := ((F((2⁴) × 8) + F(F((8 × 1))))
18843 := (((F((F(3)⁴)) × 8) + F(F(8))) + 1)
18845 := ((54 × F(8)) + F((F(8) + 1)))
18863 := ((F((F(3) × 6)) × 8) + F((F(8) + 1)))
18868 := (F(F(8)) - (F(-((F(6) - F(8)))) × (-F((8 + 1))))
18869 := ((F(9) × F(-((F(6) - F(8)))))) + ((F(F(8)) + 1))
18873 := F(3 × 7 - 8) × 81
18876 := (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(7) × F(((8 + 8) - 1))))
18877 := (((F(7) × F((7 + 8))) + F(F(8))) + 1)
18887 := (((7 × F(8)) × 8) + F((F(8) + 1)))
18937 := (((F(F(7)) + F(3)) × F(9)) + F(F(8))) + 1)
18954 := (F(4)⁵ - 9) × 81
19138 := (F(F(8)) + (F(3)^{F(-1+9-1)}))
19338 := ((83 × F(F(-((F(3) - 9)))) - 1)
19355 := 553 × (F(9) + 1)
19447 := F(7) × 44 × F(9) - 1
19448 := (((-((F(8)⁴)) + F(F(F(4)))) / (-9 + 1))
19449 := -F(9 + 4) + F(4)⁹ - 1
19494 := ((4 + F(9)) × ((F(F(4))⁹) + 1))
19622 := (F(22) + (F(F(6)) × 91))
19649 := -F(9) + (-F(4) + 6)⁹ × 1
19656 := 6^{-5+F(6)} × 91
19682 := F(2 + 8 - 6)⁹ - 1
19684 := F(4)⁸ × (-6 + 9) + 1
19694 := (((F(4)⁹) + F(F(6))) - (9 + 1))
19697 := F(7) + (9 - 6)⁹ + 1
19745 := 5 × (4 × F(7 + 9) + 1)
19747 := (7 + F(4)⁷) × 9 + 1
19828 := (F(F(8)) + ((F((2 × 8)) × 9) - 1))
19829 := ((9 × F((2 × 8))) + F(F((9 - 1))))
19866 := (((-F(6)) + F((-6) + F(8))) × (F(9) - 1))
19873 := (3⁷ + F(8)) × 9 + 1
19893 := 3⁹ + F(8) × (9 + 1)
19937 := (F(F(7)) - (-((3⁹)) - F((9 - 1))))
19965 := (-5 + F(6 + 9)) × (F(9) - 1)
20193 := 3 × (-F(9) + F(10 × 2))
20273 := 3 × (-7 + F(20)) - F(2)
20274 := F(4) × (-7 + F(20)) × F(2)
20295 := F(-5 + 9) × F(20) × F(2)
20296 := (-6 + 9) × F(20) + F(2)
20297 := ((F((F(7) - 9)) × F(20)) + 2)
20449 := ((F((9 + F(4))) - F(F(F(4))))⁰²)
20485 := 5 × (8⁴ + F(02))
20672 := (((-F((2 + F(7)))) + F(F(F(6)))) × 02)
20728 := (-8) + (F(-((F(2) - F(7))))⁰²)
20733 := (-3) + (F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(7))))⁰²)
20734 := (-F(F(4))) + (F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(7))))⁰²)
20735 := (F((5 × F(3))) × F((7 × 02)))
20736 := (F((6 × F(3)))^{7×0+2})
20737 := (F(F(7)) × F(-((3 - (7 × 02))))

- 20738** := $((F((8+3)) \times F(F(7))) + F(02))$
20739 := $((F((9+F(3))) \times F(F(7))) + 02)$
20746 := $(F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(4)) \times (-70^2)))$
20748 := $(F(8) \times (F((F(4)+F(7))) + F(02)))$
20865 := $(-5) \times (F(6) - F((F(8) - 02)))$
20886 := $6 \times (-F(8) + 80)^2$
20915 := $5 \times (F(19) + 02)$
20968 := $((F((F(8) - F(6))) \times 90) - 2)$
20969 := $((F((F(9) - F(F(6)))) \times 90) - F(2))$
20973 := $F(F(3)) + F(F(7)) \times 90 + 2$
20974 := $F(F(4)) + F(F(7)) \times 90 + 2$
21138 := $((F(F(8)) - (F((3+11)))) \times 2)$
21168 := $F(8) \times (6+1) \times F(12)$
21426 := $((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(((2 \times 4) - 1)))) \times 2)$
21546 := $(F(F(6)) \times (((4^5) \times 1) + 2))$
21604 := $(F(F(4)) \times (F(F(F(06))) - (F(12))))$
21625 := $(5 \times (F((-2) + F(F(6)))) + (F(12)))$
21636 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (F(3)^{6+1})) \times 2)$
21647 := $(-F(F(7))) - ((-F(F(4))) \times F(F(F(6)))) + 12)$
21648 := $((F(F(8)) - (F(F(4)) \times 61)) \times 2)$
21661 := $(-F(F((1+6))) - ((F(F(F(6))) + 1) \times (-2)))$
21667 := $(-((F(F(7)) - F(6))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-1 \times 2)))$
21678 := $((F(8) - F(F(7))) - ((F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times (-2)))$
21698 := $((F(F(8)) - (96+1)) \times 2)$
21728 := $((82 - F(F((7+1)))) \times (-2))$
21736 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times F(3)) - (F(7) \times 12))$
21744 := $(F((F(4) \times 4)) \times (7 + F(12)))$
21746 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times F(F(4))) - (F((F(7) - 1)) + 2))$
21748 := $((F(F(8)) \times F(F(4))) - F(((7-1) \times 2)))$
21762 := $((2 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7)) - (F(12)))$
21764 := $((F(F(4))^6 - F(F((7+1)))) \times (-2))$
21766 := $((-6) \times F(F(6))) - (F(F((7+1))) \times (-2))$
21776 := $((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(7) - 71))) \times 2)$
21782 := $((-F((2+8))) + F(F((7+1)))) \times 2$
21794 := $((-49) + F(F((7+1)))) \times 2$
21796 := $((F(F(F(6))) - ((F(9) + F(7)) + 1)) \times 2)$
21798 := $((F(F(8)) - (F(9) + F(7))) \times (1 \times 2))$
21824 := $((F((F(4)^2)) - F(F(8))) \times (-1 \times 2))$
21826 := $((F((F(6) + F(2))) - F(F(8))) - 1) \times (-2))$
21828 := $((F(F(8)) \times 2) - ((8 \times 1)^2))$
21835 := $-((F((5 \times F(3))) + ((F(F(8)) - 1) \times (-2))))$
21837 := $(-F((7+3))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-1 \times 2))$
21838 := $((F(F(8)) - (3 \times (8+1))) \times 2)$
21839 := $-((F((9+F(F(3)))) + ((F(F(8)) + 1) \times (-2)))$
21842 := $(((-24) + F(F(8))) - 1) \times 2$
21846 := $((F(F(6)) + F(F(4))) - F(F(8))) \times (-1 \times 2))$
21852 := $((F(F((F(2) + 5))) - ((F(F(8)) + 1))) \times (-2))$
21854 := $((-((4 \times 5)) + F(F(8))) + 1) \times 2$
21856 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5 + F((8-1)))) \times 2)$
21857 := $(-((7 \times 5)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-1 \times 2)))$
21858 := $((F(F(8)) - ((-5) + F(8)) + 1) \times 2)$
21862 := $((((-2) \times F(6)) + F(F(8))) + 1) \times 2$
21863 := $(-3) + ((F(F(F(6))) - F((8-1))) \times 2)$
21864 := $((F(F(4)) \times (-F(6) + F(F(8)))) - 12)$
21866 := $((F(6) - F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times (1 \times 2)$
21867 := $(-7) - (((-F(6)) + F(F(8))) - 1) \times (-2))$
21868 := $((F(F(8)) - F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) - (1+2)$
21869 := $(-9) - (((-F(6)) + F(F(8))) + 1) \times (-2))$
21871 := $(-F((1+7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-1 \times 2))$
21872 := $((((2 - F(7)) + F(F(8))) + 1) \times 2)$
21873 := $(-3) + (((-7) + F(F(8))) - 1) \times 2)$
21874 := $((4 - F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times (1 \times 2)$
21875 := $(-5) - (((7 - F(F(8))) - 1) \times 2)$
21876 := $((-F(6)) + F((F(7) + 8))) \times (1 \times 2)$
21877 := $(-F(7)) - ((F((F(7) + 8)) - 1) \times (-2))$
21878 := $((F(F(8)) - 7) \times F(F(((8 \times 1)/2)))$
21881 := $((1 + F(F(8))) + F(F(8))) - 12$
21882 := $((2 \times F(F(8))) - ((8 \times 1) + 2))$
21883 := $((F(3) \times F(F(8))) - ((8-1) + 2))$
21884 := $((F(F(4)) \times F(F(8))) - (8 \times (1^2)))$
21885 := $((5 + F(F(8))) + F(F(8))) - 12$
21886 := $((-6) + F(F(8))) + F(F((8 \times (1^2))))$
21887 := $((7 + F(F(8))) + F(F(8))) - 12$
21888 := $((F(F(8)) + F(F(8))) - ((8 \times 1)/2))$
21889 := $((9 + F(F(8))) + F(F(8))) - 12$
21891 := $((F(19) + F((F(8) + 1))) - F(2))$
21892 := $F(29 - 8) \times 1 \times 2$
21893 := $((F(3) \times F((F(9) - F((8-1)))) + F(2))$
21894 := $(F(4+9+8) + 1) \times 2$
21895 := $(F(-((5-9))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-1 \times 2)))$

- 21896** := $((F(-(6-9)) + F(F(8))) \times (1 \times 2))$
21897 := $(-(F(7)) - ((-9) - F(F(8))) \times (1 \times 2))$
21898 := $((F(F(8)) + 9) + F(F(8))) - (1 + 2)$
21899 := $(-9) - ((9 + F(F(8))) - 1) \times (-2))$
21908 := $((8 + F(F((09-1)))) \times 2)$
21912 := $(F(21) + 9 + 1) \times 2$
21918 := $((F(F(8)) + F(-((1-9) + 1))) \times 2)$
21924 := $((4^2) + F(F((9-1)))) \times 2$
21926 := $(F((F(6) + F(2))) - (F(F((9-1)))) \times (-2))$
21928 := $((F(F(8)) \times 2) + (F(9) + (1 \times 2)))$
21934 := $((F((4 \times F(3))) + F(F((9-1)))) \times 2)$
21936 := $((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))) + F(F((9-1)))) \times 2$
21938 := $((F(F(8)) \times F(3)) + (F(9) + 12))$
21946 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times F(F(4))) + (F((9+1)) - F(2)))$
21947 := $(F((F(7) - F(4))) - (F(F((9-1)))) \times (-2))$
21948 := $((F(F(8)) \times F(F(4))) + (F((9+1)) + F(2)))$
21957 := $((F(7) \times 5) - (F(F((9-1)))) \times (-2))$
21963 := $F(F(3)) + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9) + 1) \times 2$
21964 := $F(F(4)) + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9) + 1) \times 2$
21976 := $((6 \times 7) + F(F((9-1)))) \times 2$
21982 := $((2 \times F(F(8))) + (91 - F(2)))$
21983 := $((F(3) \times F(F(8))) + (91 \times F(2)))$
21984 := $((F(F(4)) \times F(F(8))) + (91 + F(2)))$
21986 := $((-F(6)) + F(F(8))) + F((9+1)) \times 2$
21994 := $((F(4) \times F(9)) - (F(F((9-1)))) \times (-2))$
22116 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (112)) \times 2)$
22127 := $(F(F(7)) - ((F(21) + F(2)) \times (-2))$
22167 := $(-F(7)) - ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(12))) \times (-2))$
22168 := $((F(F(8)) + (-6) + F(12)) \times 2)$
22176 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (71 \times 2)) \times 2)$
22178 := $((F(F(8)) + F((F(7) - 1))) - F(2)) \times 2$
22198 := $((F(F(8)) + (9 + F(12))) \times 2)$
22356 := $((F(F(F(6))) + F(F((5 + F(3)))) - F(2)) \times 2)$
22357 := $((F(F(7)) + F(F((5 + 3)))) \times 2) - F(2)$
22358 := $((F(F(8)) + F((5 \times 3) - 2)) \times 2)$
22374 := $(F(4) \times ((F(F(7)) \times 32) + 2))$
22376 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + (3^2))) \times 2)$
22468 := $((F(F(8)) + (F((F(6) + (4)))) \times 2) \times 2)$
22578 := $((F(F(8)) + (7^{5-2})) \times 2)$
22646 := $((F(F(F(6))) + F(((4 + F(6)) + 2))) \times 2)$
22647 := $((F((7 \times F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 2) + F(2)$
22776 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) \times F((7+2)))) \times 2)$
22782 := $((2^8) \times F((F(7) - 2))) - 2$
22783 := $((F(3)^8) \times F((F(7) - 2))) - F(2)$
22784 := $((F(F(4))^8) \times F(((7+2) + 2)))$
22799 := $(F(9) + 9 \times F(7))^2 - 2$
22837 := $((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(3)) + (F(8)))) + F(22))$
22877 := $((-F(7)) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(8)) + F(22)$
22879 := $(F((9+7)) - (F(F(8)) \times (F(2) \times (-2))))$
22883 := $(F((F(3) \times 8)) - ((F(F(8)) + 2) \times (-2)))$
23176 := $-F(6) + F((7+1) \times 3)/2$
23177 := $-7 + F((7+1) \times 3)/2$
23182 := $-2 + F(8 \times 1 \times 3)/2$
23183 := $F(3 \times 8)/F(1 \times 3) - F(2)$
23184 := $F(4 \times (8+1-3))/2$
23188 := $(8 + F(8 \times 1 \times 3))/2$
23197 := $F(7) + F((9-1) \times 3)/2$
23238 := $((F((F(8) - 3)) - 2) \times (3^2))$
23256 := $F(6 \times (5-2)) \times 3^2$
23264 := $(F(4)^6 - 2) \times 32$
23278 := $((F(F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) - 2) \times 3)) \times 2)$
23329 := $((F(9) + 2)^3 + F(3))/2$
23409 := $(9 + F(04 \times 3))^2$
23478 := $F(8) \times F(7) \times 43 \times 2$
23488 := $(F(F(8)) - ((F((F(8) - F(F(4)))) \times (-3)) + F(2)))$
23489 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(((F(4) + F(3))^2))$
23576 := $((F(F(F(6)))/F(7)) + (F(F((5+3)))) \times 2)$
23578 := $((F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + (F((5 \times 3)))) \times 2$
23664 := $((4 \times 6) \times (F((F(6) \times F(3))) - F(2)))$
23675 := $((-5) + (7 \times F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))))) / 2$
23676 := $(6 \times ((-F(F(7))) + F((F(F(6)) - F(3)))) - 2)$
23686 := $((F((F(6) + 8)) \times (F(6) \times 3)) - 2)$
23688 := $F(8+8) \times 6 \times F(3) \times 2$
23715 := $(-51) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(3))) + F(2))$
23716 := $((F(F(6)) + 1) \times 7)^{F(3) \times F(2)}$
23718 := $((F(8) + 1) \times 7)^{F(3)} + 2$
23732 := $((-F(2)) + (3 \times F(F(7)))) \times F((3^2))$
23736 := $((F(6) \times 3) \times (F((F(7) + 3)) + 2))$
23748 := $((F(F(8)) + (4 \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(3)))) \times 2)$

$$23762 := ((F((-F(2)) + F(F(6)))) - (F(F(7))^{F(3)})) / (-2))$$

$$23763 := (3 \times (F((F(6) + F((7 - 3)))^2)))$$

$$23764 := (((F((F(4) + (6))) \times F(F(7))) \times 3) - 2)$$

$$23767 := ((F(F(7)) \times ((F(6) \times F(7)) - F(3))) + F(2))$$

$$23776 := (F(F(F(6))) - ((-F(7)) \times F((F(7) + 3))) + F(2))$$

$$23778 := (F(F(8)) - ((-F(7)) \times F((F(7) + 3))) - F(2))$$

$$23793 := (3 \times ((F(9) \times F(F(7))) + (3^2)))$$

$$23795 := (-5) + (F(9) \times ((F(F(7)) \times 3) + F(2)))$$

$$23798 := (((F(F(8)) - F(9)) + F((F(7) + 3))) \times 2)$$

$$23799 := (F(9) + (((-F(9)) \times F(F(7))) \times (-3)) - F(2))$$

$$23826 := 6 \times (2 + (F(8) \times 3)^2)$$

$$23856 := (F(F(F(6))) - (-5) \times (F((F(8) - 3)) - 2))$$

$$23862 := (((F((2 \times F(6))) + F(F(8))) - F(3)) \times 2)$$

$$23863 := (-3) - ((F(F(F(6))) + (F((8 \times F(3)))) \times (-2))$$

$$23864 := ((F((F(F(4)) \times F(6))) + (F(F(8)) - F(F(3)))) \times 2)$$

$$23865 := (((F((-5) + F(F(6)))) + F(F(8))) \times F(3)) - F(2))$$

$$23866 := ((F((F(6) + F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times (F(3) \times F(2)))$$

$$23868 := (((F(F(8)) + F((F(6) + 8))) + F(F(3))) \times 2)$$

$$23898 := F(8) \times F(9) + F(8 \times 3) / 2$$

$$23936 := ((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))) \times (F(9) \times 32))$$

$$23945 := (-5) \times ((-F(4)) \times F((F(9) / F(3)))) + 2)$$

$$23953 := (((3 \times 5) \times F((F(9) / F(3)))) - 2)$$

$$23954 := (((F(4) \times 5) \times F((F(9) / F(3)))) - F(2))$$

$$23965 := (-5) \times ((F((F(6) + 9)) \times (-3)) - 2)$$

$$23967 := (-F(F(7))) - ((-F(6)) \times (F((9 + F(F(3))))^2))$$

$$23972 := (((2 + F(F(7))) \times (F(9) \times 3)) + 2)$$

$$23978 := (-F(8)) - (F(F(7)) \times ((F(9) \times (-3)) - F(2)))$$

$$23991 := (-1 + F(9)) \times (9^3 - 2)$$

$$24126 := F(6)^2 \times F(14) - 2$$

$$24128 := 8^2 \times F(14) \times F(2)$$

$$24198 := ((8 \times (F((9 + 1))^{F(F(4))})) - 2)$$

$$24255 := 55 \times F(2 \times 4)^2$$

$$24276 := (F(F(6)) \times (F((7 + 2))^{4-2}))$$

$$24278 := ((F(8) \times (F((7 + 2))^{F(F(4))})) + 2)$$

$$24296 := (((-F(F(6))) \times ((-F(9)^2) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(2))$$

$$24297 := F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2)$$

$$24298 := (((-F(8)) \times ((-F(9)^2) - F(F(F(4)))) + F(2))$$

$$24326 := -F(6) + 23^{F(4)} \times 2$$

$$24327 := -7 + 23^{F(4)} \times 2$$

$$24328 := ((F(8) + 2)^3 - F(4)) \times 2$$

$$24332 := (((23^3) \times F(F(4))) - 2)$$

$$24334 := (-4 + 3^3)^{F(4)} \times 2$$

$$24337 := F(7)^{F(3)} \times F(3 \times 4) + F(2)$$

$$24338 := (((-F(8) + F(3))^3) - F(F(4))) \times (-2)$$

$$24339 := (F(9)^{F(3)} + 3) \times F(4 \times 2)$$

$$24368 := (F(8) + F(6))^3 - F(4 \times 2)$$

$$24386 := (F(6) + F(8))^3 - 4 + F(2)$$

$$24387 := (F(7) + 8 \times F(3))^{F(4)} - 2$$

$$24388 := (8 + F(8))^3 - F(4 - 2)$$

$$24389 := (F(9) - 8 + 3)^{F(4)} \times F(2)$$

$$24392 := (29^3 + F(4)) \times F(2)$$

$$24395 := (-5 + F(9))^3 + 4 + 2$$

$$24447 := F(7 \times 4) / (F(4) \times 4 + F(2))$$

$$24465 := ((5 \times F(F(6))) \times F(((F(4) \times 4) + F(2))))$$

$$24467 := (((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) \times (F(F(4)) + F(4))) + 2)$$

$$24468 := (F(F(8)) + ((F((F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))) - 4) \times 2))$$

$$24475 := (-5) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-F((4 + 4)))) - 2)$$

$$24476 := -((F((6 + F(7))) - F((F((4 + 4) + 2))))$$

$$24546 := (F(6)^4 - 5) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$24574 := (((F(F(4))^{F(7)}) \times (5 - F(F(4)))) - 2)$$

$$24576 := 6 \times (F(7) - 5)^4 \times F(2)$$

$$24625 := ((5^2) \times (F((F(6) \times F(F(4)))) - 2))$$

$$24626 := (((F(F(6)) - 2) \times (6^4)) + 2)$$

$$24646 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)) - ((F(6)^4) \times 2))$$

$$24647 := (((F(7) + F((4 + F(6))))^{F(F(4))}) - 2)$$

$$24649 := (F(9) \times F(4) + F(6 + 4))^2$$

$$24662 := ((-2) + F(F(6))) \times ((6^4) + 2)$$

$$24673 := ((F((3 + F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + (4))) - 2)$$

$$24674 := ((F((F(4) + F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + (4))) - F(2))$$

$$24675 := 5 \times (F(7) - F(6)) \times F(4^2)$$

$$24696 := (F(F(6)) \times ((F(9) - (6)) \times 42))$$

$$24725 := ((5^2) \times (F((F(7) + F(4))) + 2))$$

$$24738 := (((-F(8)) + F((F(3) + F(7)))) \times 42)$$

$$24768 := ((86 \times F((F(7) - F(F(F(4)))))) \times 2)$$

$$24785 := (-5) \times ((-F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(4))) - F(2))$$

$$24843 := (3 \times ((F(F(4)) + F((8 + F(4))))^2))$$

$$24964 := (F(4) \times 6 \times 9 - 4)^2$$

- 24977** := $(F(7) + ((79 \times F(F(4)))^2))$
24989 := $((-(F(9) \times F(8))) \times (-F(9) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(2))$
24997 := $7 \times (F(9+9) + F(4^2))$
24999 := $((-F(9) + F((F(9) - 9)))/F(4) + 2)$
25086 := $(6 \times F((F(8) - ((0 \times 5) + 2)))$
25368 := $F(8) \times (-6 + F(3 \times 5)) \times 2$
25376 := $F(6) \times F(7) \times (3^5 + F(2))$
25387 := $-((F(F(7)) - ((F(8) \times F((3 \times 5))) \times 2))$
25397 := $(F(F(7)) \times (F(9) + ((3 \times (5^2))))$
25532 := $(F(23) - 5^5) \times F(2)$
25536 := $(F(F(6)) \times (((3^5) \times 5) + F(2)))$
25632 := $(-F(23) + (F((F(6) + (5)))^2))$
25661 := $((F(16) \times (F(F(6)) + (5))) - F(2))$
25662 := $26 \times F(6 + 5 \times 2)$
25663 := $((F((F(3) \times F(6))) \times (F(F(6)) + (5))) + F(2))$
25664 := $((F((F(F(4)) \times F(6))) \times (F(F(6)) + (5))) + 2)$
25678 := $((8 + (F(7) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5)))) \times 2)$
25725 := $(F(F((5 + F(2)))) \times ((7 \times 5)^2))$
25746 := $(F(F(6)) \times (F(F(F(4))) + (((7 \times 5)^2))))$
25775 := $(-5) \times (F(7) - (F((F(7) + (5))) \times 2))$
25795 := $(-5) \times (9 - (F((F(7) + (5))) \times 2))$
25834 := $((F(4) + (F((-3) + F(8))) \times (-5)) \times (-2))$
25835 := $(-5) + (F((-3) + F(8))) \times (5 \times 2))$
25921 := $(1 + (-2 + F(9)) \times 5)^2$
26047 := $(7 \times ((40 + F(F(6)))^2))$
26136 := $(6 \times ((3 \times (1 + F(F(6))))^2))$
26364 := $((F((F(F(F(4))) + 6))^3) \times (6 \times 2))$
26376 := $(6 + F(7)^3 \times 6) \times 2$
26377 := $F(7) + F(7)^3 \times 6 \times 2$
26402 := $(-(F(20)/F(4)) + F((F(F(6)) + 2)))$
26416 := $((-6) \times F(14) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-2)$
26447 := $((F(F(7)) - F(4))^{F(F(4))} - (6))/2$
26448 := $(F((F(8) - F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(4))^{F(6)+F(2)})))$
26473 := $((-(3^7) + F(4) + F((F(F(6)) + 2)))$
26474 := $(-((F(4)^7) - (4)) + F((F(F(6)) + 2)))$
26484 := $(4 \times (-F((8 + 4))) + F((F(F(6)) - F(2))))$
26496 := $((F(6) \times F((9 + F(4)))) \times (F(F(6)) + 2))$
26556 := $-((F(F(F(6))) + ((-F((5 \times 5)) + F(F(6))))/2))$
26565 := $((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) - (-((5^6) + F(2)))$
26566 := $(F(F(F(6))) - ((6 - (5^6)) - F(2)))$
26569 := $((((9 \times F(F(6))) - (5)) - F(F(6)))^2)$
26571 := $(F(F((1 + 7))) + ((5^6) \times F(2)))$
26572 := $(F(F((F(2) + (7)))) - (-((5^6) - F(2)))$
26573 := $F(3 \times 7) + 5^6 + 2$
26576 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (7 + ((5^6) - 2)))$
26578 := $(F(F(8)) - (-((7 + (5^6))) \times F(2)))$
26637 := $F(7) \times (F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(6) + F(2))$
26645 := $(-5) \times (F((4 + F(6))) + (F(F(F(6)))/(-2)))$
26647 := $((F((F(7) + F(4))) \times (F(F(6)) + (6))) - 2)$
26648 := $((F((8 \times F(F(4)))) \times (F(F(6)) + (6))) - F(2))$
26649 := $((9 \times F(4)) \times F((F(6) \times F((6/2))))$
26657 := $((F(F(7)) \times 5) - (6)) \times (F(F(6)) + 2)$
26675 := $(5 \times ((F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(6))) + F(2))$
26676 := $((6 \times F(F(7))) + (6)) \times (F(F(6)) - 2)$
26683 := $(F((F(3) + F(8))) + (F((F(6) + F(6))) \times (-2)))$
26725 := $(-5) \times ((2^7) + (F(F(F(6)))/(-2)))$
26738 := $(F(F(8)) - (F((3 + F(7))) \times (F(6) \times (-2))))$
26749 := $((F(9)^{F(F(4))} + (7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 2))$
26765 := $(-5) \times (6 - (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 2)))$
26767 := $(F((-7) + F(F(6))) \times (7 + (F(6)^2)))$
26775 := $((5 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(7)) - F(6)))/2$
26778 := $((F(8) \times F(F(7))) - (7)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 2)$
26783 := $((F(3) \times F(F(8))) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) - 2))$
26784 := $((F(F(4)) \times F(F(8))) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) - F(2)))$
26786 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(8)) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + F(2))))$
26792 := $((2 \times F(9)) \times F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2$
26793 := $((F(F(3)) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + F((F(F(6)) + 2)))$
26797 := $((F(F(7)) \times (F(9) \times 7)) - F((F(F(6)) + 2)))$
26827 := $(-F(F(7))) - (F(-((F(2) - F(8)))) \times (-6 - 2))$
26846 := $((F(F(6))^{F(F(4))} - 8) \times 62)$
26896 := $(F(6) + (F(9) - 8) \times 6)^2$
26924 := $(4 \times (-((F(2) \times F(9))) + F((F(F(6)) - F(2))))$
26928 := $(F(8) + F(2)) \times F(9) \times 6^2$
26938 := $((F(8)^3 - F(9)) + F((F(F(6)) + F(2))))$
26987 := $-F(7) + (F(8) + 9)^{6/2}$
26992 := $((-((F((2 \times 9)) - F(9))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-2))$
26998 := $(F(8) + 9)^{9-6} - 2$
27024 := $4 \times (F(20) - 7 - 2)$

- 27144** := ((F((F(4) × 4)) × F((1 + F(7))))/2)
27147 := (F(7) + 4) × F(17) - 2
27148 := (F(8) - 4) × F(17) - F(2)
27149 := ((F(9)/F(F(4))) × (F(17) × F(2)))
27164 := (4 × (F((F(F(6)) - 1)) + (F(7) × 2)))
27183 := (((F(-(F(3) - F(8)))) + 1) × (-F(7)))/(-2))
27195 := (-5) × (F(9) + (F(F((1 + 7)))/(-2)))
27216 := (F(F(6)) × (F(12) × (7 + 2)))
27225 := F(5 × 2)² × (7 + 2)
27259 := (((9 × F(F((5 + 2)))) × F(7)) - 2)
27261 := (((F(F((1 + 6)))²) + F(F(7)))/2)
27268 := ((F(F(8)) - (F(F(6)) × (-2⁷))) × 2)
27279 := (9 × ((F(F(7)) × (F(2) × F(7))) + 2))
27287 := (-F(7)) × (((-8) - F(2)) × F(F(7))) - 2))
27288 := (F(F(8)) - ((F(8) - (2^{F(7)})) × 2))
27296 := (F(F(F(6))) - (F(9) - ((2⁷)²)))
27326 := (F(F(F(6))) - (-2) × ((F(3)^{F(7)}) - 2))
27328 := (F(F(8)) + (((F(2) + 3)⁷) - 2))
27336 := (F(F(F(6))) + ((3 + (F(3)^{F(7)})) × 2))
27345 := 5 × (4 + F(3 × 7))/2
27356 := (((F(F(F(6))) × (-5))/(-F(3))) - (7 + 2))
27358 := (((F(F(8)) × (-5))/(-F(3))) - (7 × F(2)))
27363 := (-F(3) - ((F(F(F(6)))/(-F(3))) × (7 - 2)))
27364 := (((-F(F(4))) - (F(F(F(6))) × (F(3) - (7))))/2)
27365 := 5 × F((6 - 3) × 7)/2
27366 := -((F(F(F(6))) - (((F(F(F(6)))/(-F(3))) × (-7)) + F(2)))
27375 := ((-5) + ((F(F(7)) + F(3)) × F(F(7))))/2
27377 := (F(F(7)) + (F((7 × F(3))) × 72))
27379 := ((9 × ((F(F(7)) + F(F(3))) × F(7))) + F(2))
27385 := 5 × (8 + F(3 × 7))/2
27386 := (F(F(6)) - ((F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) × (7 - 2))
27398 := (F(F(8)) + ((F(9) + (F(3)^{F(7)})) × 2))
27459 := (9 × ((5 × F((F(F(4)) + (F(7)))))) + F(2))
27467 := ((F(F(7)) - (6)) × ((4 + 7)²)
27468 := F(8) × (6⁴ + F(7) - F(2))
27494 := (((F(4) + F((9 + 4))) × F(F(7)))/2)
27495 := (((59 × F(F(4))) × F(F(7))) + F(2))
27497 := (((F(7) × 9) × (F(F(4)) + F(F(7)))) + 2)
27628 := (F((F(8) + 2)) + (F(F(6)) × (-7²)))
27634 := (((-4) × F((F(3) × F(6)))) × (-7)) - 2)
27636 := (F((F(6) × F(3))) × (-6) + F((7 + 2)))
27637 := ((F((F(7) + 3)) × (F(F(6)) + (7))) + F(2))
27638 := ((F((8 × F(3))) × (F(F(6)) + (7))) + 2)
27644 := (4 × ((F((F(F(4)) × F(6))) × 7) + 2))
27648 := 8^{F(4)} × 6 × (7 + 2)
27727 := (F(F(7)) × (((2⁷) - 7) - 2))
27729 := (((9 - (2⁷)) × F(F(7))) + 2)
27753 := (F(F((3 + 5))) + ((7⁷⁻²)))
27758 := (F(F(8)) + (5 + (7⁷⁻²)))
27783 := 3 × F(8)^{7/7+2}
27792 := (2 + F(9)) × 772
27819 := ((F(9) - 1) × ((F(F(8)))/F(7)) + F(2))
27846 := (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(F(4)) + 8) × F(7))²))
27847 := F(7)⁴ - F(8) × F(7 + 2)
27848 := 8 × (F(4) + 8 × 7)²
27928 := (F((F(8) + 2)) - (((F(9) - (7))²)))
27936 := (F((6 × F(3))) × (97 × 2))
27963 := (3 × (((6 + F(9)) × F(F(7))) + F(2)))
27964 := (4 × (((F(F(6)) + 9) × F(F(7))) + F(2)))
27968 := (8 × (((6 + 9) × F(F(7))) + F(2)))
27976 := (-((F(6) × F(7))) × ((-F(9)) - F(F(7))) - 2))
28047 := -((F((F(7) + F(F(4)))) + (0 - F((F(8) + 2))))))
28146 := (-(((F(6)^{F(4)}) - 1)) + F((F(8) + 2)))
28216 := -(((F(F(6))^{1×2}) - F((F(8) + 2))))
28237 := F(7) + (F(3 × 2) × F(8))²
28266 := (F(F(6)) × (((F(6)²) × F(8)) + 2))
28275 := ((-5) - F((7 × 2))) + F((F(8) + 2))
28278 := -(((F((F(8) - (7))) + 2) - F((F(8) + 2))))
28288 := (8 × F(8))² + 8²
28328 := ((F((8 × 2)))/(-3)) + F((F(8) + 2))
28359 := (((F(9)^{5-F(3)}) - F(F(8))) + F(2))
28369 := (-((96 × 3)) + F((F(8) + 2)))
28376 := F(6) × (F(7)^{F(3)} × F(8) - 2)
28387 := (-(((F(7) × F(8)) - 3)) + F((F(8) + 2)))
28397 := -(((F(F(7)) + (9 × 3)) - F((F(8) + 2))))
28414 := (-((F(4)¹⁺⁴)) + F((F(8) + 2)))
28424 := -((F(((F(4)²) + (4))) - F((F(8) + 2))))
28425 := (((-F(F((5 + 2)))) + F(F(F(4)))) + (F((F(8) + 2))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 28426 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + 2)) + F(F(4))) - F(F((8 - F(2)))))) \\
 28427 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-F(2))) + F(4)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28428 &:= ((F((F(8) + 2)) + (4)) - F(F((8 - F(2)))))) \\
 28431 &:= 13 \times F(4)^{8-F(2)} \\
 28437 &:= ((F((7 + 3)) \times (-4)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28446 &:= (6^4 - F(4)) \times (F(8) + F(2)) \\
 28449 &:= ((9^4) - ((F(F(4)) - F(F(8))) \times 2)) \\
 28453 &:= ((3^{5+F(4)}) + (F(F(8)) \times 2)) \\
 28457 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((5 + F(4)) \times F(8))^2)) \\
 28459 &:= (((F(9) \times 5)^{F(F(4))}) - (F(8)^2)) \\
 28468 &:= ((F(8) \times (-6) - F(4)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28469 &:= (((-9) \times F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) + (F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28476 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((F(F(7)) \times (-F(4))) + (F(8))) \times (-2))) \\
 28479 &:= (-9) - ((F(7)^{F(F(4))}) - F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28486 &:= (-(((F(6) \times F(8)) + F(4))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28487 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - (F(8) \times F(4)))) - F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28488 &:= -(((((-8) + F(8))^{F(F(4))}) - F((F(8) + 2)))) \\
 28489 &:= (((F(9) + 8) \times (-4)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28492 &:= ((F((F(2) + 9)) \times (-F(4))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28513 &:= -((F(-((3 - 15))) - F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28527 &:= ((F(7)^{-F(2)+5}) - F((8 + F(2)))) \\
 28532 &:= F(23) - 5^{F(8/2)} \\
 28535 &:= ((F((5 \times 3)) / (-5)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28544 &:= 4^{F(4)} \times (5 + F(8)^2) \\
 28547 &:= F(7)^4 + 5 - F(8) + 2 \\
 28552 &:= ((F(F((F(2) + (5)))) \times (-5)) + (F((F(8) + 2)))) \\
 28561 &:= 1 \times (F(6) + 5)^{8/2} \\
 28562 &:= F(2) + ((F(6) + (5))^{8/2}) \\
 28563 &:= F(3) + ((F(6) + (5))^{8/2}) \\
 28564 &:= F(4) + ((F(6) + (5))^{8/2}) \\
 28564 &:= F(4) + (F(6) + 5)^{8/2} \\
 28566 &:= -(((F(F(6)) - (F(6)^5)) + F((F(8) - 2)))) \\
 28568 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F((6 + 5)))) + F((F(8) + F(2)))) \\
 28573 &:= -((F(-((F(3) - F(7)))) + (-5 - F((F(8) + 2)))))) \\
 28575 &:= (F(((5 + F(7)) + (5))) - (82)) \\
 28576 &:= (-((6 + 75)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28584 &:= (-((F(4) - (8^5))) - F((F(8) - 2))) \\
 28586 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((8 \times 5) \times (F(8)^2))) \\
 28587 &:= ((-((F(7) - F(8)))^5) - F((F(8) - 2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28588 &:= (-(((8 \times 8) + 5)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28589 &:= (-((F(9) \times F((8 - 5)))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28592 &:= ((F(-((2 - 9))) \times (-5)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28593 &:= (F(((F(3) \times 9) + (5))) - ((8^2))) \\
 28594 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times (-F(9))) + (5)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28602 &:= -((F((2 + F(06))) - F((F(8) + 2)))) \\
 28613 &:= ((F(3) \times (-1) - F(F(6))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28615 &:= -(((F(F((5 - 1))) \times F(F(6))) - F((F(8) + 2)))) \\
 28616 &:= -((((F(F(6)) - 1) + F(F(6))) - F((F(8) + 2)))) \\
 28622 &:= ((-F(2)) - F((F(2) + F(6)))) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28623 &:= (3 + 26) \times F(8 \times 2) \\
 28624 &:= F(4^2) \times (F(6) + F(8)) + F(2) \\
 28625 &:= (((-5) + F(2)) \times F(6)) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28626 &:= ((-((F(6) + 2)) - F(F(6))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28627 &:= (-(((7 - 2) \times 6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28628 &:= (F((F(8) + 2)) - ((6 + F(8)) + 2)) \\
 28629 &:= (-(((F(9) \times F(2)) - (6))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28632 &:= F(23) - 6 - F(8) + 2 \\
 28633 &:= (((F(3) + F(3)) \times (-6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28634 &:= (((-4) + F(3)) - F(F(6))) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28635 &:= F(5 + 3 \times 6) - F(8) - F(2) \\
 28636 &:= ((F((F(6) \times 3)) - F(F(6))) - F((F(8) + F(2)))) \\
 28637 &:= (((-7) \times F(3)) - (6)) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28638 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(3)) - F(F(6))) + F((F(8) + F(2)))) \\
 28639 &:= (-(((9/3) \times 6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28641 &:= F(-1 + 4 \times 6) - 8 \times 2 \\
 28642 &:= (-((F((2 \times 4)) - (6))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28643 &:= (((F(3) \times (-4)) - (6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28644 &:= (-4 + 4^6) \times (8 - F(2)) \\
 28645 &:= (((5 - F(4)) \times (-6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28646 &:= (((-6) + F(4)) - F(6)) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28647 &:= (F((F(7) + (4 + 6))) - (8 + 2)) \\
 28648 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(4) + (6))) + F((F(8) + F(2)))) \\
 28649 &:= (F(((F(9) - F(4)) - F(6))) - F((8 - 2))) \\
 28651 &:= (F((15 + F(6))) - (8 - 2)) \\
 28652 &:= (((-2 - 5) - F(6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28653 &:= (F(((3 \times 5) + F(6))) - (8/2)) \\
 28654 &:= -F(4) + F(-5 + (6 + 8) \times 2) \\
 28655 &:= F(5 \times 5 + 6 - 8) - 2 \\
 28656 &:= (-(((6 - 5)^6)) + F((F(8) + 2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28657 &:= F(7 \times 5 - 6 - 8 + 2) \\
 28658 &:= (F(F(8)) + (F(((5 \times 6) - 8)) + F(2))) \\
 28659 &:= F(-9 \times 5 + 68) + 2 \\
 28661 &:= (F((1 + F(F(6)))) + ((6 + F(F(8))) - 2)) \\
 28662 &:= (-(((F(2))^{F(6)}) - (6))) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28663 &:= ((36/6) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28664 &:= ((F(-((4 - 6))) + (6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28665 &:= (F((5 + (6/6))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28666 &:= ((F(6) + (6/6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28667 &:= (F(((7 + F(6)) + F(6))) + (8 + 2)) \\
 28669 &:= ((F((9 - 6)) \times 6) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28671 &:= -1 + 7 \times F(6)^{8/2} \\
 28672 &:= F(2) \times 7 \times F(6)^{8/2} \\
 28673 &:= F(F(3)) + 7 \times F(6)^{8/2} \\
 28674 &:= F(F(4)) + 7 \times F(6)^{8/2} \\
 28678 &:= F(8) + F(7 + 6 + 8 + 2) \\
 28681 &:= ((18 + 6) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28682 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((6 + F(8)) - 2)) \\
 28683 &:= (F((F(3) + F(8))) + ((6 + F(8)) - F(2))) \\
 28684 &:= ((48 - F(F(6))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28686 &:= (((F(6) + F(F(8))) + F(F(6))) + F((F(8) + F(2)))) \\
 28687 &:= (((F(7) - 8) \times 6) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28689 &:= ((F(9) - (8 - 6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 \\
 28691 &:= (F(((1^9) + F(6))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28692 &:= ((29 + 6) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28693 &:= (-(((3 - 9) \times 6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28694 &:= (-(((F(4) - F(9)) - (6))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28695 &:= ((59 - F(F(6))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28704 &:= ((40 + 7) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28712 &:= (F(((2 + 1) + 7)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28715 &:= ((51 + 7) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28719 &:= ((F((9 + 1)) + (7)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28725 &:= ((F((5 \times 2)) + F(7)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28726 &:= ((62 + 7) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28728 &:= (F((F(8) + 2)) + (7 + (8^2))) \\
 28729 &:= ((9 \times (F(2) + (7))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28732 &:= F(23) - 7 + 82 \\
 28734 &:= (((4^3) + F(7)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28735 &:= (((5 + F(F(3))) \times F(7)) + F((F(8) + 2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28736 &:= (((6^3) + F(F(7))) \times (8^2)) \\
 28737 &:= ((73 + 7) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28738 &:= ((-8) + F(-((F(3) - F(7)))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28739 &:= ((F((9 + F(3))) - (7)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28743 &:= ((-3) + F((4 + 7))) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28744 &:= -(((F(F(4)) - F((4 + 7))) - F((F(8) + 2)))) \\
 28746 &:= 6 \times F(4) \times F(7 + 8 + 2) \\
 28748 &:= ((84 + 7) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28759 &:= ((95 + 7) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28761 &:= ((F((1 \times 6)) \times F(7)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28762 &:= F(2) + F(6) \times F(7) + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28763 &:= F(3) + F(6) \times F(7) + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28764 &:= F(4) + F(6) \times F(7) + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28769 &:= ((F(9) - (-6) \times F(7)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28772 &:= (((2^7) - F(7)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28774 &:= (((-4) + F(7)) \times F(7)) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28778 &:= (((F(8) \times 7) \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(8))/(-2))) \\
 28783 &:= (((-3) + F(8)) \times 7) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28784 &:= (F((F(F(4)) + (F(8)))) + ((F(F(7)) + (F(8)))/2)) \\
 28785 &:= ((F(-((5 - 8)))^7) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28794 &:= F(4 + 9) + F(7)^{8/2} \\
 28819 &:= ((9 \times 18) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28824 &:= (4 \times (F(-((F(2) - F(8)))) + (F(8)^2)) \\
 28825 &:= ((F((5 + F(2))) \times F(8)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28826 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + 2)) + ((-8) + F(8))^2) \\
 28846 &:= (((6 + F(4)) \times F(8)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28847 &:= (((F(7))^{F(F(4))}) + (F(8))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28865 &:= (((5 + F(F(6))) \times 8) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28869 &:= (((F(9) \times 6) + 8) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28876 &:= (((-6) + F(F(7))) - 8) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28877 &:= (((F(F(7)) - (F(7))) + F(F(8))) + F((F(8) + F(2)))) \\
 28882 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - 8) + F(F((8 - F(2)))) \\
 28885 &:= ((-5) + F((-8) + F(8))) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28913 &:= ((F(3))^{-1+9}) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28924 &:= ((F(4) \times F((2 + 9))) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28928 &:= (F((F(8) + 2)) + ((F(9) \times 8) - F(2))) \\
 28929 &:= (((9 - F(2)) \times F(9)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28946 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + F(F(4)))) + ((9 + 8)^2)) \\
 28963 &:= (((3 + 6) \times F(9)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 29125 &:= ((5^{2+1}) \times F(F((9 - 2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 29163** := $(3 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((1 + F(9))^2)))$
29177 := $7 \times (-F(7) + F(19)) + F(2)$
29197 := $7 \times (-9 + F(19) - F(2))$
29241 := $(1 + (F(4) + 2) \times F(9))^2$
29264 := $(-F(4) - (F((F(F(6)) - 2)) \times (-9 - 2)))$
29267 := $7 \times F(6 + 2 + 9 + 2)$
29288 := $(F(8) - (F((F(8) - 2)) \times (-9 - 2)))$
29358 := $(-F(8) \times ((-5) - F(F(3))) \times F(F((9 - 2))))$
29364 := $(F(4) \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((F(3) + (F(9)^2))))$
29376 := $((((F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))) \times 3) + 9) \times 2)$
29442 := $(F(F((2 \times 4))) + ((4 \times F(9))^2))$
29446 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (4 + ((4 \times F(9))^2)))$
29486 := $(F(F(F(6))) - (((F(8))^{F(4)} + 9) \times (-2)))$
29529 := $((9 \times F(2))^5 + 9)/2$
29584 := $((F(F(-((4 - 8)))) + (5 \times F(9)))^2)$
29644 := $(F((4 \times 4)) + F((6 + (F(9)/2))))$
29653 := $((F(3) \times (5^6)) - F((F(9)/2)))$
29664 := $(F((4 + F(6))) \times ((6 \times F(9)) + 2))$
29736 := $(-6) \times ((-3) - F(F(7))) \times F((9 - F(2)))$
29738 := $(F(F(8)) + ((F(F(3)) - F(F(7))) \times (-9^2)))$
29766 := $(6 \times ((F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(9) \times (-2)))$
29793 := $(((-3) + F(9))^{F(F(7)-9)} + 2)$
29799 := $(99 \times (F(F(7)) - (F(9) \times (-2))))$
29813 := $F(31 - 8) + F(9)^2$
29824 := $((4^2) \times 8) \times F(F((9 - 2)))$
29887 := $((F((7 + F(8))) + F(F(8)))/9 + 2)$
29986 := $((F(F(6)) \times ((8 + F(9)) \times F(9))) - 2)$
29988 := $F(8) \times (8 + F(9)) \times F(9) \times F(2)$
29989 := $98 \times F(9) \times 9 + F(2)$
30696 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (-F(9) \times F(F(6)))) \times 03)$
30976 := $(F(6) \times (F(7) + 9))^{F(03)}$
31329 := $(F(9 + 2) \times F(3) - 1)^{F(3)}$
31584 := $((4 \times 8) \times F(((5 - 1)^{F(3)})))$
31646 := $(-((F(F(F(6))) - (4 \times ((F(F(6)) + 1)^3))))$
31668 := $((-F(8)) \times F((F(6) + (6)))) \times (-1 + 3))$
31676 := $((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) - 1)) \times F(3))$
31678 := $((F(F(8)) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) \times F((1 \times 3)))$
31684 := $((F((4 + 8)) + F((F(6) + 1)))^{F(3)})$
31848 := $(-((F((8 \times F(F(4)))) - ((F(F(8)) - 1) \times 3)))$
31928 := $(-((F(F(8)) + (F(2) - ((F(9) + 1)^3))))$
31929 := $(-((F(F((9 - F(2)))) - ((F(9) + 1)^3))))$
31944 := $(F(4) \times ((F(F(F(4))) + (F((9 - 1))))^3))$
32158 := $8^5 - F(12 + 3)$
32258 := $((F(8) + F(F((5 + 2))))^2)/F(3)$
32358 := $((F(F(8)) - (5 \times 32)) \times 3)$
32372 := $((-2) \times F(F(7))) + (3 \times F(F((2^3))))$
32448 := $((8 \times F((F(4) + (4))))^2) \times 3$
32463 := $(3 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((F(4) + 2)^3))$
32496 := $F(6) \times (-F(9) + 4^{2 \times 3})$
32526 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (2 \times 52)) \times 3)$
32538 := $((F(F(8)) - ((F(3) \times 5)^2)) \times 3)$
32539 := $((F(9)^3) - F(((5 \times 2) \times F(3))))$
32568 := $((F(F(8)) - (F((6 + 5)) + F(2))) \times 3)$
32582 := $(-(2^8) + (F(F(F((5 + F(2)))))) \times 3))$
32583 := $(3 \times (-85) + F(F((2^3))))$
32586 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (85 - F(2))) \times 3)$
32587 := $(-((F(F(7)) - ((F(F(8)) - (5 + F(2))) \times 3)))$
32646 := $((-64) + F(F((6 + 2))) \times 3)$
32652 := $((F(F(F((F(2) + (5)))))) - 62) \times 3$
32658 := $((F(F(8)) - ((5 \times 6) \times 2)) \times 3)$
32664 := $(((-4) - F(F(F(6)))) + 62) \times (-3)$
32667 := $((7 + F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(6)^2)) \times 3)$
32673 := $((F((3 + 7)) - F(F((6 + 2)))) \times (-3))$
32675 := $(-5) \times ((F(F(7)) - F((F(F(6)) - F(2)))) - 3)$
32676 := $(F(F(6)) \times (F(F(7)) - ((F(F(6))^2) \times (-3)))$
32677 := $-7 \times F(7) + F(6)^{2+3}$
32684 := $-4 \times F(8) + F(6)^{2+3}$
32688 := $((F(F(8)) - ((8 \times 6) + 2)) \times 3)$
32694 := $(-((F((F(4) + 9)) - (F(F((6 + 2))) \times 3)))$
32696 := $-F(6) \times 9 + F(6)^{2+3}$
32697 := $((-((F(7) + F(9))) + F(F((6 + 2)))) \times 3)$
32699 := $(-F(9) - (((-F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(2)) \times (-3))$
32726 := $((F(F(6)) - ((2^7)^2)) \times (-F(3)))$
32736 := $(-F(6) + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times (2 + F(3))$
32739 := $(-F(9) + F(3 \times 7) + F(2)) \times 3$
32744 := $(4 \times ((F(F(4))^{F(7)}) - (2 \times 3)))$
32746 := $F(6)^4 - 7 + F(23)$
32747 := $((F(F(7)) - (4)) \times (F((F(7) - F(2))) - F(F(3))))$

- 32748** := $(-8 + 4^7 - 2) \times F(3)$
32749 := $(-((9 - (4^7)) \times 2)) - F(F(3))$
32753 := $F(3)^{5+7} + F(23)$
32756 := $F(6)^5 - 7 - 2 - 3$
32758 := $8^5 + F(7) - 23$
32759 := $-9 + (-5 + F(7))^{2+3}$
32761 := $(1 + ((F(F(F(6)))) - (F(7) \times 2)) \times 3)$
32762 := $2^{F(6)+7} - 2 \times 3$
32763 := $-3 + F(6)^{7-2} - F(3)$
32764 := $((-4 + F(6))^7 - 2) \times F(3)$
32765 := $-5 + F(6)^{7-2} + F(3)$
32766 := $F(6)^{-6+F(7)-2} - F(3)$
32767 := $(((-F(7)) + F(F(6)))^{7-2}) - F(F(3))$
32769 := $((F((9 - 6))^{F(7)+2}) + F(F(3)))$
32772 := $(2^{7+7} + 2) \times F(3)$
32775 := $((F(F((-5) + F(7))) - (F((7 + F(2)))))) \times 3$
32776 := $(F(6) + (F((-7) + F(7)))^{2+3})$
32778 := $((F(F(8)) - (F(7) + (7))) \times (F(2) + F(3)))$
32783 := $((3 \times F(F(8))) - F(((7 - 2) \times F(3))))$
32784 := $(((-F(4)) + F(F(8))) - (F(7) + 2)) \times 3$
32786 := $(F(F(6)) + ((8^{7-2}) - 3))$
32788 := $((F(8) + (8^{7-2})) - F(F(3)))$
32789 := $(-F(9)) + ((F(F(8)) - (7 - 2)) \times 3)$
32793 := $((F(F(F(-((3 - 9)))))) - (F(7) + 2)) \times 3$
32796 := $((F(F(F(6))) - ((9 + 7) - 2)) \times 3)$
32797 := $(((-7) - F(9)) + (F(F((7 + F(2)))))) \times 3)$
32804 := $(-40) + ((F(F(8)) + 2) \times 3)$
32808 := $((F(F(8)) - (08 + 2)) \times 3)$
32811 := $(((-11) + F(F(8))) + 2) \times 3$
32813 := $(-31) + ((F(F(8)) + 2) \times 3)$
32814 := $(F(4) \times (F(F((1 \times 8)))) - (2^3))$
32815 := $((F((5 - 1)) \times F(F(8))) - 23)$
32816 := $(-(((F(F(6)) + 1) - (F(F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(3))))))$
32817 := $(((-7) + F(F((1 \times 8)))) \times (F(2) + F(3)))$
32818 := $(-((F(8) - 1)) + (F(F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(3))))$
32822 := $(-22) + ((F(F(8)) + 2) \times 3)$
32823 := $((-((3 + 2)) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(3)))$
32824 := $(-((4 \times 2)) + ((F(F(8)) - 2) \times 3))$
32825 := $(-F((5 + 2))) + (F(F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(3)))$
32826 := $((-((6 - 2)) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(3)))$
32827 := $(-((7 \times 2)) + ((F(F(8)) + F(2)) \times 3))$
32828 := $(-((8 \times 2)) + ((F(F(8)) + 2) \times 3))$
32829 := $((-9) + F((-2) + F(8))) + (F(23))$
32831 := $(1 + ((3 \times F(F(8))) - (2^3)))$
32832 := $((F(2) + F(3)) \times F(F(8))) - (2 \times 3)$
32833 := $((F((F(3) + F(3))) \times F(F(8))) - (2 + 3))$
32834 := $((F(F(4)) + F(F(3))) \times F(F(8))) - (F(2) + 3)$
32836 := $((6 - 3) \times F(F(8))) - (F(2) \times F(3))$
32837 := $((F((7 - 3)) \times F(F(8))) + ((2 - 3)))$
32838 := $F(8 + 3 + 8) + F(23)$
32839 := $F(9) + 3^8 \times (2 + 3)$
32841 := $((F((1 \times 4)) \times F(F(8))) + (F(2) + F(3)))$
32842 := $((F(2) \times F(4)) \times F(F(8))) + (F(2) + 3)$
32843 := $((F(F(3)) + F(F(4))) \times F(F(8))) + (2 + 3)$
32844 := $((4 - F(F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(3))$
32845 := $5 \times (F(4)^8 + 2^3)$
32846 := $((6 - F(4)) \times F(F(8))) + (2^3)$
32847 := $((7 - 4) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(3))$
32848 := $(F(F(8)) \times F(4)) + ((8 - F(2)) + 3)$
32856 := $(6 + F(5 + 8 \times 2)) \times 3$
32861 := $(-1) + ((-F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times (F(2) \times (-3))$
32862 := $((2 + 6) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(3))$
32863 := $F(F(3)) + (F(6) + F(F(8))) \times F(2) \times 3$
32864 := $F(F(4)) + (F(6) + F(F(8))) \times F(2) \times 3$
32865 := $((5 + 6) + F(F(8))) - 2 \times 3$
32868 := $(F(F(8)) + (6 + (8/2))) \times 3$
32869 := $(F(9) + (((6 \times F(F(8)))/2) - 3))$
32871 := $(((-1) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) - F(2) \times 3$
32872 := $F(2) + (F(7) + F(F(8)) - 2) \times 3$
32873 := $F(3) + (F(7) + F(F(8)) - 2) \times 3$
32874 := $F(4) + (F(7) + F(F(8)) - 2) \times 3$
32875 := $(-5) + (((F(7) + F(F(8))) + F(2)) \times 3)$
32876 := $(((-6) \times (-F(7) - F(F(8))))/2) - F(F(3))$
32877 := $((F(7) + F((F(7) + 8))) \times (F(2) + F(3)))$
32878 := $((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F((8/2))) + F(F(3))$
32879 := $((F(9) + (7)) + (F(F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(3))))$
32883 := $((3 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(8) \times 2) + 3))$
32884 := $((F(4) \times F(F(8))) + ((F(8) + 2) \times F(3)))$
32886 := $((F(6) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(3))$

- 32889** := $((9 + 8) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(3))$
32892 := $((2 \times 9) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(3))$
32893 := $(F((F(F(3)) + 9)) + (F(F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(3))))$
32896 := $((F(F(6)) + F(9)) + ((F(F(8)) + F(2)) \times 3))$
32898 := $(F(F(8)) + (((F(9) - (8 - 2))^3))$
32899 := $(F(9) + ((-9) - F(F(8))) \times (F(2) \times (-3)))$
32927 := $(F((F(7) - 2)) + (F(F((9 - F(2)))) \times 3))$
32928 := $((F(F(8)) + (29 + F(2))) \times 3)$
32934 := $(F(4) \times (-((F(3) - F(9))) + F(F((2^3))))$
32935 := $(-5) + (3 \times (F(9) + F(F((2^3))))$
32937 := $(F(7 \times 3) + F(9) - F(2)) \times 3$
32938 := $((F(F(8)) \times 3) + ((9 + F(2))^{F(3)}))$
32958 := $((F(F(8)) + ((5 + F(9)) + F(2))) \times 3)$
32963 := $((3 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(9))) + 23)$
32964 := $(F(4) \times ((F(6) + F(9)) + F(F((2^3))))$
32967 := $((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(9) + 2))) \times 3$
32969 := $(-F(9) + ((F(F(F(6))) + F((9 + F(2)))) \times 3))$
32976 := $((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(7) + F(9)) - F(2))) \times 3)$
32979 := $((F(9) + F(7)) + F(F((9 - F(2)))) \times 3)$
33268 := $((F(F(8)) + (F((6 \times 2)))) \times 3) - F(3)$
33276 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (F((F(7) - F(2))) + F(3))) \times 3)$
33282 := $(2^8 + 2)^{F(3)} / F(3)$
33286 := $(-F(6) + F(8 \times 2)) \times F(3 \times 3)$
33327 := $7 \times (23 \times 3)^{F(3)}$
33396 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (93 \times F(3))) \times 3)$
33446 := $F(6) \times F(4 \times 4 + 3) - F(3)$
33448 := $8 \times F(4 + 4 \times 3 + 3)$
33456 := $((F((F(F(6)) - (5))) - F(4)) \times F((3 \times 3)))$
33464 := $((F(F(4)) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))) \times F((3 + 3)))$
33466 := $((F(6) \times (F((F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))) + F(3))) + F(3))$
33474 := $((-F(4) + F((F(7) + (4)))) \times F(F((3 + 3)))$
33476 := $((F(F(6)) \times (F((F(7) + (4))) - 3)) + F(3))$
33486 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (8 \times (F(4)^3))) \times 3)$
33488 := $(8 \times (F((F(8) - F(F(4)))) + (F(3) + 3))$
33489 := $(9 \times F(8) - 4 - F(3))^{F(3)}$
33516 := $(F(F(6)) \times (-1) + F(((5 \times 3) + F(3))))$
33528 := $((F(F(8)) + F(F((2 + 5)))) - 3) \times 3$
33536 := $((F(F(6)) \times F((F(3) + (5 \times 3)))) - F(F(3)))$
33537 := $((7 \times 3) \times F(((5 \times 3) + F(3))))$
33538 := $((F(8) \times F((F(3) + (5 \times 3)))) + F(F(3)))$
33539 := $((F((F(9) / F(3))) \times F((5 + 3))) + F(3))$
33546 := $((F(F(F(6))) + F(4)) + F(F((5 + F(3)))) \times 3)$
33547 := $((F((F(7) - F(4))) \times F((5 \times 3))) - 3)$
33548 := $((F((8 + F(F(4)))) \times F((5 \times 3))) - F(3))$
33549 := $((F((9 + F(4))) \times F(F((5 + F(3)))) - 3)$
33551 := $((F(15) \times F((5 \times F(3)))) + F(F(3)))$
33552 := $F(2 \times 5) \times F(5 \times 3) + F(3)$
33553 := $((F((F(3) \times 5)) \times F((5 \times 3))) + 3)$
33558 := $(F((F(8) - (5))) \times F(((5 + F(3)) + F(3))))$
33559 := $((F(9) \times F((-5) + F((5 + 3)))) + F(F(3)))$
33566 := $(F(6) - (F((F(F(6)) - (5))) \times (-F((3 \times 3))))$
33567 := $((F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (5 \times F(3))) \times 3$
33572 := $(2 \times ((7^5) - F(F((3 + 3))))$
33576 := $((F(F(6)) + (-((7^5)) - F(3))) \times (-F(3)))$
33577 := $((F(7) \times (F((F(7) + (5))) - F(F(3)))) - F(3))$
33578 := $(-F(8) + 7^5 + 3) \times F(3)$
33589 := $((F(9) \times (F((F(8) - (5))) + F(F(3)))) - 3)$
33592 := $F(2 \times 9) \times (5 + F(3 + 3))$
33593 := $((F((F(3) \times 9)) \times F((5 + F(3)))) + F(F(3)))$
33594 := $((F((F(F(4)) \times 9)) \times F((5 + F(3)))) + F(3))$
33614 := $(F(F(4)) \times ((1 + 6)^{F(3)+3}))$
33617 := $7^{-1+6} \times F(3) + 3$
33618 := $F(8 - 1) \times (F(6 \times 3) + F(3))$
33626 := $(F((F(6) + F(2))) \times (F((F(6) \times F(3))) + F(3)))$
33629 := $((F(9) \times (2 + F((F(6) \times F(3)))) + 3)$
33631 := $13 \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3)$
33647 := $F(7) \times (4 + F(6 \times 3)) + 3$
33657 := $((7^5) + F(F(6))) \times F(3) + F(F(3))$
33659 := $((F(9) \times (F((-5) + F(F(6)))) + 3) - F(F(3)))$
33667 := $F(7) \times (6 + F(6 \times 3)) - 3$
33678 := $((F(F(8)) / F(7)) + ((F(F(F(6))) \times 3) - F(3)))$
33696 := $(-F(6) + F(9)) \times 6^{F(3) \times F(3)}$
33756 := $((F(6)^5) + F((F(7) + 3))) + F(F(3))$
33758 := $((8^5) + F((F(7) + 3))) + 3$
33767 := $(F(F(7)) + ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(7)) - F(F(3)))) \times 3))$
33785 := $5 \times (-8 + F(-7 + 3^3))$
33787 := $((F(F(7)) \times ((F(8) \times 7) - F(3))) + F(3))$
33815 := $(5 \times ((F((-1) + F(8))) - 3) + F(F(3)))$
33823 := $((3 + 2) \times F((F(8) - F(F(3)))) - F(3))$
33824 := $(F((4^2)) + ((F(F(8)) \times 3) - F(F(3))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33825 &:= (5 \times F((F(2) - ((8 - (3^3)))))) \\
 33826 &:= (F((F(6) \times 2) + ((F(F(8)) \times 3) + F(F(3)))) \\
 33827 &:= (((7 - 2) \times F((F(8) - F(F(3)))) + F(3)) \\
 33828 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(2))) \times (8 - 3)) + 3) \\
 33834 &:= (F((4^{F(3)})) + ((F(F(8)) + 3) \times 3)) \\
 33835 &:= (-5) \times (-F(3) - F((F(8) - (3/3)))) \\
 33838 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 3) + (((8 + F(3))^3)) \\
 33845 &:= (-5) \times (-4 - F((F(8) - (3/3)))) \\
 33846 &:= (F(F(6)) + (F(-((F(F(4))) - (F(8)))) \times (F(3) + 3))) \\
 33855 &:= (-5) \times ((-5) - F((F(8) - F(F(3)))) - F(F(3))) \\
 33856 &:= (F(6) \times (5 + F(8) - 3))^{F(3)} \\
 33859 &:= (F(9) + (5 \times F((F(8) - (3/3)))) \\
 33865 &:= (-5) \times (-F(6) - F((F(8) - (3/3)))) \\
 33867 &:= ((F(7) \times (F(F(6)) + F((F(8) - 3)))) + F(3)) \\
 33875 &:= (-5) \times ((-F(7) - F((F(8) - F(F(3)))) + 3)) \\
 33878 &:= (F(F(8)) + ((F(7) \times ((F(8) \times F(3))^{F(3)}))) \\
 33964 &:= ((F((F(F(4))) + (F(F(6)))) - ((9^3)) \times F(3)) \\
 33984 &:= (F((4 + 8)) \times (F(F((9 - F(3)))) + 3)) \\
 33995 &:= (-5) \times (-F(9) - F(((F(9)/F(3)) + 3))) \\
 34188 &:= F(8) \times 814 \times F(3) \\
 34269 &:= ((F(9) \times (F(F(6)) + (F((2^4)))) - 3) \\
 34285 &:= 5 \times ((F(8) - 2)^{F(4)} - F(3)) \\
 34295 &:= (5 \times (((F(9)/2) + F(F(4)))^3)) \\
 34368 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(6)^3) - F(F(4))) \times 3) \\
 34386 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((8^3) + 4)) \times 3) \\
 34445 &:= (5 \times ((F(F(4)) + ((F(4)^4))^{F(3)})) \\
 34475 &:= 5 \times 7 \times (F(4 \times 4) - F(3)) \\
 34476 &:= (-F(6) + (F(F(7)) \times (4 + F((4 \times 3)))) \\
 34477 &:= (-7) + (F(F(7)) \times (4 + F((4 \times 3)))) \\
 34484 &:= ((4 + F((8 + 4))) \times F(F((4 + 3)))) \\
 34487 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F((8 + 4) + (4))) + 3) \\
 34545 &:= 5 \times (F(4 \times 5) + F(4 \times 3)) \\
 34579 &:= (F(9) + ((7 \times 5) \times F((4^{F(3)}))) \\
 34596 &:= (6 + 9 \times 5 \times 4)^{F(3)} \\
 34666 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F((-6) + F(F(6)))) \times F(4) - F(3)) \\
 34667 &:= (((-F((7 + F(6)))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(4)) - F(F(3))) \\
 34668 &:= ((F(F(8)) + F(((6 + 6) + F(4)))) \times 3) \\
 34669 &:= (((F((9 + F(F(6))))/F(6)) + F(F(4)))/3) \\
 34674 &:= (((F((F(F(4)) + (F(7)))) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(4))) \times 3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34717 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (1 + (74 \times F(3)))) \\
 34736 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) - ((7^{F(4)})) \times F(3)) \\
 34742 &:= (2 \times ((4^7) + F((4^{F(3)}))) \\
 34776 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((7 \times (F(F(7)) + (4))) - 3)) \\
 34816 &:= (F((F(6) + 1)) \times ((8^{F(4)}) \times F(3))) \\
 34848 &:= 8 \times (F(4) \times F(8) + F(4))^{F(3)} \\
 34866 &:= (-6) \times (F(F(6)) - ((F(8) - F(4))^3)) \\
 34876 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times F(7)) - F((F(8) + F(F(F(4)))))) \times (-F(3))) \\
 34885 &:= (5 \times (F(F(8)) - ((F(8) \times F(4))^{F(3)})) \\
 34886 &:= (((6 \times F(F(8))) + (8^4))/F(3)) \\
 34946 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - ((F(4)^9)) \times (-4)) - F(3)) \\
 34948 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 4) - (94^{F(3)})) \\
 34968 &:= 8 \times (6 \times 9^{F(4)} - 3) \\
 34969 &:= (((9 \times F(F(6))) - F((9/F(4))))^{F(3)} \\
 34978 &:= -((F(F(8)) - (((7 \times 9^4) - 3))) \\
 34986 &:= (-6) \times ((-8) \times (9^{F(4)}) + F(F(3))) \\
 34992 &:= F(2) \times (9 + 9)^4/3 \\
 34994 &:= (F(F(4)) + (((9 + 9)^4)/3)) \\
 34996 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((9 - (9^4)))) \times F(3)) \\
 34998 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (-9) + (9^{F(4)})) \times 3) \\
 35152 &:= (2 \times ((5 + F(F((1 + 5))))^3)) \\
 35297 &:= ((F((F(7) + 9)) \times 2) - ((5^3))) \\
 35367 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F((3 \times 5)))) \times 3) \\
 35397 &:= ((F((F(7) + 9)) \times F(3)) - (5^{F(3)})) \\
 35412 &:= ((F((21 + F(F(F(4)))) - (5)) \times F(3)) \\
 35414 &:= ((4 - F((1 + F((F(4) + (5)))))) \times (-F(3))) \\
 35416 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + 1)) \times F(F(4))) - (5 + F(F(3)))) \\
 35418 &:= ((F((F(8) + 1)) - F(F(4))) \times (5 - 3)) \\
 35421 &:= -1 + F(2 + 4 \times 5) \times F(3) \\
 35422 &:= 2 \times F(24 - 5 + 3) \\
 35423 &:= F(F(3)) + F(2 + 4 \times 5) \times F(3) \\
 35424 &:= F(F(4)) + F(2 + 4 \times 5) \times F(3) \\
 35426 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + F(2))) \times F(F(4))) + (5 - F(F(3)))) \\
 35428 &:= ((F((F(8) + F(2))) + F(4)) \times (5 - 3)) \\
 35432 &:= ((F((F(2) + F((F(3))^{F(4)}))) + (5)) \times F(3)) \\
 35436 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) + (F(F(4)) + (5))) \times F(3)) \\
 35438 &:= ((-8) - F((F(3) + ((4 \times 5)))) \times (-F(3))) \\
 35448 &:= ((F((F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) + (F((F(F(4)) + (5)))))) \times F(3)) \\
 35462 &:= ((F((F(2) + F(F(6)))) + (4 \times 5)) \times F(3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 35464 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (F(F(6)) + F((4 \times 5) + F(3)))) \\
 35643 &:= (3 \times ((4 - (F(F(6)) \times (-5)))^{F(3)})) \\
 35649 &:= ((9 + F((4 + F(6)))) \times F(F((5 + F(3)))) \\
 35826 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (2 \times 853)) \\
 35882 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (85^{F(3)})) \\
 35916 &:= -((F(F(6)) - (((-1) + F(9))^{5-F(3)})) \\
 35934 &:= (-F(4) + (-((F(F(3)) - F(9)))^{5-F(3)})) \\
 35937 &:= ((F(7) - F(3)) \times F(9 - 5))^3 \\
 35939 &:= (((F(9) - F(F(3)))^{F(9-5)}) + F(3)) \\
 36173 &:= -3 + (F(7) + 1) \times F(6 \times 3) \\
 36174 &:= -((F(F(4)) - (((F(7) + 1) \times F((6 \times 3)))) \\
 36176 &:= (6 + 7 + 1) \times F(6 \times 3) \\
 36246 &:= -((F(F(6)) \times (F(F(4)) - ((2 \times 6)^3))) \\
 36284 &:= -4 + F(8) \times (2 \times 6)^3 \\
 36288 &:= F(8) \times (8 - 2 + 6)^3 \\
 36294 &:= (((-4) + (F(9)^2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3 \\
 36298 &:= (-8) + ((-((F(9)^2) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-3)) \\
 36366 &:= ((F(6) \times (F(F(6))^{F(3)})) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 3)) \\
 36385 &:= (-5) \times (-((8^3) - F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))))) \\
 36438 &:= (((F(8) + F(3))^{F(4)} - F(F(6))) \times 3) \\
 36446 &:= ((-((F(6)^{F(4)}) - F((F(F(4)) + (F(F(6)))))) \times (-F(3))) \\
 36449 &:= (((F(9) - F(F(F(4))))^{F(4)} + (F(6)^3)) \\
 36475 &:= (-5) \times ((7 + (-F(F(4))) \times F(F(F(6))))/3) \\
 36478 &:= (-F(F(8))) + (F(7) \times ((-F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))))/3) \\
 36481 &:= (-1 + 8 \times 4 \times 6)^{F(3)} \\
 36483 &:= ((F(3) + F(8))^{F(4)} - 6) \times 3 \\
 36485 &:= ((-5) + (F(F(8)) \times (4 + 6)))/3 \\
 36498 &:= (-F(8)) - (-((F(9) + F(4))) \times F((F(6) \times F(3)))) \\
 36519 &:= ((F(9) + F(-((1 - 5)))) \times F((F(6) \times F(3)))) \\
 36546 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (((4 \times 5) \times F(6))^{F(3)})) \\
 36576 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(7)) \times 5) \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) \\
 36579 &:= ((F(9) \times F(F(7))) + (F((5 + (6 \times 3)))) \\
 36593 &:= ((3 + F(9)) \times (F((-5) + F(F(6)))) + F(3)) \\
 36731 &:= (F(((1 + 3) + F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + F(3))) \\
 36749 &:= (((F(9)^{F(F(4))}) \times 7) + F((F(F(6)) + F(3)))) \\
 36786 &:= (((6 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(7))) - F((F(F(6)) + F(3)))) \\
 36824 &:= (-4) \times (F((2 + 8)) - (F(F(6))^3)) \\
 36875 &:= (-5) \times (-F((7 + 8))) - F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \\
 36879 &:= (((-9) + F(7))^8 - F((F(F(6)) + F(3))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36934 &:= ((4^{-3+9}) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 3)) \\
 36936 &:= ((F(F(6)) - F(3)) \times (9 \times (6^3))) \\
 36947 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (-4) \times (-F(9)) - (F(F(6))^3)) \\
 36958 &:= (((8^5) + 9) + F((F(F(6)) - F(3)))) \\
 36985 &:= (((5 \times F(F(8))) - F(9)) - F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) \\
 36992 &:= (-2 + F(9)) \times F(9) \times F(6 + 3) \\
 36994 &:= 4 \times F(9) \times F(9) \times F(6) + F(3) \\
 37044 &:= 4 \times (F(4) \times 07)^3 \\
 37047 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((40 + F(7)) \times 3)) \\
 37249 &:= ((-((F(9) + (4 + 2))) + F(F(7)))^{F(3)}) \\
 37279 &:= (((-9) + (F(7)^2)) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(3)) \\
 37288 &:= (8 \times ((F(8) - F(2)) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(3))) \\
 37295 &:= (-5) \times ((-((F(9) - 2)) \times F(F(7))) - 3) \\
 37349 &:= (9 + 4 \times F(3)) \times F(7)^3 \\
 37368 &:= -8 + F(6)^3 \times 73 \\
 37376 &:= F(6)^{F(7-3)} \times 73 \\
 37388 &:= -((F(F(8)) - ((F(8) + F(F(3))) \times (F(7)^3))) \\
 37394 &:= ((F(4)^9) + F((F(3) \times (F(7) - F(3)))) \\
 37396 &:= ((F((-6) + F(9)) - 3) - F(F(7)))/F(3) \\
 37488 &:= (-F(8)) + ((F((F(8) + (4))) - (7))/F(3)) \\
 37489 &:= (((-F(9)) + F((F(8) + (4)))) - (F(7)))/F(3) \\
 37498 &:= (-8) + ((F(9) + (4)) \times F((F(7) + 3))) \\
 37516 &:= (F((6 - 1) \times 5) + 7)/F(3) \\
 37545 &:= ((F(5^{F(4)})) - (-5) \times F(7))/F(3) \\
 37557 &:= (-F(7)) \times ((-((5^5)) + F(F(7))) + 3) \\
 37584 &:= (((F(F(4))^8) + (5)) \times F((F(7) - F(F(3)))) \\
 37619 &:= ((9 \times (-1) + F((6 + F(7)))) - F(F(3))) \\
 37623 &:= (3 \times (-2) + (F((6 + F(7))) \times 3)) \\
 37625 &:= (((F((5^2)) - F(6)) + F(F(7)))/F(3) \\
 37626 &:= (((F(6) + F(2)) \times F((6 + F(7)))) - 3) \\
 37627 &:= (((7 + 2) \times F((6 + F(7)))) - F(3) \\
 37628 &:= (((8 + F(2)) \times F((6 + F(7)))) - F(F(3))) \\
 37629 &:= 9 \times F((2^6 - 7)/3) \\
 37632 &:= ((-F(2)) - (3 \times F((6 + F(7)))) \times (-3)) \\
 37636 &:= (((-((6 \times 3)) - F(F(6))) + F(F(7)))^{F(3)}) \\
 37638 &:= ((8 + F(F(3))) \times (F((6 + F(7))) + F(F(3)))) \\
 37639 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(3)) + F((6 + F(7)))) + F(F(3))) \\
 37647 &:= ((F(7) - (4)) \times (F((6 + F(7))) + F(3))) \\
 37648 &:= (8 \times ((4^6) + F((F(7) + F(3))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 37649** := $((9 \times (F(F(4)) + F((6 + F(7)))))) + F(3)$
37658 := $((8^5) + ((F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))) - 3))$
37674 := $((F((F(4) + F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times (F(7) \times 3))$
37683 := $((F(-((F(3) - F(8)))) + 6) \times (7 + F(3)))$
37684 := $(F(F(4)) \times (F(F(8)) - (-F(6)) \times F((F(7) + 3))))$
37726 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times (-2)) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(7)))) \times (-F(3))$
37728 := $((F(F(8)) - F(2)) - (F(F(7)) \times (-7))) \times 3$
37736 := $((F(F(F(6))) + ((F((F(3) + (7))) \times F(F(7)))))) \times F(3)$
37743 := $((3^4) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(7)))) - 3$
37744 := $((F(4)^4) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(7)))) - F(3)$
37746 := $((6 \times F(4)) \times F(F(7))) \times (7 + F(3))$
37747 := $((F(7)^{F(F(4))}) - (7)) \times F(F(7)) + F(F(3))$
37749 := $((9^{F(F(4))}) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(7)))) + 3$
37835 := $5 \times (-F(3) + 87^{F(3)})$
37845 := $((5 \times F(F(F(4)))) \times (87^{F(3)}))$
37876 := $((-(6^7)) + F((F(8) + (7)))) + F(F(3))$
37884 := $((-4) + (8 \times F(8))) \times (F(F(7)) - F(3))$
37885 := $5 \times (8 + 87^{F(3)})$
37895 := $(-5) \times (((-9) \times F(F(8)))/F(7)) - F(F(3))$
37946 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (((-4) + F(9))^{F(7-3)}))$
37947 := $F(7) \times F(4) \times 973$
37968 := $((F(8) \times F(6)) \times ((-9) + F(F(7))) + F(3))$
37989 := $((9 \times F(8)) \times ((-F(9)) + F(F(7))) + F(3))$
38272 := $((2^{F(7)} - 2) + F(F(8))) \times F(3)$
38274 := $((F(F(4))^{F(7)} - F(2)) + F(F(8))) \times F(3)$
38276 := $((F(F(6)) - (-7) \times (2 + (F(F(8)))/(-F(3))))))$
38287 := $(((-7) \times F(F(8)))/(-2)) - (8 \times 3)$
38318 := $((8 - 1) \times ((-F(3)) - F(F(8)))/(-F(3)))$
38325 := $((5 + 2) \times (F(3) - (F(F(8)))/(-F(3))))$
38328 := $(F(((F(8) - 2) - F(3))) \times (8 \times 3))$
38329 := $((F((F(9)/2)) \times (3 \times 8)) + F(F(3)))$
38367 := $((F((7 + F(6))) - F(F(3))) \times (F(8) \times 3))$
38413 := $-3 + 14^{8/F(3)}$
38414 := $((F(F(4)) - (14^{8/F(3)}))$
38416 := $(6 + 1)^4 \times 8 \times F(3)$
38417 := $((F(7) + 1)^{-4+8}) + F(F(3))$
38437 := $((7 \times F(3))^4 + F(8)) \times F(F(3))$
38438 := $((F(8) \times F((F(3)^4))) + F((F(8) + F(F(3))))$
38445 := $((F((5 \times F(F(4)))) \times F(4)) \times F(F((F(8)/3)))$
38447 := $((F(F(7)) \times (F((F(4) \times 4)) + (F(8)))) + F(3))$
38448 := $F(8 + 4) \times F(4) \times F(8 + 3)$
38471 := $((1 + F(7))^4 + F((8 + F(3))))$
38478 := $((F(F(8)) - ((F(F(7)) + F(F(4))) \times (-8))) \times 3)$
38479 := $(F(9) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(4)) \times F((8 + F(3))))$
38493 := $39 \times F(48/3)$
38495 := $((5 + F(9)) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 8))) + F(3)$
38565 := $5 \times (6^5 - F(8) \times 3)$
38616 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (-F(16)) + F((F(8) + F(3))))$
38637 := $((F(F(7)) - 3) \times (F(6) \times F(8))) - 3$
38657 := $((7^5) - ((F(F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times F(3))$
38674 := $(-4) + (F(F(7)) \times ((F(6) \times F(8)) - F(3)))$
38745 := $((5 + F((F(F(4)) + (F(7)))))) \times (F(8) \times 3)$
38747 := $(-F(7)) + ((F(F(4)) + (F(7))) \times F((F(8) - 3)))$
38763 := $(F((3 \times 6)) \times (7 + 8)) + 3$
38777 := $((F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) + ((-7) \times F(F(8)))/(-F(3)))$
38784 := $(-4 + F(8 + 7)) \times 8^{F(3)}$
38792 := $-2^9 + (F(7) + F(8))^3$
38808 := $(80 + 8) \times F(8)^{F(3)}$
38809 := $(9 \times F(08) + 8)^{F(3)}$
38889 := $((-((F(9) \times F(8))) + F(F(8))) + F((F(8) + F(3))))$
38897 := $((F(7) \times F(9)) \times 88) + F(F(3))$
38927 := $(-F((7 \times 2))) + (F(9)^{F(8/F(3))})$
38967 := $((F(F(7)) - (6)) \times (-9)) - F(F(8)) \times (-3)$
39064 := $-4 \times 60 + F(9)^3$
39071 := $((-1) \times F(F(7))) + (F(09)^3)$
39072 := $F(2) - F(F(7)) + F(09)^3$
39073 := $F(3) - F(F(7)) + F(09)^3$
39074 := $F(4) - F(F(7)) + F(09)^3$
39139 := $F(9)^3 - F(1 + 9) \times 3$
39157 := $((-7) \times F(F((5 + 1)))) + (F(9)^3)$
39164 := $(4 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (-1) + (F(9)^{F(3)})))$
39168 := $((-8) \times F((F(6) + 1))) \times (-F((9 + 3)))$
39176 := $(F(6) \times ((F(F(7) - 1)) \times F(9)) + F(F(3)))$
39178 := $-F(8) \times (7 - 1) + F(9)^3$
39187 := $-F(7) \times (8 + 1) + F(9)^3$
39189 := $-F(9) - 81 + F(9)^3$
39194 := $((F(F(4)) \times (-F((9 + 1)))) + (F(9)^3)$
39223 := $-3^{2 \times 2} + F(9)^3$

$$\begin{aligned} 39236 &:= -F(6+3) \times 2 + F(9)^3 \\ 39238 &:= -8^{F(3)} - 2 + F(9)^3 \\ 39239 &:= (F(9)^{F(3)} - 2) \times F(9) + 3 \\ 39246 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(F(4))}) \times F((2+9))) - 3) \\ 39247 &:= -((F((F(7) - F(4))) + (2 - (F(9)^3))) \\ 39248 &:= (((F(8)^{F(F(4))}) \times F((2+9))) - F(F(3))) \\ 39249 &:= -F((9-4) \times 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39251 &:= -1 - 52 + F(9)^3 \\ 39252 &:= -F(2) \times 52 + F(9)^3 \\ 39253 &:= F(F(3)) - 52 + F(9)^3 \\ 39254 &:= F(F(4)) - 52 + F(9)^3 \\ 39256 &:= F(6) \times (-5 - F(2)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39258 &:= -F(8) - 5^2 + F(9)^3 \\ 39259 &:= -9 \times 5 + (F(2) \times F(9))^3 \\ 39261 &:= -(1) - ((F(F(6)) \times 2) - (F(9)^3)) \\ 39262 &:= -2 \times F(6+2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39263 &:= ((-F(3)) \times F(F(6))) + ((F(2) + (F(9)^3))) \\ 39264 &:= (F(4)^{F(6)} \times 2 - F(9)) \times 3 \\ 39265 &:= -5 \times F(6) + F(2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39266 &:= -6 \times 6 - 2 + F(9)^3 \\ 39268 &:= (((-F(8)) \times F((F(6)+2))) \times (-F(9))) - F(3) \\ 39269 &:= ((-F(9)) - F(F((6/2)))) + (F(9)^3) \\ 39281 &:= -1 - F(8) - F(2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39282 &:= -2 - F(8) + F(2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39283 &:= -F(3) \times F(8)/2 + F(9)^3 \\ 39284 &:= -4 - 8 \times 2 + F(9)^3 \\ 39286 &:= -6 \times F(8/2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39287 &:= -7 - 8 - 2 + F(9)^3 \\ 39288 &:= -8 - 8 + (F(2) \times F(9))^3 \\ 39289 &:= -9 - 8 + 2 + F(9)^3 \\ 39291 &:= -1 \times F(9-2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39292 &:= ((F(2) - F((9-2))) + (F(9)^3)) \\ 39293 &:= ((F(3) - F((9-2))) + (F(9)^3)) \\ 39294 &:= (((F(4)^9) - 2) - F(9)) \times F(3) \\ 39295 &:= -F(-5+9)^2 + F(9)^3 \\ 39296 &:= -6 + F(9)^2 \times F(9) - F(3) \\ 39297 &:= -7 + (F(9) \times F(2))^{9/3} \\ 39298 &:= -8 + F(9)^2 \times F(9) + F(3) \\ 39301 &:= 1 \times 0 - 3 + F(9)^3 \\ 39302 &:= -2 + F(0 \times 3 + 9)^3 \\ 39303 &:= -3/03 + F(9)^3 \\ 39305 &:= F(5 - 03) + F(9)^3 \\ 39306 &:= -60 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39307 &:= 7 \times 0 + 3 + F(9)^3 \\ 39308 &:= 8/F(03) + F(9)^3 \\ 39312 &:= (2 \times 1)^3 + F(9)^3 \\ 39313 &:= (3 \times 1) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\ 39314 &:= (4 + 1) \times F(3) + F(9)^3 \\ 39315 &:= -51 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39316 &:= 6 \times (-1 + 3) + F(9)^3 \\ 39317 &:= F(7) + F(1^3 \times 9)^3 \\ 39318 &:= (8 - 1) \times F(3) + F(9)^3 \\ 39322 &:= (-22 + 3^9) \times F(3) \\ 39323 &:= -F(3) + F(2^3) + F(9)^3 \\ 39324 &:= -42 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39325 &:= (5 + 2) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\ 39326 &:= (F(F(6)) - ((2 - 3) - (F(9)^3))) \\ 39327 &:= F(7) \times 2 - 3 + F(9)^3 \\ 39328 &:= F(8 - 2) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\ 39329 &:= -F(9) + 2 \times 3^9 - 3 \\ 39331 &:= 1 \times 3^3 + F(9)^3 \\ 39332 &:= F(2) + 3^3 + F(9)^3 \\ 39333 &:= -33 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39334 &:= -4 + F(3 \times 3) + F(9)^3 \\ 39336 &:= F(6 + 3)^3 + F(9) - F(3) \\ 39337 &:= (F(7) - F(3)) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\ 39338 &:= F(8 + 3/3) + F(9)^3 \\ 39339 &:= F(9)^3 - F(3) + F(9) + 3 \\ 39342 &:= -24 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39343 &:= 3 \times F(4 + 3) + F(9)^3 \\ 39344 &:= -F(4) + 43 + F(9)^3 \\ 39345 &:= -((F((5 + F(4))) - ((3^9) \times F(3)))) \\ 39346 &:= -6 - 4 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39347 &:= -F(7) + (-F(4) + 3^9) \times F(3) \\ 39348 &:= -F(8) + F(4) + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39349 &:= -9 + (-4 + 3^9) \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

- 39351** := $-15 + 3^9 \times F(3)$
39352 := $(-2 - 5 + 3^9) \times F(3)$
39353 := $F(3) \times (-5 + 3^9) - 3$
39354 := $-F(4) + 53 + F(9)^3$
39358 := $-8 + (5 - F(3))^9 \times F(3)$
39359 := $F(9) + F(5 + 3) + F(9)^3$
39372 := $2 \times (F(7 - 3)^9 + 3)$
39373 := $(F(F(3)) \times (7 + ((3^9) \times F(3))))$
39374 := $(4 + F(7 - 3)^9) \times F(3)$
39375 := $-5 + (7 + 3^9) \times F(3)$
39376 := $F(6) \times (7 + F(3)) + F(9)^3$
39377 := $F(7) \times F(7) \times F(39/3)$
39381 := $-1 + (8 + 3^9) \times F(3)$
39384 := $(F(4)^8 + 3) \times (9 - 3)$
39384 := $F(F(4)) + (8 + 3^9) \times F(3)$
39387 := $F(7) + 8 + 3^9 \times F(3)$
39388 := $(F(8) + F(8)) \times F(3) + F(9)^3$
39392 := $(F(-2 + 9) + 3^9) \times F(3)$
39393 := $3^9 \times F(3) + 9 \times 3$
39394 := $(-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3$
39395 := $-5 + F(9) + 3^9 \times F(3)$
39396 := $(6 + 9 + 3^9) \times F(3)$
39397 := $F(7) + (9 + 3^9) \times F(3)$
39398 := $-8 + F(9) \times 3 + F(9)^3$
39408 := $(F(8) + F(04)^9) \times F(3)$
39416 := $F(6) \times 14 + F(9)^3$
39432 := $2^{3+4} + F(9)^3$
39434 := $(F(4)^{3 \times F(4)} + F(9)) \times F(3)$
39439 := $-9 + F(3 \times 4) + F(9)^3$
39444 := $(F((F(4) \times 4)) + (-4) + (F(9)^3))$
39446 := $((F((F(6) + (4))) - F(F(4))) + (F(9)^3))$
39447 := $(F((F(7) - F(F(F(4)))) - ((F(F(F(4))) - (F(9)^3))))$
39448 := $(F((F((8 - 4) \times 4)) + (F(9)^3))$
39449 := $((F(9)^{F(4)} + F((F(4) + 9))) + F(F(3)))$
39467 := $((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) / F(F(4))) + (F(9)^{F(3)})$
39468 := $F(8) \times F(6) - 4 + F(9)^3$
39469 := $((F(9) + F(F(6))) \times F(4)) + (F(9)^3)$
39472 := $(-F(2)) + ((F(7)^{F(F(4))}) + (F(9)^3))$
39473 := $((F(F(3)) \times F(7))^{F(F(4))}) + (F(9)^3)$
39474 := $(-4 + F(7)^{F(4)}) \times 9 \times F(3)$
39475 := $57 \times F(4) + F(9)^3$
39476 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (((F(7)^4) - F(9)) + 3))$
39477 := $F(7) \times F(7) + 4 + F(9)^3$
39478 := $(8 \times 7 + F(4)^9) \times F(3)$
39482 := $((2 \times F((8 + F(4)))) + (F(9)^3))$
39488 := $((8 \times (F(8) + F(F(4)))) + (F(9)^3))$
39489 := $9 \times F(8) - 4 + F(9)^3$
39492 := $2 \times 94 + F(9)^3$
39496 := $((F(F(6)) \times 9) + (F(4) + (F(9)^3)))$
39504 := $40 \times 5 + F(9)^3$
39524 := $4 \times F(2 \times 5) + F(9)^3$
39527 := $(F(F(7)) - ((2 \times 5) - (F(9)^3)))$
39529 := $9 \times 25 + F(9)^3$
39534 := $((-F(4) + F(F((F(3) + (5)))))) + (F(9)^3)$
39537 := $((F(F(7)) \times F(-(3 - 5))) + (F(9)^3))$
39544 := $-F(4) + F(4)^5 + F(9)^3$
39547 := $(7 - 4)^5 + F(9)^3$
39564 := $4 \times 65 + F(9)^3$
39567 := $(F(F(7)) - (-((6 \times 5) - (F(9)^3)))$
39569 := $((-F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F((5 + (9 \times F(3))))))$
39573 := $(-F(F(3)) + F(F(7)) \times 5) \times F(9) - 3$
39574 := $((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(7)) \times 5)) \times (-F(9)) - F(3))$
39577 := $((F(7) \times F((F(7) - (5)))) + (F(9)^3))$
39579 := $(((-F(9)) \times F(F(7))) \times (-5)) - (F(9) - 3)$
39585 := $((5 \times F(8)) \times F((5 + 9))) \times F(F(3))$
39593 := $((F((-3) + F(9)) - (5)) / F(9) - 3)$
39594 := $((F(-(F(4) - F(9))) - (5)) / F(9) - F(3))$
39597 := $((F(F(7)) \times (F(9) \times 5)) - F((9 - F(3))))$
39598 := $F(8) \times (9 + 5) + F(9)^3$
39601 := $((F(F((1 + 06))) - F(9))^{F(3)})$
39603 := $(F((F(3) + F(F(06)))) + F(F(F((9 - 3))))$
39615 := $(-5) \times ((F(F((1 + 6))) \times (-F(9))) - F(F(3)))$
39625 := $(-5) \times ((F(F((F(2) + (6)))) \times (-F(9))) - 3)$
39636 := $((F(F(F(6))) + F((F(3) + F(F(6)))) + (F(9) - F(F(3))))$
39638 := $((F(F(8)) + F((F(3) + F(F(6)))) + (F(9) + F(F(3))))$
39647 := $7^{-F(4)+6} + F(9)^3$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39655 &:= 55 \times (-F(6) + 9^3) \\
 39658 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F((-5) + F(F(6)))) \times 9) \times F(3)) \\
 39663 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + (((-6) + F(9))^3)) \\
 39673 &:= (F((F(3) \times 7) - ((F(6) - (F(9)^3)))) \\
 39681 &:= F(1 \times 8 + 6) + F(9)^3 \\
 39682 &:= (F(2) + F((8 + 6))) + (F(9)^3) \\
 39683 &:= (F(3) + F((8 + 6))) + (F(9)^3) \\
 39684 &:= (F(4) + F((8 + 6))) + (F(9)^3) \\
 39687 &:= (F((-7) + F(8))) + (6 + (F(9)^3)) \\
 39688 &:= 8 \times 8 \times 6 + F(9)^3 \\
 39726 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) - 2) + F(F(7))) \times (9 \times F(F(3)))) \\
 39728 &:= (((F((F(8) - 2) + F(F(7))) \times 9) + F(3)) \\
 39733 &:= 33 \times F(7) + F(9)^3 \\
 39738 &:= F(8)^{F(3)} - 7 + F(9)^3 \\
 39746 &:= (F((6 + F(4)) \times (F(7) + (F(9)^{F(3)}))) \\
 39749 &:= F(9)^{F(4)} + F(7) \times F(9) + 3 \\
 39765 &:= ((-5) \times (F(6) + F(F(7)))) \times (-F(9) + F(F(3))) \\
 39766 &:= 66 \times 7 + F(9)^3 \\
 39795 &:= (-5) \times ((-F(9)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(9) + 3)) \\
 39836 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F((F(3) + F(8)))) + F(F(9 - F(3)))) \\
 39846 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - ((-4) - F(8)) \times (F(9)^{F(3)})) \\
 39914 &:= F(-4 + 19) + F(9)^3 \\
 39925 &:= ((5^2) \times F((9 + F(9 - 3)))) \\
 39927 &:= 7 \times F(2 + 9) + F(9)^3 \\
 39936 &:= F(6)^3 \times (9 \times 9 - 3) \\
 39984 &:= (((F(F(F(4))) - (F(8))) \times (-F(9))) + (F(9)^3)) \\
 39987 &:= -F(7) + (8 \times (F(9) - 9))^{F(3)} \\
 39997 &:= 7 \times 99 + F(9)^3 \\
 40465 &:= ((F((5 + F(F(6)))) + F(F(4)))/F(04)) \\
 40698 &:= F(8) \times F(9) \times (60 - F(4)) \\
 40775 &:= (((5 \times F(F(7))) \times 70)/F(F(4))) \\
 40938 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 3) + (90)^{F(F(4))}) \\
 41474 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times F(F(7))) \times F(-(F(4) - 14))) \\
 41603 &:= ((F(30)/F(F(6)) - 1) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 41616 &:= ((6 \times F((1 + F(6))))^{-1+F(4)}) \\
 41736 &:= (((-F(6)^3) + F(F((7 + 1)))) \times 4) \\
 41769 &:= (((F(9) \times F(F(6))) \times (F(F(7) + 1)))/4) \\
 42272 &:= -2^{F(7)}/2 + F(24)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 42276 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F((7 \times 2)))) \times (F(2) + F(4))) \\
 42336 &:= ((F(F(6))^{F(3)}) \times (32 \times F(4))) \\
 42436 &:= (((6 \times 34) + 2)^{F(F(4))}) \\
 42437 &:= (((F(F(7)) - (3^{F(4)}))^2) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 42441 &:= (-1 + 44) \times F(2^4) \\
 42488 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(8) - F(4))^2)) \times 4) \\
 42546 &:= (-F(F(6))) \times (-((45^2) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 42588 &:= F(8) \times (F(8) + 5)^2 \times F(4) \\
 42628 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 2) + ((6 \times 2)^4)) \\
 42632 &:= (((2 + F((F(3) \times 6)))^2) \times F(F(4))) \\
 42647 &:= (((F(7) \times (F(4)^{F(6)})) + F(2))/F(F(4))) \\
 42696 &:= (((-F(6) \times F(9)) + F(F((6 + 2)))) \times 4) \\
 42699 &:= (9 + F(9)) \times (6 + F(2^4)) \\
 42768 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) \times (F(2) + F(4))) \\
 42784 &:= ((4 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(7) + F(2^4)))) \\
 42797 &:= (-F((7 + 9)) + (F(F((7 + F(2)))) \times 4) \\
 42838 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 3) + (((8 + 2)^4)) \\
 42844 &:= ((F(F((F(4) + 4))) - ((F(F(8)) - 2))) \times (-4)) \\
 42845 &:= F(5 \times 4) \times (F(8) - 2)/F(4) \\
 42848 &:= ((F(F((F(8)/F(4))) - ((F(F(8)) - F(2)))) \times (-4)) \\
 42849 &:= ((9 \times ((F(4) \times 8) - F(2)))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 42852 &:= ((F(F((2 + 5))) - F(F(8))) \times (F(2) \times (-4))) \\
 42856 &:= (((F((F(6) + 5))) - F(F(8))) - F(2)) \times (-4) \\
 42864 &:= (((-F(4) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(F((8 - F(2)))) \times (-4) \\
 42872 &:= ((-2) \times F(F(7))) \times ((F(8) + 2) \times (-4)) \\
 42873 &:= -F(3) + (F(7) + F(8) + F(2))^{F(4)} \\
 42874 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (((F(7) + F(8)) + F(2))^{F(4)})) \\
 42875 &:= (5 \times 7)^{F(8 \times 2/4)} \\
 42876 &:= (((6 - F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(4))) \\
 42878 &:= (-F(F(8))) + ((F(F(7)) - F(F(F((8/2))))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 42896 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((F(9) + F(F(F((8/2))))^{F(4)})) \\
 42909 &:= F(9) + (F(09) + F(2))^{F(4)} \\
 42938 &:= F(8) \times 3 + (F(9) + F(2))^{F(4)} \\
 42964 &:= (F((F(4) + F(6))) + (((F(9) + F(2))^{F(4)})) \\
 42968 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (-6 \times F(9))) \times (F(2) + F(4))) \\
 43119 &:= (F((F(9)/(1 + 1))) \times (3^{F(4)})) \\
 43146 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) - 4)) + 1) \times (3^{F(4)})) \\
 43188 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (((F(8) + 1)^3)) \times F(F(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43216 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(12) - F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43264 &:= ((4 \times (F((F(6) + 2)) - 3))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 43267 &:= (F(7) \times F(6) \times 2)^{F(3)} + F(4) \\
 43272 &:= ((-(2^7)) + F(F((2^3)))) \times 4 \\
 43276 &:= ((F(6) \times F(7))^2 + 3) \times 4 \\
 43284 &:= (4 \times (F(F(8)) - ((2 + 3)^{F(4)}))) \\
 43343 &:= ((F(F((3 + 4)))^{F(3)} - F(F((F(3)^{F(4)})))) \\
 43346 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - (((F(F((4 + 3)))^{F(3)} + F(4)))))) \\
 43347 &:= (((F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(F((3 + 3)))) + 4) \\
 43376 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F((7 + F(3))) \times 3)) \times 4) \\
 43428 &:= (((F(8) + F(2)) \times F(F(4))) \times F((F(3)^4))) \\
 43448 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(4)^4) + 3)) \times 4) \\
 43464 &:= (4 \times ((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) - ((3^4))) \\
 43467 &:= (-F(F(7))) + ((F(F(F(6))) - F((4 \times F(3)))) \times 4) \\
 43476 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (74 + 3)) \times 4) \\
 43487 &:= -((F(F(7)) - ((F(F(8)) - ((4^{F(3)})) \times 4))) \\
 43496 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((9 \times 4) \times F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43528 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((2^5) \times F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43546 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 4) - (5 + F(F((3 + 4)))) \\
 43547 &:= -((F(F(7)) - ((4 \times F(F((5 + 3)))) - (4))) \\
 43548 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (4)) - F((5 \times F(3)))) \times 4) \\
 43556 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (55 + F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43562 &:= (-2) + ((F(F(F(6))) - F((5 \times F(3)))) \times 4) \\
 43563 &:= (-F(F(3))) + ((F(F(F(6))) - F((5 \times F(3)))) \times 4) \\
 43564 &:= ((-F((4 + 6))) + F(F((5 + 3))) \times 4) \\
 43566 &:= (-6) - ((F(F(F(6))) - 53) \times (-4)) \\
 43567 &:= (-F(F(7))) + ((F(F(F(6))) + (5 - F(F(3)))) \times 4) \\
 43572 &:= ((F(F((F(2) + 7)))) - 53) \times 4) \\
 43576 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (-F(7) \times (-5) + F(F(3)))) \times 4) \\
 43584 &:= (((-F(4)) - F(F(8))) + 53) \times (-4) \\
 43596 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((9 \times 5) + F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43616 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(F((1 \times 6))) \times F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43622 &:= (2 \times ((2 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((3^4))) \\
 43624 &:= (((-42) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(3)) \times 4) \\
 43627 &:= (-((F(7)^2)) + ((F(F(F(6))) + 3) \times 4) \\
 43628 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F((F(2) + 6))) \times 3)) \times 4) \\
 43636 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (3 + F((6 + 3)))) \times 4) \\
 43652 &:= (((-((2^5)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43656 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((5 \times 6) + F(3))) \times 4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43664 &:= (((4 + F(F(F(6)))) - F((6 + 3))) \times 4) \\
 43666 &:= ((-6) \times F(F(6))) + ((F(F(F(6))) + F(3)) \times 4) \\
 43667 &:= (((-F(F(7))) - ((F(F(F(6))) \times (-F(6))) + F(F(3)))) / F(F(4))) \\
 43668 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(F(6))) - (6 + F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43672 &:= (((-27) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43674 &:= (((-F((F(4) + 7)))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-F(3)))) \times F(F(4)) \\
 43676 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (-7) + F((6 + 3))) \times 4) \\
 43678 &:= ((8 \times (-F(7)) - (F(F(F(6))) / (-F(3)))) - F(F(4))) \\
 43679 &:= (((-9) \times F(7)) + ((F(F(F(6))) + 3) \times 4) \\
 43681 &:= (((1 - 8) + (6^3))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 43683 &:= (-F((3 + 8))) + ((F(F(F(6))) - 3) \times 4) \\
 43684 &:= (((-4) + F(F(8))) - F((6 + F(3)))) \times 4) \\
 43686 &:= (-6) + (((F(F(8)) - F(F(6))) - F(3)) \times 4) \\
 43687 &:= (-F(7)) + ((F(F(8)) - F((6 + F(3)))) \times 4) \\
 43688 &:= (-8 + 8^6 / F(3)) / F(4) \\
 43692 &:= (((F(-((F(2) - 9))) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(3)) \times (-4)) \\
 43694 &:= (-((F(4) \times F(9))) + ((F(F(F(6))) + 3) \times 4) \\
 43696 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(9) - (6 \times F(3)))) \times 4) \\
 43697 &:= (-79) + ((F(F(F(6))) - F(3)) \times 4) \\
 43699 &:= (((9 \times 9) - ((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3))) \times (-4))) \\
 43716 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - 17) \times (F(F(3)) + F(4))) \\
 43724 &:= ((F(F((4 \times 2))) - (F(7) + F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43726 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((2^{F(7)} + 3) \times 4) \\
 43728 &:= (((F(F(8)) / (-2)) + 7) \times (F(3) \times (-4))) \\
 43729 &:= -((F((9 + F(2))) + (F((7 \times 3)) \times (-4))) \\
 43732 &:= (((F(F((2^3))) - (F(7))) \times F(F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43736 &:= (-6 \times F(3) + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4) \\
 43744 &:= ((F(F((4 + 4))) - (7 + 3)) \times 4) \\
 43746 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 4) - (F((7 + F(3))) + (4))) \\
 43748 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 4) - ((7 + F(3)) \times 4) \\
 43749 &:= (((-F(9)) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F((7 \times 3)) \times 4) \\
 43752 &:= -2^5 + F(7 \times 3) \times 4) \\
 43756 &:= -F(6) + (-5 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4) \\
 43757 &:= -7 + (-5 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4) \\
 43758 &:= -F(8) - 5 + F(7 \times 3) \times 4) \\
 43771 &:= -1 \times F(7) + F(7 \times 3) \times 4) \\
 43772 &:= (F(2 \times 7 + 7) - 3) \times 4) \\
 43773 &:= ((F(3) - F(7)) - (F((7 \times 3)) \times (-4))) \\
 43774 &:= ((F(4) - F(7)) - (F((7 \times 3)) \times (-4))) \\
 43775 &:= (-5) + ((F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))) - F(F(3))) \times 4)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 43776** := ((F((F(6) + F(7))) - F(F((7 - 3)))) × 4)
43777 := (-7) + (F((7 × F((7 - 3)))) × 4)
43778 := (((-F(F(8))) - F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) + 3) × (-F(F(4)))
43779 := (-9) + ((F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + F(F(3))) × 4)
43784 := 4 × F((87 - 3)/4)
43786 := -6 + 8 + F(7 × 3) × 4
43788 := (8/8 + F(7 × 3)) × 4
43791 := (-1) + ((F((F(9) - F(7))) + F(3)) × 4)
43792 := (2 + F(9 × 7/3)) × 4
43793 := F(F(3)) + (F(F(9) - F(7)) + F(3)) × 4
43794 := F(F(4)) + (F(F(9) - F(7)) + F(3)) × 4
43796 := (-6 + 9 + F(7 × 3)) × 4
43797 := F(7) + F(9 × 7/3) × 4
43804 := (((F(F(4)) + F(F(08))) + 3) × 4)
43808 := ((F(F(8)) + (08 - F(3))) × 4)
43812 := (F(21) + F(8)/3) × 4
43814 := ((-4) × (1 - F(F(8)))) + 34
43816 := (F(6) + F(18 + 3)) × 4
43817 := (F((7 + 1)) + ((F(F(8)) + 3) × 4))
43818 := ((F(8) + 1) + ((F(F(8)) + 3) × 4))
43819 := ((F(9) + 1) + ((F(F(8)) × F(3)) × F(F(4))))
43824 := ((F(F((4 × 2))) + (8 + F(3))) × 4)
43826 := (F((F(6) + F(2))) + ((F(F(8)) + F(3)) × 4))
43828 := ((F(F(8)) + (F(2) × (8 + 3))) × 4)
43829 := ((F(9) - F(2)) + ((F(F(8)) + 3) × 4))
43832 := ((F(2) + 3) × (F(F(8)) + (3 × 4)))
43835 := (F((5 × F(3))) + ((F(F(8)) - F(F(3))) × 4))
43836 := (((F(6) + F(3)) + F(F(8))) + 3) × 4
43837 := ((7^{F(3)}) + ((F(F(8)) + F(F(3))) × 4))
43838 := ((F(8) × F(3)) + ((F(F(8)) + 3) × 4))
43839 := (F((9 + F(F(3)))) + ((F(F(8)) × F(3)) × F(F(4))))
43844 := (((F(4) × 4) + F(F(8))) + 3) × 4
43846 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 4) + ((8^{F(3)}) - F(F(4))))
43847 := (F((F(7) - F(4))) + ((F(F(8)) + F(3)) × 4))
43848 := ((F(F(8)) × 4) + ((8/F(3))^{F(4)}))
43849 := (((-F(9)) - (F(F(4)) × F(F(8)))) × (-F(3))) - F(4))
43856 := (((F(F(6)) - 5) + F(F(8))) + F(3)) × 4
43857 := ((F(7) × 5) + ((F(F(8)) + F(3)) × 4))
43858 := (((8⁵) + F(F(8))) + F((3 × 4)))
43872 := (((F((F(2) + 7))) + F(F(8))) + F(F(3))) × 4)
43873 := (F(-((F(3) - F(7)))) + ((F(F(8)) × F(3)) × F(F(4))))
43876 := ((F((F(6) + F(7))) + (F(8) + F(3))) × 4)
43877 := ((F(7) × ((7 + 8)³) + F(F(4)))
43878 := ((F(8) + ((-F(7) - F(F(8))) × (-F(3)))) × F(F(4)))
43892 := (((29 + F(F(8))) - F(3)) × 4)
43894 := ((F(4) × F(9)) + ((F(F(8)) + F(3)) × 4))
43896 := (((-((F(6) - F(9))) + F(F(8))) + F(3)) × 4)
43897 := ((F(7) × 9) + ((F(F(8)) - F(F(3))) × 4))
43899 := (-9) + (((F(9) + F(F(8))) - 3) × 4)
43908 := ((F(F(8)) + (F(09) - 3)) × 4)
43912 := (F(21) + F(9) - F(3)) × 4
43916 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (-1 + F(9))) × (F(F(3)) + F(4)))
43923 := 3 × (F(2) × 9 + F(3))⁴
43924 := (((F(F((4 × 2))) + F(9)) + F(F(3))) × 4)
43926 := -((F(F(F(6))) - (((F(2) + F(9)) + 3)^{F(4)})))
43928 := ((F(F(8)) + ((2 × 9) × F(3))) × 4)
43929 := (((F(9) × F((2 × 9))) + F(3))/F(F(4)))
43932 := ((F(F((2³))) + (F(9) + 3)) × 4)
43936 := ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(3) + F(9)) + F(3))) × 4)
43946 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 4) + ((9^{F(3)}) × F(F(4))))
43948 := ((F(F(8)) + ((4 + F(9)) + 3)) × 4)
43956 := ((F(F(F(6))) + ((5 × 9) - F(3))) × 4)
43962 := (((-2) × F(F(F(6)))) - F((9 + F(3)))) × (-F(F(4))))
43964 := (4 × (F(F(F(6))) + (9 × (F(3) + F(4))))
43974 := ((-F(4)) - (F(F(7)) × (-9))) × F((F(3))^{F(4)}))
43976 := ((F(F(6)) × ((F(F(7)) × 9) - 3)) + F(F(4)))
43978 := ((-F(8)) × ((F(F(7)) × (-9)) + 3)) + (4)
43984 := (4 × (F(F(8)) + (F(9) + (F(3))⁴)))
43988 := ((F(F(8)) + ((8 + 9) × 3)) × 4)
43996 := ((F(6) + 9) × (F((9 × F(3))) + (4)))
44016 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(10) + F(4))) × 4)
44017 := (F(F(7)) + (F(F(F((10 - 4)))) × 4))
44076 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (70 + F(4))) × 4)
44088 := ((F(F(8)) + ((80 - 4))) × 4)
44164 := ((4 × F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(14) + F(4))))
44176 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (7 × 14)) × 4)
44268 := ((F(8) × 62) × F((F(4) × F(4))))
44276 := -((F(F(F(6))) - (((F(F(7)) + 2)^{F(F(4))}) - F(4)))
44278 := (-((F(F(8)) - ((F(F(7)) + 2)^{F(F(4))}))) - F(F(F(4)))
44284 := (4 × (F(F(8)) + ((F(2) + 4))^{F(4)}))

$$\begin{aligned}
 44285 &:= (5 \times ((F(F(8) + F(2))) + F(4)) / F(F(4))) \\
 44288 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(8) \times (2 + 4))) \times 4) \\
 44296 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(9) - 2) \times 4)) \times 4) \\
 44297 &:= (F(F(7)) + (F(9) \times ((2 + 4)^4))) \\
 44348 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F((4 \times 3) - F(4))) \times 4) \\
 44376 &:= (6 \times ((F((F(7) - F(3))) - F(4))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 44395 &:= (-5) \times ((-9) \times F((F(3)^4)) + (4)) \\
 44396 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (9 + F((3 \times 4)))) \times 4) \\
 44436 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((F(3) + 44)^{F(F(4))})) \\
 44476 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(7)^{F(F(4))} + (4))) \times 4) \\
 44496 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(9) + F((F(4) \times 4)))) \times 4) \\
 44498 &:= (F(F(8)) + (F((9 + 4) \times F((F(4) \times 4)))) \\
 44517 &:= (-71) \times (-((5^4) - F(F(4)))) \\
 44538 &:= (F((8 \times 3) + (F((5 \times F(4)) \times (-F(4)))) \\
 44636 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (-3) + (6^{F(4)})) \times 4) \\
 44646 &:= (((-((6^{F(4)})) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-4) - F(F(4))) \\
 44648 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 4) + ((6^{F(4)} \times 4)) \\
 44664 &:= (((4 + F(F(F(6)))) + ((6^{F(4)})) \times 4) \\
 44666 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F(6))^{F(F(4))})) \times F(F(4))) \\
 44676 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (7 + (6^{F(4)}))) \times 4) \\
 44679 &:= (((-9) + F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 - F(F(F(4))) \\
 44684 &:= (4 \times ((F(F(8)) - F(6)) + F(F((F(4) + (4)))))) \\
 44687 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) - F(6)) \times 4) + F(4) \\
 44708 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(F(07))) - F(F(4))) \times 4) \\
 44712 &:= (((F(21) + F(F(7))) \times 4) - (4)) \\
 44715 &:= (((F(F(F(5 + 1)))) + F(F(7))) \times 4) - F(F(F(4))) \\
 44716 &:= (((6 + 1) \times F((F(7) + (4)))) \times 4) \\
 44717 &:= (((-7) \times F(17)) \times (-4) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 44718 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times (-1)) - F(F(7))) \times (-4) + F(F(4))) \\
 44719 &:= (((F(F((9 - 1))) + F(F(7))) \times 4) + F(4)) \\
 44724 &:= (((F(F((4 \times 2))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(4))) \times 4) \\
 44726 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (2 + F(F(7)))) \times 4) + F(F(4))) \\
 44728 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(2)) + F(F(7))) + (4)) \times 4) \\
 44732 &:= (((F(F((2^3))) + F(F(7))) + (4)) \times 4) \\
 44733 &:= (-3) + ((3 \times F(F(7))) \times (4^{F(4)})) \\
 44734 &:= (((4^3) \times F(F(7))) \times F(4) - F(F(4))) \\
 44736 &:= (((-((F(6) \times F(3))) \times F(F(7))) \times (-4) \times F(4))) \\
 44737 &:= (-7) \times (-3) - (F((F(7) + (4))) \times 4)) \\
 44738 &:= (((8^{F(3)}) \times F(F(7))) \times F(4) + F(F(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44746 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) + (4 - ((F(F(7)) + F(4))^{F(F(4))}))) \\
 44748 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (4)) + F(F(7))) + (4)) \times 4) \\
 44764 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (-7) + F((4 \times 4))) \\
 44767 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(7)) \times 4) - F(F(F(4))) \\
 44768 &:= (8 \times (((-6) \times F(F(7))) \times (-4) + (4))) \\
 44771 &:= -F(17) + F(7 \times 4 - 4) \\
 44776 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(7)) + (F(7))) + F(F(4)))) \times 4) \\
 44784 &:= ((4 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(7) + F((4 \times 4)))) \\
 44788 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(8))) + F(F(7))) - F(4)) \times 4) \\
 44789 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) + (4))) - (4)) \\
 44796 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times 9) \times (F(F(7)) + (4))) + F(4)) \\
 44869 &:= (((-((F(9) \times F(6))) - F(F(8))) \times (-4) - F(4)) \\
 44876 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4))) \times F(F(4))) \\
 44878 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7) \times F(8))) \times 4) + F(F(4))) \\
 44898 &:= F(8) \times (F(9) \times F(8) \times F(4) - 4) \\
 44924 &:= (F(4^2) + F(9)) \times 44 \\
 44936 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(3) \times F((9 + F(4)))) \times 4) \\
 44944 &:= (((4 + 49) \times 4)^{F(F(4))}) \\
 44946 &:= (((F(F(6)) - (F((4 + 9))))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(4))) \\
 44947 &:= (((F(F(7)) - F(F(-(F(4) - 9))))^{F(F(4))} + F(4)) \\
 44948 &:= (((F(8) - F((4 + 9))))^{F(F(4))} + (4)) \\
 44967 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times ((F(F(6)) \times 9) + (4))) - F(F(4))) \\
 44968 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(6) \times (F(9) + F(4)))) \times 4) \\
 44986 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times ((F(8) \times F(9)) \times F(4))) + (4)) \\
 44988 &:= (((F(8) \times F(8)) \times F(9)) + F(F(4))) \times F(4) \\
 44996 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((9 \times F(9)) - F(4))) \times 4) \\
 45148 &:= (F((8 \times F(4))) - (F(15) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 45177 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F(F(7)) - F(F((1 + 5))))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 45366 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F((F(F(6)) - F(3)))) - (5)) \times F(4)) \\
 45369 &:= (((-9) - F(F(6))) + ((3^5))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 45436 &:= (F((F(6) \times 3)) - (4 \times F(F((5 + F(F(4)))))) \\
 45468 &:= ((F(F(8)) / F((F(F(6)) / F(4)))) \times 54) \\
 45486 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (-F(8)) + (F(4)^{5 + F(F(4))})) \\
 45617 &:= (F((F(7) + 1)) \times ((6 + 5)^{F(F(4))})) \\
 45625 &:= ((52 + F(F(6))) \times (5^4)) \\
 45639 &:= (-((9^3)) + F(((F(F(6)) + (5)) - F(F(4)))) \\
 45648 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(4)) + (F(F(6)) \times F((5 \times F(4)))) \\
 45666 &:= (((6^6) - F((F(F(6)) - (5)))) - F(4)) \\
 45667 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-6)) \times F(F(6))) + F((5^{F(F(4))})))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 45696 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((F(9) \times F(6)) \times (5 + F(4)))) \\
 45698 &:= (-F(F(8))) + ((F((F(9) - F(F(6)))) + (5))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 45717 &:= (-7) \times ((1 + F(F(7))) - (F((5 \times 4)))) \\
 45736 &:= (F((F(6) \times 3)) - (7 + (5^4))) \\
 45738 &:= F(8) \times (3^7 - 5 - 4) \\
 45743 &:= (F((3 + (F(4) \times 7))) - ((5^4))) \\
 45747 &:= ((F((F(7) + F(F(4)))) \times 75) - F(4)) \\
 45751 &:= ((F(15) \times 75) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 45753 &:= F(3 \times 5) \times 75 + F(4) \\
 45754 &:= ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 75) + (4)) \\
 45796 &:= (((F(F(6)) + ((F(9) + F(7)) \times (-5)))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 45869 &:= ((9^6) - (F((F(8) + (5))) \times 4)) \\
 45873 &:= 3^7 \times F(8) - 54 \\
 45884 &:= (4 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(8) \times (5^{F(F(4))})))) \\
 45886 &:= (((F(F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(8)))/5) + F(F(F(4))) \\
 45888 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F(8))) \times F(8))/5) + F(4) \\
 45927 &:= (7 \times ((F(2) \times 9)^{5-F(F(F(4))})) \\
 45991 &:= F(19) \times (-9 + 5 \times 4) \\
 46048 &:= -8 \times 40 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46055 &:= (-5) \times (50 - (F(F(6))^{F(4)})) \\
 46096 &:= -F(6) \times F(9) + F(06 \times 4) \\
 46116 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (-1) + (F((1 + 6))^{F(4)})) \\
 46134 &:= -((F(F((4 + 3))) + (1 - F((6 \times 4)))) \\
 46135 &:= -((F(F(((5 + 3) - 1))) - (F((6 \times 4)))) \\
 46136 &:= ((F((F(6) \times 3)) - F(F((1 + 6)))) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 46137 &:= F(7)^3 \times (1 + 6) \times F(4) \\
 46138 &:= ((F((8 \times 3)) - F(F((1 + 6)))) + F(4)) \\
 46152 &:= F(25 - 1) - 6^{F(4)} \\
 46169 &:= ((F(9) - F(F((6 + 1)))) + (F((6 \times 4)))) \\
 46179 &:= -9 \times F(7 + 1) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46208 &:= -80 \times 2 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46216 &:= -F(6) - F(12) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46217 &:= -7 - F(12) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46224 &:= -F((4 + 2) \times 2) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46225 &:= ((-5) \times (-22 - F(F(6))))^{F(F(4))} \\
 46226 &:= -F(6 \times 2) + 2 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46242 &:= (F(24) - ((2 \times F(F(6))) \times F(4))) \\
 46245 &:= -5^{F(4)} + 2 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46247 &:= -(7 + 4)^2 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46255 &:= (-5) \times ((5 \times 2) - (F(F(6))^{F(4)})) \\
 46264 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 26 \times 4 \\
 46265 &:= 5 \times (-F(6) + F(2 + 6))^{F(4)} \\
 46274 &:= -47 \times 2 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46275 &:= (-5) \times ((7 - F(2)) - (F(F(6))^{F(4)})) \\
 46277 &:= -7 \times F(7) \times F(2) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46279 &:= (F(((9 + F(7)) + 2)) - F((F(6) + F(4)))) \\
 46283 &:= -3 - 82 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46284 &:= -4 \times F(8) \times F(2) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46285 &:= 5 \times (F(8))^{F(-2+6)} - 4 \\
 46288 &:= -8 \times (8 + 2) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46294 &:= -(F(4) + F(9)) \times 2 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46295 &:= -5 - F(9) \times 2 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46296 &:= -F(6) \times 9 \times F(2) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46298 &:= -8 \times 9 + 2 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46299 &:= -F(9) - F(9) - F(2) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46304 &:= -4^{03} + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46305 &:= (5 \times (F(F(((0 \times 3) + 6)))^{F(4)})) \\
 46306 &:= -60 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46313 &:= -F(-3 + 13) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46315 &:= -51 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46319 &:= 91 \times (-3 + F(6))^{F(4)} \\
 46322 &:= -2 \times 23 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46324 &:= -42 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46325 &:= (-5) \times ((-2) - F(3)) - (F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \\
 46326 &:= -F(6 + 2) \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46328 &:= -8 \times (2 + 3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46329 &:= -F(9 - 2) \times 3 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46332 &:= -2 - F(3 \times 3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46333 &:= -33 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46334 &:= -F(4 \times 3 - 3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46335 &:= (-5) \times (-((3 + 3)) - (F(F(6))^{F(4)})) \\
 46336 &:= -F(6) \times F(3) \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46337 &:= -((F((7 + F(3))) - (3 + F((6 \times 4)))) \\
 46338 &:= F(8 \times 3) - 3 \times (6 + 4) \\
 46339 &:= -9 \times 3 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46341 &:= -1 \times F(4)^3 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46342 &:= F(24) - F(3) - 6 \times 4 \\
 46343 &:= F(3) - F(4)^3 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46344 &:= F((4 + 4) \times 3) - 6 \times 4
 \end{aligned}$$

- 46345** := $-5 \times 4 - 3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46346 := $F(6 \times 4) - 3 \times 6 - 4$
46347 := $-F(7 + 4 - 3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46348 := $-8 - 4 \times 3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46349 := $-(F(9) + 4)/F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46351 := $-15 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46352 := $-2 \times (5 + 3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46353 := $(F(F(3)) \times -((5 \times 3) + F((6 \times 4))))$
46354 := $-4 - 5 \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46355 := $-5 - 5 - 3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46356 := $6 \times (-5 + 3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46357 := $-F(7) + 5 - 3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46358 := $-8 - 5 + 3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46359 := $-9 \times F(5 - 3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46361 := $-1 - F(6) + F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46362 := $2 \times (-6 + 3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46363 := $-3 - 6/3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46364 := $F(4 \times 6) - 3 + F(6 - 4)$
46365 := $(5 - 6) \times 3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46366 := $F(6 + 6 \times 3) - 6 + 4$
46367 := $-(7 - 6)^3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46368 := $F(8 \times 6/3 \times 6/4)$
46369 := $(9 - 6)/3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46371 := $1^7 \times 3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46372 := $F(2) + F(7 - 3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46373 := $F(3) + F(7 - 3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46374 := $F(4) + F(7 - 3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46376 := $-6 + 7 \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46377 := $F(7) - 7 + 3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46378 := $(-8 + F(7)) \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46379 := $(9 + F(7))/F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46391 := $F(-1 + 9) + F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46392 := $2 \times (9 + 3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46393 := $3 \times 9 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46394 := $(4 + 9) \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46395 := $-5 + F(9) - F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46396 := $-F(6) + F(9) + F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46397 := $-7 + F(9) + F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$
46398 := $((F(8) + 9) + F(((F(3) + (6)) \times F(4))))$
46399 := $F(9) - 9/3 + F(6 \times 4)$
46402 := $(F((20 + 4)) + F((6 + F(4))))$
46404 := $40 - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46407 := $F(7) \times F(04) + F(6 \times 4)$
46408 := $((80/F(F(4))) + (F((6 \times 4))))$
46415 := $51 - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46417 := $7^{-1+F(4)} + F(6 \times 4)$
46419 := $F(9 + 1) - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46422 := $-F(2) + F(24) + F(6 + 4)$
46423 := $F(3 \times 2 + 4) + F(6 \times 4)$
46424 := $(F(F(F(4))) + ((F(24) + F((6 + 4))))$
46425 := $((F((5 \times 2)) + F(F(4))) + (F((6 \times 4))))$
46426 := $62 - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46427 := $-((F(F(7)) - (((2 + 4)^6) + 4)))$
46428 := $8^2 - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46432 := $(F(2) + 3)^{F(4)} + F(6 \times 4)$
46434 := $((4^3) + F(F(4))) + (F((6 \times 4)))$
46436 := $F(6)^{F(3)} + 4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46437 := $73 - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46439 := $F(9) \times F(3) + F(4) + F(6 \times 4)$
46446 := $((6 \times F((F(4) + (4)))) + (F((6 \times 4))))$
46447 := $((F(F(7)) + (4))/F(4) + (F((6 \times 4))))$
46448 := $84 - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46449 := $(9/F(4))^4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46452 := $(F(((F(2) + (5)) \times 4)) - (F(F(6)) \times (-4)))$
46456 := $((F((6 + 5)) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F((6 \times 4))))$
46457 := $(F(((F(7) - (5)) + F(4))) + (F((6 \times 4))))$
46459 := $95 - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46464 := $F(4 \times 6) + 4 \times 6 \times 4$
46465 := $(5 \times ((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) + (F(6) \times 4)))$
46467 := $(-F(F(7))) + ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(4)^6))) \times 4)$
46472 := $2 \times F(7) \times 4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46475 := $((5 \times F(7))^{F(F(4))}) \times (F(6) + F(4))$
46476 := $F(6) \times F(7) + 4 + F(6 \times 4)$
46477 := $((F(7) - (F(7)^4)) + F((F(F(6)) + (4))))$
46478 := $F(8) + F(7 + 4) + F(6 \times 4)$
46485 := $(-5) \times (-((F(8)^{F(4)})) - (6^{F(F(4))}))$
46487 := $7 \times (F(8) - 4) + F(6 \times 4)$
46488 := $8 \times (-F(8) + (F(4) \times 6)^{F(4)})$
46494 := $((F((F(F(4)) \times 9)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times (6 \times F(4)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46495 &:= (-5) \times (-((F(9) + (4))) - (F(F(6))^{F(4)})) \\
 46496 &:= -F(6) + F(9) \times 4 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46497 &:= -7 + F(9) \times 4 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46512 &:= F(2 \times (1 + 5)) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46517 &:= (F((F(7) - 1)) - (-5) - F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46533 &:= 33 \times 5 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46536 &:= F(6) \times F(3 + 5) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46537 &:= F(7)^{-3+5} + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46538 &:= (F((8 \times 3)) + (5 \times F((6 + F(4)))) \\
 46546 &:= (F((6 \times 4)) + (F((5 + 6)) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 46548 &:= (F((8 \times F(4))) + (5 \times (6^{F(F(4))})) \\
 46563 &:= 3 \times 65 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46566 &:= 6^6 - 5 \times 6 \times F(4) \\
 46578 &:= ((F(8) \times F(7)) - (-5) \times (F(F(6))^{F(4)})) \\
 46584 &:= (F(-((F(F(4)) - (F(8) + (5)))) + (6^{F(4)})) \\
 46592 &:= ((2^9) \times (F((5 + 6)) + F(F(4)))) \\
 46596 &:= (F(-((F(F(6)) - F(9)))) - (5 - F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46597 &:= (F(F(7)) - ((9 - 5) - F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46601 &:= -F(10) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} \\
 46605 &:= (-((50 - (6^6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 46607 &:= (F(F(7)) - ((0 - 6) - F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46614 &:= 41 \times 6 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46617 &:= (F(F(7)) - (-16) - F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46618 &:= -F(8 + 1) + 6^6 - 4 \\
 46619 &:= -F(9) \times 1 + 6^6 - F(4) \\
 46622 &:= -2 + 2^{F(6)} + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46623 &:= -((F(F(3)) - (((2^{F(6)}) + F((6 \times 4)))) \\
 46624 &:= 4 \times 2^6 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46625 &:= (-5) \times (-((2^6)) - (F(F(6))^{F(4)})) \\
 46626 &:= -((F((F(6) + F(2))) - ((6^6) + 4)) \\
 46627 &:= -F(7) \times 2 + 6^6 - F(4) \\
 46634 &:= (((F(4) \times F(3))^6) - F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4))) \\
 46635 &:= -5^{F(3)} + 6^6 + 4 \\
 46636 &:= -F(6) \times 3 + 6^6 + 4 \\
 46637 &:= F(7) + F(3)^{F(6)} + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46638 &:= (8 - F(3))^6 - 6 \times F(4) \\
 46639 &:= -F(9)/F(3) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} \\
 46641 &:= (-((14 - (6^6))) - F(F(F(4))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46642 &:= (-((2^4) - (6^6))) + F(F(4)) \\
 46643 &:= -3 \times F(4) + 6^6 - 4 \\
 46645 &:= -5 \times F(4) + 6^6 + 4 \\
 46646 &:= -6 - 4 + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} \\
 46647 &:= -F(7) + 4 + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} \\
 46649 &:= -9/F(4) + 6^6 - 4 \\
 46652 &:= F(2)^5 \times (6^6 - 4) \\
 46653 &:= (3 - 5 + F(6))^6 - F(4) \\
 46654 &:= -4 + 5 + 6^6 - F(4) \\
 46655 &:= -5/5 + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} \\
 46657 &:= -7 + 5 + 6^6 + F(4) \\
 46658 &:= F(8 - 5) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} \\
 46659 &:= (9 + 5 - F(6))^6 + F(4) \\
 46662 &:= 2 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4 \\
 46664 &:= -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 4 \\
 46665 &:= 5 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4 \\
 46666 &:= F(6) + 6^6 + 6 - 4 \\
 46667 &:= F(7) + 6^6 - 6 + 4 \\
 46668 &:= 8 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4 \\
 46669 &:= 9 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4 \\
 46671 &:= -1 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(4) \\
 46672 &:= F(2) \times F(7) + 6^6 + F(4) \\
 46674 &:= F(4) \times 7 + 6^6 - F(4) \\
 46679 &:= F(9) - 7 + 6^6 - 4 \\
 46681 &:= F(1 \times 8) + 6^6 + 4 \\
 46682 &:= F(2) + F(8) + 6^6 + 4 \\
 46683 &:= F(3) + F(8) + 6^6 + 4 \\
 46685 &:= 5 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4) \\
 46686 &:= 6 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4) \\
 46687 &:= F(7) + F(8) + 6^6 - F(4) \\
 46688 &:= F(8) + 8 + 6^6 + F(4) \\
 46689 &:= 9 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4) \\
 46724 &:= ((4 \times F((-2) + F(7))) + (F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46742 &:= ((F(24) + F((-7) + F(F(6)))) - F(4) \\
 46743 &:= ((-F(3)) + F((F(F(4)) \times 7))) + (F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46744 &:= -(((F(F(F(4))) - F((F(F(4)) \times 7))) - (F((6 \times 4)))) \\
 46745 &:= (F(((5 - 4) + F(7))) + (F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46746 &:= ((F((6 \times F(4))) + (F(7))) \times (6 \times F(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46748 &:= ((F((8 \times F(4))) + F((-7) + F(F(6)))) + F(4)) \\
 46753 &:= ((F((F(3) \times 5)) \times 7) + (F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46764 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + (F(6)^{F(4)}))) \\
 46766 &:= ((F(F(6)) + F((F(F(6)) - (7)))) + (F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46768 &:= (8 \times (F(F(6)) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (4)))) \\
 46774 &:= (((F(4) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(7))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-4))) \\
 46779 &:= F(9) + F(7 + 7) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46784 &:= 4 \times 8 \times F(7) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46797 &:= F(7) \times F(9) - F(7) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46834 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times F(F(-(F(F(3)) - 8)))) + (F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46866 &:= 6^6 + F(8) \times (6 + 4) \\
 46872 &:= (-F(2) + (F(7) - 8)^6) \times F(4) \\
 46873 &:= -F(3) + (F(7) - 8)^6 \times F(4) \\
 46874 &:= ((F(4) \times ((F(7) - 8)^6)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 46875 &:= 5^{(-7+8) \times 6} \times F(4) \\
 46926 &:= 62 \times 9 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46944 &:= 4^{F(4)} \times 9 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46946 &:= (((F(F(6)) - (4)) \times F(9)) + (F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46965 &:= ((-((5^6) + 9)) - F(F(6))) \times (-F(4)) \\
 46969 &:= -9 + F(6 + 9) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46978 &:= F(8 + 7) + F(96/4) \\
 46987 &:= (F((7 + 8)) + 9) + F((6 \times 4)) \\
 47086 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - (80)) \times (-F(7)))/(-F(4))) \\
 47125 &:= ((5^{2+1}) \times F((7 \times F(F(4)))) \\
 47263 &:= (-((3^{F(6)})) + ((-F(2)) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 47266 &:= ((6^6) + F((-((2 - 7)) \times F(4))) \\
 47267 &:= (((F(7) - F((F(F(6)) - F(2)))) \times (-7)) + F(4)) \\
 47289 &:= (((-9) + F((F(8) - F(2)))) \times 7) - F(4) \\
 47296 &:= (((6 \times F(9)) - F(2)) \times F(F(7))) - F(4) \\
 47302 &:= ((203 \times F(F(7))) + F(4)) \\
 47327 &:= 7 \times (F(2 \times (3 + 7)) - 4) \\
 47336 &:= (((F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) - 3) \times 7) + F(F(4))) \\
 47338 &:= (((F((F(8) - F(F(3)))) - 3) \times 7) + 4) \\
 47345 &:= (F(5 \times 4) - F(3)) \times 7 + 4 \\
 47346 &:= (((F((F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(3))) \times 7) - F(F(4))) \\
 47348 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(3))) \times (7 \times F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47351 &:= ((F((-1) + F((5 + 3))) \times 7) - (4)) \\
 47352 &:= ((F(((2 \times 5) \times F(3))) \times 7) - F(4)) \\
 47353 &:= ((F(((F(3) \times 5) \times F(3))) \times 7) - F(F(4))) \\
 47354 &:= (((-F((4 \times 5))) \times F(F(3))) \times (-7)) - F(F(F(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47355 &:= (F(((5 \times 5) - F(F(3)))) + (F((F(7) + F(4)))) \\
 47356 &:= ((F(((F(6) \times 5)/F(3))) \times 7) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47357 &:= ((7 \times F(-(5 \times (3 - 7)))) + F(F(4))) \\
 47358 &:= ((F((F(8) - F((5 - 3)))) \times 7) + F(4)) \\
 47361 &:= (((1 + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \times 7) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47362 &:= (((F(2) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \times 7) \times F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47363 &:= (((F(F(3)) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \times 7) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47364 &:= (((F(F(F(4))) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \times 7) + F(F(4))) \\
 47366 &:= (F(6) + ((F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \times 7) + F(4)) \\
 47367 &:= (((7 \times F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) + F(7)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47368 &:= (8 \times ((6 \times F((3 + F(7)))) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47372 &:= (F(2 \times 7)^{F(3)} - F(7))/F(4) \\
 47374 &:= (((F((F(F(4)) \times 7))^{F(3)} - 7)/F(4)) \\
 47375 &:= ((-5) + (F(F(7)) \times F((F(3) + F(7)))))/F(4) \\
 47376 &:= (F(6) \times ((7 - F(F(3))) \times F((F(7) + F(4)))) \\
 47377 &:= (((F((F(7) + (7))) + 3) \times 7) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47384 &:= (((-4) - F((F(8) - F(F(3)))) \times (-7)) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47389 &:= ((F(9) + F((8 \times 3))) + F((F(7) + F(4)))) \\
 47395 &:= (-5) \times ((-9^3) \times F(7)) - F(F(4)) \\
 47398 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F((9 - 3))) \times F(7))/F(4)) \\
 47424 &:= (((F(F(4)) - F(F((2 \times 4))) \times (-F(7)))/F(4)) \\
 47426 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - 2)/F(4)) \times F(7)) + F(F(4)) \\
 47428 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 2)/(-F(4))) \times (-F(7)) + (4)) \\
 47432 &:= ((-2) + (F(F((F(3)^{F(4)}))) \times F(7))/F(4)) \\
 47433 &:= ((F(F(3)) + (F(F((F(3)^{F(4)}))) \times F(7))/F(4)) \\
 47434 &:= ((4 + (F(F((F(3)^{F(4)}))) \times F(7))/F(4)) \\
 47436 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3)))/(-F(4))) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47437 &:= (-F(7)) \times ((F(F(3)) + F((F(4) \times 7)))/(-F(4))) \\
 47438 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(F(3)))/(-F(4))) \times (-F(7)) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47446 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + 4)/(-F(4))) \times (-F(7)) - 4) \\
 47448 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (4))/(-F(4))) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(4))) \\
 47463 &:= (((3 + F(F(F(6)))) + 4) \times F(7))/F(4) \\
 47464 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(4) - F(F(7))) \times (-4))) \\
 47465 &:= (-5) \times (-((F(F(6))^{F(4)} + F(F(7)))) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 47467 &:= ((((-7) - F(F(F(6))))/F(4)) \times (-F(7)) + 4) \\
 47476 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - F(4))) \times F(7))/F(4)) \\
 47485 &:= (-5) \times ((-((F(8)^{F(4)})) - F(F(7))) - F(4)) \\
 47487 &:= ((((-F(7)) - F(F(8)))/F(4)) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(4))) \\
 47489 &:= (((9 + F(F(8))) + (4)) \times F(7))/F(4) \\
 47516 &:= (-F(6) + ((-15) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))})
 \end{aligned}$$

- 47517 := $(-7) + ((-15) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))}$
 47524 := $((((F(4) \times F(2)) \times (-5)) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))})$
 47526 := $(6 \times (F(-(F(2) - (5 + 7))))^{F(F(4))})$
 47529 := $((F(9) \times (F(2) + (5))) \times F(F(7))) - F(4)$
 47532 := $((2 + F((3 \times 5))) \times F(F(7))) / F(4)$
 47536 := $(F((F(6) \times 3)) - ((-5) \times F(F(7))) - F(4))$
 47537 := $(F(7) + ((-(3 \times 5)) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))})$
 47538 := $(F((8 \times 3)) - (-5) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(4))))$
 47548 := $(F((8 \times F(4))) - (-5) \times (F(F(7)) + F(4)))$
 47574 := $(F(4) \times (F(F(7)) + (5^{7-F(F(4))})))$
 47618 := $-((F(F(8)) - ((1 + F(6)) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))}))$
 47628 := $F(8)^2 \times (F(6) \times F(7) + 4)$
 47634 := $(F((F(4))^{F(3)}) \times ((6 \times F(F(7))) + F(4)))$
 47643 := $((F(3) + (4))^6 + F((F(7) + F(4))))$
 47664 := $F(4 \times 6) + 6^{7-F(4)}$
 47697 := $(F(F(7)) + (F(9) \times ((6 \times F(F(7))) - F(F(4))))$
 47726 := $((F((F(6) \times 2)) - (F(7))) \times (7^{F(F(4))}))$
 47736 := $6^3 \times F(7) \times (F(7) + 4)$
 47765 := $((5 + F((F(6) + (7)))) \times F(F(7))) / F(4)$
 47767 := $((((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) - (7)) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(4)))$
 47769 := $((-(F(9) - (6))) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(7)) + (4)$
 47784 := $(4 \times ((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) + F((F(7) + F(4))))$
 47796 := $6 \times (-F(9) + (F(7) + 7)^{F(4)})$
 47848 := $((F(F(8)) + (-4) \times (-F(8)) - F(F(7)))) \times 4$
 47849 := $((F(9)^{F(4)} + F(F(8))) - (7^4))$
 47872 := $((2^7) \times (F((F(8) - (7))) - F(4)))$
 47889 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((8 + 7)^4))$
 47897 := $(-F(7) + ((9 + F(8)) \times F((F(7) + (4))))$
 47946 := $(6 \times (F(F(F(4))) + (F(9) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(4))))$
 47961 := $((((1 - 6) - 9) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))})$
 47965 := $((5 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((9 + 7) + 4))$
 47966 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) - F((9 + F(7)))) + F(F(F(4)))$
 47968 := $((F(F(8)) \times 6) - F((9 + F(7)))) + F(4)$
 47976 := $(-6) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(9))) - (74))$
 47985 := $((-5) \times F(8)) \times (9 - (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))))$
 47996 := $((F(F(F(6))) - ((9 \times 9) \times F(7))) \times 4)$
 48334 := $((F((4 + 3))^3) \times (F(8) + F(F(F(4))))$
 48337 := $((F(7)^3) \times (F(F(3)) + (F(8)))) + F(4)$
 48342 := $((F((2^4)) \times F(3)) + F((8 \times F(4))))$
 48363 := $((F(F(3)) + (6))^{F(3)}) \times F((8 \times F(F(4))))$
 48373 := $((((3 \times F(7))^3) - F(F(8))) \times F(F(F(4))))$
 48374 := $((((F(4) \times F(7))^3) - F(F(8))) + F(F(F(4))))$
 48377 := $((((F(F(7)) - (F(7)))^{F(3)}) - (F(8))) - F(F(4)))$
 48384 := $(F(4) \times 8)^{F(3)} \times 84$
 48386 := $((((6 \times 8))^{F(3)}) \times F(8)) + F(F(4))$
 48399 := $(-9) + ((-(F(9)^{F(3)})) - F(F(8))) \times (-4))$
 48426 := $(F(F(6)) \times (2 + (48^{F(F(4))})))$
 48456 := $(F(F(F(6))) - ((5 - F((4 + F(8)))) / F(F(4))))$
 48463 := $((3 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((4 + F(8))^{F(4)}))$
 48465 := $((5^6) + ((F(4) \times F(F(8))) + F(F(4))))$
 48467 := $((F(F(7)) \times ((6^{F(4)} - 8)) + F(4))$
 48477 := $(F(7) \times (((F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times 8) + F(F(F(4))))$
 48486 := $-((F(F(F(6))) + ((-F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times F((F(8) - F(4))))$
 48576 := $(-6) \times ((F(F(7)) \times 5) - (F(8)^{F(4)}))$
 48664 := $((F(F(4)) \times F((-6) + F(F(6)))) + F(F(8))) \times 4$
 48674 := $((-F(4)) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)))) + (F(F(8)) \times 4)$
 48677 := $((F(F(7)) \times (F(7) + F(6))) + (F(F(8)) \times 4))$
 48697 := $(F(F(7)) \times ((F(9) \times 6) + 8) - F(4))$
 48768 := $(8 \times ((F(F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times (8 \times F(4))))$
 48776 := $(F(6) \times (F(7) + (78^{F(F(4))})))$
 48789 := $(9 \times ((F(F(8)) + (F(7) \times (-8))) / F(F(4))))$
 48837 := $((F(F(7))^{F(3)} + (F(8))) - (F(F(8)) / F(F(4))))$
 48864 := $(F((F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(8)^{F(4)})))$
 48927 := $((F(F(7)) \times ((F(2) + 9) \times F(8))) - F(4)$
 48936 := $((F((F(6) \times 3)) / 9) + (F(F(8)) \times 4))$
 48946 := $((-6) + F((F(F(4)) \times 9))) + (F((8 \times F(4))))$
 48952 := $(F((-((2 \times 5)) + F(9))) + F((F(8) - F(4))))$
 49152 := $2^{5 \times 1 + 9} \times F(4)$
 49164 := $(4^6 + 1) \times (9 + F(4))$
 49236 := $((F(F(F(6))) / (-F(3))) + 2) \times (-9) - F(4)$
 49238 := $((F(F(8)) / (-F(3))) + 2) \times (-9) - F(F(F(4)))$
 49239 := $(9 \times (-F(3)) - (F(F(-(F(2) - 9)))) / (-F(F(4))))$
 49246 := $((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4))) / 2) \times 9 - F(F(4))$
 49248 := $((F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times (F(2) \times 9)) / F(F(4))$
 49253 := $((F(F((3 + 5))) / (-2)) \times (-9) - (4))$
 49254 := $(4^{5+2} + F(9)) \times F(4)$
 49256 := $((F(F(F(6))) / (-F((5 - 2)))) \times (-9) - F(F(F(4))))$
 49257 := $((F((7 \times (5 - 2))) \times 9) / F(F(4)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49258 &:= (((F(F(8)))/(-F((5-2)))) \times (-9)) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 49261 &:= ((((-1) \times F(F(F(6))))/2) \times (-9)) + 4) \\
 49262 &:= ((((-2) - F(F(F(6))))/(-2)) \times 9) - 4) \\
 49263 &:= (((F(3) + F(F(F(6))))/(-2)) \times (-9)) - F(4)) \\
 49264 &:= (((F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6))))/(-2)) \times (-9)) - F(F(4)) \\
 49265 &:= (5 - (((F(F(F(6))))/(-2)) \times 9) - F(4)) \\
 49266 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((F(F(6)) + 2) \times (F(9) \times F(4)))) \\
 49267 &:= (7 - (((F(F(F(6))))/(-2)) \times 9) - F(4)) \\
 49268 &:= (8 - (((F(F(F(6))))/(-2)) \times 9) - F(4)) \\
 49269 &:= (((-9) \times F(F(F(6))))/(-2)) + (9 + F(4)) \\
 49276 &:= (-F(6)) + ((F(F(7)) - (2 + 9))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 49277 &:= (-7) + ((F(F(7)) - (2 + 9))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 49278 &:= (F(8) - ((F(F((7 + F(2)))) \times 9)/(-F(F(4)))) \\
 49283 &:= (((-3) + (F(F(8)))/(-2)) \times (-9)) - F(F(F(4))) \\
 49284 &:= (((4 \times (8^2)) - F(9))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 49285 &:= (5 \times (F(F(8)) - ((F(2) - F(9))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 49286 &:= ((((-6) - F(F(8)))/2) \times (-9)) + F(F(4)) \\
 49289 &:= ((((-9) \times F(F(8)))/(-2)) + F(9)) - F(F(4)) \\
 49337 &:= (F(F(7)) - ((F(3) - F((3 \times 9)))/4)) \\
 49376 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(7)) \times (3 - 9))) \times 4) \\
 49387 &:= ((F(F(7)) + ((F(F(8)) + 3) \times 9))/F(F(4)) \\
 49392 &:= ((-((2 - 9)^3) \times F((9 + F(4)))) \\
 49396 &:= ((-F(F(6)) + F(F((9 - F(3)))) \times F((9 + 4))) \\
 49469 &:= (((9 + 6)^4) - (F(9))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 49486 &:= -(F(F(6)) + (F((F(8) - 4)) \times (-F(9) - F(4)))) \\
 49487 &:= (F(F(7)) - (((F(F(8)))/F(F(4))) \times (-9)) + F(4)) \\
 49564 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (5 \times (F(9))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 49638 &:= -(F((8 \times F(3)) - ((6 + 9)^4))) \\
 49674 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(6))) \times (F(9) \times F(4)) \\
 49678 &:= ((F(F(8))/F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + (F(9) + 4))) \\
 49693 &:= ((-3) + F(9)) \times (6 + F((F(9)/F(F(4)))) \\
 49729 &:= (((-9) - F(2)) + F(F(7)))^{F(9/F(4))} \\
 49734 &:= ((4 + F((F(3) + F(7)))) \times (9^{F(F(4))})) \\
 49746 &:= -(F(F(F(6))) + ((F((F(F(4)) \times F(7)) - 9)/(-F(F(4)))) \\
 49764 &:= (-4) \times ((F((6 + F(7))) - F(9)) \times (-F(4))) \\
 49785 &:= (5 \times ((F(F(8)) - (F((7 + 9))) - F(F(4)))) \\
 49795 &:= (-5) \times (F((9 + 7)) - F(F(F(9 - F(4)))) \\
 49867 &:= (F((7 + F(6))) + ((F(F(8)) \times 9)/F(F(4)))) \\
 49873 &:= -(((F((F(3) \times 7)) - F(F(8))) - (F(9))^{F(F(4))})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49896 &:= (((F(6) \times (-9)) \times F(8)) \times (-F(9) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 49928 &:= (8 \times (((2 - 9 \times 9))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 49994 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((-F(9) + F((F(9) - 9)))/F(4)) \\
 51655 &:= (-5) \times ((5 - F(F(F(6)))) + F(15)) \\
 51675 &:= ((F((5 + F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 1)) - 5) \\
 51764 &:= F(4)^6 \times 71 + 5 \\
 52436 &:= (((F(F((F(6) - F(F(3)))) - 4)^2) - 5) \\
 52446 &:= (((F(F((F(F(6))/F(4))) - 4)^2) + 5) \\
 52447 &:= (((F(F(7)) - 4))^{F(F(4))} + (F(2) + 5)) \\
 52448 &:= 8 \times (F(4))^{4 \times 2} - 5) \\
 52464 &:= (((F(4)^{F(6)} - F(4)) \times F((F(2) + 5))) \\
 52484 &:= (-4) + (8 \times (F(4))^{F(F(2)+5)}) \\
 52488 &:= (8 \times (F((8 - 4))^{F(F(2)+5)}) \\
 52493 &:= (F(3) \times 9)^4 / 2 + 5 \\
 52496 &:= F(6) \times (9^4 + F(2)^5) \\
 52876 &:= ((-F(6)) \times F(F(7))) - ((F(F(8)) + 2) \times (-5)) \\
 52967 &:= ((F((7 + F(F(6)))) - 9)/F(2) + 5) \\
 53128 &:= ((F((F(8) + F(2))) \times (1 \times 3)) - 5) \\
 53132 &:= (-F(2)) - (-3) \times F((1 + F((3 + 5)))) \\
 53133 &:= 3 \times F((3 \times 1)^3 - 5) \\
 53134 &:= (F(F(F(4))) - (-3) \times F((1 + F((3 + 5)))) \\
 53136 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) + 1) \times (-F(3) - 5)) \\
 53138 &:= ((F((F(8) + F(3 - 1))) \times 3) + 5) \\
 53163 &:= (3 \times (F((F(F(6)) + 1)) + (F(3) \times 5)) \\
 53167 &:= (((-F(7)) - F((F(F(6)) + 1))) \times (-3)) - 5) \\
 53227 &:= -F(7) + 22^3 \times 5 \\
 53265 &:= (5 \times (((F(F(6)) + F(2))^3) + 5)) \\
 53356 &:= (((F((F(6) + 5))) - F(3))^{F(3)} - 5) \\
 53357 &:= (((F(F(7)) - 5) + F(F(3))) \times F(F((F(3) + 5)))) \\
 53361 &:= ((F(F((1 + 6))) - F(3))^{-3+5}) \\
 53366 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times (F(6) + 3))^{F(3)} + 5) \\
 53374 &:= (((F(F(4)) - F(F(7)))^{F(3)} + (F((F(3) + 5)))) \\
 53482 &:= -F(28) + F(4 + 3)^5 \\
 53515 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(1 + 5)))) - ((3^5))) \\
 53563 &:= (-F(3)) + ((F(F(F(6))) - F(F((5 + F(3)))) \times 5) \\
 53564 &:= -(F(F(F(4))) - ((F(F(F(6))) - F(F((5 + F(3)))) \times 5)) \\
 53565 &:= ((F((5 + F(6))) - F(F((5 + 3)))) \times (-5) \\
 53567 &:= (((F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-5)) - ((3 - 5)) \\
 53578 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(F(7))) \times 5) + F((F(3) + 5)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53586 &:= (F(F(6)) - ((F(F(8)) - F(F((5 + F(3)))))) \times (-5)) \\
 53743 &:= -((F((F(3)^4)) + (F((7 \times 3)) \times (-5))) \\
 53823 &:= ((-F(3)) + F(F(-(F(2) - 8)))) \times F(F((F(3) + (5)))) \\
 53824 &:= ((-F(F(F(4)))) + F(F(-(F(2) - 8))))^{-3+5} \\
 53827 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F((F(2) + F(8)))) \times 3) - (5)) \\
 53837 &:= (((-F(F(7))) - F((F(F(3)) + (F(8)))))) \times (-3) + (5)) \\
 53876 &:= -((F(F(F(6)))) + ((-7) \times (F(8)^3)) + (5))) \\
 53877 &:= ((F((F(7) + (7))) \times 8) - ((3^5))) \\
 53878 &:= ((F(F(8))/(-F(7))) - ((F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times (-5))) \\
 53887 &:= -((F(F(7)) + (-8) \times F(((8/F(3)) \times 5)))) \\
 53888 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (8 \times 8))/F((F(3) + (5)))) \\
 53895 &:= (((5 \times F(9)) - F(F(8))) - 3) \times (-5) \\
 53946 &:= 6 \times (F(4) + F(9)) \times 3^5 \\
 53985 &:= (((-5) + F(F(8))) - F((9 + 3))) \times 5 \\
 53987 &:= -((F(F(7)) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(9) \times (-3))) \times (-5))) \\
 54128 &:= 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5)) \\
 54136 &:= F(6) \times (F(3) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5)) \\
 54168 &:= 8 \times (6 + F(1 \times 4 \times 5)) \\
 54176 &:= F(6) \times (7 + F(1 \times 4 \times 5)) \\
 54216 &:= F(6) \times (12 + F(4 \times 5)) \\
 54234 &:= ((F(F((4 + 3)))^2) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \\
 54244 &:= ((F(F((F(4) + (4))))^2) - 45) \\
 54247 &:= ((F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}) - (2 \times F((F(4) + (5)))) \\
 54248 &:= 8 \times (4^2 + F(4 \times 5)) \\
 54257 &:= ((F(F(7))^{F(5-2)}) - (F(F(4))^5)) \\
 54262 &:= (-2) - (F(F(6)) \times (-F((2 \times (4 + 5)))) \\
 54263 &:= -((F(F(3)) + (F(F(6)) \times (-F((2 \times (4 + 5)))))) \\
 54264 &:= (F((F(4) \times 6)) \times ((2^4) + 5)) \\
 54268 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(6)))^2) - F((F(4) + (5)))) \\
 54269 &:= ((F((F(9) - F(F(6))))^2) - (4 \times 5)) \\
 54272 &:= (-2) + ((F(F(7))^2) - (F(4) \times 5)) \\
 54273 &:= -((F(F(3)) - ((F(F(7))^2) - (F(4) \times 5))) \\
 54274 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times ((F(F(7))^2) - (F(4) \times 5)) \\
 54275 &:= (-5) + ((F(F(7))^2) - (4 + 5)) \\
 54276 &:= (F(6) + ((F(F(7))^2) - F((F(4) + (5)))) \\
 54277 &:= (-7) + ((F(F(7))^{-2+4}) - (5)) \\
 54278 &:= (-8) + (((F(F(7))^2) + F(F(4))) - (5)) \\
 54279 &:= (-9) + ((F(F(7))^2) + ((4 - 5))) \\
 54281 &:= ((F(F(-(1 - 8)))^2) - (F(4) + (5)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54282 &:= (-2) + ((F(F((8 - F(2))))^{F(F(4))}) - (5)) \\
 54283 &:= (-F(F(3)) + ((F(F((8 - F(2))))^{F(F(4))}) - (5)) \\
 54284 &:= ((F((F(4) + (8 + 2)))^{F(F(4))}) - (5)) \\
 54285 &:= (F((-5) + F(8)) \times F(-((2 - 4) \times 5))) \\
 54286 &:= ((F(-(F(6) - F(8)))^2) + ((F(F(4)) - (5)))) \\
 54287 &:= ((F(F(7))^{F(F(8/2))}) + ((F(4) - (5)))) \\
 54288 &:= 8 \times (F(8) \times F(2) + F(4 \times 5)) \\
 54289 &:= F(9 + 8/2)^{-F(4)+5} \\
 54294 &:= F(4 + 9)^{-2+4} + 5 \\
 54298 &:= F(8 + 9) \times F(2) \times F(4 + 5) \\
 54325 &:= ((F(F(F((5 + F(2)))))) - ((3^4)) \times 5) \\
 54327 &:= (F(7) \times (-2) + F((-F(3)) + F((F(4) + (5)))) \\
 54334 &:= ((F(F((4 + 3)))^{F(3)}) + 45) \\
 54336 &:= F(6) \times (3^3 + F(4 \times 5)) \\
 54337 &:= ((F(F(7))^{F(3)}) + (3 + 45)) \\
 54344 &:= ((F(F((F(4) + (4))))^{F(3)}) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \\
 54347 &:= (((F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}) + 3) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \\
 54348 &:= (-F(8)) \times (-4 - F((F(3) \times (4 + 5)))) \\
 54353 &:= (F((F(3) + (5))) \times F((-F(3)) + F((F(4) + (5)))) \\
 54385 &:= ((5 \times F(F(8))) - (345)) \\
 54387 &:= ((F(7) \times F((F(8) - F(3)))) + F((4 + 5))) \\
 54455 &:= ((-55) + F(F((4 + 4))) \times 5) \\
 54465 &:= (5 \times ((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \\
 54467 &:= (7 \times ((6^{F(F(4))+F(4)}) + (5))) \\
 54476 &:= -(((F(F(6)) + F(F(7))) + (F(F((4 + 4))) \times (-5))) \\
 54477 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}) - 45)) \\
 54485 &:= (((5 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(4))) - ((F(4)^5)) \\
 54487 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (((F(F(8)) - (4)) + F(F(4))) \times 5)) \\
 54497 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (F(F((9 - (4/4)))) \times 5)) \\
 54517 &:= (-F(F(7))) + ((F(F(F((1 + 5)))) + 4) \times 5) \\
 54522 &:= ((F(2) + F(F((2 + 5)))) \times F(F((F(F(4)) + (5)))) \\
 54527 &:= ((F(F(7))^2) + (-5) + (F(4)^5)) \\
 54537 &:= ((F(F(7))^{F(3)}) + (5 + (F(4)^5)) \\
 54585 &:= (((5 + F(F(8))) - F((5 + 4))) \times 5) \\
 54594 &:= ((-4) \times F(9)) - (-5) \times F(F((F(4) + (5)))) \\
 54615 &:= ((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - (F(F(6)) + F(F(4)))) \times 5) \\
 54619 &:= (-91) - ((F(F(F(6))) - 4) \times (-5)) \\
 54625 &:= (5 \times (F(F((2 + 6))) - F((F(4) + (5)))) \\
 54626 &:= ((F(F(6)) + F((-2) + F(F(6)))) \times F((F(F(4)) + (5)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54628 &:= (-82) - ((F(F(F(6))) - 4) \times (-5)) \\
 54629 &:= (-((9^2)) - ((F(F(F(6))) - 4) \times (-5)) \\
 54635 &:= (((F(F((5+3))) - F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) \times 5) \\
 54636 &:= (-F((F(6)+3)) - ((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times (-5)) \\
 54637 &:= (-73) - ((F(F(F(6))) - 4) \times (-5)) \\
 54639 &:= (-((9^{F(3)})) - ((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4))) \times (-5)) \\
 54644 &:= (-((F(4)^4)) - ((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times (-5)) \\
 54645 &:= ((F(F((5+F(4)))) - (F(F(6)) - (4))) \times 5) \\
 54646 &:= (-F((F(6)+F(4))) + ((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5) \\
 54649 &:= (-((9^{F(4)})) - ((F(F(F(6))) \times F(F(F(4)))) \times (-5)) \\
 54653 &:= (-F(3) + (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(4) \times 5))) \\
 54654 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(4) \times 5)))) \\
 54655 &:= (-5) \times ((-5) - F(F(F(6)))) + (4 \times 5)) \\
 54656 &:= (-F((6+5)) - ((F(F(F(6))) + F(4)) \times (-5)) \\
 54657 &:= (-F(F(7)) - (-5) \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(4))^5)) \\
 54658 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 5) - (F(6) \times (4+5))) \\
 54659 &:= (F(9) + (-5) \times (F(F(6)) - F((F(4)+5)))) \\
 54663 &:= (-F(3) + ((F(F(F(6))) - F((F(6)/F(4)))) \times 5) \\
 54664 &:= (-46) - ((F(F(F(6))) - 4) \times (-5)) \\
 54665 &:= (((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) - (6 + F(F(4)))) \times 5) \\
 54666 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(6)) - (4))) \times 5) \\
 54667 &:= (-F(7) + (((6 - F(F(F(6)))) + 4) \times (-5)) \\
 54668 &:= ((-F(8) - F(F(6))) - ((F(F(F(6))) - 4) \times (-5)) \\
 54669 &:= (F(9) + ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))) \times 5) \\
 54696 &:= F(6) \times (9 \times F(6) + F(4 \times 5)) \\
 54705 &:= ((-5) + F((07 \times F(4)))) \times 5) \\
 54717 &:= -F(7) + F(17+4) \times 5 \\
 54735 &:= (5 + F(3 \times 7) - 4) \times 5 \\
 54737 &:= -F(7) + (F(3 \times 7) + 4) \times 5 \\
 54775 &:= ((F(F((-5) + F(7)))) + (F(7) - (4))) \times 5) \\
 54776 &:= (F(F(6)) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - ((F(4) - (5)))))) \\
 54779 &:= (F(9) - ((F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + F(4)) \times (-5)) \\
 54795 &:= (-5) \times (-F((F(9) - F(7))) - F((F(F(4)) + (5)))) \\
 54796 &:= (F(F(6)) - ((9 + F((7 \times F(4)))) \times (-5)) \\
 54805 &:= (-5) \times ((0 - F(F(8))) - (F(4) \times 5)) \\
 54815 &:= (((F(F((5+1))) + F(F(8))) - (4)) \times 5) \\
 54825 &:= (-5) \times ((F(2) - F(F(8))) - (4 \times 5)) \\
 54829 &:= (F((9+2)) - ((F(F(8)) + F(F(4))) \times (-5)) \\
 54835 &:= (((5^{F(3)} + F(F(8))) - (4)) \times 5) \\
 54839 &:= (F((9+F(3))) - ((F(F(8)) + (4)) \times (-5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54845 &:= (((5^{F(4)} + F(F(8))) - F(F(4))) \times 5) \\
 54849 &:= 9^{F(4)} + 8 \times F(4 \times 5) \\
 54855 &:= (-5) \times ((-5) - F(F(8))) - (4 \times 5)) \\
 54856 &:= (F(F(6)) - (-5) \times (F(F(8)) + F((F(4) + (5)))))) \\
 54864 &:= (F((4+F(6))) - ((F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times (-5)) \\
 54865 &:= (((5 \times 6) + F(F(8))) - F(4)) \times 5) \\
 54866 &:= (F(F(6)) + (((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) + F(F(4))) \times 5) \\
 54867 &:= ((7 \times F(F(6))) - ((F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times (-5)) \\
 54869 &:= (F(9) - (((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(F(4)))) \times (-5)) \\
 54873 &:= ((F(3)^7) - ((F(F(8)) + F(4)) \times (-5)) \\
 54874 &:= (F(-((F(F(F(4))) - F(7))) - ((F(F(8)) \times F(F(F(4)))) \times (-5)) \\
 54884 &:= (F((4+8)) - ((F(F(8)) + F(F(4))) \times (-5)) \\
 54885 &:= (-5) - ((F(F(8)) + (8 \times 4)) \times (-5)) \\
 54887 &:= ((7 \times F(8)) - ((F(F(8)) + F(F(4))) \times (-5)) \\
 54888 &:= ((8 \times F(8)) - ((F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times (-5)) \\
 54889 &:= (F(9) - ((F(F(8)) + (F(8) + (4))) \times (-5)) \\
 54915 &:= ((F(F(F(5+1))) + (F(9) + F(4))) \times 5) \\
 54925 &:= (5 \times F(-2+9))^{F(4)} / 5 \\
 54936 &:= F(6) \times (3 \times F(9) + F(4 \times 5)) \\
 54946 &:= ((6^{F(4)} - (F(F(F(9 - F(4)))))) \times (-5)) \\
 54955 &:= (-5) \times (-((5 \times 9) - F(F((F(4) + (5)))))) \\
 54958 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 5) + (F((9+4) - (5))) \\
 54963 &:= (F(F((F(F(3)) + (6)))) - (F(F(F(9 - F(4)))) \times (-5)) \\
 54965 &:= (5 \times ((F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) + F((F(F(4)) + (5)))) \\
 54967 &:= (-F(F(7)) + ((F(F(F(6))) + (94)) \times 5) \\
 54997 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(9)) - (F(F(F(9 - F(4)))) \times (-5)) \\
 55454 &:= (F(F((F(F(4)) + (5)))) \times ((F(4)^5) - (5)) \\
 55566 &:= (6 \times (F(F(6))^{F(5-5/5)})) \\
 55647 &:= ((F(F(7)) - (4)) \times ((F(6) - (5))^5)) \\
 55677 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) + (6))) - (5+5)) \\
 55754 &:= ((4^5) - (F(F((F(7) - (5)))) \times (-5)) \\
 55885 &:= ((5 \times F(F(8))) + (F(8) \times 55)) \\
 55924 &:= F(4)^{F(2)+9} - 5^5 \\
 56163 &:= (3 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((1 - (6^5)))) \\
 56274 &:= (((4 + F(F(7)))^2) - (F(F(6)) \times (-5)) \\
 56284 &:= (4 \times (F(F(8)) + (-((F(2) - (6))^5))) \\
 56327 &:= (F(((7 \times 2) + 3)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-5)) \\
 56329 &:= ((F((F(9)/2)) + F(3)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-5)) \\
 56337 &:= ((F(F(7))^{F(3)} + (F(3)^{6+5}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 56445 &:= (((5 + F(F(4)))^{F(4)} + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 56464 &:= (4 \times ((F(F(F(6))) \times F(F(4))) - ((6^5)))) \\
 56479 &:= (F(9) - (((7^{F(4)} + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-5))) \\
 56615 &:= ((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) + (F((F(6) + (6)))) \times 5) \\
 56795 &:= ((-((59 \times 7) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-5)) \\
 56826 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) - F(2))) \times (-F(8) - F(F(6)))) / (-5)) \\
 56827 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F(2) + 8)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-5))) \\
 56848 &:= (F((F(8) - F(4))) \times (-8 - (6 \times 5))) \\
 56997 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times 9) - ((-F(9) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 5)) \\
 57267 &:= 7 \times (-6 + 2^{F(7)} - 5) \\
 57283 &:= ((F(3) \times (F((F(8) + 2)) - (F(7)))) - (5)) \\
 57312 &:= (2 \times (-1) + F((F(3) + F((F(7) - (5)))))) \\
 57314 &:= (F(F(4)) \times F(((1 + 3) \times 7) - 5)) \\
 57322 &:= 2 \times F(23) + F(7) - 5 \\
 57323 &:= F(3) \times (F(23) + 7) - 5 \\
 57324 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (F((2 + (3 \times 7))) + (5))) \\
 57326 &:= (6 + F(23)) \times (7 - 5) \\
 57327 &:= F(7) + F(23) \times (7 - 5) \\
 57332 &:= F(23) \times F(3) + F(7) + 5 \\
 57339 &:= (9 - F(3)) \times F(3)^{F(7)} - 5 \\
 57349 &:= (((9 - F(F(4))) \times (F(3)^{F(7)})) + (5)) \\
 57353 &:= (((-((3^5) \times (-3) - F(F(7)))) + (5)) \\
 57358 &:= ((8 + F(F((5 + F(3)))) \times (F(F(7)) + (5))) \\
 57384 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (F((F(8) + F(3))) + (7 \times 5))) \\
 57387 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F((F(8) - F(3)))) \times F(7)) + (5)) \\
 57464 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (F((F(F(6)) + F(F(4)))) + (75))) \\
 57492 &:= ((2 + F(9)) \times F((-4) + F((F(7) - (5)))))) \\
 57547 &:= (F(F(7)) + (F(F(4)) \times F(((5 + F(7)) + (5)))) \\
 57669 &:= (((-((F(9) \times F(6))) \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(7)))) + (5)) \\
 57834 &:= ((F(4)^{-3+8}) \times (F(F(7)) + (5))) \\
 57845 &:= (((F((5 \times F(4))) + F(F(8))) + (F(7))) \times 5) \\
 57855 &:= ((5^5) - (F((8 + F(7))) \times (-5))) \\
 58384 &:= (((F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8))) / (-3)) \times (-F(8) - (5))) \\
 58396 &:= (F(F(6)) + (((9^3) + F(F(8))) \times 5)) \\
 58479 &:= (((9 + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))}) - (85)) \\
 58483 &:= (F(F(-((F(F(3)) - 8))) \times ((F(F(4))^8) - (5))) \\
 58674 &:= (((F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) + (F((8 + 5)))))) \\
 58686 &:= (-6) \times (F(F(8)) - (F(F(6)) \times F((F(8) - (5)))))) \\
 58716 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((-1) + F(7)) \times F((8 + 5))) \\
 58721 &:= (((-12) \times F(F(7))) \times (-F(8)) + (5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 58746 &:= (-6) \times (((F(F(4)) \times F(F(7))) \times (-F(8))) - (5)) \\
 58797 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((9 + F(F(7)))^{F(8-5)})) \\
 58911 &:= (F((1 \times 19)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-5))) \\
 58912 &:= F(2) + F(19) + F(F(8)) \times 5 \\
 58913 &:= F(3) + F(19) + F(F(8)) \times 5 \\
 58914 &:= F(4) + F(19) + F(F(8)) \times 5 \\
 58944 &:= F(4) \times (F(4)^9) - F(8) \times 5 \\
 58964 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} \times 9 - 85 \\
 59018 &:= -F(8) - 10 + 9^5 \\
 59026 &:= -((F(F(6)) + (2 - (09^5)))) \\
 59028 &:= -F(8) + 2 \times 0 + 9^5 \\
 59034 &:= F(4) \times (3^{09} - 5) \\
 59036 &:= -((F((F(6) - F(F(3)))) - (09^5))) \\
 59037 &:= (((-F(7)) + F(F(3))) + (09^5)) \\
 59039 &:= (((-9) - F(F(3))) + (09^5)) \\
 59043 &:= -3 - F(4) + 09^5 \\
 59044 &:= F(4) \times F(4)^{09} - 5 \\
 59045 &:= (((-5) + F(F(F(4)))) + (09^5)) \\
 59046 &:= -6 + F(4) + 09^5 \\
 59047 &:= -F(7 - 4) + 09^5 \\
 59048 &:= -F(8/4) + 09^5 \\
 59051 &:= (F(F(-((1 - 5)))) + (09^5)) \\
 59053 &:= -((F(F(3)) - (5 + (09^5)))) \\
 59054 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times (5 + (09^5))) \\
 59057 &:= F(7) - 5 + 09^5 \\
 59062 &:= (F((F(2) + (6))) + (09^5)) \\
 59065 &:= (((-5) + F(F(6))) + (09^5)) \\
 59083 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + 8)) + (09^5)) \\
 59137 &:= (F((F(7) - F(3))) - ((1 - (9^5)))) \\
 59138 &:= F(8 + 3) + 1 \times 9^5 \\
 59139 &:= (F((9 + F(3))) + (1 + (9^5))) \\
 59177 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(-((1 - 9)))) - (5)) \\
 59193 &:= F(3 + 9) + 1 \times 9^5 \\
 59194 &:= (F((F(4) + 9)) + (1 + (9^5))) \\
 59218 &:= F(8 - 1)^2 + 9^5 \\
 59227 &:= ((F((F(7) - 2)) \times 2) + (9^5)) \\
 59238 &:= F(8) \times 3^2 + 9^5 \\
 59257 &:= (F(F(7)) - ((5^2) - (9^5)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 59274** := $((F(F(4)) + (F(7)))^2) + (9^5)$
59275 := $((-5) + F(F(7))) - ((2 - (9^5)))$
59276 := $((-F(6)) + F(F(7))) + (2 + (9^5))$
59277 := $(F(F(7)) - (((7 - 2) - (9^5))))$
59281 := $(F(F(-(1 - 8))) - ((F(2) - (9^5))))$
59282 := $(F(F((F(2) + (8 - 2)))) + (9^5))$
59283 := $F(F(3)) + F(F(8 - F(2))) + 9^5$
59284 := $F(F(4)) + F(F(8 - F(2))) + 9^5$
59287 := $((7 \times F((8 + F(2)))) + (9^5))$
59337 := $((F((F(7) - F(F(3)))) \times F(3)) + (9^5))$
59354 := $((F((F(4) \times 5)) / F(3)) + (9^5))$
59389 := $F(9) \times (8 + F(3)) + 9^5$
59415 := $51 \times F(4 + 9) \times 5$
59418 := $-8 + F(14) + 9^5$
59426 := $F(6 + 2 \times 4) + 9^5$
59427 := $((F((7 \times 2)) + F(F(F(4)))) + (9^5))$
59432 := $23 \times F(4 + 9 + 5)$
59485 := $(-5) + ((F(8)^{F(F(4))}) + (9^5))$
59486 := $((F(F(6)) \times F(8)) - ((4 - (9^5))))$
59488 := $((F(8) \times F(8)) - F(F(4))) + (9^5)$
59497 := $((F(F(7)) - 9) \times F(F(4))) + (9^5)$
59617 := $71 \times F(6) + 9^5$
59647 := $F(7) \times 46 + 9^5$
59651 := $F(15) - F(6) + 9^5$
59653 := $F(3 \times 5) - 6 + 9^5$
59659 := $9^5 + F((-6 + 9) \times 5)$
59665 := $(5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F((F(6) \times F(F((9 - 5)))))))$
59667 := $(F((7 + F(6))) + (F(6) + (9^5)))$
59725 := $52 \times F(7) + 9^5$
59739 := $(-9) + ((3 \times F(F(7))) + (9^5))$
59744 := $(-4) + ((F(4) \times F(F(7))) + (9^5))$
59748 := $((F((8 - 4)) \times F(F(7))) + (9^5))$
59764 := $F(4 + 6) \times F(7) + 9^5$
59787 := $((F(7) \times F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - (9 + 5)))$
59794 := $((F(F(4))^9) + F(F(7))) + (9^5)$
59876 := $(F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(7)) \times ((8 + F(9)) \times (-5))))$
59947 := $((F(F(7)) \times 4) - ((F(9) - (9^5))))$
60347 := $(F(F(7)) \times (F(4) + (F(3)^{F(06)})))$
61029 := $9 \times (F(20) + 16)$
61194 := $((F(-(F(4) - F(9))) - 1) / (1 + F(F(6))))$
61467 := $(((-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4) + F((1 + F(F(6))))$
61476 := $((F(F(F(6))) - ((F(F(7)) \times F(4)) + 1)) \times 6)$
61483 := $(((-3) + F(F(8))) \times 4) + F((1 + F(F(6))))$
61485 := $((5 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(4)))) + F((-1) + F(F(6))))$
61495 := $((5 \times F(F(F((9 - F(4)))))) + (F((-1) + F(F(6))))))$
62214 := $F(4) \times F(12)^2 + 6$
62244 := $((F(4) \times (F((4^2)) + F(2))) \times F(F(6)))$
62424 := $((F((F(4)^2)) \times F(4)^2) \times 6)$
62426 := $(F(6) - F(2))^4 \times 26$
62475 := $((((-5) + F(F(7))) - F(F(F(4))))^2) + F(F(F(6)))$
62476 := $((((-6) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))}) + F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))$
62482 := $(2 \times (F((F(8) - F(4))) + F((2 + F(F(6))))))$
62568 := $(8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (5^{-F(2)+6})))$
62584 := $4 \times (F(8) + (5 \times F(2))^6)$
62656 := $((F(6) - F((-5) + F(F(6)))) \times (-2^6))$
62677 := $(F(F(7)) \times (F(7) + (F((6/2))^{F(6)})))$
62715 := $(-5) \times (-F(17) - F(F((2 + 6))))$
62736 := $((F((F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times (F(7) + 2)) + (F(F(6))))$
62749 := $(F(9) - (-((F(F(4)) + (F(7)))) \times F((-2) + F(F(6))))))$
62835 := $((5 \times 3) \times (F((F(8) - 2)) + F(6)))$
62874 := $((F(F(4)) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(8))) + F(2) \times (-6)$
62896 := $F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(8 \times 2) \times F(6))$
62976 := $(F(6) + 7 \times F(9)) \times 2^{F(6)}$
63142 := $((F(2) + 41)^3 - F(F(F(6))))$
63168 := $((8 \times F(6)) \times F((F((1 \times 3)) \times F(6))))$
63189 := $(9 \times (F((F(8) - 1)) + (F(3)^{F(6)})))$
63364 := $(-4) - ((F((F(6) + 3))^{F(3)}) \times (-F(6)))$
63368 := $(86 + 3)^{F(3)} \times F(6)$
63373 := $(-3) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F((3 \times 3)) \times F(6)))$
63374 := $-((F(F(4)) + (F(F(7)) \times (-F((3 \times 3)) \times F(6))))))$
63376 := $F(6 + 7) \times F(3 \times 3) \times F(6)$
63377 := $((F(F(7)) \times 73) + F((3 \times F(6))))$
63378 := $((8 \times F((7 \times F(3)))) + F(3)) \times F(F(6))$
63384 := $((F(F(4)) + ((F((8 + 3))^{F(3)}))) \times F(6)$
63387 := $((F(F(7)) - (8 / F(3)))^{F(3)} + F(F(F(6))))$
63392 := $(F(2 + 9)^{F(3)} + 3) \times F(6)$
63397 := $((F(F(7)) \times (F(9) \times F((3 + 3)))) + F(F(6)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 63424 &:= (4 + F(2^4)) \times F(3)^6 \\
 63462 &:= (((F((2 + F(6)))^{F(F(4))}) - 3) \times F(F(6))) \\
 63466 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (F(6) \times (4 + (3^{F(6)})))) \\
 63469 &:= ((9 \times F((F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))))) + F((3 \times 6))) \\
 63478 &:= (((-8) \times F(F(7))) - F(4)) \times (-F((3 + 6))) \\
 63483 &:= (((F((F(3) + 8))^{F(F(4))}) - F(3)) \times F(F(6))) \\
 63496 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times (9 + F(4)))^{F(3)}) - F(6)) \\
 63498 &:= (F(8) \times (9 + F(4)))^{F(3)} - 6 \\
 63523 &:= (-F(3) - (-((F((2 \times 5))^{F(3)})) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 63524 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) + (-((F((2 \times 5))^{F(3)})) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 63525 &:= ((F((5 \times 2))^{5-3}) \times F(F(6))) \\
 63546 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times F((4 + 5))) \times F((3 + F(6)))) \\
 63559 &:= (F(9) - (-((55^{F(3)})) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 63562 &:= (2 \times ((F(6)^5) - F((F(3) \times F(6)))) \\
 63567 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + 5)) - F(3)) \times F(F(6))) \\
 63579 &:= ((-9) \times F(F(7))) + (F(F((5 + 3))) \times 6) \\
 63618 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((1 + 6)^3)) \times 6) \\
 63654 &:= (((F((F(4) \times 5)) + F(6))^{F(3)})/6) \\
 63667 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6) \times (3^{F(6)}))) \\
 63672 &:= (((2^{F(7)}) - F(F((F(6) - F(F(3)))))) \times F(6)) \\
 63687 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(8)) + (6)) \times F((F(F(3)) + (6)))) \\
 63735 &:= (-5) \times ((3 - F((F(7) + F(3)))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 63744 &:= (4^4 - 7) \times F(3)^{F(6)} \\
 63777 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(7)) + (7)) + F(F(3))) \times F(F(6)) \\
 63778 &:= (((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + (F(7))) \times F((F(F(3)) + (6)))) \\
 63786 &:= (6 \times (F(F(8)) - ((F(7) + F(3)) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 63792 &:= ((F(2) + (F(9) \times F(7))) \times F((F(3) \times 6))) \\
 63798 &:= (-F(8)) \times (-9 - (F(F(7)) \times F((F(F(3)) + (6)))) \\
 63846 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + 4)) - F(F((F(8)/3)))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 63847 &:= (-(((F(F(7)) - F((4 + F(8)))) - F(F(3)))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 63888 &:= (F(8) + 8/8)^3 \times 6 \\
 63935 &:= ((F((5^{F(3)})) - F((9 + 3))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 63936 &:= 6^3 \times (F(9) + 3) \times F(6) \\
 63948 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(F(4)) \times F((9 + 3)))) \times 6) \\
 63966 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((F(F(6)) + F(9))^{F(3)}) + F(F(6)))) \\
 63985 &:= (-5) \times ((-8) \times F((F(9)/F(3)))) - F(F(6))) \\
 64024 &:= (F(4) + 20^{F(4)}) \times F(6) \\
 64058 &:= ((-F(F(8))) + F((5^{F(F(4))})) - F(F(6))) \\
 64075 &:= ((5 \times F(F(7))) \times F((04 + 6)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64079 &:= (F((9 + F(7))) + F((04 \times 6))) \\
 64155 &:= (-5) \times ((-5) \times F(14) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 64168 &:= (8 \times (((F(F(6)) - 1)^{F(4)}) + F(F(6)))) \\
 64195 &:= (-5) \times (-((F(9) \times F(14)) - F(F(6)))) \\
 64266 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - F(F((F(6) - F(2)))) - F(F(4))) \times 6) \\
 64272 &:= (((-F(2) - F(F(7))) + F(F((2 \times 4)))) \times 6) \\
 64274 &:= (-4) - ((F(F(7)) - F(F((2 \times 4)))) \times 6) \\
 64276 &:= ((F(F(6)) - F((F(7) + ((2^4)))))/(-F(6))) \\
 64277 &:= ((F(7) - F((F(7) + ((2^4)))))/(-F(6))) \\
 64278 &:= ((F(F(8)) - F(F(7))) \times ((F(2)^{F(4)}) \times 6)) \\
 64279 &:= ((F((F(9) - (7 - 2))) + F(4))/F(6)) \\
 64296 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(F((9 - 2))) - F(4))) \times 6) \\
 64307 &:= (((F(F(7)) - F(03))^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 64356 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F((5 \times F(3))) \times 4)) \times 6) \\
 64366 &:= (((6^6) - F(F(3))) + F((F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(6))))) \\
 64367 &:= -((F(F(7)) + (F((6 \times 3)) \times (-4) - F(F(6)))) \\
 64368 &:= (((F(F(8)) - ((6^3))) - F(F(4))) \times 6) \\
 64384 &:= 4^8 - F(3 \times 4) \times F(6) \\
 64386 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((F(8)^3)/F(4)) - F(F(6)))) \\
 64488 &:= (F(8) \times 8^{F(4)} - 4) \times 6 \\
 64537 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F((3 + 5)))^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(6))) \\
 64539 &:= 9 \times (F(3 \times 5) + F(4)^{F(6)}) \\
 64544 &:= -F(4 \times 4) - 5 + 4^{F(6)} \\
 64549 &:= -((F(((9 + F(F(4))) + (5))) - (4^{F(6)}))) \\
 64592 &:= ((F((2 \times 9)) \times (5^{F(F(4))})) - F(6)) \\
 64594 &:= ((F((F(F(4)) \times 9)) \times (5^{F(F(4))})) - 6) \\
 64596 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((9 \times 5) \times 4)) \times 6) \\
 64597 &:= (F(7) \times (F(9) + (5 \times F((F(F(4)) \times F(6))))) \\
 64638 &:= (-F(8)) \times ((F(F(3)) + (F(6)^{F(4)})) \times (-6)) \\
 64656 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (5 \times F((6 + F(4)))) \times 6) \\
 64665 &:= -((F((-5) + F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(F(6))) - 4) \times 6)) \\
 64668 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(F(6)) + F(F(6))) \times 4)) \times 6) \\
 64672 &:= ((F(-((F(2) - F(7)))) \times (-6)) + (4^{F(6)})) \\
 64675 &:= (-5) - (-7) \times ((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) - F(F(6))) \\
 64676 &:= (((-6) \times F(F(7))) - F(6)) \times (-46) \\
 64679 &:= (((F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(6))^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 64683 &:= (((F(F(3)) - F(F(8))) \times (-6)) - F((F(F(4)) \times F(6)))) \\
 64686 &:= (((F(F(6)) - F(F(8))) + F((F(6) + 4))) \times (-6)) \\
 64689 &:= (-F((F(9) - 8))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (4 - F(F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$64694 := ((F((-4) + F(9)))/(F(6) + F(4)) - F(F(F(6))))$$

$$64696 := ((F(F(6)) \times (-F(9) + (6))) + (4^{F(6)}))$$

$$64727 := (-F(7)) \times (-2) - ((F(F(7)) + (4)) \times F(F(6)))$$

$$64736 := (((F(F(6))^3) - F(7)) \times (F(F(F(4))) + 6))$$

$$64738 := (((F(8)^3) \times 7) - F((F(4) + F(6))))$$

$$64744 := (F(F(4)) \times (-((F(F(4)) \times F(F(7)))) + (F(4) \times F(F(F(6)))))$$

$$64764 := (F(4) \times (((F(F(6)) \times 7)^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(6))))$$

$$64769 := ((F((F(9) - F(F(6)))) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$64772 := (((-2) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(7))) + F(4) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$64773 := (((-F(3)) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(7))) + (4) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$64775 := ((F((5 + F(7))) + (7)) \times (4 + F(F(6))))$$

$$64782 := ((-2) \times F((F(8) - (7)))) + (4^{F(6)})$$

$$64788 := (((F(F(8)) + (F(8))) - (F(7)^{F(F(4))})) \times 6)$$

$$64792 := (2 \times (-((F(9) \times F(7))) + (F(4) \times F(F(F(6)))))$$

$$64812 := (F(21) - F(8 + 4)) \times 6$$

$$64818 := ((F(F(8)) - (-1) + F((8 + 4))) \times 6)$$

$$64824 := -F(4) + 2 \times F(8)^4 / 6$$

$$64826 := (-6 + 2 \times F(8)^4) / 6$$

$$64827 := 7 \times (2 \times F(8))^{F(4)} / F(6)$$

$$64835 := (5 + F(3)) \times F(8)^{F(4)} + F(6)$$

$$64836 := (((F((6 \times F(3))) - F(F(8))) - (4)) \times (-6))$$

$$64837 := ((F(F(7)) \times (-3)) + ((8 - 4)^{F(6)}))$$

$$64847 := 7 \times (4 + F(8))^{F(4)} - F(6)$$

$$64848 := (((F(8)^4) / F((8 - 4))) + F(F(6)))$$

$$64864 := 4^{F(6)} - 84 \times F(6)$$

$$64878 := ((F(F(8)) - (-7) \times (-F(8)) + F(F(4)))) \times 6$$

$$64881 := (1 + 88) \times F(4)^6$$

$$64883 := ((F(F(3)) - 8) \times (-((F(8))^{F(4)} + F(6))))$$

$$64896 := (((6 + 98)^{F(F(4))}) \times 6)$$

$$64926 := -((F((F(6) - ((2 - 9)))) - (4^{F(6)}))$$

$$64935 := -F(5 \times 3) + 9 + 4^{F(6)}$$

$$64945 := -5^4 + F(9) + 4^{F(6)}$$

$$64956 := (F(F(F(6))) - (-5) \times (-F((9 + F(4)))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$64968 := (((F(F(8)) \times 6) - (9^{F(4)})) + F(F(6)))$$

$$64976 := ((((-6) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(9))) - (4)) \times F(6)$$

$$64981 := ((F((-1) + F(8))) \times 9) + (4^6)$$

$$64986 := (((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) - (F(9) \times 4)) \times 6)$$

$$64997 := -((F(F(7)) - ((F(9) \times (-9)) + (4^{F(6)})))$$

$$65026 := (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(20) - (5)) \times F(6)))$$

$$65159 := -F(9 + 5) + (-1 + 5)^{F(6)}$$

$$65227 := (((F(F(7))^2) - F((F(2) + (5)))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$65235 := ((F(F((5 + F(3))))^{F(-2+5)}) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$65237 := (((F(F(7))^{F(3)}) + F(-((2 - 5)))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$65286 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (F((8 - F(2))) \times 5)) \times 6)$$

$$65298 := ((F(F(8)) - (9 \times (2 + 5))) \times 6)$$

$$65346 := ((-F((6 + 4))) + F(F((3 + 5))) \times 6)$$

$$65364 := (((F(4) + F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(3) \times 5))) \times 6)$$

$$65368 := (-8) \times (F(F(6)) - ((F(3)^{5+F(6)}))$$

$$65376 := ((F(F(F(6))) - ((7 + 3) \times 5)) \times 6)$$

$$65388 := ((F(F(8)) - (8 \times (F(F(3)) + (5)))) \times 6)$$

$$65406 := ((F(F(F(6))) - 045) \times 6)$$

$$65424 := ((-42) + F(F((F(4) + (5)))) \times 6)$$

$$65436 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(3) \times (4 \times 5))) \times 6)$$

$$65437 := (-F(F(7))) - ((F(F(3)) - F(F((F(4) + (5)))) \times 6)$$

$$65443 := (-F(F((3 + 4))) + ((F(F(F(4))) + (5)) \times F(F(F(6))))$$

$$65447 := (F(7) + F(4))^4 - F(5 + 6)$$

$$65448 := ((F(F(8)) - (4 + F((4 + 5)))) \times 6)$$

$$65464 := 4^{F(6)} - (4 + 5) \times F(6)$$

$$65466 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) - ((F(F(4)) \times 5) \times F(F(6))))$$

$$65467 := (-F(F(7))) + (((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) + (5)) \times 6)$$

$$65472 := (2^{F(7)} - F(4) - 5) \times F(6)$$

$$65478 := ((F(F(8)) - ((7 \times 4) + 5)) \times 6)$$

$$65482 := (-2) - ((F(F(8)) - (F(F(4))^5)) \times (-6))$$

$$65483 := -((F(F(3)) + ((F(F(8)) - (F(F(4))^5)) \times (-6)))$$

$$65494 := (F(F(4)) \times ((F((9 - F(4)))^5) - F(F(6))))$$

$$65496 := ((-6) - F(9)) + (F(F(4))^{-5+F(F(6))})$$

$$65497 := (-F(F(7))) + ((9 + F(F((F(4) + (5)))) \times 6)$$

$$65524 := (F(F(4)) \times ((F((F(2) + (5)))^5) - (6)))$$

$$65526 := ((F(F((6 + 2))) - ((5 \times 5))) \times 6)$$

$$65533 := -3 + F(3)^{5+5+6}$$

$$65534 := ((4^{3+5}) - F((-5) + F(6)))$$

$$65538 := ((F(F(8)) + ((F(3) - ((5 \times 5)))) \times 6)$$

$$65541 := (-((1 \times 4) - (5^5))) \times F(F(6))$$

$$65542 := 2 \times (F(4) + 5)^5 + 6$$

$$65543 := (F(3) + (-((4 - (5^5))) \times F(F(6))))$$

$$65544 := 4^{F(-4+5+5)} + F(6)$$

$$65549 := (-F(9)) - ((F(F(4)) - ((5^5))) \times F(F(6)))$$

- 65556 := ((F(F(F(6))) - ((5 × 5) - 5)) × 6)
 65562 := 2 × (F(6)⁵ + 5 + F(6))
 65566 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 6) - (5 - (-5) × F(F(6))))
 65568 := ((F(F(8)) - (F(6) + (5 + 5))) × 6)
 65576 := ((-6) - (F(F(7)) × 5)) × (-56)
 65583 := (-((F(3) × F(8))) + ((5⁵) × F(F(6))))
 65585 := (-((5 × 8)) + ((5⁵) × F(F(6))))
 65586 := (6 × (F(F(8)) - (-5) × (5 - F(6))))
 65591 := ((-1) × F(9)) + ((5⁵) × F(F(6)))
 65592 := F(2) - F(9) + 5⁵ × F(F(6))
 65593 := F(3) - F(9) + 5⁵ × F(F(6))
 65594 := F(4) - F(9) + 5⁵ × F(F(6))
 65598 := ((F(F(8)) - F((F(F(9 - 5)))) + (5))) × 6
 65616 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (((1 - 6) - 5))) × 6)
 65622 := (((-((2 + 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (5)) × 6)
 65623 := (-F(3)) + (((-((F(2) - (6)))⁵) × F(F(6))))
 65624 := -((F(F(F(4))) - (((-((F(2) - (6)))⁵) × F(F(6))))))
 65625 := (5 - F(2))^{F(6)} + F(5 + 6)
 65626 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F(2)) × 6) - 56)
 65627 := (-F(7)) + (((-F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (5)) × 6)
 65628 := (-8 + F(26 - 5)) × 6
 65629 := ((F(9)/(-2)) + ((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) × 6))
 65632 := (-2) + (((-F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (5)) × 6)
 65633 := (-F(F(3))) + (((-F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (5)) × 6)
 65634 := (((-F(F(4))) + F(F((F(3) + (6)))) - (5)) × 6)
 65635 := (-5) + (((-F(F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))) - (5)) × 6)
 65636 := ((F(F(F(6))) × (-F(3) - F(6))) - (5 × F(6)))
 65637 := ((F(7) × (-3)) + ((F(F(F(6))) × 5) + F(F(F(6))))
 65638 := (((F(F(8)) + 3) × 6) - 56)
 65639 := (-((F(9) + 3)) + ((F(F(F(6))) × 5) + F(F(F(6))))
 65641 := (((1 × 4)^{F(6)}) - (-5) × F(F(6)))
 65642 := F(2) + 4^{F(6)} + 5 × F(F(6))
 65643 := F(3) + 4^{F(6)} + 5 × F(F(6))
 65644 := F(4) + 4^{F(6)} + 5 × F(F(6))
 65645 := (5 + (((F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) + (5)) × (-6)))
 65646 := (F(F(6)) + (((4^{F(6)}) + F((5 + 6))))
 65647 := (7 + (((F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) + (5)) × (-6)))
 65648 := (((F(F(8)) + F(F(4))) × 6) - (5 × F(6)))
 65649 := (9 + (((F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) + (5)) × (-6)))
 65651 := (((-((1 × 5)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 5) + F(F(F(6))))
 65652 := F(2) + (-5 + F(F(F(6)))) × 5 + F(F(F(6)))
 65653 := F(3) + (-5 + F(F(F(6)))) × 5 + F(F(F(6)))
 65654 := F(4) + (-5 + F(F(F(6)))) × 5 + F(F(F(6)))
 65655 := (((5⁵) × F(F(6))) + (5 × 6))
 65658 := ((F(F(8)) - F(((5 - 6) + 5))) × 6)
 65659 := (F(9) + (((5⁶)/5) × F(F(6))))
 65671 := (((1 × 7) × F(F(F(6)))) - (5)) - F(F(F(6)))
 65672 := F(2) + 7 × F(F(F(6))) - 5 - F(F(F(6)))
 65673 := F(3 × 7) × 6 + 5 - F(6)
 65674 := F(4) + 7 × F(F(F(6))) - 5 - F(F(F(6)))
 65675 := ((F(F((-5) + F(7))) × 6) + ((5 - 6)))
 65676 := (6 × F(F((7 + ((6 - 5)⁶))))
 65677 := (((-7) + F(7)) × F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 - 6))
 65678 := ((F((8 + F(7))) × 6) + F((-5) + F(6)))
 65679 := ((F((F(9) - F(7))) × 6) + (-5) + F(6))
 65681 := (((-1) - F(F(8))) × (-6)) + ((5 - 6))
 65682 := ((-F(2)) - F(F(8))) × (6 × (5 - 6))
 65683 := (((F(F(3)) - F(F(8))) × (-6)) + (5 + F(6)))
 65684 := (((F(F(4)) × F(F(8))) × (F(6) - (5))) + F(6))
 65686 := (((6 × F(F(8))) + F(6)) + F((-5) + F(6)))
 65687 := ((F((F(7) + 8)) × 6) + (5 + 6))
 65688 := ((F(F(8)) + F(-((8 - 6) - 5))) × 6)
 65689 := ((F(9) - F(8)) + ((F(F(F(6))) × 5) + F(F(F(6))))
 65692 := ((F(F(-((F(2) - 9)))) × 6) + (-5) + F(F(6)))
 65693 := -((F(-((F(3) - 9))) - ((F(F(F(6))) + (5)) × 6))
 65694 := ((F(4) + F(F((9 - 6) + 5))) × 6)
 65695 := (-5) + ((9 + F(F(F(6)))) - (5)) × 6)
 65697 := (F(-((F(7) - F(9)))) - ((F(F(F(6))) × (-5)) - (F(F(6))))
 65706 := ((F((F(6) + F(07))) + (5)) × 6)
 65712 := (((F(2) + F(F((1 + 7)))) + (5)) × 6)
 65716 := ((6 × F(F((1 + 7)))) + (5 × F(6)))
 65718 := ((F(F(8)) + ((-1) + F(7)) - (5)) × 6)
 65724 := ((F(F((4 × 2))) + (F(7) - (5))) × 6)
 65736 := ((F(F(6)) + ((3⁷) × 5)) × 6)
 65746 := (((F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(4)) × 7)) × 5) + F(F(F(6))))
 65748 := ((F(F(8)) + ((4 + F(7)) - (5))) × 6)
 65754 := ((F((F(F(4)) + (5))) + F(F((F(7) - (5)))) × 6)
 65765 := (F((5 + 6)) + (F(F((F(7) - (5)))) × 6))
 65766 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (-6) + F((F(7) - (5)))) × 6)

$$\begin{aligned}
 65768 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 6) - (F(7))) - (-5) \times F(F(6))) \\
 65776 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) + (7))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 65782 &:= (-2) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(7) + (5))) \times 6) \\
 65783 &:= -((F(F(3)) - ((F(F(8)) + (F(7) + (5))) \times 6)) \\
 65784 &:= (((F(4) - F(F(8))) - F((F(7) - (5)))) \times (-6)) \\
 65796 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((-9) + F(7)) \times 5) \times 6) \\
 65826 &:= (((F(F(6)) - F(2)) + F(F(8))) + (5)) \times 6) \\
 65832 &:= ((F(F((2^3))) + (F(8) + (5))) \times 6) \\
 65838 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (3^{8-5})) \times 6) \\
 65844 &:= (F(4) \times ((F(F(4)) \times F(F(8))) + 56)) \\
 65846 &:= (((F((6 + F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 65862 &:= (((26 + F(F(8))) + (5)) \times 6) \\
 65868 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (-((6 - 8)^5)) \times 6) \\
 65874 &:= (((4 \times 7) + F(F(8))) + (5)) \times 6) \\
 65886 &:= (-6) \times ((F(8) - F(F(8))) - 56) \\
 65887 &:= ((F(F(7)) + 8) + ((F(F(8)) - (5)) \times 6)) \\
 65896 &:= ((-6) \times (-F(9) - F(F(8)))) + (-5) + F(F(6))) \\
 65897 &:= (-F(7)) + (((F(9) + F(F(8))) + (5)) \times 6) \\
 65898 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(9) + (8 - 5))) \times 6) \\
 65916 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((1 - 9) \times 5)) \times 6) \\
 65946 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times F(F(F(4)))) + (9 \times 5)) \times 6) \\
 65964 &:= (((F(4) + F(F(F(6)))) + (9 \times 5)) \times 6) \\
 66012 &:= (((F(2) + F(10)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66129 &:= (((F(9) \times 2) - 1) \times F((F(6) + F(6)))) \\
 66156 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (5 \times 16)) \times 6) \\
 66168 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (61)) + F(F(6))) \times 6) \\
 66194 &:= ((F(F(4))^9) + ((-1) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6)) \\
 66274 &:= (F((F(F(4)) + (F(7)))) - ((2 - F(F(F(6)))) \times 6)) \\
 66278 &:= ((-8) + F((F(7) + 2))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6)) \\
 66286 &:= ((6 \times F(F(8))) + F(((F(2) + F(6)) + (6)))) \\
 66287 &:= ((F((7 + 8)) + F(2)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6)) \\
 66294 &:= (((F(4) \times F(9)) + F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66336 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(3) \times F((F(3) + F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66372 &:= (((F(2) - F(F(7)))/(-F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66373 &:= (((3 \times F(F(7))) - F(3)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6)) \\
 66374 &:= (((F(4) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(3))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6)) \\
 66378 &:= ((F(F(8))/F(7)) + (F(3)^{F(6)+F(6)})) \\
 66386 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - ((-((F(8)^3)) + F(F(6))) \times 6)) \\
 66388 &:= ((8 \times F((8 + 3))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6)) \\
 66389 &:= (((F(9) \times F(8)) - F(F(3))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 66396 &:= (((6 + F(9)) \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66414 &:= (((41 \times F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66426 &:= (((6 - F(2))^{F(4)} + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66444 &:= (((F(F(4))^{F(4)+4}) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66447 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 4) + (4^{F(6)})) - F(F(6))) \\
 66456 &:= (((65 \times F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66468 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(F(6)) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6)) \times 6) \\
 66474 &:= ((4 \times F(F(7))) + ((4^{F(6)} + (6))) \\
 66491 &:= (-1) - (((F(9) \times 4) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6)) \\
 66492 &:= (((F(2) \times F(9)) \times 4) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66493 &:= F(F(3)) + (F(9) \times 4 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66494 &:= F(F(4)) + (F(9) \times 4 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66498 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(9) \times 4)) \times 6) + (6)) \\
 66558 &:= (F((F(8) + (5))) + (-5) \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(6)))))) \\
 66565 &:= (-5) + ((-((6^5)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 66576 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F((7 + 5)) + (6))) \times 6) \\
 66629 &:= ((-F(9)) + F((2 \times F(6)))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6)) \\
 66636 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(3)) - F(F(6))) \times (-F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66638 &:= (((-((F(8)^3)) - F(F(6))) \times (-6)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 66642 &:= (F((2^4)) + ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) - (F(F(6)))) \\
 66662 &:= (-F(2)) + ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (F((F(6) + F(6)))) \\
 66663 &:= ((-((F(3) - F(6))) \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((F(6) + F(6)))) \\
 66664 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (F((F(6) + F(6)))) \\
 66666 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (-F((6 + 6))) - F(F(6))) \times 6) \\
 66678 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) - (66)) \times 6) \\
 66682 &:= (-2) - ((F(F(8)) + (F(6) \times F(F(6)))) \times (-6)) \\
 66683 &:= -((F(F(3)) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(6) \times F(F(6)))) \times (-6))) \\
 66684 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times ((F(F(8)) + (F(6) \times F(F(6)))) \times 6)) \\
 66728 &:= (8 \times ((2 \times F((F(7) + (6)))) - F(F(6))) \\
 66729 &:= (((9^2) \times F(7)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6)) \\
 66744 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times F((4 + 7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66768 &:= ((-8) + F((6 + F(7)))) \times (F(6) + F(6)) \\
 66784 &:= ((F(-((F(F(4)) - (F(8)))) - 7) \times (F(6) + F(6))) \\
 66786 &:= (6 \times ((F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) - (F(6) \times 6)) \\
 66792 &:= ((-((F((2 \times 9)) + F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(6)) \\
 66832 &:= (((2 \times F(-((F(3) - F(8)))) - F(6)) \times F(6)) \\
 66846 &:= (((6^{F(4)} + F(F(8))) - F(F(6))) \times 6) \\
 66848 &:= (((F((F(8) - F(4))) - F(F(8))) + (6)) \times (-F(6)) \\
 66875 &:= (((F((5 + F(7))) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(6))) - F(F(6)) \\
 66877 &:= -((F(F(7)) - ((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) + (6)) \times 6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 66896 &:= (F((6 + F(9)) - F(8))) \times (F(6) + F(6)) \\
 66912 &:= 2 \times (F(19) \times F(6) + F(6)) \\
 66927 &:= ((-7) - (-2) \times F((9 + F(6)))) \times F(F(6)) \\
 66936 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66948 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F((4 + 9)))) - F(F(6))) \times 6) \\
 66964 &:= ((4^{F(6)}) - (-F(9)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(6)))) \\
 66972 &:= ((F(-((F(2) - F(7)))) \times 9) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6))) \\
 66975 &:= (((5^7) + (F(9) \times (-6))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 66976 &:= (-((F(6) \times F(7))) \times (-F(9)) - F((-6) + F(F(6)))) \\
 66978 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(7) - (F(9) \times (-6)))) \times 6) \\
 67062 &:= (((-2) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(07))) \times 6) \\
 67066 &:= (-F(6) - ((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(07))) \times (-6))) \\
 67067 &:= (-7) - ((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(07))) \times (-6)) \\
 67074 &:= (F((4 + F(7))) \times (07 \times 6)) \\
 67087 &:= (F(7) - ((F(F(8)) + F(F(07))) \times (-6))) \\
 67158 &:= -(((F(F(8)) - ((5 \times 1)^7)) + F(F(6))) \\
 67176 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(7)) + 17))) \times 6) \\
 67179 &:= ((((-9) + F(7)) + 1)^7) - F(F(F(6))) \\
 67188 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(8) \times (1 - F(7)))) \times 6) \\
 67273 &:= (-F(((F(3) \times F(7)) - F(2))) - (-F(7)) \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 67278 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + F((2 + 7))) \times 6) \\
 67329 &:= (((F(9)/2)^{F(3)}) \times F(F(7))) - F(6) \\
 67347 &:= (((F((F(7) + 4))) \times F(3)) + (F(7))) \times F(F(6)) \\
 67357 &:= (((F(F(7)) + 5)^{F(3)}) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 67361 &:= ((-1) \times (F(F(6))^3) + (7 \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 67362 &:= F(2) - F(F(6))^3 + 7 \times F(F(F(6))) \\
 67363 &:= F(3) - F(F(6))^3 + 7 \times F(F(F(6))) \\
 67364 &:= F(4) - F(F(6))^3 + 7 \times F(F(F(6))) \\
 67384 &:= ((4^8) - ((F(3) - F(F(7))) \times F(6))) \\
 67392 &:= ((2 + F(9)) \times ((F(F(3)) + F(F(7))) \times F(6))) \\
 67398 &:= (8 \times 9)^{F(3)} \times F(7) + 6 \\
 67554 &:= (-((F(4)^5)) \times (-5) - (F(7) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 67565 &:= ((((-5) + F(6))^5) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 67666 &:= (((-F(F(6))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + (F(F(7)) \times F(6))) \\
 67739 &:= ((-9) \times F((3 + F(7)))) + (7 \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 67772 &:= (((2 - F(F(7))) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 67849 &:= (((F(9) + 4) \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(7)))) / 6) \\
 67938 &:= ((F(F(8)) + F(((3 \times 9) - F(7)))) \times 6) \\
 67977 &:= (((F(F(7)) + (7 + 9)) \times F(7)) \times F(F(6)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 67986 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(8) + F(9)) \times 7)) \times 6) \\
 68247 &:= ((-F(7)) + (F(F(4)) \times F((2 + F(8)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 68248 &:= (F((F(8) - F(4))) + ((2 - F(F(8))) \times (-6))) \\
 68252 &:= ((F(25) - F(-((F(2) - F(8)))) - F(6)) \\
 68274 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times (7 + F((2 + F(8)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 68286 &:= (((-6) + (F(8)^2)) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 68328 &:= (((-((F(8)^2)) - F(F(3))) - F(F(8))) \times (-6)) \\
 68376 &:= (((F(6) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(3))) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 68397 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (F((9 + 3)) \times F(8))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 68464 &:= (-((F(4)^{F(6)})) + F((-4) + F(8) + F(6))) \\
 68467 &:= (7 \times ((F(F(6)) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 8))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 68471 &:= (-1) + (((F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 68472 &:= (((F((F(2) \times F(7))) \times F(F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 68473 &:= F(F(3)) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 68474 &:= F(F(4)) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 68476 &:= ((-((F(F(6)) - F(F(7)))) \times F(-((F(4) - F(8)))) / F(6)) \\
 68497 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-9) + (F(F(4))^8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 68537 &:= (7 \times ((F((F(3) \times 5)) \times (-F(8))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 68628 &:= (((82 \times 6) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 68671 &:= (F(17) \times ((F(6) \times 8) - F(F(6)))) \\
 68748 &:= (((8^{F(4)}) + F((F(7) + 8))) \times 6) \\
 68796 &:= (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(7) \times F(8) \times 6) \\
 68894 &:= (F(4)^9 \times F(8) + F(8)) / 6) \\
 68947 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times ((F(4) + F(9)) \times 8)) - F(F(6))) \\
 68978 &:= (((F(8) \times F(F(7))) + F(9)) \times (8 + 6)) \\
 69336 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + F(((3 + 3) + 9))) \times 6) \\
 69552 &:= ((F(-((F(2) - ((5 \times 5)))) \times (-9)) / (-6)) \\
 69579 &:= (9 \times (((F(F(7)) - 5) \times F(9)) - F(F(6)))) \\
 69624 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) - ((2^{F(6)}) \times F(9))) \times (-F(6))) \\
 69626 &:= -6 + 2^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6) \\
 69631 &:= -1 + F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6) \\
 69632 &:= (F(2) \times F(3))^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6) \\
 69633 &:= F(F(3)) + F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6) \\
 69634 &:= F(F(4)) + F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6) \\
 69638 &:= 8 \times F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(9) + 6) \\
 69653 &:= (((F(3)^{5+6}) \times F(9)) + F(F(6))) \\
 69667 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - (-6) - (F(9) \times F(6)))) \\
 69696 &:= (F(6) \times F(9) - F(6))^{F(9-6)} \\
 69727 &:= (7 \times ((2 - F((7 + 9))) + F(F(F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 69768 &:= ((F(8) + (6)) \times F((F((F(7) - 9)) \times 6))) \\
 69836 &:= (-((F(F(6)) + F((F(3) + F(8)))) - (-9) \times F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 69857 &:= (-F(((7 - 5) + F(8)))) - (-9) \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 69863 &:= -((F((F(3) + F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(8)) \times 9) + (6)))) \\
 69875 &:= (-5) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (F(8) - F(9))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 69938 &:= (-F((F(8) + F(3)))) + (9 \times (9 + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 69956 &:= 6^5 \times 9 - F(9) + 6 \\
 69972 &:= (F(2 \times 7) - F(9)) \times F(9) \times 6 \\
 69984 &:= F(4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6 \\
 70844 &:= (4 \times F((F(F(F(4))) + F((8 + (0 \times 7)))))) \\
 71065 &:= ((5 \times (60 + 1)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 71136 &:= (((F(F(F(6)))/(-F(3))) + 1) \times (-1) \times F(7)) \\
 71149 &:= ((F(F(F((9 - F(4)))))/(-1 + 1)) \times (-F(7))) \\
 71162 &:= (((-2) - F(F(F(6))))/(1 + 1)) \times (-F(7)) \\
 71266 &:= ((-F(6) + ((F(F(F(6)))/(-2) - 1)) \times (-F(7))) \\
 71297 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(9))^2) + (1 + 7)) \\
 71564 &:= -F(4)^{F(6)} + (5 \times 1)^7 \\
 71736 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((-3) \times F(F(7))) + 1) \times 7) \\
 71764 &:= ((4 \times (6 + 71)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 71997 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (-((F(9) + F(9))) + F((1 + F(7)))))) \\
 72268 &:= ((F(F(8)) - 622) \times 7) \\
 72384 &:= F(4) \times 8^{F(3)} \times F(2 \times 7) \\
 72666 &:= (6 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((-6) + F(2)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 72696 &:= ((6 \times ((9 \times 6) - 2)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 72828 &:= (((F(8) \times F((F(2) + 8)))^2)/7) \\
 72893 &:= -F(3) + (F(9) \times 8)^2 + 7 \\
 72929 &:= (((F(9) + F(2)) \times 9) - 2) \times F(F(7)) \\
 72946 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + (4))) - (9 \times (-2) + F(F(7)))) \\
 72999 &:= 9 \times (-9 \times 9 + 2^{F(7)}) \\
 73284 &:= (4 \times (F((F(8) + F(2))) + F((F(3) + F(7)))))) \\
 73341 &:= ((F((14 \times F(3))) \times (-3))/(-F(7))) \\
 73367 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(3)) + (-F(3)) \times F(F(7)))))) \\
 73389 &:= (((F(9) + 8)^3) - (3 \times F(F(7)))) \\
 73395 &:= (((5 \times F(F((9 - 3)))) \times 3) \times F(F(7))) \\
 73459 &:= ((F((F(9) - (5))) - ((4^{F(3)}))/7) \\
 73539 &:= -9 \times (F(3 + 5) - F(3)^{F(7)}) \\
 73644 &:= -((F((F(4) \times F(4))) \times (F(F(6)) - (3^7))) \\
 73645 &:= (F((5^{F(F(4))})) + (-6) \times (-3) + F(F(7)))) \\
 73674 &:= (-4 + F(7)) \times (-6 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \\
 73719 &:= 9 \times (-1^7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \\
 73724 &:= -4 + 2^{F(7)} \times (F(3) + 7) \\
 73728 &:= (8 \times 2 - 7) \times F(3)^{F(7)} \\
 73729 &:= ((9 \times (2^{F(7)})) + (F(F(3))^{F(F(7))})) \\
 73736 &:= F(6) + F(3)^{F(7)} \times (F(3) + 7) \\
 73739 &:= 9 \times F(3)^{F(7)} - F(3) + F(7) \\
 73749 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(4))^{F(7)})) + (3 \times 7)) \\
 73791 &:= 1 \times 9 \times (7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \\
 73792 &:= F(2) - (9 \times (-7) - (F(3)^{F(7)})) \\
 73793 &:= F(3) - (9 \times (-7) - (F(3)^{F(7)})) \\
 73794 &:= F(4) - (9 \times (-7) - (F(3)^{F(7)})) \\
 73794 &:= F(4) + 9 \times (7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \\
 73864 &:= (-4) + ((6 \times F(F(8))) + (F(3)^{F(7)})) \\
 73868 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 6) + (F(F((8/F(3))))^{F(7)})) \\
 73889 &:= ((F(9) + ((F(8) + F(8))^3)) - F(F(7))) \\
 73892 &:= ((2 \times 98) \times F((F(3) \times 7))) \\
 73896 &:= -((F(F(6)) + (-9) \times (F(8) + (F(3)^{F(7)})))) \\
 73961 &:= (F(F((1 + 6))) + (9 \times (F(3)^{F(7)})) \\
 73967 &:= (F(F(7)) + (6 - (-9) \times (F(3)^{F(7)})) \\
 73971 &:= ((1 + 7) \times F(9))^{F(3)} - F(7) \\
 73975 &:= (-5) \times (F(F(7)) - ((F(9)^{F(3)}) \times F(7))) \\
 73977 &:= (((F((-7) + F(7))) \times F(9))^{F(3)} - (7)) \\
 73982 &:= (-2) + ((8 \times F(9))^{F(F(-3+7))}) \\
 73983 &:= (-F(F(3))) + ((8 \times F(9))^{F(F(-3+7))}) \\
 73984 &:= (-4 + F(8)) \times F(9) \times F(3)^7 \\
 73991 &:= ((-1 + 9) \times F(9))^{F(3)} + 7 \\
 73997 &:= (7 \times F(9) + F(9))^{F(3)} + F(7) \\
 74088 &:= (F(8) + F(8))^{-04+7} \\
 74096 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (-90) + F(F(4)))/(-F(7))) \\
 74324 &:= (((42^3) + F(4)) + F(F(7))) \\
 74325 &:= ((F((5^2)) - F(F(3))) - (F(4) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 74326 &:= (F(((6 - F(2))^{F(3)})) - (F(4) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 74335 &:= (F((5^{F(3)})) - (3 \times (-F(4) + F(F(7)))) \\
 74349 &:= (-9) + (F((F(4)^{F(3)})) \times (F(4)^7)) \\
 74358 &:= F((8 - 5) \times 3) \times F(4)^7 \\
 74366 &:= F(6) + F(6 + 3) \times F(4)^7 \\
 74382 &:= ((F(-(F(2) - F(8)))) - 3) \times (4 + 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74391 &:= (-1) - (-F(9) \times (F(F(3)) + ((F(4)^7)))) \\
 74392 &:= ((F(2) \times F(9)) \times (F(F(3)) + ((F(4)^7))) \\
 74393 &:= F(F(3)) + F(9) \times (F(F(3)) + F(4)^7) \\
 74394 &:= F(F(4)) + F(9) \times (F(F(3)) + F(4)^7) \\
 74415 &:= F(5 \times 1 \times 4) \times (4 + 7) \\
 74426 &:= (F((F(6) + F(2))) \times (F(F(4)) + ((F(4)^7))) \\
 74448 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(F(F(4)))) + F(4)) \times (4 + 7)) \\
 74487 &:= (7 \times (((F(8) + F(F(F(4))))^{F(4)} - 7)) \\
 74492 &:= -2 + F(9) \times (4 + F(4)^7) \\
 74493 &:= -((F(F(3)) - (F(9) \times (4 + (F(4)^7)))) \\
 74494 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times (F(9) \times (4 + (F(4)^7))) \\
 74528 &:= (F((8 + F(2))) \times (5 + (F(4)^7))) \\
 74536 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times F((F(3) + (5))))^{F(F(4))}) + (7)) \\
 74557 &:= -((((F(F(7)) - (F((5 \times 5)))) + F(F(4))) + F(F(7)))) \\
 74564 &:= (F((4 + F(F(6)))) - (-5 + (F(F(4)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 74567 &:= (-((F(F(7)) - F(6))) + F((5^{F(F(4))})) - F(F(7))) \\
 74568 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((5^{F(4)}) \times F(7)))) \\
 74572 &:= (((-2) \times F(F(7))) + F((5^{F(F(4))})) + F(7)) \\
 74627 &:= (7 \times (((F(2) + F(F(6)))^{F(4)} + (F(7)))) \\
 74641 &:= ((-F(14)) + F((F(F(6)) + (4)))) - 7) \\
 74644 &:= ((-4) + F((4 + F(F(6)))) - F((F(F(4)) \times 7))) \\
 74646 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F(F(6)))) \times (4 + 7)) \\
 74648 &:= (F((F(8) + (4))) - (F(((6 - 4) \times 7)))) \\
 74665 &:= (5 \times (F(F(6)) + (64 \times F(F(7)))) \\
 74666 &:= (((-6) \times F(F(6))) + F((F(F(6)) + (4)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 74676 &:= (((F(F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) \times F(F(4))) \times 7) \\
 74688 &:= (8 \times ((F(F(8)) - F((F(F(6)) - (4)))) - F(7))) \\
 74719 &:= F(9) \times (1 + F(7)^{F(4)}) - F(7) \\
 74736 &:= (((F(6)^3) + (7)) \times F(-((F(F(F(4)) - F(7)))) \\
 74739 &:= ((F(9) \times (F(F(3)) + (F(7)^{F(4)}))) + (7)) \\
 74745 &:= (F((5^{F(F(4))})) - (F(F(7)) + 47)) \\
 74752 &:= F(25) - F(7) \times F(4) \times 7 \\
 74761 &:= (-1) + (((F(F(6)) \times F(7))^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(7))) \\
 74762 &:= (((F((2 + 6)) \times F(7))^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(7))) \\
 74763 &:= F(F(3)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(7))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(7)) \\
 74764 &:= F(F(4)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(7))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(7)) \\
 74784 &:= (((F((4 + F(8))) - F(F(7))) - F(F(F(4)))) - 7) \\
 74786 &:= ((-6) + F(((8 + F(7)) + (4)))) - F(F(7)) \\
 74788 &:= (F(F(8)) - (((F(8) \times F(7)) + F(F(F(4)))) \times (-F(F(7))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74789 &:= ((F(((9) + F(8)) + F(7))) - F(4)) - F(F(7)) \\
 74791 &:= ((-1) + F(((F(9) - F(7)) + (4)))) - F(F(7)) \\
 74792 &:= (F(-(2 - (9 \times (7 - 4)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 74793 &:= F(F(3)) + F(F(9) - F(7) + 4) - F(F(7)) \\
 74794 &:= F(F(4)) + F(F(9) - F(7) + 4) - F(F(7)) \\
 74795 &:= -5 + F(9) \times (F(7) + F(4)^7) \\
 74796 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + (-9) + F(7))) + (4 - F(F(7)))) \\
 74798 &:= (-F(F(8))) - ((-9) + F((7 \times F(F(4)))) \times (-F(F(7)))) \\
 74799 &:= (((F((F(9) - 9)) - F(F(7))) \times F(F(F(4)))) + 7) \\
 74826 &:= ((F((F(6) + F(2))) + F((F(8) + (4)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 74844 &:= (((4^4) - F(F(8))) - F(F(4))) \times (-7) \\
 74847 &:= ((F((F(7) - F(4))) + F((F(8) + (4)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 74855 &:= ((F((5 \times 5)) + (F(8) \times F(4))) - F(F(7))) \\
 74857 &:= (((F(7) \times 5) + F((F(8) + (4)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 74864 &:= (F((4 + F(F(6)))) - ((F(8) + F(F(4))) \times 7)) \\
 74867 &:= (-F(7)) \times (((F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + F(F(4))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 74874 &:= -((F(-((F(F(F(4)) - F(7)))) - ((F((F(8) + (4))) - (7)))) \\
 74878 &:= -F(8) \times 7 + F(8 \times 4 - 7) \\
 74884 &:= (F((4 + F(8))) - (F((8 \times F(F(4))))/7)) \\
 74886 &:= (((-6) \times F(8)) + F((F(8) + (4)))) - (F(7)) \\
 74894 &:= (((F(4) \times F(9)) + F((F(8) + (4)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 74897 &:= (F(((F(7) - 9) + F(8))) - (F(F(4))^7)) \\
 74899 &:= (F((F(9) - 9)) - ((F(8) - F(4)) \times 7)) \\
 74935 &:= (F((5^{F(3)})) - (9 \times (F(4) + (7)))) \\
 74936 &:= F(6 \times 3) \times (9 \times 4 - 7) \\
 74938 &:= ((F(F(8))/F(-((F(3) - 9)))) \times F((4 + 7))) \\
 74944 &:= (-((F(4)^4)) + F(((9 + F(4)) + F(7)))) \\
 74945 &:= (-5) \times ((F(4) - (F(9)^{F(F(4))})) \times F(7)) \\
 74948 &:= (F((F(8) + (4))) - ((9 + F(F(4))) \times 7)) \\
 74952 &:= F(25) - F(9) - F(4) \times F(7) \\
 74955 &:= (F((5 \times 5)) - ((9 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 7)) \\
 74956 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (5 + F((9 + 4)))) \times 7) \\
 74964 &:= (F((4 + F(F(6)))) - (9 + (4 \times F(7)))) \\
 74968 &:= (F((F(8) - (6))) + (F(9) \times (F(4)^7))) \\
 74973 &:= (F(((3 + F(7)) + 9)) - (4 \times F(7))) \\
 74977 &:= (((-F(F(7))) + F(-((F(7) - F(9)))) - F(F(4))) \times 7) \\
 74978 &:= (F(((F(8) + F(7)) - 9)) - 47) \\
 74983 &:= (-((F(3) \times F(8))) + F(((9 + F(4)) + F(7)))) \\
 74984 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(8)) - (F((9 + 4)))) \times (-7)) \\
 74985 &:= (-((5 \times 8)) + F(((9 + F(4)) + F(7))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$74986 := (F((F(6) + ((8 + 9)))) - ((F(4) \times F(7))))$$

$$74991 := ((-1) \times F(9)) + F(((9 + F(4)) + F(7)))$$

$$74992 := F(2) - F(9) + F(9 + F(4)) + F(7)$$

$$74993 := F(3) - F(9) + F(9 + F(4)) + F(7)$$

$$74994 := F(4) - F(9) + F(9 + F(4)) + F(7)$$

$$74996 := ((-F(6)) + F((F(9) - 9))) - (F(4) \times 7)$$

$$74997 := F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7$$

$$74998 := (((-F(8)) + F((F(9) - 9))) + F(F(F(4)))) - 7$$

$$74999 := (F((F(9) - 9)) - ((9 + 4) + F(7)))$$

$$75012 := F(2 \times 10 + 5) - F(7)$$

$$75018 := (F((F(8) - ((1 - 05)))) - (7))$$

$$75023 := -F(3) + F(2^{05} - 7)$$

$$75024 := -((F(F(F(4))) - (F(((2^{05}) - 7))))$$

$$75025 := F(5^{2 \times 0 - 5 + 7})$$

$$75026 := -6 + F(20 + 5) + 7$$

$$75029 := -9 + F(20 + 5) + F(7)$$

$$75031 := -1 + F(30 - 5) + 7$$

$$75032 := F((2 + 3) \times 05) + 7$$

$$75033 := F(F(3)) + F(30 - 5) + 7$$

$$75034 := -4 + F(30 - 5) + F(7)$$

$$75038 := F((8 - 3) \times 05) + F(7)$$

$$75046 := (F(F(6)) + F((-40) + (5 \times F(7))))$$

$$75059 := F(9) + F(5^{-05+7})$$

$$75169 := (F(((F(9) - F(6)) - 1)) + (F((5 + 7))))$$

$$75224 := -(((F((F(4)^2)) - F(25)) - F(F(7))))$$

$$75236 := -(((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))) - F(25)) - F(F(7)))$$

$$75237 := ((-((7 \times 3)) + F(25)) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75238 := (((-F(8)) + F(F(3))) + F(25)) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75242 := ((-((2^4)) + F(25)) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75245 := (F((5^{F(F(4))})) + (F(F((2 + 5))) - (F(7))))$$

$$75246 := (-(((F(6) + (4)) - F(25))) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75247 := (F(F(7)) - ((4 - F(25)) + (7)))$$

$$75248 := (((-8) - F(F(4))) + F(25)) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75249 := ((-9) + F(((4 - F(2)) \times (-5)))) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75252 := (((F(25) - F(2)) - (5)) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75253 := ((F(F(3)) \times (-5) + F(25)) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75254 := ((-4) + F(((5 \times F(2)) \times 5))) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75255 := ((F((5 \times 5)) + ((2 - 5))) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75256 := -(((F((F(6) - (5))) - F(25)) - F(F(7))))$$

$$75257 := ((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) - F(-((5 - 7)))$$

$$75258 := F(8 + 5) + F(2^5 - 7)$$

$$75259 := (F(F(F((9 - 5)))) + (F(25) + F(F(7))))$$

$$75262 := ((-((2 - 6)) + F(25)) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75263 := (((-3) + F(6)) + F(25)) + F(F(7))$$

$$75264 := -(((F(F(4)) - ((F(6) + F(25)))) - F(F(7))))$$

$$75265 := (F((5 + F(6))) + ((F(25) + (7))))$$

$$75266 := ((F(6) + F(((6 - F(2)) \times 5))) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75271 := (F(F((1 \times 7))) + ((F(25) + F(7))))$$

$$75272 := F(2) + F(F(7)) + F(25) + F(7)$$

$$75273 := F(3) + F(F(7)) + F(25) + F(7)$$

$$75274 := F(4) + F(F(7)) + F(25) + F(7)$$

$$75276 := ((F((6 + F(7))) + F(2)) \times (5 + F(7)))$$

$$75279 := ((F(9) + F(F(7))) + ((F(25) - F(7))))$$

$$75291 := (((-1) + F(9)) + F(25)) + F(F(7))$$

$$75292 := (((F(2) \times F(9)) + F(25)) + F(F(7)))$$

$$75293 := F(F(3)) + F(9) + F(25) + F(F(7))$$

$$75294 := F(F(4)) + F(9) + F(25) + F(F(7))$$

$$75348 := ((F((8 \times F(4)))/(-3 + 5)) \times (-F(7)))$$

$$75366 := ((6 + F((F(F(6)) - F(3)))) \times (5 + F(7)))$$

$$75376 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(7)) - F((F(3) \times 5)))) \times 7)$$

$$75457 := ((7 \times F(F((5 + F(4)))) - (5 \times F(F(7))))$$

$$75466 := ((F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) + F((4 + F((-5) + F(7))))$$

$$75492 := (((2 + F(9)) \times (4 + 5)) \times F(F(7)))$$

$$75536 := -F(6 \times 3) - 5 + 5^7$$

$$75546 := -((F((6 \times F(4))) - ((5 + (5^7))))$$

$$75625 := ((5 \times F((2 + F(6))))^{-5+7})$$

$$75628 := (((F(F(8)) + F((-2) + F(F(6)))) \times 5) - 7)$$

$$75635 := (F((5^{F(3)})) + F((-6) + F((-5) + F(7))))$$

$$75636 := ((F(F(6)) + F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) \times (5 + F(7)))$$

$$75648 := (F((F(8) + (4))) + (F((6 + 5) \times 7))$$

$$75649 := (((-F((9 + F(4)))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (5)) \times 7$$

$$75685 := (-5) \times (8 - (65 \times F(F(7))))$$

$$75725 := ((5 \times F((F(2) \times F(7)))) \times (5 \times F(7)))$$

$$75735 := (-5) \times (-F(3) - (F(F(7)) \times (5 \times F(7))))$$

$$75745 := (-5) \times (-4 - (F(F(7)) \times (5 \times F(7))))$$

$$75759 := (F(9) + ((5 \times F(F(7))) \times (5 \times F(7))))$$

$$75765 := (-5) \times (-F(6) - (F(F(7)) \times (5 \times F(7))))$$

$$75768 := ((F(F(8)) - (F((F(6) + (7)))/5)) \times 7)$$

$$75866 := (-F(F(6))) + ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(8) \times (-5))) \times 7)$$

$$75884 := (-F(4)) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(8) \times (-5))) \times 7)$$

- 75887 := ((7 × F(F(8))) − (F(8) × (5 × 7)))
- 75936 := ((F(F(F(6))) − (3 + 95)) × 7)
- 75937 := −F(7)³ + 9 + 5⁷
- 75957 := ((F(F((F(7) − (5)))) − (95)) × 7)
- 75964 := (((F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) − (95)) × 7)
- 75983 := −3 × F(8) × F(9) + 5⁷
- 76076 := (((6 × F(7)) − F(F(F(06)))) × (−7))
- 76083 := (((3 − 80) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76139 := ((−(((F(9) × F(3)) + 1)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76146 := ((F(F(F(6))) − (F(F(4)) × F((1 + F(6)))) × 7)
- 76167 := (((F(7) × (6 − 1)) − F(F(F(6)))) × (−7))
- 76174 := (((F(F(4))^{7−1}) − F(F(F(6)))) × (−7))
- 76179 := (−(((F(9) × F(7)) + 1)) + (F(F(F(6))) × 7))
- 76188 := (−((F(8) × F(8))) + ((−(1) − F(F(F(6)))) × (−7)))
- 76237 := ((−(F((7 + 3))) + F(F((2 + 6)))) × 7)
- 76244 := (((F(4)^{F(4)}) × 2) − F(F(F(6)))) × (−7))
- 76245 := (F((5^{F(F(4))})) − (−(2) × F((F(6) + (7))))))
- 76247 := (−(((F((7 × F(F(4)))) − 2) − (F(F(F(6))) × 7)))
- 76251 := ((−((1 + 52)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76254 := (−(4) + ((−(52) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7))
- 76258 := ((F(F(8)) − 52) × (−(6) + F(7)))
- 76259 := (−(F((9 + 5))) + ((−(2) − F(F(F(6)))) × (−7)))
- 76272 := ((−((F(2) + ((7²)))) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76279 := (((F(9) + F(7)) + 2) − F(F(F(6)))) × (−7))
- 76286 := ((−((6 × 8)) + F(F((2 + 6)))) × 7)
- 76297 := (−((F(F(7)) + (92))) + (F(F(F(6))) × 7))
- 76314 := ((−((41 + 3)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76328 := (((F(8) − F(F((2³)))) + F(F(6))) × (−7))
- 76334 := (−((F((4 × 3)) × F(3))) + (F(F(F(6))) × 7))
- 76347 := (−(F(F(7))) + ((F(F((4 × F(3)))) − 6) × 7))
- 76349 := ((−(((9 × 4) + 3)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76356 := (((F(6) × (−5)) + F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76363 := (((−(3) + F(F(F(6)))) − F((3 + 6))) × 7)
- 76364 := (−(((F(F(4))^{F(6)}) + F(3))) + (F(F(F(6))) × 7))
- 76365 := (−(5) − ((F(F(F(6))) − 36) × (−7)))
- 76366 := (−(((F(6) + F(6))^{F(3)})) + (F(F(F(6))) × 7))
- 76367 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) − (((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))) + F(F(7))))))
- 76368 := (((F(F(8)) × F(F(6)))/3) − F(F(6))) − F(F(7)))
- 76373 := ((−(F(3)) − F(F(7))) + ((−(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7))
- 76374 := (−(((F(F(F(4))) + F(F(7))) − ((−(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)))
- 76376 := (((F(F(F(6))) × 7) − F((F(F(3)) + (6)))) − F(F(7)))
- 76377 := (((−(7) × (7 − F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76378 := (((F(F(8)) × 7) − (3 + F(6))) − F(F(7)))
- 76379 := (((−(9) − F(F(7))) − F(F(3))) + (F(F(F(6))) × 7))
- 76382 := (−(2) − ((F(F(8)) − F((3 + 6))) × (−7)))
- 76383 := −((F(F(3)) + ((F(F(8)) − F((3 + 6))) × (−7)))
- 76384 := (((F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) − 36) × 7)
- 76386 := (((6 × F(F(8))) − 3) + F(F(F(6)))) − F(F(7)))
- 76387 := ((7 × F(F(8))) − (F(3) + F((6 + 7))))
- 76388 := (((8 × F(F(8))) − F(F(3))) − F(F(F(6)))) − F(F(7)))
- 76389 := (((−(9) + (8 × F(3))) × F(F(F(6)))) − F(F(7)))
- 76391 := (((1 − F(9)) + F(F((F(3) + (6)))) × 7)
- 76392 := F(2) + (−F(9) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76393 := F(3) + (−F(9) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76394 := F(4) + (−F(9) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76396 := (−((F(−((F(F(6)) − F(9)))) − ((F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)))
- 76397 := ((7 × F(F(F(9 − 3)))) + (F(6) − F(F(7))))
- 76398 := F(8) × F(9) × (3 + F(6) × F(7))
- 76399 := (−(F(9)) + ((−((9 × 3)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7))
- 76406 := (−((6^{F(04)})) + (F(F(F(6))) × 7))
- 76417 := (−(F(F(7))) + (((1 × 4) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7))
- 76419 := ((−((F(9) − (1 + 4))) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76423 := (F((F(F(3)) + 24)) − (−(6) × F(F(7))))
- 76424 := (−(4) × ((2 + (−(4) × F(F(6)))) × F(F(7))))
- 76425 := ((F((5²)) + F(F(4))) − (−(6) × F(F(7))))
- 76426 := (((F(6) − F(2)) × (−4)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76432 := (−(F(2)) + ((−((3^{F(4)})) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7))
- 76433 := (((−((3 × 3)) × F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76434 := (F(F(F(4))) + ((−((3^{F(4)})) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7))
- 76447 := (((F((7 × F(4))) − (4)) − F(F(6))) × 7)
- 76453 := (−((F((F(3) + (5)))^{F(F(4))})) + (F(F(F(6))) × 7))
- 76454 := ((F(F((F(4) + (5)))) − (4 × 6)) × 7)
- 76457 := (−(F((7 + 5))) + ((−(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7))
- 76459 := ((F(9) × (−5)) − ((F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) × (−7)))
- 76461 := ((F(F(F(1 × 6)))) − (F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))) × 7)
- 76462 := F(2) + (F(F(F(6))) − F(F(4)) − F(F(6))) × 7)
- 76463 := F(3) + (F(F(F(6))) − F(F(4)) − F(F(6))) × 7)
- 76464 := F(4) + (F(F(F(6))) − F(F(4)) − F(F(6))) × 7)
- 76467 := (F(7) + ((F(F(F(6))) − (4 × 6)) × 7))
- 76468 := ((F(F(8)) − F(F(6))) + (((4^{F(6)}) + (7))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 76469 &:= (-F(9) + ((F(F(F(6))) - (-4 + F(F(6)))) \times 7)) \\
 76471 &:= (-F((-1) + F(7))) + ((F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76473 &:= (-F(3) + ((F((7 \times F(4))) - F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76474 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times (-74)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76475 &:= ((F(F(((5 + 7) - 4))) - F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76476 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-7 - ((4^{F(6)}) - F(7)))) \\
 76478 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 7) + F((F(4) + F(6)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 76481 &:= ((-1) + F(F(8))) + (4^{F(F(6))-F(7)}) \\
 76482 &:= (((2 \times 8)^4) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 76483 &:= ((F(F(3)) + F(F(8))) + (4^{F(F(6))-F(7)})) \\
 76484 &:= (((4^8) + F(F(4))) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 76486 &:= ((F(6) - F((8 + 4))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76488 &:= (-8) + ((F(F(8)) - (F(4) \times 6)) \times 7) \\
 76489 &:= (((-9) + F(F(8))) - (4 + 6)) \times 7) \\
 76493 &:= (-3) + (((-9) \times F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76494 &:= (-F(F(4))) + (((-9) \times F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76496 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (9 \times F(F(4)))) \times (-6) + F(7)) \\
 76498 &:= (F(F(8)) + (9 + ((4^{F(6)}) + (7)))) \\
 76499 &:= ((-F(9)) - F((9 + F(F(4)))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76514 &:= (-F(4) + ((-15) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76517 &:= (-7) \times (15 - F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 76518 &:= (-F(F(8))) - (-F((1 + 5)) \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(7))) \\
 76524 &:= (((-4) + (2 \times 5)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76531 &:= (((-1) \times F((F(3) + (5)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76532 &:= F(2) + (-F(F(3) + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76533 &:= F(3) + (-F(F(3) + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76534 &:= F(4) + (-F(F(3) + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76538 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (((3 - 5) \times 6))) \times 7) \\
 76539 &:= (-F(9) - (((F(3) + (5))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76542 &:= (-((2^4) \times 5)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76545 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(4)))) - (5 + 6)) \times 7) \\
 76546 &:= (-6) + (((F(F(4)) \times (-5)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76547 &:= (((F(7) + F(F(4))) \times (-5)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76549 &:= (-((F(9) + (4))) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76551 &:= (-1) + (((-5) + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76552 &:= (((F(2) \times (-5 + 5)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76553 &:= F(F(3)) + (-5 - 5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76554 &:= F(F(4)) + (-5 - 5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76558 &:= (F(F(8)) + (((5^5) \times F(F(6))) - (F(7)))) \\
 76559 &:= ((-9) + F(F(F(((5 - 5) + 6)))) \times 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76562 &:= (-((2 \times 6) \times 5)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76563 &:= ((-3) \times F(6)) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76564 &:= (-((F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76566 &:= ((-F(6)) + F(((F(6) + (5)) + F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76567 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F(((5) + F(6) + (7)))) \\
 76572 &:= ((-2) - F(7)) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76573 &:= (((-F(F(3))) + F(F((F(7) - (5)))) - 6) \times 7) \\
 76574 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) \times (-F(7))) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76575 &:= (-5) + ((F(F((F(7) - (5)))) - 6) \times 7) \\
 76578 &:= ((F(8) - (F(7) \times 5)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76581 &:= (-((1 + (8 \times 5))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76582 &:= ((F(2) \times (-8 \times 5)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76583 &:= (-((3 \times (8 + 5))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76584 &:= (-F(4) + ((F(F(8)) - (5)) \times (-6) + F(7))) \\
 76585 &:= (-F(-((5 - 8))) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76586 &:= ((F(6)/(-8)) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76587 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) - (-5) \times (6 - F(7))) \\
 76588 &:= ((8/8) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76589 &:= ((-F(9)) + F(F((8 - 5))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76592 &:= (-2) + (((-9) - 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76593 &:= (-F(F(3))) + (((-9) - 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76594 &:= ((-4) + F(F(((9 + 5) - 6))) \times 7) \\
 76598 &:= ((-8) \times F((9 - 5))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76599 &:= (-9) + (((-F(F((9 - 5))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76601 &:= (((-F((10 - 6))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76602 &:= (-20) + (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6) + F(7)) \\
 76603 &:= ((F(3) - F(F(06))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76604 &:= ((F(4) \times (0 - 6)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76606 &:= (-((F(6) + F(06))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76607 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(06)))) - (F(6) + (7))) \\
 76608 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(06) - (6))) \times 7) \\
 76609 &:= ((-F(9)) + F(F(06))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76611 &:= (-11) + (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6) + F(7)) \\
 76612 &:= ((2 \times (1 - 6)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76613 &:= (-F(3)) + ((1 - F(F(F(6)))) \times (6 - F(7))) \\
 76614 &:= (-((F(4) - (1 - 6))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76615 &:= ((F(F(F((5 - 1)))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (6 - F(7))) \\
 76616 &:= (-6) + ((1 + 6) \times F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 76617 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) + ((F(6) - F(7)))) \\
 76619 &:= (-((9 \times 1) - 6)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76621 &:= (-1) + ((F(2) + (6)) \times F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 76622 &:= F(22 - 6/6) \times 7 \\
 76623 &:= F(F(3)) + (F(2) + 6) \times F(F(6) + F(7)) \\
 76624 &:= F(F(3)) + (F(2) + 6) \times F(F(6) + F(7)) \\
 76625 &:= (((5 + 2) \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F(6))/7)) \\
 76626 &:= ((6 - 2) + (F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + F(7))) \\
 76627 &:= ((7 \times F(F(2 + 6))) - ((F(6) - F(7)))) \\
 76628 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(2)) \times 6) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 76629 &:= (((9 + F(F(2 + 6))) - F(6)) \times 7) \\
 76631 &:= (((1 \times 3) + 6) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76632 &:= ((F(2) + (3 + 6)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76633 &:= (-3) + ((F(3) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + F(7))) \\
 76634 &:= (-F(F(4))) + ((F(3) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + F(7))) \\
 76635 &:= (((5 + F(3)) \times F(F(F(6)))) + (6 + 7)) \\
 76636 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + F(3)) \times ((6 - 6) + 7)) \\
 76637 &:= ((7 \times F(F((F(3) + (6)))) + (F(6) + (7))) \\
 76638 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(3)) \times F(6)) - F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 76639 &:= ((F(9)/F(3)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6) + F(7))) \\
 76641 &:= ((1 + (F(4) \times 6)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76642 &:= (-F(2)) + ((F(4) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + F(7))) \\
 76643 &:= (((F(F(3)) + F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + F(7))) \\
 76644 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + ((F(4) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + F(7))) \\
 76645 &:= (-5) + ((4 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + F(7))) \\
 76646 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + 4) \times 6) + (F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 76647 &:= (-((F(7) + (4))) + ((-6) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7))) \\
 76648 &:= 8 \times (F(4))^6 + F(6) \times F(7) \\
 76649 &:= ((F((F(9)/F(F(4)))) \times (F(6) \times 6)) - 7) \\
 76651 &:= (-((1 - (5 \times 6))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76652 &:= ((F(2) \times (5 \times 6)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76653 &:= F(F(3)) + 5 \times 6 + F(F(F(6))) \times 7 \\
 76654 &:= F(F(4)) + 5 \times 6 + F(F(F(6))) \times 7 \\
 76655 &:= (((5 \times 5) + F(6)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76656 &:= (((F(6) \times 5) - (6)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76657 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((56 \times 6) - 7)) \\
 76659 &:= (((9 \times 5) - F(6)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76662 &:= (-2) + ((-6) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (6 - F(7))) \\
 76663 &:= (-F(F(3))) + ((-6) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (6 - F(7))) \\
 76664 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) + 6) \times (6 + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 76665 &:= (((-5) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(7) \\
 76666 &:= ((F(6) - (6)) + ((-6) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76667 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 6)) + (F(F(6))/7)) \\
 76669 &:= ((F((9 + F(6))) \times (F(6) \times 6)) + (F(7))) \\
 76671 &:= (((-1) + F((F(7) + F(6)))) + F(6)) \times 7 \\
 76672 &:= F(2) + (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\
 76673 &:= F(3) + (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\
 76674 &:= F(4) + (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\
 76676 &:= -((F((F(F(6))/7)) - ((-F(6)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7))) \\
 76677 &:= (F(7) + ((F((F(7) + F(6))) + (6)) \times 7)) \\
 76678 &:= (F(8 + 7 + 6) + F(6)) \times 7 \\
 76679 &:= (-F(9)) + ((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (6 - F(7))) \\
 76682 &:= ((2 + 8) \times 6) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76683 &:= (-((3 - 8)) + ((-F(6)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76684 &:= (-((4^8)) + ((6 - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 76685 &:= (((-5) + F(F(8))) + (F(6) + (6))) \times 7 \\
 76686 &:= (((-F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(6))) - F((F(6) + F(7))) \\
 76687 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) + ((-F(6)) \times F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) \\
 76689 &:= (((-9) - F(F(8))) \times (-6) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(7) \\
 76692 &:= ((F(2) + 9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + F(7) \\
 76693 &:= (-((F(F(3)) + (-9) \times F(6))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76694 &:= ((-4) + F(9)) + ((-6) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76697 &:= ((F(7) \times 9) + ((6 - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76698 &:= (-8) + (((-9) + F(F(6))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76699 &:= (((9 + F((9 - 6))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76711 &:= (F(11) + (7 \times F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 76712 &:= (-F(2)) + ((F((1 \times 7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76713 &:= (((F((3 - 1)) \times F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76714 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + ((F((1 \times 7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76715 &:= (-5) + (((1 + F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76717 &:= (F((F(7) - 1)) - ((-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76718 &:= ((8 \times (-1) + F(7)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76732 &:= (-2) + (((3 + F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76733 &:= (-F(F(3))) + (((3 + F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76734 &:= (((4^{F(3)}) + F((F(7) + F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76736 &:= ((F(F(6)) + F(3)) + ((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76737 &:= (-((F(7) - (F(3)^7))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76739 &:= ((F(9) \times F(3)) + ((-7) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76741 &:= (((1 \times 4) + F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\
 76742 &:= F(2) + (4 + F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\
 76743 &:= F(3) + (4 + F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\
 76744 &:= F(4) + (4 + F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76745 &:= ((-5) + (F(F(4))^7) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76747 &:= (F(7) + (((F(4) + F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7)) \\
 76748 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (((4 - 7) \times 6))) \times 7) \\
 76749 &:= ((9 \times 4) + ((-F(7) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7))) \\
 76752 &:= (((2 \times 5) \times F(7)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76756 &:= (F(6) + (((5 + F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7)) \\
 76758 &:= ((-8) + F((5 + 7))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76762 &:= (((-F(2)) + F(F(6))) + F((F(7) + F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76763 &:= ((F((F(3) \times F(6)))/7) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76764 &:= (((F(F(F(4))) + 6) \times (-F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) \\
 76765 &:= (((5 + 6) \times F(7)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76766 &:= (F((6 + 6)) + (7 \times F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\
 76768 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (6)) \times 7) + ((F(6) \times F(7)))) \\
 76769 &:= ((F(((9 - 6) \times 7)) + F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76773 &:= (F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(7)))) + ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + 7)) \\
 76776 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 7) + ((7 \times F(F(6))) + (7))) \\
 76777 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (F(7))) + ((-F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7)) \\
 76778 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(F(7)) + (7)) \times F(F(6)))) \times F(7)) \\
 76783 &:= (((F(3) + F(8)) + F((F(7) + F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76788 &:= (((-F(8)) - F(F(8))) \times (-7)) + (6 + F(7)) \\
 76789 &:= (((-9) - F(F(8))) \times (-7)) + ((F(6) \times F(7))) \\
 76797 &:= ((F(F(7)) - 9) - ((-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76798 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 9) \times 7) + (6)) + F(F(7)) \\
 76818 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F((1 + 8)) - (6))) \times 7) \\
 76825 &:= (((F((5 + F(2))) + F(F(8))) + F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76826 &:= (F(6) + ((28 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7)) \\
 76827 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((2 + F(F(8))) - (6)) \times 7)) \\
 76829 &:= ((9 \times (2 + F(8))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76834 &:= (((4 + 3) \times F(F(8))) - F(F(6))) + F(F(7)) \\
 76837 &:= ((F(F(7)) - (-3) + F(8)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76839 &:= (((F(9) - 3) + F(F(8))) \times (-6) + F(7)) \\
 76843 &:= (-3) + (((4 \times 8) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76844 &:= (-F(F(4))) + (((4 \times 8) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76846 &:= (((F(6) \times 4) + F(F(8))) \times (-6) + F(7)) \\
 76847 &:= ((F(7))^{F(F(4))}) + ((F(F(8)) + F(6)) \times 7) \\
 76848 &:= (((F((F(8) - F(F(4)))) \times F(8)) - F(F(F(6)))) - 7) \\
 76849 &:= (((9 - F(F(4))) \times F(F(8))) - (6)) + F(F(7)) \\
 76853 &:= F(3 \times 5) \times F(8) \times 6 - (7) \\
 76854 &:= ((4 \times 58) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76855 &:= (((-((5/5) - 8)) \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76857 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(-((5 - 8))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76873 &:= ((F((F(3) + F(7))) \times (F(8) \times 6)) + (F(7))) \\
 76874 &:= (((F(F(4)) + (F(7))) + F(F(8))) + F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76876 &:= ((((-6) + F(7)) \times F(F(8))) + F(F(6))) + F(F(7)) \\
 76878 &:= ((F((F(8)/7))^8) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76887 &:= (((7 \times F(F(8))) - 8) + (F(F(6)) \times F(7))) \\
 76889 &:= ((F((9 + 8)) \times (8 \times 6)) + F(F(7))) \\
 76916 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F((1 \times 9)) + F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76917 &:= ((F(F(7)) - 1) + ((-9) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76918 &:= (F(F((8 - 1))) + ((-9) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7)) \\
 76919 &:= (((F(9) - 1) \times 9) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76923 &:= ((F(F(3)) - ((F(2) + 9)^6))/(-F(7))) \\
 76928 &:= (((8 + F(2)) \times F(9)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76937 &:= (((7 - F(3)) \times 9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76944 &:= (((F(4) \times 4) + F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76946 &:= (((6^{F(F(4))}) \times 9) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76949 &:= (F((9 + F(F(4)))) - ((-F(9)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76958 &:= (F(8) + ((5 \times 9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \\
 76962 &:= (((2 + F(6)) \times F(9)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)) \\
 76965 &:= (((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) + (9 \times 6)) \times 7) \\
 76973 &:= ((F(F(3)) + (F((7 + 9)) \times (-6))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 76978 &:= -8 + F(7 + 9) \times 6 \times F(7) \\
 76986 &:= ((-6) \times F((8 \times F((9 - 6)))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 76987 &:= (-F(7)) + ((F(F(8)) + (9 \times 6)) \times 7) \\
 77128 &:= -((F(F(8)) + ((-F(2)) - F((1 + F(7)))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 77168 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (6 \times F((1 \times 7)))) \times 7) \\
 77238 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(F(3))) + F((-2) + F(7))) \times 7) \\
 77245 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(4)))) + (F((-2) + F(7)))) \times 7) \\
 77266 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((F(F(F(6))) + (F((-2) + F(7)))) \times 7) \\
 77336 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (3 \times F((F(3) + (7)))) \times 7) \\
 77355 &:= (F((5 \times 5)) + ((3 + 7) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 77363 &:= (((3^{F(6)}) + F((F(3) + F(7)))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 77376 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 7) + (F(3) \times F((7 + 7)))) \\
 77384 &:= (-4) \times ((-83) \times F(F(7))) - (7)) \\
 77445 &:= (F((5^{F(F(4))}) + ((F(4)^7) + F(F(7)))) \\
 77478 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F((7 + 4))) \times 7) + F(F(7))) \\
 77484 &:= (4 \times (F(F(8)) + ((F(F(4))^{F(7)}) + F(F(7)))) \\
 77518 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(F(-((1 - 5))))^7)) \times 7) \\
 77589 &:= (((9 \times F(8)) + F((5 + 7))) \times F(F(7))) \\
 77616 &:= ((F(F(6)) + F(16)) \times 77)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77617 &:= (((F((F(7) - 1)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) - F(7)) \\
 77637 &:= (((F((F(7) - F(F(3)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) + 7) \\
 77643 &:= (((F((3 \times 4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) + F(7)) \\
 77651 &:= ((F(F(F((1 + 5)))) + (F(F(6)) \times 7)) \times 7) \\
 77658 &:= (((-85) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) \times 7) \\
 77664 &:= (F((4 + F(F(6)))) + (F((F(F(6)) - (7))) \times 7)) \\
 77686 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (8 \times (6 + F(7)))) \times 7) \\
 77748 &:= (8 - F(4))^7 - F(7 + 7) \\
 77756 &:= F(6) + 5^7 - F(7 + 7) \\
 77784 &:= (((-F(4)) + F(F(8))) + (F(7) \times F(7))) \times 7) \\
 77787 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 7) - F(F(7))) - F(F(7))) \\
 77842 &:= (F((2^4)) - ((F(F(8)) \times (-7)) - F(F(7)))) \\
 77847 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F(F(4))) \times ((8 \times F(7)) + F(F(7)))) \\
 77863 &:= (((F((F(3) \times 6)) + F(F(8))) \times 7) + F(F(7))) \\
 77876 &:= -((F((F(F(6)) - (7))) - ((F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times 7))) \\
 77889 &:= (((F(9) + F(F(8))) + (F(8) \times 7)) \times 7) \\
 77892 &:= (((F(-((2 - 9))) - 8)^7) - F(F(7))) \\
 77896 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times 9) + F(F(8))) - (7)) \times 7) \\
 78123 &:= -F(3) + (-2 - 1 + 8)^7 \\
 78124 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (((-((2 + 1) - 8))^7)))) \\
 78138 &:= (8 - 3)^{-1+8} + F(7) \\
 78146 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((4 + (1^8))^7)) \\
 78159 &:= F(9) + 5^{1^8 \times 7} \\
 78197 &:= (((F(F(7)) - (9 - 1)) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78219 &:= (F((F(9)/(1 \times 2))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-7))) \\
 78239 &:= ((9 - F(3)) \times ((-2) + F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) \\
 78246 &:= ((F(F(6))/F(4)) \times ((-F(2)) + F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) \\
 78252 &:= (-F(2) - ((F(F((5 + 2))) + F(F(8))) \times (-7))) \\
 78253 &:= ((F(((3 \times 5) - 2)) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78254 &:= (F(F(F(4))) - ((F(F((5 + 2))) + F(F(8))) \times (-7))) \\
 78256 &:= ((F(F(6)) - (5)) \times (-2) + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 78267 &:= (((F((7 + 6)) + 2) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78274 &:= (((F(4) + F(F(7))) + F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \times 7) \\
 78284 &:= (-4) + ((F(8) \times (2 \times 8)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 78288 &:= (((8 + F((8 - 2))) \times F(8)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 78323 &:= (((3^{2+3}) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78336 &:= ((F(6) \times F(3)) \times (3 + (F(8) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 78354 &:= (-4) + ((5^{-F(F(3))+8}) + F(F(7))) \\
 78358 &:= F(8 + 5) + (-3 + 8)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78367 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((-6^3) - F(F(8))) \times (-7))) \\
 78384 &:= ((4 + 8) \times (F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(8)))) - F(F(7)))) \\
 78386 &:= (((6 \times F(8)) \times F(3)) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78399 &:= 9 \times (F(9) \times F(3)^8 + 7) \\
 78414 &:= (((4 \times 1)^4) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78428 &:= (((F(F(8)) + 2) + (F(F(4))^8)) \times 7) \\
 78429 &:= (((F(9)/2)^{F(4)}) + F(F(8))) \times F(7) \\
 78478 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(4)))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-7))) \\
 78486 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times F(F(8)))/F(4)) + (8 \times F(F(7)))) \\
 78487 &:= (((7 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(F(4)))) + (8 \times F(F(7)))) \\
 78498 &:= (((8 \times F(9)) - (4)) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78547 &:= (((F((F(7) - F(4))) \times 5) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78568 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (-5) \times (-8) + F(F(7)))) \\
 78594 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((F(9)^{-5+8}) - (7))) \\
 78624 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((F((2 \times 6)) \times F(8)) \times F(7))) \\
 78638 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((36 \times 8))) \times 7) \\
 78647 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((F(F(4))^{F(6)}) + F(F(8))) \times 7)) \\
 78689 &:= (((F((F(9) - F(8))) \times F(F(6))) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(7))) \\
 78694 &:= (((F(4) + F(9)) \times F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78719 &:= ((9 \times F(F((1 \times 7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-7))) \\
 78729 &:= (((F(9) \times 2) + F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78735 &:= F(5 \times 3) + (F(7) - 8)^7 \\
 78756 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((5^7) + F((8 + 7)))) \\
 78827 &:= (((F(7) + 2) \times F(8)) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78883 &:= (((F((-3) + F(8)))/8) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78944 &:= (((4 \times (F(4)^9)) - F(8)) + F(F(7))) \\
 78987 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (8 + 98)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 78997 &:= (F(F(7)) - (((F(9) \times (-9)) - F(F(8))) \times 7)) \\
 79199 &:= (F((F(9) - 9)) + ((F(19) - (7)))) \\
 79215 &:= (-5) \times (1 + ((-2) \times F(9)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 79225 &:= (-5) \times (-F(2)) + (((-2) \times F(9)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 79235 &:= (-5) \times (-3) + (((-2) \times F(9)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 79268 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(F(6)) \times (2 \times 9))) \times 7) \\
 79299 &:= ((-9) \times (F(9) - F(2))) \times (-F(9) - F(F(7))) \\
 79453 &:= (((3 \times (5^{F(4)})) - F(9)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 79477 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (7^{F(4)})) - (F(9) \times F(7))) \\
 79478 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(7) - F(F(F(4)))) \times F(9))) \times 7) \\
 79492 &:= 2 \times (F(9)^{F(4)} + F(9) \times F(7)) \\
 79638 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(F(3))) \times F(6)) + (-F(9)) \times F(F(7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 79646 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(F(4)) + (6))) + (-F(9) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 79648 &:= (8 \times ((-F(4) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F((9+7)))) \\
 79662 &:= (((-2) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(6))) + (-F(9) \times F(F(7))) \\
 79666 &:= (-6) + (F(6) \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F((9+7)))) \\
 79672 &:= ((F(2) + 7) \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F((9+7)))) \\
 79677 &:= (-F(7) \times ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (-F(9) - 7))) \\
 79686 &:= ((6 \times ((8 \times 6) + 9)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 79716 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((-1) \times F(7)) \times F(9)) \times 7) \\
 79744 &:= ((4 \times F((4+7))) \times (-9) + F(F(7))) \\
 79815 &:= (-51) \times ((F(F(8)) + 9) / (-7)) \\
 79927 &:= (((F(F(7)) - F((2 \times 9))) \times (-F(9))) - 7) \\
 79929 &:= 9 \times (-2 + 9 \times F(9 + 7)) \\
 79934 &:= ((F((4^{F(3)})) \times (9 \times 9)) - (F(7))) \\
 79947 &:= (F(7) - 4) \times 9 \times F(9 + 7) \\
 79968 &:= 8 \times (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(9) \times 7 \\
 80688 &:= ((F(F(8)) - 860) \times 8) \\
 80934 &:= (F((4^{F(3)})) \times (90 - 8)) \\
 81175 &:= (-5) - (-((F(7) - 1) \times F((-1) + F(8)))) \\
 81186 &:= (6 \times (F(F(8)) + (1 + F(18)))) \\
 81557 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - (F((5 \times 5)))) - F((-1) + F(8)))) \\
 81736 &:= (F(6) \times (-((3^{7-1})) + F(F(8)))) \\
 81794 &:= ((4 \times (F((9 + F(7))) + 1)) + F(F(8))) \\
 82366 &:= (((6^6) \times F(3)) - F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \\
 82667 &:= -(((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + (F(6) \times (F(2) - F(F(8)))) \\
 82672 &:= (((-F((2 + F(7)))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 2) \times 8) \\
 82688 &:= ((F(F(8)) - F((F(8) - 6))) \times (F(2) \times 8)) \\
 82696 &:= (F(6) \times (-((F((9 + 6)) - F(2))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 82824 &:= 4 \times (-F(2) + F(8 \times 2)) \times F(8) \\
 82923 &:= (32 \times 9)^2 - F(8) \\
 82936 &:= (F(6) \times (F(3) + F(9)))^2 - 8 \\
 82937 &:= (((F(F(7))^{F(3)} - 9) + F((2 + F(8)))) \\
 83349 &:= (9 \times (4 + 3))^{F(3)} \times F(8) \\
 83369 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(6))^3)) - (F(F(3)) - (F(8)))) \\
 83385 &:= (((5 \times F(F(8))) - F(3)) + F((F(3) + F(8)))) \\
 83386 &:= (((6 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(3))) + F((F(F(3)) + (F(8)))) \\
 83387 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) + F((-((3/3)) + F(8)))) \\
 83388 &:= (((8 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(3))) - F(-((F(3) - F(8)))) \\
 83478 &:= -8 + F(7)^{F(4)} \times 38 \\
 83486 &:= (-F(6) + F(8))^{F(4)} \times 38
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 83488 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((8^{F(4)} - F(3)))) \times 8) \\
 83498 &:= (8 + 9)^4 - F(3) - F(8) \\
 83529 &:= (((F(9)/2)^{5-F(F(3))}) + 8) \\
 83615 &:= (-5) + ((-1) + F(F(6))) \times F(-((F(3) - F(8)))) \\
 83749 &:= ((9 + (4 \times F(F(7)))) \times F((3 + 8))) \\
 83764 &:= -((F(-((F(F(4)) - F(F(6)))) + (-F(7) \times F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(8)))))) \\
 83826 &:= (-6) \times (-((F((2 + 8))^{F(3)})) - F(F(8))) \\
 83895 &:= ((5 \times (9 + 8)) \times F((F(3) \times 8))) \\
 84092 &:= ((290^{F(F(4))}) - 8) \\
 84286 &:= ((F(F(6))^{F(8/2)}) + F((4 + F(8)))) \\
 84367 &:= (((F(F(7)) - 6)^{F(3)} + (F(4) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 84368 &:= (-8) \times (((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(8))) \\
 84374 &:= (-F((4 + F(7)))) - (-3) \times F((F(F(4)) + (F(8)))) \\
 84387 &:= (((F(7) \times F(8)) - F(3))^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(8)) \\
 84617 &:= (F(7) \times (F((-1) + F(F(6)))) - (F(F(4))^8)) \\
 84664 &:= ((F(4) \times ((F(6) \times F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))}) - 8) \\
 84674 &:= (((F(F(4))^{F(7)}) \times (6 + F(4))) + F(F(8))) \\
 84697 &:= -((F(F(7)) - ((F(9) \times F(6))^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(8)))) \\
 84777 &:= (-7) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-7) + F(F(4))) - F(F(8))) \\
 84866 &:= ((-F(6) \times (F(F(6)) - (F(8)^{F(4)}))) + F(F(8))) \\
 84872 &:= (((F(2) + (F(7) \times (-8)))^{F(F(4))}) \times 8) \\
 84882 &:= (-((2 - 88) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 8))) \\
 84946 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 9) + F((-4) + F(8))) \\
 84984 &:= -((F((F(4) \times 8)) - ((9 + F(4)) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 84985 &:= (-5) \times ((F(8) \times F(9)) - F((F(F(4)) + (F(8)))) \\
 85184 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times (F(8) + 1))^{-5+8}) \\
 85293 &:= 3^{9-F(2)} \times (5 + 8) \\
 85366 &:= (((F((-6) + F(F(6))))^{F(3)}) / 5) + F(F(8)) \\
 85368 &:= (8 \times ((F((F(6) + F(3))) \times (-5)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 85397 &:= (F(7) \times ((9^{-F(F(3))+5}) + 8)) \\
 85528 &:= ((F(F(8)) - 255) \times 8) \\
 85664 &:= ((F(F((F(F(F(4)))) + 6)) - (F(F(F(6))) - 5)) \times (-8)) \\
 85672 &:= (((-F(2)) + F(F(7))) - F(F(F(6)))) + 5) \times (-8) \\
 85677 &:= (F(7) - (((-F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5) \times (-8)) \\
 85678 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(F(7))) \times F(6)) + (-5) - F(8)) \\
 85696 &:= (F(6) \times ((-9) \times (F(F(6)) + 5)) + F(F(8))) \\
 85728 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 2) - F(F(7))) + 5) \times 8) \\
 85736 &:= (-F(6) \times (((F(F(3)) + F(F(7))) - 5) - F(F(8)))) \\
 85744 &:= (((F(F((4 + 4))) - F(F(7))) + 5) \times 8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 85764 &:= (4^6 - 7 - 5) \times F(8) \\
 85888 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(8) + F(8)) \times 5)) \times 8) \\
 85896 &:= ((((-6) \times F(9)) + F(F(8))) - (5)) \times 8) \\
 85963 &:= ((3 \times F((-6) + F(9)) - (5))) - 8) \\
 85966 &:= ((F(((F(6) + F(6)) + 9)) - (5)) + F(F(8))) \\
 85968 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((6 + F(9)) \times 5)) \times 8) \\
 85971 &:= (F(F((1 + 7))) + F(((9 - 5) + F(8)))) \\
 85974 &:= (-F(4) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(9 + 5)) - 8)) \\
 85976 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + (F(7) - 9))) - (-5 - F(F(8)))) \\
 85977 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((F(7) + F(9 + 5)) - F(8))) \\
 85978 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (7)) + F(((9 - 5) + F(8)))) \\
 86016 &:= (F(6)^{10-6}) \times F(8) \\
 86034 &:= (F(4) \times (F((F(3) + F(F(06)))) + (F(8)))) \\
 86176 &:= ((-6) \times (F(F(7)) - 1)) - (-F(6) \times F(F(8))) \\
 86216 &:= ((-((F((6 + 1))^2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8) \\
 86247 &:= ((-74) + F((-2) + F(F(6)))) \times F(8) \\
 86248 &:= (8 \times ((-F(4)) \times F((2 + F(6)))) + F(F(8))) \\
 86266 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (-62)) - (-F(6) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86288 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(8) - F(2)) \times F(6))) \times 8) \\
 86289 &:= ((-((9 \times 8)) + F((-2) + F(F(6)))) \times F(8)) \\
 86348 &:= ((F((F(8) + F(F(4)))) \times 3) + (F((6 + 8)))) \\
 86368 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (6)) - F((F(3) \times 6))) \times 8) \\
 86376 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times (-7)) - F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8) \\
 86384 &:= (((-4) + F(F(8))) - F((F(3) \times 6))) \times 8) \\
 86416 &:= (F(6) \times ((-1) \times F((4 + F(6)))) + F(F(8))) \\
 86432 &:= (((2 - F((3 \times 4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8) \\
 86436 &:= (((F(F(6)) - F(F(3))) + (4^6)) \times F(8)) \\
 86437 &:= ((F((7 \times F(3))) \times (-F(4))) - (-F(6) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86448 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (4)) - F((4 + F(6)))) \times 8) \\
 86456 &:= (F(6) \times ((5 - F((4 + F(6)))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 86457 &:= (F((F(7) - (5))) \times ((4^6) + F(8))) \\
 86464 &:= (((46 \times F(4)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-8)) \\
 86476 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (F(7) \times (-4))) - (-F(6) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86477 &:= -((F(F(7)) + ((F(F(7)) - F(4)) \times (-F((6 + 8)))))) \\
 86497 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (((F(9) + (4^6)) \times F(8)))) \\
 86542 &:= (-((2 + (4^5))) - (-F(6) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86543 &:= -(((F(F(3)) + (4^5)) + (-F(6) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86544 &:= -((((F(F(4)) + F(F(4)))^5) + (-F(6) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86581 &:= ((-1) \times F((F(8) - (5)))) - (-F(6) \times F(F(8))) \\
 86582 &:= F(2) - F(F(8) - 5) + F(6) \times F(F(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 86583 &:= F(3) - F(F(8) - 5) + F(6) \times F(F(8)) \\
 86584 &:= F(4) - F(F(8) - 5) + F(6) \times F(F(8)) \\
 86586 &:= (((F(6) \times F(F(8))) + (5)) - F((F(6) + 8))) \\
 86644 &:= ((-44) \times F(F(6))) - (-F(6) \times F(F(8))) \\
 86672 &:= (((2 \times 7) \times F(6)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-8) \\
 86676 &:= ((-6) \times F(F(7))) \times (6 - 68) \\
 86678 &:= ((F(F(8)) / (-F(7))) + (F(6) \times (-6) + F(F(8)))) \\
 86686 &:= ((F(6) \times F(F(8))) - ((F(F(6)) + F(F(6))) \times F(8))) \\
 86688 &:= F(8) \times 86 \times 6 \times 8 \\
 86726 &:= ((F(F((6 + 2))) / (-F(7))) - (-F(6) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86728 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(2) + (F(7) \times F(6)))) \times 8) \\
 86736 &:= (F(6) \times ((F(F(3)) \times (-F(7) \times F(6)))) + F(F(8))) \\
 86776 &:= (F(6) \times (((-7) \times F(7)) - F(6)) + F(F(8))) \\
 86791 &:= (-1) - ((-97) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-8) \\
 86792 &:= (((F(2) \times (-97)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8) \\
 86793 &:= F(F(3)) + (-97 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8 \\
 86794 &:= F(F(4)) + (-97 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8 \\
 86798 &:= (-((F(8) \times F(9))) - ((-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-8)) \\
 86819 &:= (((-91) + F(F(8))) \times F(6)) - (F(8)) \\
 86848 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (4 + 86)) \times 8) \\
 86854 &:= (-((F((4 + 5)) \times F(8))) - (-F(6) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86856 &:= (((6 + 5) \times 8) \times F((F(6) + 8))) \\
 86864 &:= (((F((F(4) + F(6))) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(6))) + 8) \\
 86867 &:= (-F(7) + (F(6) \times (-86) + F(F(8)))) \\
 86899 &:= (((-((9 \times 9)) + F(F(8))) \times F(6)) - (F(8))) \\
 86919 &:= (-F(9) + F(19) - F(6)) \times F(8) \\
 86928 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(2) + 9) \times F(6))) \times 8) \\
 86944 &:= (((-44) - F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8) \\
 86966 &:= ((F(6) - F((6 + 9))) - (-F(6) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86967 &:= -(((F((7 + F(6))) - 9) + (-F(6) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86968 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (69 + 6)) \times 8) \\
 86984 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(8)) + (-9) \times F(6))) \times (-8)) \\
 86986 &:= (-6) - ((F(F(8)) + (-9) \times F(6)) \times (-8)) \\
 86992 &:= (-((F(2) - 9)) \times ((-9) \times F(6)) + F(F(8))) \\
 87078 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 70) \times 7) + F(F(8))) \\
 87128 &:= ((F(F(8)) - F(((2 + 1) + 7))) \times 8) \\
 87167 &:= -((F(F(7)) + ((F(F(6)) - F(F((1 + 7)))) \times 8)) \\
 87176 &:= (F(6) \times (-((7 \times 1) \times 7) + F(F(8)))) \\
 87184 &:= ((-48) + F(F((1 + 7))) \times 8) \\
 87256 &:= (F(6) \times ((-5) - F((2 + 7))) + F(F(8)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87264 &:= (((-4) + F(F(F(6)))) - F((2+7))) \times 8) \\
 87285 &:= (5 \times ((F((F(8) + F(2))) - F(F(7))) - (F(8)))) \\
 87287 &:= -((F(F(7)) + ((F(F(8)) + ((F(2) - (7)))) \times (-8))) \\
 87288 &:= (((8 - F(F(8))) + 27) \times (-8)) \\
 87293 &:= (-3) - ((-F(9)) + F(F((F(2) + (7)))) \times (-8))) \\
 87294 &:= (-F(F(4))) - ((-F(9)) + F(F((F(2) + (7)))) \times (-8))) \\
 87296 &:= (F(6) \times (-F(9)) + F(((F(2)^{F(7)}) \times F(8)))) \\
 87327 &:= -((F(F(7)) + ((F(2) - F((3 \times 7))) \times 8))) \\
 87328 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (23 + 7)) \times 8) \\
 87335 &:= -((F(F((5 + F(3)))) + (F((3 \times 7)) \times (-8))) \\
 87336 &:= (F(6) \times ((-3) - (F(3) \times F(7))) + F(F(8))) \\
 87337 &:= -((F(F(7)) - ((F(3) + (F((3 \times 7)) \times 8)))) \\
 87354 &:= (((F(4) \times (5^3)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(8))) \\
 87356 &:= (((F(6) \times F(F((5 + 3)))) - F(F(7))) + (F(8))) \\
 87358 &:= (((8^5) \times 3) - F((F(7) + 8))) \\
 87373 &:= (-F(3)) + (F(F(7)) \times (-F(3)) + F((-7) + F(8))) \\
 87374 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(3)) + F((-7) + F(8)))) \\
 87375 &:= ((5 \times F(F(7))) \times (-3 - 78)) \\
 87376 &:= (F(6) \times ((F(7) - 37) + F(F(8)))) \\
 87384 &:= (((F(4) + F(F(8))) - (F(3) \times F(7))) \times 8) \\
 87387 &:= -F(7) + (-F(8) + F(3 \times 7)) \times 8 \\
 87428 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (2^{F(4)+F(7)})) + F(F(8))) \\
 87432 &:= ((F(F((2^3))) - (4 + F(7))) \times 8) \\
 87448 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((4 + 4) + 7)) \times 8) \\
 87454 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (-5) + (-4) \times (F(7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87455 &:= -5 \times (5 - F(4)^7 \times 8) \\
 87456 &:= (F(6) \times (((5 - F(4)) \times (-7)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 87457 &:= (-7) - ((5 + F(4)) \times (F(7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87462 &:= (-2) - ((6 + F(F(4))) \times (F(7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87463 &:= -((F(F(3)) + ((6 + F(F(4))) \times (F(7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87464 &:= ((F(F((4 \times (6 - 4)))) - (F(7))) \times 8) \\
 87466 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times F(6)) - (F(4) \times (F(7) + F(8)))) \\
 87467 &:= (-F(7)) + (F(6) \times (-((4 + 7)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 87468 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (-4) - (F(7) \times (-8))) \\
 87469 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (4 + 7))) - F(F(8))) \\
 87472 &:= (((F(2) - F(7)) + F((F(4) \times 7))) \times 8) \\
 87477 &:= (((-F(7)) + F((7 \times F(4)))) \times 7) + F(F(8)) \\
 87491 &:= (((1 + F(9)) \times (F(4)^7)) + F(F(8))) \\
 87493 &:= (-3) + ((-9) + F((F(4) \times 7))) \times 8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87494 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (-9) + (-4) \times (7 - F(F(8)))) \\
 87496 &:= (-F(6)) \times ((F((9/F(4))) + (7)) - F(F(8))) \\
 87498 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 9) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 7) + F(F(8)) \\
 87511 &:= (-1) + (F((1 + 5)) \times (-7) + F(F(8))) \\
 87512 &:= ((F(F((2 + 1) + 5))) - (7)) \times 8) \\
 87513 &:= F(F(3)) + F(1 + 5) \times (-7 + F(F(8))) \\
 87514 &:= F(F(4)) + F(1 + 5) \times (-7 + F(F(8))) \\
 87526 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (-2)) + ((-5) + F(7)) \times F(F(8))) \\
 87528 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(2) \times 5)) \times (-F(7) - F(8))) \\
 87533 &:= (((F(F(F(3 + 3))) - (5)) \times 7) + F(F(8))) \\
 87534 &:= -((F((F(4)^{F(3)})) - ((-5) + F(7)) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 87535 &:= (-5) \times (-((3^{-5+F(7)}) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87536 &:= (F(6) \times ((F(F(3)) - (5)) + F((F(7) + 8)))) \\
 87537 &:= (-7) + ((-3) + F(F((-5) + F(7)))) \times 8) \\
 87542 &:= (-2) - ((-F(4)) + F(F((-5) + F(7)))) \times (-8)) \\
 87543 &:= (-F(F(3))) - ((-F(4)) + F(F((-5) + F(7)))) \times (-8)) \\
 87544 &:= ((-F(4)) + F((F(4 + 5)) - F(7))) \times 8) \\
 87546 &:= ((-F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) - ((5 - F(7)) \times F(F(8))) \\
 87547 &:= ((F((7 \times F(4))) \times (-5) + F(7)) - (F(8))) \\
 87548 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (4)) \times (-5)) - (-F(7)) \times F(F(8))) \\
 87552 &:= ((-2) + F(F((5/5) + 7))) \times 8) \\
 87553 &:= (-((3 \times 5)) + ((-5) + F(7)) \times F(F(8))) \\
 87558 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (5 + 5)) - (-7) \times F(F(8))) \\
 87559 &:= (-9) - (F(F((5/5) + 7)) \times (-8)) \\
 87573 &:= (-((F(3) - (7))) + ((-5) + F(7)) \times F(F(8))) \\
 87574 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) + (-7) - ((-5) + F(7)) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 87576 &:= ((F((F(6) + F(7))) + F(-((5 - 7)))) \times 8) \\
 87581 &:= (((1 - F(F(8))) \times (5 - F(7))) + (F(8))) \\
 87582 &:= (2 \times (((F(F(8)) \times 5) + (7)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87583 &:= (((-3) + F(F(8))) \times (-5)) - (-F(7)) \times F(F(8))) \\
 87584 &:= ((F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times F((5 - 7) + 8)) \\
 87586 &:= ((F(6) \times F(F(8))) + (F((5 + 7)/8))) \\
 87588 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 + 7) + 8)) \\
 87589 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F((-5) + F(7))) - F(F(8))) \\
 87596 &:= ((-6) + F(9)) + ((-5) + F(7)) \times F(F(8)) \\
 87597 &:= (F(7) + (F(9) \times (F((5 + F(7)) - 8))) \\
 87598 &:= ((F(8) + 9) + ((-5) + F(7)) \times F(F(8))) \\
 87608 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((0 - F(6)) + F(7))) \times 8) \\
 87613 &:= (-3) + (((-1) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7) \times 8) \\
 87614 &:= (-F(F(4))) + (((-1) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7) \times 8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87616 &:= ((6 + F(F((1^6) + 7))) \times 8) \\
 87617 &:= (-7) - (F((1 \times 6)) \times (-7) - F(F(8))) \\
 87621 &:= (-((1 + 2)) - (F(6) \times (-7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87622 &:= (-2) - ((F(F(2 + 6))) + (7)) \times (-8) \\
 87623 &:= (-((3 - 2)) - (F(6) \times (-7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87624 &:= ((F(F(4 \times 2))) \times F(6)) + (7 \times 8) \\
 87625 &:= (F(F((5 - 2))) - (F(6) \times (-7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87626 &:= (F((6/2)) - (F(6) \times (-7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87627 &:= (-F(7)) + (((-2) - F(F(F(6)))) - 7) \times (-8) \\
 87628 &:= ((8/2) - (F(6) \times (-7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87631 &:= (-1) + (((F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7) \times 8) \\
 87632 &:= ((F(F(2^3))) + F(6)) \times (-F(7) - F(8)) \\
 87633 &:= ((F(3 + 3)) - F((6 + F(7)))) \times (-F(8)) \\
 87634 &:= (F(F(4)) + (((F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7) \times 8)) \\
 87635 &:= (-5) + (((F(3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7) \times 8) \\
 87636 &:= ((6 \times F(3)) - (F(6) \times (-7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87637 &:= (F(7) - ((F(3) + (6)) \times (-7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87638 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(F(3))) \times F(6)) + (78)) \\
 87639 &:= F(9) \times (F(3 \times 6) - 7) + F(8) \\
 87651 &:= -((F(F((1 + 5))) + (F(6) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(8)))))) \\
 87654 &:= (((F(F(4)) + (5)) - F((6 + F(7)))) \times (-F(8))) \\
 87656 &:= (((6 + 5) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \times 8) \\
 87657 &:= (-F((7 + 5))) - (F((6 + F(7))) \times (-F(8))) \\
 87662 &:= ((-2) - F(6)) - (F(6) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(8))) \\
 87663 &:= (-((3 + 6)) - (F(6) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87664 &:= (((4 + F(6)) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \times 8) \\
 87666 &:= (-6) - (F(6) \times (-((6 + 7)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87667 &:= (-F(7)) - (-F(6)) \times ((F(F(6)) - 7) + F(F(8))) \\
 87669 &:= (-((9 - 6)) - (F(6) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87671 &:= (-1) - ((F(7) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \times (-8)) \\
 87672 &:= (F(27 - 6) + F(7)) \times 8 \\
 87673 &:= F(F(3)) + (F(7) + F(F(6) + F(7))) \times 8 \\
 87674 &:= F(F(4)) + (F(7) + F(F(6) + F(7))) \times 8 \\
 87675 &:= (-5) - (((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + 7) \times (-8)) \\
 87676 &:= -(((F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) + (F(6) \times (F(7) - F(F(8)))))) \\
 87691 &:= (19 - (F(6) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87692 &:= ((2 \times F(9)) - (F(6) \times (-7) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87693 &:= (F(F(-((3 - 9)))) - (F(6) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87694 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times 9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) + F(F(8)) \\
 87696 &:= (F(6) \times ((9 - 6) + F(7)) + F(F(8)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87698 &:= ((-8) + F(9)) - (F(6) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(8))) \\
 87728 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (27 - 7)) \times 8) \\
 87736 &:= (F(6) + F(3 \times 7) + F(7)) \times 8 \\
 87737 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times F((F(3) \times 7))) + (F(7) \times (-8))) \\
 87738 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 3) - F((F(7) + (7)))) \times F(8)) \\
 87739 &:= ((F(9) \times (-3)) + (F(F(7)) \times F((-7) + F(8)))) \\
 87754 &:= ((-F(4)) + F((5 + F(7)))) \times (F(7) + F(8)) \\
 87764 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((7 \times 7) + F(F(8)))) \\
 87766 &:= ((F(6) \times (F(F(F(6)) - 7)) + ((F(F(7)) + (F(8)))) \\
 87768 &:= (-8) - (F(6) \times (-((F(7) + F(7))) - F(F(8)))) \\
 87769 &:= ((-9) \times F(6)) + (F(F(7)) \times F((-7) + F(8))) \\
 87776 &:= ((F((F(6) + F(7))) + (F(7) + F(7))) \times 8) \\
 87784 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(8)) + (F(7) + F(7)))) \times 8) \\
 87786 &:= (((F(6) \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (7 + 8)) \\
 87816 &:= (F(6) \times ((18 + F(7)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 87822 &:= ((F(2) + F((-2) + F(8))) \times (F(7) + 8)) \\
 87833 &:= ((F(((3 + 3) + 8)) \times F(F(7))) - 8) \\
 87835 &:= (F((5^{F(3)})) + (F(8) \times F((7 + 8)))) \\
 87836 &:= (((6 \times F((F(3) + 8))) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) \\
 87838 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(3)) \times 8) + F(F(7))) + F(F(8)) \\
 87856 &:= F(6 \times (-5 + 8)) \times (F(7) + F(8)) \\
 87861 &:= (-1) - ((-F((6 + 8))) \times F(F(7)) - (F(8))) \\
 87862 &:= (((2 \times F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times 7) + F(F(8)) \\
 87863 &:= (F(F(3)) - ((-F((6 + 8))) \times F(F(7))) - (F(8))) \\
 87864 &:= (((4 \times 6) + F(F(8))) + (F(7))) \times 8 \\
 87867 &:= (-F(7)) \times (6 - F((F(8) + ((7 - 8)))) \\
 87878 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times 8) + F(F(7))) + (F(8)) \\
 87886 &:= (((-F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times (-8)) + F(F(7)) + (F(8)) \\
 87888 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (8 \times (-8) + F(7))) \times 8) \\
 87893 &:= (-3) - (((F(9) + F(F(8))) + (7)) \times (-8)) \\
 87894 &:= -((F(F(4)) + ((F(9) + F(F(8))) + (7)) \times (-8))) \\
 87896 &:= (((-6) + F(9)) + F(F(8))) + (F(7)) \times 8) \\
 87897 &:= (((F(7) + F(9)) + F(F(8))) \times 7) + F(F(8)) \\
 87924 &:= ((F(F(4)) + F((2 \times 9))) \times (F(7) + F(8))) \\
 87927 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-2 \times 9)) + (7)) \times (-F(8))) \\
 87928 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((-2) + F(9)) + F(7))) \times 8) \\
 87936 &:= (F(6) \times ((39 + 7) + F(F(8)))) \\
 87937 &:= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8 \\
 87944 &:= ((F(F((4 + 4))) + (F(9) + F(7))) \times 8) \\
 87945 &:= F(5 \times 4) \times (F(9) - F(7) - 8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 887948 &:= ((F((-8) + (F(4) \times 9))) + (7)) \times F(8)) \\
 887966 &:= ((F(((F(-6) - F(6)) + F(9))) \times F(7)) + (F(8))) \\
 887979 &:= (((F(9) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(9) \times F(7))) + (F(8))) \\
 888016 &:= (F(6) - ((-F(10)) - F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888064 &:= (((F(F(4)) + (60)) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888128 &:= (F((8 + F(2))) \times (F(18) + 8)) \\
 888178 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(7)) + (F((-1) + F(8))) \times (-8)) \\
 888184 &:= ((-((4 - 81)) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888186 &:= (F((-6) + F(8))) + ((-1) - F(F(8))) \times (-8)) \\
 888208 &:= ((80 + F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \times 8) \\
 888216 &:= (((F(6) + 1)^2) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888218 &:= (F((8 - 1)) \times (F(-((F(2) - F(8)))) + (F(8)))) \\
 888242 &:= ((-F((2 \times 4))) - F((-2) + F(8))) \times (-F(8)) \\
 888248 &:= (((84 + F(2)) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888263 &:= (((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))) + F((-2) + F(8))) \times F(8)) \\
 888264 &:= (((F((F(4) + F(6))) - 2) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888267 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (6/2)) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 888272 &:= (((-F(2)) + F((F(7) - 2))) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888273 &:= ((3 \times (F(F(7)) + 2)) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 888275 &:= (-5) - ((F((F(7) - 2)) + F(F(8))) \times (-8)) \\
 888284 &:= (((F(F(4)) + (F(8))) + F((-2) + F(8))) \times F(8)) \\
 888288 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (82 + 8)) \times 8) \\
 888296 &:= (-F(6)) - ((92 + F(F(8))) \times (-8)) \\
 888297 &:= (-7) - ((92 + F(F(8))) \times (-8)) \\
 888298 &:= ((F(8) \times F(9)) - ((-2) - F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888299 &:= (9 \times (-((F(9)^2) - F(8))) + F(F(8))) \\
 888347 &:= (((-F(7)) \times F(F(4))) - F(-((F(3) - F(8)))) \times (-F(8))) \\
 888366 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times F(6)) + (38 \times F(8))) \\
 888368 &:= (((F(8) + (6)) + F(-((F(3) - F(8)))) \times F(8)) \\
 888369 &:= ((9 \times F((F(6) + 3))) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 888376 &:= (((F(6) \times F(7)) - 3) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888384 &:= (((F(4) \times F((8 + F(F(3)))) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888387 &:= (((F(7) \times F(8)) \times 3) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 888392 &:= (((F(2) - (F(9) \times (-3))) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888397 &:= (F(7) - (((F(9) \times 3) + F(F(8))) \times (-8)) \\
 888435 &:= (-5) \times ((3 - F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8)))) + (F(8))) \\
 888445 &:= (-5) \times ((F(F(F(4))) - F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8)))) + (F(8))) \\
 888448 &:= (((F((8 + F(F(4)))) \times F(F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888476 &:= (((6 - F(F(7))) \times (-4)) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 888487 &:= ((-F(F(7)) + ((F(F(8)) + F((4 + 8))) \times (-8)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 888494 &:= (((-((F(F(F(4))) - F(9))) + F(-((F(F(4)) - (F(8)))))) \times F(8)) \\
 888495 &:= (-5) \times (((-9) - F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8)))) + (F(8))) \\
 888515 &:= (5 \times (F(((1^5) + F(8))) - 8)) \\
 888526 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + F(2))) \times 5) - (8 + F(8))) \\
 888545 &:= (-5) \times (F(F(4)) - F((F(F(-((5 - 8)))) + (F(8)))) \\
 888553 &:= (-F(3)) - (-5) \times F((F(F(-((5 - 8)))) + (F(8)))) \\
 888554 &:= (-F(F(F(4))) - (-5) \times F((F(F(-((5 - 8)))) + (F(8)))) \\
 888555 &:= (5 \times F(((5/5)^8) + F(8))) \\
 888563 &:= ((-3) \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((5 + F(8))) + 8) \\
 888576 &:= (((6 \times F((F(7) - 5))) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888578 &:= (((F(F(8)) / (-F(7))) \times (-5)) + 8) \times F(8) \\
 888584 &:= ((F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) \times 5) + (8 + F(8))) \\
 888589 &:= ((F(9) + F((F(8) - 5))) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 888595 &:= 5 \times (F(9 + 5 + 8) + 8) \\
 888597 &:= ((F((F(7) + 9)) \times 5) + (F(8) + F(8))) \\
 888635 &:= (5 \times (F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + (8 + 8))) \\
 888672 &:= ((F(-((F(2) - F(7)))) - (6 - F(F(8)))) \times 8) \\
 888683 &:= ((F(-((F(3) - F(8)))) + (F(F(6)) + (F(8)))) \times F(8)) \\
 888712 &:= (((-F(2)) + F((-1) + F(7))) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888715 &:= (-5) - ((F((-1) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times (-8)) \\
 888733 &:= (((F(3) + 3) \times F(F(7))) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 888736 &:= (-F(6)) \times ((F(F(3)) - (7 \times F(8))) - F(F(8))) \\
 888744 &:= ((F(F((4 + 4))) + (7 \times F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888777 &:= (F(7) \times (F((F(7) + 7))) + (8 \times 8)) \\
 888778 &:= -((F(F(8)) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(7) - (F(8) \times F(8)))))) \\
 888788 &:= (((8 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (F((8 + 8)))) \\
 888809 &:= 90 \times F(8 + 8) - F(8) \\
 888848 &:= (((F(8) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 8) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888936 &:= (((F(F(6)) - F(3)) \times (-9)) - F(F(8))) \times (-8) \\
 888966 &:= ((6 \times F(-((F(F(6)) - F(9)))) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 888967 &:= -((F(F(7)) + (((6 \times F(9)) + F(F(8))) \times (-8))) \\
 888976 &:= (((F(6) \times (F(7) + 9)) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 888996 &:= (((F(6) + F(9)) \times F(9)) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 89166 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times F(6)) + (1 + F((9 + 8)))) \\
 89355 &:= (5 + 5^3 \times F(9)) \times F(8) \\
 89368 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((6^3) + 9)) \times 8) \\
 89376 &:= (F(6) \times ((F(F(7)) + ((F(3) - 9))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 89432 &:= ((F(F((2^3))) + (F((4 + 9)))) \times 8) \\
 89448 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(F(4))) + (F((4 + 9)))) \times 8) \\
 89464 &:= (((4 + F(F(F(6)))) + (F((4 + 9)))) \times 8)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 89472** := $((-2) \times F(F(7))) \times (-F(4) + (9 \times F(8)))$
89488 := $F(8 + 8) / F(4) \times F(9) \times 8$
89647 := $((F(F(7)) - F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9 - F(F(8))$
89665 := $((F((5 + F(6))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9) - F(F(8))$
89747 := $((F((7 \times F(F(4)))) \times (7 \times F(9))) + F(8))$
89768 := $((F(F(8)) + F(6)) + F(F(7))) + F(9) \times 8$
89817 := $(F(7) \times (F((-1) + F(8))) + F((-9) + F(8)))$
89837 := $((F(7)^3) - ((F(F(8)) + 9) \times (-8)))$
89964 := $F(4) \times (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(9) \times F(8)$
89968 := $((F(F(8)) - (6 - (9 \times F(9)))) \times 8$
89976 := $(F(6) \times ((-7) \times (-9) - F(9))) + F(F(8))$
89984 := $((-4) + F(F(8))) + (9 \times F(9)) \times 8$
91664 := $((4^6) + (F(F(F(6))) \times (-1 - 9)))$
91728 := $((F(F(8)) - (2 \times F((F(7) + 1)))) \times 9$
91976 := $-6 + (F(7) + 9) \times F(19)$
91982 := $(F(2) + F(8)) \times F(9 + 1 + 9)$
92448 := $((8 - F((-4) + F((F(4)^2)))) / (-9)$
92449 := $((F((F(9) - 4)) + F((4 - 2))) / 9$
92727 := $((F(((F(7) - 2) + F(7))) \times 2) - 9$
92728 := $(-8) + (2 \times F((F(7) + (2 + 9))))$
92732 := $(2 \times (-F(3)) + F((F(7) + (2 + 9))))$
92733 := $(-3) + (F(3) \times F((F(7) + (2 + 9))))$
92734 := $-((F(F(4)) - (F(3) \times F((F(7) + (2 + 9))))))$
92736 := $((6/3) \times F((F(7) + (2 + 9))))$
92742 := $(2 \times (F(4) + F((F(7) + (2 + 9))))$
92744 := $(F(F(4)) \times (4 + F((F(7) + (2 + 9))))$
92754 := $(F(F(4)) \times (F(((5 + 7) \times 2) + 9))$
92784 := $((F((F(4) \times 8)) + (7)) \times 2) + F(9)$
92967 := $(F(F(7)) \times (((-6) \times F(9)) \times (-2)) - 9)$
92991 := $(-1 + 9 \times F(9))^2 - F(9)$
93024 := $((4 \times F((20 - F(3)))) \times 9$
93248 := $((F((8 \times F(4))) \times 2) + (F(3)^9))$
93294 := $(F(F(4)) \times (((F(9) + 2)^3) - 9)$
93296 := $F(6) \times (9 - 2)^3 \times F(9)$
93346 := $6^{4+3} / 3 + F(9)$
93636 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (F(3)^{F(F(6)-F(F(3))})) \times F(9))$
93665 := $((-F((5 \times 6)) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(3))) / (-9)$
93696 := $((F(F(6)) \times 9) - (6)) \times (F(3)^9)$
93738 := $((F(F(8)) - ((F(3)^{F(7)}) - 3)) \times F(9))$
93765 := $(F((-5) + F(F(6)))) \times (-7) - (-3) \times F(9))$
93789 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) - (F(7) + (F(3)^9))))$
93898 := $(-8) + (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (F(3)^9)))$
94476 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (((F(7) + 4)^4) + 9))$
94626 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (F((2 \times 6)) \times F(4))) \times 9$
94647 := $(7 \times ((F(F(4)) \times F((F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))))) - 9)$
94676 := $((F(F(6)) - 7) \times F((F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))))) - F(9)$
94831 := $(F(13) \times ((F(8)^{F(F(4))}) - F(9)))$
94928 := $(82 \times F(9) + 4) \times F(9)$
95297 := $(F(F(7)) \times ((F(9) - 2) + F((5 + 9))))$
95488 := $(8 \times (F(F(8)) - (-((4^5) + F(9))))$
95744 := $(-4) \times (((F(4) \times F(F(7))) + 5) \times (-F(9)))$
95766 := $(F(6) - ((F(F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times (-F((5 + 9))))$
95774 := $(-4) + ((F(F(7)) + F((F(7) + 5))) \times F(9))$
95778 := $((F(8) + (F(F(7)) \times (7 + 5))) \times F(9))$
96228 := $((F(F(8)) + (2 - (2^{F(6)}))) \times 9$
96246 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (42 \times 6)) \times 9$
96317 := $(-((F(7)^{1 \times 3})) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-9)))$
96354 := $((-(((F(4)^5) - 3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9$
96372 := $((((-2) - F(F(7))) - 3) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9$
96377 := $(-F(7) - ((-((F(F(7)) + 3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-9)))$
96378 := $(-F(8) + ((-((F(F(7)) + F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9)$
96396 := $(-F(F(6)) - ((F(F(9 - F(3)))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 9)$
96417 := $((F(F(7)) - F(F((14 - 6)))) \times (-9))$
96426 := $((F(F((F(6) - F(2)))) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-9)$
96435 := $((F(F((5 + F(3)))) - F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-9)$
96438 := $(F(8) - ((-F(F(3 + 4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-9))$
96444 := $((F(4) - F(F((F(4) + 4)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9$
96453 := $((F(F((F(3) + 5))) - 4) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-9)$
96462 := $(F(F((F(2) + 6))) \times (46 \times 9))$
96471 := $((1 + (F(F(7)) \times 46)) \times 9)$
96478 := $((F((F(8) - 7))) \times (F(F(4))^{F(6)})) - F(9)$
96489 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) - ((4 + F(F(6))) \times 9))$
96498 := $((F(F(8)) + 9) - F(F((F(F(F(4))) + 6)))) \times 9$
96534 := $(((-4) \times F((F(3) \times 5))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9$
96674 := $((F(4) - F(F(7))) \times F(6)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-9))$
96678 := $((F(F(8)) - F(F(7))) + F(6)) + F(F(6)) \times 9$
96684 := $((-F(4)) \times F((F(8) - 6))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-9))$
96687 := $((7 \times (F(8) + F(6))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-9)$
96696 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (F(9) + (F(6) \times F(F(6)))) \times 9$
96723 := $((F((3^2)) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9$

$$\begin{aligned}
 96767 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(6))) + ((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-9)) \\
 96768 &:= ((F(8) \times F(6)) \times (F((7 + F(6))) - F(9))) \\
 96795 &:= ((5 \times 9) \times ((F(F(7)) + (6)) \times 9)) \\
 96838 &:= ((F(8)^3) - ((F(F(8)) \times (-F(6))) - 9)) \\
 96849 &:= (9 \times ((4 + F(F(8))) + (F(F(6)) \times (-9)))) \\
 96876 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(7) \times (8 + 6))) \times 9) \\
 96896 &:= -((F(F(6)) + ((-9) \times F(F(8))) + F((F(6) + 9)))) \\
 96917 &:= ((F(F((7 + 1))) \times 9) - F((F(6) + 9))) \\
 96926 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(2)) \times 9) - F((F(6) + 9))) \\
 96984 &:= (((-((F(4) - 8) \times F(9))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-9)) \\
 96998 &:= (((F(F(8)) + 9) \times 9) - F((F(6) + 9))) \\
 97218 &:= ((F(F(8)) - F(((1 - 2) + F(7)))) \times 9) \\
 97236 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(3)) - F(-(F(2) - F(7)))) \times 9) \\
 97336 &:= (((F(F(6)) + F(3)) \times F(3))^{F(F(7)-9)}) \\
 97361 &:= (-1) - ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(3)^7)) \times (-9)) \\
 97362 &:= ((F(F((2 + 6))) - (F(3)^7)) \times 9) \\
 97363 &:= F(F(3)) + (F(F(F(6))) - F(3)^7) \times 9 \\
 97364 &:= F(F(4)) + (F(F(F(6))) - F(3)^7) \times 9 \\
 97569 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (-5) \times (F(7) - F(9)))) \\
 97578 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(7) - 5) \times F(7))) \times 9) \\
 97596 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (95 + 7)) \times 9) \\
 97627 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((-2) - F(F(6))) + (F(7) \times F(9))) \\
 97644 &:= (-F((4 \times 4)) + ((F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 9)) \\
 97655 &:= (-5 + 5^{F(6)}) / (F(7) - 9) \\
 97659 &:= ((-95) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \times 9) \\
 97672 &:= ((F(2) - F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - (F(7) \times F(9)))) \\
 97758 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((5 + 7) \times 7)) \times 9) \\
 97824 &:= 4 \times (F(28) / F(7) + 9) \\
 97826 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times (-F(2) - F(8))) \times F(F(7))) - F(9)) \\
 97839 &:= (((-((F(9) \times F(3))) + F(F(8))) - 7) \times 9) \\
 97859 &:= ((9 \times (-5) - F(F(8))) + F((-7) + F(9))) \\
 97875 &:= (-5) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (-8)) - F((F(7) + 9))) \\
 97884 &:= (((F(4) \times F(8)) - F(F(8))) + 7) \times (-9) \\
 97886 &:= (((6 \times F(8)) \times F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \\
 97896 &:= (-F(6) - ((9 \times F(F(8))) - F((-7) + F(9)))) \\
 97897 &:= (-7) - ((9 \times F(F(8))) - F((-7) + F(9))) \\
 97938 &:= (((-8^{F(3)}) + F((F(9) - F(7)))) \times 9) \\
 97947 &:= ((F((7 \times F(4))) - (9 \times 7)) \times 9) \\
 97967 &:= (((-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-9)) + (F((-7) + F(9))) \\
 97968 &:= (F(8) - ((F(F(F(6))) - (9 \times 7)) \times (-9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98019 &:= (((-F((9 + 1))) + F(F(08))) \times 9) \\
 98056 &:= (-F(6) - ((-50) + F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98057 &:= (-7) - ((-50) + F(F(8))) \times (-9) \\
 98136 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times (-F(3))) + F(F((1 \times 8)))) \times 9) \\
 98137 &:= (F((F(7) \times F(3))) - (F(18) \times 9)) \\
 98143 &:= (-F(3) - ((-41) + F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98144 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) + ((-41) + F(F(8))) \times (-9))) \\
 98157 &:= (-((7 \times 51)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98163 &:= (((-3) \times F((6 + 1))) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98183 &:= 38 \times F(18) - 9 \\
 98196 &:= -((F(F(6)) + ((-((F(9) - 1)) + F(F(8))) \times (-9)))) \\
 98199 &:= (-9) - ((-F(9)) + F(F((1 \times 8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98208 &:= ((F(F(8)) - F((F(02) + 8))) \times 9) \\
 98226 &:= (((F(6) \times (-2 + 2)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98239 &:= F(9 \times 3) / 2 + F(8) + 9 \\
 98244 &:= (((4 - F((F(4)^2))) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98245 &:= 5 \times (F(4)^{F(2)+8} - F(9)) \\
 98247 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (((F(4)^2) \times F(F(8))) - F(9))) \\
 98253 &:= (-((3^5)) + ((2 - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98258 &:= (-((F(8) - 5)^2) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98261 &:= (-1) + ((F(F(F(6))) - 28) \times 9) \\
 98262 &:= ((F(F((2 + 6))) - 28) \times 9) \\
 98263 &:= F(F(3)) + (F(F(F(6))) - 28) \times 9 \\
 98264 &:= F(F(4)) + (F(F(F(6))) - 28) \times 9 \\
 98267 &:= ((-F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) - 2) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98271 &:= (((-1) - (F(7) \times 2)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98272 &:= ((-F(2)) \times F(F(7))) + ((F(2) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98275 &:= (-5) + (((F(7) \times (-2)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98276 &:= (((-6) - F(F(7))) + F(2) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98277 &:= ((-F(7)) - F(F(7))) + ((-F(2) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98278 &:= ((-F(8)) - F(F(7))) + ((-2) - F(F(8))) \times (-9) \\
 98281 &:= -((F(F((1 + 8) - 2))) + (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98282 &:= F(2) - F(F(8 - F(2))) + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\
 98283 &:= F(3) - F(F(8 - F(2))) + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\
 98284 &:= F(4) - F(F(8 - F(2))) + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\
 98286 &:= -((F(F(6)) + ((F(F(8)) - (2 + F(8))) \times (-9))) \\
 98287 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - (8 - 2)) + (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98289 &:= (((-F(9)) + F(F(8))) + (F(2) + 8)) \times 9) \\
 98294 &:= ((-4) \times F((9 + F(2)))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98297 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - F(9)) - ((2 - F(F(8))) \times (-9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98298 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(9) - (2 + 8))) \times 9) \\
 98316 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times (-1)) - F(F(3))) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98317 &:= -((F(F(7)) - ((1 + 3) + F(F(8)))) \times 9)) \\
 98323 &:= -(F(3) + ((F((2^3)) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))) \\
 98324 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - ((F((2^3)) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)))) \\
 98325 &:= ((F(((5 + 2) \times 3)) - F(8)) \times 9) \\
 98325 &:= (F((5 + 2) \times 3) - F(8)) \times 9 \\
 98327 &:= -((F(7)^2) - ((F(3) - F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98328 &:= (F(8) + ((-23) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98334 &:= (((-4) \times (F(3) + 3)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98336 &:= ((F((F(6) + 3)) \times (-F(3))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98343 &:= (((-3) - (4^{F(3)})) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98345 &:= -(((F((5 + F(F(4))))^{F(3)} + (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))) \\
 98346 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((F((4 \times F(3))) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))) \\
 98347 &:= -((((F(7)^{F(F(4))}) - F(3)) + (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))) \\
 98349 &:= ((F((9 + F(F(F(4)))) \times (-3)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98352 &:= (((F(2) + 5) \times (-3)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98358 &:= -(F(8) + ((-((5 \times 3)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98359 &:= (F(9) + ((F(F((5 + 3))) - (F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98361 &:= (((1 - (6 \times 3)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98365 &:= (-5) - (((-((F(6) \times F(3))) + F(F(8))) \times (-9))) \\
 98367 &:= ((-7) \times F(F(6))) + ((F(F(3)) \times F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98369 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(3)) + F((F(8) - 9)))) \\
 98386 &:= (((F(6) \times (-8)) \times F(3)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98387 &:= (((F(F(7)) + (F(8)))/(-F(3))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98388 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((8 - F(3)) + 8)) \times 9) \\
 98389 &:= (-98) + ((-3) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98393 &:= -((((F(3) + 9)^{F(3)} - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))) \\
 98394 &:= -(F(4) + ((F((9 - F(3))) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))) \\
 98397 &:= ((-((7 + 9) - 3)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98398 &:= (-8) + ((-((9 + 3)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98399 &:= -(F(9) + (((-9) \times F(F(3))) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98406 &:= ((-((F(6) - (0 - 4))) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98412 &:= ((2 + 1) \times ((F(4) \times F(F(8))) - F(9))) \\
 98419 &:= -((91 + 4) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98424 &:= (((F(F((4 \times 2))) - F(F(4))) - 8) \times 9) \\
 98425 &:= 5 \times (2 + F(-4 + 8)^9) \\
 98426 &:= (((F(F(6)) + F(2)) \times (-4)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98427 &:= -((((F((F(7) - 2)) - F(F(4))) + (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))) \\
 98428 &:= -((82 + 4) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98429 &:= (-((9^2) + 4) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98432 &:= -(F(2) + (((-3) \times F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98433 &:= (((3 - (3 \times 4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98434 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + (((-3) \times F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98436 &:= (-6) + (((F(3) \times (-4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98437 &:= -((73 + 4) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98438 &:= (((F(8) - F(3)) \times (-4)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98439 &:= ((F(9) \times (-3)) + ((-F(4) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))) \\
 98441 &:= (-1) + ((F(F((4 + 4))) - 8) \times 9) \\
 98442 &:= ((F((F(2) \times F((4 + 4)))) - 8) \times 9) \\
 98445 &:= ((-5) - (4^{F(4)})) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98446 &:= ((F(6) \times (-4)) + ((-4) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98447 &:= -(F(7) + (((-((F(4) + F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98448 &:= -(F(8) + (((-F(4) - F(F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98449 &:= -((F(9) + 4)) + ((-F(4) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98451 &:= (((1 - 5) - F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98452 &:= F(2) + (-5 - F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98453 &:= F(3) + (-5 - F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98454 &:= F(4) + (-5 - F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98455 &:= -((5 + 54) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98456 &:= ((F(6) \times (-5)) - ((F(F(4)) - F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98457 &:= (-75) + ((F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98458 &:= ((8 \times (-5) - F(F(4))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98469 &:= (9 + F(6)^{F(4)}) \times F(8) \times 9) \\
 98471 &:= -((1 \times 7) + ((-4) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98472 &:= ((-2) - F(7) + ((-F(4) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98473 &:= ((F(3) \times (-7)) + ((-F(4) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98474 &:= (-4) + (((-7) + F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98475 &:= (-5) + (((F(7) - 4) \times F(F(8))) - F(9)) \\
 98476 &:= ((F(6) \times (-7)) + ((F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98477 &:= -((7/7) + ((-4) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98478 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((-7) + F(4)) + 8) \times 9) \\
 98479 &:= (F((9 - 7) + ((-4) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98481 &:= -((1 + (8 \times 4)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98482 &:= -((28 + 4) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98483 &:= -((3 - 8) + ((-4) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98484 &:= (((F(4) \times F(F(8))) \times F(4)) - (F(8) + 9)) \\
 98485 &:= (((-5) - F(8)) - F(4)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98486 &:= (F(6) + ((F(F(8)) + ((4 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 98487 &:= (((-7) + F(F(8))) - ((4 - 8))) \times 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 98488** := $(-8) + ((-(8/4) + F(F(8))) \times 9)$
98489 := $(-F(9) + ((F((8/4) + F(F(8))) \times 9))$
98491 := $(-(19 + 4) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98492 := $(-((2 \times 9) + 4) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98493 := $(-3) + ((F((9/F(4))) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98494 := $((-4) - F(9) + ((F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9))$
98495 := $(-(F(F(F(-(5-9)))) + ((F(F(4)) - F(F(8))) \times 9)))$
98496 := $((-(6)/(9/F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times 9$
98497 := $(F(-(7-9)) - ((F(F(4)) - F(F(8))) \times 9))$
98498 := $((F(F(8)) \times 9) - (F((4+8)/9))$
98499 := $((-(9+9) + F(4)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98504 := $((F(F(4)) \times (0-5)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98505 := $((5/(0-5) + F(F(8))) \times 9$
98506 := $(-F(6) + (((0 \times 5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)))$
98507 := $(-7) + (((0 \times 5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98509 := $((9 \times 0) - 5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))$
98521 := $((1 \times 2) + 5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))$
98522 := $(-F(2) + (((F(2)^5) + F(F(8))) \times 9))$
98523 := $((-(3 \times (2-5)) \times F(F(8))) + 9)$
98524 := $((4-2) \times 5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))$
98525 := $((5 + F(2) + 5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98526 := $(-6) + ((F(-(2-5)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)$
98527 := $(F(7) + (F(((F(2)^5) \times F(8))) \times 9))$
98528 := $((F(8) - (2+5)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98529 := $((9 + F(2) + 5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98531 := $(-1) + ((-(3-5) + F(F(8))) \times 9)$
98532 := $((F(F((2^3))) + F(-(5-8))) \times 9)$
98535 := $(F(((5 - F(3)) + 5)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98536 := $((F(F(6)) + F(-(3-5))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98537 := $(-F(7) + (((F(F(3)) - 5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)))$
98538 := $(-F(8) + (((F(F(3)) \times 5) + F(F(8))) \times 9))$
98539 := $(F(9) + ((F(-(3-5)) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)))$
98541 := $((1 - F(4) + 5) + F(F(8))) \times 9$
98542 := $F(2) + (-F(F(4)) + 5 + F(F(8))) \times 9$
98543 := $F(3) + (-F(F(4)) + 5 + F(F(8))) \times 9$
98544 := $F(4) + (-F(F(4)) + 5 + F(F(8))) \times 9$
98545 := $(-5) - ((F(F(F(4))) + (-5) - F(F(8))) \times 9))$
98546 := $((6-4)^5 - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98547 := $((7 \times 4) + 5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))$
98548 := $((F(F(8)) \times -(4-5-8)) + F(9))$
98549 := $((F(9) - ((4-5))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98551 := $(-F((1+5))) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98552 := $(-(2+5) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98553 := $(-(F(F(3)) + 5) - ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)))$
98554 := $((45-5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98556 := $(-(F(6) - 5)) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98557 := $(-(7-5) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98558 := $(-(F(F((8-5))) - ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)))$
98559 := $(9 \times (5 + F(-(5+8) + F(9))))$
98562 := $(F(-(2-6)) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98563 := $(-(F(3) - 6)) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98564 := $(-(F(4) - F(6)) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98565 := $((56-5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98567 := $((-F(7) + F(F(6))) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98568 := $((F(F(8)) + F(6) - F(-(5-8))) \times 9)$
98569 := $(F(((9+6) - 5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98571 := $((-1) + F(7) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98572 := $((F(2) \times F(7) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98573 := $((F(3) \times 7) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98574 := $((F(F(4)) + F(7)) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98576 := $((67-5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98577 := $(7 + F(7 \times (-5+8))) \times 9$
98578 := $(-8) + (((F(7) - 5) + F(F(8))) \times 9)$
98586 := $(F(6) + F(8+5+8)) \times 9$
98592 := $(-(F(2) - F(9)) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98593 := $((F(F(3)) \times F(9) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98594 := $(F(F(F(4))) + F(9) + ((-5) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)))$
98595 := $((5 \times 9)/5 + F(F(8))) \times 9$
98598 := $((F(F(8)) \times 9) - ((5-89)))$
98603 := $(F((3 + F(06))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98604 := $((4 + 06) + F(F(8))) \times 9$
98611 := $((F(11) + F(6)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98613 := $((3 + F((1 \times 6))) + F(F(8))) \times 9$
98616 := $(F(F(6)) + (((1 + F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9))$
98618 := $((8 \times F((1+6))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
98619 := $((F(9) - 1) + ((-F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))$
98621 := $(-1) + (((2 \times 6) + F(F(8))) \times 9)$
98622 := $((F(2) \times (2 \times 6) + F(F(8))) \times 9)$
98623 := $F(F(3)) + (2 \times 6 + F(F(8))) \times 9$
98624 := $F(F(4)) + (2 \times 6 + F(F(8))) \times 9$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98628 &:= ((F(8) \times 2) + ((-F(6) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))) \\
 98629 &:= (F(9) + (((F(2) + F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98631 &:= ((F(((1^3) + 6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98632 &:= F(2) + (F(F(F(3)) + 6) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98633 &:= F(3) + (F(F(F(3)) + 6) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98634 &:= F(4) + (F(F(F(3)) + 6) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98637 &:= (F((F(7) - F(F(3)))) - ((F(F(6)) + (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))) \\
 98642 &:= (((2^4) \times F(6)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98645 &:= (((5^{F(4)}) + 6) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98646 &:= -((F(F(6)) - (((-4) + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98647 &:= ((-7) \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(6)))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98648 &:= -((F((8 + F(F(4)))) - ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98649 &:= ((-((9 - (4 \times 6))) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98654 &:= (-4) - (((-5) + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98657 &:= ((F(7) \times (5 + 6)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98658 &:= (((F(8 - 5)) \times F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98661 &:= (((1 + 6) \times F(F(6))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98664 &:= ((F((4 + F(6))) + 6) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98666 &:= (F(6) + (((F(6) + F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98667 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F(6)) + ((-F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98673 &:= ((-F(3)) + F(F(7))) + ((-F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98674 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(7)) + ((-F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9))) \\
 98676 &:= (((F(F(6))/7) \times 6) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98677 &:= ((F(7) \times 7) + ((-F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98681 &:= ((-1) - F(8)) + ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98682 &:= -((F(2) \times F(8))) + ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98683 &:= F(F(3)) - F(8) + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98684 &:= F(F(4)) - F(8) + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98685 &:= (((5 + F(F(8))) + (6 + 8)) \times 9) \\
 98688 &:= (((-8) - F(8)) \times (-6)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98692 &:= -((2 + 9)) + ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98693 &:= -(((F(F(3)) + 9) - ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98694 &:= (((F(4) + 9) + F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98703 &:= (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9 \\
 98712 &:= (((F(2) + F((1 + 7))) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98721 &:= (F(12) + ((-7) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98726 &:= ((-F((6 + 2))) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98728 &:= ((-((F(8) - 2)) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98729 &:= ((-((9 \times 2)) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98733 &:= (3 \times ((3 \times (F(7) + F(F(8)))) + F(9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98734 &:= ((4 \times F((3 + 7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98736 &:= ((6 \times 37) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98737 &:= ((F(F(7)) - (3 + 7)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98738 &:= (((-8) - F(F(3))) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98739 &:= (((9 + 3) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98742 &:= (((-2) - F(4)) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98743 &:= (((F(F(3)) \times (-4)) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98744 &:= (-4) + (((F(F(4)) \times F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98745 &:= (((-5) + F(4)) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98746 &:= ((-F((6 - 4))) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98747 &:= ((F(F((7 - 4))) \times F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98748 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (47 - F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98749 &:= ((F((9/F(4))) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98751 &:= ((-(1 - 5)) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98752 &:= (((F(2) \times 5) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98753 &:= F(F(3)) + 5 + F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\
 98754 &:= F(F(4)) + 5 + F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\
 98763 &:= (-3) + (((F(F(6)) + 7) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98764 &:= (((-4) + F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98766 &:= (((F(F(6)) + (-6) + F(7))) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98768 &:= ((F(8) + F((6 + 7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98773 &:= ((37 \times 7) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98774 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(8))) - 9) \\
 98775 &:= (F((5 + 7)) + ((-F(7)) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98778 &:= (((F((F(8) - 7))) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) - 9) \\
 98781 &:= ((F((1 + 8)) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98783 &:= (((F(3)^8) + F(7)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98784 &:= (((-4) + F(F(8))) + (F(7) + F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98786 &:= ((F(6) \times (F(8) + F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98787 &:= ((F(7) \times F(8)) - (F((F(7) + 8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98789 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (8 + F(9))) \\
 98793 &:= (((-3) + F(9)) + F((F(7) + 8))) \times 9 \\
 98796 &:= ((6 \times (F(9) + F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98811 &:= (((1 - F((1 + 8))) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98815 &:= (-5) + ((F((1 + 8)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98837 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((F(3) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98847 &:= (((F(7) + F(4)) + F(8)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98856 &:= (((6 \times 5) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98857 &:= ((7^{-5+8}) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)) \\
 98871 &:= ((17 \times F(8)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98874 &:= (((F(F(4)) - (7)) \times (-8)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98883 &:= (((F(F(3)) - F(F(8))) - (F(8) + F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98886 &:= (-6) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(8) + F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98891 &:= (-1) + (((F(9) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98892 &:= (((F(2) \times F(9)) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98893 &:= F(F(3)) + (F(9) + 8 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98894 &:= F(F(4)) + (F(9) + 8 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98928 &:= (((F(8 + 2)) - 9) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98937 &:= (((-F(7)) \times F(F(3))) - F(9) - F(F(8))) \times (-9) \\
 98945 &:= ((5^{F(4)}) - ((-F(9)) - F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98946 &:= ((-((F(6) \times (F(4) - 9))) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98956 &:= (((F(6) + 5) \times F(9)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98964 &:= ((-((4 - (6 \times 9))) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98967 &:= ((7 \times F(F(6))) - ((-F(9)) - F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98972 &:= (F((2 \times 7)) + ((-9) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98976 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (F(7) + 9)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98982 &:= ((2 \times (-8) + F(9)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98988 &:= (-F(8)) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(9) + F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98991 &:= (((19 + F(9)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98992 &:= ((2^9) + ((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(9))) \\
 99018 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(10))) \times 9) + 9) \\
 99126 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (2 \times F((1 \times 9)))) \times 9) \\
 99243 &:= (((3^4) + F(F(-(F(2) - 9)))) \times 9) \\
 99286 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (82)) \times 9) + F(9)) \\
 99315 &:= ((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) + F((F(3) + 9))) \times 9) \\
 99378 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (7)) + F((F(3) + 9))) \times 9) \\
 99396 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (9 + F((F(3) + 9)))) \times 9) \\
 99398 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F(9) \times (-3))) \times 9) - F(9)) \\
 99432 &:= ((F(F((2^3))) + ((F(4) \times F(9)))) \times 9) \\
 99486 &:= (((6 + F(F(8))) + ((F(4) \times F(9)))) \times 9) \\
 99648 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(4) \times (F(6) + F(9)))) \times 9) \\
 99688 &:= (8 + 86 \times F(9)) \times F(9) \\
 99738 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (-((3 - 7)) \times F(9))) \times 9) \\
 99828 &:= (((F(F(8)) + 2) + F((F(8) - 9))) \times 9) \\
 99844 &:= (((F((F(4) \times 4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) + F(9)) \\
 99846 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (4 + F((F(8) - 9)))) \times 9) \\
 99945 &:= 5 \times (F(4))^9 + 9 \times F(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

4 Summary: Selfie Numbers

The author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers** [2, 3, 4]. Friedmann [6, 7] also made some study in this direction. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Following subsections give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers are with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **Quadratic numbers**, **Cubic numbers**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. The other way of writing **selfie numbers** is by use of **permutable powers**, where **bases** and **exponents** are of same digits. See the subsection below with some examples.

4.1 Permutable Powers

Below are some examples of **permutable power selfie numbers**. By **permutable powers**, we understand that bases and exponents are of same digits with different permutations. Some times we may call them as **flexible power selfie numbers**.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &:= 1^1 & 2137 &:= -2^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^2 \\
 23 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 & 2173 &:= -2^3 + 1^2 - 7^1 + 3^7 \\
 1239 &:= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 & 2537 &:= 2^5 - 5^2 + 3^7 + 7^3 \\
 1364 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3 & 3125 &:= -3^2 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 5^5 \\
 1654 &:= -1^6 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5 & 3275 &:= -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5 \\
 1837 &:= 1^8 - 8^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 & 3435 &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3529 &:= -3^3 + 5^5 + 2^9 - 9^2 & 397612 &:= 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3 \\
 4316 &:= 4^6 + 3^1 + 1^4 + 6^3 & 423858 &:= 4^3 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^8 + 8^5 \\
 4355 &:= 4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5 & 637395 &:= 6^5 + 3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^6 + 5^7 \\
 39339 &:= -3^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 9^3 & 758014 &:= 7^7 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 0^5 + 1^4 - 4^8 \\
 46350 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^4 & 778530 &:= 7^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 5^7 + 3^0 + 0^8 \\
 46360 &:= 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 - 6^3 + 0^6 & 804637 &:= 8^0 + 0^4 - 4^8 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 7^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 15647982 &:= 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 7^7 - 9^1 + 8^8 + 2^6 \\
 17946238 &:= 1^6 + 7^8 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 6^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 8^7 \\
 57396108 &:= -5^6 + 7^9 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^7 + 1^1 + 0^0 + 8^8 \\
 134287690 &:= 1^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 8^9 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^1 \\
 387945261 &:= 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^6 + 9^9 + 4^7 + 5^8 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 1^5 \\
 392876054 &:= 3^0 + 9^9 - 2^2 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 + 0^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 \\
 392876540 &:= -3^0 + 9^9 - 2^4 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 - 5^3 + 4^6 + 0^2
 \end{aligned}$$

More details can be seen in author's work [20].

4.2 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders:

$$\begin{aligned}
 13825 &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5-2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\
 14641 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 &= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 \\
 15552 &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1 \\
 16377 &:= (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7-3)^{6+1} \\
 23328 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8-2)^{3+3}/2 \\
 116565 &:= (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) = 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 131072 &:= (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\
 156252 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 &= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned}
 656250 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 0 = 0 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656251 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 1 = 1 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656252 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 2 = 2 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656253 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 3 = 3 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656254 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 4 = 4 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 656255 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 5 = 5 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656256 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 6 = 6 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656257 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 7 = 7 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656258 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 8 = 8 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656259 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 9 = 9 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6. \end{aligned}$$

The past work up to 6 digits numbers can be seen in [14, 15, 16, 30].

4.3 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned} 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\ 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\ 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\ 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\ 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\ 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\ 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\ 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\ 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\ 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1! \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and are only with positive and negative coefficients. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways:

$$\begin{aligned} 35280 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35281 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35282 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35283 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35284 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35285 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35286 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35287 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35288 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35289 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!. \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [26, 27].

4.4 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$1764 := 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$ $2378 := -23 + \sqrt{7^8}$ $19454 := 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4}$ $19459 := 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9}$ $19684 := 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}}$ $839793 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$ $839795 := -8 + (-3 + 9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$ $839804 := (-8 + (3 - 9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4}$ $839816 := (8 + (3 - 9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$ $995544 := ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4$ $999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9 + 1)^6$ $999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^6$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$ $1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 1}$ $1296 := 6^{\sqrt{9+2-1}}$ $2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$ $3867 := (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3$ $9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 9}$ $12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$ $19693 := 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1$ $42436 := (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$ $59051 := \sqrt{-1 + 5 + 0 + 9^5}$ $999901 := (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99$ $999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$
--	---

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer author's work [14, 15].

4.5 Factorial and Square-Root

Below are some examples with **factorial** and **square-root** written in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and its reverse

$$936 := (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! = 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1296 := \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6} = 6^{(\sqrt{9+2-1})}$$

$$2896 := 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) = (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2$$

$$331779 := 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} = \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3$$

$$342995 := (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 = -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3$$

$$759375 := (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 = (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9-5+7}}$$

$$759381 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 = -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7.$$

$$5040 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 0 = 0 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5041 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 1 = 1 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5042 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 2 = 2 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5043 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 = 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5044 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 4 = 4 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5045 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 5 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5046 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 6 = 6 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5047 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 7 = 7 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5048 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 8 = 8 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5049 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 9 = 9 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

The following examples are in **digit's order** and its **reverse** separately:

$120 := ((1 + 2)! - 0)!$	$25 := 5^2$
$127 := -1 + 2^7$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$1673 := -1 - 6 + 7!/3$	$289 := (9 + 8)^2$
$1679 := 1 + (-6 + 7!)/\sqrt{9}$	$3894 := (\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!^8}) \times 3$
$1680 := (1 + 6)!/\sqrt{8 + 0!}$	$4957 := 7! - 59 - 4!$
$38970 := -3!! + 8! - 9 \times 70$	$6992 := 2^9 + 9 \times 6!$
$38986 := -3 + 8! - \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^6}$	$26493 := (2 + 6)! - 4!^{\sqrt{9}} - 3$
$40310 := (\sqrt{4^{03}})! - 10$	$30792 := 3! \times ((0 + 7)! + 92)$
$90894 := -(\sqrt{9})! + ((0! + 8)! + (\sqrt{9})!!)/4$	$54476 := (5! + 4!^4 - 7!)/6$
$91560 := ((\sqrt{9})! + 1)! + 5! \times (6! + 0!)$	$75989 := \sqrt{9} \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!!) + 5^7$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [14, 15, 16].

4.6 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n+1) = F(n) + F(n-1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. This we have done in different situations, such as using $F(\cdot)$ and $F(F(\cdot))$ in separate works. See below examples:

$143 := -1 + F(4 \times 3)$	$= F(3 \times 4) - 1$
$986 := F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6))$	$= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9)$
$1178 := F(11) \times F(7) + F(8)$	$= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11)$
$2585 := F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5)$	$= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2)$
$12819 := 1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9)$	$= F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1$
$24297 := F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7)$	$= F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2)$
$39394 := -3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)}$	$= (-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3$
$74997 := -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7)$	$= F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7$
$87937 := -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7)$	$= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8$
$98703 := 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03))$	$= (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34 &:= F(3 \times F(4)) & 36 &:= 6^{F(3)} \\
 233 &:= F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3)) & 143 &:= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\
 630 &:= F(F(6)) \times 30 & 231 &:= F(13) - 2 \\
 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) & 377 &:= F(-7 + 7 \times 3) \\
 2079 &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9 & 986 &:= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\
 4864 &:= F(F(4))^8 \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) & 1165 &:= 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1)) \\
 8759 &:= -F(9 - 5)^7 + F(F(8)) & 1596 &:= F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1))) \\
 8849 &:= -9 \times F(F(F(F(F(4)))) - 8) + F(F(8)) & 2592 &:= F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2)) \\
 9349 &:= -F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F(-3 + 9))) & 9756 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 7 \times F(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 834660 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834661 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834662 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834663 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834664 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834665 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834666 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834667 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834668 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834669 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21960 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21961 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21962 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21963 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21964 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21965 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21966 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21967 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21968 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21969 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2.
 \end{aligned}$$

First three blocks are in both ways. In the last block the first column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [23, 24].

4.7 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{1069} := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9)) & \mathbf{874} := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8) \\
 \mathbf{1081} := T(1 + T(08 + 1)) & \mathbf{0105} := 50 + T(10) \\
 \mathbf{2887} := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7) & \mathbf{1155} := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{4965} := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5))) & \mathbf{1224} := T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{4999} := 49 + T(99) & \mathbf{2418} := T(81) - T(42) \\
 \mathbf{99545} := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5 & \mathbf{99632} := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{99546} := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6. & \mathbf{99633} := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9).
 \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \mathbf{2210} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0 = 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2211} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1 = 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2212} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2 = 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2213} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3 = 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2214} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4 = 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2215} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5 = 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2216} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6 = 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2217} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 7 = 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2218} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 8 = 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2219} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 9 = 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))).
 \end{array}$$

For more details see author's work [21, 31].

4.8 Binomial Coefficients

Binomial coefficients are well known in literature. They are given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m - r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbb{N}.$$

In above subsections, we gave examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. Still, one can have similar kind results using **binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways**, **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{6435} := C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) & = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\
 \mathbf{15504} := C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) & = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{42504} := C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) & = C(4!, -05 + 24) \\
 \mathbf{54264} := C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) & = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) \\
 \mathbf{74613} := C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) & = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!).
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12650 &:= C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) \\ 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) \\ 14950 &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) \\ 18564 &:= C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) \\ 19448 &:= C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) \\ 26334 &:= C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) \\ 43758 &:= C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8) \\ 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28 &:= C(8, 2) \\ 792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\ 924 &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\ 2024 &:= C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \\ 4845 &:= C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4) \\ 00378 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!) \\ 00792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!) \\ 00924 &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)). \end{aligned}$$

Consecutive sequential representations:

$$\begin{aligned} 25920 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 0 \\ 25921 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 1 \\ 25922 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 2 \\ 25923 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 3 \\ 25924 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 4 \\ 25925 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 5 \\ 25926 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 6 \\ 25927 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 7 \\ 25928 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 8 \\ 25929 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 9. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98280 &:= 0 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98281 &:= 1 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98282 &:= 2 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98283 &:= 3 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98284 &:= 4 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98285 &:= 5 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98286 &:= 6 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98287 &:= 7 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98288 &:= 8 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98289 &:= 9 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}). \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [22].

4.9 S-gonal numbers

The formula for **S-gonal numbers** is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

This subsection brings some examples of selfie numbrs using **S-gonal numbers**. These examples are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 4992 &:= P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2) & 8967 &:= 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8) \\
 7744 &:= (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} & 9504 &:= 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9) \\
 7896 &:= 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) & 9744 &:= 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \\
 65485 &:= -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5 & 49281 &:= 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!) \\
 65943 &:= P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3) & 49548 &:= -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4 \\
 67977 &:= (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!) & 50424 &:= 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!}) \\
 72495 &:= -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5 & 52895 &:= (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5 \\
 83544 &:= \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}. & 53995 &:= (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 86640 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 0 & 5640 &:= 0 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86641 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 1 & 5641 &:= 1 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86642 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 2 & 5642 &:= 2 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86643 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 3 & 5643 &:= 3 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86644 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 4 & 5644 &:= 4 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86645 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 5 & 5645 &:= 5 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86646 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 6 & 5646 &:= 6 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86647 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 7 & 5647 &:= 7 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86648 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 8 & 5648 &:= 8 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86649 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 9. & 5649 &:= 9 + P(4!, 6) \times 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

4.10 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The formula for **centered polygonal numbers** is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{t n(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **centered polygonal numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2883} &:= K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3 & \mathbf{00938} &:= K(\sqrt{K(8, 3)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{2888} &:= K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8 & \mathbf{01051} &:= K(15, 010) \\
 \mathbf{3640} &:= K(3!, 6) \times 40 & \mathbf{01199} &:= K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10) \\
 \mathbf{14939} &:= -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9 & \mathbf{59938} &:= K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5 \\
 \mathbf{14959} &:= (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9 & \mathbf{62424} &:= 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6) \\
 \mathbf{15144} &:= K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4! & \mathbf{63384} &:= 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6! \\
 \mathbf{15347} &:= (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7) & \mathbf{63744} &:= 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!) \\
 \mathbf{15399} &:= K(1 \times 5!/3!, 9) \times 9 & \mathbf{63973} &:= K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6).
 \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{99360} &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99361} &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99362} &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99363} &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99364} &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99365} &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99366} &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99367} &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99368} &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99369} &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

4.11 Quadratic-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, n > 0, n \in N.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **quadratic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$48 := -Q(4) + Q(8)$	$49 := Q(-9 + Q(4))$
$81 := Q(8 + 1)$	$89 := Q(9) + 8$
$128 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(8)$	$224 := (Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2))$
$292 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2)$	$275 := Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2))$
$322 := Q(Q(3) \times 2) - 2$	$736 := Q(Q(6) - Q(3)) + 7$
$1036 := 10^3 + Q(6)$	$0107 := 7 + Q(010)$
$1125 := Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5$	$0231 := -Q(13) + Q(20)$
$1729 := 1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9)$	$1257 := 7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1$
$9843 := (Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3$	$2239 := -Q(9) + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2))$
$10025 := 100^2 + Q(5)$	$08136 := Q(6) + Q(Q(3) + 1 + 80)$
$10384 := (-1 + Q(Q(03))) \times 8 \times Q(4)$	$99712 := Q(Q(2)) \times 1 \times (Q(79) - 9)$
$99378 := 9 \times (Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8$	$37293 := -3 + (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2)) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3).$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 12680 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12681 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12682 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12683 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12684 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12685 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12686 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12687 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12688 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12689 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [25].

4.12 Cubic-Type Selfies

The formula for **cubic numbers** is given by

$$U(n) := n^3, n > 0, n \in N.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **cubic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$125 := 1^2 \times U(5)$	$512 := U(2 + 1 + 5)$
$522 := 5 \times 2 + U(U(2))$	$991 := (U(1 + 9) - 9)$
$991 := -9 + U(9 + 1)$	$0235 := 5 \times (U(3) + 20)$
$1371 := (1 + 3) \times U(7) - 1$	$0263 := U(3) + U(6) + 20$
$1715 := 1 \times U(7) \times 1 \times 5$	$1735 := 5 \times (3 + U(7) + 1)$
$2587 := -U(2) + 5 \times (U(8) + 7)$	$5974 := -4 + 7 \times (U(9) + U(5))$
$9945 := U(9) + 9 \times 4^5$	$00157 := -U(7) + 5 \times 100$
$10125 := (10 - 1)^2 \times U(5)$	$01928 := 8 \times (U(U(2)) + U(9) - U(10))$
$16444 := U(16) \times 4 + U(4) - 4$	$45194 := -4 + U(9) \times (1 + U(5) - U(4))$
$30375 := U(30) + U(3 + 7 + 5)$	$99535 := 5 \times (U(U(3)) + U(5) + 99)$
$99873 := U(9) \times (9 + U(8)) / (7 - 3)$	

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 22950 &:= (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\
 22951 &:= (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\
 22952 &:= (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\
 22953 &:= (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\
 22954 &:= (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\
 22955 &:= (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\
 22956 &:= (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\
 22957 &:= (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\
 22958 &:= (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\
 22959 &:= (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [25].

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